

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in technology and law

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
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 Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 A prestigious research practitioner (RP) in technology, academic, and law since 2006

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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

Graphical abstract

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

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Page | 2

A thesis published in fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of
Doctor of Philosophy in Law

Md. Anowar Hossain

Permanent Address (by birth)

Name of father: Dr. Md. Abdur Rashid, Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, Post Office: K. Mohonpur (1990),
Police Station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Year of research, 2006-2026

Year of publication, 2026

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Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

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of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime, human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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Abstract

PhD¹ research and scholarly practice were registered at University Calcutta in 2015. The thesis was concentrated on textile and color technology to satisfy the global priority themes of research and development. At the end of this situational PhD¹ article, there is a full attachment of author's first PhD⁰ and first PhD¹ thesis to remark on his first PhD¹ proposal, research practice, achievement, advancement, and guidance in research and development. This article is a forwarding philosophy of first PhD⁰, and first PhD¹ of author to University of Calcutta, India in the name of doctoral philosophy in law and criminology. This article has the full attachments of author's first PhD⁰ thesis in textile technology; author's first PhD¹ thesis in textile technology; and author's PhD thesis in law and criminology to satisfy the judicial claim of PhD⁰ and PhD¹. The general facts of research, PhD researcher, PhD supervisor, PhD thesis, PhD⁰⁻³ compliance, vice-chancellor, and PhD^{1,2} certificate are approached and remarked for the support of higher education and research for the PhD industries to adjust to display the evidence, achievement, and relevant discussion of the PhD¹ thesis of author. This first PhD¹ thesis of author has an additional approach of 'twin PhD¹ contribution' of PhD administration and PhD law; textile technology and color engineering. To enhance the institutional quality, the author also assessed the Department of Jute and Fibre Technology (DJFT), Institute of Jute Technology (IJT), University of Calcutta, India in 2013-2020; Department of Textile Engineering (DTE), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh in 2006-2010 in 2017-2020; School of Fashion and textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia in 2020-2026. This is also a milestone report and administrative bulleting to enhance the quality of higher education and research of University of Calcutta, City University, and RMIT University in global academia and philosophia. Author was also approached compensation awards to the Universities. A short summery of research billing or subsidiary of PhD¹ research costs was also submitted and approached to DJFT, University of Calcutta, India. This report also signifies the supporting documents of PhD⁰, PhD¹, PhD², and PhD³ project of author and philosophy of achieving PhD⁰⁻³ of author. Numerous limitations of PhD industries, intellectual history in academia and philosophia, research funding, research profession, higher education quality, and relevant contradictions have been judicially illustrated, remarked, and analyzed for the understanding of funding authorities, government authorities, universities, researchers, professors, PhD supervisors, PhD researchers, PhD industries, vice-chancellors, and research organizations. The comprehensive assessment of quality enhancement and professional guideline charge of author to DJFT, University of Calcutta, India should be minimum 40,000 USD or two-years duration full-time salary of a senior professor of an Indian professor in India or two-years duration full-time salary of a chief researcher of an Indian researcher in India. Ministry of higher education, India; ministry of higher education, Australia; and ministry of higher education, Bangladesh should assess should extend should approve the necessary action and support to satisfy their response of higher education to satisfy the national and international performance. Therefore, University may display and judge this report for the research fund of government, authority of the university, university grants commission, board of accreditation for engineering and technical education, institutional

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quality assurance cell of university, higher education quality enhancement project of government or university, United Nations, and central peer review purposes of the university.

Article/thesis highlights and relevant attachments

- ✓ *First PhD⁰ thesis of author in textile technology on “simultaneous dyeing and fragrance finishing of cotton fabric (2015-2016)” [1-10]*
- ✓ *First PhD¹ thesis of author in textile technology on “simultaneous dyeing and finishing with natural dyes and natural finishing agents on cotton textiles (2015-2020)”, an extension of PhD⁰ thesis [1, 2, 11] [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [4, 10, 21] [6, 8, 10-12, 19].*
- ✓ *PhD thesis of author in law on “Judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India in 2015-2020”*

Keywords: PhD researcher, PhD supervisor, PhD, PhD industry, University of Calcutta, City University, RMIT University, color, textile.

Outcomes

Judicial outcomes and approaches of professional law for the university professors, vice-chancellors, researchers, and PhD industries are mentioned.

1. Every PhD researcher and PhD supervisor should get a prestigious allowance for a PhD thesis for a ready thesis. Every thesis should have a financial benefit for a researcher should have a cash benefit for a PhD researcher.
2. If a PhD supervisor is doing PhD supervision but he/she has no proper PhD training, PhD thesis, and PhD certificate; he/she is doing judicial crime in a PhD industry.
3. A PhD supervisor can not issue a PhD experience certificate if he/she has no proper PhD training, PhD certificate, and PhD thesis.
4. A PhD supervisor can not issue a recommendation of a PhD thesis/PhD certificate if he/she has no PhD training, PhD certificate, and PhD thesis.
5. Signature scanning of a vice-chancellor in a PhD degree of a PhD certificate is a penalty of 1,00,000 Australian penalty units.
6. A schooling university and/or department should be judicially liable to certify a PhD degree. A registered university is the PhD school of a PhD candidate. A registered supervisor is responsible for taking care the policy if he/she is a registered supervisor if he/she is claiming as a PhD professor.
7. PhD certificate is a legal right of a PhD candidate at any national and international university. Every university should take care the policy.

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8. A retired professor should not get a 'no objection certificate' without completion of any PhD process of any PhD researcher of any university.
9. Every PhD supervisor should have a PhD training, PhD thesis, and PhD certificate to continue his/her service as a valid PhD supervisor of any university of any country.
10. No PhD supervisor can supervise can recommend a research degree if he/she has no 'PhD certificate and PhD thesis' of any research degree of any research university.
11. To ensure the thesis clarity and judicial transparency, every PhD thesis may have an attachment of a scanned copy of a PhD certificate of a PhD supervisor to satisfy the validity of a PhD supervisor when transparency in a PhD is a global challenge. A PhD recommendation from a PhD supervisor should also be attached and displayed with the PhD thesis of the PhD student to claim a PhD supervision to claim a PhD professor of the PhD student.
12. Every country should have the central support and affiliation policy of a valid PhD supervisor. Every country/university may publish a list of valid PhD supervisors in terms of their PhD expertise. Every country may have a central office of registrar for the valid PhD supervisors.
13. Every university should have an anonymous assessment of the PhD thesis and certification policy if the genuine duty of a valid PhD supervisor collapse or retired for the recommendation of PhD certificate. Hence, a PhD student may receive a PhD certificate from the same university without the hassle of any PhD supervisor. The performance of a PhD supervisor should be remarked accordingly and a note should be registered to the office of higher degree by research to the office of registrar.
14. Every PhD experience and PhD history should be officially registered at the department of the university.
15. Policy of PhD certificate production should be a chapter of teaching and learning in the PhD school in the PhD industry. Every PhD supervisor should be judicially liable to take the necessary action and support to guide for a transparent PhD certification to satisfy the existing university policy.
16. At any moment at any support at any investigation of the PhD achiever, a duplicate copy of a 'PhD certificate and PhD thesis' should be issuable by the university of any country of any government.
17. Every PhD outcome should be officially and parallelly registered at the department and the central registrar office of university.
18. Every BPhil/MPhil/DPhil/DTech/PhD supervisor should understand the full thesis to recommend a research degree to become to claim a valid supervisor. This is the judicial requirement to claim to be a valid supervisor. If a PhD professor can not recommend a

PhD certificate, he should not supervise the PhD student; without which a penalty of 100 Australian penalty unit should be imposed.

19. Every philosophical degree of BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/DTech/PhD, and Postdoc should register the thesis in the relevant school and central archive of the university. Every government/international authority may have a central archive to register the PhD thesis.
20. If a PhD supervisor has no PhD thesis and PhD degree, his/her PhD supervisorship will be/should be automatically cancelled in a PhD industry/university/international platform. A penalty of 100-1,000 Australian penalty unit should be automatically imposed to the PhD lawbreaker.
21. A financial dealing of any scholarly exchange is a crime of 100-1,000 Australian penalty unit.
22. A PhD supervisor can not transfer his PhD supervisionship can not transfer his PhD student without valid reasons if the PhD supervisor has no medical reason if the PhD supervisor is alive in the planet.
23. Every research degree should have the relevant administrative and academic practice to build the product of future leadership to build the product for a chancellery team, research organization, and administrative excellency in higher education and research.
24. No administration should show the attitude of asking money in the name of viva/interview technique. The penalty of financial asking and/or salary commission asking and/or creating any such artificial situation and/or showing any such attitude of any academic nomination of any PhD process with any academic candidate or professional candidate should be the punishment of 100 Australian penalty unit.
25. Every PhD thesis should be officially registered at university should have a number of registration should have a valid registration number of the PhD thesis.
26. If a professor does the hamper of natural growth/scholarly growth of any student/researcher of any colleague in profession, the 1,000-10,000 Australian penalty unit should be imposed to satisfy the compensation of his/her student/colleague.
27. Every PhD professor/supervisor should have a valid capability should have concrete understanding to supervise and certify his PhD student independently in his field of technology in his field of philosophy in his field of doctoral studies.
28. Misguiding to PhD student and negative supervision in academia and philosophia is a crime of 1,00-1,000 Australian penalty unit.
29. Assessment of experts of minimum two/three different universities are required to assess a PhD thesis.
30. Every PhD supervisor should guide should teach the PhD certification process of university to his PhD researcher to the PhD achiever.

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31. Every professor, PhD professor, and PhD supervisor should be a professional engineer in his/her relevant field of technology.
32. A self-funded MPhil/PhD thesis achiever may also ask full-funding of MPhil/PhD scholarship of any university and/or government which may be termed as 'thesis scholarship' instead of 'PhD scholarship' in terms of research funding in terms of subsidiary in research. This fund should be issued after achieving the thesis. Nobody should deny should neglect the policy to respect academia and philosophia.
33. A MPhil/PhD 'study leave' should be the judicial requirement to become a university teacher whatever may be funded by university and/or scholarship and/or self-funded and/or government authority.
34. Every PhD researcher should have a compliance office should have a compliance study place at university, research organization, and/or outside location.
35. A valid supervisor of a research degree of an academic degree is the scholarly requirement in academia and philosophia.
36. If a person has no valid PhD degree, he/she can not supervise any academic project of thesis production of BSc/MSc/BTech/MTech/BPhil/MPhil/DPhil/PhD/Postdoc degree of any university.
37. Every academic project supervisor of BSc/MSc/BTech/MTech/BPhil/MPhil/PhD should have a transparent PhD degree. Every supervisor of professional project or industrial project should have a transparent training of BSc/MSc/BTech/MTech/BPhil/MPhil/PhD.
38. A nomination of a vice-chancellor and chancellor of a university should satisfy the judicial process.
39. Every professor of university should write and record a 3P (PhD, promotion, and professor) history to satisfy the judicial requirement to get the 'no objection certificate' of his/her retirement in academia and philosophia.
40. Every promotion should have a record of promotion history to satisfy the promotion law to get the promotion in academia and philosophia.
41. Every PhD should have a record of PhD history to satisfy the PhD law to get the PhD to claim a PhD in academia and philosophia.
42. Every professor Dr. should have a valid reason to write Dr. and/or professor before the name in academia and philosophia.
43. Verifications of the promotion and nomination history in academia and philosophia are the core duty of an academic magistrate or vice-chancellor. If a vice-chancellor is a chief magistrate of a university, he/she should have a sound knowledge of academic and administrative law.
44. A vice-chancellor should not continue his/her job under the non-judicial guidance of departmental professor of any university.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

45. A non-PhD should not take an interview of a PhD. A non-professor should not take an interview of a professor. A non-engineer should not take interview of an engineer.
46. Scholars are not only life-long owner of his/her scholarly research, he/she is the still the judicial successor after his/her death.
47. Every person of PhD peer reviewer, PhD committee, and PhD administration should have a PhD thesis and PhD certificate to satisfy the judicial requirement. Page | 8
48. No journal should correspond with the corresponding author without the main author of the manuscript.

General notice to whom it may concern

A general notice is being forwarded to the academicians, research practitioners, PhD industries, and relevant administrations in global academia and philosophy.

1. All prestigious PhD industries should keep the record of their certified PhD students/foreign certified PhD student in their website/archive for the global transparency in research and development if the achievement of a PhD degree is a prestigious milestone is a life-long milestone is a long-term milestone to assess the PhD scholar.
2. The whole education ministry of higher education and research all over the country all over the world should assess the transparency of PhD thesis and PhD certificate in PhD industry.
3. All universities should judge and verify the 'PhD certificate and PhD thesis' of their PhD supervisor to eliminate the PhD crimes in the global academia and research service.
4. All scanned PhD certified holders and/or PhD supervisors and/or duplicate professor (Dr.) are being urgently requested to surrender to the government/university to avoid their penalty of 1,000 Australian penalty units.
5. In the first meeting, every research professor should show his/her thesis and certificate to his/her student to become a research professor and/or research supervisor and/or research practitioner with his/her student.
6. All international supervisors are being requested to submit their PhD certificate to attach with the PhD thesis of his/her PhD student to claim their PhD supervisorship.
7. Every PhD researcher is being requested to admit in PhD course after verifying the 'PhD thesis and PhD certificate' of his/her PhD supervisor.
8. If a person has a second/third PhD, the salary in the profession should be double/triple/supportable/competitive to cover the professional compensation.
9. If the research contribution of foreigner is not the scholarly contribution of foreigner; foreign universities should not admit/invite foreign students/foreign researchers in the

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Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

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Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in technology and law

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
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- name of PhD course. Every contribution of foreigner/every thesis of foreign student should be officially registered at foreign university.
10. Every government should develop the judicial protocols to approve research fund at universities and research centres rather than the policy of special dealings.
 11. Every government should/can judge the truthiness of foreign degree at any time. Every foreign university should support the policy should extend the academic service should record the PhD degree.
 12. If foreign vice-chancellor is not prioritized in foreign university, foreign students should not be allowed in foreign universities.

1 Introduction

Figure 1. Every PhD research/researcher should have the training of two-dimensional functions of PhD law and subject expertise to win a passing grade of 40% to 50% marks [22, 23].

Every PhD training and/or PhD degree should have a concrete understanding of PhD research, academic protocol of the PhD degree, administrative protocol of the PhD degree, and relevant technology in terms of subject expertise. Hence, every PhD thesis achiever should have a judicial understanding about a PhD degree should have an academic training about a PhD degree, and technological or subject understanding to achieve a PhD degree[4]. Figure 1, a professor may have a high-quality PhD thesis in his subject expertise, but he does not know the PhD compliance during his/her retirement, but he does not know PhD compliance after the long-term

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service to the PhD students and long-term engagement in academia and philosophia. So, a judicial learning on PhD and academic should be the vital segment of a compliance PhD of any research university to survive in the future profession of academia and philosophia. So, a high-quality PhD training is more necessary than a high-quality PhD thesis in a PhD program. So, a dual performance is necessary should have a judicial value in academia and philosophia.

1.1 *PhD⁰ thesis on*

Simultaneous dyeing and fragrance finishing of cotton fabric

1.2 *PhD¹ thesis on*

Simultaneous dyeing and finishing with natural dyes and natural finishing agents on cotton textiles

1.3 *PhD^{0,1} contribution on*

- Material design and method design for dyes and color engineering in textile technology.
- Material design, method design, and product design for technical textiles.

1.4 *Sole authored by*

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

1.5 *Thesis achievement of PhD², Nobel prize¹, honorary doctorate (honoris causa)¹, and Doctor of Science (DSc) of author*

Tremendous contribution, advancement, and achievement in science and technology since 2020 [4, 22].

1.6 *Thesis achievement of PhD³, Nobel prize², honorary doctorate (honoris causa)², and Doctor of Laws (LLD) of author*

Tremendous contribution, advancement, and achievement in law, academic, and PhD industry since 2021[4, 23].

1.7 *Total achievement of sole author contribution, research, and publication practices since since 2006 since 1986*

- ✓ Sole author thesis of BSc in Textile Engineering and relevant record at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh[4, 24].

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- ✓ Sole author thesis of MTech and/or MPhil/PhD⁰ thesis in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) and relevant record at University of Calcutta, India[3, 4].
- ✓ Sole author thesis of twin PhD¹ in Textile Technology and Law, and relevant record at University of Calcutta, India [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [6, 8, 10].
- ✓ Sole author thesis of twin PhD² in Textile Technology and Law, and relevant record at RMIT University, Australia[4, 22, 23].
- ✓ Sole author Postdoc thesis in Textile Technology and Law, and relevant record at RMIT University, Australia[4].
- ✓ Sole author experience of thesis supervision of BSc in textile engineering students in color engineering and textile engineering[4].
- ✓ Sole author thesis from primary schooling to PhD school and academic since 31 December 1986[4].

1.8 Scholarly registered of PhD^{0,1} at University of Calcutta, India on 17 July 2015

Name of registrar and/or PhD supervisor

Professor Dr. Asish Kumar Samanta, Former Head/Chairman, Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, Kolkata, India [2, 25].

1.9 PhD^{0,1} thesis peer reviewed by (2015-2020)

Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, Former Head, Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, Kolkata, India; relevant experts; and relevant journals [11].

1.10 Additional consequence, credit, and support of this article (2015-2020)

- ✓ This is an academic promotion file at City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh. This is a PhD^{0,1} performance at University of Calcutta, India since 2014-2015 before achieving PhD² before enrolling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia since 2020 [4, 11].
- ✓ This is also a judicial and academic articles to convince professor designation at university grants commission of Bangladesh.
- ✓ To claim an official duty allowance, this report is also validated by the official duty of City University as a member, institutional quality assurance cell, City university, Dhaka, Bangladesh since 2019 [2, 11, 21, 25, 26].

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1.11 Limitations of industrial research material rather than natural source of material

Researchers are purchasing the research materials from the industry source and trialing for research and innovation. Researchers are also citing the name of companies. But the maximum companies have no contribution have no understanding for the research and development. Therefore, both party should have a negotiation for research funding; and relevant financial and research support to research and researcher. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain maintained a compliance communication with the supplier of industrial research material. This thesis was also extended and prioritized the design of natural source of materials in terms of color, cosmetic, aroma, and medicinal property of materials.

1.12 An extension of the research questions and philosophical grounds of MTech and/or MPhil/PhD⁰/PhD¹ thesis[27]

- To dye and finish of textile substances with new materials.
- To analyse simultaneous property of dyed textiles and medical textiles.
- To standardize the methodology for the industrial applications for the product development.
- To analyse product and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments.

1.13 Notice to registrar/function of registrar, University of Calcutta, India

Registrar office of University of Calcutta and Department of Jute and Fibre Technology (DJFT), Institute of Jute Technology (IJT), University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Faculty councils for post graduate studies in Science, Technology & Engineering and Agriculture & Vet. Science, University of Calcutta should record a printed copy and a pdf file of this report for the future reference of University of Calcutta and chief researcher, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Registered PhD research-2015, Reference No: 157, office of registrar, University of Calcutta, 87/1, college street, Kolkata-700073, India. In terms of PhD registration, this thesis has an attachment of the signed copy of the secretary, University of Calcutta; and chairman/head, DJFT, IJT, University of Calcutta, India, 2015.

1.14 Notice to ministry of education, India; and ministry of education, Bangladesh

Ministry of education, India; and ministry of education, Bangladesh should record a printed copy and a pdf file of this report for the assessment reference of University of Calcutta, India; and the assessment reference of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh for the quality enhancement support of higher education in India and Bangladesh.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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1.15 Type of compensation award¹⁻³ asked to University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India and City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh; approached and judicially argued by Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Name of compensation	Compensation approached to	Expected value of compensation	Type of evidence
BSc engineering compensation award ¹	City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh	10,000 Australian penalty unit	Explained in this article [1, 2, 4, 24, 26, 28-61]
MTech compensation award ²	University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India	10,000 Australian penalty unit	Explained in this article [1-10]
PhD ¹ compensation award ³	University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India	1,00,000 USD	Explained and attached in this article [1, 2, 11] [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [4, 10, 21] [6, 8, 10-12, 19]

1.16 Type of self-investment of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Name of degree	Registered universities and year of academic practice	Investments (approximately)	Type of evidence
BSc in Textile Engineering	City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh (2006-2010)	Self-investment and self-salary (minimum) 10,00,000 BDT	Explained in this article [1, 2, 4, 24, 26, 28-61]
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)	University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India (2013-2015)	Self-investment and self-salary (minimum) 8,00,000 BDT-10,00,000 BDT	Explained in this article [1-10]
PhD ¹ in Textile Technology	University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India (2015-2020)	Self-salary for a nine months project of PhD ⁰ 27,00,000BDT[27] and relevant costs	Explained and attached in this article [1, 2, 11] [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [4, 10, 21] [6, 8, 10-12, 19]

1.17 Full-time salary compensation and salary investment of PhD⁰⁻³ project was calculated and expected approximately for PhD⁰, PhD¹, PhD², and PhD³

PhD	Duration	Total salary compensation in million in BDT
Zero PhD ⁰ [1-10]	12 months	2.4
Zero PhD ⁰ [1-10]	9 months	2.7
First PhD ¹ [1, 2, 11] [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [4, 10, 21] [6, 8, 10-12, 19]	24 months	3.6
Second PhD ² (first year and second year)[22]	24 months	48
Second PhD ² and third PhD ³ (third year and fourth year)[22] [23]	24 months	120
Second PhD ² and third PhD ³ (fifth year and sixth year)[23] [22]	24 months	240

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1.18 Sole author contribution of the thesis of PhD¹

Due to the sole author contribution, the depth and length of analysis is proportionally designed under the limitation of research fund. The thesis was examined and published since 2017-2020. The quality of a PhD thesis is also proportionally relevant to scholar and finance. Although, a person can continue can extend the practice of life-time duration PhD research if he/she has PhD funding [1-10] [1, 2, 11] [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [4, 10, 21] [6, 8, 10-12, 19].

1.18.1 Self-funded PhD¹ thesis on “simultaneous dyeing and finishing with natural dyes and natural finishing agents on cotton textiles (2015-2020)”

As the PhD¹ thesis is self-funded and sole authored, the thesis may be registered at any university all over the world to receive a certified copy and/or authorship copy and/or registered copy. In general process of eye-washing, author gets more priority for the registration at branded university for the certified copy and/or registered copy of any branded university. But practically, brand is also a matter of personal excellency and professional excellency of the PhD researcher. Practically research value should not increase or decrease in terms of branded university or non-branded university. Sometimes, a senior graded assessor can not assess or understand the research manuscript, how can he assess the value of a branded university or non-branded university? In general, researcher may also respect the brand of a research organization without self-assessing and self-understanding.

1.18.2 Request to the relevant authority due to having online publication of PhD¹ thesis since 2017-2018

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) would like to request to take necessary action and support to the university/universities to ensure the permanent registry to approve a certified copy of PhD¹ to the author.

1.18.3 Research compliance and research assessment year of author in PhD^{0,1} 2014-2020

2 Research questions and philosophical grounds

- What are the judicial crimes in university and PhD industries in academia and philosophia?
- How to eliminate the judicial crimes and penalties in academia and philosophia?

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Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT
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3 Reasons and facts of PhD tuition fees in academia and philosophia

Figure 2. General purpose of tuition fees for the support of a self-funded PhD or scholarship funded PhD at any university [22, 23]

Figure 2, there are reasons and facts of practice of having tuition fees for the support of a self-funded PhD or scholarship funded PhD at any university. Numerous grounds of investment of a PhD researcher in university which are PhD registration, PhD tuition fees, PhD conference, PhD research, PhD materials, PhD time, PhD office, PhD laboratory, PhD safety, PhD sex[4, 21, 62], PhD living allowance and relevant funding, PhD manpower, PhD supervisor, PhD expert, PhD writing and drafting, PhD publication, PhD field trialing[27], PhD peer review[63], PhD thesis register and registrar, PhD certificate, post-PhD fund searching[64-66], and relevant costs. Moreover, Post-PhD award/thesis award may be negligible practice in PhD industry. A trained expert in his/her field of study can continue a PhD research without the training and support of a PhD supervisor and PhD expert. But a PhD supervisor may/should perform a scholarly referee to certify a PhD degree on behalf of any university. PhD tuition fees is a global challenge and global contradiction. Teaching, training, research material, research laboratory, technicians of the laboratory/machine, peer review, continuous assessments, registration, conference participation, office space/study space, office instruments, internet support, library, thesis publication, thesis assessment, school safety, school compliance, PhD certification, PhD register, PhD registrar are the vital facts of PhD tuition fees/research degree under the policy of a self-funded PhD or

scholarship funded PhD at any research university. If a PhD has a requirement of training and relevant PhD support, the tuition fees policy may be continued by the government. If a PhD thesis is done without financial support of any university, the tuition fees policy may be exempted or minimized by the government and/or university. Every self-funded/scholarship funded PhD researcher may have an allowance and/or PhD thesis award for achieving the outcomes of a PhD thesis if the thesis and research are the requirement of a PhD of a university of a department of a PhD school of a country. If PhD is a matter of tuition fees of a PhD candidate, what should be the outcome value of a PhD scientist? Who should take care the PhD law? In general theme, every PhD research should be a paid job or a ready cash job of university and/or research organization rather than promotional benefit in future. Therefore, the higher length of a research journey of a PhD thesis may be negligible for a self-funded PhD for a PhD certification policy for a PhD training policy. Although the length, strength, philosophy, and sole authorship of PhD research at RMIT University of Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain covers the full requirement of BSc by research, MSc by research, BPhil, MPhil, PhD² (DSc), PhD³ (LLD), and Postdoc at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia in 2020-2026[22, 23]. Research training is the major prerequisite of a PhD degree of a PhD certificate when research contribution is also a matter of research funding, research timing, and additional scholarly practice and record of a PhD researcher. Without PhD certification, the practice of university policy, the practice of scholarly policy may decline may confuse. An expert researcher may also do research without the support of any university without the support of supervisor without the support of research organization [4, 67]. An expert supervisor may also supervise PhD research without the support of any university. A PhD supervisor should display both PhD publications and PhD certificate of a PhD student to claim the professional experience of a PhD supervisor. Similarly, a PhD student should display both PhD publications and PhD certificate of his PhD studentship to claim the professional experience of a PhD student. Both party should sign to the experience of the opposite party. Without which, university policy of a PhD education may be hampered and demotivated.

3.1 PhD¹ thesis self-funded by Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain since 2015

PhD¹ thesis was self-funded by Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain since 2015 under the PhD memorandum at DJFT, IJT, University of Calcutta, India under the PhD signing with DJFT, University of Calcutta. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is self-funded for this PhD¹ research on ‘natural dyed textiles and cosmetic textiles’[11, 27]. If a scholarship funder if a university if a government if a country has a value for their research funding, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should also get an additional value in the profession for his self-funding of research and publication since 2006[4]. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have legal right to ask the judicial authority of

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university. Moreover, every government have a judicial right to print money to inflate money, university has no judicial right to print money to inflate money; hence Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not print the currency. So, who should financially take care the PhD¹ compensation support to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) if he maintains a self-funded office since 2006 to prepare to develop the brain and psychophysics of doctoral studies in engineering in law and relevant development in research for global surviving in academia and philosophia? [4, 22, 23]

3.2 Tutition fees and recent conference may be exempted

Tution fees and recent conference may be exempted for PhD¹ degree of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at University of Calcutta, India.

3.2.1 Tutition fees

The fees of PhD¹ supervisor or tutition fees for academic supervisor was also officially paid in USD through the tutition fees of MTech (Master of Technology) degree at University of Calcutta, India [2, 25]. An international category MTech tutition fees was paid to University of Calcutta, India in 2013-2015. Hence, the research question of MTech thesis was extended and sequentially modified to continue the relevant field of research in textile technology. Hence, the research question of MTech thesis was practiced, studied, and extended sequentially and independently since 2015. The additional research was also conducted at the outside location of DJFT at the outside fund of DJFT. There was no PhD¹ material costs, PhD¹ office cost, and PhD¹ laboratory cost at DJFT, University of Calcutta. The PhD¹ research office and relevant research costs were contributed by the self-funded PhD¹ researcher since 2015. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is attached a short summery of billing evidence in 2016[27]. Moreover, the self-supervised PhD¹ thesis was developed, peer reviewed, and published in journal since 2017-2020. A percentage of peer review costs of a PhD¹ supervisor was also partially supported by the self-funded or project funded of PhD¹ researcher[11].

3.2.2 Conference

Product analysis and merchandising of MTech research[27], the extension of MTech research with different materials, the extension of MTech research questions with different methodologies, peer review report, discussion report, relevant publications, and distribution of publications at DJFT and relevant expert panel since 2017 also signifies the substitute of self-funded research conference at DJFT, CU [1-10] [1, 2, 11] [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [4, 10, 21] [6, 8, 10-12, 19] [27]. Moreover, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also facing safety crisis as camouflage scientist since 2021-2022 at RMIT University, Australia[23].

Table 1. History of PhD investment, PhD fund crisis, and award-winning of Australian government for sole author category ‘second PhD²’ and twin PhD of PhD² and PhD³ at RMIT University, Australia in 2020-2026 [4, 22, 23].

Name of award/scholarship	Results	Funded by
Indian government scholarship, ICCR in Bangladesh	Failed under the valid recommendation, offer letter, and research proposal (2015-2019)	Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain, author
Chinese government scholarship in Bangladesh	Failed under valid recommendation, offer letter, and research proposal (2015-2019)	Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain, author
Bangabandhu science and technology fellowship, Bangladesh	Failed under valid recommendation, offer letter, and research proposal (2015-2019)	Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain, author
Commonwealth scholarship, UK; assessed in Bangladesh	Failed under valid recommendation, offer letter, and research proposal (2015-2019)	Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain, author
Scholarship/project at Indian Institute of Technology, Delhi, India	Failed under the valid recommendation, offer letter, and research proposal (2015-2019)	Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain, author
Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship at RMIT University, Australia [22, 23, 68]	Winner under the valid recommendation and research proposal (2018-2026)	Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain, author

Table 2. Evidences of scholarly witness and research publications to satisfy the PhD¹ requirement of research to issue PhD¹ certificate from University of Calcutta, India and/or Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur under the registration of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, University of Calcutta, India in 2015 in terms of chain extension of MTech research and PhD¹ study[4, 27].

SN	Title of publications	Journal (online)	DOI/ID	Author and author type	Registered supervisor/peer reviewer, scholarly witness, external witness
1.	Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric, 2(4), 25-34 [69]. Role of chief scientist since 2014	Journal of Materials Sciences and Applications	10.13140/RG.2.2.1 6757.35048	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, Dr. Kashmita Bhattacharya, Dr. Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik, CU, India
2.	Cyclodextrin for Aroma Finishing on Textile	International Journal of Science and	10.5281/zenodo.82 42756	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar	Professor (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, Dr.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

Author’s biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

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	Substrate-A Review Article, 2019. 8(89) [10]. Role of chief scientist since 2014	Engineering Investigations		Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Arindam Bagchi, CU, India
3.	Textile coloration and fragrance finishing for perfumed garments [Textile Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-70019, West Bengal, India][8]. Role of chief scientist since 2014	MTech Thesis	10.13140/RG.2.2.15918.48965; 10.5281/zenodo.7854437	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, CU, India
4.	Integrated dyeing and cosmetic finishing on cotton fabric 6th all India Inter Engineering college academic meet-2015 and Science & Technology exhibition for a sustainable society, Organised by Forum of Scientist, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET), 15N, Nelli Sengupta Sarani (Lindsay Street), Kolkata-7000087, India [6]. Role of chief scientist since 2014	Conference	10.13140/RG.2.2.29340.2624; 10.5281/zenodo.13304637	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, CU, India Professor (Dr.) Swapon Kumar Gosh (conference support) CU, India
5.	Anowar's Handbook on Advance Textile Technology School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh;	Preprint book ResearchGate Zenodo Searching 'Chief Professor/	10.13140/RG.2.2.35648.8576; 10.5281/zenodo.15068136	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Self

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

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International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
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	Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35 Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India (engr.anowar@yahoo.co) [5]	Chief Scientist' category fund to accomplish the book			
6.	Power Point Presentation on Applications and Engineering of Geotextiles (Department of Textile Engineering, City university, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh (engr.anowar@yahoo.com, Issue; 2015 [19, 20]. Role of chief scientist since 2014	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.1 7899.3152; 10.5281/zenodo.83 11345	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Self
7.	Power Point Presentation on Combined dyeing and cosmetic finishing of woven cotton fabric for garments (Department of Jute and Fibre technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, India, Issue; 2015 [9] Role of chief scientist since 2014	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.2 8804.5056; 10.5281/zenodo.83 11367	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, CU, India
8.	Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India, 2013-2015 [3]. Role of chief scientist since 2014	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.1 2565.0944; 10.5281/zenodo.15 068327	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Self
9.	Product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments[27]	ResearchGate Zenodo Journal of Dr. Anowar	10.13140/RG.2.2.2 5123.92967; 10.5281/zenodo.18 885116	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain,	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India

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	Role of chief scientist since 2014			RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	
10.	<i>A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020)</i> R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh [11] Role of chief scientist since 2014	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.16273.08801; 10.5281/zenodo.17389964	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT University, Australia.
11.	A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre, 2019. 3(1): p. 1-3 [12]. Role of chief scientist since 2014	International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering	10.29011/IJTSE-126/100026; 10.13140/RG.2.2.36811.36648; 10.5281/zenodo.8245079	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India; Prof. (Dr.) Md. Nurul Abser, JU, Bangladesh; Dr. Ferdous Ara Dilruba, BJRI, Bangladesh

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

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Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

12.	Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent, 2018. 2(2): p. 1-8 [16]. Role of chief scientist since 2014	Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing	MS.ID: 000132	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India
13.	Non-toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric using Non-toxic Colorant and Nontoxic Crosslinker, 2018. 8(5): p. 1-5 [14]. Role of chief scientist since 2014	Journal of Textile Science & Engineering	10.4172/2165-8064.1000374	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India; Dr. Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik, CU, India; Dr. Padma S. Vankar, IIT, India; Dr. Dhara Shukla, IIT, India
14.	Organic Colouration and Antimicrobial Finishing of Organic Cotton Fabric by Exploiting Distillated Organic Extraction of Organic Tectona grandis and Azardirachta indica with Organic Mordanting Compare to Conventional Inorganic Mordants, 2018. 2018(1): p. 1-12[15]. Role of chief scientist since 2014	International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering	10.29011/IJTSE-113/100013	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India; Dr. Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik, CU, India; Dr. Padma S. Vankar, IIT, India; Dr. Dhara Shukla, IIT, India
15.	Pollution Free Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted from Swietenia macrophylla and Musa Acuminata as Unpolluted Dyes and Citrus. Limon (L.) as Unpolluted Mordanting Agent, 2018, 3(2): p. 1-8[18]. Role of chief scientist since 2014	Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology	10.31031/TTEFT.2018.03.000558	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India; Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, CU, Bangladesh

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Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

16.	A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles, Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments (pp. 151-170) [17]. Role of chief scientist since 2014	IntechOpen	10.5772/intechopen .92360	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India;
17.	Zero Toxic Approach of Cotton Fabric Coloration with Botanical Waste resource via Psidium P. guajava (Guava Leaves) as Natural Dyes and Citrus Lemon (Lemon Leaves) as Natural Mordanting Agent. 2019 [70]. Role of chief scientist since 2014	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.1 8112.75524	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India Prof. (Dr.) Md. Nurul Abser, JU, Bangladesh

4 Limitations and contradictions are forwarded to University of Calcutta

The limitations and contradictions of author's understanding is forwarded to head/former heads, Department of Jute and Fibre Technology (DJFT), University of Calcutta, India; and vice-chancellor, University of Calcutta in 2026. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain did and contributed two thesis at DJFT, University of Calcutta. But the thesis should be free of cost register at University of Calcutta if the university also need the thesis/research rather than author at DJFT and/or Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Moreover, the thesis was completely done by self-funded and sole-funded since 2014. If a PhD researcher can continue his PhD independently, the PhD tuition fees at university may be exempted for non-scholarship PhD researcher. If he did two PhD thesis at University of Calcutta, if he approached two philosophies, if he approached one-dimensional philosophy in two thesis, at least University of Calcutta should register one PhD and/or one certified copy of the PhD thesis. It should not be a matter of high court of India. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not be liable if he needs to go to the high court for his PhD certificate for his PhD argument at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India. Although, all arguments are judicially explained, represented, and scholarly attached for the assessment of academia and philosophia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not interested to proceed with high court of India. Moreover, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is still sufferer and sufferer to manage high court costs in Australia[23]. Moreover,

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department and/or university should pay and contribute a financial award to the author if department/university didn't financially contribute single dollar to achieve the attached thesis on 'natural dyes and cosmetic textiles' [1-10] [1, 2, 11] [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [4, 10, 21] [6, 8, 10-12, 19, 27]. A PhD/MPhil training denotes a PhD certificate, a PhD/MPhil training means a PhD/MPhil tuition fees for the university but a PhD/MPhil thesis states the philosophical glory and academic evidence of the department. If University of Calcutta didn't pay for MTech thesis, the MTech publications and contributions may also be claimed for an additional degree of MPhil/PhD¹. A self-funded MPhil/PhD thesis achiever may also ask for full-funding of MPhil/PhD scholarship of any university and/or government which may be termed as 'thesis scholarship' in terms of research funding in terms of subsidiary in research. A 'thesis scholarship' is a post-paid allowance of research contribution. A thesis scholarship/subsidiary of research may full cover the thesis cost of MPhil/PhD. Practically, a 'thesis scholarship' should be greater than a PhD scholarship. Although the term of 'thesis scholarship' and/or 'subsidiary of research funding' and/or 'post PhD funding' in research are not established in academia and philosophia may be implemented for the self-funded PhD researcher and scholarship funded PhD researcher. If an MTech thesis has any sole contribution, DJFT, University of Calcutta may additionally assess, certify, and register an additional degree of MPhil/PhD¹ for the professional support/contribution of a researcher. Without which, how can Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain contribute as an 'independent researcher' to accomplish the attached PhD¹ thesis on "simultaneous dyeing and finishing with natural dyes and natural finishing agents on cotton textiles (2015-2020)" [1-10] [1, 2, 11] [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [4, 10, 21] [6, 8, 10-12, 19] This PhD¹ thesis is also evidence of research extension, research flow, and research chain of an 'independent researcher' since 2014[27]. Moreover, he extended the research study, research understanding, self-invested, and established his MTech thesis by product development and marketing in Bangladesh in terms of academic research duty of PhD¹ [11, 27]. He funded and extended an additional research practice and additional effort in research in Bangladesh. Moreover, he also independently idea generated and/or sole authored for his MTech thesis at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India since 2014. Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain got an MTech degree for his theoretical courses and/or training courses and academic process of routine examination, but he didn't get any additional degree/philosophical degree to invest to submit to approve his thesis on cosmetic textiles and/or medical textiles. MTech degree at DJFT had/has a long running theoretical courses and routine examinations[71]. Moreover, RMIT University, Australia provides Master of Science (MSc) by thesis for a thesis for a research performance for a professional support for a professional investment. If RMIT University is awarding MSc degree by research, there is also a limitation in course design if they have no broader theory of advanced course works and advanced research compliance. But, RMIT university tries to proceed to motivate with the advancement in research and development in one-dimensional goal

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Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director

of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical

processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime,

human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home

ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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of research and development; and research training and learning. The name of degree of MSc degree by research may also be termed as BPhil/MPhil in technology. Therefore, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain may claim an additional degree of MPhil/PhD¹ in technology for his MTech thesis at University of Calcutta if his MTech thesis has any specific philosophy has any MPhil/PhD¹ [7] [6]. Possibly, he has also an MPhil/DPhil/PhD¹/DTech in his MTech thesis[27]. What is the real-life purpose of supervisor involvement and attachment with an 'independent researcher' in the name of degree in the name of MTech/MPhil/PhD/DPhil/Postdoc? The scholarly attestation, the scholarly evidence, professional support, the scholarly archive in university, certified copy, and contribution of the thesis are the major purposes of academic involvement for the professional growth for surviving support in the research profession. Moreover, a degree/research outcomes also glorifies the department and university for funding support for surviving support for branding support in global academia, philosophia, and research. DJFT and/or University of Calcutta should pay should scholarly respect every hour of research payment of research service to Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain since 2014-2015[1, 2, 11] [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [4, 10, 21] [6, 8, 10-12, 19]. Without which the PhD¹ practice tend to the practice of non-compliance to respect the research, researcher, and supervisor in the global community of academia and philosophia. The bank account number of Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also mentioned here for the assessment and approval of the concern authority. Md. Anowar Hossain, savings account no: 0178 12200003933, First Security Islami Bank PLC, Birulia Branch, Dhaka-(routing No: 105260808). The DJFT should also collect the bank account number of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta. The DJFT should also collect the bank account number of Dr. Padma S. Vankar, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur, India if she had the support of any peer review process. The administrative chief of DJFT and/or concern official of University of Calcutta should officially assess and coordinate the action and support if he/she is approaching and/or leading guardianship of DJFT. The permanent address of Md. Anowar Hossain is also mentioned here. Name of father: Dr. Md. Abdur Rashid, Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, Post Office: K. Mohonpur (1990), Police Station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh (by birth).

5 Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is recommending and approaching two-dimensional PhD allowance for a cash benefit of a researcher

Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain is recommending and approaching scholarship for a research practitioner and thesis allowance for a thesis achiever. There is far deviation between the achiever of PhD scholarship and PhD thesis. A PhD scholarship is a research funding. A PhD scholarship is not a PhD thesis. A PhD scholarship is not a PhD certificate. Moreover, a scholarship achiever/research fund achiever of university may not generate a PhD thesis. Practically, some professor may not have a PhD thesis under the non-judicial process of

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academia and philosophia. Every PhD researcher may receive two-dimensional research fund during PhD training and after having the PhD thesis. A PhD scholarship pays for a research training and research learning. A PhD scholarship pays for a research practitioner. The payment amount of a research practitioner is small is negligible. A PhD scholarship don't directly pay for a PhD thesis achiever. MPhil/PhD thesis is not directly paying to the research practitioner. Every owner of PhD thesis and/or MPhil thesis should get a payment although the thesis is done by self-funded and/or scholarship funded. Every owner of thesis in academia in university should have a cash benefit rather than certified copy rather than life-long earning rather than high salaried job in future. Every owner of a coffee shop claims a cash money to his/her customer. Without which, people will not do thesis, people will do PhD training, people will only learn the research if there is no cash benefit against a PhD thesis. People will not do PhD thesis if there is life-threatening conspiracy in international platform. Moreover, researcher will get afraid will be demotivated to sustain academia and philosophia [23]. There are also global limitations in academia and philosophia. Training and learning are the academic duty, but the PhD thesis is a professional outcome in academia and philosophia. Academician, professor, supervisor, and PhD researcher should approach and/or assess to the government authority, if they are government professor and/or government authority, if they are not retired professor. Every owner of MPhil thesis should get an international allowance of 50,000-1,00,000 USD. Every owner of PhD thesis should get an international allowance of 1,00,000-2,00,000 USD. There is far difference between thesis allowance and training allowance/study allowance/practice allowance/scholarship of a PhD research of a PhD researcher. Both the self-funded and/or scholarship funded researcher should get the fund for the research contribution and thesis allowance. There is far deviation between the allowance of research practitioner and the generation of a PhD thesis. The allowance of a research practitioner signifies the allowance of a research training, research practice, research study, and research learning. The allowance of a research thesis signifies the allowance of a PhD thesis. Thesis allowance should be higher than the allowance of research practice/scholarship in academia and philosophia. Self-funding is money; scholarship is also money; but both monies may have/should have an equal force should have 360° force to achieve the scholarly allowance of a PhD thesis. Moreover, self-funded researcher should also get more priority in assessment in research funding in terms of contribution and achievement rather than scholarship funded PhD researcher. A scholarship contribution is valuable. Similarly, a self-funded contribution should also be valuable should be remarked should be registered at branded university. Without which, nobody will invest in higher education and research, academia and philosophia. Moreover, a certificate should not be a common objective to achieve BPhil/MPhil/PhD/Postdoc thesis. Although, a PhD certificates/research certificates ensures a life-time official registration of the PhD thesis of the PhD achiever. Every PhD scholarship,

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every PhD university may have a separate fund of full registering process/certification process of PhD thesis at any university.

6 Burden philosophy to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher who is asking and claiming a 'PhD¹ compensation award' to University of Calcutta, India

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain did self-funded research for University of Calcutta since 2014, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also did self-funded research to complete the PhD¹ requirement at University of Calcutta, if he needs to pay any additional tuition fees of his contribution it should be an additional burden for a non-paid researcher for a self-funded researcher. What should be the general philosophy of PhD registration and PhD register? The policy should be more transparent at University of Calcutta. Who is the registrar of a PhD? Who should be the long-term registrar of the PhD¹ when a PhD¹ supervisor is a retired professor? Tuition fees/scholarship of a PhD for a PhD is a matter of PhD training and/or PhD learning. But the tuition fees/scholarship/research funding has no the guarantee of the generation a PhD/MPhil thesis. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain invested around 3000 hours to write the PhD¹ thesis to generate an innovative idea on natural dyes, textile coloration, and cosmetic textiles since 2014 in 2015-2020. Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-invested around 1,00,000 USD to generate the PhD¹ thesis in terms of international standard costs in academia and philosophy. He didn't get single dollar from University of Calcutta to accomplish the thesis to contribute the PhD¹ thesis since 2014 in 2015-2020. Although, he didn't get any part-time service allowance from DJFT, University of Calcutta as Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a foreign category PhD researcher at DJFT, University of Calcutta. Moreover, he self-invested and published few manuscripts in the department incorporated with Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, DJFT, University of Calcutta. During the part-time service period of Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain, the research paper was also nationally and internationally circulated in the department by Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta in 2017-2020. Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta and Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had also a lot of e-mail communications of peer review and publication process of the research outcomes for the development for the research service at DJFT, University of Calcutta (evidence attached). Therefore, department and/or university may approve a part-time research fund to recover the long-term allowance of research service for Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain and Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta. Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta should also receive an allowance from University of Calcutta for his research service in peer review and publication process in 2016-2020. DJFT and secretary of University of Calcutta should sincerely take care the policy in terms of PhD law at University of Calcutta. The publications were registered and circulated in the name of DJFT, University of Calcutta. A part-time PhD¹ fund, a post PhD-thesis fund may be approved by the PhD authority of university in terms of PhD¹ achievement and

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

relevant publications. PhD research should not only be the matter of PhD researcher, PhD research should also be a dwell matter should also be a two-dimensional service of PhD researcher and PhD university. Who should take care the reason and season at DJFT, University of Calcutta on behalf of vice-chancellor? Who was/is the chief administration of DJFT since 2014? But, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not more invest to improve the thesis to continue the PhD¹ research (part-time category) whatever he did by self-funded in 2015-2020 since 2014. The stomach of Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain is almost empty now[22, 23, 64]. Parallely, Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta is retired now[67]. Should Professor Md. Anowar Hossain record the PhD¹ thesis without PhD¹ supervisor under the situation? What should be the PhD protocol of University of Calcutta? Although the school professor is retired, but the whole DJFT is not retired, but the DJFT should not be retired, but the DJFT should be sustained in academia and philosophia. DJFT and/or existing professor should take necessary action to certify to register the PhD¹ thesis on behalf of DJFT and/or University of Calcutta without hampering without disturbing without affecting any retirement support and retirement care to any retired professor. Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have right to ask a certified copy of a PhD¹ thesis of a PhD degree against the attached PhD¹ thesis if there is existing policy at university [1-10] [1, 2, 11] [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [4, 10, 21] [6, 8, 10-12, 19]. If the thesis has any contribution of knowledge at DJFT, the PhD researcher should receive a part-time funding since 2015 should receive a 'PhD¹ compensation award', if applicable by the central authority of research degree of University of Calcutta, India. Every compliance PhD should have a compensation support to the PhD achiever. Who should take care the judicial policy in academia and philosophia?

6.1 Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta should recommend a 'PhD¹ compensation award' to the office vice-chancellor and/or higher degree by research and/or relevant government authority of India

The PhD¹ research had fund crisis since 2015. A copy of PhD offer letter of University of Calcutta is attached. So, PhD¹ thesis should have a 'PhD¹ compensation award'. If the published thesis has any contribution to DJFT, University of Calcutta for the global performance of research and development. Retired Professor Ashis Kumar Samanta, DJFT should also get his charge of peer review service from DJFT, University of Calcutta. PhD¹ thesis should be valid should be compliance if University of Calcutta pays a 'PhD¹ compensation award' to the author. A PhD thesis without compensation support of university is not a thesis of university is not a PhD research of university. Every philosophical thesis of university should have a financial support of university should have a compensation on behalf of university to satisfy a minimum compliance of research and development. A research professor is a chief director category service in a university and a PhD student is a director category job in university and academia. If

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Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

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 BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; research organization; public service, crime, human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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the chief director has any income, the director should also have an income; if the director has an income, the chief director should also have an income. Every research director of university should take care the policy if a research director is a post of research service in academia and philosophia. Office of DJFT and/or office of Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh should/may approach to the office of vice-chancellor and/or higher degree by research, University of Calcutta and/or relevant government authority of India if they are administering, advertising, progressing, and leading the DJFT in terms of academia and philosophia.

6.2 Financial support to author and editor/supervisor, if applicable by the relevant authority

If University of Calcutta had/has no financial contribution of the PhD¹ thesis of author, the PhD¹ requirement and PhD compliance look like incomplete in academia and philosophia. Without having any award/funding, a PhD is a non-compliance PhD of any university. If there is existing thesis, what is the wrong to approve a ‘PhD¹ compensation award’ to author and editor/supervisor? The present existing value/existing practice of an Australian PhD is around 2,50,000AUD to 3,00,000AUD without material cost of the PhD research. Although materials costs may also be covered by the laboratory costs or tuition fees in terms of the limitation of price. Without paying to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); editor, and supervisor; no university should claim the thesis ownership under the judicial support of PhD law. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not interested to submit his thesis to any university without receiving 2,50,000USD and/or any financial compensation award of any university. Hence, all employers and/or administrative concerns are being requested to assess the approach for the general support of the scientist and researcher. What is the financial and cash motivation of a PhD thesis to PhD researcher if a thesis is the production practice/target in university and academia? In general, if a person can not continue routine duty, he/she can not claim money can not claim single dollar to the employer to the community to the association to the country. So, there is scope of research and development to satisfy the situation to satisfy the global trend in PhD if PhD is a professional duty in university in academia and philosophia. Although professor have a non-judicial tendency to cease the money of PhD researcher in academia and philosophia[23]. Who should take care the policy?

7 Thesis accomplishment and assessment comment of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, University of Calcutta, India

Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2015 in a research meeting, “can you put the name of a Bangladeshi professor in your PhD research in your PhD publication?” Collaboration at University of Calcutta, India should not be a matter of sole research funding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Every collaboration is also expensive process is a judicial process of research service in academia and philosophia. If PhD

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researcher participates in collaboration participates in research funding, what should be the financial contribution of University of Calcutta in PhD¹ of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain? What should be the judicial reason and season to make a research collaboration. Every collaboration should be compliance. Every authorship should also be a matter of research contribution and active participation in research. In a telephonic communication in 2019, Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta told to Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “your PhD thesis is completed now, you may submit the thesis to Jahangirnagar University”, Dhaka, Bangladesh[21]. But University of Calcutta, India has/had no official memorandum with Jahangirnagar University, Bangladesh. But Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has no official and personal memorandum with Jahangirnagar University about the achievement of PhD¹ thesis. The name of University Calcutta was already mentioned in the name of research publications which are online displayed since 2017-2018 in the name of University of Calcutta, India. The name of Jahangirnagar University, Bangladesh was not mentioned in the name of research publications which are online displayed since 2017-2018. Although, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain registered a new PhD at Jahangirnagar University to extend his analytical part of the research to extend to practice his relevant research field to search the relevant research funding to extend the relevant work of PhD¹ in Bangladesh to achieve the philosophy of another ‘new PhD’ in the relevant field of textile technology and advanced analytical findings. Moreover, Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta didn’t approach didn’t advise didn’t instruct to complete the certification process of University of Calcutta, India as per his PhD signing process of head of the department at DJFT. This misguiding philosophy of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a non-judicial is a non-compliance PhD process is a symptom of penalty of 1,000 Australian penalty unit. Presently, Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta is a retired professor and pension holder of University of Calcutta as per the below e-mail in 2026[67]. Therefore, a thesis certification may be approved and requisited if the PhD¹ thesis was assessed by Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta engaged, affiliated, and registered by Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta and supported for relevant publications. Short evidences of e-mail communication are also attached to satisfy the global academia and philosophia. Possibly, this is the judicial compliance and scholarly transparent to register the PhD thesis at University of Calcutta at the former research office of professorship of PhD¹ supervisor. This PhD¹ thesis should be registered at University of Calcutta, India. Moreover, nobody will take scholarly responsibility of the PhD¹ thesis without Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta if he is still alive in the planet if he has no physical limitations. Moreover, Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta is aligned with the subject expertise in textile technology and color engineering as per his profile summery. Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta and Dr. Arindam Bagchi was the supervisor of MTech/PhD⁰ thesis. PhD¹ thesis was the extension part of the MTech thesis[27]. Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, DJFT, University of Calcutta should

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manage the PhD¹ certificate of University of Calcutta or Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur, India where the PhD¹ thesis was jointly peer reviewed where the PhD¹ thesis was circulated who also mentioned the name of affiliations in the PhD¹ publications. Moreover, Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain is still busy to pursue his second PhD² to accomplish the certification process at RMIT University, Australia[23]. Similarly, Professor Dr. Lijing Wang, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia didn't approach to issue a PhD² certification at RMIT University after having two milestones, although he e-mailed and approached the submission of PhD² thesis in 2021 after having the first milestone at RMIT University. It was the middle time of PhD² between the first milestone and second milestone at RMIT University [22, 23]. Moreover, nobody will/should take scholarly responsibility of the PhD² thesis without PhD² supervisors in terms of PhD² compliance in academia and philosophia[67]. Moreover, Professor Dr. Lijing Wang also approved and recommended to extend the PhD² 'study leave' to continue the PhD² research in 2021. A PhD supervisor takes the scholarly responsibility, so he is designated as PhD supervisor/PhD professor/PhD registrar, so the post is prestigious and luminous and glorious in academia and philosophia. Every PhD^{1,2} thesis of Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain has different philosophies in his profession which are also individually published and displayed in different journals. He is facing fund crisis of research since 2014 whatever he managed from his self-pocket and presently his pocket/stomach is almost empty now is gradually empty now is gradually finished now. Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain sacrificed his quality of life and sacrificed the self-fund of retirement since 2014 against the registered research[22, 23] against the research and publications since 2006[4]. This filing and drafting cost of this final report of this present article is 40,000 USD at the office of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain was unable to make a further investment for the development of the thesis for the development of the DJFT, IJT, University of Calcutta although he self-invested until the date of this report and forwarded to the office of head/chairman, DJFT; and vice chancellor, University of Calcutta; and relevant government authorities. Moreover, Retired Professor Dr. Sadhan Chandra Roy, DJFT, University of Calcutta told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2017 in the geotextile laboratory, "PhD at University Calcutta has a very minor registration fee." Professor Dr. Sadhan Chandra Roy mentioned a three-digit PhD registration fee (Indian rupee) at University Calcutta when Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain attended at University Calcutta in 2017. Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, University of Calcutta was saying about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in a viva board at DJFT in 2017, "everyone takes the subject from their choice in his department, but he can not take classes from his choice of subject, he is only taking/teaching the left-over subjects in his department". Professor Dr. Sunil Kumar Sett told to Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2015, "you will just connect with a professor for your PhD." Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh told to Professor

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Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2017 in front of Kenedy Hall, DJFT “if you get PhD registration, you will get PhD”. Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh told to Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2014-2015, “we will pay your living and food cost if you continue your PhD here”[21]. If any employer asks the PhD¹ certificate rather than PhD¹ thesis; what should Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain say if Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta is a retired professor if he discontinues the professional communication with Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain at University of Calcutta, India [67]? Moreover, every employer can not assess can not understand the publications and PhD thesis. Moreover, every subject expert can not assess the publication and PhD thesis in different field of study. Although, every subject expert should have the judicial and academic capability to assess the PhD thesis when the thesis of Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain also wrote and summarized simply, public-friendly, researcher-friendly, and research-friendly. Although Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain may show his thesis instead of certified copy of the university/universities. So, what was the assessment protocol of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta of part-time PhD¹ of self-funded PhD¹ since 2015 (evidence attached)? The assessment protocol of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta was a valid PhD memorandum at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India [1-10] [1, 2, 11] [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [4, 10, 21] [6, 8, 10-12, 19]. Therefore, University of Calcutta/DJFT, IJT should respect should register the self-funded philosophical contribution to generate two thesis in the name of MTech thesis in cosmetic textiles[8, 69] and PhD¹ thesis in natural dyed textiles and cosmetic textiles at DJFT, University of Calcutta. Although, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain received MTech certificate under the theoretical training, four hours examinations, and routine examinations. Although, the structure of the MTech degree was more focused on advanced theory and training in textile technology. The sole author contribution of MTech thesis of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain[6-9] may also be additionally claimed for an additional degree of MPhil/PhD¹ whatever he did independently whatever he also practically extended, practiced, and self-invested around 27,00,000BDT in 2016 [27] in Bangladesh whatever he also expert connected with Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, University of Calcutta, India to achieve the philosophical thesis of PhD¹[4]. A pictorial attachment and evidence of self-funded PhD¹ research office is also briefly cited (2015-2017)[72].

7.1 Representation for a philosophical (Phil) degree in textile technology at DJFT, University of Calcutta

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain invested around 8,00,000 BDT to 10,00,000 BDT to pursue his MTech degree (2013-2015) in terms of self-sacrifice of self-salary in terms of non-paid ‘study leave’ in the profession in terms of research service at DJFT (2014-2015)[6, 7]. Moreover, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was also studied in a cyber-café at Ballygung circular road, Kolkata beside a tri-angle park when he had no personal laptop when

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there was no/little computer support and internet support at DJFT. Although he purchased laptop and self-invested for his additional research practice and/or holiday practice at DJFT. He also self-invested for printing of research paper in a cyber-café. Research supervisors and DJFT didn't advise didn't support about any 'endnote software' for the reference management. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain did analytical research from the outside of DJFT laboratory. Possibly FTIR machine of DJFT was not in good condition in 2014-2015 as per the departmental response and comment. He visited Jadavpur University, different testing laboratories, different material/chemical shops at Kolkata, India for his research support at University of Calcutta, India. Moreover, there was also huge lack of research training and project training when Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta was so much busy professor at DJFT in terms of head of the department, research professor, theory professor, and project works of Indian government. Who should be judicially liable to allot to assign the project teacher at DJFT? Definitely, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not be liable to allot a project teacher for the self-research training of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Although Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain paid to DJFT in USD in terms of international tuition fees in terms of the cost of research materials, research training, and relevant costs. Research contribution and research funding should not only necessary for Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, it should also be parallelly necessary for DJFT, University of Calcutta[21]. He also additionally invested in his office for MTech filing, MTech communication, MTech preparation with MTech coordinator, and MTech submission for admission (2011-2013). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should believe should approach that DJFT is special caring for developing and climbing in research in teaching and training. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have legal right to ask a Phil. (BPhil/MPhil/DPhil/PhD) Degree to University of Calcutta, India if he self-invested at DJFT if he is investing and serving in research and development at DJFT since 2014. If Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, PhD¹ supervisor assessed, published, affiliated, distributed the manuscript since 2016-2018, he should take full liability of registration, certification, and attestation of the PhD degree under the judicial protocol of a retired professor at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India.

7.2 E-mail record of retired Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, DJFT, University of Calcutta on 8 January 2026[67].

Re: Regreting your request to issue or upload a letter of recommendation for you, as I am retired now and have no official power to issue or upload any such recommendation from me.

Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: me, Cc: Prof. · Thu, Jan 8 at 9:41 AM

Message Body

As I am retired from university, as a retired pension holder, as per rules of our university, I can not write any recommendation letter or any such communication any more, using my

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

past professorship. Sorry for the inconvenience. Pls change the name of referee putting name of some other existing professor or director, who are still working in their office and is not retired.

All good wishes.

A k samanta

Ex RETIRED Professor , DJFT, IJT, KOLKATA, INDIA.

8 Investigation of Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT University, Australia

The PhD industry at DJFT, University of Calcutta should be suspended; Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh, DJFT, University of Calcutta should be suspended and/or terminated and/or early retired in his profession if he needs additional money or additional benefit or additional profit to enroll any PhD at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India and/or any relevant services to continue his university service to survive at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India. Moreover, he should not be the chairman of PhD committee and/or nomination committee and/or PhD registration committee at DJFT, he should not be the chairman of PhD committee and/or any assessment committee if he needs additional money/additional support/additional benefit from the non-paid PhD researcher and self-funded PhD researcher. Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh mentioned his salary '1,00,000 INR' to Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2014-2015 in his laboratory of geotextile. But Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't ask the salary of Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh. But, Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain had a curiosity to know about the salary of Professor Dr. Saifur Rahman, City University, Bangladesh who told to Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2006-2007, "salary of male and age of female should not say, my salary would be higher in industry rather than academic, my salary would be 2,00,000 BDT to 2,50,000 BDT in industry"[4]. But academic salary of an engineer should also be higher like an industrial engineer. Professor Dr. Saifur Rahman was the associate professor in 2006-2007 at Department of Textile Engineering (DTE), City University, Dhaka. Possibly, he got the post of associate professor at City University by his single PhD. What was the philosophy to be an associate professor at City University? To achieve and continue the requirement of a professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain submitted a printed manuscript of a book on garments manufacturing technology to Professor Dr. Saifur Rahman for a peer review/edition support in 2010 who telephoned after three years[1]. Although, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't offer any peer review fee to Professor Dr. Saifur Rahman in 2010. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain believes that the salary of professor is comparatively poor and poor. Sometimes, a professor may not enjoy a compliance house rent in the city for surviving in the planet. Every professor should have a house should have a compliance housing support who have no compliance housing support by birth[4]. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw

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Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

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A prestigious research practitioner (RP) in technology, academic, and law since 2006

International Professor and consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, Higher Education, PhD, & Postdoc)

BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD &

Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director

of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical

processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime,

human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home

ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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houses of Bangladeshi freedom fighters in 1971 for their contributions to the nation. There was also nameplated and funded by Bangladesh government. But the professors are not freedom fighters, although they also contribute for the nation for the nations. No professor should be homeless in any country. Possibly, every government also invests housing support for the poor people of a country who can not contribute for the government like the professors like professor (Dr.). Government may/should inflate should print should invest more money for the ethical professors rather than non-judicial professors. Professor/professor community should fight with the government. Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh, University of Calcutta may fight with the Indian government rather than students. Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh should do administrative work of research project without hampering any routine duty at DJFT. Possibly, there is also scope at university to take 'administrative leave'/'research leave' to continue to administer the administrative work of the project if he can not manage his duty time of class teaching/class load if the income of project is higher than DJFT. Although research project should be the additional duty of a professor in terms of additional income or proportional income of a professor. How can a person continue the triple duty of research project, head of the department, research professor, theory professor, and professorship at the department at DJFT? Government should take care, scrutiny, and assess the policy of professorship, projectship, and headship. The whole profile of Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh should be peer reviewed if he wrote the publications if he got the study leave support of University of Calcutta if he got time of research publications in his profession or only put the name with other researchers to claim authorship and promotion at DJFT, University of Calcutta. Moreover, his PhD thesis may also get priority of assessment in terms of compliance study leave support of University of Calcutta. Moreover, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to submit his full profile to the office of DJFT; to the office of Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh, DJFT, University of Calcutta, India; and secretary and vice-chancellor, university of Calcutta, India[4]. The office of Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh, DJFT, University of Calcutta, India; and secretary and vice-chancellor, University of Calcutta, India should peer review the profile of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to lead the academia and philosophia in the manner of ethical psycho-physics. Every ethical psycho-physics should have higher salary to recover the compensation in the profession when a non-ethical psycho-physics may automatically earn additional benefit to recover the professional compensation. The whole psycho-physics of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta and Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh was assessed and biologically recorded by Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Possibly, it can be sequenced as the profile of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain> the profile of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta; and the profile of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain> the profile of Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh. Although, they are also expert in their field of study in their field of research in their field of technology. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is already achieved and

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successfully achieved the quality of Bangladeshi professor, Indian professor, Australian professor, American professor, and the professor of United Kingdom. So, who should be the head/chief of the department and/or vice chancellor of University of Calcutta, India? What should be the compliance salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain[23]? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have judicial right to ask a global standard salary and global top-ranking salary of a professor to the professor community of academia and philosophia? If Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh paid benefit for his academic climbing, surviving, and sustaining in the profession at DJFT; if he is also showing similar attitude of asking benefit to his students in terms of recovery of his non-judicial compensation; if this is the chain reaction and chain philosophy in academia and philosophia which may be sourced and generated from his PhD supervisor and/or self-understanding and/or non-judicial self-understanding. This attitude is alarming and alarming against the sustainability and creditibility of academia and philosophia. Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh didn't directly ask didn't say the word of 'money' to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; but he asked sweet to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Although he may ask it by joking phenomena of Bengali nature and Bengali culture. But he showed the attitude of asking benefit/profit. Every approach and attitude of a valid professor should be the word of 'bullet and judicial' to satisfy the legal authority to satisfy the government authority to satisfy the global PhD community in academia and philosophia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is trying to convince and motivate the global academia and philosophia in PhD industries. This is also a matter of expert investigation for surviving in the academia and philosophia. If Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh neglected the continuous assessment of the students in 2013-2015, he should send back money/tuition fees to the bank account of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. What should be the academic rules in higher education at University of Calcutta? Although Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh took the MTech classes of geotextile at DJFT who had a power point presentation in front of MTech students who shouted with the irregular MTech students [5, 19]. Although Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh tried to invite guest professors/experts tried to ensure administrative support tried to ensure quality support to the foreign students at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India. Although office of Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh invited, motivated, and telephoned to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to participate in local conference at Kolkata to publish in conference at Kolkata in 2015 [6]. Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh/his office also managed the visiting of three textile industries at Kolkata. Dr. Satyaranjan Bairagi, DJFT told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2013-2015, "Professor Swapon Kumar Gosh is favored to student, his mentality is good; he is a local person, he has also local connection with politics/politicians." Dr. Satyaranjan Bairagi, DJFT told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Kenedy hall at DJFT when pro-vice-chancellor attended at DJFT in 2014-2015 "SKG uses some common English in his speech." SKG is a short name of Swapon Kumar Gosh (SKG) at DJFT. Dr.

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Arindam Bagchi, Senior Research Fellow, DJFT told to Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2014-2015, “Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta and Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh may ask money from you in the name of PhD, I did the PhD thesis of Professor Ashis Kumar Samanta when I served as a scientist”. Engr. Sabbir Pathan, MTech (2013-2015) told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2015-2017, “Samanta sir (Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta) is saying good for you.” Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta told to Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2015, “Bagchi did PhD under me, I just approved his PhD thesis without any correction.” Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta told to Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2015, “Tapasranjan Kar is doing PhD under me, he is not asking any money to me, he is doing test from his self-funding”. If people are doing research for global surviving and globally publishing the research articles, there is no far difference between the currency of Indian government and Bangladesh government, but there is deviation of printed paper of currency for the support of surviving in the planet. There is also necessary to continue an expert investigation of an expert professional at DJFT. If Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain invested and attended at DJFT since 2013-2015, the DJFT should plan to sustain the department. If DJFT is doing crime, the brand value of DJFT will decline, but the brand value of Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not impact should not decline will not decline under the valid support of this article. DJFT and/or Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh should not show any mental attitude to ask to trap any non-judicial attitude to any local student and/or foreign student at DJFT. If Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain paid tuition fees to DJFT in 2013-2015 and life-time citing the name of the affiliation/alumni of DJFT, the DJFT should be determined to do the practice of quality enhancement in higher education and research. Who is the present guardian of DJFT at University of Calcutta? He/she should take should extend should progress the necessary action and support at DJFT. Every person should not be the head of the department at DJFT. This is not a matter of age of a person. This is not a matter of age of a profession. This is not a matter of any political involvement. This is not a matter of routine rolling, routine changing, and routine modification to continue the administration at DJFT. This is a matter of ethical performance of academia and philosophia for global surviving in the planet. Although, a vice-chancellor of any university should be the post of a valid academician rather than a politician. Vice chancellor of University of Calcutta and/or government of India should invest should monitor the DJFT if DJFT is also the department of University of Calcutta, India is also contributing in higher education and research in terms of global surviving philosophy. Investment in quality professor, investment in MTech and PhD scholarship, and relevant funding and relevant care may glorify the department may sustain the department for the chain growth of the merit for the chain nursing of the merit for the global surviving in academia and philosophia.

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Table 3. Supervisor's function of first PhD¹, DJFT, University of Calcutta, India; and second PhD², twin PhD² or third PhD³ of author, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia [4]

Number of PhD	Name of supervisor/PhD registrar, acknowledged by Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain	Study field	Function of PhD ¹⁻³ supervisors
Third PhD ³ and/or twin PhD ² with second PhD ²	Professor Dr. Lijing Wang, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia Professor Dr. Robert Shanks, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia	Law and criminology	➤ PhD ³ registrar or PhD ³ witness
Second PhD ²	Professor Dr. Robert Shanks, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia	Textile, color, and camouflage technology	➤ Approval of PhD ² proposal ➤ Peer review ➤ General supervision ➤ PhD ² registrar or PhD ² witness
Second PhD ²	Professor Dr. Lijing Wang, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia	Textile, color, and camouflage technology	➤ Approval of PhD ² proposal ➤ Peer review ➤ General supervision ➤ PhD ² registrar or PhD ² witness
First PhD ¹	Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India	Textile, color, and natural dyes	➤ Approval of PhD ¹ proposal ➤ Peer review ➤ Scholarly witness during publication ➤ PhD ¹ registrar or PhD ¹ witness
First PhD ¹	Professor Dr. Nurul Abser, Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Bangladesh	Textile, color, and natural dyes	➤ Approval of PhD ¹ proposal for a new PhD which is relevant to PhD ¹ ➤ PhD registrar or PhD witness ➤ General supervision (5%), evidence attached

9 Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain asked to University of Calcutta in 2022 for the assessment of honorary doctorate degree

Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain asked and submitted the separate thesis to University of Calcutta for the assessment of honorary doctorate degree for his struggling in RMIT PhD school, reporting, and facing a critical conspiracy of life-threatening in Australian PhD school [23, 73]. Chancellor is the post of life-time and/or contractual honorary payment. Similarly, honorary

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doctorate should also be the post of life-time or one-time honorary payment. Every honorary assessor and honorary receiver should also get an honorary payment from the university. What should be the judicial philosophy of honorary doctorate degree? Who is take caring the philosophy of honorary doctorate degree in global academia and philosophia? Hence, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching chancellor position and/or honorary doctorate position of prestigious universities in global academia and philosophia [4, 23].

10 Concrete warning and approach to Department of Jute and Fibre Technology (DJFT), University of Calcutta, India for quality enhancement of DJFT

DJFT and University of Calcutta should note and record the self-nomination for the post of vice chancellor (part-time), University of Calcutta, India[4]. Moreover, Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not accept the international quality of DJFT, University of Calcutta since 2013. DJFT is practicing theoretically. But four hours examination in MTech is the non-compliance process of any theoretical assessment. A professor (Dr.) category invigilator needs to stay around five hours in the hall of examination. One-to-two-hour examination policy in school should/may be the global standard for the human assessment policy. Possibly, MTech students are also passing in exam without coming to routine class room at DJFT. There is also huge lacking in the assessment policy in terms of continuous assessment. Standardization of assessment, research project, and funding of MTech, MPhil, and PhD should improve at DJFT. Moreover, DJFT was not well prepared to invite foreign students at DJFT in 2013-2015. As per the comments of Professor Dr. Dhruvajyoti Chattopadhyay, Pro-vice- chancellor; the residential support of international students at University Calcutta in 2013-2015 was not well prepared was not well coordinated [21]. Similarly, and globally; every university should be well prepared and planned to invite foreign students to admit foreign students and/or local students. Although Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain invested and paid an international tuition fees in USD. Hence, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should also have right to ask a 'compensation award of MTech degree'. Smoking inside of DJFT should be completely demotivated and banned. Moreover, smoking and/or wine room may also be practiced and monitored in separate location in café to administer/satisfy the local culture at any location of any government of any university. One of maternal grandfather of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain pulled and enjoyed 'hookah' in his residence whatever seen by Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in his childhood life in 1989-1992. 'Hookah' is a piping process of smoking; and enjoying and relaxing like cigarette. Possibly, cigarette is the transforming version of 'hookah'. Every class should be taken in hygiene class room rather than small office room of a professor. Although the class room at the conference room was comparatively good at DJFT. Research students should have quality study places and/or separate laboratories. Hygiene of washroom should be daily monitored. Every BTech and MTech exam hall should be full monitored by the Professor (Dr.) if

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Professor (Dr.) is also taking government money for the routine invigilation of the exam hall. Professor (Dr.) should also come should also full-time present should also four hours present in the examination hall if the four hours examination is the academic standard at University of Calcutta, India. Professor (Dr.) should also come to the laboratory classes. It should not be the global academia and philosophia that Professor (Dr.) should not come to laboratory. Every answer script should be self-evaluated and self-scrutinized by the Professor (Dr.) if BTech/MTech is also the academic degree at DJFT if Professor (Dr.) is also taking the money of university for the review of the answer scripts. By research practice in academia and philosophia; BTech thesis and MTech thesis should also be a matter of expert training and routine classes. BTech thesis and MTech thesis should also be a project should also be a thesis should also be a matter of expert monitor. Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta told and shouted to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in a one-to-one research meeting, “I will make you cry to pass in MTech Thesis”. Crying is a personal matter, personal philosophy, and biological phenomena of a person. It may vary human to human. Everyone don’t cry in front of people. Someone may shy to cry in front of people. Someone may cry artificially in any moment although he/she is not shocked whatever he/she is showing in the philosophy of crowded crying. Someone may cry emotionally and automatically. Someone may stop crying immediately. Someone may not stop crying immediately. Crying of short-time may refresh the human brain. Crying of long-time or uncontrolled crying may be the source of physical and mental sickness. If a person can not establish his legal rights, he/she may cry automatically to overcome the self-biological situation. A baby cries for a chocolate or a biscuit or a bottle of juice, but an adult but a director but a chief executive officer should not cry when his/her full industry is burning by accident when he/she tries to mitigate to overcome the critical situation for surviving in the planet. A professor shouts by writing, a writer shouts by writing, a writer cries by writing and writing. An impression of verbal crime is automatically recorded in the human brain of opposite person if the brain is concentrated if the brain is one-dimensional. Everyone should not be upset due to non-judicial threat in academia and philosophia. This is the symptom of the penalty of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta should be imposed 1000 Australian penalty unit. Possibly, everyone was afraid to Engr. Arun, MTech, DJFT (2013-2015). Nobody could threat or suspend to Engr. Arun. If Engr. Arun had no problem at DJFT, if Engr. Arun had no situation of crying at DJFT, if Engr. Arun should not cry at DJFT; if nobody could disturb to Engr. Arun at DJFT; if Engr. Arun laughed and laughed at DJFT; what was the problem with Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at DJFT? What was the philosophy about Engr. Arun at DJFT? Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in an MTech class room, “if you pay to teacher, you will get the life-long benefit”. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain supported to university through the tuition fees in USD at DJFT, University of Calcutta. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn’t directly pay to Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar

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Author’s biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

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Samanta. Although Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta repeatedly asked benefit and benefit in 2014-2015. So, the MTech student should pay the tuition fees directly to the professor at DJFT rather than the official support of DJFT if University of Calcutta couldn't pay to Professor Dr.. Possibly, a portion of tuition fees may be paid directly to the professors through the students in global academia and philosophia. Moreover, DJFT may increase the MTech tuition fees for the international students if the operation costs of DJFT is higher due to the international service. Possibly, there is scope of judicial research and development at DJFT. What was the philosophy of higher education at DJFT? Although Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta shouted and told in 2014-2015 in the Kenedy hall at DJFT, "foreign students have no time of playing." One day, Professor Dr. Adwaita Konar told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in front of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, "I will not pass you if you can not answer the question in viva examination." Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta was tried to control Professor Dr. Adwaita Konar. Examination should not be the issue of making afraid to student in higher education in academia. If Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain fails in exam, he will participate in the repeated exam again, again, and again in terms of his one-dimensional focus of higher education in academia. Possibly, engineering of MTech questions were higher than the engineering in teaching and learning. Practically, engineering in teaching and learning should be higher and engineered than the engineering of MTech questions. Moreover, who took the laboratory classes of MTech of garments manufacturing in 2013-2015?[71] Possibly, head of the department didn't monitor at DJFT. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also invested to visit few garments industry in 2016 to overcome the lacking of his MTech degree of his MTech certificate (evidence attached). Furthermore, how to take a laboratory exam in engineering? Laboratory teaching, laboratory training, laboratory operation, written exam to prove the teaching and learning, viva exam to prove the teaching and learning, marking for continuous assessment, and total marking are the process of the total laboratory training and assessment. Who should guide/post the DJFT if DJFT has/had the existing professor in technology in laboratory in 2013-2015? Although, Professor Dr. Sunil Kumar Sett was self-taking his laboratory class of ring frame in spinning laboratory who was confidentially expressing his depth knowledge and confidence of his sole expertise, "nobody knows more than me about ring frame." Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also did practice of spinning in 2017-2019 in Bangladesh[74-76]. Moreover, who was the expert professor of garments manufacturing at DJFT? Some local Indian students of MTech were also disturbed by verbal crime to stop to participate in routine classes at DJFT, University of Calcutta when they can not self-participate in the routine classes. What was the dress code compliance of MTech students at DJFT?[21] Sometimes, a professor and/or a student may not invest to purchase a shirt; but nobody can force to wear the exact dress in academia and philosophia when they are matured and matured. Dress code of teachers and students is also the symptom of maturity index in profession. Every school

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and office should have a dress code. Dress code should not only the matter of a defence force when they also carry weapon and bag in their shoulder; but they don't forget to maintain a dress code. What is the philosophy of a defence force if they maintain dress code when they are busy? Day labours of companies are also maintaining a dress code in their work place. A poor person wears a tear or scratch cloth if he/she can not purchase the cloth. A fashionable person also wears a tear cloth when he/she purchases the cloth with comparatively higher price. Every teacher and student should have a dress code during the process of any schooling in academia and philosophia. They should self-think that they have involvement with a prestigious duty and professional service. Dress code is the established phenomena of human civilization and human surviving. A university should be the symbol of highest civilization. A male or female may forget to wear a full-covering dress when they are busy in schooling process. Because, there is no marks in dress code, hair code, and face code; there is no benefit of dress code, there is no profit in dress code, there is no credit in dress code, there is no promotion criteria to wear to maintain a dress code in the class room in the university. Possibly, black apron of university students and teachers is not only the standard dress code of a convocation of graduating ceremony. Possibly, black apron of university students and teachers may be the dress code of daily assembly in routine teaching and learning process. Engr. Arun, MTech, DJFT (2013-2015) also disturbed to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain and Dr. Jonathan Tersur Orasugh to stop the routine classes of Engr. Kalyan Roy Gupta, Assistant Professor and/or other routine classes. Verbal discussion of Engr. Sudarshan, MTech and Engr. Arun, MTech were not academic and professional at DJFT. Engr. Sudarshan told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in a class room, "DD (Professor Dr. Debasis Das) is one group and SKG (Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh) is another group, Anowar (Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain) will not understand these matters." Professor Dr. Debasis Das, DJFT talked about Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh, DJFT. Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh, DJFT told about Professor Dr. Sadhan Chandra Roy, DJFT. Professor Dr. Sadhan Chandra Roy, DJFT told about Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh, DJFT. Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta and Professor Dr. Sunil Kumar Sett were shouting to each other. Their shouting was flowing, crossing, and passing to the window of post graduate technology hall, University of Calcutta. These are the twisting phenomena of professor community for surviving philosophy at DJFT in academia and philosophia. One day, Engr. Kalyan Roy Gupta, DJFT told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, DJFT; "Arun (Engr. Arun, MTech, 2013-2015) is the owner of crore crore money, he is signing the bank cheque of crore crore rupee." Possibly, Engr. Kalyan Roy Gupta was respecting and caring to Engr. Arun for his money. Although Engr. Kalyan Roy Gupta, Assistant Professor tried to convince the local MTech students to stop any violence of the local MTech students. How can they pass without participating in routine classes? Their marks of continuous assessment should be poor than the regular participator in the process of teaching and learning in two years duration

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of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical

processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime,

human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home

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journey of MTech schooling. Who monitored the continuous assessment at DJFT on behalf of vice-chancellor of University of Calcutta when a vice-chancellor signs on the certificate on behalf of a professor/assessor/head of the department/reviewer/exam invigilator? Head of the department should also sign on the certificate of university. Who should take the judicial responsibility of a head of the department of a university? A vice-chancellor should not take the full liability of a Head of the department. Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta and Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh also tried to convince the local MTech students to stop any violence of the local MTech students. Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh also guided to the local student/students to improve the relationship with the foreign students. Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh tried to show to convince the theory of benefit/profit to the local students in terms of relationship with the foreign students. Some local Indian students were also disturbed by verbal crime under the addiction of wine at Post Graduate Technology Hall, University of Calcutta. It was the first morning time of a day during 'Saraswati Puja'. These are the total symptom of psychological harm and judicial crime with Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain against the natural schooling process, natural schooling growth, natural thinking process, and natural technological growth of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India. If DJFT hampered against the natural growth of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, DJFT may assess may allow may approve an 'MTech compensation award' to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't drink wine didn't drink wine with the Indian students. Taking class of professor in standing condition is more scientific rhythm to overcome than the seating condition under the movement of body which create an ideal brain environment to deliver the long-time class lecture to interact with the ready students in a ready class room. Technological universities invest for the purchasing of machines and machines, but they may have limited investment to make the digital class rooms for theory classes. Making the digital class rooms are not so much expensive for a government when the government has the judicial rights to print the money to build the infrastructure. No professor should take class in seating condition without having any physical limitation. The lecture sheet of Professor Dr. Debasis Das in polymer science was not readable when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was repeatedly tried to read in Bangladesh to continue his academic practice in polymer science and composite technology, it was also so difficult to read the letters in the lecture sheets. He should supply computerized lecture sheet or clear hand-written lecture sheet at DJFT[57]. Moreover, lecture sheet monitoring/lecture sheet training should be the routine duty of a chief professor/senior professor of any qualified department of any university of any country. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain participated in the training with the students of Eastern Michigan University but Professor Dr. Debasis Das didn't issue any certificate to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; possibly Professor Dr. Debasis Das certified to the students of Eastern Michigan University. Professor Dr.

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Debasis Das had a presentation on traditional clothing and history of traditional textiles at DJFT conference room [4, 21, 23]. A research student of Professor Dr. Debasis Das, Ms. Roopkatha Pallye was/is doing research on aroma textiles [7, 27] with Professor Dr. Subhas Ghosh at Eastern Michigan University, United States of America. Professor Dr. Sadhan Chandra Roy, retired professor, University of Calcutta told his DJFT office room in 2014-2015, “Debasis asked to put my name in his paper, he is just saying international and international”. No research authorship should be automatic rather than contribution. Engr. Sirshendu Mukherjee, Dr. Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, and Dr. Rajib Bhattacharyay; DJFT tried to ensure the casual support in casual meetings at DJFT. Dr. Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik, DJFT told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2014-2015 in wet processing laboratory, “if you have money, if you don’t give money to people, people may cease your money in your local area.” Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in a research meeting, “I don’t evaluate the thesis of BTech and MTech, I don’t see the thesis of BTech and MTech; I only see the thesis of PhD”. Who should see the thesis of BTech and MTech? If a person can do thesis in BTech/BSc if a person can perform in BTech/BSc thesis, he/she should/may get an additional degree/bonus degree of BPhil/MPhil/PhD/DPhil/DTech. If a person can do thesis in MSc/MTech if a person can perform in MSc/MTech thesis, he/she should/may get an additional degree/bonus degree of BPhil/MPhil/PhD/DPhil/DTech. So, a valid professor (Dr.) should supervise the thesis of BTech/MTech. Every academia and philosophia may assess and continue their scholarly duty accordingly. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain approached him PhD supervisor and sent him PhD manuscripts which are already published in different journal since 2017-2018 which are also peer reviewed by Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta. PhD¹ enrolment should not only be a matter of additional benefit at DJFT. What should be the judicial function of a research professor/residential professor in BTech/BPhil, MTech/MPhil school at DJFT? Research compliance should get priority to increase the Brand value of DJFT. Nobody should play with the brand value of DJFT. BPhil and MPhil degree may also be added with the program of research degree[77-79]. Course curriculum of MTech degree, DJFT is still attractive to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to fight with the global competition in technical textiles and textile technology[71]. There were also subject experts according to MTech course curriculum at DJFT, University of Calcutta in 2013-2015[5]. The course of research methodology and research compliance should also be included to teach the local students and foreign students. This course should design to teach in the routine class of BTech and MTech at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India. But there was lack of laboratory training in terms of technical textiles whatever Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain tried to recover by two-months additional training at KE technical textiles private limited, India under the supervision of Engr. Sukumar Roy, chairman and managing director; and Dr. Sankar C. Khatua, head, quality control and assurance. There was also a day long training at

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KE technical textiles private limited under the guidance of Professor Dr. Sunil Kumar Sett and Engr. Kalyan Roy Gupta, Assistant Professor, DJFT. Every theory of syllabus should have an impression of laboratory to enhance the continuous development of the engineering education. Every laboratory should also have an impression of theory. At least, 50% of taught courses of theory of BTech and MTech in engineering should have the training of laboratory. Possibly, proper aligning between theory and laboratory is the global challenge is the global limitation in academia in engineering education. Although, there is existing research and development. Possibly, university has the poor investment in syllabus development. But, what should be the exact purpose of PhD schooling? There is scope of research and development. Research proposal should be the major discussion, understanding, and priority theme for the PhD¹ enrolment for the enrolment of a research degree. A research proposal is also a milestone of a PhD degree. Sometimes, a research proposal may also be a philosophical degree may also judge for a PhD funding or research funding. The whole PhD thesis of DJFT should be displayed and scrutinized for the quality enhancement support at DJFT. Who should take care the PhD industry at DJFT? Who should take care the DJFT? Professors of DJFT are gradually emptying and emptying. Professors of DJFT are going back to home and home. There is existing basket, there is existing laboratory, there is existing investment of the government, there is existing infrastructure of the government; but there is lack of knowledge industry, but there is huge lacking of professor in technology and philosophy. Similarly, and globally; there is so many branded baskets so many prestigious baskets in the academia and philosophia all over the world, everywhere is baskets and baskets, but there is huge lacking of professor (Dr.) inside the prestigious baskets, but there is huge lacking of knowledge industry inside the prestigious baskets, but there is huge lacking of PhD industry inside the prestigious baskets. Possibly, some government invest for baskets rather than professor (Dr.). What is the reason and season at DJFT? Moreover, DJFT should have the policy to build professor in the relevant field of expertise to sustain the department to survive the department in the global competition of higher education and research. Philosophically, DJFT is crying and crying for having quality teacher and research professors. But nobody is hearing the crying of DJFT? Immediately, quality teacher should appoint/search when maximum teachers are being retired and retired. Although, expert professor is a global limitation and global crisis in global academia. Training and making expert professor are also very expensive process. Nobody has a tendency to invest, but everyone has a tendency to eat the fruit. Every department should have a funding to make to build to train expert professor in academia in science and technology. By chance, expert professor is being developed. Sometimes, expert professor may get a poor salary than the secretarial job than the common job of a central government. Moreover, expert professor can not exist/sustain in the department due to life-threatening conspiracy, an Australian example is also cited to satisfy the global academia and philosophia[22, 23]. The professional snake/snakes may bite may attack may harm to the expert professors if there is basket if the

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

basket has any professional snake. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw a real snake of around one foot length in front of post graduate technology hall, University of Calcutta in 2014. A ground of university should be clean and clean. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also saw a real snake of around three feet length at Salt Lake, Kolkata in 2017. Lake is the place of snake, but the university is not a place of snake. Practically, non-expert professor don't like the expert professor in academia and philosophia but they can not run the department but they harm the national and/or global development policy and global surviving philosophy. These are also the situation of additional challenge in the global academia against surviving philosophy in the planet. What is happening in the global academia? Moreover, expert professor is also very expensive and expensive in the global platform of academia and research[4]. So, who is teaching in the department at DJFT? Every nomination policy should monitor should transparent at DJFT. Moreover, as alumni of DJFT, as alumni contribution at DJFT; Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a concrete warning to make a transparency in quality enhancement policy. The PhD degree of DJFT should be suspended if the existing professor has no PhD 'study leave', PhD certificate, and PhD thesis. DJFT has huge lack of PhD expert. DJFT should not take PhD student if DJFT has no PhD expert. DJFT should invest to build to appoint PhD expert. PhD experts are not readymade that the experts can be found in a casual shop. Possibly, nobody got PhD funding at DJFT from the MTech student group at DJFT in 2013-2015. So, the salary of readymade expert is always higher should be extremely higher[4]. If DJFT have no quality practice of 'study leave'; DJFT need not research training and need not research practice need not research professor. Possibly, every professor search PhD student for self-climbing for self-surviving. What is the philosophy of self-surviving in the name of PhD student? Possibly, professor should also take self-study leave for self-climbing for self-improving for self-training. A professor should not forget to take self-study leave. Who should take care the policy? Similarly, every country/university should take care the PhD process for global surviving in academia and philosophia. Nobody should cheat should misguide with academia and philosophia against global surviving philosophy. Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not take any liability as alumni of DJFT. As foreign national, as alumni contribution at DJFT, Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain also self-invested by developing and publishing two sole author thesis in textile technology at DJFT, University of Calcutta since 2014. Both thesis are online displayed and recorded for the support of future researcher in national and global community since 2016[6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [6, 8, 10]. He is still writing and contributing in 2026 at DJFT for the quality enhancement at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India. Judicially, professionally, and academically; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had no communication with the teachers of primary school, secondary school, and higher secondary school in terms of any pending certification since 2005-2006[1, 4, 21]. By chance, he is also life-time citing the name of DJFT, University of Calcutta. By chance, he is also liable to enhance the

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quality of DJFT. Foreign candidate, foreign scholar, and foreign alumni should also get free of cost priority in DJFT nomination if they have quality for the service in higher education and research for knowledge transfer for global surviving. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is ready to serve is ready to approach to DJFT and vice-chancellor, University of Calcutta under the remuneration of 20,000USD per month under the category of part-time service to enhance the quality of higher education and research for global surviving[65].

11 What was the administrative contradiction of PhD¹ and still mis-understanding to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain?

In 2017, Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, DJFT verbally and non-officially forwarded to Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh, DJFT about PhD¹ discussion at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, DJFT had no scholarly communication of PhD¹ with Professor Swapon Kumar Gosh, DJFT. Every PhD dealing should be suspended, should be immediately suspended at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India if DJFT would like to continue PhD degree in textile technology. Every dealing should be transparent and student-friendly for sustaining DJFT for sustaining the PhD industry for surviving in the global policy of PhD. What was/is the limitation of PhD registration of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain? Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh should assess to satisfy his professional duty at DJFT. PhD is a matter of scholarly assessment and scholarly contribution; PhD should not be the matter of any special dealing with DJFT. This is the frustrating phenomena to the scholar to the academia and philosophia. There is no chance of any special dealing of any PhD degree in PhD community for global surviving in academia and philosophia. These are the global challenge in PhD industries[22, 23]. Therefore, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a judicial right to ask to request to approve a ‘PhD¹ accomplishment allowance’ to ensure a ‘PhD¹ compensation award’ to accomplish the process of ‘PhD certification’ to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain under the research service protocol of University of Calcutta, India. Full peer review and publication process of PhD¹ is attached for the relevant assessment and consideration of DJFT, University of Calcutta, India. Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh should manage the whole situation of PhD¹ if he is long-term claiming the guardianship/directorship of DJFT if he is claiming a residential professor at DJFT if he is claiming the seniority phenomena at DJFT. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have right to ask a Phil. Degree to University of Calcutta if he self-funded served to University of Calcutta under the valid PhD¹ memorandum/PhD¹ registration with Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, Head, DJFT, IJT, CU and secretary, University of Calcutta, India in 2015 since 2014. Signed copies of the DJFT offer letter and PhD memorandum are also attached to satisfy the judicial transparency.

12 Authorship, PhD funding, PhD researcher, PhD administration, and PhD supervisor are five different phenomena in a PhD industry

Possibly, some PhD supervisors have no time to read the full manuscript, but they are happy and agree to be an author of the manuscript of the research publications. Every author should understand the research should read the research. Every author should understand the publication should understand the philosophy. PhD supervision should not be the non-judicial way of achieving authorship of the research of the philosophy. PhD supervision is the judicial philosophy of research witness, research training, research understanding, research teaching, and knowing/certifying/registering scholarly ownership, scholarly contribution, and scholarly credit of the researcher. PhD supervision and PhD researcher are the duty of high standard ethical performance in academia and philosophia. A PhD supervisor may also black-mail his student in the name of research funding to achieve authorship to achieve a commission of PhD scholarship to achieve commission of fellowship to achieve commission of professional earnings. Authorship distribution, certification, and legal attestation are the major duty of a valid PhD supervisor. So, people respect PhD industry; so, people come to PhD industry; so, people come to PhD supervisor; so, people come to PhD professor; so, people register the PhD; so, people also invests for a PhD degree. Assessment and certification are the core duty are the routine duty of a PhD industry of a PhD professor of a PhD supervisor. If Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is paying a PhD scholarship to a PhD student, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not be an author of the research in the PhD industry for his funding in the research. Although research funding has a financial contribution rather than scholarly contribution in the research. The name of Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh, DJFT, University of Calcutta was mentioned in the brief list of PhD publications (attached the e-mail evidence). Possibly he is not an author, possibly he can not understand the publications but he is a scholarly witness when Dr. Jonathon Tersur Orasugh self-funded for his PhD research at University of Calcutta, India. But possibly, he is doing his second PhD² at another university. Every second/third PhD is a repeated investment of a PhD researcher is a burden philosophy in a single life is an additional pressure of a researcher if the PhD topic is not relevant to the first PhD is not relevant to the self-expertise in research and development is not relevant to the advancement in self-expertise, one-dimensional expertise, one-dimensional growth, and one-rope expertise in research. What is the PhD drama in the PhD industry? If a person has a second/third PhD, the salary in the profession should be double/triple/competitive to cover the professional compensation. Who should take care the policy? Who should claim the policy of compensation in PhD profession? If a person has two houses at Kolkata City, he/she will get double rent from the houses. Nobody should appoint PhD student without full-understanding the judicial philosophy of PhD. PhD is not a joking phenomenon if PhD is a matter of training and learning if PhD is a matter of contribution in research and development.

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12.1 List of PhD articles of Dr. Jonathon Tersur Orasugh, DJFT, University of Calcutta, India who included authorship in terms of research witness and/or research contribution

A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020)
 ijtskg40@gmail.com

To: me, engr.anowar@yahoo.com Cc: , and 95 others · Sun, Oct 19, 2025 at 8:51 PM
 ...engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264 Please...

Many thanks for your email,pl.

Dr. Swapan Kumar Ghosh

Professor and Former Head of the Department

Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta

35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata - 700019, West Bengal, India

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=nV77ThAAAAAJ>

Jute cellulose nano-fibrils/hydroxypropylmethylcellulose nanocomposite: A novel material with potential for application in packaging and transdermal drug delivery system

JT Orasugh, NR Saha, D Rana, G Sarkar, MMR Mollick, Industrial crops and products 112, 633-643, 126, 2018

Construction of unpaved rural road using jute-synthetic blended woven geotextile—A case study

G Basu, AN Roy, SK Bhattacharyya, SK Ghosh, Geotextiles and Geomembranes 27 (6), 506-512, 111, 2009

Effect of cellulose nanocrystals on the performance of drug loaded in situ gelling thermo-responsive ophthalmic formulations

Jonathan Tersur Orasugh, Gunjan Sarkara, Nayan Ranjan Sahaa, BeautyDasa, Amartya Bhattacharyyaa, Sreyasi Das, Roshnara Mishra, Indranil Roy, Atiskumar Chattoopadhyay, Swapan Kumar Ghoshb

International journal of biological macromolecules 124, 235-245, 89, 2019

Nanofiber-reinforced biocomposites

JT Orasugh, SK Ghosh, D Chattopadhyay

Fiber-reinforced nanocomposites: Fundamentals and applications, 199-233, 52, 2020

Synthesis of methylcellulose/cellulose nano-crystals nanocomposites: Material properties and study of sustained release of ketorolac tromethamine

JT Orasugh, NR Saha, G Sarkar, D Rana, R Mishra, D Mondal, SK Ghosh

Carbohydrate Polymers 188, 168-180, 51, 2018

A facile comparative approach towards utilization of waste cotton lint for the synthesis of nano-crystalline cellulose crystals along with acid recovery

JT Orasugh, NR Saha, G Sarkar, D Rana, D Mondal, SK Ghosh, ...

International journal of biological macromolecules 109, 1246-1252

List of articles of Dr. Jonathon Tersur Orasugh also authored by Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh, DJFT although the name of PhD supervisor can only be mentioned as corresponding author and/or scholarly witness as pre-requisite of valid PhD supervisionship and authorship.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

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Possibly, some supervisors are never authored are never supervised are never read the PhD article; but they claim both functions to achieve additional credit and fund in the profession. Although Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain don't know about the research contribution of Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh in the PhD thesis of Dr. Jonathon Tersur Orasugh at DJFT to satisfy the authorship and/or judicial compliance of PhD supervision and authorship. The recognition of PhD supervisor and authorship has two different meaning and research understanding in PhD industry. But, still the supervisors claim as PhD professor in PhD industry when PhD professor/PhD supervisor is very prestigious position in academia in philosophia in PhD industry. Everyone likes to show and display the prestigious position rather than professional duty rather than professional practice. Century in publications should not be mandatory should not be the global tendency for a PhD supervisor. Sometimes, a PhD student may be more scholar than a PhD supervisor and/or PhD professor when getting a right PhD supervisor and/or quality PhD supervisor is also tough journey due to lack of government policy due to lack of university policy due to the spreading of academic crimes and academic diseases. Possibly, there is also university who rent or appoint or invite research officer and/or PhD student to achieve authorship rather than scholarly contribution. Some academicians or PhD supervisors can rent or appoint PhD student, but they can not be a PhD student. But they are shaming to be a PhD student. Practically, PhD student is not a smaller position than a PhD supervisor. They imagine that the PhD studentship is not a prestigious position, but PhD supervision is a prestigious position. If a lecturer/PhD professor/PhD supervisor can self-understand his/her poor quality, he/she may be a PhD student, he/she may self-surrender, he/she may take 'study leave' from his university rather than searching a PhD student. Some non-judicial academician may contract with non-judicial academician for non-judicial surviving, non-judicial climbing, and non-judicial sustaining in the profession in academia and philosophia. These are the global drama in academia and philosophia. Hence, a non-judicial team or chain may be generated may serve against the peace in the profession against the judicial surviving in the planet. What is the existing philosophy of the PhD supervisors? What should be the real philosophy of a PhD supervisors? These are the laughing and challenging phenomena in academia and philosophia. Sometimes, a research director may not be a scholarly author with the researchers who are doing work in a research project. Sometimes, a researcher may not be a scholarly author of his research director. A PhD supervisor may also black-mail his student in the name of research funding to achieve scholarly authorship to cease the scholarly authorship. These should not be the philosophia in the PhD industries. These are the ignorance and/or non-judicial practice in PhD industry. These are the symptom of crime of 1,000-10,000 Australian penalty unit. Moreover, sole authorship is required to certify a PhD degree on behalf of any university. The number of sole authored PhD achiever are also minimum in PhD industry. The transfer of scholarly wealth and money transfer are the common phenomena are the common

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Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director

of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical

processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime,

human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home

ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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assessment scale in PhD industry. Every transfer of scholarly wealth is non-judicial. A professor may scholarly transfer for his/her self-benefit and/or misunderstanding and/or ignorance in academia and philosophia. Authorship is not transferrable. Research authorship is not only life-time, research authorship is permanent, research authorship is judicial. Authorship of knowledge is the authorship of research are not transferrable like money transfer in the bank account. Some professors are totally confusing the right goal of academia and philosophia. Possibly and philosophically, global PhD industries are crying to enhance the ethics in PhD industry. But nobody is hearing and caring to satisfy the judicial goal in PhD industry. Every branded university and/or non-branded university should take care to sustain the PhD industry. What should be the purpose of a PhD industry? A PhD researcher sacrifices quality of life, time, salary, sex, and family life. But, at the end of PhD situation; he is not getting sole authorship, he is not getting PhD certificate, he is not getting recognition and PhD award in academia and philosophia. So, what is the genuine duty of a PhD supervisor if he/she is self-claiming a prestigious position of PhD supervisor and/or PhD professor? What is the exact purpose of a PhD supervisor? These are the symptom of judicial crime against the peace and genuine purpose of a PhD school. These are the symptom of applying and imposing a penalty unit of 1,000-10,000 Australian penalty unit. If a professor occupies one room in university, he/she may keep his/her PhD thesis in his office and repeatedly show his/her thesis to his/her student to train his/her student to motivate his/her student to guide his/her student. Moreover, PhD student may not have a study place may not have a study element may not have internet service may not have food in stomach may not have the proper nutrition for the total functioning for the one-dimensional functioning of the brain and body in academia and philosophia. PhD student may move here and there for his/her study. What is the preparation of university to admit PhD student although the university may claim PhD tuition fees and/or PhD interview and/or PhD professor and/or PhD drama in academia and philosophia? Professor may prioritize money rather than talent. Possibly, director graded person and/or high salaried person and/or non-researcher may get priority for a PhD registration at DJFT, University of Calcutta. If the high-salaried person is the requirement of an academic PhD at DJFT, what is the assessment philosophy at DJFT, University of Calcutta? But PhD researcher should also get priority for a PhD certification. It seems that PhD certification is a matter of non-scholar and/or non-researcher and/or high salaried person and/or sex-oriented person who can not clearly understand can not clearly define the philosophy of doctoral study who have little time for doctoral study who have little time for research. But PhD thesis and relevant publications are the matter of PhD researcher rather than PhD certificate. What is the philosophy in PhD awarding at university? What are the reasons of PhD awarding at university? Every PhD industry should be toxic-free, PhD-friendly, and research-friendly. If professor prioritize money and sex rather than talent, 1,000-10,000 Australian penalty unit should be imposed to the professor. Although PhD student can not

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

complain against the designated position of PhD supervisor and/or PhD professor in terms of high professional respect, high dignity, and a beautiful office room at university inside of university. Although PhD student hides and hides the crime of professor to satisfy the professor to respect the professor to sustain the PhD funding in academia and philosophia. Possibly, a routine class teaching of a professor/research professor is a matter of joking and laughing although a research professor claims a PhD professor and/or PhD supervisor. At the end of the situation, a PhD student may also face a life-threatening conspiracy in PhD school for his scholarly contribution [22, 23]. If university can respect PhD scholar and PhD compliance, the global beauty of higher education and research may enhance for judicial surviving for total surviving in the planet.

12.2 Remarked authorship compliance at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India

More numbers of authorship decline the grade of philosophical contribution of a PhD candidate against the judicial requirement of a single philosophical degree of a short journey in research and development. Sometimes, a PhD researcher can not understand the authorship compliance and PhD compliance. They just put the name of supervisor and colleague researcher due to lack of authorship guidance, authorship knowledge, and training of a PhD supervisor. Sometimes, PhD researcher tries to satisfy to the PhD supervisor in the name of gift authorship or honorary authorship or ghost authorship to secure the PhD funding to increase the self-protection in academia and philosophia to achieve to secure the process of PhD certificate. In misunderstanding and authorship ignorance, PhD researcher may try to satisfy try to attract try to non-judicially respect by putting name of PhD supervisor and/or colleague researchers. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should ask them if Professor Dr. Dipankar Chattopadhyay and Dr. Jonathon Tersur Orasugh, DJFT, University of Calcutta should/may have an authorship explanation in the PhD thesis of Dr. Jonathon Tersur Orasugh, DJFT (2015-2019). In 2017, Dr. Jonathon Tersur Orasugh also told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain about the authorship issue. Dr. Jonathon Tersur Orasugh was not happy about the authorship in his journey of PhD research under the supervision of Professor Dr. Dipankar Chattopadhyay, University of Calcutta (2015-2019). Dr. Jonathon Tersur Orasugh was not happy with Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh in terms of non-judicial proposal of PhD funding of Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh [21]. Every PhD funding should have the financial benefit of PhD supervisor and PhD researcher should have the two-dimensional benefit. Similarly, Dr. Satyaranjan Bairagi, DJFT, University of Calcutta is also doing second PhD². Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't know if he got his first PhD¹ certificate and authorship of the PhD thesis at Indian Institute of Technology, Delhi, India (2015-2020). If Dr. Satyaranjan Bairagi can create an extension of his first PhD¹ with second PhD², it is more beneficial to improve the expertise in the relevant field of study, academia, and philosophia. BTech, MTech, PhD¹, and PhD² should have a

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Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

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BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD &

Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director

of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical

processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime,

human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home

ministry, crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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similarity in the professional expertise for the self-development and self-climbing in academia and philosophia. If Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain briefly wrote the history of his local degree and foreign degree to satisfy judicial compliance, similarly every degree achiever should also write their history of their degree; without which Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not accept any local degree and foreign degree of any university of any country. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain don't know the PhD certificate and PhD history of Dr. Kashmita Bhattacharya and Dr. Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India. Although, Dr. Kashmita Bhattacharya told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, "I am not going to DJFT." Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain don't know the PhD certificate and PhD history of Dr. Abdur Rahman, Dr. Abu Shaid, Dr. Sutapa Choudhury, Dr. Tanushree Saha, Dr. Rumbidzi, Dr. Nauman Choudhury, Dr. Aisha Rehman at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. Dr. Andrea Eckersley, Coordinator of higher degree by research, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia; and Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, vice-chancellor should be judicially responsible to take care the PhD policy, PhD history, PhD training, and judicial transparency of PhD at RMIT University, Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain don't know the PhD certificate and PhD history of Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, Herriot watt University, United Kingdom since 2006-2007. Hence, some PhD students may also self-make a PhD certificate of his foreign PhD to overcome the situation of shame and international PhD game in academia and philosophia. Although PhD supervisor may self-submit/self-claim the non-registered PhD thesis of his/her student for his/her self-PhD and/or another PhD student who pay for a PhD certificate who do sex for a PhD certificate who show non-judicial benefit and profit for a PhD certificate who have a special dealing for a PhD certificate in academia and philosophia. If a person has no research, if he/she can put the name of author in the publication of another researcher, he may be more accepted may be more credited in PhD community in academia and philosophia. This is a wrong concept in PhD community in academia and philosophia under the guidance of a non-judicial PhD supervisor. Although maximum PhD supervisors and/or university professor are doing the crimes in terms money in terms sex in terms ignorance in terms of relation in terms of special benefit. Sometimes, research laboratory may be a risk zone for a research scholar who is generated/generating new idea continuously. Thesis transfer and scholarly transfer are the global challenge in academic, philosophia, and PhD industry. Hence, authorship compliance should be a major training should have a major guidance for a vice-chancellor, PhD researcher, PhD supervisor, and PhD industry. A wrong understanding may generate may continue a chain mistake in PhD industry in global academia and philosophia. If the chain is so much longer and stronger if the number of chains are longer if the chain is also expanded to international; there is possibility of practicing the life-threatening conspiracy and non-judicial drama in academia and philosophia. Hence, a bad person and non-qualified person may sing may enjoy the planet, may be promoted as non-judicial

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member of a chancellery team, they have no financial crisis, they have no sex crisis; but a good and qualified person can not serve the academia and philosophia can not enjoy the planet. What should be the judicial philosophy for surviving in the planet in academia and philosophia? Therefore, every PhD researcher and PhD supervisor may keep a PhD record of PhD history to satisfy the transparency of the PhD thesis in academia and philosophia.

12.3 Name putting and authorship compliance of PhD¹ publications of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

Name putting in publication is the global drama in academia and philosophia. Dr. Ferdous Ara Dilruba told in a meeting at Bangladesh Jute Research Institute, “I saw a small publication of nature with many authors”. Hence, she generally motivated multi-authors in publications. Possibly, Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta didn’t get authorship training at University of Calcutta. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain don’t know, if there was the research funding of University of Calcutta to Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta to develop to train to Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta? Vice-chancellor, University of Calcutta should regularly approve and allow PhD ‘study leave’ and research training for the DJFT teachers. Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta and head of DJFT should officially and judicially register and note at DJFT that Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, Dr. Kashmita Bhattacharya, Dr. Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik, DJFT, University of Calcutta, India; Professor Dr. Md. Nurul Absar, Jahangirnagar University, Bangladesh; Dr. Ferdous Ara Dilruba, BJRI, Bangladesh; Dr. Padma S. Vankar, Dr. Dhara Shukla, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur, India; Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, City University, Bangladesh are not scholarly authors of the PhD^{0,1} publications of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, table 2. Possibly, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, Dr. Kashmita Bhattacharya, and Dr. Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik, DJFT, University of Calcutta, India didn’t read the full manuscript for one-time duration. So, they are not the genuine peer reviewer of the manuscript. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should claim the full authorship should take the full responsibility of his research and publication of his PhD^{0,1}. These are the sole authored and sole funded PhD^{0,1} publications of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2014-2020. DJFT, University of Calcutta, India; and Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur, India had zero funding in the PhD^{0,1} research of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. There was no judicial reason and season to mention the authorship to mention the name of Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur, India to satisfy the global academia and philosophia if the institute peer reviewed the manuscript. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have judicial right to ask the machine training in a research laboratory to a laboratory trainer/officer. Dr. Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik supported for the machine training. What was the thesis support of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta and Dr. Arindam Bagchi? Possibly, they didn’t read the full

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manuscript for one time peer review of the full publication of MTech[8]. The salary of a project teacher/supervisor should be higher than the theory teacher in academia and philosophia. A project teacher is not a general laboratory technician. What was the academic and professional reason, season, and philosophy to include Dr. Kashmita Bhattacharya with the self-funded and sole authored project of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at DJFT, University of Calcutta in 2015? There was no academic and professional reason, season, and philosophy to include Dr. Kashmita Bhattacharya with the self-funded and sole authored project of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at DJFT, University of Calcutta. Similarly, Professor Dr. Lijing Wang, RMIT University told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT University in 2021, “publish with Abdur Rahman (Dr. Md. Abdur Rahman), put the name of Abdur in your publications; publish with Belinda (Ms. Belinda)”. What was the academic and professional reason, season, and philosophy to include Ms. Belinda and Dr. Md. Abdur Rahman with the self-funded and sole authored project of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University? There was no academic and professional reason, season, and philosophy to include Ms. Belinda and Dr. Md. Abdur Rahman with the self-funded and sole authored project of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University. If five PhD expert is writing and parallelly contributing to write a PhD manuscript, the quality, number of research questions, length, analysis, strength of the PhD manuscript will be/should be comparatively judicial and higher. If one person if one PhD expert is working, writing, and contributing to write a manuscript; the number of research questions, length, and analysis may be comparatively reduced. So, multi-authorship and gift authorship in sole authored PhD manuscript may reduce the total contribution of an author which may be generated a non-judicial PhD drama in academia and philosophia. Although, the number of authorships may not increase the thesis quality. Every length of research relates to research funding and research salary of a PhD researcher. Every hour of a PhD researcher relates to dollar and dollar. Every office of a PhD researcher relates to money and money[27]. Number of gift authorship automatically declines the scholarly credit of the main author in PhD research in publication in academia and philosophia. Research compliance should be the key functions of a PhD supervisor if PhD is a learning stage in academia and philosophia. So, people are going to university, so people are coming to academia and philosophia. People are not going to PhD school to achieve the century of publications. Century of publications are the post-PhD drama are the post-academic drama if he/she continues the relevant research if he/she has research funding to continue the research and relevant development. Although, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has century of sole author PhD⁰⁻³ publications [1]. Hence, there is no relation between PhD degree and life-time practice of the relevant research in academia and philosophia. DJFT, University of Calcutta, India should verify should make an assessment if the PhD students of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta got any philosophical degree or PhD degree or PhD

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thesis in terms of DJFT record and the record of the central administration of University of Calcutta, India. Possibly, he had few PhD students at DJFT, University of Calcutta. Possibly, he supervised and completed few PhD thesis at DJFT. Global academia and philosophia should have capability to evaluate the publications and person in terms of article in terms of profession rather than the brand value of institute, research centre, supervisor, and relevant researcher.

12.4 Name putting and authorship compliance of PhD² publications of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT University, Australia

Authorship situation of PhD¹ publications of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, India was almost similar in PhD² publications of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at School of Fashion and textiles, RMIT University, Australia. Professor Dr. Lijing Wang also made and intended a non-judicial drama to include the non-judicial authorship of different persons in the PhD² publications of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain[21-23, 80]. In the meantime, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also faced a critical conspiracy of life-threatening in PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia whatever the way of conspiracy, he is still suffering and suffering [4]. Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University was/is non-judicially determined and sincerely determined to harm to kill to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain[23]. What is/was the philosophy of global academia and philosophia? What is happening in global academia and philosophia in the name of PhD school in academia and philosophia? Moreover, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also self-funded and self-invested around 8,00,000BDT to 10,00,000BDT for the official coordination for the official preparation process for international attending and schooling at RMIT University, Australia. What was the judicial and financial benefit of his self-investment for attending and schooling at RMIT University, Australia? What was the judicial responsibility of RMIT University and Australian government since 2021-2022[81-83]? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was still writing and writing since 2021-2022, he was self-investing dollar and dollar since 2021-2022. Hence, nobody is the judicial successor of PhD⁰⁻³ research of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain since 2014.

12.5 Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh and Retired Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, DJFT, University of Calcutta may write a book

Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh and Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta may write a book about their self-PhD-climbing and self-promotional-climbing in academia and philosophia at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India in terms of the limitations of DJFT and/or support of the University of Calcutta and/or Indian government. What is the judicial philosophy of research,

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Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

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Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva

Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020; Room: 512.01.12.25; School of

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PhD, and promotion at University of Calcutta? What was the limitations at DJFT? How can overcome the limitations in academia and philosophia? Did Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh non-judicially pay for his PhD and PhD registration? Did Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh non-judicially pay for his promotion? Did Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta non-judicially pay for his PhD and PhD registration? Did Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta non-judicially pay for his promotion? If they paid, they should judicially satisfy to the global community if there is limitations if there contradictions in academia and philosophia. Did Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh take any 'study leave' for his PhD thesis? If they had no 'study leave', Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh can still take a 'study leave' to pursue a PhD thesis to study the PhD compliance under the higher education and promotion policy of University of Calcutta, India. Every compliance PhD should have a 'study leave'[22, 23]. 'Study leave' should be the pre-requisite of quality higher education and research. Every engineering professor should have a minimum two-years duration 'professional leave' or 'industrial experience' to satisfy to continue their professional practice in engineering, academia, and philosophia. Without 'study leave', a non-compliance profile may be automatically generated in the academia and philosophia. Every compliance promotion should have a PhD 'study leave'. Every compliance promotion in engineering in academia and philosophia should have an 'industrial experience'. How can a non-engineer teach in engineering in academia in philosophia? How can a non-engineer claim a professor in engineering in academia in philosophia? These are the matter of laughing and joking in engineering, academia, and philosophia against the global surviving in higher education and research. Every compliance professor should have a PhD 'study leave'. In general; promotion, professor, and PhD without 'study leave' confuses the global community of academia and philosophia. Possibly, 'study leave' should be the judicial requirement for having promotion in academia and philosophia. This article is also the production of a 'study leave' of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain during his 'study leave' at City University, Bangladesh. If a person has no 'study leave' in his/her profession in his/her PhD, he should not be a PhD supervisor of any university of any country. Some clever academician takes 'study leave' takes government support and involve in another full-time job. Every 'study leave' should have the investment of self-funding and/or scholarship funding to satisfy the 'study leave' criterion. It should be stated that one biological brain = one professional task. Although, every person needs to do a lot of routine tasks for his routine surviving in the planet. Every process should be transparent, academic-friendly, and law-friendly. PhD and promotion should not be a matter of hidden satisfaction to the professor community. Every professor should have a judicial PhD in academia and philosophia. Every PhD achiever should be a professor in academia and philosophia. Every professor should be an engineer in the field of his/her technology. Non-PhD academician should be designated as course instructor to eliminate the confusing the designations of professor and professor (Dr.) in university in the global academia and philosophia. Professor is not a fashion in

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academia and philosophia, professorship should be a passion in academia and philosophia. If a professor can not take lab classes can not contribute in research in academia and philosophia; he/she should not be a designated professor in technology in university. This is also necessary to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to satisfy PhD study, promotion study, PhD practice, promotion practice, and professional service to global community. What should be the transparency? Everyone should know in global academia and philosophia. Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh and Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta may write a book about their self-PhD-climbing and self-promotional-climbing in academia and philosophia at DJFT if they non-judicially paid to any professor at University of Calcutta, India and/or Jadavpur University, India. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain will be liable to ask to reimburse every coin of their money in their pocket in their bank account. If Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh can not convince to global academia, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should again write to vice-chancellor, University of Calcutta, India. Similarly, every professor (Dr.) and PhD researcher may write to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain for their judicial support of professional surviving in academia and philosophia. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is doing professional research in academia since 2006. DJFT should not be a department of Professor Swapon Kumar Gosh although he may have contribution of long-term professional service and administrative coordination with registrar office and/or office of chancellery team, University of Calcutta. This is a university of global community if the university is inviting foreign students. Students, teachers, and chancellery team are the three-dimensional administration of a university. DJFT should be determined should be worried to enhance to achieve the global quality in academia and philosophia. Moreover, there is no single student of Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh in the professor list at DJFT. Why? What is the existing philosophy at DJFT? What should be the genuine philosophy? If there is problem, there is solution, there is also legal remedies for sustaining in academia and philosophia. Let's eliminate the cancer of DJFT, University of Calcutta, India.

13 Concrete warning and approach to the vice chancellor, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, university grants commission of Bangladesh, and government of Bangladesh for quality enhancement of department of textile engineering (DTE), City University.

City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh didn't provide proper laboratory training as prerequisite of the BSc engineering degree/training (2006-2010). City University officially neglected laboratory training and project training as prerequisite of the BSc engineering degree in textile engineering [58, 60, 71]. If Dr. AKM Saiful Islam didn't care the laboratory support at DTE, City University; what was the ethical grade and learning philosophy of his bachelor degree? Dr. AKM Saiful Islam should judicially convince the global academia about his laboratory training of his

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bachelor degree. Every project/thesis supervisor should have a MPhil/PhD degree and MPhil/PhD thesis in the relevant field of technology. Vice chancellor and/or chairman of City University tried to confuse to misguide with the professional dream with the professional goal of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2006-2010. What was the joint philosophy of head, dean, vice chancellor, and chairman of City University in 2006-2010? What was the joint philosophy of City University, University Grants Commission, and ministry of education of Bangladesh in 2006-2010 since 2006? These are the symptom of non-judicial philosophy in academia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-invested at City University since 2006. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain tried to self-recover by additional funding and additional training in textile industries. Hence, City University should ensure should assess should approve a 'BSc engineering compensation award' to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain invested his tuition fees, sacrificed the quality of life, sacrificed the sex life/family life, sacrificed the personal income/routine income in 2006-2010 since 2006 [2, 4, 11, 25, 26, 84]. The quality of higher education also negatively impacted to his natural growth in the profession, professional income, daily earnings, and quality of daily life in Bangladesh. City University should have a penalty of 10,000 Australian penalty unit should pay immediately to the bank account of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. It should not be the matter of high court of Bangladesh. It should not be the matter of judicial asking through the high court of Bangladesh. Head of the Department, DTE, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh (2006-2010) should have a penalty of 1,000 Australian penalty unit if he neglected to notify to inform the departmental requirements to the office of registrar, City University, Bangladesh to talk to convince to write to represent to the office of dean/vice-chancellor/chairman of the university if he only tried and intended to self-guard his daily earnings of his routine job rather than judicial duty rather than professional duty at City University. Chairman, University Grants Commission, Dhaka, Bangladesh and/or ministry of higher education, Dhaka, Bangladesh (2006-2010) should have a penalty of 10,000 Australian penalty unit if he/she neglected to notify to inform the departmental requirements to the office of registrar, City University, Bangladesh and/or high court of Bangladesh since 2006. Ministry of higher education, Dhaka, Bangladesh should have a valid investigation to overcome the situation to solve the situation of higher education. Ministry of higher education, Dhaka, Bangladesh should have a judicial action and support to pay the 'BSc engineering compensation award' immediately to the bank account of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Md. Anowar Hossain, savings account no: 0178 12200003933, First Security Islami Bank PLC, Birulia Branch, Dhaka-(routing No: 105260808). It should not be a matter of high court of Bangladesh. There was also official quality assessment of City University in 2018-2019. Foreign expert and local expert were included to enhance to signify the quality of higher education. Professor Dr. Shah Alimuzzaman Belal, Bangladesh University of Textiles, Dhaka, Bangladesh; and Professor

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IR. Dr. Mohammad Yeakub Ali, International Islamic University, Malaysia were jointly attended at the conference room of City University. Professor IR. Dr. Mohammad Yeakub Ali discussed and friendly-mentioned and shared in the conference that he self-invested or spent money for his profession and promotion in academia and philosophia. What was the assessment report of DTE about DTE at City University? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't know officially and academically at City university. If there was any wrong assessment and/or dealing assessment, the committee and/or City University should be liable should have a penalty. University grants commission and ministry of higher education, Bangladesh should take care the whole situation to enhance the quality of DTE, City University. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had no any signature in the policy of external assessment with the team of external assessment in 2018-2019. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not take any liability of their report and/or quality grading of DTE in 2018-2019. To claim a casual duty allowance, this report is also validated by the official duty of City University as a member, institutional quality assurance cell, City university, Dhaka, Bangladesh since 2019 [2, 11, 21, 25, 26].

14 RMIT University, University of Calcutta, and City University should take care the financial support, safety support, welfare support, and honorary support to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) for his self-contribution to the organization

14.1 This judicial article also identifies and reflects a joint service record of a vice-chancellor

If the vice-chancellors couldn't identify the departmental problem, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get the financial, professional safety, and honorary support from the universities. This article also identifies and reflects a joint service record of a vice-chancellor of University of Calcutta, India; a vice-chancellor of City University, Bangladesh; and a vice-chancellor of RMIT University, Australia. The professional service of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should be enough for his life-time quality surviving in the planet, but the pocket and retirement fund of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is almost empty [4, 22, 23]. Who should take care the philosophy?

14.2 Life-time contribution to Department of Jute and Fibre Technology (DJFT), University of Calcutta, India since 2013 [3, 4] [1-10] [1, 2, 11] [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [4, 10, 21] [6, 8, 10-12, 19]

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had a speech at the celebration meeting of 'Saraswati Puja' under the request of the organizing committee of 'Saraswati Puja' (2014-2015) at Post Graduate Technology Hall, University of Calcutta. DJFT alumni and/or Post Graduate Technology Hall, University of Calcutta ask/asked money to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar

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Hossain in ‘Saraswati Puja’ for the purpose of ‘Saraswati Puja’ (2015-2023). But he already invested for DJFT, University of Calcutta, but the local Indian student didn’t participate accordingly. DJFT should notify the local students to convince their understanding and contribution of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at DJFT, University of Calcutta. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is already dedicated and invested to the ‘God of Knowledge’ since 2014. Presently he is also founder of a ‘knowledge industry’ at RMIT University, Australia. He can only pay and dedicate knowledge for the contribution and global religious belief of ‘Saraswati Puja’[4, 23]. DJFT alumni and Post Graduate Technology Hall, University of Calcutta should read the whole articles to enhance the quality in higher education and research. Every national and international contributor of DJFT should get a welfare support of DJFT, University of Calcutta, India. DJFT should take care the welfare support to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain for his contribution, dedication, and self-funding to DJFT[27]. If DJFT is doing crime, the brand value of DJFT will decline, but the brand value of Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not impact should not decline, will not decline under the valid support of this judicial article. Moreover, Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain notified to DJFT and University of Calcutta from his self-funded liability rather than government funded liability in India rather than university funded liability in India.

14.3 Life-time contribution to Department of Textile Engineering (DTE), City university, Dhaka, Bangladesh since 2006[4, 24] [1, 2, 4, 24, 26, 28-61] [58, 60] [12, 14-18, 59, 61, 75, 76, 85-88] [10, 28] [11, 28-57, 70, 74]

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is thinking, writing, motivating, identifying, solving, arguing, publishing, and investing to enhance the quality of higher education at City University to increase to sustain the brand value of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh since 2006[1, 2]. He is also dedicating his full writings for academia and philosophia for global surviving [3]. So, the alumni of City University and textile engineers alumni association of City University (TEAACU) should not ask the funding of any ‘Iftar party’ to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain may assess may continue to certify ‘chartered engineer’ on behalf of TEAACU in terms of funding support of TEAACU. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain participated in two founding meetings of TEAACU at Nikunja-2 at Khilkhet, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had a speech at the first founding meeting under the request of Engr. Shaheed, first batch/second batch alumni of DTE, City University (2007-2008). The place of first meeting at Nikunja-2 was also the rented and shared residence of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain incorporated with Mr. Sani, student of Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA), City University, Dhaka (2007-2008) who was also from Tangail district, Bangladesh. Initially, the TEAACU was also proposed and named as ‘Tangail Textile Engineers Association’. The residence was the nearest the park of

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Nikunja-2. The second meeting was organized at another residence of Khilkhet at the roof of a house. Different names of association were also proposed by the members. Possibly, the founding association of textile engineers had the maximum members from the Tangail district, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Hence, a minimum portion of the earnings of City University/tuition fees of City University/student funds of City University may be transferred to the trustee board of TEAACU for the welfare of TEAACU to the successor of City University, and the trustee board of founder chairman to the successor of City University; if they self-invested and scholarly contributed for the development of DTE, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh. In general philosophy of profession, every university graduate gets the chain contribution and chain reputation in the profession in the job market in the community of their alumni. Every contributor of DTE should get a welfare support of DTE, City University. If DTE is doing crime, the brand value of DTE will decline, but the brand value of Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not impact should not decline, will not decline under the valid support of this judicial article. Moreover, Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain notified to DTE and City University from his self-funded liability rather than government funded liability in Bangladesh rather than university funded liability in Bangladesh.

14.4 Life-time contribution to School of Fashion and Textiles (SFT), RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia since 2020 [4, 22, 23] [22, 23, 80, 89-94] [1, 21, 95-108] [22, 23, 80, 89-94, 107] [11, 21, 26, 62, 63, 65, 68, 72, 73, 78, 81-83, 95-99, 109-140]

360⁰ theory of criminal attack of Australian criminal were observed and assessed by Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Australian PhD school. 360⁰ theory of criminal attack is the highest technique in academia and philosophia to confuse to kill a PhD researcher inside of RMIT university. 360⁰ theory of criminal attack should be judicially banned in academia and philosophia[23]. RMIT university should not have any practice of student association if they have no contribution for the support of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain if he is facing conspiracy of life-threatening since 2021-2022. Every national and international contributor of SFT, RMIT University should get a welfare support of SFT, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had publications and numerous guidelines to enhance the quality of higher education and research since 2021-2022. His financial contribution to SFT, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia is the global example of academia and philosophia since 2020-2021[22, 23]. By chance, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is alive now in the planet[4, 23]. Every contributor of SFT should get a welfare support of SFT, RMIT University. SFT should have a special take care the welfare support to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain for his contribution, dedication, and self-funding to SFT. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain claimed to Australian High Court to pay 8390000 Australian penalty units (230,72,50,000AUD) to the persons, Australian government, and RMIT University[23]. If

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Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia

Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh

Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD

Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech, University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh

Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva

Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

SFT is doing crime, the brand value of SFT will decline, but the brand value of Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not impact should not decline, will not decline under the valid support of this article. Moreover, Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain notified to the persons, Australian government, SFT, and RMIT University from his self-funded liability rather than government funded liability in Australia rather than university funded liability in Australia.

14.5 Investment philosophy of Md. Anowar Hossain to become Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Md. Anowar Hossain love, respect, and acknowledge every judicial training and counselling of PhD supervisors, and relevant teachers since 2006 to become Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) from Md. Anowar Hossain. But Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain continuously invested and invested since child schooling to still now[1, 4]. When Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was walking in the morning beside the agricultural fields beside the paddy fields beside the vegetable fields. The farmers and farm owners were planting and planting. After few months, farmers were singing and harvesting their crops. Nobody ceased their crops and jobs. They had no special guards; they had no safety of the special force. But Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain faced robbers who tried to cease the valid income of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's knowledge industry. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't get any judicial support of natural growth and the support of natural surviving in academia and philosophia [22, 23, 78]. Maximum supervisors in the total profession of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain tried to decline the professional income of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain [4]. Almost every academia, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain faced the symptom of sex black-mail rather than any judicial support of sex. Possibly, everyone had no super quality to supervise to guide to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. By chance, by organization; they supervised to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was looking and enjoying that a boy was forcing a football into the water in a river. Possibly, the angle of force was multidimensional was around 360° to sink the football into the water. Immediately, the football was floating and floating on the water surface of the river at the nearest distance of the boy. It was the game of the boy in the river, but the boy was not afraid in the river. Similarly, few birds were bathing or playing on the water surface when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was enjoying a morning beauty in a summer morning. But the birds got afraid by looking to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Although, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had no intention to harm to disturb the birds. But the birds again continued bathing and bathing when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't create any symptom of making afraid to the birds. A bird was forcing to sink into water to another bird, but the bird was floating and floating on the water surface at the nearest distance. Similarly, some 'God father' and

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

‘second God’ tries and plays to force with the merit to sink like football and bird. God father plays the game in academia and philosophia. Some God father may display manpower. But nobody can catch the real philosophy of the ‘God father’ and ‘second God’ at the right time at the right moment. Who invited, supported, and established God father and second God in academia and philosophia? There is scope of continuous research and development in academia and philosophia. There is ready office, there is also ready basket, there is also ready manpower; but there is ready lacking of proper planning and execution. There is also existing side-effect of PhD practice in PhD industry in global academia and philosophia. Every ‘God father’ and ‘second God’ should be eliminated. Government and/or relevant authorities should take care the policy, possibly everyone serve for the personal benefit rather than professional beauty and responsibility. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain attended and funded at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh to become a professional engineer since 2006. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain attended and funded at University of Calcutta, India to overcome the lacking of training at City University. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain attended and funded at RMIT University, Australia to overcome the lacking of training at University of Calcutta in academia and philosophia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain attended and funded at different textile industries and training centres in Bangladesh and India to overcome the academic lacking of training at University of Calcutta and City University since 2006. Who should take care the judicial compensation to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain? Who should asses the academic limitation? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a judicial rights to ask higher compensation and salary to ask general surviving support rather than routine compensation and routine salary to the authorities to the government of Bangladesh [83] to the government of India to the government of Australia[81, 82] to the United Nations[136] to the global academia and philosophia.

14.6 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is proposing and searching the fund in terms of following roles of senior professor/chief professor/chief scientist in technical textiles, camouflage technology, and color technology

- Chief Professor (reader/writer/general study/PhD study/Postdoc study in camouflage, color, and textile technology) [22, 23]
- Chief Professor (research)
- Chief Professor (peer review and promotion of scientist/professor)
- Chief Professor (magistracy in higher education and research)
- Chief Professor (BSc thesis/MSc thesis/BTech thesis/MTech thesis/MPhil thesis/PhD thesis/Postdoc thesis/ job promotion thesis in textile technology)

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

Author’s biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in technology and law

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*

Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*

Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia

A prestigious research practitioner (RP) in technology, academic, and law since 2006

International Professor and consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, Higher Education, PhD, & Postdoc) BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime, human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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- Chief Professor and Founder, department of technical textiles
- Chief Professor and Founder, department of color and camouflage technology
- Chief Professor/Chief Scientist and Founder; textiles, color, and material research centre
- Chancellor/Chief Vice-chancellor/Vice-chancellor; research and innovation

14.7 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is proposing and searching the fund in terms of following roles of senior professor/chief professor in law and criminology

- Chief Professor (reader/reader/general study/PhD study/Postdoc study in law and criminology) [22, 23]
- Chief Professor (research)
- Chief Professor (peer review and promotion of professor)
- Chief Professor/Vice-chancellor/Chancellor (magistracy in higher education and research)
- Chief Professor (academic law and professional law)
- Chief Professor (Bachelor thesis/Master thesis/MPhil thesis/PhD thesis/Postdoc thesis/job promotion thesis in law and criminology)
- Chief Professor/Chief Scientist and Founder; defence and law research centre
- Chancellor/Chief Vice-chancellor/Vice-chancellor; research and innovation

14.8 Searching chief professor/senior professor category salary of international standard, office, and quality research fund to national and international universities

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is offering BSc Engineering degree by thesis in textile technology, Master of Technology by thesis in textile technology, Master of Science by thesis in textile technology, MPhil degree by thesis in textile technology, PhD degree by thesis in textile technology, Postdoc degree by thesis in textile technology [78, 79]. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also offering Bachelor degree by thesis in law, Master degree by thesis in law, MPhil degree by thesis in law, PhD degree by thesis in law, Postdoc degree by thesis in law [77, 78]. Accordingly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is approaching and asking quality funding and quality platform at national and international universities. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain will take 70% of the total tuition fees and university will take 30% of the total tuition fees. A subsidiary fund of university or scholarship, a government subsidiary fund or scholarship may be implemented to cover the costs of research fund, research student, research referee, and research professor [11, 22, 65, 67, 141].

14.9 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain¹⁻⁷, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is the founder of research centre and contributor of research service in different national and international organizations

14.9.1 Chief Researcher and Founder⁷

Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁶; Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia

14.9.2 Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)⁶

Defence & Law Research Centre; Fund Claimed to Australian Government; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia

14.9.3 Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)⁵

Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁵; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh

14.9.4 Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)⁴

Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Research product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh

14.9.5 Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)³

Textile, Color & Material Research Centre³; Fund Approved by City University; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh

14.9.6 Textile, Color & Material Research Centre²

Textile, Color & Material Research Centre²; Bangladesh Textile and Fashion, House#12, Road#15, Nikunja-2, Khilkhet, Dhaka-1229, Bangladesh

14.9.7 Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)¹

Textile, Color & Material Research Centre¹; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, 40, Kemal Ataturk Avenue, Banani, Dhaka 1213, Bangladesh

Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

15 Exemption of referee recommendation in global academia and philosophia

Referee recommendation should be exempted for any nomination of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in nationally and internationally if he is facing judicial crisis of referee and/or referee funding in academia and philosophia [67].

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Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in technology and law

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International Professor and consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, Higher Education, PhD, & Postdoc) BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime, human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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16 Production process of PhD certificate in university in academia and philosophia

A quality PhD researcher has a bright scope to be a vice chancellor of the university. Every PhD supervisor should extend, manage, and acknowledge the professional duty accordingly. Although the PhD supervisor may not be a vice chancellor of the university may not think to be a vice-chancellor may not dream to be a vice-chancellor or chancellor. Every prestigious PhD university should teach the standard process of production of PhD certificate to minimize the cheating of any PhD supervisor. Production process of a PhD certificate should be a part of teaching and learning should be a part of valid credit hours of PhD university. RMIT University, Australia didn't teach the production process of a PhD certificate. Therefore, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is asking an additional support/award to learn the production process of PhD certificate from any prestigious university who are doing double practice of research and academia. On 14 January 2026, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain checked the website of University of Dhaka, Bangladesh[124] and University of Calcutta, India[73]. Both universities had the online record of honorary doctorate degree. Possibly, every university prioritize to register honorary doctorate rather than thesis doctorate rather than research doctorate. Possibly, the number of PhD doctorates are higher than the number of honorary doctorates. It seems that the value of honorary doctorate is higher than the PhD/DPhil degree. Who should get more priority and more credit? There is huge scope of research and development in university in academia and philosophia. Moreover, the web-site of the university/universities has no specific lists of the PhD doctorate/academic doctorate due to having the higher numbers and/or routine certification and/or routine training of the PhD degree. Although PhD doctorate may also be additionally listed as honorary doctorate for their tremendous contribution, professional performance, and personal excellency. Although PhD doctorate may also be automatically reviewed for the capacity and capability of honorary doctorate in terms of scholarly rather than money or sex or other benefit. Although, PhD supervisor may not have an honorary doctorate. Although, PhD supervisor may not think about the honorary doctorate. So, there is no judicial crime of a PhD researcher? In practical philosophia, it seems that the value and contribution of honorary doctorate is higher than the thesis doctorate/research doctorate. Every thesis doctorate should also have a copy of list in the department and/or the university website. Possibly, PhD supervisor may also use a scanned signature of vice chancellor to certify a PhD degree to confuse the PhD student to misguide the PhD student in academia and philosophia. Whatever, the situation can not be imagined by the PhD student. This is a global headache in PhD industries. Possibly, PhD researcher also gets an experience certificate of his PhD supervisor rather than PhD certificate. Moreover, every department/university may have a senior professor who control the genuine certificate and/or duplicate certificate of a PhD of a department/school. Moreover, a university or department may not have single senior professor although the university advertises for PhD enrolment, PhD degree, PhD interview, and PhD education. What is the judicial drama

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

in PhD industries? These are the global challenge in academia and philosophia. So, what is the rank value of the office of vice-chancellor for a degree registration and certification policy. A vice-chancellor should perform his/her magistracy in his/her university. If a vice-chancellor is taking any commission, he is not a vice chancellor, he is harming to the total academia and philosophia. Every compliance vice-chancellor should have a higher salary than a non-compliance vice-chancellor in academia and philosophia than a political vice-chancellor in university. An office of vice-chancellor should not be the office of display; he should officially and physically visit the departments, laboratories, institutes, and relevant PhD schools. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't physically see the magistracy of vice-chancellor at University of Calcutta, India (2013-2015); and RMIT University, Australia (2020-2021). Sometimes, professor teach and supervise PhD, but he/she can not understand the policy of PhD certification and PhD attestation. Sometimes, professor teach and supervise PhD, but he/she can not understand can not catch the peak point and peak time of a PhD contribution and PhD certification. There are far deviations among PhD expertise and laboratory expertise and theory expertise. Sometimes, a laboratory technician/class trainer serves 40-50 years in a PhD laboratory, but he/she can not understand can not think the PhD can not dream the PhD. Although, a laboratory technician serves very close with the PhD students and PhD supervisors. The crime of PhD degree, transparency of a PhD degree, purpose of a PhD degree, and the philosophy of a PhD degree are the global challenge in PhD industry. PhD supervisor may exchange the PhD contribution of his/her students in terms of additional benefit and/or financial exchange and/or scholarly exchange. Every PhD supervisor and PhD candidate should get an official training for the production process of PhD certificate. Every university certificate should have an original signature rather than scanned signature rather than non-authorized signature. Every signature should have a valid authorization. A signature signifies the assessment. Every university and every PhD may have a separate funding to vice-chancellor, PhD supervisor, and PhD researcher to generate to continue the process of PhD certificate or honorary certificate. Without which scholarly registration and scholarly practice may be demotivated. Moreover, PhD certification and honorary certification process may also have the financial involvement versus scholarly excellency under the process of transparency and/or non-transparency in academia and philosophia [22, 23]. If PhD supervisor has a valid PhD certificate and a valid PhD thesis, he/she will ensure PhD certificate for his/her PhD student. Moreover, a PhD student is not a life-time student for his/her 'PhD certificate and PhD thesis'. Moreover, a PhD student is completely independent to climb in his profession in academia and philosophia. Moreover, a PhD student should be purely independent to climb in his profession in academia and philosophia. Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, DJFT, University of Calcutta and Professor Dr. Lijing Wang, SFT, RMIT University should notify should clarify should write the flow chart of production of PhD certificate to claim their professional validity to claim the PhD supervision validity of PhD¹ and

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PhD² of author. Without which, their judicial credit of PhD^{1,2} supervision should be contaminated at University of Calcutta, India and RMIT University, Australia.

16.1 What should mention in doctoral degree?

In global platform of academia, DPhil/DTech/PhD is practicing in a common meaning, although a degree should/may clearly mention the field of doctoral contribution in one sentence. Every certificate of DPhil/DTech/PhD should have a full name, identity, and a valid registration number of the PhD researcher and PhD achiever.

16.2 Certificate specimen of PhD¹

- Doctor of Philosophy
- In color and textile technology
- Signature of vice-chancellor
- Signature of supervisors and/or research witness
- Signature of PhD achiever

16.3 Certificate specimen of PhD²

- Doctor of Philosophy
- In color, camouflage, and textile technology
- Signature of vice chancellor
- Signature of supervisors and/or research witness
- Signature of PhD achiever

16.4 Certificate specimen of PhD³

- Doctor of Philosophy
- In law and criminology
- Signature of vice-chancellor
- Signature of supervisors and/or research witness
- Signature of PhD achiever

16.5 Certificate specimen of twin PhD²

- Doctor of Philosophy
- In color, camouflage, textile technology, and law
- Signature of vice-chancellor
- Signature of supervisors and/or research witness
- Signature of PhD achiever

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD
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16.6 Relation between 'PhD thesis and PhD certificate' to satisfy a PhD degree of any university

Figure 3. Both 'PhD thesis and PhD certificate' are required for a PhD degree to claim a degree, so people are saying PhD degree, so people are connected with a research university, so people are connected with a research supervisor, so people are going to university than research centre.

Figure 3, in special circumstances of a PhD situation, a PhD achiever may also sign a self-PhD certificate as he/she is the main successor as he/she is the sole owner as he/she is the single entrepreneur of his/her contribution in academia and philosophia[2, 4, 25]. A PhD achiever may also make a self-PhD certificate as he is the sole owner and sole successor of his/her research contribution under the witness of a valid PhD supervisor of any university of any country. Hence, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has full judicial witness and evidences of his achievement since 2006[4]. Moreover, a PhD certificate is not a general certificate like theory training and routine examination. PhD thesis without a certificate is a PhD experience. PhD certificate without thesis is a symptom of crime and/or non-transparency in academia and philosophia. If a person has a sole-author category PhD experience and/or PhD publication, what is the wrong to certify to register a PhD degree on behalf of any university in global academia and global philosophia? A PhD certificate, PhD thesis, and relevant achievement are the professional licenses of a PhD supervisor of a professional PhD supervisor. A tea-stall company also maintain also hang a one page 'business license' to satisfy to respect to transparent the administration of the country. Supervisor and PhD researcher may jointly fall into danger and cancer. Let's eliminate the cancer in the PhD industry. Every surrender minimizes the administrative cost of the government. So, surrender is also a symptom of reduction in judicial punishment.

16.7 Practice and limitation of PhD certification from the residence of a PhD supervisor

PhD is a one-dimensional teaching and learning. So, one-to-one teaching and learning in any place is also possible is also acceptable. A philosopher may certify another philosopher. A scientist may certify another scientist. Still, a PhD philosopher may write the PhD after the name for his self-motivation of self-practice in academia and philosophia. Although, there is deviation

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between the practice of traditional philosopher and PhD philosopher in academia and philosophia. If there is lack of PhD certification of PhD industry/PhD university; the policy of university, the policy of registry may decline may hamper. PhD supervisors may certify his/her PhD student from his/her residence from his/her personal office from his/her family office. But there is limitation of permanent registry in the personal office and/or family office of a PhD supervisor when a PhD supervisor may be retired or expired. But there is also limitation of witness in academia and philosophia to satisfy the PhD thesis and PhD training. Hence, a PhD supervisor and/or PhD researcher may also registry the PhD in any university in terms of judicial evidences. Table 4, let's protect PhD industry, let's survive in the academia in the PhD industry.

Table 4. Pending the process of PhD certification at University of Calcutta, India and RMIT University, Australia; moreover, DJFT, University of Calcutta and/or IIT, Kanpur may declare and additionally announce the rank of associate professor; and RMIT University may declare and additionally announce the rank of senior professor/chief professor

Name of PhD supervisor	Type of judicial authority	Year of PhD accomplish ment as per supervisor's comment	PhD ^{1,2} funding	Type of PhD certification	Type of achievement of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain	Symptom of academic crime of PhD ^{1,2} supervisors
Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, Senior Supervisor of PhD ¹	University of Calcutta, India	2019 [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [6, 8, 10].	Self-funded for first PhD ¹	Pending since 2019 [1-10] [1, 2, 11] [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [4, 10, 21] [6, 8, 10-12, 19]	Sole author	Penalty of 1,00,000 Australian penalty unit
Professor Dr. Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor of PhD ²	RMIT University, Australia	2021 [22] [23]	Scholarship funded for second PhD ² ; self-funded for second PhD ²	Pending since 2021 [22, 23]	Sole author	Penalty of 1,00,000 Australian penalty unit

17 Comparison between PhD¹ and PhD² to face a critical situation to overcome a parallel situation at University of Calcutta, India; and RMIT University, Australia

Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, MTech coordinator, DJFT, University of Calcutta told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in front of Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh in 2013, “he (Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh) did everything for your MTech admission”. One day, Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2015,

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“you will understand later” It was the philosophical sentence of Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh. The sentence of the voice was non-judicially remarking and forwarding the academic and professional air of future, but the voice was indirect and a silent philosophy to the symbol of future. Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, senior supervisor of PhD¹ also verbally forwarded to Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh who was not a PhD¹ supervisor of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at University of Calcutta, India in 2015-2017. Similarly, Professor Dr. Lijing Wang, senior supervisor of PhD² verbally forwarded to Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye who was not a PhD² supervisor of Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain at RMIT University, Australia (2020-2021). Both senior professors may have the judicial and official explanation about their oral forwarding which are indirectly showing the symptom of academic crime and/or academic confusing to the brain of a valid PhD^{1,2} researcher. Every voice of a professor should be judicial, official, bullet, and transparent for the peace of the PhD student. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain judicially argued and recommended death penalty of Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye, RMIT University to the government of Australia, government of Bangladesh, United Nations, global community of judicial authority, and global community of academia and philosophia[4, 21, 23]. Possibly, the psycho-physics between Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh and Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were found similarity against the peace of PhD student and PhD school against the judicial practice in PhD school in academia and philosophia against the goal of the central government of a country. Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh, DJFT, University of Calcutta, India also kept and recorded/registered the photocopy of the nomination letter of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain of BCMC college of engineering and technology, Bangladesh in 2015. Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh, DJFT, University of Calcutta, India maintained a special filing for Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India. The psycho-physics of Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh is like the elder brother of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain recommended death penalty to his elder brother, Mr. Md. Sanowar Hossain [93]. Although the office peon or office assistant of Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh knew/told about the elder brother about the family matter about the MTech funding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain[21]. The psycho-physics of Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman, Assistant Professor, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh is like the elder brother of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman who also had/have hidden connection with the family of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain[21]. Possibly, Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman prioritize to Mr. Mahmudur Rahman Idris for his surviving at City University, a male assistant professor of chemistry at City University. The psycho-physics of Mr. Mahmudur Rahman Idris, City University, Dhaka was not professional in academia who also advanced and commented about the personal matters of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Mr. Mahmudur Rahman Idris also had a lot of side-discussion about sex/family/official matters of Professor Dr. Engr. Md.

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processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime,

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Anowar Hossain beside Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in front of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Where was the source of his information at City University? Mr. Mahmudur Rahman Idris may help to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain by writing his judicial, academic, and professional explanation at City University[23]. Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye, RMIT University, Australia also had a lot of side-discussion about sex/family/official matters of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain beside Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in front of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, Assistant Professor, City University also had side-discussion about family/official matters of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Possibly, Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, Assistant Professor, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh also had a good connection with the family people and/or professional people and/or surrounding people of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. It seems that Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain faced a parallel conspiracy in his profession and family against the general/professional surviving philosophy. A four-dimensional connection, a 360° connection of criminal (360°) with RMIT University, Australia-University of Calcutta, India-City University, Bangladesh-family of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in the parallel way and hidden way of communication under the hidden connection of academia and philosophia[21]. Possibly, there was also four-dimensional connection was also 360° connection was hidden connection of Australian criminal with Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2020-2021[4, 21]. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also faced a critical conspiracy of life-threatening in Australian PhD school in 2021 whatever also parallelly extended to Bangladesh whatever also parallelly extended to family [4, 21-23, 92-94]. The four-dimensional connection of criminal with Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain artificially creates the sustaining disorder, earning disorder, safety disorder to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain which are also the parallel reasons of financial disorder of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain which are also the parallel philosophy of ceasing the sex/family life of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Possibly, criminal also connected with Mrs. Sakera Begam, mother of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. City University, Dhaka; and RMIT university, Australia verbally and individually recommended to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to pay to mother of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain[21]. Possibly, criminal also connected with Mrs. Rashida Begam, sister of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Possibly, criminal also connected with Mrs. Sharifa Akter, wife of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Australia and Bangladesh[92-94]. These are the symptom of bullet conspiracy, bullet target, 360° theory of target, and hidden target of Australian professor since 2020-2021. 360° theory of target is a critical target of criminal and/or chain criminal. No female should be hidden connected should be telephoned connected with different people for the self-protection for the husband protection for the protection of self-family for the surviving philosophy in the planet. Sometimes, professional criminals are so much advance than

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the general thinking, simple belief, and general discussion of the women. The functions of criminals are so much professional, official, and anonymous. The target of Australian criminal was/is multidimensional was/is around 360°. The continuous techniques of target were/are very critical, and anonymous. Possibly, criminals also target different people in the symmetrical techniques of criminology. Criminal may try to hide the crimes in different ways of repeated crimes and repeated techniques. The international criminals may create the judicial problem may artificially create the reasons of death penalty may create the peoples of death penalty may create the reasons of harassment in personal and professional life, by which way the criminals may black-mail the people for forcing to do hidden crime under the illegal support of any 'God father'. Hence, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also asked a safety support of Bangladesh government and Australian government since 2021-2022[81, 83]. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was writing and writing, he was asking and asking, he was reporting and reporting to the governments to the global academia and philosophia to the universities to the PhD industries and PhD industries. What was/is the reason of financial disorder of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain? Possibly, maximum department of global academia and philosophia has 'God father' or 'second God'. Sometimes, a duplicate PhD also gets a beautiful chair and long-term salary under the non-judicial payment policy under the non-judicial benefit policy under the non-judicial guidance and non-judicial support of non-judicial senior officials and/or non-judicial colleagues. Some professional peoples may fail in judicial and scholarly surviving, but they try to win in the alternative way of non-judicial surviving. But the government can not easily catch them for their beautiful chair for their beautiful office room for their illegal chain with the top administration and surrounding colleagues. So, what is the real situation in global academia and philosophia when a professor never dream to be a 'God father' or 'second God' for surviving in the planet for food managing for his/her stomach? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not face any 'God father' or 'second God' to survive in the profession in academia and philosophia. Who should take care the academia and philosophia? Nobody should face 'God father' and 'second God' for climbing in academia and philosophia for surviving in academia and philosophia for sustaining in global academia and philosophia in profession. A scholar should not face any 'God father' to be a vice-chancellor or chancellor of any university of any country. Possibly maximum 'God father' and 'second God' are doing non-judicial service rather than scholarly service in academia and philosophia rather than the government goal rather than the genuine surviving goal in academia and philosophia. Possibly, 'God father' and 'second God' can not scholarly contribute rather than scholarly harass for global surviving philosophy.

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18 Peer review of PhD² and professional connection of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain with DJFT, University of Calcutta, India during the achievement of PhD² thesis [4, 23]

One day, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had a telephonic communication with Professor Dr. Sadhan Chandra Roy, Retired Professor, University of Calcutta in 2021. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain critically and biologically recorded, and analyzed the discussion of Professor Dr. Sadhan Chandra Roy in 2021. Professor Dr. Sadhan Chandra Roy told during the situation of COVID-9, “you may give some mask in your local area.” Somehow, Professor Dr. Sadhan Chandra Roy also got/know the information about a PhD² manuscript of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain[142]. Professor Dr. Sadhan Chandra Roy also simply commented about the manuscript. But Professor Dr. Sadhan Chandra Roy was not a subject expert of PhD² manuscript. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain submitted his PhD² milestone report to the RMIT University, Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't mention the name of Professor Dr. Sadhan Chandra Roy in any peer review of journals. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain mentioned the name of Professor Dr. Debasis Das and Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta as subject expert in chemical processing for the anonymous peer review of the journal. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain send one manuscript of PhD² directly to Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, PhD¹ supervisor for his peer review support for his support of subject expertise when he told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2021 in a telephonic conversation, “if I harm you”. Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, PhD¹ supervisor also told, “you may put my name in your publications”. These are the publications of PhD² at RMIT University and Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta had zero involvement and connection with Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta. Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta should not harm to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain if Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta is a PhD¹ supervisor. But Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta should not ask any authorship of PhD² manuscript of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not misguide to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in academia and philosophia if Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta was/is a designated professor of University of Calcutta[22, 23]. What was/is the authorship and promotion compliance at University of Calcutta? Although a manuscript of PhD² was published as a book chapter rather than journal article, peer reviewed/edited by Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, sole authored by Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain [142]. Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, PhD¹ supervisor also told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2021, “Guddi is writing your e-mail.” What was the purpose of saying Guddi? What was the meaning of “Guddi is writing your e-mail?” The English meaning of ‘Guddi’ is ‘kite’ if the ‘Guddi’ is a Bengali word in Kolkata. Possibly, this is also the symptom of judicial crime of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, PhD¹ supervisor to confuse to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain [21]. Moreover, Australian criminal at RMIT

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

university recorded and critically analyzed the telephonic and e-mail conversation of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to harm to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to PhD² of author[4, 22, 23].

19 PhD drama in engineering in PhD industries

What should be the purpose of research testing. The testing which logically, visually, and technically clarifies and signifies the specific research questions, specific experimental findings, specific judicial support to claim any technology to claim any theory, and advancement in research and development. There is far difference between general experimentation and research experimentation. FTIR (Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy), SEM (scanning electron microscopy), and analytical machines are the beauty of a research laboratory to claim to display a research laboratory. The training of analytical machines should be mandatory in MTech/MSc training. It is true that the invention of FTIR, SEM, and analytical machines are not the purpose of MPhil/PhD/Postdoc degree. These are the purpose to satisfy specific testing if necessary. Moreover, every machine has also limitation has also limited parameters in specific conditions. Analytical and experimental drama in PhD thesis should be eliminated rather than PhD research questions in PhD. Is it possible to make a scientific thesis without FTIR and SEM? Yes, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain tried to make a thesis without highlighting the unnecessary analytical drama in his first PhD¹ thesis? If any research satisfies the goal of any specific research question in terms of experimentation and/or research theory and/or research discussion, the research may be claimed for a research contribution for a research degree, the thesis may be recorded may be registered at any research university to continue to invest to support to improve to display for further research for research funding for quality surviving in the planet.

20 Limitations in PhD industry and academia

Possibly, a total university and/or a total department have no original PhD but the university and/or department is also enrolling PhD student, broadly advertising, internationally advertising, and broadly interviewing the PhD admission/PhD course. What is the global situation in academia and philosophy in PhD industry? Who should take care the PhD industry? Moreover, some university may assess the professor in terms their performance of secondary school, higher secondary school; and non-judicial phenomena rather than higher education and research schooling, research performance, and professional excellency. There are also the limitation, condition, and situation to appoint permanent faculty in public universities to continue the crime inside the department inside the university inside the chain community.

21 Recommendation of a central auditorium of a country/international for PhD supervisors for the PhD experts

A central auditorium and office places may be founded and funded for the support of valid PhD supervisors and/or retired category PhD supervisors if they are life-long healthy to supervise to serve in their field of research and development. A general auditorium or a common auditorium of a country may be established for PhD supervisors for their life-time practice in research and development. Possibly, there is existing attitude of childness for the life-time communication support of PhD researchers with a PhD supervisor with a retired professor. Therefore, every central government should have a list of general PhD supervisors and PhD expert for global surviving. Therefore, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also searching to enroll as a PhD supervisor and PhD expert in the global platform of academia and PhD research for maintaining a professional office and a contact centre[121]. Possibly, there is no central auditorium in Bangladesh, India, and Australia for the support of retired PhD supervisor and/or non-retired PhD supervisor. So, who is take caring the support of PhD supervisors? How can a PhD student search valid PhD supervisor of a university of a government?

22 Facts and contradictions in PhD industries and universities

22.1 Who should get experience certificate of PhD and who should be a PhD supervisor?

If a supervisor remarks a poor contribution in his/her PhD research, he/she may issue an experience certificate from his/her self-office from his/her secretarial office of registrar without scanning without having the signature of the vice chancellor. Some supervisor may also cleverly manage a PhD certificate during interim vice-chancellor or associate vice-chancellor or dean or associate dean, this is also the symptom of scholarly cheating, scholarly confusing, and judicial crime in academia and philosophia. An interim vice-chancellor or associate vice-chancellor or associate dean or secretary of the university can not sign or issue a PhD certificate of any university. Some supervisors/directors have so much non-judicial talency rather than administrative talency, scholarly talency, and transparency in research and philosophia. Some supervisors may try to create the situation of confusing rather than right guidance in academia and philosophia. Although, the thesis and/or experience should be registered at the secretary office and/or registrar office of a PhD supervisor, relevant department, and central archive of the university. Possibly, non-scholarly PhD researcher respect to PhD supervisor as 'second God'. Practically, nobody is 'second God' in academia and philosophia. A PhD supervisor is a PhD colleague who should be scholarly senior than PhD researcher who should be a valid professor (Dr.). Sometimes, PhD researcher may fall into danger and cancer. Sometimes, PhD and post-doctorate researchers may pay monthly to their supervisors for their surviving in research profession, academia, and philosophia. Hence, PhD researcher may non-judicially and non-scholarly respect their PhD supervisors in their life-time profession in academia and/or other

profession. Hence, PhD supervisor may non-judicially and non-scholarly support their PhD student in their life-time profession in academia and/or other profession. These are also the harming situation in research and academia. Comparatively, lady PhD researcher may get more experience certificate/certificate from PhD supervisor. Still, the PhD researcher may write PhD after his/her name to survive in the PhD community. Still the PhD researcher may practice research may survive in the profession. But, the signature scanning for a duplicate purpose is an academic offence in the office of a PhD supervisor. Moreover, there is also human limitation in the assessment policy. Sometimes, a PhD professor has no genuine PhD certificate, how can he think/issue/assess/communicate/manage/direct/enroll/appoint for a genuine PhD certificate of his/her student? A chain violation and mis-understanding may happen in the PhD industry in the academia and philosophia. Therefore, every PhD supervisor should have a genuine PhD certificate should have a genuine signature of vice chancellor in his/her PhD certificate. Every genuine PhD certificate holder and genuine registered PhD thesis holder may be highlighted in the website of university like honoraray doctorate achiever and/or valid successor of the university. Without which, there is possibility of cheating in PhD industry, academia, and philosophia. A valid professor (Dr.) category person should take an intake enrolment of the PhD students. It should be the international standard of academia and philosophia. No ‘God father’ or ‘second God’ should supervise any PhD. No ‘God father’ should be connected with any PhD student. Possibly, the number of duplicate professors and duplicate promotions are also numerous in academia and philosophia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw at RMIT university, Australia[21] and University of Manchester, UK in the website that a lecturer category person is supervising/hunting the PhD students. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain don’t know about the originality and genuinely of their doctorate degree for a valid PhD supervisionship, but he believes their contribution, achievement, valid capability, and advancement to supervise a PhD category student. There is also possibility of scholarly cheating is also possibility of intention in terms of achieving scholarly authorship from his/her PhD student. Moreover, they may have PhD experience and/or research experience and/or PhD certificate from any recognized university from any branded university from any branded basket from any branded PhD supervisor. If a PhD supervisor has an experience certificate than the original documented PhD certificate than the original registered PhD certificate, he will never allow/recommend PhD certificate, he will never allow and recommend an original PhD certificate for his/her student, he will never manage and guide for an original PhD certificate for his/her student. Moreover, PhD supervisor may self-try to achieve for his/her original PhD certificate. This is the situation of global challenge in the PhD industries in the branded universities and non-branded universities. Therefore, every PhD industry should have a transparent PhD record policy to motivate the global PhD scholars to motivate the researchers to motivate the scientists to protect the scientist community to protect the PhD industry to protect

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Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTEch in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in technology and law

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*

Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*

Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia

A prestigious research practitioner (RP) in technology, academic, and law since 2006

International Professor and consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, Higher Education, PhD, & Postdoc)

BSc, MSc, BTEch, MTech, BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime, human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia

Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh

Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD

Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh

Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India

Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva

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the judicial policy of research university. In the PhD² of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at RMIT University, Australia there was around 20-35 academic professionals and/or academic witness of Dr. Anowar's PhD² thesis in the list of online portal in the thesis portal/milestone submission process, still the school administration was successfully managed and continued the PhD crimes. How is it possible? Who are they? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain have no professional record of their professional identity. So, where was the supervisor support to PhD² scholar? So, where was the university support to PhD² scholar? So, where was the government support to PhD² scholar? So, where was the global support to PhD² scholar? But, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain successfully identified and invented the 'PhD disease and PhD cancer' in academia and philosophia whatever he is writing and distributing to global academia and philosophia since 2021-2022 [22, 23]. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-investing dollar and dollar since 2021-2022. In PhD¹⁻³ profession of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, he had four PhD¹⁻³ supervisors at different universities to establish three different PhD and/or research questions and/or achievements.

1. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; PhD supervisor of third PhD³ [4].
2. Professor Dr. Robert Shanks, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; PhD supervisor of second PhD² and twin PhD²
3. Professor Dr. Lijing Wang, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; PhD supervisor of second PhD² and twin PhD²
4. Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, Former Head & Retired Professor, Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, Kolkata, India; PhD supervisor of first PhD¹
5. Professor Dr. Nurul Abser, Former Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; PhD supervisor of a new PhD of first PhD¹

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain don't/didn't know if they have the PhD thesis and original PhD certificate and/or they have the PhD experience certificate from their PhD supervisors. Although, Professor Dr. Robert Shanks showed his PhD thesis to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain for one to two minutes. But he hurried and quickly kept his PhD thesis in his hand bag. It was the PhD thesis of around 50-70 pages. But, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain believes their 'PhD thesis and PhD certificate'. If a PhD supervisor have no 'PhD thesis and PhD certificate' from any university, they can not self-claim their PhD supervisorship. There is judicial restriction in academia and philosophia. Although, Professor Dr.

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Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain did sole author PhD thesis, attached the first PhD¹ thesis [1-10] [1, 2, 11] [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [4, 10, 21] [6, 8, 10-12, 19], second PhD² thesis [22, 23] and notified to the public to the expert panel since 2016-2018. A valid PhD supervisor and a certified PhD achiever are the judicial requirement for the recommendation of a PhD certificate of any university. Every PhD authority should take the necessary action for the global surviving in PhD industry. All PhD supervisors of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should legally and independently understand that Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain need not any non-judicial support need not any non-judicial support in his profession in his research profession in his PhD profession if he can independently generate idea and perform the tasks as ‘independent researcher’ as academic practitioner since 2006[4]. Possibly, there are also non-judicial persons and profiles who are also climbing and sustaining in academia and philosophia. Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta need not the PhD¹ certificate of his PhD¹ student although he is retired now. Similarly, Professor Dr. Lijing Wang need not the PhD² certificate of his PhD² student. Without having the ‘PhD certificate and PhD thesis’ of his/her PhD student, a PhD supervisor can not/should not judicially claim his/her PhD supervision and PhD experience in their university in their self-profession although the PhD manuscripts are published. What was the purpose of their PhD^{1,2} supervisionship in academia and philosophia if they tried to claim their PhD supervisionship in their profession in their university? The PhD is not only one-dimensional drama of a self-funded/scholarship-funded PhD researcher. The PhD is also a three-dimensional drama of PhD researcher, PhD supervisor, and PhD administration in university. The PhD^{1,2} situation clearly demonstrates the symptom of judicial crime of PhD^{1,2} supervisors in PhD^{1,2} industry in academia and philosophia.

22.2 What is the key purpose of a PhD supervisor in a PhD industry?

A PhD supervisor is a scholarly evidence and/or scholarly witness and/or scholarly registrar of a thesis on behalf of any university/department/vice-chancellor. A PhD supervisor is a senior academician who has a pure experience of achieving ‘PhD thesis and PhD certificate’ in university who can share and transfer his experience to make to develop to design an expert academician and/or expert researcher in his/her field of technology or subject.

22.3 What should be the basic requirement to issue a PhD certificate?

- Depth expertise and broad knowledge of a PhD researcher in the relevant field of technology[4].
- The concrete capability of PhD understanding, peer review, research supervision, research compliance, and PhD knowledge[4].
- The concrete capability of pure understanding about academic and PhD law[4].

22.4 What is the duty of a PhD supervisor

- ✓ Who should get the credit of the research work?

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

Author’s biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

- ✓ When should get the PhD degree?
- ✓ When should recommend the PhD degree?
- ✓ When should tell something?
- ✓ When should not tell something?

A PhD supervisor approach the right time and right progress of his/her PhD. A medical doctor should decide the right time of a pregnancy operation of a patient. Without which the patient may die. If the PhD student die/expire/retire, the PhD supervisor will not get the credit of the PhD thesis for a sole authored PhD. A PhD committee or PhD administration may also immediately announce and record of a PhD degree to a PhD achiever after his/her death when nobody is the successor of PhD knowledge of a PhD degree of a PhD achiever. What should be the judicial duty of a PhD committee or PhD administration? A judicial penalty was argued and recommended to the whole PhD administration of RMIT University in 2020-2022. What should be purpose of a PhD committee or PhD university? Without which, PhD supervisor may try to appoint a ready expert/ready PhD student in the field, the PhD supervisor will have a chance to make a relevant thesis if PhD supervisor and PhD student has relevant expertise if PhD supervisor and PhD student can jointly understand the PhD thesis[22, 23]. But nobody can achieve the study experience of the expired/retired PhD student like expired/retired PhD student. Nobody can steal the knowledge rather than self-practice rather than self-investment. So, killing a PhD student is a symptom of childness of crime in academia and philosophia. So, the situation is very simple in academia and philosophia. Sometimes, the situation may be complicated and non-judicial due to having human limitation. Therefore, crime in the name of PhD and crime in the name of PhD supervisor are increasing and expanding in the global academia and philosophia. Who should take care the global academia and philosophia?

22.5 Who should get more credit between PhD supervisor and PhD student for a PhD certificate?

PhD supervisor is a PhD supervisor if PhD supervisor is not doing any crime. A PhD supervisor also gets an extraordinary credit for the success of a PhD student to achieve a PhD certificate, if a PhD supervisor has a PhD thesis and PhD degree. A PhD supervisor may also record the PhD publications and PhD certificates for the experience support of his/her PhD supervision. What is the necessity to be an authorship in the research work of a PhD student, if the PhD supervisor already has a 'PhD thesis and PhD certificate'? If the PhD supervisor has no 'PhD thesis and PhD certificate', the PhD supervisor is not eligible to be a valid PhD supervisor of any PhD student. A general supervision credit of a PhD supervisor should be enough for his research fund searching, climbing in profession and/or promotion if he/she can fully understand the PhD work of the PhD student. A PhD supervisor should understand the full research of a PhD student to claim as a valid PhD supervisor. This is also the judicial requirement to claim as a PhD

supervisor in academia and philosophia. Although the financial value and financial recognition of a qualified PhD supervisor is comparatively poor in the global academia and philosophia. Who is take caring the global academia and philosophia? A general theory teacher teaches ready knowledge year after year, era after era when his/her hand sheets become gradually foggy and foggy. But a research professor should study more and more to supervise to examine to review to continue a single thesis to expand the new knowledge if every research opens a new door of science, technology, and philosophy. Who should take care the support of a research professor if everyone needs the illegal benefit?

22.6 What should be the purpose of BPhil, MPhil, and DPhil/PhD degree?

Product development of PhD research is not a core duty of a PhD[27]; thesis is the academic product of BPhil, MPhil, and PhD degree. These are also the academic and professional learning stage in research in academia in philosophia. So, these are called degree in school in university in PhD industry. These are not the stage of high-quality invention when the PhD student gets a student graded scholarship when they invest their tuition fees when they sacrifice their quality of life and/or invest for a future job for future food for future surviving for life-long service in the profession. The high-quality invention in research should be the post-PhD drama in terms of professional opportunity. Possibly, the word DPhil/DTech should be more acceptable term than the term of PhD. But practically and comparatively, PhD is more popular term in university and academia.

Table 5. BPhil degree in specific subject is very important for university and research organization whatever offered by Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain [4, 77, 79].

Name of degree	Number of Philosophy	Number of publications	Alignment with university designation
BPhil (Bachelor in Philosophy)	One	one/ based on funding and philosophical study	Lecturer
MPhil (Master in Philosophy)	One and/or extension of BPhil research	One/two/ based on funding and philosophical study	Assistant Professor
DTech/DPhil/PhD	One and/or extension of MPhil research	Two/three/based on funding and philosophical study	Associate Professor
Postdoc	One and/or extension of DPhil/PhD research	One/two/based on funding and philosophical study	Professor

Table 5, BPhil should be the general requirement of MPhil, PhD, academic service, research service, professional engineer, chartered engineer, and research organization. Professional engineers are addicted to do Master of Business Administration (MBA). But BPhil degree should also have a general priority theme for a professional engineer for professional surviving. Some student/course may have the degree of BSc and MSc. But they have no degree of BPhil and MPhil in their degree, they have no experience of BPhil and MPhil, they have no thesis of BPhil and MPhil. So, they should not be allowed for MPhil/PhD/academic service/research

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD
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Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in technology and law

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*

Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia

A prestigious research practitioner (RP) in technology, academic, and law since 2006

International Professor and consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, Higher Education, PhD, & Postdoc)
 BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime, human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva

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service/research organization. If a person can do BPhil thesis, he can also do MPhil/PhD thesis directly or independently within a shorter period of time. BPhil is the general requirement to be an industry expert and/or professional expert. But BPhil should be the mandatory requirement for lecturer/trainer job in university, research category jobs in industry, and the jobs of research organizations. So, the salary of lecturer should also higher or competitive in the lecturer job in academia and philosophia. Although, every decision of a professional expert/industry expert/daily life is also relevant to research and development. A global policy of BPhil degree (research) is approached and prioritized by Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain since 2022.

BPhil degree + BPhil thesis + MPhil degree + MPhil thesis + PhD/DPhil/DTech/DSc degree + PhD/DPhil thesis = PhD supervisor[4]

BPhil degree + BPhil thesis + MPhil degree + MPhil thesis + PhD/DPhil/DTech/DSc degree + PhD/DPhil/DTech/DSc thesis + Postdoc degree + Postdoc thesis = Postdoc supervisor[4]

22.7 Who can issue a valid PhD experience certificate as a valid PhD supervisor?

Who have an original PhD certificate and sole author PhD thesis who can confidentially serve as an ‘independent researcher’ in the global platform of research and development in academia and philosophia[4].

22.8 PhD supervision is a high-quality job of research service in academia and philosophia

Becoming author of a PhD student’s work is not necessary to become a genuine PhD supervisor who have a genuine PhD certificate who already serving as a professor/senior professor who already have a research expertise in academia and philosophia. Both of PhD supervisor and PhD student may mention their name in author list, but the words of PhD supervisor, PhD reviewer, and PhD student may be mentioned, but the contributions of PhD supervisor and PhD student may be mentioned.

Table 6. What should be the schematic design of BPhil/MPhil/PhD taught course in university in PhD industry?

Thesis	Written and thesis	Viva	Total marks	Research compliance	Written and thesis	Viva	Total marks
Thesis (part-01)	50	50	100	Research compliance (part-01)	50	50	100
Thesis (part-02)	50	50	100	Research compliance (part-02)	50	50	100
Thesis (part-03)	50	50	100	Research compliance (part-03)	50	50	100
Thesis (part-04)	50	50	100	Research compliance (part-04)	50	50	100
Final thesis	50	50	100	Reporting research compliance	50	50	100

Table 6, a BPhil/MPhil/PhD may be awarded in terms of a routine teaching, learning, and marking in academia and philosophia. A candidate of BPhil/MPhil/PhD may get a training

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

certificate of BPhil/MPhil/PhD without having an achiever of a quality thesis and research contribution in academia and philosophia.

22.9 Contradictions and non-judicial situations in PhD industry in academia and philosophia

In the present contradictions of academia; thesis and research have the minimum value. Possibly money and/or scholarly transfer has the maximum value to issue to recommend a research certificate. Possibly, every PhD industry has professional and non-professional person. A non-professional person deals and takes money. A professional person may also take money or non-judicial benefit indirectly without dealing. Moreover, the practice of scholar and/or non-scholar is not getting full priority in the assessment process. Moreover, money and sex may get the priority in the assessment process. Possibly, some professor sells PhD certificate, but they don't allow for scholarly certificate without money without sex without non-judicial benefit. These are also the global drama and PhD limitations in PhD industry. Every peer review process is also risky and risky to satisfy the scholarly protection. Scholarly wealth may also be stolen and/or ceased by computer hacking, professor hacking, e-mail hacking, journal hacking, involvement of researcher in laboratory, and peer reviewers. Possibly, Professor/supervisor may also expect a non-judicial percentage of salary/scholarship/non-judicial benefit from his/her junior researcher/student/colleague. The standardization in PhD policy should design for the right scholarly service in academia and PhD industry. Global academia and philosophia should take care the judicial policy.

22.10 Limitations to appoint vice-chancellor and professor/senior professor

Some university may prefer the nomination of vice-chancellor and professor who have academic and professional connection with the professor of the concern university which may create the non-judicial environment to administer the duty of a vice-chancellor. Every scholar should be vice chancellor and professor of the university without having any non-scholarly support of 'God father' and 'second God'. The chain connection of referee, PhD, promotion, profession, vice chancellor, and professor should be eliminated should be standardized in academia and philosophia. A third-party nomination of vice chancellor and professor of a country may solve the limitation to appoint vice-chancellor and professor of the university. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain faced the non-judicial techniques of 'God father' and 'second God'. At the end of the situation, the pocket and stomach of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was/is empty and empty was gradually empty and empty[23]. The technique of 'God father' and 'second God' policy should be eliminated for the peace surviving in the profession in the planet.

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23 Limitations of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD¹ researcher

23.1 Author lost research data information of his first PhD¹ at Melbourne, Australia when he pursued his second PhD² at RMIT University

Unfortunately, author lost research data information, test data information, analytical data information of his first PhD¹ at Melbourne, Australia when he faced critical conspiracy of life-threatening in Australian PhD school. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also did a general diary at Brunswick police station, Melbourne [23, 92].

23.2 Limitation of researcher during thesis of his first PhD¹

Unfortunately, author faced the force of surrounding persons to put the name in the author list of publications. Author also faced administrative force to put the name in the author list of publications[21]. Among them, there was also the person who is Dr. AKM Saiful Islam who wrote Dr. before the name at Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh who claimed seniority by profession by age by academia by philosophia who financially earned higher than Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (2007-2020) at City University by profession by age by academia by philosophia. Dr. AKM Saiful Islam demotivated/stopped to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to participate in a local conference at Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh when Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, PhD¹ supervisor internationally attended when Dr. AKM Saiful Islam was not attended in conference in 2019. So, what was the professional compliance of Dr. AKM Saiful Islam at City University? Who appointed him as head of the department? There is scope of advanced investigation and chain investigation since 2007. If Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-saying about Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, what was the duty of dean and vice-chancellor of the university since 2007? What was the philosophy of dean and vice-chancellor of City University university since 2007? Dr. AKM Saiful Islam should also write his PhD history and promotion history at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh to satisfy his service experience at City University at any university if he was the paid-practitioner at City University in terms of his PhD or doctoral study since 2007. When Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain trained and guided the project students of BSc engineering academically, Dr. Ranojit Kumar Dutta, Associate Professor, Department of General Education, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “you didn’t get any written permission to supervise the project students.” What was the philosophy of his non-judicial comments at City University. Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman, Assistant Professor, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2019, “you need to promote Dr. AKM Saiful Islam to get your self-promotion”. Promotion of Dr. AKM Saiful Islam and promotion of Engr. Md. Arifuzzaman should not be the academic and judicial pre-requisite of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain for the promotion of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at DTE, City University,

Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Shawkut Ali Khan, Dean, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka was telephoning and non-judicially discussing with someone in his office room in front of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2019-2020 when Professor Dr. Shawkut Ali Khan was seating on a chair of dean in a personal room of dean, “put my name in your publication, you are not putting may name in your publication.” Somehow, he was showing his deanship with someone to be author of non-judicial publication with another researcher. Possibly, Ms. Jarin Yasmin, Assistant Professor, City university expected authorship in publications automatically, but she couldn’t clearly tell to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Ms. Zeba Khanam, a lady teacher of mathematics was expressing her non-judicial voice to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2019 at DTE, City University, City Campus, “we will just edit something in your manuscript and we will get the name in your publication.” Possibly, she used the word of ‘we’ instead of ‘I’. These are the non-judicial philosophy of the promotion and surviving philosophy in academia and philosophia. These are the symptom of crimes of 1000 Australian penalty units. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also writing this article to convince the global academia and philosophia to eliminate the judicial crimes to increase the transparency [11, 21, 26].

23.3 Judicial compliance of PhD¹ register of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

PhD¹ thesis of author is more compliance to register at University of Calcutta, India and/or Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Kanpur, India who assessed the PhD manuscripts [6-8, 12] [4, 12-18] [3] [9] [19, 20] [5] [6, 8, 10]. Although the IIT, Kanpur has no any department of textile engineering (DTE). Similarly, PhD² thesis [22] of author is more compliance to register at RMIT University, Australia. PhD³ thesis [23] of author is also more compliance to register at RMIT University, Australia. Approval and confirmation of a PhD proposal is called PhD registration and/or PhD enrolment. PhD registration is also a part of a PhD certificate. This is the primary process of a PhD certification. Approval, confirmation, and registering of a PhD thesis is called PhD thesis registration. This is the last stage of a PhD process in academia and philosophia. To certify the brand value of a PhD thesis of a PhD researcher, a PhD thesis/PhD outcome may also be registered at branded university/universities under the relevant evidence and supporting discussion of author and supervisor and/or administrative authority of the university. Still the primary registered university should also register the PhD evidence of another university, PhD thesis, relevant evidence, relevant forwarding, and supporting discussion. This is not a simple drama in a PhD industry to satisfy the PhD compliance. This is the judicial drama in a PhD industry. So, the researchers come to university come to PhD supervisor come to PhD professor come to PhD community come to PhD industry. There is no chance to cease the scholarly performance of any researcher of any scholar if he/she is alive or

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non-alive in the planet under the existing process of academia and philosophia[23]. These are the mis-understanding of non-judicial PhD supervisor. Therefore, scholarly assessment in PhD industry in journal in the total peer review process is also a global challenge.

24 Let's establish transparency, let's eliminate the criminal, let's overcome the human limitation to survive in the planet, let's overcome the limitation of law implementation of barristerial community

Possibly and historically, bad people may do conspiracy may kill the person of good psychophysics and bad people also name-plate and display the names of good psychophysics for the contribution of the person in the planet. So, what is the judicial benefit of a good psychophysics? A land or property criminal may kill a judicial owner of the land and judicial witness of the land to become the non-judicial owner of the land or property. Similarly, a scholarly criminal may also kill a judicial owner of the thesis of the scholarly property and judicial witness of the thesis to become the owner of the thesis or scholarly property. A scholarly criminal may may ask may take illegal money to appoint a scholar or employee. Later, a scholarly criminal may also kill the scholar or employee to make a repeated nomination of a scholar or employee in his/her office. A scholarly criminal may certify a PhD degree in terms of a valid PhD thesis. Later, a scholarly criminal may kill the scholar or student to make a repeated PhD certification of another new PhD student. The situation may gradually plan and happen locally and internationally. Hence, some groups of academia and philosophia are non-judicially surviving and successfully surviving. Some groups of academia and philosophia can not survive judicially and scholarly. A criminal group may kill the scholar of the department for their non-judicial surviving in academia and philosophia if the criminal group can not continue their crimes in academia and philosophia. Wife and/or family connection and/or misguiding in different way may be the non-judicial technique and/or non-judicial business of the killing conspiracy. Possibly, criminal is not a single person[4, 23]. Nationally and internationally, criminals may target young scholars to involve them target crimes with the professional criminals. These are also the global limitation of academia and philosophia. Let's overcome the critical situation to survive in academia and philosophia to survive in the planet.

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25 Research evidences of author for ‘first PhD!’ thesis on “simultaneous dyeing and finishing with natural dyes and natural finishing agents on cotton textiles (2015-2020)”

157
 17-7-15

Date: 17-07-15

To
 Head of the Department,
 Department of Jute and Fibre Technology,
 University of Calcutta

Sub: Application for admission of Ph. D. Program.

Dear Sir,

I am very pleased and grateful to you that I have recently passed M. Tech. in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) from your Department. Now I hope, you will be happy that I am interested to further study Ph. D. (Tech.) in textile technology from your department where I am expecting to extend your continuous support. As I did my M. Tech. project work under the guidance of you, May I offer you to be my Ph. D. guide including honourable Professor (Dr.) Swapan Kumar Ghosh & Dr. Arindam Bagchi who are also very favourite to be my Ph. D guide.

As your obedient student you may know that I did my research work on dyeing and finishing in B.Sc. & M. Tech project. So may I also propose you to do my Ph. D research work in topics like “Dyeing and chemical finishing on cotton & cotton blended textile.”

As foreign student of your department, I want to continue my research work without going back to Bangladesh. So for staying in India, I need to extend my VISA for which I need an official letter from you about permission for pursuing my doctoral research work in your department.

I shall be highly obliged if you kindly arrange my necessary letter for Ph. D research work.

Thanking You

 Md. Anowar Hossain

C.C:
 Professor (Dr.) Swapankumar Ghosh, DJFT, IIT, CU
 Dr. Arindam Bagchi, DJFT, IIT, CU

Forwarded to the Registrar, CU
 17/7/15

Forwarded to the Registrar, CU
 17/7/15

(Prof. A. K. Samanta)
 Professor & Head of the Department
 Department of Jute & Fibre Technology
 Institute of Jute Technology
 University of Calcutta
 25 B. C. Road, Kol-19

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

Author’s biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

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Proposed Plan of Work & Related Explanation For Ph. D Research Programme

Title of the Thesis: Simultaneous Dyeing and Finishing with Natural Dyes and Natural Finishing Agents on Cotton Textiles as Natural Fibre

Subject/Discipline: Textile Technology

University: University of Calcutta

Name of the candidate: Md. Anowar Hossain, M.Tech.

Place of Work: Department of Jute and Fibre Technology,
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31/07/2017
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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

21/07/2017
Prof. (Dr.) A. K. Samanta
Professor
Dept. of Jute & Fibre Technology
Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta
35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata - 700 019

Title of the Thesis: Simultaneous Dyeing and Finishing with Natural Dyes and Natural Finishing Agents on Cotton Textiles as Natural Fibre.

Name of the candidate: Md. Anowar Hossain

Objectives:

1. To Develop completely ecofriendly natural dyed and Natural Agent will be applied on finished Cotton Textile Fabrics (Oeko-Tech Products) by adopting a Newer Technique of Simultaneous Mordanting – Dyeing-Finishing in a single step to reduce energy cost, process Time , Processing costs and Effluent Load,(which has not been done earlier)
2. To develop the single step processes and also completely Eco-Friendly Products of Cotton textiles using selective natural dyes and natural finishing agents using bio mordants and bio finishing agents obtained from extract of natural resources at reduced cost and energy. ⁴
3. Commercialization of such Oeko-Tech (Eco Friendly) Products of natural dyed and finished cotton textile Products for Domestic and Export market.

Literature Review:

Growing consciousness for eco-friendly textile products has caused more interest on these two natural fibres viz. Cotton and Silk as well as on natural dyes as well as natural finish. Due to compositional difference of Silk and Cotton, they differ much as dye receptor. Productions of synthetic dyes are dependent on petrochemical source and some of the synthetic dyes contain toxic / carcinogenic amines, and are not eco-friendly. Contrary to this, most of the natural dyes as well as natural finish with few exceptions are based on vegetable/ animal origin and are renewable, biodegradable, energy-efficient and eco-friendly^(1,2). Natural dyes can produce uncommon and soothing shades, and in some cases the shades are enhanced with age during use⁽¹⁾. Most of the natural dyes are usually non-toxic/ non-carcinogen and non-allergic. However the common drawbacks of natural dyes are its difficulty in reproducibility, non-uniform shade, poor to moderate fastness and non-availability of standard application methods⁽²⁾.

Most important issue now is origin and classification of some natural dyes applicable for different fibres are available in literature⁽³⁻⁵⁾. Gupta et al⁽⁶⁾ have documented some of the traditional processes of application of some natural dyes. Kawahito et al⁽⁷⁾ have compared the dyeing of cellulosic fabric with natural indigo and synthetic indigo. Radhakrishan⁽⁸⁾ as well as Ajita et al⁽⁹⁾ have reported effect of different mordants on selective natural dyes. Ahmed et al⁽¹⁰⁾ have studied the effect of application of natural dyes on the physical properties of Silk textiles. Agarwal⁽¹¹⁾ has studied the use of lac as natural dye. Ghosh and Samanta et.al⁽¹²⁾ have reported chemical modification of cotton by grafting with acrylamide in limited aqueous system to study its dyeability with acid dye and reactive dye. Samanta et al^(1,13,14) have studied the application of selective natural dyes on cotton and chemically modified cotton⁽¹³⁾ and application of appropriate mixture of natural dyes on cotton^(1,14) also.

Grierson⁽¹⁵⁾ has studied colour fastness characteristics of some natural dyes. Lee⁽¹⁶⁾ have studied the colour fastness properties of some natural dyes by applying uv-absorbers. Effect of chemical structure on light fastness property of some natural dyes has been reported by Gupta⁽¹⁷⁾. Oda⁽¹⁸⁾

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

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Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
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 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

B	Application of Natural finishes	Chemical pre treatment and dyeing and natural finishing in sequence	Study of Effect of Chemical pre-treatment at natural finishing on colour strength and fastness	Application of 10 selective natural finishes on Cotton and Silk textiles.	Finishing with improved colour strength and fastness.
C	Simultaneous Natural dyeing and finishing of cotton , silk and other natural textiles	(v) Chemical pretreatment & then Natural dyeing and finishing in simultaneous technique in one bath Identification by UV -VIS Absorbance Peaks Identification by FTIR Peak Identification by HPLC Identification by GCMS Identification by TLC Identification by CHNS Analyzer	Study of Improving colour fastness by applying cationic dye fixer and UV Absorber, anti-microbial effect etc. Identification of at least 5 dyes on cotton and 5 dyes on silk by using the Shade analytical instrument .	Simultaneous natural dyeing & finishing technique and its optimisation	Establishing of new process saving time, process steps, process cost and energy data

AKC
 31/07/2017
 Prof. (Dr.) A. K. Samanta
 Professor
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 Institute of Jute Technology
 University of Calcutta
 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata - 700 019

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**DEPARTMENT OF JUTE AND FIBRE TECHNOLOGY
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Kolkata - 700 019

July 31, 2017

To whom it may concern

This is to certify that **Md. Anowar Hossain S/o of Late Md. Abdur Rashid** presently residing at House: 478, Vill: Purbo-Nuthurchar, P.O: K, Mohonpur, (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, who has passed M. Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) from Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta in the year 2015 having 1st Class with 75.70% aggregate marks combining all four semesters of the said M Tech Course in Textile Technology. I found him innovative and outstanding in carrying out Master level research on Chemical Processing, Dyeing and Finishing of Cotton Textiles during completion of his M. Tech Thesis.

As per Calcutta University norms, he is eligible for admission in Ph. D Research program in Textile Technology under the guidance of any recognized supervisor of this Department under this University.

He has already applied to the undersigned, for enrolling him as PhD Research student for carrying out PhD research work with a details of the plan of work approved by the undersigned on "Simultaneous Dyeing and Finishing with Natural Dyes and Natural Finishing Agents on Cotton Textiles as Natural Fibre" which is to be carried out in this Department of Calcutta University under the supervision of the undersigned and Dr. P S Vankar, Sr. Consultant, DJFT, IJT, CU as Joint Supervisor after his final admission to the PhD Program of Calcutta University in Textile Technology subject to obtaining students visa, and other clearances for foreign student and receiving his PhD Scholarship from Govt. of Bangladesh or any other agency.

There is no PhD Scholarship available in this Department at present and hence, I recommend his name to be considered with merit for PhD Scholarship of Govt. of Bangladesh enabling him to enroll and to carry out his PhD research program in this dept. under University of Calcutta in Textile Technology.

As his professor and his M Tech Thesis guide, I had an opportunity to act as his mentor for his day to day studies and laboratory work and capability of carrying out research under my instruction, where I have found his in depth knowledge of the subject matter in Textile Chemical Processing of Natural Fibres (Cotton and Jute) with sound background of Analytical Chemistry. He has published one research paper from his M Tech Thesis in reputed Journal of American Association for Science and Technology (AASCIT), USA in Journal of Materials Science and Applications in Vol-2 (4), 2016, pp 25-34. He has also published one book on "Basic Knowledge of Wet Processing Technology" published by Rupak Publications, Dhaka, Bangladesh. So, I wish him to continue his research in PhD level in our University under my guidance/supervision. So, I have full consent to supervise him in his proposed PhD research program under University of Calcutta for enrolling him as full time PhD research Student of this Department for PhD Research Degree Program in Textile Technology as per norms of University of Calcutta, subject to receiving his PhD Scholarship from Government of Bangladesh or any other Funding Agency.

For any further information to consider his candidature for PhD Research Scholarship of Bangladesh Govt. related to his admission and enrollment here as PhD student w.e.f the current/next session, we are ready to submit any other required information as and when required. My contact details are as given below for any further query about this.

Place: Kolkata

 (Prof. A. K. Samanta)
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35, Ballygunge Circular Road,
Kolkata - 700 019

Ref.: Certificate/ 39 December 17, 2018

CERTIFICATE OF RECOMMENDATION

To whom it may concern

This is to certify that **Md. Anowar Hossain S/o of Late Md. Abdur Rashid** presently residing at House: 478, Vill: Purbo-Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur, (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, who has passed M. Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) from Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta in the year 2015 having 1st Class with 75.70% aggregate marks in M Tech Course in Textile Technology.

Md. Anowar Hossain also completed B.Sc. in Textile Engineering from City University, Dhaka. He achieved 1st Class in both B.Sc in Textile Engineering from City University, Dhaka and M.Tech in Textile Technology (TT) from University of Calcutta.

So far, He published seven research papers with textile engineering based research in international peer reviewed and USA based journal as well as author of three books in Textile Engineering. He has carried out P.G. Level Research Project under my supervision during his study of M.Tech in Textile Technology under University of Calcutta for M. Tech Thesis entitled "Combined Dyeing and Aroma Finishing of Woven Cotton Fabric for Garments". During supervision of his M. Tech Thesis carried out in this Department under myself, I found him very innovative in carrying out research on Chemical Processing, Dyeing and Finishing of Cotton Textiles. As his M Tech Thesis guide, I had an opportunity to act as his mentor for his day to day studies and laboratory work, where I have found his in depth knowledge of the subject matter in Textile Chemical Processing of Natural Fibres (Cotton and silk and jute) with sound background of Analytical Chemistry. He has published more than five research paper with me and one of them is from his M Tech Thesis work published in reputed Journal of American Association for Science and Technology(AASCT), USA in Journal of Materials Science and Applications in Vol-2 (4), 2016, pp25-34.

Md. Anowar Hossain is presently a Lecturer in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka. He has more than 5 years' work experience in fields of textile production, R & D of technical textiles and clothing, as well as teaching and research based activities. During interaction with him I came to know that he was a former Assistant Professor, BCMC College of Engineering and Technology, Affiliated by University of Rajshahi. He was also a former Lecturer of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College, Affiliated by University of Chittagong.

I strongly recommend him to be considered for Common Wealth Scholarship or any other Scholarship for carrying out his PhD research program related to Textile Technology/ Textile Chemistry or any other Chemical Processing area related to its application in Textiles. I wish him all the success in life.

Place: Kolkata

(Prof. A K Samanta)
Professor & Former HOD
Department of Jute and Fibre Technology
Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta
Mail id: ijitksamanta@hotmail.com
Mobile : 0091 9831161529

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University of Calcutta

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD
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Page | 94

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Ref.DJFT/IJT/CU/PhD/

July 26, 2017

To whom it may concern

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As per Calcutta University norms, he is eligible for admission in Ph. D Research program in Textile Technology under the guidance of any recognized supervisor of this Department under this University.

He has already applied to the undersigned, as Head of The Department for enrolling him as PhD Research student for carrying out PhD research work on suitable topic in Chemical Processing, Dyeing and Finishing of Cotton Textiles to be carried out in this Department of Calcutta University. His proposed PhD research topic is "Simultaneous Dyeing and Finishing with Natural Dyes and Natural Finishing Agents on Cotton Textiles as Natural Fibre", which he can carry out in our Department after his admission to PhD Program of Calcutta University in Textile Technology subject to receiving the PhD Scholarship from Govt. of Bangladesh or any other agency.

As per norms of Calcutta University, if he gets no objection, embassy clearance, PhD Students' visa mentioning the name of University of Calcutta and finally if he is selected and gets the PhD Scholarship from Bangladesh Govt. we are ready to admit him as PhD Research Scholar in this dept. for carrying out PhD Research program in Textile Technology under any one or two Sr. Faculty members including Prof A K Samanta or else (allotment of Guide/supervisor for PhD Research is done after final admission to PhD Program during registration in the University of Calcutta as PhD Student).

There is no PhD Scholarship available in this Department at present and Hence We recommend his name to be considered with merit for PhD Scholarship of Govt. of Bangladesh enabling him to enroll and to carry out his PhD research program in this dept. under University of Calcutta in Textile Technology. We wish him all success to continue his PhD Level research subject to confirmation of his receiving PhD scholarship from Govt. of Bangladesh or any other agency

For any further information to consider his candidature for PhD Research Scholarship of Bangladesh Govt. related to his admission and enrollment here as PhD student wef the current/next session, we are ready to submit any other required information as and when required. My contact details are as given below for any further query about this:

Place: Kolkata

(Prof. S K Ghosh)
Professor & HOD
Department of Jute and Fibre Technology
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Mail id- ijtsk40@gmail.com
Mobile : + 91 9831324354

Dear Student,

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

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Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh

Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD

Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of

Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);

Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh

Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India

Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design

Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix

Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and

University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Please find hrewith the recommendation letter from Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta for your PhD Admission as the attachement (1 (one) page for submitting the same to Bangladesh Government for PhD. Scholarship along with approved and signed Plan of Work for proposed PhD Research for you in this Department.

Page | 95

This may be treated as recommendation letter cum offer letter for the proposed PhD Research for you in this department of Calcutta University subject to receiving Ph.D. Scholarship from Bangladesh Government or any other funding agency and obtaining student visa and other clearance during admission in Ph.D Research Program under University of Calcutta as per norms of the University of Calcutta.

Hoping, you to make all arrangement for PhD Admission in Textile Technology under University of Calcutta after confirming scholarship from your Country or any other source as we have no PhD Scholarship at present.

Thanks,

(Prof. A K Samanta)

Professor and PG Admission Co-ordinator
DJFT, IJT, CU

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

নোটি

১০/১২/২০১৮ ইং

জনাব মোঃ আনোয়ার হোসেন, প্রভাষক, টেক্সটাইল ইঞ্জিনিয়ারিং বিভাগ, জাহাঙ্গীরনগর বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়ে পি.এইচ.ডি কোর্সে (খন্ডকালীন) ভর্তির জন্য বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়ের অনুমতি পত্র চেয়ে ০১/১২/২০১৮ ইং তারিখে রেজিস্ট্রার দপ্তরে একটি লিখিত আবেদন করেছেন। তাঁর আবেদন পড়ে বিভাগীয় প্রধান এবং ডীন মহোদয় সুপারিশ করেছেন। রেজিস্ট্রার মহোদয় প্রাপ্ত আবেদন পত্রটি মতামত প্রদানের জন্য গত ০৬/১২/২০১৮ ইং তারিখে অতিরিক্ত রেজিস্ট্রার বরাবর প্রেরণ করেন। অতিরিক্ত রেজিস্ট্রার তাঁর লিখিত মতামতসহ গত ০৭/১২/২০১৮ ইং তারিখে রেজিস্ট্রার বরাবর প্রেরণ করেন।

জনাব মোঃ আনোয়ার হোসেন পি.এইচ.ডি কোর্সে ভর্তির নোটিশ অনুযায়ী উক্ত কোর্সে ভর্তির জন্য চাকুরিরত প্রতিষ্ঠানের শুধুমাত্র অনুমতি পত্র প্রয়োজন। তিনি গবেষণা করার জন্য ছুটি প্রার্থনা করেননি। ছুটি ব্যক্তিরকে তিনি তাঁর গবেষণা কর্ম সম্পাদন করতে পারবেন।

জনাব মোঃ আনোয়ার হোসেন একজন সৎ এবং নিষ্ঠাবান শিক্ষক। তিনি উচ্চ শিক্ষা গ্রহণ করে বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়, দেশ ও জাতির কল্যাণ সাধনে নিজেকে নিয়োজিত করবেন বলে আমাদের বিশ্বাস। তাই তাঁর সেই উচ্চ শিক্ষা গ্রহণের স্বপ্নকে বাস্তবায়নের জন্য সার্বিক দিক বিবেচনা করে অনুমতি পত্র প্রদান করা যেতে পারে। সদয় সিদ্ধান্তের জন্য নথি পেশ করা হল।

Kamal
10/12/18
(Md. Kamal, A/O)

[Signature]
10.12.18
Additional Registrar sir

Registrar Sir

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Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
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People's Republic of Bangladesh Office of the Notary Public-Bangladesh

S.N. ISLAM & ASSOCIATE'S

Advocate & Notary Public
(Whole Bangladesh)

According to the Section 8 (1)(h) of Notary ordinance 1961 Ad

Translated Copy

[City University Monogram]
Date: 18/11/2019

Ref No. - City University/Reg./9083/2019

To,
Mr. Md Anowar Hossain (Chief Researcher)
Lecturer
Textile Engineering Department
City University

Subject: **Regarding research projects and allocation of approvals.**

Dear Sir,

This is hereby informing you, for your kind consideration that, Your Recommended Research Project: Zero Toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural Mordanting Agents [A Six Months Duration of Project, September, 2019 - February, 2020 and the allotment of the said research Tk. 1,00,000/- (One Lac) was approved by the university authorities. The authority has to be notified before starting the project. After receiving your letter 50% of the money allocated to start the project, 25% in terms of getting a Progress Report at the end of the half term and upon completion of the project, the Project Completion Report (PCR) will submit and the remaining amount will be disbursed immediately after receiving it.

In this regards you are requested to begin the work of your proposed research project as soon as possible.

Thanking you,
Signature/ Illegible
18/11/2019
M.A Hannan
Registrar
City University

Permanent Certified University

Permanent Campus: Khagan Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Cell: 01854-640476, 01862-213214, E-mail: ar@cityuniversity.edu.bd
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Translated By
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Mob: 01711397342, Tel: 9513785
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30 NOV 2019

ATTESTED
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...creating a culture of excellence

তারিখ: ১৮/১১/২০১৯ইং

স্মারক নং- সিটি ইউনিভার্সিটি/রেজি./৯০৮৩/২০১৯ইং

বরাবর,
জনাব মোঃ আনোয়ার হোসেন (প্রধান গবেষক)
প্রভাষক
টেক্সটাইল ইঞ্জিনিয়ারিং বিভাগ
সিটি ইউনিভার্সিটি।

বিষয়ঃ গবেষণা প্রকল্প এবং বরাদ্দ অনুমোদন প্রসঙ্গে।

জনাব,

আপনার সদয় অবগতির জন্য জানানো যাচ্ছে যে, আপনার প্রস্তাবিত গবেষণা প্রকল্প Zero Toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural Mordanting Agents [A Six Months Duration of Project, September, 2019- February, 2020] এবং উক্ত গবেষণার বরাদ্দ ১,০০,০০০/- (এক লক্ষ) টাকা বিশ্ববিদ্যালয় কর্তৃপক্ষ কর্তৃক অনুমোদিত হয়েছে। উক্ত প্রকল্পের কাজ শুরু করার অব্যবহিত পূর্বে কর্তৃপক্ষকে অবহিত করতে হবে। আপনার পত্র পাওয়ার পরে প্রকল্পের কাজ শুরু করার জন্য বরাদ্দকৃত অর্থের ৫০%, মেয়াদকালের অর্ধেককাল সমাপনান্তে সন্তোষজনক অগ্রগতির প্রতিবেদন (Progress Report) পাওয়ার শর্তে ২৫% এবং প্রকল্প কাজ পূর্ণ সমাপনান্তে Project Completion Report (PCR) জমা এবং তা গৃহীত হওয়ার পরপরই বরাদ্দকৃত অর্থের অবশিষ্ট ২৫% অর্থ ছাড় করা হবে।

এমতাবস্থায় আপনার প্রস্তাবিত গবেষণা প্রকল্পের কাজ যথাশীঘ্র সম্ভব শুরু করার জন্য আপনাকে অনুরোধ করা হলো।

ধন্যবাদান্তে

এম এ হোসেন
রেজিস্ট্রার
সিটি ইউনিভার্সিটি।

26 NOV 2019

স্থায়ী সনদ প্রাপ্ত বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়
Permanent Campus : Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Cell: 01854-640476, 01862-213214, E-mail: info@cityu.edu.bd
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Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

সিটি ইউনিভার্সিটি

স্থায়ী ক্যাম্পাসঃ খাগান, বিরুলিয়া, সাভার, ঢাকা-১২১৬।
তথ্য অফিসঃ ১৩/এ পাছপথ, ঢাকা-১২১৫।

তারিখঃ ১৭/১১/২০২১

Mr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Lecturer
Dept. of Textile Engineering
City University

জনাব,

এই মর্মে আপনাকে অবহিত করা যাচ্ছে যে, ২০১৯-২০২০ অর্থ বছরে সিটি ইউনিভার্সিটির কর্তৃপক্ষ গবেষণা কার্যক্রম পরিচালনার জন্য গত ৫/১১/২০১৯ইং তারিখে আপনার প্রস্তাবিত গবেষণার বিপরীতে ১,০০,০০০/- টাকা বরাদ্দ করা হয়েছে।

উল্লেখ্য যে, আপনার গবেষণার অগ্রগতি প্রতিবেদনসহ আগামী ২৫/১১/২০২১ইং রোজ বৃহস্পতিবার বিকেল ৩.০০ ঘটিকায় ইউনিভার্সিটির স্থায়ী ক্যাম্পাসে কনফারেন্স রুমে উপস্থিত থাকার জন্য বিশেষভাবে অনুরোধ করা হলো।

ধন্যবাদান্তে

প্রফেসর মীর আকতার হোসেন
রেজিস্ট্রার
সিটি ইউনিভার্সিটি

সদয় অবগতির জন্য অনুলিপি ঃ

- ১। মাননীয় ভাইস-চ্যান্সেলর
- ২। ডেপুটি চ্যান্সেলর
- ৩। ডেপুটি কন্ট্রোলিং অফিসার
- ৪। ডেপুটি রেজিস্ট্রার
- ৫। সহকারী রেজিস্ট্রার
- ৬। সদস্য সচিব, রিসার্চ সেল
- ৬। অফিস কপি

স্থায়ী সনদ প্রাপ্ত বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়

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Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD
Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
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Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Page | 100

Date: 22/11/2021

Professor Mir Akhter Hossain
Registrar
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Letter of withdrawal the sanctioned research fund BDT 1, 00,000 (one lac), approved for Md. Anowar Hossain, lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Permanent campus, academic year: 2019-20.

Dear Sir,

I would like to notify that I am a lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science and Engineering; presently I am pursuing Ph.D research at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia funded by RTP stipend scholarship, an Australian Government Research program. I got a letter of "study leave" from registrar office, city university approved by Mr. M A Hannan, former Registrar, City University on 26 January 2020, ref: City University/Faculty/BSTE/4029/2020 and I left Bangladesh on 28 January 2020 and commenced Ph.D research at School of Fashion and Textiles on 5 February 2020.

In these circumstances, I would like to withdraw the official allotment of approved research fund BDT 1, 00, 000 (one lac), project duration: six months, academic year 2019-2020, notified by registrar office on 18 November 2019, proposal accepted by the committee of research cell, City University to continue the proposed research works on "zero toxic coloration on cotton fabric with natural dyes and natural mordanting agents" at office location, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, permanent campus and research location at chemistry lab, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka.

Thanks

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

Supporting information

Letter of research reporting issued by registrar office on 17 November 2021
Letter of study leave

Copy forwarded To

Professor (Dr.) Md. Humaun Kabir
Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Dean, Faculty of Science and Engineering

A/Professor (Dr.) Saiful Islam
Former Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

1

Research Proposal

On

Zero Toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural Mordanting Agents

[A Six Months Duration of Project, September, 2019-January, 2020]

Proposed By

Md. Anowar Hossain,

M.Tech. in Textile Technology, University of Calcutta, India

Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering, City University

Principal Investigator

Mobile: +8801732681104, E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Department of Textile Engineering, City University

Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka.

September-2019

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2

Research Track Record of Md. Anowar Hossain, Principal Investigator (PI):

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is presently a Lecturer in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka and a Ph.D researcher of Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka. He is a former Assistant Professor and Head of Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering and Technology, Jessore, Affiliated by University of Rajshahi. He is also a former Lecturer and Head of Department of Textile Engineering and Assistant Registrar (Additional), Newcastle University College, Chittagong, Affiliated by University of Chittagong. He worked as chairman & member of Examination Committee both for University of Rajshahi and University of Chittagong. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a former CEO of Bangladesh Textile and Fashion, Dhaka, former Coordinator of Gothic Design Ltd., Viyellatex Group, Tongi, former merchandiser of Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain studied two years Master of Technology in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) from University of Calcutta, India and also completed four years B.Sc. in Textile Engineering from City University, Dhaka. He published different research papers as principal author connected with international universities where twelve research papers with textile engineering based research in international peer reviewed journal. He is an author of three books in Textile Engineering, "Basic knowledge of Wet Processing Technology", "Principle of Garments Production" and "Garments Technology for Merchandiser and Fashion Designer". Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has certified training on coated textile production and glass fabric manufacturing (KE Technical Textiles Ltd, India), Dyeing and Finishing, Spinning, Weaving and Knitting, Merchandising (National Institute of Textile Training, Research and Design NITRAD, Savar, Dhaka, Faculty of Niederrhein University, Germany), Export and Import (DCCI Business Institute, Dhaka, Affiliated by ITC UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva) as well as other training in related profession of textile engineering. [Below mentioned national and foreign researchers are already connected with related fields of proposed project investigator (PI) and he has already Six (6) publications as first and corresponding author in international peer reviewed journal with all the mentioned national and foreign experts in textile coloration addressing the present working place, City University]

National consultants and experts in textile coloration:

Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, Assistant Professor and Head, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka.
 Dr. Md. Nurul Abser, Professor and Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka.
 Dr. Ferdous ara Dilruba, Chief Scientific Officer, Bangladesh Jute Research Institute (BJRI), Dhaka.

Foreign Consultants and experts in textile coloration:

Dr. AK Samanta, Professor and Former Chairman, Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India.
 Dr. Padma S. Vanakr, Professor & Principal Research FEAT Lab, Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Kanpur, India.

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City University

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3

Introduction:

Bangladesh is presently exporting a good quantum of coloured and decorative textile products made of natural fibres like silk, cotton and jute mainly to Japan, USA, Korea, European community countries and African countries. Worldwide growing consciousness for eco-friendly production process is generating more and more customer's interests on natural fibre, natural dyes and natural finished based textile products, particularly for the export market due to having an approach of zero toxic coloration of cotton fabric with natural dyes under consideration of toxic free product and environment friendly production process. Considering the product development and production process corner, textile sector has the highest scope to apply this research work for attracting the value-added customer. But, till today there is a huge lack of research and development of natural dyeing and finishing based textile product.

However, there are some discrete reports available that indicate the application of natural dyes for producing uncommon shades on natural fibers like cotton (Anowar and et al. 2018, 2019, Cristea and Vilarem 2006; Gahlot et al. 2008; Sentikumar et al. 2002), jute (Samanta and Agarwal 2008a; Samanta and Agarwal 2007; Samanta et al. 2008b; Samanta and Konar 2012a; Samanta and Konar 2015; Samanta et al. 2010, 2011; Samanta et al. 2012b; Samanta et al. 2008c; Samanta et al. 2012b, 2009), silk (Gahlot et al. 2008; Javali et al. 2009; Katti et al. 1996; Mahale et al. 2003a; Mahale et al. 2003b; Sidhu and Grewal 2008; Vankar and Shankar 2008; Vinod et al. 2010), wool (Gahlot, Fatima, and Papnai 2008; Gulrajani et al. 2003; Shanker and Vankar 2005; Yoshizumi and Crews 2003). Hence there are ample scopes of doing scientific research on the application of natural dyes on cotton and other textiles aimed at obtaining newer shade with acceptable colour fastness behavior, uniform and reproducible colour yield through appropriate techniques. Simultaneous natural dyeing, natural mordanting and natural finishing process can be a new approach of technique which will minimize the process steps different cost related production like energy and total process cost. Reducing process cost will minimize total cost of the product in the export market, it will be highly beneficial to sustain in a competitive market if the expected research output can be applied successfully in Government and non-government textile mill at home and abroad.

Natural dyes are considered to be eco-friendly as these are obtained from renewable resources as compared to synthetic dyes which are derived from non-renewable petroleum resources. These are biodegradable and the residual vegetal matter left after extraction of dyes can be easily composted and used as fertilizer. They produce soft colours soothing to the eye which is in harmony with nature which is gradually gaining popularity due to its non-toxicity and eco-friendly character against possible unsafe ecotoxicity criteria of synthetic dyes. Most of the studies available for dyeing with natural dyes relates to cotton textiles and such studies on cotton are still insufficient to establish. Hence, there are ample scope of undertaking an integrated study in this area for cotton and chemically modified cotton to study its surface appearance, durability and dyeing of cotton and chemically modified cotton with natural dyes.

The research and development in natural dyed based textile products conducted by textile researcher has been confused to solve technological problem for the production of ecofriendly based textiles and earlier investigation prove that the standard technology and production aspects are the core barrier for the standardization and commercialization of nature friendly textiles and there is unlimited technical demand for ensuring novel production and synthesis method for production process. Currently developed only natural dyed based textiles have so much limitations and have synthetic mordanting application which is not ecofriendly and not fulfilling the requirements of nontoxic coloration of textiles and till today there is a huge lack of research and development of natural dyed and finished textile products as reviewed in literature.

Proposed research on Zero Toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural mordanting agent generated by natural dyes and selective natural mordanting agent through selective dyeing process and the completely ecofriendly products was not experimented till now and the output of this research may be a greater and attractive invention for the development of value added textiles with the theoeokotex based textiles as well as improve the textiles with significant and special properties like UV protection and antibacterial property etc. comparing to reviewed method and developed natural dyed based textiles and there is little/limited research has been conducted with the proposed materials and method. Natural dyeing and finishing in the stage of development process and still many important accomplishments are hidden with the success corner of related researchers due to unavailability of testing standards for clothing, lower fastness properties and reproducibilities are the question marks to the textile scientist for natural dyed based textiles.

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Review of Literature:

Anowar and et al. (2018) were experimented in earlier research on natural coloration that natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural finishing agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing. A combined green dyeing and mordanting method was applied on cotton fabric in which natural coloring agents were extracted from Diospyros malabarica (Green Gaub fruit) and Camellia sinensis (Green Tea Leaf) where green lemon juice had been used as green mordanting agent and there is no artificial chemical was used during demodulation process of coloring agent, dyeing and mordanting. Both the treated and untreated fabric samples were tested for the mechanical properties (color fastness to washing and rubbing) and dyeing performance in terms of color fastness properties (light fastness) and color strength, K/S value. For dyeing with green gaub fruit, color fastness to wash and rubbing = Very excellent, color fastness to light = good and for dyeing with green tea leaf, color fastness to wash = very excellent, color fastness to rubbing = excellent, color fastness to light = good. An improved color strength, K/S value had been found for both dyeing with green gaub fruit and green tea leaf while mordanting was applied with green lemon juice.

Anowar and et al. (2018) studied on pollution free dyeing and mordanting is indicated as a creative innovation of textile coloration on cotton fabric in which natural dyes were extracted from Swietenia macrophylla (Mahogany leaf) and Musa acuminata (Green Banana Peel) as an unpolluted dyes and Citrus limon (L.) juice was applied as an unpolluted natural mordanting agent. There is no synthetic chemical was used during the whole progression in dyes extraction process and dyeing method. Both the treated and untreated fabric samples were tested for their dyeing performance in terms of color strength, K/S value and color fastness properties like color fastness to washing, rubbing and light. Higher K/S value of lemon mordanted sample was investigated by analysis of spectrophotometer for both dyeing with mahogany and green banana pill. Color fastness to washing and rubbing had been found moderately good for both dyeing with mahogany leaves and green banana pill with lemon mordanting. Moderately good color fastness to light had been found for dyeing with only mahogany leaves and green banana pill but improved light fastness was found for green banana pill with lemon mordanting. As per visual appearance, dyed fabric with green banana pill and lemon mordanting was found very even distribution of color on the surface of cotton fabric. An exceptionally attractive soft hand feel and color shading outcome was observed for dyeing with green banana pill comparing to mahogany leaves without having any additional application of synthetic softer which is the demand of both local and foreign customers in clothing industries.

Anowar and et al. (2018) focused that a toxicity free cotton fabric coloration and antibacterial technique was developed where natural colorant curcumin and tannin were applied for instigating a substitute of toxic colorant. Considering the negative impacts of man-made dyes in environment, non-toxic coloring and sterile finishing was carried out with curcumin and tannin as non-toxic colorant quintessence from pure natural sources of Curcuma longa (Turmeric) and Camellia sinensis (Tea Leaf) using environment friendly lemon extracted (Natural Citric acid) solution as natural mordant and their color shading and functional outcomes were evaluated in variety of shades as compared with colour yield/outcomes with ferrous sulphate and copper sulphate as two most extensively practiced conventional chemical mordants. Critical performances of mordanted and unmordanted cotton fabric samples were tested for their color parameters like Colour Strength, K/S value and Colour fastness (color fastness to Washing, UV- Light and Rubbing) properties, besides measurement of other colour interaction parameters (L*, a*, b* and ΔE) as well as anti-bacterial performance as per AATCC-100-2012 method. The dye absorption determined by color spectrophotometer showed higher color strength when treated with curcumin and tannin colorant in the presence of natural extracted citric acid from lemon as toxic free mordanting agent compared to mordanting with Ferrous sulphate as well as conventional mordanting with Copper Sulphate. Higher rubbing fastness was observed for both dyeing with Turmeric and Tea Leaves when mordanting with lemon and ferrous sulphate. Curcumin demonstrates a pharmacological properties that curcumin found effective against E. coli bacteria in laboratory experiment well as FTIR study of Turmeric with lemon mordanted sample was confirmed the natural crosslinking among cotton fibre cellulose, turmeric curcumin and lemon-citric acid. Consequently, this work has led to development of a process of concurrent natural dyeing and finishing with natural extracted agents on cotton with natural mordants to make the fabric colour full and anti-bacterial also. If the present work is trailed commercially to make it feasible, undoubtedly present finding of research may be an exceptional source of eco-garments production which has a higher demand in local and foreign customer.

Anowar and et al. (2018) investigated that eco-friendly dyeing on cotton fabric was conceded out with organic dyes distillate from organic extraction process of organic Tectonagrandis (Teak Leaf) and Azadirachta indica (Neem Leaf) using ecofriendly metallic mordants and natural mordants (Ferrous Sulphate as ecofriendly metallic mordant and Lemon juice as an organic mordant) were used in the research work and their results were compared with results of copper sulphate as conventionally used mordant. All the treated and untreated cotton fabric samples were tested for their Colour Strength and Colour fastness (colour fastness to Washing, UV Light and Rubbing) properties, besides measurement of other colour interaction parameters (L*, a*, b* and ΔE) as well as antibacterial performance as per AATCC-100-2012 method. Results of colour parameters showed lower ΔE values are obtained when treated with lemon mordanting agent for both the case of dyeing cum finishing treatment with Teak leaf and Neem leaf (though amongst the two dye extract used, Neem leaf extract showed higher K/S value) as compared to

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5

conventional mordanting with Copper Sulphate. While, Ferrous Sulphate render moderate K/S value than all due to inherent own colour of ironinFeSO4. comparing lemon mordanting with conventional copper sulphate mordant, colour fastness properties of teak leaf extract with lemon mordanting are found to be better and is in the order of Rubbing Fastness > followed by colour fastness to Light > colour fastness to wash than that for synthetic mordanting, but for dyeing with extract of neem leaf with lemon mordanting showed very attractive colour fastness considering to all colour fastness properties studied here. In this study, a newer approach / attempt had been made to impart a simultaneous antibacterial finish along with above said natural dyeing. Hence, the antibacterial properties of neem leaf extract dyed cotton using lemon mor-danted sample resulted better reduction/killing of bacteria. Thus, this work has led to development of a process of simultaneous dyeing and finishing with natural agents on organic cotton with organic mordants to make the fabric colour full and anti-bacterial too.

Anowar and et al. (2019) reviewed on Natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural finishing agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing can be established by developing completely eco-friendly natural dyes and natural finishing agent which can be applied on cotton textiles (Oeko-Tech Products) by adopting a newer technique of simultaneous Mordanting-Dyeing-Finishing in a single step to reduce energy cost, process time, processing costs and effluent load as well as to develop the single step processes and also completely eco-friendly products of cotton textiles using selective natural dyes and natural finishing agents using bio mordants and bio finishing agents obtained from an extract of natural resources at reduced cost and energy. There is huge scope of commercialization of such Oeko-Tech (Eco-Friendly) products of natural dyed and finished cotton textile products for domestic and export market. Different selective natural dyes like teak leaf, turmeric, jackfruit wood, sappan wood, skin of onion, arjuna bark etc., bio-mordanting agent like bio-enzyme, harda, lemon as natural mordanting agents, extracted soyabean seed as natural chemical modification as well as natural finishing agent like coconut oil as UV absorber, neem and guava leaf as antimicrobial agent where all dyed and finished fabric can be scientifically tested by SEM, FTIR, DSC, HPLC, GCMS, TLC, CHNS, X-ray diffraction pattern etc.

Samanta and et. al (2003) and Dedhia E.M (1998) studied that growing consciousness for eco-friendly textile products has created more interest on cotton fibre based natural dyeing and finishing. Productions of synthetic dyes are dependent on the petrochemical source and some of the synthetic dyes contain toxic/carcinogenic amines and are not eco-friendly. Contrary to this, most of the natural dyes as well as natural finish with few exceptions are based on vegetable/ animal origin and are renewable, biodegradable, energy-efficient and eco-friendly.

Kawahito, et al. (2002) have compared the dyeing of cellulosic fabric with natural indigo and synthetic indigo. Radhakrishnan as well as Ajita, et al. have reported the effect of different mordants on selective natural dyes. **Grierson, et al. (1995)** has studied colour fastness characteristics of some natural dyes. **Lee, et al. (2001)** have studied the colour fastness properties of some natural dyes by applying UV-absorbers. **Gupta, et al (1998)** have reported that the effect of chemical structure on light fastness property of some natural dyes.

Oda, et al. (2001) was studied the effect of phenyl ester functional group on photofading of carthamin on cellulose acetate. Most of the studies are sporadic and insufficient in developing scientific knowledge base on the subject. Therefore, very less study on simultaneous natural dyeing and finishing, dyeing process variables and characterisation etc.

Reviewed study shows that natural dyes was applied with synthetic mordanting agents on textile substrates and its feasibility of application has been positively remarked by the researcher in the area of textile coloration, but the application of completely biomordanting agents/natural mordanting agents/natural finishing agents, standardization of process development, industrial application and commercialization of natural dyed product are the major gaps of research and development in the area of natural dyeing and finishing which may be focused area of research in proposal on zero toxic coloration. Hence, an integrated scientific study for selective natural dye-fibre-mordanting system, for selective natural dyes and natural mordanting agents can be applied on cotton and other textiles is felt necessary, for establishing the ecofriendly process of textile colorations for natural dyed textiles.

The natural coloration on cotton fabric is an approach of zero toxic coloration of cotton fabric with natural dyes and natural mordanting agent will be the alternative way of conventional synthetic dyeing which is a threat of ecofriendly environment. Proposed technique can be implemented in the textile industries for having the nature friendly agro renewable sources of natural dyes. On the otherhand synthetic dyes is a petroleum sources of production. The concept and the workable procedures developed from the research can be transferred to industrial practice in home and abroad. The proposed research can provide simultaneous effect of dyeing, mordanting, technical finishing, ecofriendly coloration process in textiles is definitely a technological light in the door of colored textile production. Thus, there are sufficient scopes of doing scientific research on making standardization of technique, increasing color fastness to conventional process, adaptability, durability and suitability of process and product development.

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Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

6

Objectives of Research:

- To develop completely eco friendly natural dyed and Natural Agent finished Cotton Textile Fabrics (Oeko-Tech Products) by adopting a Newer Technique of Simultaneous Natural Mordanting–Natural Dyeing–Natural Finishing in a single step to reduce energy cost, process Time , Processing costs and Effluent Load (which has not been done earlier).
- To investigate the single step processes and also completely eco-Friendly Products of cotton textiles using selective natural dyes and natural finishing agents using bio mordants and bio finishing agents obtained from extract of natural resources at reduced cost and energy.
- To analyse methods for specific identification of natural dyes on natural dyed and finished textile products for establishing natural dye mark.
- To commercialize of such oeko-tech (eco friendly) products of natural dyed and finished cotton textile products.

Materials and Methods:

Application of Different Biomordanting with Biomordanting Agents:

Effects of different degrees of premordanting, simultaneous mordanting, post mordanting with lemon leaves as natural mordanting agents and natural dye ability with selective natural dyes (say a banana pill, neem leaves, tea leaves, teak leaves, guava leaves, Jackfruit wood, basil leaves, eucalyptus leaves, pecker leaves, peach leaves as well as as per availability natural sources etc.) can be investigated. Effect of such biomodifications on colour parameters after dyeing of cotton and chemically and biochemically modified cotton and its colour fastness properties to light, washing, perspiration and rubbing can be studied. The photo fading behaviour of cotton and chemically and biochemically modified and dyed cotton materials after those modifications and pre-treatments and subsequent dyeing can be studied and an attempt can be taken to improve the same to a much better level of customer acceptability. Effects of different degree of chemical modifications on colour yield for the selective natural dyes can be studied. Cotton Textile materials dyed with natural dyes can be post-treated/finished with suitable natural agents for studying the effect of these after treatments on the improvement of colour yield, brightness and colour fastness behaviour of the dyed material. To improve the colour fastness properties for the selective natural dyes some pre or post-treatment with cationic or metallic complex compound or UV absorbers/suitable modifiers can be studied.

Process Development:

The fabrics can be pre-treated by the eco-friendly enzyme-based chemical pre-treatment processes for preparing it for simultaneous dyeing and finishing. After that different natural dyes say a banana pill, neem leaves, tea leaves, teak leaf, guava leaves, neem leaves, Jackfruit wood, basil leaves, eucalyptus leaves, pecker leaves, peach leaves as well as as per availability natural sources etc.) and natural finishing agent like coconut oil as UV absorber, neem and guava leaf as antimicrobial agent as well as selective mordanting agents can be applied on cotton fabric for trailing and experimentations on application of dyes and finishing agent on cotton and optimization of dyeing process variables for improved colour development and improvement of colour fastness, all analytical testing. Effects of variations of dyeing process variables on colour yield and dyeing kinetics for application of selective natural dyes on cotton and chemically modified cotton substrate can be investigated to understand the dyeing isotherm, rate of dyeing and other thermodynamic parameters for such dyeing. This will help to understand the dyeing behaviours of different natural dyes applied on cotton to get an idea of formulating better colour yield having specific standardized dyeing recipe for combined/compound shades by use of binary or ternary mixture of these natural dyes. For use of combination of natural dyes for generating compound shades, a study on the compatibility of such binary and a ternary mixture of dyes can be also studied, to understand and find a compatible combination of such dyes for cotton and chemically treated and modified cotton fabrics.

Process of Textile Properties and Dyeability Analysis:

Changes in structural features for different degrees of mordanting on cotton substrate can be investigated with the help of Spectrophotometer, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), FTIR Spectroscopy and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), High-Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPLC), Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GCMS), Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC), Carbon, Hydrogen, Nitrogen and Sulphur (CHNS) analyzer and X-ray diffraction pattern etc. and different fastness properties for explaining the major observations in these aspects. This will help to understand scientifically the scientific analysis of different changes in textile related property behaviour and dyeability in terms of changes in structural features of chemically modified cotton substrate along with changes in surface characteristics and durability etc.

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Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

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Major activities to be undertaken as follows during the total project implementation period :

[Implemented By Md. Anowar Hossain, Principal Investigator (PI)]

	Experimental Work Phases	Research Lab
1.	Extraction of natural dyes from dyed cotton textiles and their identification.	Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University
2.	Study of extraction of different natural dyes in different media and study of the chemistry and colour characteristics of the colour component of selective natural dyes to establish standard method and optimum conditions of extracting those natural dyes from different sources	Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University
3.	Studies on dyeing process variables and effect of different mordanting agents / mordanting methods on colour yield and fastness behaviour.	Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University
4.	Studies on effect of different degree of chemical modifications of cotton textiles on colour yield behaviour of selective natural dyes as well as natural mordanting.	Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University Dyeing lab-Mascom Composite Ltd, Konabari.
5.	Studies on effect of different degree of colour fastness behaviour of selective natural dyes as well as natural mordanting.	Wet Processing lab-Bangladesh Jute Research Institute (BJRI), Textile Dyeing lab-Mascom Composite Ltd, Konabari.
6.	Studies on authentication of test methods of identification of natural dye from outside nation and International accredited laboratories and analysis of results.	FEAT lab, Indian Institute of Technology, IIT, Kanpur, India Textile Coloration Lab, Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India
7.	Experimental Work-Phase –XII: Patenting and Publication of technical mammals/ notes Publication and Popularisation of natural dye standards at National and International level with establishing natural dye/finish mark to be implemented worldwide of natural dyed textiles.	City University
8.	Field Trial	Production Unit, Mascom Composite Ltd, Konabari.

Expected Outcomes:

Feasibility of natural dyeing, natural mordanting, natural finishing will be studied to achieve an ecofriendly approach of zero toxic coloration of cotton fabric with natural dyes and natural mordanting agents which will be tested by different advanced analytical method of natural coloration.

Natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural finishing agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing can be established by developing completely eco-friendly natural dyes and natural finishing agent which can be applied on cotton textiles (Oeko-Tech Products) by adopting a newer technique of simultaneous Mordanting-Dyeing-Finishing in a single step to reduce energy cost, process time, processing costs and effluent load as well as to develop the single step processes and also completely eco-friendly products of cotton textiles using selective natural dyes and natural finishing agents using bio mordants and bio finishing agents obtained from an extract of natural resources at reduced cost and energy. There is huge scope of commercialization of such Oeko-Tech (Eco-Friendly) products of natural dyed and finished cotton textile products for domestic and export market.

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8

Budget:	
Project activities with breakdown of cost of 1,50,000 BDT	Total Cost in BDT
Raw materials, Extraction, processing and experimentation charges: [Sample Collection (Natural Dyes) charge (10 Sample×500 BDT = 5000 BDT), Dyes preparation, Drying and Powder forming charge (10 Sample ×500 BDT = 5000 BDT), Machine charge for extraction of dyes: 5000 BDT, Fabric cost for trialing: 5000 BDT, Fabric pretreatment charge: 1500 BDT, Machine charge for dyeing and finishing (Laboratory stage trialing): 13000 BDT, Field trial = 5800 BDT]	35,300 BDT
Testing fees [Spectrophotometer (10 sample × 2000 BDT =20000 BDT), SEM-(5 sample × 2000 BDT =10000 BDT), Light fastness-(5 sample × 1000 BDT=5000 BDT), Color Fastness-(5 sample × 1000 BDT =5000 BDT), Wash Fastness (5 sample × 1000 BDT =5000 BDT), Color Fastness to perspiration (5 sample × 1000 BDT =5000 BDT)]	50,000 BDT
Conveyance, Research Coordination and Research Meeting Conveyance and allowance (Day Long) [Office/ residence to Jahangirnagar University (5 Day long × 300 BDT =1500 BDT), Residence to Mascom Composite (5 Day long×300 BDT=1500 BDT),Residence to Bangladesh Jute Research Institute (3 Day long × 500 BDT = 1500 BDT, Residence to Science Lab 3 Day long × 500BDT = 1500 BDT, Residence to SGS (Testing Lab) 2 Day long × 500 BDT=1000 BDT)] Conveyance and allowance (Half Day) [Office, Khagan to Jahangirnagar University (20 Day × 100 BDT=2000 BDT), Office to Mascom Composite Ltd. (20 Day×200BDT=4000 BDT),Permanent Campus to City Campus ,City University (10 Day× 500 BDT =5000 BDT)] Preliminary meeting with experts (2 expert×1000 BDT=2000 BDT), Meeting in experimental stage with experts (2 expert × 1000 BDT = 2000 BDT), Report preparation and review meeting (2 expert × 1000 BDT = 2000 BDT)] Mobile bill for raw material purchasing, Lab coordination, expert coordination and other coordination (6 Month × 1000 BDT= 6000 BDT).	30,000 BDT
Stationary and Administrative cost [Sample tube, Scissor, Tape, Tissue, Soap, Mask, Hand gloves, Sample file, Sample Swatch Board ,Aprone, Stapler, Punch m/c, Calculator, Pendrive, Filter paper, PH Strip, Seal, Tracing Paper, Note Book and others: 3000 BDT, Review allowance and study materials (Book/Journal): 2000 BDT, Networking and computer support (6 month× 500 BDT= 3000 BDT), Casual Personal Assistant Fees (10 days×400 BDT=4000 BDT), Refreshment for Lab assistant /Lab technician (20 Person×60 BDT=1200 BDT), Research Office access /Casual Office Refreshment (15 weeks×200 BDT=3000 BDT).	16200BDT
Report writing, edition and submission process Report writing allowance: 3000 BDT, Computer Compose allowance: 5000 BDT, Graphical Design & Edition allowance: 2000 BDT, Report Edition allowance: (5 time × 1000 BDT =5000 BDT, Printing and Drafting: (5 time × 200 BDT =1000 BDT, 10 Copy Thesis Binding: (10 copy × 250 BDT = 2500 BDT)	18,500BDT
Total	1,50,000BDT
<p>[Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain will oversee the overall project and he will spend 20 hours/week as project investigator (additional duty of research and development), City University in different research laboratories like Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University, wet processing lab-Bangladesh Jute Research Institute, Textile Chemistry lab-City University, Dyeing lab-Mascom Composite Ltd, Konabari as well as others laboratory as per needs of proposed research.]</p> <p>[A subsidiary fund (20,000 BDT) for working with research graded foreign lab (natural coloration lab, Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India) may be included with proposed budget/replaced with some activities (if possible) although foreign visit has been banned in notification]</p> <p>[Breakdown of cost may be changed/replaced by the principal investigator as per suitability of research progression during practical implementation of proposed research work]</p>	
Six Months/Twenty Four Weeks Timeline to Complete the Research:	

Proposed By Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Principal Investigator

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Activities breakdown of twenty four weeks	1-2	3-4	5-6	6-7	8-9	10-11	12-13	14-16	17-24
[Activity:1] Raw materials Collections and feasibility analysis	█								
[Activity:2] Development of extraction process of natural dyes and specification testing		█							
[Activity:3] Development of Dyeing process of cotton fabric with different shades (5×2 =10 shades)			█						
[Activity:4] Development of Testing and Identification Methods for Natural Dyed Cotton					█				
[Activity:5] Field trialling for implementation of output of present research work					█				
[Activity:6] Report writing and submission, publications								█	

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

10

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জাহাঙ্গীরনগর বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়
 সাভার, ঢাকা।
২০১৮-২০১৯ শিক্ষাবর্ষে এম.ফিল ও পিএইচ.ডি গবেষণা কোর্সে ভর্তির বিজ্ঞপ্তি

সংশ্লিষ্ট সকলের অবগতি ও প্রয়োজনীয় ব্যবস্থা গ্রহণের জন্য কর্তৃপক্ষের অনুমোদনক্রমে জানানো যাচ্ছে যে, ২০১৮-২০১৯ শিক্ষাবর্ষে এম.ফিল ও পিএইচ.ডি গবেষণা কোর্সে ভর্তির কার্যক্রম সম্পাদনের জন্য ০২-১২-২০১৮ থেকে ১৫-০১-২০১৯ তারিখ পর্যন্ত (ছুটির দিন ব্যতীত) সকল কার্য দিবসে সকাল ৮.৩০ টা থেকে দুপুর ৩.০০ টা পর্যন্ত বিভাগে প্রাপ্তব্য ভর্তি ফরম পূরণ করত: তত্ত্বাবধায়ক ও বিভাগীয় সভাপতির মাধ্যমে উচ্চশিক্ষা ও বৃত্তি শাখায় নিম্নলিখিত কাগজপত্রসহ জমা দিতে হবে:

- সকল পর্যায়ে পরীক্ষার সত্যায়িত মার্কশীট ও সার্টিফিকেট। সকল মার্কশীট ও সার্টিফিকেটের মূল কপি যাচাইয়ের জন্য সঙ্গে আনতে হবে।
- গবেষক ও তত্ত্বাবধায়ক কর্তৃক স্বাক্ষরিত দুই সেট গবেষণা প্রস্তাব/সিনপসিস (A4 সাইজ কাগজে)।
- খণ্ডকালীন গবেষক চাকরিরত হলে সংশ্লিষ্ট প্রতিষ্ঠানের নিয়োগকর্তার অনুমতিপত্র এবং পূর্ণকালীন গবেষক চাকরিরত হলে সংশ্লিষ্ট প্রতিষ্ঠানের ছুটির কাগজ জমা দিতে হবে।
- সদ্য তোলা পাসপোর্ট আকারের ৩ কপি রঙীন ছবি।
- অন্য বিশ্ববিদ্যালয় থেকে পাশ করা প্রার্থীদের ক্ষেত্রে ঐ বিশ্ববিদ্যালয় থেকে সংগৃহীত মাইগ্রেশন সনদের মূল কপি জমা দিতে হবে।
- ভর্তি বিজ্ঞপ্তি ও ভর্তি ফরমে উল্লেখিত অন্য সকল প্রয়োজনীয় কাগজপত্র।

বি:দ্রঃ (ক) উচ্চশিক্ষা ও বৃত্তি শাখা থেকে ভর্তি ফিস জমা দেয়ার অনুমতিপত্র সংগ্রহ করে অগ্রণী ব্যাংক লিমিটেড, জাহাঙ্গীরনগর বিশ্ববিদ্যালয় শাখায় নগদ পিএইচ.ডি কোর্সে ভর্তির জন্য ২৯,৬০০/- (উনত্রিশ হাজার ছয়শত) টাকা এবং এম.ফিল কোর্সে ভর্তির জন্য ২২,১০০/- (বাইশ হাজার একশত) (ভর্তি ফি এর বিবরণপত্র সংযুক্ত) জমা দান ও জমার রশিদ উচ্চশিক্ষা ও বৃত্তি শাখায় দাখিল করে নির্ধারিত সময়ের মধ্যে ভর্তির কাজ সম্পাদন করতে হবে।

কলা ও মানবিকী অনুসদ (এম.ফিল)

ক্রমিক নং	গবেষকের নাম	বিভাগ	তত্ত্বাবধায়কের নাম ও গবেষণার শিরোনাম	গবেষণা সময়কাল
১.	জনাব সাদিয়া আফরোজ ফ্ল্যাট # ডি-৪, বাড়ি # ১৮, রোড # ৪, ধানমন্ডি, ঢাকা। মোবাইল: ০১৭১১৮৫০০১২	ইংরেজি	প্রফেসর আহমেদ রেজা, ইংরেজি বিভাগ, জাবি। Radical Feminist elements in Rokeya's Sultana's Dream and Woolf's A Room of One's Own: A Comparative Study	খণ্ডকালীন
২.	জনাব আরিফ মঈন উদ্দিন খান প্রযুক্ত: তানিজা জাহান, প্রমোশন অফিসার, বিসিক ভবন(২য় তলা), আছাবাদ, চট্টগ্রাম মোবাইল # ০১৮১৯-১৪ ৭৩৬৬	ইংরেজি	প্রফেসর ড. মো. মনিরুজ্জামান, ইংরেজি বিভাগ, জাবি। Postcolonial Insights into the Partition of India as Reflected in Indian Novels in English	খণ্ডকালীন
৩.	জনাব সফাত উল্লাহ হীড ইন্টারন্যাশনাল স্কুল, প্লট-১৯, ব্লক-এ, সেকশন-১১, মিরপুর, ঢাকা-১২১৬। মোবাইল # ০১৭৪২-২০৫২৩০	ইংরেজি	প্রফেসর ড. মো. মনিরুজ্জামান, ইংরেজি বিভাগ, জাবি। The Use of Technology in English Language Learning at the Tertiary Level: Problems and Probable Solutions	খণ্ডকালীন
৪.	জনাব আয়েশা খাতুন বাড়ি নং ১০৭৮, রোড-৬, মিরপুর, ডিওএইচএম মোব: ০১৭৫২-৭৯০৬৬২	ইংরেজি	প্রফেসর ড. মো. মনিরুজ্জামান, ইংরেজি বিভাগ, জাবি। English Language Education at the SSC Level: Examining the Teaching Methodology	খণ্ডকালীন
৫.	জনাব সামিয়া বিনতে হাই ১৫, মধ্যপাইকপাড়, মিরপুর-১ ঢাকা-১২১৬। মোবাইল # ০১৯৯৭-১৬৬১৯৯	ইংরেজি	প্রফেসর ড. মো. মনিরুজ্জামান, ইংরেজি বিভাগ, জাবি। Challenges of Using Technology in English Language Education in the Polytechnic Institutes	পূর্ণকালীন
৬.	জনাব আবদুল কাইয়ুম দক্ষিণ বেতিয়ারা, বিজয় করা, চৌদ্দগ্রাম, কুমিল্লা।	ইংরেজি	প্রফেসর ড. মো. মনিরুজ্জামান, ইংরেজি বিভাগ, জাবি। Teaching English Grammar at the Secondary Level: Learner Perceptions and Teacher Actions.	খণ্ডকালীন

১৬.	মোঃ আনোয়ার হোসেন টেবুটাইল ইঞ্জিনিয়ারিং বিভাগ সিটি বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়, সাভার, ঢাকা। মোবাইল # ০১৭৩২৬৮১১০৪ engr.anowar@yahoo.com	রসায়ন	প্রফেসর ড. মোঃ নূরুল আবিছার, রসায়ন বিভাগ, জাবি Simultaneous dyeing and finishing with natural dyes and natural finishing agents on cotton textiles	খণ্ডকালীন
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Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD
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কর্তৃক লেখিত নং-ক
অথনী ব্যাংক লিমিটেড
জাহাঙ্গীরনগর বিশ্ববিদ্যালয় শাখা, ঢাকা।
ফোন: গোদোয়ার পয়েন্ট
বিভাগ: বৃন্দাম্বর পৌ. পি. ড. ... গোল নং. ৪৩
বক. গা. ক. কাক্সালটেশীন. জটিলত শিকারব. ২০১৫-১৯

১। ছাত্র সেরজন..... হতে..... পর্যন্ত।
২। বন সীট অভা.....
৩। জর্ড/পুনঃ জর্ড ফিস.....
৪। বিলম্ব জর্ড ফিস.....
৫। হস্তগার/পেরেননা জমানতে.....
৬। ছাত্র সেরজন টালা.....
৭। কীড়া টালা.....
৮। বন ছাত্র সেরজন.....
৯। বন ছাত্র কীড়া ফি.....
১০। কমানক্রম ফি.....
১১। সেন্সন চার্জ.....
১২। ছাত্র রক্যাগ তর্কবিল.....
১৩। রেজিষ্টেশন ফি.....
১৪। বন জমানতের টালা.....
১৫। বাসনপত্র ফি.....
১৬। পরিসংখ্যান কটিনজেক্সী.....
১৭। সাময়িক পত্র/স্বাস্থ্য পরীক্ষা ফি.....
১৮। গোত্র কট্ট/পরিচয় পত্র ফি.....
১৯। পরিষ্কার ফি.....
২০। অন্যান্য/জরিমানা.....
২১। অনটন ফি.....

১৯,৬০০/-

১০ DEC 2018

অর্থ/ছাত্রের স্বাক্ষর
তারিখ: ১৫/১২/১৫

কর্তৃক লেখিত নং-ক
অথনী ব্যাংক লিমিটেড
জাহাঙ্গীরনগর বিশ্ববিদ্যালয় শাখা, ঢাকা।
ফোন: গোদোয়ার পয়েন্ট
বিভাগ: বৃন্দাম্বর পৌ. পি. ড. ... গোল নং. ৪৩
বক. গা. ক. কাক্সালটেশীন. জটিলত শিকারব. ২০১৫-১৯

১। ছাত্র সেরজন..... হতে..... পর্যন্ত।
২। বন সীট অভা.....
৩। জর্ড/পুনঃ জর্ড ফিস.....
৪। বিলম্ব জর্ড ফিস.....
৫। হস্তগার/পেরেননা জমানতে.....
৬। ছাত্র সেরজন টালা.....
৭। কীড়া টালা.....
৮। বন ছাত্র সেরজন.....
৯। বন ছাত্র কীড়া ফি.....
১০। কমানক্রম ফি.....
১১। সেন্সন চার্জ.....
১২। ছাত্র রক্যাগ তর্কবিল.....
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১৯। পরিষ্কার ফি.....
২০। অন্যান্য/জরিমানা.....
২১। অনটন ফি.....

২১,৫০০/-

২ NOV 2018

অর্থ/ছাত্রের স্বাক্ষর
তারিখ: ১১-১১-২০১৯

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY

JAHANGIRNAGAR UNIVERSITY

Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh

Tel. (PABX) : (880-2) 7791045-51, Ext. 1437 (Office), Fax : 880-2-7791052

E-mail : chem_ju@yahoo.com

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, M.Tech. is a Ph.D researcher in textile chemistry at Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University entitled on "Simultaneous Dyeing and Finishing with Natural Dyes and Natural Finishing Agents on Cotton Textiles" under my supervision. His Ph.D Registration no: 3010 and Roll no: 41. During his work in my lab, Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain demonstrated an innovative performance in his research field.

I wish him success in his life

(Professor Dr. Md. Nurul Abser)
Chairman
Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka.

Chairman
Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University
Savar, Dhaka-1342

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

26 Evidence of peer review and publication process of PhD¹ thesis on “simultaneous dyeing and finishing with natural dyes and natural finishing agents on cotton textiles” at University of Calcutta, India.

Fwd: Modified PDF of an article: LTTFD-RA-18-132

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta
To: me, and 1 other · Sat, Apr 11, 2020 at 2:13 PM

Message Body

Sent from [Outlook Mobile](#)

From: Textile and Fashion Designing: LTTFD <fashion@lupinepublishers.us>
Sent: Tuesday, May 22, 2018 6:28:32 PM
To: ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>
Cc: engr.anowar@yahoo.com <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>
Subject: Modified PDF of an article: LTTFD-RA-18-132

Dear Dr. Ashis kumar Samanta,

Thank you for your mail.

As per your mail changes have been made and done and uploaded in our journal website.

Please find the attachment of **PDF**.

Hope to receive more informative articles from you.

Await your positive response.

Have a great day!!

Regards,
Jennifer Nicole

From: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta [mailto:ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com]
Sent: 21 May 2018 13:35
To: Textile and Fashion Designing: LTTFD
Cc: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta; Anwar Hoasian for M Tech Admission
Subject: Re: Returning Proof Check of PDF of an article: LTTFD-RA-18-132

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Jennifer Nicole

Editorial Coordinator .

Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing (LTTFD)

Hope everything is good at your end.

We are happy to inform you that we have Checked the **galley proof** and **PDF** of your article ID: **LTTFD-RA-18-132** entitled “**Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent**” for publication in our **Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing (LTTFD)**. It is **Ok** except in table no **Table @** and **Table 4** , where **following corrections are needed** .

1. Table 2: Row No. 2 - Light Fastness , instead of 1.5 it will be 1-2
2. Table 2 : Row No. 3 - Rubbing Fastness Dry , instead of 4.5 it will be 4-5
3. Table 4 : Row No. 2 - Light fastness, instead of 2.5 it will be 2-3

Rest of the matter is all o.k. So with the above said correction you can go for final publishing this paper at free of cost publication in your journal. Please send us one e-print of the paper with DOI, Page No. and Vol. Number of the Journal.
 Thanks,

From: Textile and Fashion Designing: LTTFD <fashion@lupinepublishers.us>

Sent: Thursday, May 10, 2018 7:20 PM

To: ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

Subject: PDF of an article: LTTFD-RA-18-132

Dear Dr. Ashis kumar Samanta,

Hope everything is good at your end.

We are happy to inform you that we are done with the **galley proof** and **PDF** of your article ID: **LTTFD-RA-18-132** entitled “**Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent**” for publication in our **Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing (LTTFD)**.

Please find the attachment of **PDF** and let us know if any further modifications that you are willing us to do.

As per our previous conversation we are providing you **complete waiver** towards publication of your manuscript ref no: **LTTFD-RA-18-132**.

Hope to receive more **informative** articles soon.

Page | 116

Have a great day!!

Regards,
Jennifer Nicole

Fw: Complete waiver : LTTFD-RA-18-132

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta
To: me · Mon, May 7, 2018 at 8:05 PM

Message Body

Dear Anowar ,

See the below mail taht they have agreed to publish it free of charge by complete waiver, if the paper is acceted and proof will come. Wait for that.

Thank you ,
Prof A K Samanta

From: Textile and Fashion Designing <fashion@lupinepublishers.us>

Sent: Monday, May 7, 2018 6:51 PM

To: ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

Subject: Complete waiver : LTTFD-RA-18-132

Dear Dr. Ashis kumar Samanta,

Thank you for your prompt reply,

We can **completely understand your prospective**, As per your email I had personally discussed with our **Editor in chief** regarding the contribution for publication of your manuscripts.

I had convinced them and finally they agreed to provide **Complete waiver** for **article id: LTTFD-RA-18-132**.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

We will get back to you with the timely updates.

Await to hear your positive reply.

Have a nice day!!

Regards,

Jennifer Nicole

From: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta [mailto:ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com]

Sent: 03 May 2018 20:33

To: Textile and Fashion Designing

Cc: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta

Subject: Re: Manuscript ID: LTTFD-RA-18-132

Jennifer Nicole

EDitorial Coordinator

Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing (LTTFD).

Dear Jenifer ,

You are aware that our university does not allow any sort of payment for publishing any paper in any journal and hence I am unable to pay you single dollar or even

\$50 asked by you as processing or uploading charges for this article id: LTTFD-RA-18-

132 submitted as a substituted article no LTTFD-RA-18-124 , which eventually was

stopped /withdrawn and hided on my request for publication in your journal for some

technical reason you know and explained to you earlier , which was earlier received full

and complete waiver of any sorts of publication charges, which by rules of our

University , we can not pay .

So like previous consideration , I hope you will again consider to publish this

article LTTFD-RA-18-132 submitted as a substituted article against withdrawal of LTTFD-

RA-18-124 and will publish it completely free of cost , without charging even single

dollar or USD 50 (we can not pay it by rule of our university).

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

Hoping your kind consideration please for complete waiver of all sorts of charges , as I am helpless to pay any single dollar for this as per our University rule.

with regrads

Prof Ashis Kumar Samanta

If you'd like to unsubscribe and stop receiving these emails [click here](#).

Fw: Manuscript ID: LTTFD-RA-18-132

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: me, Cc: Prof. · Thu, May 3, 2018 at 9:09 PM

Message Body

Dear Anowar ,

Pls Find Acknowledgement of receipt of your 2nd paper by journal office with new MS no for Reference as follows:

Title : Green Dyeing on Cotton Fabric demodulated from Diospyros malabarica and Camellia sinensis with green mordanting agent

Manuscript ID: LTTFD-RA-18-132.

As a Editorial In Charge Member of this Journal , They have given due weightage of my membership and given waiver of main publication charges , but has asked for payment of only USD 50 as Processing and Uploading charges to publish this after acceptance.

I have further written them to make it complete waiver . let us see . Hope they will consider . Let the paper be reviewed and accepted first . Ok.

Thanks

Prof A K Samanta

From: Textile and Fashion Designing <fashion@lupinepublishers.us>

Sent: Thursday, May 3, 2018 7:02 PM

To: ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

Subject: Manuscript ID: LTTFD-RA-18-132

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Dear Dr. Ashis kumar Samanta,

Thank you for your prompt submission!!

Your article entitled “**Green Dyeing on Cotton Fabric demodulated from Diospyros malabarica and Camellia sinensis with green mordanting agent**” is quite interesting.

We are very glad to receive your valuable **Research Article** at our request towards our **Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing (LTTFD)**.

Please use the below Manuscript ID for further communication.

Manuscript ID: **LTTFD-RA-18-132**.

So we are pleased to inform you that we had discussion with our **Editorial In charge member**, and are glad to notify you we are ready to provide you **complete waiver** and request you to pay **\$50** for this article id: **LTTFD-RA-18-132**.

We will let you know the article updates timely.

Hope this is fine with you and await your rapid and positive response.

Have a Great day ahead!!

Regards,

Jennifer Nicole

From: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta [mailto:ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com]

Sent: 02 May 2018 23:06

To: Textile and Fashion Designing

Subject: Fw: Submitting another substituted new manuscript now For Free Of Cost publication with Full waiver instead of withdrwan paper of us from publication of our earlier article ID: LTTFD-RW-18-124 on our request in your journal

Subject: Sub: Submitting another substituted new manuscript now For Free Of Cost publication with Full waiver instead of withdrwan paper of us from publication of our earlier article ID: LTTFD-RW-18-124 on our request in your journal

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

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To: me · Thu, May 3, 2018 at 9:11 PM

Message Body

Dear Anowar,

Page | 120

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Thank you

Prof A K Samanta

From: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>

Sent: Thursday, May 3, 2018 8:32 PM

To: Textile and Fashion Designing

Cc: ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

Subject: Re: Manuscript ID: LTTFD-RA-18-132

Jennifer Nicole

EDitorial Coordinator

Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing (LTTFD).

Dear Jenifer ,

You are aware that our university does not allow any sort of payment for publishing any paper in any journal and hence I am unable to pay you sigle dollar or even

\$50 asked by you as processing or uploading charges for this article id: **LTTFD-RA-18-132 submitted as a substituted article**

no LTTFD-RA-18-124 , which eventually was stopped

/withdrawn and hided on my request for publication in your journal for some technical reason you know and explained to

you earlier , which was earlier received full and complete

waiver of any sorts of publication charges, which by rules of

our University , we can not pay .

So like previous consideration , I hope you will again consider to publish this article LTTFD-RA-18-132 submitted as a

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substituted article against withdrawal of LTTFD-RA-18-124 and will publish it completely free of cost , without charging even single dollar or USD 50 (we can not pay it by rule of our university).

Hoping your kind consideration please for complete waiver of all sorts of charges , as I am helpless to pay any single dollar for this as per our University rule.

with regrads
Prof Ashis Kumar Samanta

Fwd: Full Text of Article published on line - click link in below mail for full text

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: me, and 11 others · Mon, Aug 13, 2018 at 9:36 PM

Message Body

Sent from my Samsung Galaxy smartphone.

----- Original message -----

From: "Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing (LTTFD)"

<jennifernicole@lupineonline.us>

Date: 8/13/18 6:58 PM (GMT+05:30)

To: ijtaxsamanta@hotmail.com

Subject: Full Text of Article

Dear Dr. Ashis kumar Samanta,

Greetings from “**Lupine Publishers**”

We are very glad to inform you that we are done with the Full text of your article ID: **LTTFD-RA-18-132** entitled “**Green Dyeing on Cotton Fabric demodulated from Diospyros malabarica and Camellia sinensis with green mordanting agent**”.

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

And, we hope you will continue the same support in future too in the aspect of submitting your most precious manuscripts for publication in our **LTTFD**.

Await your positive reply.

Regards,
Jennifer Nicole

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To: me, Cc: me · Tue, Jul 16, 2019 at 7:56 PM

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Manuscript Details:

» Reference number: **2019-IJTSC-126**

» Journal Title: **International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering**

» Manuscript Title: **A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concept for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre**

» Corresponding Author: **Anowar Hossain**

Dear Dr. Anowar Hossain,

Greetings from Gavin Publishers!

Please find the attached galley proof (final PDF) and QC proof (word document) along with the invoice for your manuscript.

Check the proof carefully and return within 2-3 days. Please arrange to make the payment within one week.

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On behalf of **International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering**.

With best regards for your on-going research.

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International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering

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To: contact · Wed, Jul 17, 2019 at 10:45 AM

Message Body

Laura Anderson | Editorial Manager
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Laura

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To: Prof. · Fri, Aug 9, 2019 at 9:27 PM

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta, <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>

Message Body

Dear Respected Sir,

Please note that attached paper entitled "A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concept for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre." has been conditionally accepted (USD 60).

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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Thanks

Md. Anowar Hossain

PLs send me the e copy of our Published paper IJTSE-2018-113 and weblink of that volume and issue of your IJTSE JOURNAL which includes our published paper 2018- IJTSE-113 .

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: contact@gavinpublishers.org, and 1 other, Cc: me, and 2 others · Mon, Nov 19, 2018 at 3:10 PM

To:

- <contact@gavinpublishers.org>
- <editor@textileengineering.org>

Cc:

- Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta,<ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>
- Anwar Hoasian for M Tech Admission,<engr.anowar@yahoo.com>
- Ashis Kumar Samanta Email of Prof AKS for ISDS project,<ijtaksamanta@gmail.com >

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Lucy Chartera , Editorial coordinator ,IJTSE
 and
 Laura Anderson | Editorial Head, IJTSE
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Dear Sir/Madam,

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Please send me the e copy of our Published paper IJTSE-2018-113 and weblink of that volume and issue of your IJTSE JOURNAL which includes our published paper 2018-IJTSE-113 .

pls reply immediately to me . Pls send the e copy of the above said e paper to my e mail ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com.

Page | 126

Thanks in anticipation and expecting your quick response .

With regards .

Prof A K Samanta
Professor , DJFT, IJT Calcutta university
and Member of Editorial Board , IJTSE , Gavin publishers

- ASHISKUMAR SAMANTA

To: me, and 3 others · Mon, Nov 19, 2018 at 3:11 PM

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To:

- <contact@gavinpublishers.org>,
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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

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Laura Anderson | Editorial Head, IJTSE
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1. Page - 7 under testing method, 1st stanza: (K/S value) can bedetermined, should be in the same line (the line has been broken) and the formula of K/S should be as follows (square is missing with (1- R_{λmax}) which should be (1- R_{λmax})² and this should be aligned properly in the same line as follows :-

$$K/S_{\lambda_{max}} = \frac{(1 - R_{\lambda_{max}})^2}{\alpha} = \alpha C_D$$

2R_{λmax}

2. The Captions of each of the Tables 1 to 4 should be placed on the top of the each of the Table instead of below. Please do this correction.

Page | 138

3. Table - 2, 3 and 4 are spread over consecutive two pages, which should rather be each table to place in one page (not spreading and breaking over two pages). Please do this correction.

4. Page -12 in reference, Ref. No. 5 is unnecessary bold. Kindly un-bold it.

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Accordingly you finally informed me by mail to give complete waiver and to publish it free of charge . Probably your production dept do not know this . Pls instruct them to note complete waiver for publication charge for this paper and publish it with full free of cost .

Pls confirm me by mail again from prodiction dept on free of cpst publication of this paper and then only I shall send proof check report.

Thanking you
Prof a k samanta

From: editor@textileengineering.org <editor@textileengineering.org>
Sent: Tuesday, M May 8, 2018 6:13 PM ay 8, 2018 6:13 PM
To: 'Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta'
Subject: RE: We have started the review process soon we will update you the status of the article

Dear Prof Ashis Kumar Samanta,

Warm greetings!

Thank you for your valuable response.

As you are an editorial board member our organization has decide to give you complete waiver.

We have started the review process soon we will update you the status of the article.

Kindly suggest your colleagues, friends and research scholars for our journal development.

We will provide them huge discount of behalf of you we charge only 250USD per manuscript.

Thank you.

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Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

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VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Regards

Lucy

From: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta [<mailto:ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>]

Sent: Tuesday, May 8, 2018 3:20 PM

To: editor@textileengineering.org

Subject: Re: Waiting for your quick response

**Lucy Charter,
Editorial Coordinator
International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering**

Dear Lucy,

Thank you for your quick response and acknowledgement. Please give us a M.S. No. for this article for future reference.

We will wait for the review process for this article. However, please note that as per our University Rules we are not allowed to pay any single dollar or rupee as any other charges for Pdf and uploading etc. and need full and complete waiver of all the charges related to publication of any paper of us to any journal from this University of Calcutta. Hence, I am sorry and I can't pay any charges for it.

You are perhaps aware that our university does not allow any sort of payment for publishing any paper in any journal and hence I am unable to pay you single dollar or even as processing or uploading charges for this article submitted to you for its publication in your journal, to be published with full and complete waiver of any sorts of publication charges, which by rules of our University, we can not pay. Pls understand our perspective and kindly Waive the publication charges. No way we can pay any charges and not even a single dollar or Rupee.

So I hope you will consider our case specially to publish this article being submitted now to you on your request at Free of cost without charging any publication charges and will publish it completely free of cost, without charging even single dollar (which we can not pay it by rule of our university).

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

Hoping your kind consideration please for complete waiver of all sorts of charges , as I am helpless to pay any single dollar for this as per our University rule for considering publication of this paper in your journal. .

With regards,
(Prof. A K Samanta)
Professor

Page | 144

From: editor@textileengineering.org <editor@textileengineering.org>
Sent: Tuesday, May 8, 2018 2:08 PM
To: 'Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta'
Subject: RE: Waiting for your quick response

Dear Prof Ashis Kumar Samanta,

Warm greetings!

Thank you for your valuable submission.

We have received your valuable will soon start the review process.

As you are an eminent author and playing an vital role as our editorial board member we are providing complete wavier for your manuscript.

But kindly pay 149 USD for PDF and HTML charges.

Waiting for your quick response.

Thank you.

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Lucy Charter

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- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta
To: me, Cc: Prof. · Tue, May 8, 2018 at 1:10 PM

Message Body

Dear Anowar ,

Pls Find the copy of mail for submitting your third paper to Intl Journal of Textile Sc and Engg for Publication on line , for manuscript entitled "**Eco Friendly Colouration and antimicrobial Finishing of Cotton Fabric using Distilled extract of Tectona-Grandis (Teak Leaf) and Azardirachta-Indica (Neem Leaf) with different Ecofriendly/Natural Mordants as compared to Conventional used Copper Sulphate mordant.**" authored

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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020; Room: 512.01.12.25; School of

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VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

by Md. Anowar Hossain^{1*}, Ashis Kumar Samanta^{2#}, Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik²,
Padma S Vankar³ & Dhara Shukla³ with following affiliation of them :

¹Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh
and earlier M Tech Student of Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of
Calcutta, Kolkata-700019

²Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata-700019,
India

³IIT-Kanpur Campus, Kanpur-208016, Uttarpradesh, India, as per the sent mail to
journal office to Mr Lucy Carter, Editorial Coordinator of this journal.

Let us wait and see about their Review process and consideration of free of
cost publication charges etc. and receiving of MS no for future correspondence with
them.

I hope, You are satisfied now, as we have submitted three publication in rapid fire
time on urgent basis keeping beside all work, inspite of busy schedule.

Thanking you

Prof A K Samanta

From: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta [<mailto:ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>]

Sent: Tuesday, May 8, 2018 12:33 PM

To: editor@textileengineering.org

Subject: Re: Sunbmitting and sending herewith one of our ready manuscript (two files in both word file and Pdf file for same paper) for Publication free of Cost in Your Journal - Intl Journal of Textile Science and Engg. for Upcoming Issue

Lucy Charter

Editorial Coordinator

International Journal of Textile Science & Engineering

Sub : Sunbmitting and sending herewith one of our ready manuscript (two files in both word file and Pdf file for same paper) for its Publication free of Cost in Your Journal - Intl Journal of Textile Science and Engg. for Upcoming Issue

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As Per Your Request in trailing mail , I am now sunbmitting and sending herewith one of our ready manuscript **for Publication free of Cost in Your Journal** - Intl Journal of Textile Science and Engg. submitting and attaching two files both in WORD file and PDF file for Manuscript entitled **"Eco Friendly Colouration and antimicrobial Finishing of Cotton Fabric using Distilled extract of Tectona-Grandis (Teak Leaf) and Azardirachta-Indica (Neem Leaf) with different Ecofriendly/Natural Mordants as compared to Conventional used Copper Sulphate mordant."** authored by **My Ex M Tech and current part time PhD enrolled student Md. Anowar Hossain*** presently working at Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh and myself Prof Ashis Kumar Samanta , Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India and DR Padma S Vankar , FEAT,IIT-Kanpur, Kanpur, Uttarpradesh , India as well as Our Reserch fellow Shri Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik working under me & DR Dhara Shukla working under Dr P S Vankar . i.e Sequentially the authors are **Md. Anowar Hossain^{1*}, Ashis Kumar Samanta^{2#} , Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik ², Padma S Vankar³ & Dhara Shukla³** and their affiliations are as follows :

¹Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh and earlier M Tech Student of Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata-700019

²Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata-700019, India

³IIT-Kanpur Campus , Kanpur-208016, Uttarpradesh , India

Please note that as per PhD rules of our University the name of My PhD student Md Anowar Hossain should appear as first and correpondence author , required for his phd Thesis document to university, while Md Anowar Hossain have Email address as : engr.anowar@yahoo.com (A. Hossain) and his name should be shown as first and corresponding author , though I shall do all correspondence my name will appear as 2nd corresponding or Executive Corresponding Author having my e mail : ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com (A. K. Samanta) , where I shall do all correspondence with you regarding this paper .

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Pls Acknowledge and Give Us Manuscript Submission No for future correspondence and send us its acceptance and PDF proof in due time as per your convenience .

With regards
Prof Ashis Kumar Samanta
Department of Jute and Fibre Technology,
Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta,
35 < Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata,-700 019
West Bengal , India
Email : ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

From: editor@textileengineering.org <editor@textileengineering.org>
Sent: Saturday, May 5, 2018 4:40 PM

To: ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

Subject: Submit Article for Upcoming Issue

Dear Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta,
Greetings from the Journal of International Journal of Textile Science & Engineering!!!

Page | 148

Hope you and your research work was well.

I would like to express my sincere gratitude for being so supportive towards the development of the journal in a very short time and would be more than glad to acknowledge your sincere efforts in making this Journal of international repute in Open Access Publication era.

I would really appreciate if you could send your valuable submissions (editorial/Short communication/Review/Research etc.) for publication in the upcoming issue.

We are Planning to release our upcoming issue by this month kindly, support us with your valuable work your articles add more value to our upcoming issue.

Can we know the feasible time for your submission so, that we can extend our upcoming issue date for eminent people like you?

I'd be more than happy to hear from you in this context.

Looking forward to work with you.

Thank you.

Regards,
Lucy Charter
Editorial Coordinator
International Journal of Textile Science & Engineering

Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: contact@gavinpublishers.org, and 1 other, Cc: me, and 1 other · Tue, Oct 9, 2018 at 7:07 PM

Message Body

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

----- Original message -----

From: "Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta" <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>

Date: 10/8/18 11:57 PM (GMT+05:30)

To: Gavin Publishers <contact@gavinpublishers.org>, editor@textileengineering.org

Cc: Anwar Hoasian for M Tech Admission <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>, "Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta" <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>

Subject: RE: Please send me the e copy of our Published paper IJTSE-2018-113 and weblink of that volume and issue of your IJTSE JOURNA which includes our published paper 2018- IJTSE-113 .

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Laura Anderson | Editorial Head, IJTSE
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Email: contact@gavinpublishers.org
Website: <http://gavinpublishers.com/>
editor@textileengineering.org

Sub: Please send me the e copy of our Published paper IJTSE-2018-113 and weblink of that volume and issue of your IJTSE JOURNA which includes our published paper 2018- IJTSE-113 .

Dear Madam Lucy and Laura Anderson,

I am sure by this time our paper **M.S. No. 2018- IJTSE 113** has been published on line free of cost with complete and full waiver of any publication or uploading charges as confirmed by mail below to me by both you (Laura Anderson and also from Lucy charter)

So may I request you to Please send me the e copy of our Published paper IJTSE-2018-113 and weblink of that volume and issue of your IJTSE JOURNA which includes our published paper 2018- IJTSE-113 .

Thanks in anticipation and expecting your quick response .

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

With regards .

Prof A K Samanta

Professor , DJFT, IJT Calcutta university

and Member of Editorial Board , IJTSE , Gavin publishers

RE: We have started the review process soon we will update you the status of the article

E

editor@textileengineering.org

Reply |

Tue 5/8, 6:13 PM

You

This message was sent with high importance.

You forwarded this message on 5/8/2018 6:26 PM

Dear Prof Ashis Kumar Samanta,

Warm greetings!

Thank you for your valuable response.

As you are an editorial board member our organization has decide to give you complete waiver.

We have started the review process soon we will update you the status of the article.

Kindly suggest your colleagues, friends and research scholars for our journal development.

We will provide them huge discount of behalf of you we charge only 250USD per manuscript.

Thank you.

Regards

Lucy

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: Gavin, and 1 other, Cc: me, and 1 other · Wed, Oct 10, 2018 at 10:54 PM

Message Body

RE: We have started the review process soon we will update you the status of the article

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Re: Please resolve the payment issue and publish our paper and send the e copy and weblink of that volume and issue of your IJTSE JOURNAL for our published paper 2018- IJTSE-113 .

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: editor@textileengineering.org, and 1 other, Cc: me, and 1 other · Mon, Oct 1, 2018 at 4:02 PM

Message Body

Lucy Charter , Editorial coordinator ,IJTSE

and

Laura Anderson | Editorial Head, IJTSE
Gavin International Conferences and Publishers Inc.,
5911 Oka Ridge Way
Lisle IL 60532 USA

Email: contact@gavinpublishers.org

Website: <http://gavinpublishers.com/>
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Please find the below our earlier mail for both to you and Lucy Charter, reminding you and Lucy also that Lucy confirmed and committed me by mail on 30th May again that as a editorial board member your board has considered to publish my paper **M.S. No. 2018- IJTSE 113 at free of cost with complete waiver of any publication charges (not even charges for uploading or any other else), as our University do not allow any sorts of publication charge for any paper.**

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So, please confirm me that you are still committed to keep your decision of your Board (as informed to me by Lucy Charter of your Journal Office by mail to me which is available in the trailing mail below your mail sending Invoice and Galley Proof, send by Lucy Charter on 8th May 2018 regarding this paper and further confirmed me on 30th may 2018 as per below mail). So, no question of invoice or sending payment arises and it is not permitted at all by our University. Pls you talk with lucy and confirm me .

Page | 152

Therefore, you confirm me publication of this paper M.S. No. 2018- IJTSE 113 immediately at free of cost with complete waiver of any publication charges and send me the e copy and weblink of the journal for downloading our published copy of this paper.

I am very much annoyed on your lack of coordination on this matter and you have kept this paper unpublished for such a long time unnecessarily. Pls do the needful and confirm me ,.

Please respond immediately from both of you so, that I understand that this misunderstanding on payment related issue has been resolved once for all and publish our above referred paper free of any cost and send me the e-copy of the paper and weblink of the journal issue including our published paper.

Thanks in anticipation

Prof A K Samanta
Professor , DJFT, IJT Calcutta university
and Member of Editorial Board , IJTSE , Gavin publishers

RE: We have started the review process soon we will update you the status of the article

E
editor@textileengineering.org

- Gavin Publishers
To: Prof., and 1 other, Cc: me · Mon, Oct 1, 2018 at 4:28 PM
Message Body
Dear Samanta,

Thank you for your mail.

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Thank you.

Regards,

Laura

Show trimmed content

- Gavin Publishers

To: Prof., and 1 other, Cc: me · Wed, Oct 3, 2018 at 5:31 PM

Message Body

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To: Prof., and 1 other, Cc: me · Wed, Oct 10, 2018 at 7:47 PM

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E

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- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: editor@textileengineering.org, Cc: me, and 1 other · Wed, Oct 3, 2018 at
5:54 PM

Message Body

Dear Laura Anderson and Lucy Charter ,

Noted and Thanks for everything .

Prof A K Samanta

DJFt, IJT University of Calcutta

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

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From: editor@textileengineering.org <editor@textileengineering.org>
Sent: Tuesday, October 2, 2018 1:35 PM
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Page | 154

Dear Dr. Samanta,

Thank you for your mail.

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Thank you.

Regards,
Lucy

From: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta [mailto:ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com]
Sent: Monday, October 1, 2018 3:32 PM
To: editor@textileengineering.org; contact@gavinpublishers.org
Cc: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>; Anwar Hoasian for M Tech Admission < engr.anowar@yahoo.com >
Subject: Re: Please resolve the payment issue and publish our paper and send the e copy and weblink of that volume and issue of your IJTSE JOURNAL for our published paper 2018- IJTSE-113 .

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Laura Anderson | Editorial Head, IJTSE
Gavin International Conferences and Publishers Inc.,
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So, please confirm me that you are still committed to keep your decision of your Board (as informed to me by Lucy Charter of your Journal Office by mail to me which is available in the trailing mail below your mail sending Invoice and Galley Proof, send by Lucy Charter on 8th May 2018 regarding this paper and further confirmed me on 30th may 2018 as per below mail). So, no question of invoice or sending payment arises and it is not permitted at all by our University. Pls you talk with lucy and confirm me .

Therefore, you confirm me publication of this paper M.S. No. 2018- IJTSE 113 immediately at free of cost with complete waiver of any publication charges and send me the e copy and weblink of the journal for downloading our published copy of this paper.

I am very much annoyed on your lack of coordination on this matter and you have kept this paper unpublished for such a long time unnecessarily. Pls do the needful and confirm me ,.

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E
editor@textileengineering.org

Fwd: Submitting Further Some corrections from My Co Author on PDF preapred for our paper IJTSE-113 for preparing Final Galley Proofs along with my sent list of earlier corrections -to do the needful

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta
To: contact@gavinpublishers.org, Cc: me, and 1 other · Thu, May 31, 2018 at 7:43 PM

Message Body

Laura Anderson | Editorial Head
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5911 Oka Ridge Way
Lisle IL 60532 USA
Email: contact@gavinpublishers.org
Website: <http://gavinpublishers.com/>

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lucy has further confirmed me by today's mail about free of cost publication of this paper of me , as an editorial board member. Thank you you and Lucy for this.

However, my coauthor Anowar Hossain , who is doing PhD under Me , has identified some more corrections and mailed me to forward you. So , I am now forwarding some more corrections and spelling mistakes marked in red and yellow colour marked and corrected by him in word version attached here and also two annex tables , which was missed are given in separate file attached (attached as annexed tables separately) to incorporate during preparing corrected PDF of this Paper IJTSE-113 along with my sent list of earlier corrections.

Pls do the needful

Thanking you
Prof Ashis Kumar Samanta
Professor, DJFT,IJT, CU

Fw: Thank you for submitting revised manuscript

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta
To: me, Cc: Prof. · Mon, May 21, 2018 at 5:09 PM

Message Body

Dear Anowar ,

See The Journal office Mail that they have received the revised paper as per below mail .

Thx
Prof A K Samanta

From: editor@textileengineering.org <editor@textileengineering.org>

Sent: Monday, May 21, 2018 3:12 PM

To: 'Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta'

Subject: RE: Thank you for submitting revised manuscript

Dear Dr. Ashis kumar Samanta,

Greetings from the journal!
Thank you for submitting revised manuscript.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

Now we will go to the next step on your manuscript, we will let you know the status frequently.

We are released our June issue, we are looking for fit articles, so if you have known any friends please suggest our journal their articles publish in our journal. We are giving huge discount (60-70%) on publication charge to our invited authors.

In case if you need any further information, please don't hesitate to contact us.

Thank you so much for your support and suggestion to our journal.

Thanks & Regards

Lucy

From: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta [mailto:ijtakSAMANTA@hotmail.com]

Sent: Monday, May 21, 2018 12:44 PM

To: editor@textileengineering.org

Cc: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta <ijtakSAMANTA@hotmail.com>; Anwar Hoasian for M Tech Admission <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

Subject: Submitting REVISED and corrected manuscript ID: IJTSE-113. (two files in word, one file containing corrected paper and another file containing corrected tables) for Publication free of Cost in Your Journal - Intl Journal of Textile Science and Engg.

Subject: Submitting REVISED and corrected manuscript **ID: IJTSE-113.**(two files in word, one file containing corrected paper and another file containing corrected tables) for Publication free of Cost in Your Journal - Intl Journal of Textile Science and Engg. for Upcoming Issue

Lucy Charter

Editorial Coordinator

International Journal of Textile Science & Engineering

Sub : Sunbmitting REVISED and corrected manuscript **ID: IJTSE-113.**(two files in word, one file containing corrected paper and another file containing corrected tables) for Publication free of Cost in Your Journal - Intl Journal of Textile Science and Engg. for Upcoming Issue

Dear Lucy ,

As Per comments of the two referees attached in you trailing mail , I am now Sunbmitting REVISED and corrected manuscript **ID: IJTSE-113.**(two files

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh

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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University; 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

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Page | 159

Thanks,

(Prof. A K Samanta)

Professor

Department of Jute and Fibre Technology

Institute of Jute Technology,

University of Calcutta

Kolkata

INDIA

From: editor@textileengineering.org <editor@textileengineering.org>

Sent: Thursday, May 17, 2018 11:17 AM

To: 'Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta'

Subject: RE: Comments to Author

Dear Dr. Ashis kumar Samanta,

Greeting from the journal!!!!!!

Hope you are well!

We would be glad to get to your notice that we are done with the review process of your manuscript with **reference ID: IJTSE-113**.

Please find the attached Comments to Author form and Original Manuscript for your reference. Kindly make the necessary changes as suggested by reviewers and send the revised manuscript to us on/**before May 23, 2018**.

I will be happy to assist you for any further queries. I look forward to hear from you soon.

Thank you in advance and have a great weekend Doctor.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

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Regards,
Lucy

Could you please verify attached article which are not available in your archive and google scholar?

Page | 160

- Anowar Hossain

To: contact@gavinpublishers.org · Mon, Oct 11, 2021 at 5:46 PM

Message Body

Editor

International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering

- **Gavin Publishers, 5911 Oak Ridge Way, Lisle, IL 60532, USA.**
- **Dear Sir,**
- **I would like to seek your sincere attention that I am not getting attached research articles in your archive and online available. I am feeling dishearted as first and corresponding author of both article.**
- **Could you please verify from your office concern of production and online management team?**
- **Regards**
- **Md. Anowar Hossain**
- **Ph.D Researcher**
- **School of Fashion and Textiles**
- **RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia**

2 attachmentsDownload all

- **IJTSE-113.pdf**

PDF · 1.5 MB

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

o IJTSE-126.pdf

PDF · 470.6 KB

• Editorial Head

To: me · Mon, Oct 11, 2021 at 5:56 PM

Message Body

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Thanks for the reply. As per your records, you haven't paid for the 2 articles so that we haven't published your articles. We will publish only paid articles. If you want to publish the articles then please proceed with the payment and let us know the status.

Regards,

Laura

Show trimmed content

• Anowar Hossain

To: Editorial · Tue, Oct 12, 2021 at 12:03 AM

Message Body

Dear Laura,

I have attached a proof that the research article was completely free of cost which was approved by Lucy. I was also found the published article in online and it was also cited by few papers through google scholar. As attached proof, the manuscript is supposed to have a record in your journal archive with online availability.

I have also attached the invoice of review article if the bank account is ok which was previously mentioned in invoice.

Two article was checked when I was planning to submit a good quality review article in your journal for consideration. I would like to submit it if you approve me free of cost.

Regards

Md. Anowar Hossain

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

On Monday, October 11, 2021, 10:56:20 PM GMT+11, Editorial Head <contact@gavinpublishers.org> wrote:

Dear Anowar Hossain,

Thanks for the reply. As per your records, you haven't paid for the 2 articles so that we haven't published your articles. We will publish only paid articles. If you want to publish the articles then please proceed with the payment and let us know the status.

Regards,
Laura

Page | 162

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta
To: me · Wed, Oct 10, 2018 at 10:52 PM
Message Body

- ASHISKUMAR SAMANTA
To: Trends, and 1 other, Cc: me, and 2 others · Sun, Nov 11, 2018 at 11:18 AM

To:

- Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology, <fashion@crimsonpublishers.org>,
• <fashion@crimsononline.org>

Cc:

- Ashis Kr Samanta Professor, <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>,
• ASHISKUMAR SAMANTA, <ijtaksamanta@gmail.com>,
• Anwar Hoasian for M Tech Admission, <enr.anowar@yahoo.com>
Message Body

To
Catherine Ali
Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology

Dear cathrine ,

I hope that our paper TTEFT-18-RA-585 entitled “Cost Minimisation in Sample Development and Approval Process by Proper Merchandising Action for kids and Ladies Garments” has been published in your TTEFT

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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Research office of Dr. Anwar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

on line journal . But you have not send me so far any information on its final publication and not send the author's e copy of it.

Pls send the e copy and weblink of our on line published Paper TTEFT-18-RA-585 with doi no. at earliest to my e-mail ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

Thx .

Prof A K Samanta

Professor , DJFT.IJT.CU

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: fashion@crimsononline.org, and 1 other, Cc: me, and 2 others · Sun, Nov 11, 2018 at 11:25 AM

- <fashion@crimsononline.org>
- Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology, <fashion@crimsonpublishers.org>

Cc:

- Anwar Hoasian for M Tech Admission, <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>
- ASHISKUMAR SAMANTA, <ijtaksamanta@gmail.com>
- Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta, <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>

Fwd: checking of the pdf of your Research paper to be published

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta
 To: me, Cc: Prof. · Fri, Sep 28, 2018 at 9:53 AM

Message Body

Dear anwar,

pls see the atached final galley proof of this paper for which you paid 109 usd as final proof before publication consent for your following paper .

"Natural Coloration and Finishing of Cotton Fabric Using Non-toxic Natural Colorant and Crosslinker"

JTESE-2165-8064-18-8-374

Kindly Send me immediately your response after checking it if any correction is needed.

Pls do check and respond by tomorrow to send publication consent yo journal office , if no further correction are needed.

Thanks

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Prof AK Samanta
 Djft.ijt.CU
 Sent from my Samsung Galaxy smartphone.

----- Original message -----

From: Journal of Textile Science and Engineering
 <editor.jtесе@peerreviewjournal.org>
 Date: 9/28/18 9:12 AM (GMT+05:30)
 To: "Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta" <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>
 Subject: Research paper

Hi,

Kindly find the pdf into the attachment and let me know if any correction is needed.

Thank you and have a nice day.

Regards,
 Peterson S
 Editorial Office
 RIPED Journal

From: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta [mailto:ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com]
Sent: 27 September 2018 19:12
To: editor.jtесе@peerreviewjournal.org; textilesci@peerreviewedjournals.com
Cc: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta; Anwar Hoasian for M Tech Admission
Subject: Sub: Enquiry about publication of our paper "Natural Coloration and Finishing of Cotton Fabric Using Non-toxic Natural Colorant and Crosslinker" JTESE-2165-8064-18-8-374 in JTESE journal and request to send e copy for uploaded paper immediately

Mr Anna Holmes
 Journal Coordinator
 Journal of Textile Science and Engineering
 Tel: +1-650-618-9889
 Fax: +1-650-618-1414
 E-mail: textilesci@peerreviewedjournals.com

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editor.jtese@peerreviewedjournals.org

Dear Mr A Holmes,

I am wondered that we have not received yet the Pdf Proof or E copy of our paper accepted and to be published.

My co author Md Anowar Hossain from Bangladesh has already paid requisite charges of 109 USD, which you have acknowlowged and wrote me that we will receive pdf proof next day. But we did not received it or missed your mail of our following paper (Pls See the below mail of my coauthor sending enquiry to me for status of the paper to be published for which he has paid 109 USD and see your acknowledgement in below mail committing to send Pdf Uploaded paper soon, but nothing received as yet, which is worrying us)

"Natural Coloration and Finishing of Cotton Fabric Using Non-toxic Natural Colorant and Crosslinker"

JTESE-2165-8064-18-8-374

Kindly Send me immediately the E-copy of the Published paper and e web-link of your journal to get print of the published paper to submit to my co-author's Institute account and also for our publication record .

pls respond immediately.

Thank You
 Prof A K Samanta
 Professor, DJFT, IJT, CU
 email : ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

From: Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>
Sent: Thursday, September 27, 2018 4:22 PM
To: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta
Subject: Re: Fw: Thank you for the payment

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"Natural Coloration and Finishing of Cotton Fabric Using Non-toxic Natural Colorant and Crosslinker"

Page | 166

JTESE-2165-8064-18-8-374

Thanks for your kind attention
Md. Anowar Hossain

On Friday, September 14, 2018, 7:25:12 PM GMT+6, Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com> wrote:

From: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 1:47 PM
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From: Journal of Textile Science and Engineering
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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

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Thank you.
Regards,
Anna Holmes
Editorial Office
Journal of Textile Science and Engineering

From: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta [<mailto:ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>]
Sent: 12 September 2018 21:39
To: editor.jtесе@peerreviewjournal.org
Cc: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta; Anwar Hoasian for M Tech Admission
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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

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With regards
Yours faithfully
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University of calcutta
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Sub: Enquiry about publication of our paper "Natural Coloration and Finishing of Cotton Fabric Using Non-toxic Natural Colorant and Crosslinker" JTESE-2165-8064-18-8-374 in JTESE journal and request to send e copy for uploaded paper immediately

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To: editor.jtese@peerreviewjournal.org, and 1 other, Cc: me, and 1 other · Thu, Sep 27, 2018 at 7:42 PM

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Mr Anna Holmes

Journal Coordinator

Journal of Textile Science and Engineering

Tel: +1-650-618-9889

Fax: +1-650-618-1414

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

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Professor.djft, ijt ,

University of calcutta

E mail : ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

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With regards
Yours faithfully
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Professor.djft, ijt ,
University of calcutta
E mail : ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

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- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta
To: me, Cc: Prof. · Fri, Sep 7, 2018 at 8:17 PM

Message Body

Dear Anowar ,

You have received the below mail and you have to pay the required USD via link for payment in this mail probably 109 USD through Authorize .net link given .

I do not understand what is your problem for payment there . Any International Credit card or debit card can do it easily with title of your paper etc and name etc as per author's list and send me e copy of receipt .

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If you can not , take help of any foreign currency bank i.e overseas branch of bank to pay to them through pay-pal link and in that case you need account no etc of the journal and bank details etc , which you can easily get by direct mail to Dr Anna Holmes , Editorial

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

co-ordinator of JTESE journal , giving your paper reference and invoice ref -- **Invoice No for your manuscript is JTESE-2165-8064-18-8-374** etc as per below mail .

Pls do it by yourself or taking help from any professional money transferer or any foreign /overseas barnch of any bank in bangladesh .

They may take a small charges from you .

Thanks

Prof A K Samanta

From: editor.jtese@peerreviewjournal.org <editor.jtese@peerreviewjournal.org>

Sent: Thursday, August 30, 2018 11:42 AM

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Cc: ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

Subject: Regarding to the manuscript

Dear Researcher,

Hope this mail will receive you well.

Your manuscript entitled as "**Natural Coloration and Finishing of Cotton Fabric Using Non-toxic Natural Colorant and Crosslinker**" is accepted for publication but prior to that few minor changes are required kindly make it done and submit it me at the earliest possible time so that we will proceed for the galley proof of it.

Here are the review comments for your manuscript.

Reviewer 1:

The paper entitled " Natural Coloration and Finishing of Cotton Fabric Using Non-toxic Natural Colorant and Crosslinker" this paper deal with the natural dyes and natural mordant as a substitute of toxic colorant and mordant. So I recommended for published this paper in your Journal.

Reviewer 2:

This publication addresses a very innovative subject. Indeed a green industry is necessary and obligatory to save our planet. In fact, natural dyes have been used since antiquity but their use remains limited to traditional methods. This work isn't perfect but there is some failure sector and some criticism can be considered:

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

* Then, the use of mordant does not completely avoid the phenomenon of pollution because of the presence of complex dyes / Metal. For this, the author must seek to use natural mordant and have a biodegradable character in other research.

* In order to evaluate the success of this process, it is necessary to compare the results obtained with the same material dyed with a synthetic dye.

* The result of dyeing process without mordant (purely ecological dye)

* There were some grammatical and structural mistakes that must be corrected.

* The use of Kawabata chain tests KES-FB3 and KES-FB4 is mandatory to see the physical, thermal and metrological behavior of supports dyed with this natural dye.

Then, success in this line of research can help and make a solution for industrial and clothing customers. For this reason, you have to make sure of the new processes and implement the proper recipes. Finally, this paper after such minor correction allows completing scientific work. Therefore, the publication may be published in the Journal of Textile Science & Engineering.

Kindly proceed for the payment of the manuscript too by the following payment link: <https://www.imedpub.com/onlinepayment/>

The Invoice No for your manuscript is JTESE-2165-8064-18-8-374

Once the payment will be done kindly submit the payment receipt to us for the cross-check along with the revised manuscript.

Awaiting your prompt response.

Regards,

Anna Holmes

Editorial office

Re: Revised Paper submission removing and changing red part as reported matching with our earlier publication for considering the revised paper for peer review process after further Pre-Qc of our manuscript

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: textilesci@peerreviewedjournals.com, Cc: me, and 1 other · Fri, Aug 17, 2018 at 5:20 PM

Message Body

Anna Holmes

Editorial Office

Journal of Textile Science and Engineering

Dear Anna Holmes,

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020; Room: 512.01.12.25; School of

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

I am hereby re submitting attached two files one in word file and one in pdf file for resubmission of our Revised Paper after removing and changing red part (marked by your journal office) as reported matching with our earlier publications or other publications for further considering the revised version of this paper for peer review process after further Pre-Qc of our manuscript from your journal office for start review process for acceptance in Journal of Textile Science and Engineering .

Page | 177

I hope You can remember that our university do not allow any priced publication paying any charges to any journal and hence you agreed that if it is accepted you will charge only 109 dollar for indexing and uploading charges which Mr Anowar Hossain my co author will pay from his bangladesh office/university personally to you .

we have changed the title to a little extent and modified title is as follows :

Natural Coloration and Finishing of Cotton Fabric Using Non-toxic Natural Colorant and Crosslinker

Authored by : Md. Anowar Hossain^{1*}, Ashis Kumar Samanta^{2#} , Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik² , Padma S Vankar³ & Dhara Shukla³

¹Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

²Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata-700019, India.

³IIT-Kanpur Campus , Kanpur-208016, Uttarpradesh , India.

***First & Coresponding Author: Md. Anowar Hossain, e mail**

: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

#2nd Coresponding Author : A K Samanta, E mail

: ijtakamanta@hotmail.com

Kindly acknowledge

With Thanks

Prof A K Samanta

Professor, DJFT,IJT, University of Calcutta , Kolkata , India .

From: textilesci@peerreviewedjournals.com <textilesci@peerreviewedjournals.com>

Sent: Tuesday, August 14, 2018 1:36 PM

To: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta

Subject: Pre-Qc Reported for your manuscript

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

Dear Researcher,

Hope this mail will receive you well.

We would like to inform you that your manuscript is unable to pass our preliminary quality control test. It is caught to more than 50 % plagiarized content.

If you will rewrite the content which is highlighted as red into the attached pdf than we will consider your manuscript for peer review process.

Meanwhile in your previous mail you have told us many thing and even ready for publication too but we would like to inform you that we always look first for the scientific community and meanwhile ask for charges to compensate the charges which we have to pay for **Indexing, DOI activation, website maintenance and other things for a manuscript.**

Hope you got the things which we would like to clear you.

Thank you.

Regards,

Anna Holmes

Editorial Office

Journal of Textile Science and Engineering

Re: Submission of one of our research paper for publication in Journal of Textile Science and Engineering after your consent to charge only \$ 109 USD for activation and DOI indexing etc. which will be paid by Co=author Md. Anowar Hossain from Bangladesh

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: Journal, and 2 others, Cc: me, and 1 other · Sat, Aug 11, 2018 at 4:52 PM

Message Body

Anna Holmes

Editorial office

Journal of Textile Science and Engineering

Dear Holmes,

As you have mention that you can not waive full publication charges and need 109 USD to pay for activation charge and doi indexing charge for publication of our Paper, as per your mail on Monday, July 16, 2018 10:23 AM.

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VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

You are well aware that University of Calcutta, West Bengal, India do not allow any priced publication and hence I cannot pay even a single dollar to you for publication of our paper.

However, this can be paid by Co-author Md. Anowar Hossain from Bangladesh for our Joint Paper from a Research Team under my guidance. So, consider the name of Md. Anowar Hossain as first corresponding author and my name as 2nd corresponding author.

Page | 179

I am now submitting the attached paper for considering its publication in your Journal of Textile Science and Engineering. After review and its acceptance, please send me the invoice for payment of only \$ 109 USD as **activation charge and doi indexing charge for publication**. After receiving the Invoice, I shall forward the Invoice to Md. Anowar Hossain of Bangladesh to pay your journal office account a sum of \$ 109 USD through his bank or his Pay Pal a/c..

After payment, I shall send you the scanned payment document and receipt, for confirmation of payment for publication of this paper on-line in the **Journal of Textile Science and Engineering**.

You have to sent e-copy of printed paper to both of us.

The Title and Name of the Authors for the submitted paper for your journal are as follows :-

Title : Non-toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric Using Non-toxic Natural Colorant and Crosslinking agent.

Authors : Md. Anowar Hossain^{1*}, Ashis Kumar Samanta^{2#}, Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik², Padma S Vankar³ & Dhara Shukla³

¹Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

²Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata-700019, India.

³IIT-Kanpur Campus, Kanpur-208016, Uttarpradesh, India.

***First & Coresponding Author: Md. Anowar Hossain, e mail**

: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

#2ndCoresponding Author : A K Samanta, E mail

: ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

Kindly acknowledge the receipt of this manuscript and give us Manuscript ID No. and process it for publication.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

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Thanks,
(Prof. A K Samanta)
Professor and Former HOD
DJFT, IJT, CU
mobile No. 0091 98311 61529
email : ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

Page | 180

Md Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

Wed 8/8/2018, 9:38 AM

You

Prof. A K Samanta, DJFT, IJT, Calcutta University

Dear Respected Sir,

Good Morning.

OK, we can proceed 5th paper for peer review process.

I will pay 109 USD as you already discussed several time for free of cost publication.

Thanks
Md. Anowar Hossain

On Tuesday, August 7, 2018, 12:11:22 PM GMT+6, Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com> wrote:
From:"Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta"

Dear Anowar,

Please find the attached paper recorded to me as 4th Paper (5th Paper is already communicated but 4th Paper was not sent to any Journal as yet).

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²³ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Please confirm me your consent.

If yes, I shall submit the paper and after review and its acceptance invoice will come to pay, which I shall forward to you to pay through bank or Pay Pal.

After payment, you have to send me scanned payment document and receipt, which I shall forward to the Journal for confirmation of payment and its publication on-line in the **Journal of Textile Science and Engineering**.

Thanks,
(Prof. A K Samanta)
Professor

From: jtese@engineeringinsights.org <jtese@engineeringinsights.org> on behalf of Journal of Textile Science and Engineering <jtese@engineeringinsights.org>

Sent: Monday, July 16, 2018 10:23 AM

To: ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

Cc: textilesci@peerreviewedjournals.com

Subject: Awaiting for the kind note

*Dear Ashish Kumar Samanta,
Gratitude for the mail.*

*Firstly we would like to say thank you to you, for sparing your precious time to response our mail. We would like to inform you that our journal is **Open access peer-review journal** and open access journals are solely depends on the author's contribution to making the website up to date.*

*We also like to inform you that from **manuscript plagiarism check, peer review process, DOI activation to publication** we cost **131 USD** and other than that if we go for Indexing than for each different indexing sites we have to pay the required amount which they had fixed for the manuscript for evaluation.*

As an eminent personality kindly let us know if we will provide the only waiver to all manuscript than how we will update our journal and how will we go for the approval for other indexing sites.

*At the last if any author wishes to publish his/her research work to any of the journals firstly they ask for **Indexing and ISSN** if any journals do not have such*

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

things then they will not support the journal to raise up. Everyone wants to publish their research work in a well-established journal and to establish a journal it costs too much.

We can't provide a full waiver to you for manuscript publication but if you serve our journal with your knowledge and experience than we are ready to publish your every manuscript in **109 USD** with **Indexing and DOI activation**.

We are looking for the betterment of the scientific community and everything needs a little sacrifice to get the success.

Hope you will not mind this mail and acknowledged it with your valuable response.

Awaiting the response.

Regards,

Anna Holmes

Editorial office

Journal of Textile Science and Engineering

From:"Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta"

To:"textilesci@peerreviewedjournals.com"

Cc:"Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta"

Date:Sat, July 14, 2018 6:25 pm

Subject:Re: Manuscript capitulation requisition

Anna Holmes

Journal Coordinator

Journal of Textile Science and Engineering

Tel: +1-650-618-9889

Fax: +1-650-618-1414

E-mail: textilesci@peerreviewedjournals.com

Dear A Holmes ,

I am Thankful for your invitation for submitting research article/manuscript in your Journal of Textile Science and Engg,

But Sorry to say that Our University /Department / Institute does not allow any Chargeable publication in anyjournal.

So no Professor/Associate Professor/Lecturer or Researcher of Our University (University of Calcutta) will agree to send their papers to this journal for any short of price publication, even we are not allowed to

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

pay DOI insertion/Activation or any short of Up loading fee of single Dollar or Rupees .

so , if you publish my paper free of cost , inform me and then i shall send you one of fast track paper on natural dyeing , otherwise I have to Abstain from it to submit any paper to your open access journal .

So , Pls Understand that under any circums tances , There is no way to pay you a single dollar for publication charge or uploading charge of our paper in anyjournal.

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please reply and try to accomodate one of our paper /manuscript for on line publication in your journal as a spl invited article /research paper , if possible.

If Printed version of Your Journal is also avialble with you , pls send one set printed copy of fulljournalto make it popularise in indian Textile Colleges /Universities by showing it to different researchers and librarian.

In india without printed hard copy, no library wants to purchase a newjournal. I can help you this way or serve you by giving technical service as a editorial board member of your journal (If you agree and accept it) , but not to able to pay any sorts of money for publishing a research paper in yourjournal.

Pls Reply

THx and regds

Prof Ashis Kumar Samanta
Professor , DJFt, IJT, CU

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

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Re: Submission of Revised version as per Reviewer's Comments: Ms No TTEFT-18-RA-561 , complying all suggestions of the reviewer

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta
To: Trends, Cc: me, and 1 other · Thu, Jun 7, 2018 at 6:53 PM
- Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology, <fashion@crimsonpublishers.org>

Page | 184

Cc:

- Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta, <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com> ,
- Anwar Hoasian for M Tech Admission, <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

Message Body

Catherine Ali

Editorial Coordinator.

Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology

Dear C Ali ,

Please find herewith the Revised manuscript (TTEFT-18-RA-561) in both Word File (with yellow marked revision/correction part) and pdf file attached herewith for considering its publication in your journal at free of cost without any sorts of publication cahrges, as committed earlier.

Thank you

Prof A K Samanta

RE: Modified PDF: TTEFT-18-RA-561

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta
To: Trends, Cc: me · Fri, Jun 22, 2018 at 7:48 PM

Message Body

Catherine Ali

Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology

Dear sir/ madam ,

Thank you. the final modified pdf TTEFT-18-RA-561 is all ok. So pls publish it on line in your journal of TTEFT .

Thx

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 Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Prof a k samanta

Sent from my Samsung Galaxy smartphone.

PDF: TTEFT-18-RA-561

- Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology

To: 'Prof., Cc: me · Tue, Jun 19, 2018 at 7:31 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta,

Hope this email finds you in high spirits.

We are delighted to notify that your research entitled "**Pollution Free Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted from *Swieteniamacrophylla* and *Musa Acuminata* as Unpolluted Dyes and *Citrus. Limon (L.)* as Unpolluted Mordanting Agent**" has done with galley proof a moment ago. Please have a quick glance on your article PDF and inform us for any further modifications, we are at your service round the clock.

Please don't hesitate to contact us.

Look forward to hear from you soon.

Have a great day!

Best Regards,

Catherine Ali

Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology

Fwd: Acceptance of an Article: TTEFT-18-RA-561

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: me · Fri, Jun 8, 2018 at 8:43 PM

Message Body

Dear anowar ,

At last , your paper 2 has also been accepted after revision . Thx God. It is done. See below mail from journal office .

Thx
Prof a k samanta

Re: Status: Submission of Revised Paper TTEFT-18-RA-561 for considering its acceptance and publication in your Journal

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

Page | 186

To: Trends, Cc: Prof. · Wed, May 30, 2018 at 12:37 PM

Message Body

Catherine Ali

Editorial Coordinator

Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology

Dear Sir,

Please find herewith our Revised Paper TTEFT-18-RA-561 for considering its acceptance and publication in your Journal both in word file (with yellow mark for corrected part) and also in pdf file attached in this mail. As per earlier commitment kindly publish this article free of cost with complete waiver for all shorts of charges for this publication, as our University do not allow any sort of publication charge for any paper.

Kindly acknowledge the receipt of the Revised Paper.

Please send the acceptance and galley proof of the paper in due time in my mail.

Thanks,
(Prof. A K Samanta)
Professor
DJFT, IJT, CU

Review Comments: TTEFT-18-RA-561

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology

To: 'Prof., Cc: me · Wed, May 23, 2018 at 7:34 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta,

Hope you are doing well.

We are glad to inform you that, we have received review comments of your manuscript (TTEFT-18-RA-561). Hence, we request you to submit your analysis revised manuscript at your earliest possibility.

Await your response.

Have a good day!

Best Regards,

Catherine Ali

Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology

Fw: Still under Review Process: TTEFT-18-RA-561

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: me, Cc: Prof. · Mon, May 21, 2018 at 7:11 PM

Message Body

Dear Anowar ,

Pls Find Reply from Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology

<fashion@crimsonpublishers.org for Our another paper which is still under review .

Pls wait to obtain review report

Thx

Prof A K Samanta

Sub.: Enquiry about the status of publication of Manuscript ID: TTEFT-18-RA-561

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: fashion@crimsonpublishers.com, Cc: me, and 1 other · Mon, May 21, 2018 at 2:16 PM

Message Body

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

Catherine Ali

Editorial Coordinator

Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology

Dear Ali,

I have not yet received reviewer response or any communication from you reg. the status of the publication of the following paper ID No. TTEFT-18-RA-561 as given below

Title: Natural Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted from Swieteniamacrophylla and Musa acuminata with natural mordanting agent

ID: **TTEFT-18-RA-561"**

Kindly inform me its present status about free of cost publication of this paper in your reputed journal.

Await your response.

Have a good day!

Fw: Manuscript ID: TTEFT-18-RA-561

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta
To: me, Cc: Prof. · Thu, May 3, 2018 at 8:50 PM

Message Body

Dear Anowar ,
Find Submission acknowledgement and Ms no REf from the journal office for your first paper as follws

Title: Natural Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted from Swieteniamacrophylla and Musa acuminata with natural mordanting agent

ID: **TTEFT-18-RA-561**

Thank you

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Prof A K Samanta

From: Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology

<fashion@crimsonpublishers.com>

Sent: Thursday, May 3, 2018 6:45 PM

To: 'Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta'

Subject: Manuscript ID: TTEFT-18-RA-561

Dear Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta,

We sincerely appreciate your valuable submission.

After having glanced at your manuscript we let you know that, your article has been effectively acknowledged for further peer review process and will get back to you with the article updates timely.

Track the below manuscript ID for further communication

Title: Natural Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted from Swieteniamacrophylla and Musa acuminata with natural mordanting agent

ID: **TTEFT-18-RA-561**

Await your response.

Have a good day!

Best Regards,

Catherine Ali

Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology

From: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta [<mailto:ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>]

Sent: 02 May 2018 21:44

To: Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology; Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology

Cc: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta

RE: Need to revise fully to avoid plagiarism for your 4th paper sent to me as Another manuscript of paper with simulation and much similarity of your previous one

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta
To: me · Wed, May 9, 2018 at 4:49 PM

Message Body

Page | 190

Dear Anowar ,

I have gone through your new 4th paper draft inspite of my busy schedule and observed following lackkuna in it for which the whole paper need to be revised and to be rewritten again to make it publishable at all

1. As per rules of plagiarism you can not copy any part of text even few sentences or stanza and tables or figures from one paper to other paper even if it is your own paper published elsewhere (as per copy right rule) and it is checked by plagirism software and if it is found more than 10 % same or similar even for review or material mehods part etc or results and discussion etc you are punishable and you may even suspended from further teaching and research jobs and may be sued.

So as your this 4th paPer has more than 80 % similarity with previous 3rd paper submitted for publication which will become public after its on line publication , you and me and all the co authors will be under criticism for plagiarism offense. Even with same aithors group you can not do this more tha 10 % that too with reference .

Though your dyes are different , to break this simlirity or copying nature from your previous paper you have to put everything in new language and new style of sentences removing unnecessary lengthy review and have to adopt diferent (not same) way of describing materials and methods part in different style and results and discusion are to be put also in non simulated and non copying stule in dofferent way with new languages if anything is essentially reproduced or remove those which are not essential in this paper.

Then check by plagiarism software with your own previous paper or also check whether it is matching with any one elses' paper or not . More than 10 % similarity is not allowed in publication even from own previous paper or any bodyelses' paper that too you have yo mention ref of that paper for sentences found similar or style is similar for any part of your new paper.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

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2. Your FTIR CURVES APOEAR TO BE WRONG AND GOING DOWN AND VERY CLUMSY AND NOISY WITHOUT CLEAR PEAKS AND NOT ANALYSED WELL. TAKE HELP OF GOOD FTIR RESOLUTION MACHINE AND REPEAT IT

3 FOR ANTIMICROBIAL RESULTS ARE TO BE GIVEN IN % BACTERIAL REDUCTION R TWO KINDS OF STANDARD MICROBES WITH PICTURE OF PETRI PLATES . SEE OTHER'S PAPER on antimicrobial treatment who have shown picture of petri plate dishes showing growth or reduction of bacteria species (see tapas ranjan kar' s paper on rot resistance treatment showing such petri plates.

4. You have to explain clearly how these dyes are acting as bacteria inhibitor or killer to give better properties for antimicrobial effect in treated fabric i.e the mechanism of action here .

5 The review part and refence is too long and unnecessary and copied from previous paper of you . This is not allowed as per plagiarism rule and protection of copy right rule.

So . You rewrite this paper with new attractive title and newer heading and sub heafing in new form with new style of sentences removing all unnecessry sentence and adding some more parameters of study of your research and review and discussion part to have a new look so that under plagiarism detection software not having more than 5 to 10 % similarity any way .

Hope you will do some new expt and redo ftir and rewrite whole paper in tthis new persoective taking your own time to do the best . Then after doing all these you send me back within 3 months or so adding new results and testing . Test of fastness for washing , light , rubbing and petspiration are must to be rechecked and to be confimed and need to be discussed the reasonings for all major obsetvation to explain the observed results .

Hope you will do best and revet back to me again.

Thanks for your constant effort to improve yourself .

Prof a k samanta

Djft . Ijt. CU .

Sent from my Samsung Galaxy smartphone.

Fw: We have started the review process soon we will update you the status of the article

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: me, and 1 other · Tue, May 8, 2018 at 6:56 PM

Message Body

Dear Anowar,

Please note that for your 3rd Paper, Lucy Charter has responded in the below mail allowing complete waiver as editorial board member of this Journal as a special case waiving 250 USD per Manuscript usually they charge for publication in their Journal. The paper is in review process. Wait for the review result to come.

Thanks,

(Prof. A K Samanta)

reply of your mail

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: me, Cc: Prof. · Mon, Jun 18, 2018 at 2:37 PM

Message Body

Dear Anowar,

I am very busy with the exam.

Plz. have patience.

About 2nd and 3rd Paper, only journal office can say when it will be published. After receiving notification from them I will send you.

About 4th Paper, I have received it but I have no time to check its accuracy.

Hence, 4th paper is not yet submitted to any Journal. Moreover, most of the journal take huge charge for publication and therefore difficult for me to sent to any journal without confirmation of free of cost publication which takes time.

No need of repeatedly reminding me or asking me the status.

Thanks,

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

(Prof. A K Samanta)

Re: Fw: Rreply of your query about co authors

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: me · Tue, May 8, 2018 at 2:32 PM

Message Body

Dear Anowar ,

Dr Dhara Shukla is Sr research Fellow Under DR P S Vankar and is working with her and also with us as like Nilendu is working with me in natural Dyes R & D Project .

Prof A K Samanta

Hide trimmed content

From: Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

Sent: Tuesday, May 8, 2018 9:45 AM

To: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta

Subject: Re: Fw: Corrections done by my project team to Submit your Article for Upcoming Issue of Journal of International Journal of Textile Science & Engineering, after receiving your consent and confirmation of attached corrected form

Dear Respected Sir,

Good Morning and Hope, you are well.

All of your added name is Ok for publishing this paper as you have decided accordingly. But let me know about Dhara Shukla who is looking unknown name to me. Please confirm the publication of this paper.

Please find both attachments of word and PDF file.

Thanks and Regards

Md. Anowar Hossain

On Monday, May 7, 2018, 8:22:30 PM GMT+6, Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta <jtaksamanta@hotmail.com> wrote:

Dear Anowar ,

Your third paper was a mesh in many places . I have made it corrected by my project team including Dr Vankar of IIT kanpur and they have corrected title , abstract and many places inside the papers and conclusions etc as far as practicable and as they have understood it.

Page | 194

I am attaching now the word file of corrected paper for your check and confirmation please including your consent for names of Co-authors , put by me for my project team , who have made this corrections and contributed a lot in this paper , otherwise it was not in publishable form at all . Even now Some corrections are needed .

So , in this paper , this time, I have added their names as some co authors for our on going R & D project on natural dyeing including our partner IIT kanpur team for better acceptance and correction done by them as they have understood it.

Hope you will agree and check their corrections and give your confirmation . Pls check the language and correctness of statements word by word and line by line and correct again , wherever required with red colour letters and send me both in word and pdf format as usual for checking and formatting please..

After your confirmation of everything by mail and after receiving your consent on authors and coauthors names etc , I shall submit it in both WORD and PDF format .

Pls acknowledge and send your confirmation about corrections and consent on co-authors'names etc

Thanking you
Prof A K Samanta

Re: Reply of status after checking of the status of your paper as per the attached list of draft copy of all five (5) papers received from you.

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta
To: me · Mon, May 21, 2018 at 2:34 PM

Message Body
Md. Anowar Hossain

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Plz. find the attached file with Reply of status in the last col. of the table after checking of the status of your paper as per the attached list of draft copy of all five (5) papers received from you.

Hope you are fine.

Thanks,

Prof. A K Samanta

Professor

RE: To be replied later after checking the status of these papers, not by a glance condition of my draft copy of all papers.

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: me · Sun, May 20, 2018 at 11:46 PM

Message Body

Dear anowar,

I shall check and reply later, as I am very busy with project audit and my tech project exam etc.

Pls bear with me.

Thx

Prof a k samanta

Fw: Note Submitting another substituted manuscript now For Free Of Cost publication with Full waiver instead of hiding and stopping publication of our earlier Manuscript ID: TTEFT-18-MRW-551 on our request

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: me, Cc: Prof. · Wed, May 2, 2018 at 10:23 PM

Message Body

Dear Anowar,

Your First paper was submitted to the On Line Journal " Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology " having ISSN no **ISSN: 2578-0271, as per below mail, requesting stopping and hiding one of our accepted paper not to publish now and to be substituted by your paper to be considered first to publish in this journal for your early**

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

publications as needed by you , if accepted /revised after review .

I shall send you feedback as and when hear from them (Catherine Ali -Editorial Coordinator of This Journal named as Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology having ISSN no-ISSN: 2578-0271**) .**

Page | 196

**Prof A K Samanta
ProFessor, DJFT, IJT, CU**

From: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>
Sent: Wednesday, May 2, 2018 9:43 PM
To: Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology; Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology
Cc: ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com
Subject: Fw: Submitting another substituted manuscript now For Free Of Cost publication with Full waiver instead of hiding and stopping publication of our earlier Manuscript ID: TTEFT-18-MRW-551 on our request

From: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>
Sent: Wednesday, May 2, 2018 9:36 PM
To: Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology
Cc: ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com
Subject: Re: Submitting another substituted manuscript now For Free Of Cost publication with Full waiver instead of hiding and stopping publication of our earlier Manuscript ID: TTEFT-18-MRW-551 on our request

Catherine Ali
Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology

Dear Sir/ madam ,

Happy to know your ISSN no of this journal as **ISSN: 2578-0271**.

As Per Your Request , I am sending herewith one ready manuscript both in WORD file and PDF file for Manuscript entitled " **Natural Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted**

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

from **Swieteniamacrophylla** and **Musa acuminata** with **natural mordanting agent** " authored by My PhD student **Md. Anowar Hossain*** and AKM Saiful Islam, from Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh and Ashis Kumar Samanta , Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India, having Email address of Md Anowar Hossain as : **engr.anowar@yahoo.com (A. Hossain)** as **correspondence and first author as per PhD rules of our University his name should appear as first and correspondence author** and then my name as Executive Corresponding Author having e mail : **ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com (A. K. Samanta)** , where I shall do all correspondence with you reagrding this paper. Pls Give a manuscript no. and publish it free of cost as per complete waiver you allowed in TTEFT -18 -MRW-551 , which was to be hidid and sttpoted publishing then on my request to you for not getting permission from our project funding authority and need to be hidid must. So pls replace TTEFT -18 -MRW-551 by this newly today submitted manuscript with same DOI no etc for considering its early publication.

Kindly Acknowledge it and confirm MS no to us and publication issue and pls send PDF as Galley proof to both of us (Md Anowar Hossain and Myself Prof Ashis Kunmar Samanta) for Check before final publication with page no , vol no , issue no and DOI no.

Thanking you for cooperation

Prof AK Samanta
Professor , DJFT, IJT, Calcutta University

RE: FURTHER REVISION IS REQD AND YOUR correctons are not still up to the mark . Do it further minor modification needed in your Draft copy of the paper sent to me .

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta
To: me · Tue, May 1, 2018 at 10:43 PM

Message Body
Dear Anowar ,

I am sorry that ypur corection , language and each sentence are to be cheked and to be corrected n paper form . You are not undrstanding my words and language. Follow aascit paper language exactly or any of my natural dye IJFTR PAPER available in google scholar or ijftr site in pdf form. Down load and follow it.

No dyeing process flow chart with arrow is allowed to continue in next page including its heading to end . So heading and full flow chart or tables can not allowed to be spread or placed or kept in continuation to next page i.e not spread over in consecutive two pages, rather it is to be placed in such a area so that a complete flow chart or a complete table fully remains at one page including its heading .

Page | 198

So do that pls . It is not so here. Both of your flow chart are spreading over two continuing pages. One table heading is in earlier page. After doing so adjustment .send me again both in word and pdf format as final .

Ref 7 do not meant anything and is not any specific paper of us. What is this ? Go to google scholar search and search paer of a k samanta on natural dye in last 10 yrs , you will get 10 to 15 papers from which you add any one. In results and discussion part pls discuss k/ s values as given in new curves or plot stating which one is what and what is final observation . Say these also in conclusion and mention about k/ s in abstract also . In ref part keep only those whose ref is given and somethong scientific is said .

If you find difficulty call me by phone now .

Again modify and send me back by tomorrow morning .

Thanks
Prof a k samanta

Any way make it final and send me back.

Sent from my Samsung Galaxy smartphone.

Hide trimmed content

----- Original message -----

From: Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

Date: 5/1/18 9:17 PM (GMT+05:30)

To: "Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta" <ijtak samanta@hotmail.com>

Subject: Re: Fwd: RE: RE: see your correctons are not still up to the mark . Do it further minor modification needed in your Draft copy of the paper sent to me .

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Dear Respected Sir,

Attached with edition as per your comments and in my computer, no broken table is showing.

Thanks

Md. Anowar Hossain

On Tuesday, May 1, 2018, 3:48:34 PM GMT+6, Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com> wrote:

Dear anowar ,

Pls note you have to add k/s and dE data in this paper without which paper has no value . Pls do that also and send back to me.

Prof a k samanta

Sent from my Samsung Galaxy smartphone.

----- Original message -----

From: "Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta" <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>

Date: 5/1/18 11:02 AM (GMT+05:30)

To: Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

Subject: Fwd: RE: RE: see your correctons are not still up to the mark . Do it further minor modification needed in your Draft copy of the paper sent to me .

From: "Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta" <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>

Date: 5/1/18 10:45 AM (GMT+05:30)

To: Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

Subject: RE: RE: RE: see your corrctons are not still up to the mark . Do it further minor modification by shifting and adjusting any of the flow chart and tables completed in the same page ..with the correction needed in your Draft copy of the paper sent to me and deleting ref 14. .

Dear Anowar ,

Pls see your corrctons are not still up to the mark . Do it further for minor modification by shifting and adjusting any of the flow chart and tables completed in the same page .and .with these correction needed in your Draft copy of the paper sent back to me after deleting ref 14. .

Page | 200

I repeatedly told you that any flow chart or table can not be kept half in one page and rest part in next page . You have to keep one flow chart completely in the same page only to finish it.

So further adjust it with shifting some part of written word text in pages where flow chart or tables are spread in two pages instead of keeping it within the sane page , so that you can keep your any one flow chart or tables or figures completed in the same page by shifting text part later from word text .

Do it now and send back again to me immediately

Prof a k samanta

Sent from my Samsung Galaxy smartphone.

----- Original message -----

From: Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>
Date: 5/1/18 9:47 AM (GMT+05:30)
To: "Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta" <ijtakamanta@hotmail.com>
Subject: Re: RE: RE: further minor modification needed in your Draft copy of the paper sent to me .

Dear Respected Sir,
Good Morning

I have added three papers of you in number 1,6 and 7 as well as also added others papers and now total reference is 14.

Related to K/s, I added test method but actually I didn,t add/work with K/s data Light fastness was tested from Intertek whatever I got from them I already included.

Thanks for your kind attention
Md. Anowar Hossain

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

On Monday, April 30, 2018, 11:35:10 AM GMT+6, Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com> wrote:

Dear Anowar,

I have gone through your paper . Add atleast 4 to 5 more reference of my published papers in natural dyeing (you can get my papers on natural dyeing by search in google search by my name and yopics natural dyeing) mentioning those in literature review given in introduction part , when I am one Of the author at the end .there are space left also.

Moreover, add test methods of k/ s and colour fastness adding two three lines for each with test std nos to be given. Do it now.

Moreover some flowchart and some tables are broken covering two pages. Adjust them in one pages only (no table or figure or flowchary should be spread over two consecutive pages. Do this by shifting write up part from here to there si that those tables and any of the flow chart is spread over in one page only, not to spread in next page.

Do this again and resend it by today. Save it in word format 1997-2003 format in .doc version so that I can edit if require. I have to add one OR TWO more authorS If you have no objection.

Thanks .

Prof a k samanta

Sent from my Samsung Galaxy smartphone.

----- Original message -----

From: Anowar Hossain <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

Date: 4/30/18 10:17 AM (GMT+05:30)

To: "Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta" <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>

Subject: Re: RE: A Draft copy of my one paper

Dear Respected Sir,

Good Morning

As per your comments I have decided to publish this work into two small papers whatever already sent to you. Please check the the one of two

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

papers which one is designed as per paper format and improved. Please confirm my understanding of proceeding one paper and find it from attachment.

Thanks and Regards

Page | 202

Md. Anowar Hossain

On Sunday, April 29, 2018, 6:34:14 PM GMT+6, Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com> wrote:

Dear Anowar ,

Yes . Now recd it. But I am wondering that you have sent it in project report form without working on it again to covert it in paper form. Same you did in your m tech thesis paper. A lot of work and editing I had to do then to convert that in paper form . Make it similar conversion to paper form as per your aascit paper published which you have copy and send me it by tomorrow.

Be serious if want to make carrier in teaching and research. Go to google scholar and search some of our paper on natural dyes and add those in references .

Literature review part to be written shortly as people does in paper form . Results and discussion part need to be elaborated as per observations and giving their explanation. Abstrat to be made relevant mentioning what is done and what are observed citing major results. So is the conclusions stating only main findings . Follow aascit papers of yours already published with me on fragrance finishing. Make it within 11 to 12 pages or nearer not 26 to 30 pages.

Another paper you send me within another two days afyer such modifucation and corrections and conversions. Do not send me in project report form of students .

Hope you undrrstand. I have no time to make such conversion or correction or ediyng the whole.

Thank you
Prof a k Samanta

Sent from my Samsung Galaxy smartphone.
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Date: 4/29/18 5:45 PM (GMT+05:30)
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Thanks and Regards
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To: me · Tue, May 1, 2018 at 11:15 AM

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Prof a k samanta

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Hide trimmed content

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**Thanks and Regards
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Dear Anowar ,

Yes . Now recd it. But I am wondering that you have sent it in project report form without working on it again to covert it in paper form. Same you did in your m tech thesis paper. A lot of work and editing I had to do then to convert that in paper form . Make it similar conversion to paper form as per your aascit paper published which you have copy and send me it by tomorrow.

Be serious if want to make carrier in teaching and research. Go to google scholar and search some of our paper on natural dyes and add those in references .

Literature review part to be written shortly as people does in paper form . Results and discussion part need to be elaborated as per observations and giving their explanation. Abstrat to be made relevant mentioning what is done and what are observed citing major results. So is the conclusions stating only main findings . Follow aascit papers of yours already published with me on fragrance finishing. Make it within 11 to 12 pages or nearer not 26 to 30 pages.

Another paper you send me within another two days afyer such modifucation and corrections and conversions. Do not send me in project report form of students .

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Subject: A Draft copy of my one paper

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Thanks and Regards
Md. Anowar Hossain

Send me draft papers of you for publication . I shall try to publish it.

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta
To: me · Sun, Apr 29, 2018 at 12:10 PM

Message Body

Dear anowar ,

I have not received any draft paper from you.

Send me small two papers instead of one .

I shall try to publish it in some on line foreign journal .

Thank you
Prof a k samanta

Re: Information about Ph.D admission

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta
To: me · Thu, Nov 30, 2017 at 2:15 PM

Message Body

Dear Anawar,

It is difficult to include your name this time as per committee members view for your poor response in interview. Still you can talk with prof s k ghosh.

So I can not do anything now. Do not copy or forward my mail to anybody as this information are unofficial and is for you only .

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; defence research organization; public service, crime, human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Hope you understand . Still you mail and talk with hod for final decision of the committee.

Wish you best luck .

Thanks

Prof a k samanta

Fw: preparation regarding the interview on 8th November, 2017

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: me · Tue, Oct 24, 2017 at 5:51 PM

Message Body

Dear Anowar ,

1 Your schedule is ok and so far there is no change of date and time of interview.

2. Yes , you will have to carry all original main certificates and marksheets fromm 12th class to M Tech final sem for showing and verification during interview and it is mandatory even for all former student.

3. Regarding further interview preparation, you shouldable to explain plan of work , what I Gave it to you for scholarship application and it is to be carried in hand with a spare copy to submit after interview on 8th November, 2017.

Thanks and wish you good luck .

More when we will meet.

Prof A K Samanta

27 Evidence of peer review and publication process of MTech thesis and/or MPhil/PhD⁰ thesis at University of Calcutta, India

FW: Notice of Publication of Your Paper 8910853 from AASCIT

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: me, and 3 others · Sat, Aug 27, 2016 at 3:10 PM

Message Body

Dear Anowar & Kashmita,

Please find the following link to get your published Paper downloaded from AASCIT Journal of Materials Sciences and Applications Vol-2 No. 4, Page-25-34, 2016 for your record.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

Congratulation for publishing your nice work in such a reputed International Journal of USA.

Keep it up.
Thanks,
(Prof. A K Samanta)
Professor

From: aascit002@gmail.com
Date: Sat, 27 Aug 2016 16:21:48 +0800
Subject: Notice of Publication of Your Paper 8910853 from AASCIT
To: kashmita.bh@gmail.com; ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

Dear kashmita bhattacharya,

Good day.

Thanks very much for your great contribution to AASCIT.

We are writing to inform you that your paper 8910853 entitled *Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric* has been published in *Journal of Materials Sciences and Applications*.

You can pay a visit to the following links:
<http://www.aascit.org/journal/archive2?journalId=891&paperId=4459>

Up to now, there are some Members and authors have organized events about call-for-paper for American Association for Science and Technology (AASCIT) and invited many friends and colleagues to submit paper to AASCIT.

So if it's convenience to you, could you please write some letters about call-for-paper for AASCIT?

After you write submission invitations, for one thing, hope you can send them to your friends and colleagues, for another, you can send them to us.

If you, your friends and colleagues have submitted papers successfully, just contact us, we'll pay attention to them.

We sincerely hope that we can build up long-term cooperation and we will receive more excellent papers from you and your colleagues in the near future.

Best regards,

Lee
Editorial assistant
American Association for Science and Technology
<http://www.aascit.org>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- kashmita.bh@gmail.com

To: me · Mon, Aug 29, 2016 at 2:54 PM

Message Body

Dear Anowar,

Thanks for your acknowledgement.

I wish all success in your coming life.

With best wishes

Kashmita

FW: Paper submission in AASCIT

- Prof. Ashis Kumar Samanta

To: me, and 1 other · Mon, Aug 1, 2016 at 2:29 PM

Message Body

Dr. Bagchi & Anowar,

Please find the full corrected paper submitted to AASCIT USA in journal of Material Science and Application.

The details are given below:

Paper title: Simultaneous dyeing and aroma finishing of cotton fabric.

Journal Title: Journal of Material Sciences and Applications

Manuscript No.: 8910853

Please follow up your paper.

Thanks,

Prof. A K Samanta

Professor

28 Cited author's achievement in research and personal details of author

Sole author, Chief Director, PhD Research; Chief Director, Defence and Law research Centre; Chief Researcher, Textile, Color, and Material Research Centre, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287> Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.); [16] [6, 10, 12, 14, 15, 17, 18, 20, 59, 61, 70, 74, 76, 85-88, 142-148] [149] [149] [13, 150-153] [1-3, 8, 9, 13, 17, 19-21, 23-26, 28-57, 62, 63, 65, 68, 69, 71-73, 75, 77-84, 89, 91-106, 108-140, 142-148, 150-182] name of father: late Dr. Md. Abdur Rashid, medical practitioner; permanent residence (PR): village: Purbo Nuthurchar, post office: K. Mohonpur (1990), police station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia (PR by birth); nationality, national ID, passport and birth registration number: Bangladeshi, 19862692620993890, A15988852/EE0444946/AF3831770, 003236; PhD (doctor of philosophy) application ID: 2612540, PhD student ID: 3820066, program name: DR213, PhD (fashion and textiles), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; lecturer on textile engineering (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

29 Legal authorization and signing

2 March 2026

(Md. Anowar Hossain)

Signature (scanned)

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.); Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc & PhD in Applied Law; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, and BSc Engineering in Textile Technology

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.

Office of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; Defence Scientist; Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc & PhD in Applied Law; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, and BSc Engineering in Textile Technology

29.1 Research address and contact since 2020

512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile Phone: +8801788396264

29.2 Permanent Address

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, Post Office: K. Mohonpur (1990), Police Station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh (by birth)

29.3 Professional Address

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, Mobile phone: +8801788396264

29.4 Pictorial evidence of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

30 Author contribution and authorship status of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

The author has contribution in conceptualization, visualization, resource, self-supervision, funding acquisition, project administration, research communications, planning and prediction, analysis, writing the original draft, manuscript editing, and publication process. The scholarship or funder has no scholarly role of the design of research, research idea or visualization, research and innovation, drafting of manuscript, editing of manuscript, and publication of manuscript.

31 Declaration of conflicting interests

The author declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

32 Funding

The author received no financial support for the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

33 Judicial compliances of using name, people, and organization in the thesis

1. The protection philosophy of the individual person.
2. The protection philosophy of the individual organization.
3. The protection philosophy of the peoples.
4. The protection philosophy of the community.
5. The protection philosophy of academia and philosophia.
6. The protection philosophy of the ethical liability of author.
7. The protection philosophy of the researcher liability of author since 2006.
8. The protection philosophy of the professor (Dr.) liability of author.
9. The protection philosophy of the defence scientist (Dr.) liability of author.
10. The protection philosophy of the barrister (Dr.) liability of author.
11. The protection philosophy of the universities.
12. The protection philosophy of the PhD industries.
13. The protection philosophy of the scholar and scientist community.
14. The protection philosophy of the professor community.
15. The protection philosophy of the government wealth.
16. The protection philosophy of the higher education and research.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

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17. The protection philosophy of the engineering education.
18. The protection philosophy of the personal wealth.
19. The protection philosophy of the scholarly wealth.
20. The protection philosophy of the PhD compliance.
21. The protection philosophy of the judicial compliance in academia and philosophia.
22. The protection philosophy of the peace surviving in the planet.

34 Data availability

All data generated during the coalescing of this article are included, attached and briefly cited in reference list.

35 Glossaries

Cancer: a destructive way of academia and philosophia.

God father: words of philosophy who applies non-judicial power of administration.

PhD¹: first PhD of author.

PhD²: second PhD of author.

PhD³: third PhD of author.

Second God: words of philosophy who applies non-judicial power of administration.

360⁰ theory of target: a multi-dimensional target of criminal

36 Professional excellency of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,

engr.anowar@yahoo.com

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8268846>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13240.32001>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360586>

Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

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Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>

Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11516770>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an international standard University.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>

Invitation of law researchers in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30060.63369>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16995119>

Invitation of legal client for legal service to individual and/or organization.

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Invitation of researchers in textile engineering in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17215.57765>

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37 Following updated online links are remarked in the professional profile of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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38 A copy of this online publication is being forwarded (randomly sequenced) to satisfy knowledge transfer requirement

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Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in technology and law

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Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

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Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTEch in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8239492>.

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Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

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59. Hossain, M.A., *Garments Technology for Merchandiser and Fashion Designer*, ISBN- 978-984-35-2883-4, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh. 2010, Rupok Publications, 140, Islamia market, Nilkhet, Dhaka, 2010 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844933>.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

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(engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au)
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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in technology and law

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*

Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*

Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia

A prestigious research practitioner (RP) in technology, academic, and law since 2006

International Professor and consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, Higher Education, PhD, & Postdoc)

BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime, human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia

Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh

Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD

Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh

Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India

Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au

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Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

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[http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849;](http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849)
[https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583.](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583)

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTEch in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in technology and law

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*

Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia

A prestigious research practitioner (RP) in technology, academic, and law since 2006
International Professor and consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, Higher Education, PhD, & Postdoc)
BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; defence research organization; public service, crime, human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD
Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

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96. Hossain, M.A., *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-05)*. 2023, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia;
 (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23045.93929>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137396>.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), M.Tech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in technology and law

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
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BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime, human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

97. Hossain, M.A., *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-06)*. 2023, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27723.57120>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146631>.
98. Hossain, M.A., *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01)*. 2023, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>.
99. Hossain, M.A., *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02)*. 2023, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/0WXXVkgicfKg>.
100. Hossain, M.A., *Decision of RMIT University against Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye did a conspiracy to kill Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD candidate, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University; Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain faced hidden conspiracy of life threatening and notified to Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor and delegate, RMIT University 2023, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Australia* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33536.61441>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8317924>.
101. Hossain, M.A., *Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . 2023, RMIT University,*

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

- Melbourne, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8315574>.
102. Hossain, M.A., *PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform*. 2023: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8254280>.
103. Hossain, M.A., *Reporting to Tertiary Education Quality & Standards Agency of Australian Government for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship*. . 2023: School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University; 25 Dawson Street, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>.
104. Hossain, M.A., *Reporting for psychologist involvement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University as per office order of RMIT University, Australia*. 2023: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11792.99846>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8330262>.
105. Hossain, M.A., *Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019*, R.U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, Editor. 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13431.39840>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8280942>.
106. Hossain, M.A., *Reporting to Victoria Legal Aid, Australia for the grant of legal assistance for ethical defending for the peace in PhD education against conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD School*. 2023, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8320778>.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), M.Tech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia

Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh

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Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh

Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

107. Hossain, M.A., Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection. 2023, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286908>.
108. Hossain, M.A., Reporting to Honorable Minister, Department of Home Affairs, Australia and delegates for activation and extension of VISA of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University until the final order of Australian Supreme Court, Australian human rights commission and chief authorities of Australian Government relates to PhD harassment and conspiracy of life-threatening of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. 2023, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, engr.anowar@yahoo.com <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.17927>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8336839>.
109. Hossain, M.A., Self-declared certificate on PhD (Fashion & Textiles). 2023: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30457.65123>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286788>.
110. Hossain, M.A., Self-declared certificate on Professor (Textile Engineering). 2023: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36591.82084>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275164>.
111. Hossain, M.A., Self-declared certificate on Scientist (Camouflage Physics), R.U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, Editor. 2023: Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13103.71848>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275143>.
112. Hossain, M.A., Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Bangladeshi Passport No: EE0444946; Bangladeshi Address: Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh is reporting life-threatening conspiracy to Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Australian High Commissioner to Bangladesh located at 184 Gulshan Avenue, Gulshan, Dhaka, Bangladesh. 2023: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28153.24164>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10025287>.
113. Hossain, M.A., Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, R.U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, Editor. 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13431.39840>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8280942>.
114. Hossain, M.A., Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform, R.U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com), Editor. 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

115. Hossain, M.A., *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform*, R.U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh, Editor. 2023
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>.
116. Hossain, M.A., *Reporting and filing to High Court of Australia for court hearing & court writ of life-threatening conspiracy to kill PhD researcher and artificial killing conspiracy of PhD dream of a PhD scholar in a prestigious platform of PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia*. 2023: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20689.30567>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10986579>.
117. Hossain, M.A., *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking necessary action by the Australian crime commission act (ACC), 2002; 7A, 7C and/or relevant act of criminal investigation in PhD school*. 2023, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26327.04002>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10116196>.
118. Hossain, M.A., *Non-paid salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University submitted for approval of Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia*. 2023, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27962.16328>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10132457>.
119. Hossain, M.A., *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking free of cost legal action to high court of Australia and/or fully funded PhD Scholarship for every cost of high court of Australia*. 2023, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27057.76642>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10182345>.
120. Hossain, M.A., *50% income support and 100% life-safety compensation were requested and proposed to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University for 63 years duration under calculation of 100 years life-time of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist*. 2023, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29528.47360>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159331>.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTEch in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia

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Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh

Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India

Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd, Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

121. Hossain, M.A., *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world.* 2023, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; 12 December 2023; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13240.32001>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360586>.
122. Hossain, M.A., *Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government.* 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14776.72967>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>.
123. Hossain, M.A., *Cyber securities for protection of cyber-crimes.* 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14367.98729>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841349>.
124. Hossain, M.A., *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Dhaka for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.* 2024 <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36388.08325>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841964>.
125. Hossain, M.A., *Letter to Nobel Committee for Nobel Prize in Peace.* 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35129.79208>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842361>.
126. Hossain, M.A., *Letter to Nobel committee for Nobel prize in camouflage physics.* 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36807.51367>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842435>.
127. Hossain, M.A., *A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school.* 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964382>.
128. Hossain, M.A., *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor.* 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

129. Hossain, M.A., Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'. 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>.
130. Hossain, M.A., Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>.
131. Hossain, M.A., Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is asking an exemption of visa fees for the 'Australian global talent permanent residence visa (subclass 858)' under the Australian migration act 45C (c), 1958 and 500.211, 1994. 2024: Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25869.14560>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12754106>.
132. Hossain, M.A., Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs. 2024: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>.
133. Hossain, M.A., Research services, journal peer reviews, and editorial support of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist. 2024: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15157.90080>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13142538>.
134. Hossain, M.A., Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of 'free of cost google drive (2TB) access' to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com. 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28761.94568>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13994976>.
135. Hossain, M.A., Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education. 2024: School of Fashion

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTEch in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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International Professor and consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, Higher Education, PhD, & Postdoc) BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime, human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia

Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh

Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh

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Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);

Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh

Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India

Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design

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Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix

Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and

University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699107>.

136. Hossain, M.A., Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school. 2025, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14934539>.
137. Hossain, M.A., Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching for the prestigious 'best researcher award' under the provisional nomination of organizing committee, research scientist awards of Indian government. 2025, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com): School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36413.17128>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064119>.
138. Hossain, M.A., Local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country. 2025: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28463.85929>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826808>.
139. Hossain, M.A., Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia to United Nations. 2025: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 24 October 2025. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21791.21922>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17430696>.
140. Hossain, M.A., Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre. 2025: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24765.32485>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16961335>.
141. Hossain, M.A., Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University. 2023, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12742364>.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

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 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

142. Hossain, M.A., *Evaluation of Camouflage Coloration of Polyamide-6,6 Fabric by Comparing Simultaneous Spectrum in Visible and Near-Infrared Region for Defense Applications, in Colorimetry*, A.K. Samanta, Editor. 2021, IntechOpen: London, United Kingdom. p. 1-22 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.101537>.
143. Hossain, M.A., *Simulation of chromatic and achromatic assessments for camouflage textiles and combat background*. Journal of Defense Modeling and Simulation: Applications, Methodology, Technology, 2022. 10.1177/15485129211067759: p. 1-16 <https://doi.org/10.1177/15485129211067759>.
144. Hossain, A., *Spectral simulation and method design of camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral imaging in UV-Vis-IR against multidimensional combat background*. The Journal of the Textile Institute, 2021. 10.1080/00405000.2022.2027074: p. 1-12 <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405000.2022.2027074>.
145. Hossain, M.A., *Adaptive Camouflage Textiles with Thermochromic Colorant and Liquid Crystal for Multidimensional Combat Background, a Technical Approach for Advancement in Defence Protection*. American Journal of Materials Engineering and Technology, 2021. 9(1): p. 31-47 <http://pubs.sciepub.com/materials/9/1/3/>.
146. Hossain, M.A., *Camouflage Assessment Of Aluminium Coated Textiles for Woodland and Desertland Combat Background in Visible and Infrared Spectrum under UV-Vis-IR Background Illumination*. Defence Science Journal, 2022. 72(3): p. 359-370 <https://publications.drdo.gov.in/ojs/index.php/dsj/article/view/17731/7785>.
147. Hossain, A., *Concealment, Detection, Recognition, and Identification of Target Signature on Water Background under Natural Illumination*. International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations, 2021. 10(117): p. 1-11 <http://www.ijsei.com/papers/ijsei-1011721-01.pdf>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242827>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10885.32487>.
148. Hossain, M.A., *Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV-Visible-IR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging*. Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square 2023. 10.21203/rs.3.rs-2298847/v1: p. 1-18 <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2298847/v1>.
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150. Hossain, M.A. *Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds*. in 5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Accepted on 28 March 2023. 2023. Valencia, Spain <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22550.73282>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844652>.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,10,000 USD

Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime, human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
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Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

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152. Hossain, M.A., *Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums*. MRS Communications 2023. 10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3
<https://doi.org/10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3>.
153. Hossain, M.A., *Neuro-camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking*. Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square, 2023. 10.21203/rs.3.rs-2710224/v1
<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2710224/v1>.
154. Hossain, M.A. *Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Background*. in Presented in humanities and social context conference, second milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University; 15 February 2022. 2022. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Melbourne, Australia; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844729>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32252.92803>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844729>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32252.92803>.
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28897.48488>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844692>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28897.48488>.
156. Hossain, M.A. *An optical platform of material engineering for design of camouflage product against multidimensional combat backgrounds from 400 nm to 2500 nm*. in Scholars World Congress on Material Science and Nanotechnology" (MatScience 2023), Accepted on 18 April 2023. 2023. Paris, France <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844597>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28176.28165>.
157. Hossain, M.A. *Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds*. in Global Summit on Chemical Engineering and Catalysis (ISTRCEC 2023), accepted on 20 March 2023. 2023. Rome, Italy <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7847802>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23969.17766>.
158. Hossain, M.A., *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination, PhD student: 3820066, First milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy, in School of fashion and Textiles*. 2023, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus,

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

- Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>,
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161. Hossain, M.A. *My first presentation at PhD School for selection of PhD research proposal on camouflage textiles in 2020*. in Academic conference at PhD School. 2020. School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Australia, Vic-3056, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7918250>,
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33383.11680>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7918250>.
162. Hossain, M.A., *First Action and Support Plan at PhD School during COVID-19 in 2020*, Supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks. 2023, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Australia, Vic-3056, <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26567.68006>,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7923009>
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26567.68006>,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7923009>.
163. Hossain, M.A., *Neuro-Camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking*. Journal of Applied Material Science & Engineering Research, 2023. 7(1): p. 67-71
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13401.90729>.
164. Hossain, M.A., *Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM) incorporated with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials for special workers and extreme weather conditions*. School of Fashions and Textiles, RMIT University, Victoria 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com), 2023. 10.13140/RG.2.2.32289.79204 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8112357>,
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32289.79204>.
165. Hossain, M.A., *Presentation on Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds*, PhD student: 3820066, RMIT University. 2023: School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29042.48322;>

[https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048.](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048)

166. Hossain, M.A. Md. Anowar Hossain, Video presentation of Anowar Hossain's PhD invention in PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. 2023; Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21104.43524>.
167. Hossain, M.A., Application for promotion as Professor (Textile Engineering) and/or right adjustment of my designation under consideration of my Curriculum Vitae (CV), publications and teaching experiences under the promotion act of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh; supported by the act of University Grants Commission of Bangladesh, Dhaka, Bangladesh. 2023 [http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35245.05606;](http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35245.05606) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286913>.
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Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 2 March 2026.

- Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25967.41129>;
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175. Hossain, M.A., Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world. 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>.
 176. Hossain, M.A., Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an international standard University. 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814275>.
 177. Hossain, M.A., Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research. 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>;
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 178. Hossain, M.A., A self-understanding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist about Bangladeshi Nobel laureate Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus and law implementation of Bangladesh Government. 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 5 January 2024. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26912.35846>;
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36325.61929>;
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 180. Hossain, M.A., Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist, in Scholarly Community Encyclopedia. 2023 <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49098>;
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15550150>.

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Author's biography since 1986: Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

182. Hossain, M.A., *Invitation of legal client for legal service to individual and/or organization*. 2025: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13073.70249>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16990186>.

Expected position: chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher/vice-chancellor/chief vice-chancellor/chancellor/chief scientist/research director (tech)/chief director (R & D), and chief executive officer; **professional experience since 2006:** 19-20 years; **monthly expected salary (full-time):** 1,00,000 USD

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Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric

A thesis published in fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of
**MPhil in Textile Technology or Doctor of Philosophy in Textile Technology
(Technical Textiles)**

Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta
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Dr. Arindam Bagchi, Senior Research Fellow

Type of publication and online display since 2015

Year of research: 2014-2016

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Author's biography since 1986

Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, *Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection* [Biodata].

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

1 Personal profile and professional achievement of author since 2006

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2 Research and publication practice centre since 2006

Chief Researcher and Founder⁶; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁵; Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; study leave approved by City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh.

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Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)³; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre³; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; research product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

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Table 1. Evidences of scholarly witness and research publications to satisfy the PhD¹ requirement of research to issue PhD¹ certificate from University of Calcutta, India and/or Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur under the registration of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, University of Calcutta, India in 2015 in terms of chain extension of MTech research and study[1].

SN	Title of publications	Journal (online)	DOI/ID	Author and author type	Registered supervisor/peer reviewer, scholarly witness, external witness
1.	Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of	Journal of Materials	10.13140/RG.2.2.16757.35048	Professor Dr. Engr. Md.	Professor (Dr.) Ashis Kumar

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

	Cotton Fabric, 2(4), 25-34 [2].	Sciences and Applications		Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Samanta, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, Dr. Kashmita Bhattacharya, Dr. Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik, CU, India
2.	Cyclodextrin for Aroma Finishing on Textile Substrate-A Review Article, 2019. 8(89) [3].	International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations	10.5281/zenodo.8242756	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, CU, India
3.	Textile coloration and fragrance finishing for perfumed garments [Textile Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-70019, West Bengal, India][4].	MTech Thesis	10.13140/RG.2.2.15918.48965; 10.5281/zenodo.7854437	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, CU, India
4.	Integrated dyeing and cosmetic finishing on cotton fabric 6th all India Inter Engineering college academic meet-2015 and Science & Technology exhibition for a sustainable society, Organised by Forum of Scientist, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET), 15N, Nelli Sengupta Sarani (Lindsay Street), Kolkata-7000087, India [5].	Conference	10.13140/RG.2.2.29340.2624; 10.5281/zenodo.13304637	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, CU, India Professor (Dr.) Swapon Kumar Gosh (conference support) CU, India
5.	Anowar's Handbook on Advance Textile Technology School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25	Preprint book ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.35648.8576; 10.5281/zenodo.15068136	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain,	Self

Author's biography since 1986

Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata].

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	Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35 Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India (enr.anowar@yahoo.com) [6]	Searching 'Chief Professor/ Chief Scientist' category fund to accomplish the book		RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	
6.	Power Point Presentation on Applications and Engineering of Geotextiles (Department of Textile Engineering, City university, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh (enr.anowar@yahoo.com, Issue; 2015 [7, 8].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.1 7899.3152; 10.5281/zenodo.83 11345	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Self
7.	Power Point Presentation on Combined dyeing and cosmetic finishing of woven cotton fabric for garments (Department of Jute and Fibre technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, India, Issue; 2015 [9]	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.2 8804.5056; 10.5281/zenodo.83 11367	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, CU, India
8.	Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India, 2013-2015 [10].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.1 2565.0944; 10.5281/zenodo.15 068327	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Self
9.	Product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments[11]	ResearchGate Zenodo Journal of Dr. Anowar	10.13140/RG.2.2.2 5123.92967; 10.5281/zenodo.18 885116	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India

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				sole author; chief researcher	
10.	<i>A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020)</i> R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh [12]	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.16273.08801; 10.5281/zenodo.17389964	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT University, Australia.
11.	A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre, 2019. 3(1): p. 1-3 [13].	International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering	10.29011/IJTSE-126/100026; 10.13140/RG.2.2.36811.36648; 10.5281/zenodo.8245079	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India; Prof. (Dr.) Md. Nurul Abser, JU, Bangladesh; Dr. Ferdous Ara Dilruba, BJRI, Bangladesh
12.	Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent, 2018. 2(2): p. 1-8 [14].	Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing	MS.ID: 000132	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India

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				sole author; chief researcher	
13.	Non-toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric using Non-toxic Colorant and Nontoxic Crosslinker, 2018. 8(5): p. 1-5 [15].	Journal of Textile Science & Engineering	10.4172/2165-8064.1000374	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India; Dr. Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik, CU, India; Dr. Padma S. Vankar, IIT, India; Dr. Dhara Shukla, IIT, India
14.	Organic Colouration and Antimicrobial Finishing of Organic Cotton Fabric by Exploiting Distillated Organic Extraction of Organic Tectona grandis and Azadirachta indica with Organic Mordanting Compare to Conventional Inorganic Mordants, 2018. 2018(1): p. 1-12[16].	International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering	10.29011/IJTSE-113/100013	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India; Dr. Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik, CU, India; Dr. Padma S. Vankar, IIT, India; Dr. Dhara Shukla, IIT, India
15.	Pollution Free Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted from Swietenia macrophylla and Musa Acuminata as Unpolluted Dyes and Citrus. Limon (L.) as Unpolluted Mordanting Agent, 2018, 3(2): p. 1-8[17].	Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology	10.31031/TTEFT.2018.03.000558	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India; Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, CU, Bangladesh
16.	A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles, Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments (pp. 151-170) [18].	IntechOpen	10.5772/intechopen.92360	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India;
17.	Zero Toxic Approach of Cotton Fabric Coloration with Botanical Waste resource via Psidium P. guajava (Guava Leaves) as Natural Dyes and Citrus Lemon (Lemon Leaves) as Natural Mordanting Agent. 2019; [19].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.18112.75524	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India Prof. (Dr.) Md. Nurul Abser, JU, Bangladesh

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Table 2. Charted overview of research and publications in five-years duration (full-time) PhD^{2*} and in textile technology, technical textiles & color Engineering; a thesis for Nobel prize¹ in physics and/or camouflage physics and/or color physics, 2020-2026 [1].

SN	Title of publications	Journal/ preprint/ conference (online)	DOI/ISSN	Author and author type	Registered Supervisor and/or scholarly witness
1.	Advancement in UV-Vis-IR camouflage Textiles for concealment of defense surveillance against multidimensional combat background; 2024, 19:45, P: 1-38 [20].	Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Engineering, Springer; Research Square	10.1186/s40712-024-00182-8	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
2.	Adaptive Camouflage Textiles with Thermochromic Colorant and Liquid Crystal for Multidimensional Combat Background, a Technical Approach for Advancement in Defence Protection; 9(1), 31-47, 2021 [21]	American Journal of Materials Engineering and Technology; Published by Science and Education Publishing	10.12691/materials-9-1-3	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
3.	Simulation of chromatic and achromatic assessments for camouflage textiles and combat background, 2022, 1-16 [22].	Journal of Defense Modeling and Simulation: Applications, Methodology, Technology; Sage	10.1177/15485129211067759	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia

				sole author; chief researcher	
4.	Spectral simulation and method design of camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral imaging in UV-Vis-IR against multidimensional combat background, 1-12, 2021 [23]	The Journal of the Textile Institute; Taylor & Francis	10.1080/00405000.2022.2027074	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
5.	Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums, 3 April 2023; Volume 13, Pages: 306-319 [24]	MRS Communication s; Springer	10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
6.	Concealment, Detection, Recognition, and Identification of Target Signature on Water Background under Natural Illumination, 10(117), 1-11, Article 1011721-01, 2021 [25]	International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations; ISSN: 2251-8843	10.5281/zenodo.8242827 ; 10.13140/RG.2.2.10885.32487 Paper ID: 1011721-01	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
7.	Evaluation of Camouflage Coloration of Polyamide-6,6 Fabric by Comparing Simultaneous Spectrum in Visible and Near-Infrared Region for Defense Applications; (pp. 1-22); 2022 [26]	Colorimetry; IntechOpen	10.5772/intechopen.101537	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia

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8.	Coloration of polyamide-6,6 fabric with carbon black nano particle for camouflage textiles of simultaneous spectrum probe in visible and near infrared [27].	Advance Research in Textile Engineering, Austin Publishing Group.	10.13140/R.G.2.2.36504.98560; 10.5281/zenodo.8297554	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
9.	Camouflage Assessment Of Aluminium Coated Textiles for Woodland and Desertland Combat Background in Visible and Infrared Spectrum under UV-Vis-IR Background Illumination, 1 July 2022; 72(3), 359-370 [28]	Defence Science Journal	10.14429/dsj.72.17731	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
10.	UV-Visible-NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection, 28 March 2023, 13:5021 [29]	Scientific Reports, Nature	10.1038/s41598-023-31725-2	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
11.	Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV-Visible-IR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging; Preprint (Version 1); 11 May 2023; 1-15 [30]	Heliyon Research Square	10.21203/rs.3.rs-2298847/v1	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia

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				sole author; chief researcher	
12.	Ecofriendly Camouflage Textiles with Natural Sand-based Silicon Dioxide against Simultaneous Combat Background of Woodland, Desertland, Rockland, Concreteland and Water/Marine. Preprint (Version 1) [30].	Research Square	10.21203/rs.3.rs-2359705/v1	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
13.	Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination (Presented in academic conference, First milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University, 12 February 2021, Issue [31].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7844692 ; 10.13140/R G.2.2.28897. 48488	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
14.	My first presentation at PhD School for selection of PhD research proposal on camouflage textiles in 2020. Academic conference at PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Australia, Vic-3056 [32].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7918250 ; 10.13140/R G.2.2.33383. 11680	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
15.	Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Background (Presented in humanities and social context conference, second milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University; 15 February 2022, Issue [33].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.32252. 92803; 10.5281/zenodo.7844729	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia

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16.	Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds (5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Accepted on 28 March 2023; Valencia, Spain, Issue [34].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.22550. 73282; 10.5281/zen odo.7844652	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
17.	Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds (Global Summit on Chemical Engineering and Catalysis (ISTRCEC 2023), accepted on 20 March 2023; Rome, Italy, Issue [35].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.5281/zen odo.7847802 ; 10.13140/R G.2.2.23969. 17766	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
18.	Advancement in UV-Visible-IR Camouflage Textiles and Camouflage Physics; 2023 [36]	Scholarly Community Encyclopedia	10.13140/R G.2.2.34177. 43368; 10.5281/zen odo.1020838 4 ID: 49095	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
19.	Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination, PhD student: 3820066, First milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus,	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.15701. 50403, 10.5281/zen odo.7898541	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia

	Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021] [37].			sole author; chief researcher	
20.	Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, Second milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022] [38].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.15701. 50403, 10.5281/zen odo.7898707	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
21.	Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University [39].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.29936. 23048; 10.5281/zen odo.1428206 3	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
22.	Conference Presentation on "Camouflage Engineering and Camouflage Textiles for Defence Technology"; 2023 Philippine Textile Congress, Future Thinking for Philippine Textiles, Philippine Textile Research Institute (PTRI), Department of Science and Technology-Central Office (DOST-CO), General Santos Avenue Bicutan, Taguig City, Metro Manila, 1631, Philippine; Speaker during the Textile for Human Security and Defense Session (Session 8) of the Congress on 20 November 2023; Accepted [40].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.19380. 22407; 10.5281/zen odo.1011734 0	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
23.	First Action and Support Plan at PhD School during COVID-19 in 2020, Supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks [41].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.26567. 68006, 10.5281/zen odo.7923009	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia

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				sole author; chief researcher	
24.	My declaration, acknowledgement and dedication to achieve PhD degree (Fashion & Textiles) on “camouflage textiles with technical coloration and incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds” [Textile Engineering, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021] [42].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.18532. 65925; 10.5281/zen odo.7898850	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
25.	An optical platform of material engineering for design of camouflage product against multidimensional combat backgrounds from 400 nm to 2500 nm (Scholars World Congress on Material Science and Nanotechnology” (MatScience 2023), Accepted on 18 April 2023, Issue [43].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.5281/zen odo.7844597 ; 10.13140/R G.2.2.28176. 28165	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
26.	Power Point Presentation on Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Vis-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds (5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Issue [44].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.5281/zen odo.8298582	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
27.	Power Point Presentation on Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds (School of fashion and	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.5281/zen odo.8311145	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain,	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert

Author's biography since 1986

Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata].

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

	Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022, Issue [45].			RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Shanks; RMIT, Australia
28.	Presentation on Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, RMIT University [45]	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.29042.48322; 10.5281/zenodo.8146048	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
29.	Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain. Scholarly Community Encyclopedia [46].	ResearchGate	10.13140/R G.2.2.34177.43368; 10.5281/zenodo.10208384; ID: 9098	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
30.	Video presentation of Anwar Hossain's PhD invention in PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. In. School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia [47]	ResearchGate	10.13140/R G.2.2.21104.43524	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
31.	Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of “Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist” on “Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds” School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick,	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.36270.32328; 10.5281/zenodo.13182515	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia

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	Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) [48].			sole author; chief researcher	
32.	Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is self-nominating for 'global excellence award' at Functional Textiles and Clothing (FTC), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India under the category of 'Leadership in Research' and/or 'Emerging Innovator' under the invitation of FTC team, IIT, Delhi, India [49].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.36325.61929; 10.5281/zenodo.14213757	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
33.	Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching for the prestigious 'best researcher award' under the provisional nomination of organizing committee, research scientist awards of Indian government [Grant]. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) [50].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.36413.17128; 10.5281/zenodo.15064119	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
34.	A short summery and evidences of Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia [51].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.14593.43368; 10.5281/zenodo.12722555	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
35.	Letter to Nobel committee for Nobel prize in camouflage physics [52].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.36807.51367; 10.5281/zenodo.18231656	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain,	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert

			odo.1084243 5	RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Shanks; RMIT, Australia
36.	Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV-visible-NIR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging (supporting information), M.A. Hossain, Editor. 2026: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au) [53]	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.1847653 3	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
37.	Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV-visible-NIR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging (video of supporting information), M.A. Hossain, Editor. 2026: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au)[54]	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.35535. 14244; 10.5281/zenodo.1848124 6	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia

Table 3. Total contents of the thesis

Description of the contents	Page numbers	Pages with separate numerical sequence
Title page of the thesis	1	
Personal details of author	2	
Personal profile and professional achievement of author since 1986	3	
Relevant research of this first PhD¹ thesis was also studied for second PhD² to satisfy different philosophy at School of fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia (2020-2023)	3	
Research and publication practice centre since 2006	3	
Evidences of scholarly witness and research publications to satisfy the PhD1 requirement of research to issue PhD1 certificate from University of Calcutta, India and/or Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur under the registration of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, University of Calcutta, India in 2015 in terms of chain extension of MTech research and study, 2015-2020	3-8	

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Charted overview of research and publications in five-years duration (full-time) PhD^{2*} and in textile technology, technical textiles & color Engineering; a thesis for Nobel prize¹ in physics and/or camouflage physics and/or color physics, 2020-2026	8-17	
Total contents of the thesis	17-19	
Key themes and prospects of research contribution in terms of multidimensional source of research and future analysis	19	
Keynote of the thesis	19	
Research questions of the thesis	19	
Reference	20-24	
Introduction		
Cyclodextrin for Aroma Finishing on Textile Substrate-A Review	25-43	
Experimentations		
Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric	44-53	
Integrated dyeing and cosmetic finishing on cotton fabric	54-99	
Conclusion		
Product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments	100-402	
Total pages of the thesis	1-402	
This thesis has the attachment of one separate file of PhD situation with the separate title and separate page numbers (Administrative functions of the thesis, PhD expertise of author, thesis development process, judicial functions of the PhD, administrative duty of researchers, evidences and relevant references, relevant approach, comments, and guidelines for PhD industries)		
Judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD ¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia		1-257

Figure 1. Key themes and prospects of research contribution in terms of multidimensional source of research and future analysis

3 Keynote of the thesis

An analysis of medicinal property was experimentally trailed, field trailed, and commercialized for textile encapsulation in terms of cosmetic textiles and/or medical textiles (2014-2016).

4 Research questions and philosophical grounds of the MTech thesis and/or PhD⁰ thesis at University of Calcutta, India (2014-2016)[11]

Reference

1. Hossain, M.A., Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, *Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection*. 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25

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Cyclodextrin for Aroma Finishing on Textile Substrates-A Review

By

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Abstract: Effective implementation of microencapsulation technique and cyclodextrin for the production of cosmetic textiles can be introduced as a technical textiles-based product. α -, β - and γ -cyclodextrin can be applied for the aromatherapeutic textile as host molecule, because it exhibits qualities of controlled release which may be beneficial for the improvement of human life style. Cyclodextrin molecules are capable of forming inclusion compounds with fragrances that fit into the cone-shaped hydrophobic cavity. As a result, the release-fragrance rates are greatly decreased. There are many possibilities for the development of new textile products with advanced properties based on cyclodextrin. Microencapsulation technology is an effective technique used to control the release properties of active ingredients that prolong the functionality of cosmetic textiles. Focusing on the field of cosmetic textiles, the major interest in microencapsulation is currently in the application of attractive fragrances, vitamins, essential oils, skin moisturizing agents, skin cooling agents etc.

Keywords: Cyclodextrin (CD), Aroma Finishing, Microencapsulation, Inclusion complexes, Cotton Fabric

Introduction:

In recent years, textile materials have been found in applications in the cosmetics field. A new sector of

cosmetic textiles is introduced and several commercial cosmetic textile products are currently available in the market. On contact with human body and skin, cosmetic textiles are designed to transfer an active substance for cosmetic purposes. The principle is achieved by simply imparting the cosmetic and pharmaceutical ingredients into the fabric of clothing so that with the natural movement of the body, the skin is slowly freshened and revitalized. Microencapsulation technology is an effective technique used to control the release properties of active ingredients that prolong the functionality of cosmetic textiles.

Aroma finishing as cosmetic textiles have become very attractive innovations resulting from technological advancements represent the best strategy for success in the increasingly competitive textile industry. Fragrance finishing of textile materials has been greatly expanded and used in recent years. Fragrance finishing can be done effectively using exhaust method than any other methods. Recently, fragrances have become available that can be readily formulated into fabrics. Properly designed textiles containing effective, long-lasting fragrances would provide a significant contribution to the textile industry. The proposed research will investigate new fragrance technologies. The fragrance finished fabrics can be used in home textile applications such as wall hangings, table covers, carpets and sofa covers.

Fragrance finishing of textiles is one of the processes which enhance the value of the product by adding various odours to it. The world marketplace is constantly changing and so the demand of consumers is also increased. Everyone

desires for continuous change .i.e. something different and unique. This increase in demand, as well as tremendous competition in the market, opens up opportunities for value addition to all forms of textile materials[1]. The effective change has to be implemented in the market. By this extensive analysis, fragrance finishing is considered as emerging area and which has tumble-down the textile industry with lively value added finish by incorporating different fragrances into fabrics, leading to the production of fragranced fabrics[2]. This proved a good way to meet important emotional and emotional needs, as well as those of a pure and sensorial nature.

The human sense of smell registers not only the quality of different odours but also combines it automatic and often unconsciously with feelings ranging from agreeable to unpleasant. This connection is used in many ways. Perfumed people and merchandise become more attractive and stink bombs are used to the opposite effect. Textiles have a very large specific surface (for example 0.1 to 1 m² g⁻¹). Therefore they attract, adsorb and store various gaseous or volatile substances from their surroundings. This high adsorption capacity can become a problem with unpleasant smelling substances under desorption conditions. Desorption is accelerated by temperature, time and the possibility of gaseous exchange, for example airing. Structure of Dextrin and Cyclodextrin:

The investigation ⁽¹⁾ of US retail sales of home fragrance shows that sales increased 9.7 percent, from \$1.35 billion in 1995 to \$1.96 billion in 1999, and are projected to increase by 7.9 percent to \$2.87 billion in 2004. Pleasure and enjoyment⁽²⁾ on the one hand, is about daring to be different, but also about forgetting stress. Excitement and active wear are a form of communication. ⁽³⁾ The scents of lavender, rose, citrus or vanilla were encapsulated into fabrics, which proved a good way to meet important psychological and emotional needs, as well as those of a purely physical and sensorial nature aromatherapy was coined in the late 1920s by the French cosmetic chemist R.M. Gattefosse,

who noticed the excellent antiseptic properties and skin permeability of essential oils

Dr. Charles Tomasino⁴ reviewed that natural starches are not very soluble in cold water. Cooking is necessary to get the starch granules to form a homogenous solution. Typically the starch granules are stirred in cold water and kept suspended by high speed mixing. As the temperature is raised, water penetrates through the amylopectin membrane solubilizing amylose. The granules swell as more and more water diffuses in enlarging to many times their original dimensions. The viscosity of the solution increases as the granules swell, reaching a maximum at the point where the swollen granules are crowding against each other. Prolonged heating and mechanical shearing cause the swollen granule membrane to rupture allowing the solubilized amylose to spill into the bulk of the solution. At this point the viscosity begins to fall off, finds a stabilized level and remains there. The starch solution can be considered as solubilized amylose molecules intermingled with ruptured swollen fragments of the amylopectin membrane. Dextrine is made by heating dry starch with a mineral acid. White dextrin is made by heating at moderate temperatures and yellow dextrin is made by heating at higher temperatures with less acid. The degree of hydrolysis is higher than for thin boiling starch so dextrine solutions have lower viscosities.

26

Figure-1: Structure of Dextrin⁽⁵⁾

Cyclodextrin: David Rowe reviewed that Corn is the raw material that provides the starch for cyclodextrin production

Figure-2: Microencapsulation of α -cyclodextrin, β -cyclodextrin, γ -cyclodextrin

M. Sundrarajan and Rukmani reviewed⁴ that Cyclodextrins are a group of structurally related natural products formed during bacterial digestion of cellulose. These cyclic oligosaccharides consist of (α -1,4)-linked α -D-glucopyranose units and contain a somewhat lipophilic central cavity and a hydrophilic outer surface. Due to the chair conformation of the glucopyranose units, the cyclodextrins are shaped like a truncated cone rather than perfect cylinders. The hydroxyl functions are orientated to the cone exterior with the primary hydroxyl groups of the sugar residues at the narrow edge of the cone and the secondary hydroxyl groups at the wide edge.

The central cavity is lined by the skeletal carbons and ethereal oxygens of the glucose residues, which gives it a lipophilic character. The polarity of the cavity has been estimated to be similar to that of an aqueous ethanolic solution. The natural α -, β - and γ -cyclodextrin consist of six, seven, and eight glucopyranose units, respectively. The natural cyclodextrins, in particular β -cyclodextrin, are of limited aqueous solubility meaning that complexes resulting from interaction of lipophiles with these cyclodextrin can be of limited solubility resulting in precipitation of solid cyclodextrin complexes from water and other aqueous systems. In fact, the aqueous solubility of the natural cyclodextrins is much lower than that of comparable acyclic saccharides. This is thought to be due to relatively strong intermolecular hydrogen bonding in the crystal state. Substitution of any of the hydrogen bond forming hydroxyl groups, even by lipophilic methoxy functions, results in dramatic improvement

in their aqueous solubility. Cyclodextrin derivatives of pharmaceutical interest include the hydroxypropyl derivatives of β - and γ -cyclodextrin, the randomly methylated β -cyclodextrin, sulfobutylether β -cyclodextrin, and the so-called branched cyclodextrins such as glucosyl- β -cyclodextrin.

The general features of β -cyclodextrin⁽⁷⁾ and their applications in the textile industry have been reviewed. The use of β -cyclodextrin in the textile industry is great significance due to its wide range of application. One of the key aspects is the attachment technique of β -cyclodextrin to the textile's surface. This review deals with this in depth. Some quantification and characterization methods of Textile- β -cyclodextrin are discussed. In the last few years, the new direction in textile research is the functionalization of textile systems. It is believed that β -cyclodextrin will play a very important role in these new developments. β -cyclodextrin can act as a host for various guest molecules. This enables the development of fabrics that release chemical compounds such as fragrances and antimicrobial agents. It is concluded that there are many possibilities for the development of new textile products with advanced properties based on β -cyclodextrin.

⁽⁵⁾ **Table-01: physical properties of Alfa CD, Beta CD, Gama CD, Lamda CD**

Physicochemical properties	Alfa CD	Beta CD	Gama CD	Lamda CD
No of glycopyranose units	6	7	8	9
Central cavity diameter	4.7-5.3	6.0-6.5	7.5-8.3	10.3-11.2
Water solubility at 25°C	14.5	1.85	23.2	8.19
Molecular weight	972	1135	1297	1459

Devinderkaur and Neelam Grewal⁽⁶⁾ reviewed that the cyclodextrin capacity to form inclusion

complexes is known for a long time, this property being used in textile industry to obtain products with applications in increasing wear comfort and realization of medical textiles.

Figure-03: Structure of α -, β - and γ -cyclodextrin
 Cyclodextrins⁽⁸⁾ clamped on cellulose do not affect the cellulose's properties, and cyclodextrins keep their ability to form inclusion complex with other suitable molecules. J. Kotch⁽⁹⁾ reviewed that Complexed with cyclodextrin, perfumes are stable. B. Martel and et.al⁽¹⁰⁾ reviewed that Permanent fixation of cyclodextrins onto textiles occurred either through reaction of the functional groups of the fibre (covalent bonding), or through the formation of a crosslinked polymer that is tangled up in the fibres (noncovalent bonding)

Figure-4: Fiber-cyclodextrin binding types: a) Triazinylchloride is reacted with cyclodextrin. The product has reacted with the fiber. b) Polycarboxylic acid reacts with the fiber. The formed ester is converted to a cyclic anhydride, which is then reacted with cyclodextrin. c) The cyclodextrin and epichlorohydrin reacts with strong alkali treated cellulose.

Figure-02: Different sources of perfumed oil can be applied on cotton textiles with cyclodextrin:

Perfumed oils are found in:

flowers	cloves, hyacinth, mimosa, jasmine, orange blossom, roses, reseda, heliotrope
petals and leaves	lavender, rosemary, peppermint
leaves and stems	geranium, cinnamon, patchouli
bark	cinnamon
roots	angelica, sassafras, vetiver
tubers	ginger, iris
fruits	bergamot, lemon, lime, orange
seeds	bitter almonds, anise, nutmeg
resin	myrrh, Peru balsam, styrax

J.-P. Moldenhauer⁽¹¹⁾ and other researcher found that β -cyclodextrin is a reactive cyclodextrin derivative that can be covalently fixed to nucleophilic substrates by a substitution reaction carried out by the usual finishing procedure. This new type of surface modification means a permanent transfer of cyclodextrin properties to the treated materials. Both alkaline and acidic methods⁽¹²⁾ for MCT- β -cyclodextrin finishes have been developed to suit customers. Particularly interesting is the treatment with fragrances and antimicrobial and pharmaceutical preparations, which can be released continuously over a long period on exposure to moisture. Underwear, gloves, socks⁽¹³⁾ can be loaded with the necessary antifungal, antihistaminic, and antiinflammatory agents. Curtains with cyclodextrins can be used to improve the air in rooms or offices with smokers.

Aroma/Scent/Fragrance aesthetics:⁽¹⁴⁾

When notice a smell, sensory organs unlock in you a subjective dimension, a memory, perhaps, or a feeling – a sensory experience inside the body. This doesn't happen if only looking at something. If we consider smell a roast turkey, for example,

rather than just see it, all your memories of roast turkeys are activated – an instantaneous accessing of relevant information and memory. Smells can

Aroma Category	Aroma Compound / Aroma Chemical
Citrus: Lemon Orange	Citral, Citronellal Mandarin Oil, Decyl acetate
Floral: Carnation Gardenia Geranium Lilac Lily Rose Violet	Phenethyl salicylate Nonyl acetate Citronellal Anisyl acetate Hydroxy citronellal Rose absolute Costus oil, Methyl-2-nonenolate
Fruity: Apple Apricot Banana Grape Peach Strawberry	Benzyl acetate Allyl butyrate Amyl acetate Isobutyl isobutyrate Allyl butyrate Benzyl benzoate
Herbaceous: Clove Minty	Eugenyl acetate l-carveol, l-carvone, l-menthol
Sweet: Anise Cinnamon Honey Sweet Vanilla	Ethyl acetate, methyl sorbate Cinnamonaldehyde Allylphenoxyacetate Acetanisole Anisyl acetate

Ingredients of perfume (14,15,16): **Sources of natural essential oils for perfumes (from Encyclopaedia Britannica).**

thus both create a sense of anticipation and a memory of the past – and gaining access to hidden or forgotten parts of our own history is a gift indeed. It is not yet known exactly how the sense of smell works. It might be the size, shape, spin, wave length or vibration of particular molecules matching or interlocking with special receptors in the nose that cause us to react or recognize a smell. Only a few molecules are necessary for us to experience or identify scents, and characteristically, the worse a smell is, the less it takes to notice it.

Md. Anowar Hossain

Sources of natural essential oils for perfumes (from Encyclopaedia Britannica).

Assessment of the Highest Aroma Effect of Herbal Extracts :

Extraction from the Herb

↓

Fresh flowers

↓

Boil the water

↓

Add the flowers (still it separates the Essence)

Aroma or fragrance is a chemical compound that has a pleasant smell or odor. According to research of World health organization, human stress is a problem that reduces quality of life for a large proportion of world's citizens & scientifically it was proved fragrance reduces stress has both long term and short term health benefit.

29

Table-03: Different sedative effects/or emotion of essential oils:

Emotion	Essential Oils with the Sedative Effects
Anxiety	Benzoin, Lemon, Chamomile. Rose, Cardamom, Clove, Jasmine
Lament	Rose
Stimulation	Camphor, Balm oil
Anger	Chamomile, Balm oil. Rose, Ylangylang
Wretchedness	Basil, Cypress, Mint, Patchouli
Allergy	Chamomile, Jasmine, Balm oil
Distrustfulness	Lavender
Tension	Camphor, Cypress, Vanilla. Jasmine. Balm oil. Lavender, Sandalwood
Melancholy	Basil, Lemon, Chamomile, Vanilla, Jasmine, Lavender, Mint, Rose
Hysteria	Chamomile, Balm oil, Lavender, Jasmine
Mania	Basil, Jasmine, Pine
Irritability	Chamomile, Camphor, Cypress, Lavender
Desolation	Jasmine, Pine, Patchouli, Rosemary

Beta cyclodextrin⁽¹⁶⁾ for fragrance finishing:

1. Successful medical application
2. It has cone shaped hydrophobic cavity which released fragrance rates are greatly decreased.
3. Finishing with cyclodextrin on cotton textiles.
4. Fragrance was encapsulated with beta cyclodextrin and perfume retention onto the fabric after number of washing and exposure to sunlight.

Successful fixation technique of cyclodextrin¹¹⁵ like Crosslinking, Grafting, Reactive fixation, Disperse dyeing method, Electrospinning, Sol gel process, Enzymatic coupling, Polymer extrusion&Fragrance release property etc.

Finishing with microencapsulation:

The fragrance compound⁽¹⁷⁾ and the essential oil are volatile substances. The most difficult task in preparing the aromatherapy textile is how to prolong its lifetime of odours. Micro-encapsulation is an effective technique to solve this. Micro encapsulation technology¹⁸ has its vast application in various fields including textile wet processing. It is a technology, in which very small particles of liquids, solids and gases are trapped within a very thin coating of polymeric material(s). For textile wet processing applications core materials includes dyes, pigments, essential oils, vitamins, anti bacterial agents, anti UV agents etc. The microcapsules obtained in slurry or free flowing powder form is applied to fabric to achieve various effects. In today's life customer needs differ from that of conventional needs, where micro encapsulation technology plays a significant role to meet today's market demand by providing multiple advantage using one single product. So textile is a product, which can easily fulfill for fashion and also protection at the same time.

Micro encapsulation has different purposes like

- Protection of enclosed material and improved storage life
- Conversion of liquid component to dry solid system
- Ensuring separation of incompatible components
- Odour masking
- Dust and pH control
- Controlled diffusion of active components, through the shell wall
- Change of weight or volume

Mechanism of microencapsulation (19):

30

Figure-05: Mechanism of microencapsulation

Many different manufacturing approaches have been adopted for microencapsulation. The most commonly used microencapsulation processes⁽²⁰⁾, including Complex Coacervation, Polymer-Polymer Incompatibility, Interfacial Polymerisation and In Situ Polymerisation, Spray Drying, Centrifugal Extrusion, Air Suspension Coating, Pan Coating, and Emulsion Hardening Process

Important testing of cyclodextrin and cosmetic textiles⁽²¹⁾:

1. **SEM (Scanning electron microscopy):** is used to study the microscopic aspect of the raw material (cyclodextrin and guest

substances respectively) and the product obtained by co-precipitation/evaporation.

2. **Infra-Red (IR) Spectroscopy:** is used to estimate the interaction between cyclodextrin and guest molecules in the solid state
3. **Thin Layer chromatography (TLC):** helps to identify the complex formation between guest and host molecule.
4. **X-ray diffractometry:** to detect inclusion complexation in the solid state.
5. **Single crystal X-ray structure analysis:** to determine the detailed inclusion structure and mode of interaction
6. **Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR):** to determine the cyclodextrin cavity in solution as well as direction of penetration of guest molecules into the cyclodextrin cavity.
7. **Olfactometry:** to know the intensity of fragrance

Successful example of using cyclodextrin for aroma finishing⁽²²⁾ :

Sensorial evaluation of scent intensity with cyclodextrin

Fragrance	Scent intensity					
	5 days	10 days	15 days	20 days	25 days	30 days
Rosemary	++ ++ +	+++++	++++	+++	+++	++
Lavender	++ ++ +	++++	+++	++	++	+
Jasmine	++ ++ +	+++++	++++	+++	++	++
Lemon	++ ++ +	++++	+++	++	+	+
Sandalwood	++ ++	+++++	++++	+++	+++	++

	+					
--	---	--	--	--	--	--

+++++ express very strong, ++++ express strong, +++ express common, ++ express weak, + express very weak.

Safety and pre-caution of Cyclodextrin for Aroma finishing on textile substrate:

Although there are many effective approaches to micro-encapsulation⁽²³⁾ for de-creasing fragrance-release, cyclodextrins are the best regarding safety to the human body, because β -cyclodextrin has no skin irritation, no skin sensibilisation and no mutagenic effect. Detailed studies of toxicology⁽⁵⁾, mutagegicity, teratogenity and carcinogenity were indicated that the cyclodextrin can effect the human organism only at extremely high concentrations. According to OECD (Organization for economic co-operation and development) test, these cyclodextrin derivatives have no irritating or sensitivation effects and it was also proved by the clinical test of T-shirt. Cyclodextrins^(24, 25) are cyclic oligosacchraides containing six, seven eight, nine ten, eleven, twelve, thirteen 1,4-linked glycopyranose units with a hydrophilic hydroxyl group on their outer surface and a hydrophobic cavity in the center.

31

⁽²⁵⁾Md. Anowar Hossain studied that Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine) with beta cyclodextrin showed high level of fragrance intensity in combined dyeing and finishing than double stage method. Fragrance intensity was tested by human sensorial evaluation was found 10% after 70 days without washing and 30% retained after five time washing.

⁽²⁶⁾AK Samanta and Anowar Hossain studied that Fragrance intensity with beta cyclodextrin after different duration of normal stoppage and also after nos. of wash cycles was tested by gas chromatography and the fragrance intensity of Jasminewas found to be 15.88% after five repeat washing and the fragrance intensity wasretained 39.5% in the cotton fabric up to 100 days of normal storing without washing.⁽²⁷⁾Cyclodextrins shows greater feasibility in connection with sustainable textile finishing. Cyclodextrins are cyclic oligosaccharides with hydrophilic outer surface and a lipophilic central cavity. ⁽²⁸⁾Chitin and chitosan as multifunctional materials for surface modification

of textiles in order to enhance the properties has risen significantly. The most important applications of chitosan in textile finishing include antimicrobial, antiodor, blood coagulant, antistatic, and crease-resistant finishing which provide the potential usage in various fields.

Conclusion: Microencapsulation technique and cyclodextrin for the production of cosmetic textiles is to explore the application of cyclodextrin for the purpose of incorporating fragrance oil into cotton fabrics which will create film forming ability. 100% cotton is predominant fibre used for underwear and socks producing textiles where fragrance finishing has a great value. In literature review, the use of beta cyclodextrin as a binder for the application of microencapsulated fragrance oil results in high fragrance retention in 100% cotton fabrics. Therefore, beta cyclodextrin with microencapsulated fragrance oil can be utilised to develop textiles to achieve the necessary antiodour finishing. Since 1980, when szejtli first patented the bonding of CDs onto textile fibres, a lot of research has gone into the application of CDs on to textile substrates. But there is still a gap between original high level basic science and commercial applications of CDs in all industrial sectors.

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Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric

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Abstract

A newer method of simultaneous dyeing and finishing has been developed using pad-dry-cure method by using limited aqueous solution of reactive dye, citric acid and suitable fragrance chemical microencapsulated in beta-cyclodextrin solubilized in PEG 200 and water (1:3) along with Citric acid and Sodium hypophosphite as catalyst applied on cotton fabric by pad-dry-cure method. Spectrophotometer analysis of combined dyed and finished cotton fabric show a deeper color yield and good aroma finishing using monochlorotriazine reactive dye along with jasmine oil microencapsulated in beta cyclodextrin in presence of citric acid and sodium hypophosphite applied on cotton fabric. For comparison purpose, beta cyclodextrin encapsulated aroma finish was also applied after dyeing cotton fabric with the same monochlorotriazine on cotton fabric in conventional two stage process. Simultaneous reactive dyeing and aroma finishing with beta cyclodextrin and citric acid show yield of K/S value, dry crease recovery angle and better retention of tensile strength than the two stage conventional method. FTIR spectra confirm that crosslinking successfully formed among the carboxyl group of citric acids and hydroxyl groups of cellulose and beta cyclodextrin forming ester crosslinks. Jasmine oil was also applied on cotton with beta cyclodextrin by micro encapsulation technique and without beta cyclodextrin by normal pad-dry-cure method. Jasmine oil applied with beta cyclodextrin by microencapsulation show higher level of retention of fragrance intensity for simultaneous in combined dyeing and finishing technique than two stage conventional methods. Human sensory evaluation indicates that fragrance intensity became gradually weaker with respect to time and higher nos. of washing cycle. Fragrance intensity after different duration of normal stoppage and also after nos. of wash cycles was tested by gas chromatography and, the fragrance intensity of Jasmine was found to be 15.88% after five repeat washing and the fragrance intensity was retained 39.5% in the cotton fabric up to 100 days of normal storing without washing. This single bath simultaneous reactive dyeing and aroma finishing also offers advantages of reduction of process cost, saving in energy, reduction in treatment time as well as better color yield and therefore is of commercial importance too.

1. Introduction

Simultaneous dyeing and finishing in a single bath offers considerable economy in operating costs because of the reduction in process steps, time, energy etc besides simplicity of the operations. So, an attempt was made in the present work to carry out

simultaneous reactive dyeing and aroma finishing in a single step instead of two step conventional processes. Aroma finish on cotton fabric or garments render special value addition in terms of reducing stress, relaxation of minds by release of pleasant odor from textiles even helping nice sleep etc. Aroma finishing after reactive dyeing by conventional two stage process as reported in literature [1] but simultaneous reactive dyeing and aroma finishing of cotton in a single bath technique is a newer concept, attempted in the present work. The investigation [2] of US retail sales of home fragrance for pleasure, enjoyment and reducing stress shows that total sales increased to about 9-10%, in 4 yrs time i.e. from \$1.35 billion in 1995 to \$1.96 billion in 1999. The scents of lavender, rose, citrus or vanilla were micro encapsulated into cotton fabrics [3, 31, 32] with or without dyeing in a conventional method, which is proved to be a good approach to meet the customers demand of important psychological and emotional needs, as well as also for purely physical and sensorial nature-aromatherapy. This concept was first coined in the late 1920s by the French cosmetic chemist R.M. Gattefosse [4], who noticed the excellent antiseptic properties and skin permeability of some fragrance. Dextrin has OH group and Cyclodextrins [3, 5] are cyclic oligosaccharides containing six to thirteen 1,4-linked glycopyranose units with hydrophilic hydroxyl groups on their outer surface creating also a hydrophobic cavity in the center capable of incorporating any hydrophobic or oleophilic material, like fragrance oil as well. D. kaur et al and other researcher [9-15] informed that the cyclodextrin has capacity to form inclusion of other hydrophobic materials to form a complex. J.-P. Moldenhauer [7] found that β -cyclodextrin is a reactive cyclodextrin derivative that can be covalently fixed to nucleophilic substrates by a substitution reaction. Textile used as Underwear, gloves, socks [5, 8] may be loaded with the necessary antifungal, antihistaminic, and anti-inflammatory agents by such microencapsulation. Similarly Flowers, leaves and fruit used as ingredients [16, 17] of perfume a few a molecule [18] of which is sufficient for us to experience its odor or to identify the smell. There are many microencapsulation technique [19, 20, 21] including Complex Coacervation, Polymer-Polymer Incompatibility, Interfacial Polymerisation and In Situ Polymerisation, Spray Drying, Centrifugal Extrusion, Air Suspension Coating, Pan Coating, Emulsion Hardening Process and Co-precipitation method etc [27, 30] β -cyclodextrin is said to free from skin irritation, no skin sensibilisation and any mutagenic effect.

β -cyclodextrin molecules has cone-shaped hydrophobic [28] cavity where aroma oils are microencapsulated and as a result, the rate of release of fragrance are greatly reduce for a long period of storage.

Considering all the above said information, it is thought appropriate to undertake an attempt to develop a newer one bath simultaneous reactive dyeing and aroma finishing of cotton fabric for special value addition in a economic approach.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

2.1.1. Cotton Fabric

Bleached Plain weave 100% cotton fabric was used as per following particulars. Fabric ends/decimeter: 13.75, pick/decimeter: 14.73, GSM: 54.

2.1.2. Chemicals and Dyes

Reactive dye of Dyechem international, Kolkata, Beta Cyclodextrin of TCI Chemical Ltd. India.

Dextrin, Polyethylene Glycol, Sodium hypophosphite, Sodium Carbonate, Sodium chloride, Citric acid of laboratory grade were used. Fragrance chemical (Jasmine) \rightarrow LN chemical industries ltd, Mumbai, India.

Polyethylene Glycol-200 and Distilled water in ratio 1:3 was used as solvent, Citric acid was used as crosslinking agent, Sodium hypophosphite was used as catalyst and Beta Cyclodextrin was used in different dosage like 5%, 10% & 15%. Fragrance chemical like Jasmine oil, usual dyeing auxiliaries (like NaCl, Na_2CO_3 etc) for reactive dye. Beta cyclodextrin (95% purity) was used as microencapsulating agent. Reactive dye-Lemon Yellow-CN-1% obtained from Dyechem International, was used besides Jasmine oil -1%, 2%, 3% application was used for both simultaneous reactive dyeing and aroma finishing as well as for two stage dyeing and finishing process.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Preparation of Microencapsulation of Fragrance Chemical

A solubilized solution of beta cyclodextrin was prepared with the addition of polyethylene glycol and water (1:3) at 50°C. Fragrance Chemical was added in the solution drop by drop with continuous stirring for proper microencapsulation.

2.2.2. Method of Combined Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing

Reactive dye lemon yellow-CN (CI Reactive Lemon Yellow) -1%, Citric acid - 10% and Sodium hypophosphite-6% were added in the above microencapsulated solution containing beta cyclodextrin (5%, 10%, 15%) and synthetic fragrance-1% with stirring for dissolving. Bleached fabric was impregnated in above solution and padded with 80% expression by two dip two nip process. Then, the cotton fabric was dried at 100°C and Cured at 150°C for 5 min. Similarly Dextrin (5%, 10%, and 15%) was used for comparative study.

To study the role of beta cyclodextrin, experiments were also conducted by using synthetic fragrance (1%, 2%, 3%) with 10% beta cyclodextrin and without beta cyclodextrin to find out fragrance intensity as well as microencapsulation capability of beta cyclodextrin.

2.2.3. Method of Conventional Two Stage Dyeing and Finishing

First stage (Dyeing):

Bleached cotton fabric was first dyed with reactive dye lemon yellow CN-1% with 1:20 liquor ratio at 80°C and after 15 min required amount of sodium chloride and sodium carbonate was added two parts. After dyeing the sample was rinsed, soaped and dried.

Second Stage (Finishing): The above ready dyed fabric was finished with the same recipe (without dyestuff) and procedure of above combined dyeing and finishing.

2.2.4. Testing Methods

- i) Color strength (K/S value) was measured by measuring surface reflectance value where Computer color measuring instrument (Macbeth 2020 plus spectrophotometer). Color strength of untreated and treated cotton fabric samples is measured from the reflectance value at maximum wave length from which surface color strength (K/S value) can be determined by Kubelka-Munk equation:

$$\frac{K}{S} = \frac{(1 - R_{\lambda_{max}})^2}{2R_{\lambda_{max}}} \alpha C_D$$

Where, K = coefficient of absorption.

S = coefficient of scattering.

$R_{\lambda_{max}}$ = reflectance of the substrate at maximum absorbance wavelength.

C_D = concentration of dye.

- ii) Color fastness to wash was tested by IS II method (i.e. ISO – 105-C-10, 2006 standard using 5 gpl soap, 2 gpl soda ash at 60°C for 30 mins, IS -3361-1984 method) with Launder-o-Meter. The wash cycles were repeated 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 times to examine the fragrance retention after respective nos. of wash cycles.
- iii) Light fastness to wash was tested by AATCC TM16 in Q-SUN XE-2 Xenon Test chamber against blue wool standards (BS -1006-BOI – 1978).
- iv) Dry crease recovery was measured by ASTM-D-1295-67 in Shirley crease recovery tester.
- v) Tensile strength and elongation % were evaluated by Ravel strip method using 20 mm X 5 mm sample size after raveling as per IS-1969-1985 method using Instron machine.
- vi) Fourier transform infrared spectra (FTIR) FTIR spectroscopic analysis of untreated and treated cotton fibre was palletted in spectroscopic grade KBr pallet and was subjected to generate FTIR spectra for respective samples using Parkin Elmer, UK. Model: Spectrum-100 FTIR spectrometer.
- vii) Olfactometric analysis of odour retention (for retention of fragrance):

A Human sensory analysis by opinion pole of group of experts – Human sensory analysis to establish the presence of intensity of odour of Rose by Nasal sensory opinion of a group of expert panel was taken after each wash (1 to 5 cycles) and after 10 to 100 days of storing without wash. The odour concentration / intensity was subdivided into the following categories [27]:

- 0 – No Odour (0%)
- 1 – Very weak (Around 5 – 15%)
- 2- Weak (Around 20 – 40%)
- 3 – Medium strong (Around 50 – 70%)
- 4 – Strong (Around 75 – 85%)
- 5 – Very strong (Around 90 – 95%)

B Gas Chromatography Testing (Capillary method) for test of retention of Aroma oil(Rose oil) after different cycle of wash and different durations of storage:

Detail procedure of GC analysis is as follows:-

High purity gases are supplied to the GC. One of the gases (called the carrier gas) flows into the injector, through the column and then into the detector. All gases-injector carrier, detector gases are fully electronically controlled through advanced flow controller and advanced pressure controller. Firstly standard rose has been injected with a syringe or an exterior sampling device in gas chromatography machine and the volatile solution are transported into the column by the carrier gas where the column is maintained in a temperature controlled oven. Solution enters heated detector and an electronic signal is generated upon interaction of the solute with the detector. The size of the signal is recorded by a data system and is plotted against elapsed time to produce a chromatogram and peak of fragrance has been recorded automatically by detector software from card Fragrance treated fabric has been extracted by acetone. Then extracted solution has been injected and expected peak of sample/fragrance treated fabric has been found comparing recorded peak of standard rose for quantitative analysis of rose oil quantity still present after different duration of storage or after different nos. of wash cycles / different days of storing.

Testing was done by using Column: TG 5 MS, Capillary Column, Column Temperature 100°C, injected temperature 190°C, Detector temperature 220°C, Nitrogen carrier gas flow 1.5 ml /min, speed ratio 1:33, Software detector: FID (Flame ionization detector) and software from card using a Gas Chromatography Instrument make: Thermo fisher, Trace GC 1110, India.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Study on Dyeing Properties of Dyed and Finished Cotton Fabric

First of all, dyeing property of combined dyeing fragrance finishing as well as conventional two stage process has been studied. The changes in dyeing property of bleached cotton fabric dyed with reactive lemon yellow-CN for combined dyed and fragrance finished fabric as well as conventional two stage dyed and fragrance finished fabric have been assessed and shown in Table-1. Relevant data in Table 1 indicate that K/S value, color fastness rating, Light fastness to understand the feasibility of combined dyeing and finishing in compare to conventional two stages dyeing and finishing using Reactive-Lemon yellow CN, Citric acid, synthetic fragrance chemicals-Jasmine and auxiliaries such as beta cyclodextrin/Dextrin.

Table 1. Analysis of dyeing properties of conventional two stage dyeing and finishing as well as simultaneous dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric.

SL. No	Treatments of Fabric	K/S value	Color fastness Rating	Lightfastness
1	Bleached untreated cotton	0.100	-	-
2	Reactive Dyed cotton by conventional alkali and exhaust process (No finishing)	2.999	3	3
3	Two step sequentially dyed and finished cotton fabric with same reactive dye in conventional process finished by beta cyclodextrin, fragrance (Jasmine) and Citric acid	2.454	4	4
4	Two step sequentially dyed and finished cotton fabric with same reactive dye in conventional process finished by Dextrin, fragrance (Jasmine) and Citric acid	1.534	2	2
5	Two step sequentially dyed and finished cotton fabric with same reactive dye in conventional process finished by beta cyclodextrin, fragrance (Jasmine) and without Citric acid	2.572	3	3
6	Two step sequentially dyed and finished cotton fabric with same reactive dye in conventional process finished by Dextrin, fragrance (Jasmine) and without Citric acid	1.230	2	2
7	Combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric with same reactive dye and finished by Beta Cyclodextrin, fragrance (Jasmine) and Citric acid	3.239	3	3
8	Combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric with same reactive dye and finished by Dextrin, fragrance (Jasmine) and Citric acid	1.990	2	2
9	Combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric with same reactive dye and finished by Beta Cyclodextrin, fragrance (Jasmine) and without Citric acid	3.010	2	2
10	Combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric with same reactive dye and finished by Dextrin, fragrance (Jasmine) and without Citric acid	1.435	2	2

The color strength(K/S) value (shown in Table-1) of combined dyed and finished cotton fabric have been found better than two stage conventional process for all three dosage of beta-cyclodextrins indicated by k/s value while beta cyclodextrin showed higher k/s value for both combined and two stage process than that for dextrin. Combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric obtained deeper color yield for reactive dyeing with monochlorotriazine group of reactive dye using beta cyclodextrin, citric acid & sodium hypophosphite and fragrance finish applied simultaneously. It is known that the said reactive dye forms covalent bond with cellulose and beta cyclodextrin. Due to the covalent bonding between dye, fibre and beta cyclodextrin, it also show at par / marginally level of color fastness to wash and light (shown in table-1).

In conventional method of dyeing and finishing, the major drawback of reactive dyes is hydrolysis in which dye instead of reacting with fibre reacts with hydroxide ion of base, as a result high amount of wastage of dyestuff occurs in conventional dyeing. But in combined dyeing and finishing with padding method hydrolysis rate of dyestuff is being minimized and wastage of dyestuff therefore negligible [29], resulting higher colour strength. So this simultaneous dyeing and finishing work is more beneficial to minimizing the wastage of dyestuff, rendering higher colour strength and overall at par level of fastness to wash and light.

K/s value was improved 31% for beta cyclodextrin in combined dyeing and finishing method. As the price of

Table 2. Analysis of physical properties of conventional two stage dyeing and finishing as well as simultaneous dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric (for reactive dyeing and fragrance finishing) using beta-cyclodextrin and citric acid with SHP as catalyst.

SL. No	Treatments of Fabric	Warp Way TenacityN/Tex	Weft Way TenacityN/Tex	Loss/Gain% in Tenacity(Warp way)	Loss/Gain% in Tenacity(Weft way)	Dry crease recovery angle
1	Bleached untreated cotton	2.78	2.08			162
2	Reactive Dyed cotton by conventional alkali and exhaust process (No finishing)	2.70	2.00	-2.96%	-4%	180
3	Conventional two step sequentially dyed and finished cotton fabric with same reactive dye in conventional	2.76	2.05	-0.72%	-1.46%	256

dyestuff is the highest among all chemical of dyeing and finishing process so it is a worth achievement.

3.2. Study on Physical Properties of Dyed and Finished Cotton Fabric

Bleached cotton fabric has been dyed and fragrance finished in simultaneous single stage operation as well as in conventional two stage process. Table-2 shows the different physical properties in combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric as well as conventional two stage dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric studied various types of properties such as Fabric strength, Dry crease recovery angle to observe the feasibility of combined dyeing and finishing comparing with double stage dyeing and finishing using Reactive-Lemon yellow CN-1%, Citric acid-10%, synthetic fragrance chemicals (Jasmine): 1% and auxiliaries such as beta cyclodextrin/Dextrin.

Combined dyeing and finishing with beta cyclodextrin was successfully improved the dry crease recovery angle (shown in table-2) of cotton fabric which is a major benefit of using beta cyclodextrin. Beta cyclodextrin may be improving (shown in table-2) the molecular chain in the amorphous region & improved the weak hydrogen bond. Similarly, Dextrin also improved the dry crease recovery property (shown in table-2) may be its similar function of beta cyclodextrin as dextrin is a mother chemical of beta cyclodextrin.

SL. No	Treatments of Fabric	Warp Way TenacityN/Tex	Weft Way TenacityN/Tex	Loss/Gain% in Tenacity(Warp way)	Loss/Gain% in Tenacity(Weft way)	Dry crease recovery angle
4	process finished with beta cyclodextrin, fragrance (Jasmine) and Citric acid and SHP Two step sequentially dyed and finished cotton fabric with same reactive dye in conventional process finished with Dextrin, fragrance (Jasmine) and Citric acid and SHP	2.74	1.99	-1.45%	-4.52%	230
5	Two step sequentially dyed and finished cotton fabric with same reactive dye in conventional process finished with beta cyclodextrin, fragrance (Jasmine) and without Citric acid and without SHP	2.70	2.00	-2.96%	-4%	240
6	Two step sequentially dyed and finished cotton fabric with same reactive dye in conventional process finished with Dextrin, fragrance (Jasmine) and without Citric acid and without SHP	2.68	1.90	-3.73%	-9.47%	200
7	Combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric with same reactive dye and finished with Beta Cyclodextrin, fragrance (Jasmine) and Citric acid and SHP	2.90	2.80	+4.13%	25%	269
8	Combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric with same reactive dye and finished by Dextrin, fragrance (Jasmine) and Citric acid	2.78	2.08	0%	0%	220
9	Combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric with same reactive dye and finished with Beta Cyclodextrin, fragrance (Jasmine) and without Citric acid and without SHP	2.86	2.70	+2.79%	22.96%	248
10	Combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric with same reactive dye and finished with Dextrin, fragrance (Jasmine) and without Citric acid and without SHP	2.72	2.01	-2.20%	-3.48%	200

3.3. Study on Fragrance Intensity of Dyed and Finished Cotton Fabric

Fragrance Intensity testing of the cotton fabric was tested by Human sensorial evaluation (Shown in Table-3) Gas chromatography testing (Capillary method) For analysis fragrance intensity in combined dyeing and finishing method were carried out to study the fragrance intensity in double stage dyeing and finishing. It was also studied to know fragrance intensity in two conditions. Such as: after number of days without washing and after five time washing. Finally it was concluded that fragrance on combined dyeing and finishing has been found higher intensity than double stage dyeing and finishing, so details study on fragrance intensity has been proceeded only for combined dyeing and finishing for showing specific

concept of retention% of fragrance chemical in fragrance grading scale 0-100% (Shown in Table-3) was experimented by human sensorial evaluation (by systematic evaluation of the fragrance and opinion of 10 different persons) after number of days without washing. Treated by Reactive-Lemon yellow CN-1%, Beta Cyclodextrin-10%, Citric acid-10% and synthetic fragrance chemicals (Jasmine-1%) were found good intensity of fragrance which was tested by Gas chromatography (Shown in Graph -1&2) method for further confirmation of fragrance retention. Human sensory evaluation (Shown in Table-3) was also confirmed fragrance retention/microencapsulation on cotton fabric of synthetic Jasmine was retained up to 100 days without washing where beta cyclodextrin was used 10% but fragrance finishing without beta cyclodextrin retained up to 30 days.

Table 3. Fragrance retention grading scale (0-100%) by human sensorial evaluation by opinion pole after number of days without washing upto 100 days for sample no: 7 with 20-40 Beta cyclodextrin, citric acid and SHP.

Fragrance Concentration	Beta Cyclodextrin	Citric Acid	First day	10th day	20th day	30 th Day	40th day	50th day	60th day	70th day	80th day	90th day	100th day
Jasmine	1%	10%	90%	80%	80%	70%	70%	30%	20%	15%	10%	8%	5%
			(5)	(4)	(4)	(3)	(3)	(2)	(2)	(1)	(1)	(1)	(1)
			95%	85%	85%	80%	70%	40%	20%	15%	10%	8%	5%
	3%	10%	95%	85%	85%	80%	70%	40%	20%	15%	10%	8%	5%
			(5)	(4)	(4)	(4)	(3)	(2)	(2)	(1)	(1)	(1)	(1)
1%	0%	10%	90%	70%	50%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
			(5)	(3)	(3)	(1)	(0)	(0)	(0)	(0)	(0)	(0)	(0)
2%	0%	10%	90%	70%	50%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
			(5)	(3)	(3)	(1)	(0)	(0)	(0)	(0)	(0)	(0)	(0)

Fragrance	Beta	Citric	First	10th	20th	30 th	40th	50th	60th	70th	80th	90th	100th
Concentration	Cyclodextrin	Acid	day	day	day	Day	day	day	day	day	day	day	day
Jasmine	3%	0%	10%	90%	70%	50%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
			(5)	(3)	(3)	(1)	(0)	(0)	(0)	(0)	(0)	(0)	(0)
	1%	10%	0%	90%	80%	80%	70%	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%	0%
			(5)	(4)	(4)	(3)	(3)	(2)	(1)	(0)	(0)	(0)	(0)
	2%	10%	0%	95%	85%	85%	80%	70%	40%	10%	0%	0%	0%
			(5)	(4)	(4)	(4)	(3)	(2)	(1)	(0)	(0)	(0)	(0)
Jasmine	3%	10%	0%	95%	85%	85%	80%	70%	40%	10%	0%	0%	0%
			(5)	(4)	(4)	(4)	(3)	(2)	(1)	(0)	(0)	(0)	(0)

Table 4. Fragrance retention grading scale (0-100%) by human sensorial evaluation by opinion pole after number of days without washing upto five time washing by using neutral soap-2gm/l, time-3min, RPM-40, Temp-40°C for sample no: 7 with or without Beta cyclodextrin and with or without citric acid.

Types of fragrance	Fragrance conc.	BetaCyclodextrin	Citric Acid	Before washing	First	Second	Third	Fourth	Fifth
Synthetic (Jasmine)	1%	10%	10%	90%	90%	80%	60%	50%	30%
				(5)	(5)	(4)	(3)	(3)	(2)
	2%	10%	10%	95%	90%	80%	70%	60%	40%
				(5)	(5)	(4)	(3)	(3)	(2)
	3%	10%	10%	95%	90%	80%	70%	60%	40%
				(5)	(5)	(4)	(3)	(3)	(2)
Synthetic(Jasmine)	1%	0%	10%	90%	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
				(5)	(3)	(2)	(1)	(0)	(0)
	2%	0%	10%	95%	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
				(5)	(3)	(2)	(1)	(0)	(0)
	3%	0%	10%	95%	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
				(5)	(3)	(2)	(1)	(0)	(0)
Synthetic (Jasmine)	1%	10%	0%	90%	90%	80%	60%	50%	30%
				(5)	(5)	(4)	(3)	(3)	(2)
	2%	10%	0%	95%	90%	80%	70%	60%	40%
				(5)	(5)	(4)	(3)	(3)	(2)
	3%	10%	0%	95%	90%	80%	70%	60%	40%
				(5)	(5)	(4)	(3)	(3)	(2)

3.4. Study on Gas Chromatography for Fragrance Intensity Testing Without Washing

In combined dyed and finished cotton fabric which was treated by Reactive-Lemon yellow CN-1%, beta-cyclodextrin-10%, Citric acid-10% and synthetic fragrance chemicals (Jasmine-1%) and tested by gas chromatography method (Shown in Fig.-2). For testing GC, firstly standard Jasmine was tested shown in Fig.-1 and secondly fragrance treated fabric was tested by extraction method shown in Fig.-2. The intensity of jasmine fragrance retained after 100 days without washing in cotton fabric is 39.5%. This

percentage was found by the calculation method of area%. Since combined dyed and finished cotton fabric was extracted by acetone and standard fragrance chemical also mixed with acetone, So almost similar rectangular curve showed for both bleached and treated cotton fabric. Fragrance retention time was gradually decreased in case of treated sample. Technical language of another Y-axis curve is called T-peak and another small vibration due to the use of synthetic fragrance. An extended area was showed in the Fig.-2 of standard Jasmine due to mixed of unknown substance in synthetic fragrance where may be used varieties quality of natural and artificial fragrance to produce synthetic fragrance of Jasmine.

Fig. 1. Chromatograph of fragrance intensity of synthetic Jasmine as standard.

Fig. 2. Chromatogram of fragrance intensity (synthetic Jasmine) on combined dyed and fragrance finished cotton fabric after 100 days without washing.

Fig. 3. Chromatogram of fragrance intensity as standard synthetic Jasmine.

Fig. 4. Chromatogram of fragrance intensity (synthetic Jasmine) on combined dyed and fragrance finished fabric after five time washing.

3.5. Study on Gas Chromatography After Five Time Washing

In combined dyed and finished cotton fabric which was treated by Reactive-Lemon yellow CN-1%, Beta-cyclodextrin-10%, Citric acid-10% and synthetic fragrance chemicals (Jasmine-1%) and tested by gas chromatography method (Shown in Fig. 4). For testing GC, firstly standard Jasmine was tested shown in Graph-3 and secondly fragrance treated fabric was tested by extraction method shown in Fig. 4. The intensity of jasmine fragrance retained after five time washing in cotton fabric is 15.88%. This percentage was found by the calculation method of area%. Since combined dyed and finished cotton fabric was extracted by acetone and standard fragrance chemical also mixed with acetone. So almost similar rectangular curve showed for both bleached and treated cotton fabric. Fragrance retention time was gradually decreased in case of treated sample. Technical language of another Y-axis curve is called T-peak and

another small vibration due to the use of synthetic fragrance.

Thus from Gas Chromatography analysis it may be concluded that combined dyeing and finishing can retain good amount of fragrance 39.5% after 100 days without washing due to the presence of beta cyclodextrin as microencapsulation as well as crosslinking of citric acid and similarly retaining 15.88% fragrance was observed after five time washing due to the presence of beta cyclodextrin as microencapsulation as well as crosslinking of citric acid.

3.6. FTIR Study of Combined Dyed and Fragrance Finished Cotton Fabric

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra analysis for (a) Bleached cotton fabric (shown in Fig-5) as well as (b) combined dyed and fragrance finished of cotton fabric treated with Reactive-Lemon yellow CN-1%, beta-cyclodextrin-10%, Citric acid-10%, 2% SHP and synthetic fragrance chemicals (Jasmine-1%) 3305.91 cm^{-1} peak (Shown in Fig.-6) indicates (-OH) group where clearly showed more extended

area of (-OH) group in combined dyed and finished fabric than bleached cotton fabric (shown in Fig.-5). From where it may be assumed that (-OH) group of cellulose is bonding with the (-OH) group of beta cyclodextrin. From 1600 cm^{-1} to 1000 cm^{-1} no new peak has been formed but a new peak fully removed 983.62 peaks from the graph-6 of bleached cotton fabric which may be due to some reaction among monochlorotriazine group of reactive dye, synthetic fragrance chemical, cellulosic fibre and citric acid. (Shown in Fig.-6) for combined dyeing and finishing fabric a new absorption curve appeared 1728 cm^{-1} (C=O) and the C-H stretching vibration 2902.38 cm^{-1} was improved slightly due to the improvement of macromolecular chain. The new strong absorption peak 1728 cm^{-1} , 902.03 cm^{-1} , 819 appeared due to C=O stretching vibration, which was accord with the theory of cotton fabric treated by beta cyclodextrin and citric

acid. Ester bond (-COO-) was generated between hydroxyl group of beta cyclodextrin and cotton fabric reacted with citric acid which was used as crosslinking agent. Fig.-2 showed that beta cyclodextrin was fixed on cotton fabric with the aid of citric acid which crosslinking among the carboxyl group of acids, the hydroxyl group of cellulose and beta cyclodextrin occurred due to the esterification reaction where the new strong absorption peak 1728 cm^{-1} . So it was speculated cotton fabric was cross linked successfully. Finally it may be assumed that beta cyclodextrin and fragrance chemical are not making any negative reaction with monochlorotriazine group of reactive dyestuff. Although, jasmine the fragrance oil was microencapsulated primarily before making any reaction with fibre and the strong absorption peak (Shown in Fig.-6) confirmed that beta cyclodextrin was bonding with monochlorotriazine group.

Fig. 5. FTIR of bleached cotton fabric.

Fig. 6. FTIR of combined dyed and finished fabric.

4. Conclusion

From the present study it is revealed that combination of dyed and microencapsulated aroma finished fabric shows adequate wrinkle resistance, high tensile strength retention property and higher colour value of cotton fabric and also rendered high retention of aroma property as indicated by gas chromatography test and human sensorial evaluation as compared to untreated fabric as well as compared to sequential two step process of dyeing and finishing. The optimum performances were obtained with Synthetic Fragrance (Jasmine): 1%, Reactive dye-lemon yellow-CN: 1%, Beta Cyclodextrin: 10%, Citric Acid: 10%, Sodium Hypophosphite: 6%, Solvent composed of PEG & Water in ratio 1:3:72%.

Irrespective of the technique followed, the surface colour strength of simultaneous dyed and aroma finished cotton fabric is found to increase with an increase the percentage of application of both beta-cyclodextrin from and beyond which it almost tends to level off. The fastness parameters are also moderately satisfactory.

Single step simultaneous dyeing (with reactive dye) and aroma finishing of cotton fabric by pad-dry-cure technique thus offers savings in energy, process time, giving satisfactory colour strength and acceptable other physical parameters as compared to the conventional two-step sequential dyeing and aroma finishing process. Hence this process may be implemented industry for savings of time/energy/ labour and process cost etc.

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JFT-05

INTEGRATED DYEING AND COSMETIC FINISHING ON COTTON FABRIC**Md. Anowar Hossain**

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ABSTRACT

Textile science of chemical processing encompass diverse disciplines and areas of expertise. In the present scenario of industrial consciousness, integration in all aspects of textile wet processing is commercial ultimatum where everyone is repeatedly querying to textile scientist. The present research on combined dyeing and finishing is prime of them. Combined dyeing and finishing offers considerable economy in operating costs because of the simplicity of the operations. Project work was proceeded to study the feasibility of combined dyeing and multifinishing (fragrance, water repellency, anticrease, crease recovery) in one step to reduce process cost like as time saving , heat energy saving, water, low vapour-gas-emission, low labour cost, environment –friendly and also worked on to develop and optimize durable fragrance finishing for cotton textiles which may be an alternative invention of artificial application of perfume on textile substrate named as cosmetic finishing. Beta cyclodextrin, Dextrin and DMDHEU were applied for reactive dyeing and finishing of cotton fabric unconventional double stage exhaust and combined pad-dry-cure method where combined method of dyeing and finishing with beta cyclodextrin showed higher K/S value, dry crease recovery angle, tensile strength than using double stage method. As fragrance chemical: synthetic fragrance (Jasmine), Rose oil and Pachouli oil were used with beta cyclodextrin and without beta cyclodextrin. Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine) with beta cyclodextrin showed high level of fragrance intensity in combined dyeing and finishing than double stage method. Fragrance intensity was tested by human sensorial evaluation was found 10% after 70 days without washing and 30% retained after five time washing.

Keywords : Dyeing, finishing, Beta Cyclodextrin, Aroma finish, Microencapsulation, Emulsion.

54

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6TH ALL INDIA INTER ENGINEERING COLLEGE ACADEMIC MEET -2015

&

SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY EXHIBITION FOR A SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY

26TH APRIL, 2015

Organised by

FORUM OF SCIENTISTS, ENGINEERS & TECHNOLOGISTS (FOSET)

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In Association with

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CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This is to certify that Sri / Smt MD. ANOWAR HOSSAIN of University of Calcutta has presented a paper (Principal Author) titled Integrated Dyeing and Cosmetic Finishing on Cotton Fabric in **JUTE, TEXTILE & FIBRE TECHNOLOGY** Stream in the 6th ALL INDIA INTER ENGINEERING COLLEGE ACADEMIC MEET-2015 AND SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY EXHIBITION FOR A SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY organised by *Forum of Scientists, Engineers and Technologists (FOSET)* in association with *MCKV Institute of Engineering* on 26th April, 2015.

Date : 26.04.2015
Howrah

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ACADEMIC MEET 2015

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SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY EXHIBITION
FOR A SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY

26th April, 2015

Organized by

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& Technologists (FOSET)**

On Association with

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Approved by the AICTE, affiliated to the WBUT and accredited
by the NBA for CSE and ECE department

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Guidelines for Model Exhibition (For 111 Students)

SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY EXHIBITION FOR A SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY

Introduction

"FOSET" is organizing a science & technological exhibition through models and exhibits as made by the skilled artisans to develop an understanding about the role of science & technology to meet the demand of the future towards sustainable development of the society.

The main objective to organize such exhibition first time in the arena of "Academic Meet", to envisage the engineers & technicians of the future would try to analyse all aspects of the role of science & technology for a sustainable world. This will enable the Target group to generate scientific and technological ideas for addressing various problems of the society. Scientific and technological ideas in this context may be referred to as innovative ways of doing things or development of new values through solutions that meet new requirement leading to sustainable production and uses. The youth must be aware about how human society's unsustainable use of natural resources affects the quality of life and environment. The young engineers and technicians should identify where and how new researches and development in science & technology can bring sustainable development of the society.

This exhibition aims to cover areas

- 1) Mechanical & Production Engineering
- 2) Civil and Architecture Engineering
- 3) Electrical Engineering
- 4) Computer Science and Information Technology
- 5) Electronics

(Areas listed above are suggestive. The young engineers and technicians are free to choose any other area.)

Objectives

- To provide a forum to nurture science & technology
- To explore and encourage scientific and technological talent and creative thinking among youth.
- To develop an understanding about the role of science and technology towards sustainable development of the society.
- To analyse how science and technology have affected individuals, culture and society.
- To motivate the youth that science and technology are instrument for achieving self-reliance in socio-economic development.

Criteria for selection of the participants

1	Creative imagination	15%
2	Scientific thought and approach	15%
3	Originality & innovations in the model	15%
4	Technical Skill	15%
5	Economic (low cost / portability / durability)	15%
6	Presentation(demonstration & explanation)	15%
7	Educational Value	10%

Registration

Two participants per Model have to submit individually the attached Registration Form duly filled-in and signed and should be authorized by Head of the Department / Institute. The Registration Fee @ **Rs. 150.00 per head** is exempted for the **Principle / Presenting Model maker**.

Call For Papers

Papers are invited from Under Graduate & Post graduate students of Universities & Engineering Colleges on **Ready-to-Transfer Technologies and Field-level and Cost-effective Applications of Science and Technology**.

Call For Models

Models are invited from 111 students of different institutes on **Ready-to-Transfer Technology and Field-level and Cost-effective Applications of Skills in various department of Craftmanship**.

Awards

- Certificates will be awarded to all selected papers presenters and model makers.
- Cash Prizes of **Rs. 2,000/-** and **Rs. 1,000/-** will be awarded to the First & Second Prize winning papers respectively.
- Cash Prizes of **Rs. 2,000/-** will be awarded to the First Prize winning among the model makers.

Transport, Accommodation and other details

To and Fro Bus Fare / 2nd Class Train Fare will be reimbursed to each selected Out-station (beyond 100 Km from Kolkata) participant (One person per paper).

Tariff For Sponsorship / Advertisement

Collaborator	Rs. 50,000.00
Sponsorship of Exhibition	Rs. 25,000.00
Sponsorship of Stream	Rs. 15,000.00
Advertisement (Full Page)	Rs. 10,000.00
Sponsorship of prize	Rs. 5,000.00

Registration

At least one participant per Paper have to submit individually the attached Registration Form duly filled-in and signed and should be authorized by Head of the Department / Institute. The Registration Fee @ **Rs. 150.00 per head** is exempted for the **Principle / Presenting Author**.

Guidelines for Paper Submission (For UG & PG Students)

- The **Abstract** should generally not exceed **100 words** with maximum 5 key words.
- Submit one soft copy of the Manuscript (only through e-mail) and a CD containing the camera ready version of the paper at the time of presentation. The **Manuscript** should be within **maximum 4 pages in A4 paper**.
- The paper should be as per template of **Standard IEEE Conference format**, template can be downloaded from <http://www.fosetonline.org>.
- Please include black & white photographs only. The Paper should be ready-to-print in .doc format.

Abstract and Full Papers must be sent by e-mail to : foset@foset.in

Registration Form has to be sent by post/courier to FOSET office or e-mail the scanned copy of filled Registration.

ACADEMIC MEET - 2015

&

SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY EXHIBITION FOR A SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY

26th April, 2015

Organized by

Forum of Scientists, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET)

In Association with

MCKV Institute of Engineering

Approved by the AICTE, affiliated to the WBUT and accredited by the NBA for CSE and ECE department

About the Academic Meet

After an overwhelming response from the students of Engineering Colleges all over the country in the Academic Meets of 2010 to 2014, Forum of Scientists, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET), a national level voluntary organization of professionals feels proud once again to organize the **6th All India Inter Engineering College Academic Meet - 2015 & Science & Technology Exhibition for a Sustainable Society on 26th April, 2015** in association with MCKV Institute of Engineering. West Bengal produces some of the finest talent in the field of Engineering and Technology through its systematic and well-organized network of colleges and universities. The Academic Meet is recognized as an effective platform for exploration and brainstorming by UG and PG students of engineering Colleges / Institutes / Universities in India, who have that positive inclination in translating their theoretical knowledge into technology for people. The event includes paper presentations before eminent experts in different fields. Avenues are also opened for presenting skill of craftsmanship for ITI students. Also, the two best papers of each stream would be awarded as a token of recognition and also would be published in a special issue of the journal **THOUGHT - A Socio Technical Round Up**. The **6th All India Inter Engineering College Academic Meet - 2015** will therefore look forward for an organizational expansion amongst the budding Engineers participating in the meet.

About FOSET's activities and Membership information and also for more detail about the **6th All India Inter Engineering College Academic Meet - 2015** please log on to our website: <http://www.fosetonline.org>

About MCKVIE

MCKVIE is a premiere co-ed Post Graduate Degree Engineering College in West Bengal. Approved by the All India Council for Technical Education, affiliated to the West Bengal University of Technology and accredited by the National Board of Accreditation for CSE and ECE departments, MCKVIE offers B. Tech, M. Tech and MCA degree courses. It has around 1500 students spread over six disciplines preparing to make their mark in the world.

Venue

MCKV Institute of Engineering
243 G. T. Road (N), Liluah Howrah - 711204
Phone: (033) 2654 9315/17, Fax: (033) 2654 9318
Website: <http://www.mckvie.edu.in>

Contact Details

Full Paper/s along with the filled-in Registration form to be E-mailed to the following address within due date:

The Convener,
6th All India Inter Engineering College Academic Meet - 2015 & Science & Technology Exhibition for a Sustainable Society Forum of Scientists, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET)
15N, Nelli Sengupta Sarani (Lindsay Street),
New KMC Building (5th Floor), Kolkata - 700 087
Phone: 033 2252 9675, Fax: 033 2252 0521
Email: foset@foset.in, Web: <http://www.fosetonline.org>

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Important Dates

- ◆ Last date of submission of Full Text of Paper / Model Proposal : 3rd April, 2015
- ◆ Date of Notification of Acceptance : 10th April, 2015
- ◆ Last Date Submission of Registration : 15th April, 2015
- ◆ Last date for Submission of Camera Ready Paper : 15th April, 2015
- ◆ ACADEMIC MEET Paper Presentation : 26th April, 2015

Programme Details

DATE	SESSION	TIME
26 th April, 2015	Registration	10.00 AM to 11.00 AM
	Technical Session - I	11.00 AM to 01.30 PM
	Technical Session - II	02.30 PM to 05.00 PM
	Valedictory Session	05.30 PM to 06.30 PM
	Exhibition of Models	11.00 AM to 03.00 PM

Theme & Scope

STREAM	AREA
A. MECHANICAL ENGINEERING; INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING; MATERIAL SCIENCE & ENGINEERING	Mechanical Design, Thermal Engineering, Mechanics, Marine Engineering, Aerospace Engineering, Automotive Engineering, Computer Aided Engineering, Mechatronics; Production & related issues, Manufacturing Systems Engineering, Product and Quality Engineering, Economics and Work Design; Facility Engineering and Management, Test/Technology & Maintenance Management, Process Engineering and Production Planning; Service Systems; Application of Optimization, Meta heuristic and Management Decision Techniques, Material Science and Advanced Application Materials; Nano-materials; Metallurgical Engineering
B. JUTE TEXTILE AND FIBER TECHNOLOGY	Technological Innovations in Jute & Textiles, Technical fabrics and textile, smart Textile, Application of Geo Textile in Engineering, Biotechnological Application of Geo Jute, Alternate fibers.
C. CIVIL ENGINEERING & ARCHITECTURE	Structural Engineering; Construction Engineering & Management; Geotechnical Engineering; Transportation Engineering; Water Resources Engineering; Architecture; Eco-City Planning, Smart city
D. ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING; INSTRUMENTATION ENGINEERING	Electrical Machines and Drives; Micro-Simulac; Power Systems and high voltage Engineering; Power Plant Engineering, Distribution and Transmission, Non-conventional Energy; control, instrumentation and measurement, biosensor and smart sensors. Orientation and Human Computer interface.
E. ELECTRONICS & COMMUNICATION ENGINEERING	Electronic Chip Design (VLSI), Microwave Engineering, Signal Processing, Communication Engineering, Embedded System, EMI & EMC - health & hazards, antenna design, communication & networking.
F. COMPUTER SCIENCE & ENGINEERING; INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY	Networking, Image Processing, Computer Architecture; Digital Technology, Information & Communication Technology, Application of Free & Open Source Software, Data Communication Technology, Cybernetics, E-Governance, DBMS & MISOS, Data mining.
G. CHEMICAL ENGINEERING; ENVIRONMENT ENGG.; PHARMACEUTICAL ENGINEERING	Chemical Process and Plant Design; Chemical Reaction Engineering, Catalysts development; Nanotechnology; Industrial Waste Treatment & Recovery; Environmental Process Design, Global Warming, Pharmaceuticals, Pharmaceutical Bio-Technology & Industrial Microbiology, Pharmaceutical Bio-Technology & Industrial Microbiology
H. BIO-TECHNOLOGY; FOOD TECHNOLOGY; AGRICULTURAL ENGG.	Biotechnology; Molecular and Microbial Biotechnology; Genetic Engineering; Biochemistry; Food Product and Process Design; Food Innovation and Management; Bioengineering; Bioinformatics; Agricultural Product Production and processing of agricultural products; Agricultural Equipment and Technology.

**6th ALL INDIA INTER ENGINEERING COLLEGE ACADEMIC MEET – 2015
& SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY EXHIBITION FOR A SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY**

Organised by FORUM OF SCIENTISTS, ENGINEERS & TECHNOLOGISTS (FOSET)

AT MCKV INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING

26TH APRIL, 2015

INAUGURAL PROGRAMME

Welcome Address	Prof (Dr) Jaya Sil Chairperson, Organising Committee	11.00 AM
Guest of Honour	Sri Kishan Kumar Kejriwal Managing Trustee, MCKVIE	11.05 AM
Guest of Honour	Prof (Dr) Parasar Bandopadhyay Director, MCKVIE	11.10 AM
Chief Guest	Sri Tapobrata Sanyal Chief Consultant, National Jute Board	11.15 AM
Presidential Address	Prof (Dr) Subimal Sen President, FOSET	11.25 AM
Inaugural Address	Prof (Dr) Parijat De Director of Technical Education & Training, Govt. of WB	11.30 AM
Vote of Thanks	Prof (Dr) Asok Kumar Principal, MCKVIE	11.40 AM

VALIDATORY SESSION

Introductory Address	Prof (Dr) Jaya Sil Chairperson, Organising Committee	04.45 PM
Validatory Address	Prof (Dr) Nil Ratan Bandopadhyay IEST, Sibpore	04.50 PM
Guest of Honour	Prof (Dr) Asok Kumar Principal, MCKV IE	05.00 PM
Certificate & Prize Award		05.05 PM to 05.30 PM

“Integrated Dyeing and Cosmetic Finishing on Cotton Fabric”

By

Md. Anowar Hossain

M.Tech. Student

Under the Guidance of

Professor (Dr.) A.K. Samanta

Professor and Head of the Department

Department of Jute and Fibre technology

Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta

Objectives of the Present Work

Feasibility of Single stage dyeing and multifinishing comparing with conventional double stage dyeing and finishing

Durable fragrance finishing for cotton textiles which may be an alternative invention of artificial perfume.

61

Effective use of beta cyclodextrin as dyeing bath auxiliaries as well as fragrance finishing also.

Why Integration in Dyeing and Finishing

One Stage Reducing

Time saving

Water saving and minimising WTP cost

Environment –friendly

Drying Cost

Low vapour-gas-emission

Heat energy saving

Low labour cost

62

Very low Effluent Treatment cost

Why Cosmetic Finishing on Textile

Relaxation
Sensuality
Exhilaration
Happiness
Well being

Stress reducing
High blood pressure reducing
Psychological & emotional improvement

Demands of Fragrance in Global Market

Fragrances Industry

Global Market for Flavors
2006 (US\$ Million)

Introduction on Cotton fibre

Schematic Structure of cotton fibre

Cotton Fibre

Repeat unit cellulose in cotton fibre

Introduction on Reactive dyes and Dyeing

Schematic Structure of Reactive Dye

Structure of Reactive Dye

Reaction between reactive dye and cellulose

Characteristics of Reactive dye:

Chromogenic part of the reactive dye

Reactive Groups

Monochlorotriazine ring.

Sulphonate ($-SO_3Na$) Group

Literature review
on
Simultaneous dyeing and finishing

Benefit of combined dyeing and finishing

Specialized section	Fuel	Electricity	Total	Percentage share
				in total
Fiber production	32551	21498	54049	21.0
Spinning	3224	44262	47480	18.4
Twisting	219	1660	1879	0.7
Textured yarn production	120	1543	1663	0.6
Weaving	4467	24848	29315	11.4
Knitting	4059	11709	15858	6.1
Conventional Dyeing and subsequent finishing in separate two step process (for both knitted and woven fabrics)				
	37661	28412	66073	25.0
Clothing manufacturing	8240	15420	23660	9.2
Others	5959	12000	17959	7.0
Total	96500	161442	257942	100.0

69

Energy consumption (in million Yen*) in the Japanese textile industry¹

Simultaneous dyeing and finishing

Bleached jute, Reactive dyes, DMDHEU

Bleached jute fabric, acid dye, DMDHEU

Significant improvement found:

Highly increased K/S value

Good levelness of dyeing

Higher dry crease recovery angle

Improved strength for beta Cyclodextrin

Dye fixation

Surface colour strength

Washing, rubbing & Light fastness

Ref-1: M Kamaluddin, M E Molla, S M B Rahman, M A K Azad, H M ZakirHossain &M M U Jubayer, J Bio Sci, 7(1) (2007)68

Ref-2: N C Pan, S N Chattopadhyay & A Day, Colourage, 4(1996) 32-36.

Ref-3: A K Samanta, D Singhee & K K Mahalanabis ,IE (I) Journal, 88(2) (2008) 17-25.

Ref-4: Improvement of ink jet printing performance using beta cyclodextrin on cotton fabric, Textile research journal, Manuscript ID TRJ-15-0179

Literature review
on
Aroma finishing

Fragrance and its function

Jasmine

Pachouli

Rose

72

Fragrance versus human sensory organs

By human olfactory neurons, only a few molecules are necessary for us to experience or identify scents.

Cyclodextrin

Corn is the raw material that provides the starch for cyclodextrin production

73

Structure of Dextrin

α , β & γ Cyclodextrin for microencapsulation

Figure: Structure of α -cyclodextrin, β -cyclodextrin, γ -cyclodextrin

Ref: David Rowe, WILEY publications, Chemistry and technology of flavours and fragrances.

α, β & γ Cyclodextrin for microencapsulation

Physicochemical properties	Alfa	Beta	Gama	Lamda
No of glycopyranose units	6	7	8	9
Central cavity diameter	4.7-5.3	6.0-6.5	7.5-8.3	10.3-11.2 ⁷⁵
Water solubility at 25°C	14.5	1.85	23.2	8.19
Molecular weight	972	1135	1297	1459

Ref: Development of cosmetic textiles using microencapsulation technology, S.Y. cheng, C.W.M. Yuen, C.W. Kan and K.K.L. Cheuk, RJTA Vol.12 (4) 2008.

Mechanism of microencapsulation

Natural Example of Microencapsulation

Why Microencapsulation

1. Controlled release or sustained release.
2. Protection of core content
3. Prevent interaction with other chemicals in the system
4. Protect active component from physical damage.

78

Ref: Development of cosmetic textiles using microencapsulation technology, S. Y. cheng, C.W.M. Yuen, C.W. Kan and K.K.L. Cheuk, RJTA Vol.12 (4) 2008.

Materials and Method ⁷⁹

Chemical Selection

Alcohol: Distilled water=1:3

Citric acid-6%, Sodium hypophosphite-6%

Beta Cyclodextrin 1-50%

Sodium carbonate for alkaline pH

Percentage of dyestuff was kept constant & three types of fragrance chemical was⁸⁰ trialed to get better performance in double stage as well as combined dyeing and finishing.

References

Aromachology and its application in the textile field, C.X. Wang, Sh.L.Chen, email: Wangchaoxia@sohu.com, College of textile and garments, Southern Yangtze University, College of chemistry and Chemical engineering, Donghua University, Shanghai 200051, P.R. China

Imparting antimicrobial and fragrance finish on cotton using chitosan with silicon softner, Anjali Karolia, Snehal Mendapara, Indian journal of fibre and textile science, Volume-32, March-2007, PP-99-104.

Cyclodextrin in the textile industry, Jozsef Szejtli, CYCLOLAB , Research and development laboratory ltd., Budapest, Hungary, Starch/Starke 55, (2003) 191- 196.

Synthesis of reactive fragranced entities and their application to cotton textiles, D.P. Chattopadhyay, Shweta, J.Doctor, Textiles and light industrial science and technology, Volume-2, Issue-2, April-2013.

Microencapsulation Methods:

Ref: Development of cosmetic textiles using microencapsulation technology, S. Y. cheng, C.W.M. Yuen, C.W. Kan and K.K.L. Cheuk, RJTA Vol.12 (4) 2008.

Double stage dyeing and Finishing machine **Single stage dyeing and finishing machine**

**Effect of beta cyclodextrin for microencapsulation
in combined dyeing and finishing comparing with dextrin and DMDHEU**

An Emulsifier was prepared by Polyethylene glycol & Distilled water (1:3)

Types of chemical	Conc.	R. Lemon yellow –CN	Synthetic Fragrance	Citric Acid	Sodium Hypophospite	Emulsifier	Sodium Carbonate
Beta Cyclodextrin	5%	1%	1%	10%	6%	77%	for ph 10-11
	10%	1%	1%	10%	6%	72%	for ph 10-11
	15%	1%	1%	10%	6%	67%	for ph 10-11
Dextrin	5%	1%	1%	10%	6%	77%	for ph 10-11
	10%	1%	1%	10%	6%	72%	for ph 10-11
	15%	1%	1%	10%	6%	67%	for ph 10-11
DMDHEU	5%	1%	1%	10%	6%	77%	for ph 10-11
	10%	1%	1%	10%	6%	72%	for ph 10-11
	15%	1%	1%	10%	6%	67%	for ph 10-11

Effect of fragrance and beta cyclodextrin in combined dyeing and finishing							
An Emulsifier was prepared by Polyethylene glycol & Distilled water (1:3) ⁽²²⁾							
Types of fragrance	Fragrance conc.	Dye-Lemon yellow CN	Beta Cyclodextrin	Emulsifier	Citric Acid	Sodium hypophosphate	Sodium Carbonate
Synthetic (Jasmine)	1%	1%	10%	72%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	2%	1%	10%	71%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	3%	1%	10%	70%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
Rose oil	1%	1%	10%	72%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	2%	1%	10%	71%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	3%	1%	10%	70%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
Pachouli oil	1%	1%	10%	72%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	2%	1%	10%	71%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	3%	1%	10%	70%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine)	1%	1%	0%	72%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	2%	1%	0%	71%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	3%	1%	0%	70%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
Rose oil	1%	1%	0%	72%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	2%	1%	0%	71%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	3%	1%	0%	70%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
Pachouli oil	1%	1%	0%	72%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	2%	1%	0%	71%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11
	3%	1%	0%	70%	10%	6%	For ph 10-11

Probable reaction in combined dyeing and finishing where monochlorotriazinyl group of reactive dye is making covalent bond with beta cyclodextrin and OH group of cotton fibre:

Major Benefit of combined dyeing and finishing:

Increasing the color strength (K/S) (**Shown in table 3**)

Controlled release of fragrance (**shown in table-04 & 5**)

Dry crease recovery angle (**Shown in table 3**)

Hydrolysis rate of dyestuff is minimizing and wastage rate of dyestuff is very minor.

Soft hand feel of fabric

86

Time, heat energy & water saving

low vapour-gas-emission

Low labour cost

Environment –friendly

Alternative of DMDHEU

Effect of physical properties, dyeing properties and finishing properties of Double stage dyeing and finishing as well as Combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric:

Treatments	T. strength (N/M)Wp & Wf	(+) in strength	(-) in strength	K/S value	Color fastness To wash	Light fastness	Dry crease Angle
Bleached untreated cotton fabric	0.278, 0.208		.002,.003	.0542	-	-	162
Dyed cotton fabric with conventional method	.270,.200		.008,.008	3.001	3	3	180
Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and beta cyclodextrin	.276, .205		.008, .013	2.898	4	4	256
Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and without beta cyclodextrin	.270,.195		.004,.009	2.999	2	2	200
Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and dexrin instead of B-CD	.274,.199		.018,.013	2.695	2	2	230
Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and DMDHEU instead of B-CD	.260,.195		-	2.565	2	2	250
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and beta cyclodextrin	.290, .280	.012, .072	.003, .008	3.239	3	3	264
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and without beta cyclodextrin	.275,.200	0	0	3.338	2	2	190
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and dexrin instead of B-CD	.278,.208		.009,.010	2.765	2	2	220
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and DMDHEU instead of B-CD	.269,.198		.002,.003	2.865	2	2	240

Data Table-03

Fragrance grading scale 0-100%, sensorial evaluation after number of days without washing

Types of fragrance	Fragrance concentration	Beta Cyclodextrin	First days	10th days	20th days	30 th days	40th days	50th days	60th days	70th days	80th days
Synthetic (Jasmine)	1%	10%	90%	80%	80%	70%	70%	30%	20%	10%	0%
	2%	10%	95%	85%	85%	80%	70%	40%	20%	10%	0%
	3%	10%	95%	85%	85%	80%	70%	40%	20%	10%	0%
Rose oil	1%	10%	50%	40%	20%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	10%	55%	40%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	10%	55%	40%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Pachouli oil	1%	10%	85%	70%	40%	10%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	10%	90%	70%	40%	10%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0% ⁸⁸
	3%	10%	90%	70%	40%	10%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine)	1%	0%	90%	70%	50%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	90%	70%	50%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	90%	70%	50%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Rose oil	1%	0%	90%	20%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	90%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	90%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Pachouli oil	1%	0%	90%	40%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	90%	40%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	90%	40%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

Data Table-04

Fragrance grading scale 0-100%, human sensorial evaluation after number of washing

Types of fragrance	Fragrance conc.	B. Cyclodextrin	Before washing	First	Second	Third	Fourth	Fifth
Synthetic (Jasmine)	1%	10%	90%	90%	80%	60%	50%	30%
	2%	10%	95%	90%	80%	70%	60%	40%
	3%	10%	95%	90%	80%	70%	60%	40%
Rose oil	1%	10%	50%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	10%	55%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	10%	55%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Pachouli oil	1%	10%	85%	50%	20%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	10%	90%	60%	30%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	10%	90%	60%	30%	0%	0%	0%
Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine)	1%	0%	90%	60%	40%	10%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	95%	70%	90%	10%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	95%	70%	90%	10%	0%	0%
Rose oil	1%	0%	40%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	45%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	45%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Pachouli oil	1%	0%	85%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	90%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	90%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%

Data Table-05

**Expected Application Areas
of
Fragrance finishing on Textile Substrates**

Bed Room curtains

Windows curtains

91

Sofa cover

Bed cover

Pillow cover

Sports wear

93

Exercise wear

Socks

Gloves

Ties

Handkerchief

Ladies inner

Fragrance finishing On Garments products

Womens
Product ID#1026

Womens
Product ID#1027

Womens
Product ID#1028

Conclusion

Process Minimisation = Cost Minimisation

Chemical Minimisation = Cost Minimisation

Technical finishing = Value added Product

Process minimisation + Chemical Minimisation = Ecofriendly Tech = Healthy life

Sample Exhibition

And

Garments video.flv

97

Question and Answering Session

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Dr. Arindam Bagchi

Teaching associates, ISDS, DJFT, IJT, CU,

Prof.(Dr.) Adwaita Konar,

GCETT, Serampur, Govt. of west Bengal, India.

Mr. Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik

Ph.D Research Scholar (Part time)

Under Prof. Dr. A.K. Samanta, DJFT, IJT, CU

Mrs. Kashmita Bhattacharjey

Ph.D Research Scholar (Part time)

Under Prof. Dr. A.K. Samanta, DJFT, IJT, CU

Mr. Nanda Gopal Chakraborty,

Project Assistant (Technical), ISDS project, DJFT, IJT, CU

Never forget how to dream

Thank you

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Product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, Product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com, s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 5 March 2026.

Keynote

A merchandising report of aroma encapsulated inner garments in 2015-2016 was reported to satisfy the funding authority of higher education and research. A merchandising of PhD research outcome was continued, overviewed, and assessed the comments of customers and relevant retailers of textile and fashion. It was a nine months duration full-time research project of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. The nine-month salary compensation was 27,00,000BDT for merchandising, founding, branding, running a new project, extra hours contributions, and research services. A short summary of research outcomes, research project billing, and financial record were also officially reported to University of Calcutta to satisfy PhD research, academic practice, PhD funding, PhD salary, PhD project, and 'PhD¹ compensation award' of author in 2015-2017 [1-4] [1, 2, 4, 5] [5-12] [13] [3] [14, 15] [16] [2, 4, 12, 17].

1 Discussion

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-sold and self-supplied the cosmetic textiles in the name of ladies inner garments in the name of 'fragrance finished bra' in 2016. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain got and recorded a lot of positive comments from local retailers in Bangladeshi supermarkets at Dhaka and Chittagong. He self-visited around 100 supermarkets in Dhaka City and Chittagong City in Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also self-collected and self-reviewed around 500 customer's overviews at his self-show room at Rajuk Trade Center Shopping Mall, Regency Hotel Building, Nikunja-2, Khilkhet, Dhaka-1229, Bangladesh[18]. Many local businessmen in garments show room commented positively about the cosmetic textiles in 2016 who told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in different ways in different review meetings, "your product is the new product in Bangladeshi markets in terms of fragrance-finished inner garments, we didn't get, we didn't sell such type of product in previous time; although we also purchased product from India." Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also self-visited K-mart in Australia in 2020-2022. K-Mart was selling different Bangladeshi products in Melbourne, Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also self-funded and

self-visited different local shops in Melbourne. But Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn't see any product of cosmetic textiles, any product of cosmetic finished inner garments in Melbourne. So, there is scope to develop the technology of technical textiles in terms of cosmetic and medicinal properties of textiles. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also extended his relevant research in relevant material design for aroma encapsulated inner garments for medical textiles, and color engineering. Materials of natural source were prioritized due to eco-friendly method design and human-friendly product design [1-4] [1, 2, 4, 5] [5-12] [13] [3] [14, 15] [16] [2, 4, 17].

Figure 1. Office of PhD research of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain on 'cosmetic textiles' at Dhaka, Bangladesh; funded by chief executive officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion.

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2 A short summary and evidence of field trialing costs of cosmetic textiles of MTech thesis and/or MPhil/PhD¹ thesis on “simultaneous dyeing and fragrance finishing of cotton fabric” at University of Calcutta, India

Figure 1, a field trialing of cosmetic textiles at University of Calcutta, India marketed and branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion; sole authored and sole funded by Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. The thesis was also officially registered and archived a printed copy and a digital copy at University Grants Commission of Bangladesh since 2017[12]. Every self-funded research should keep a record of the expenses for claiming his research and development costs. Every research is a contribution to the global community under the representation of university in academia and philosophia. What should be the judicial benefit of an author? Who paid money to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain? No government paid money to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. No university paid money to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India can/should manage a recognition of certificate and/or ‘PhD¹ compensation award’ to the author.

Date: 01/03/26
Office Expenditure, January: 2026

Office Salary : 50,000₹
Office Advance : 17,000₹
Furniture : 29490₹
Conveyance : 3650₹
Lunch : 2134₹
Entertainment : 500₹
Office rent : 2000₹
Office Stationery : 3604₹
Sample purchasing : 2690₹
Purchasing poly : 100₹
Office Nameplate : 1000₹
Mobile Bill : 2200₹
Internet Bill : 500₹
Burrnet : 900₹
Hanger : 200₹
Purchasing Tray & glass for tea : 390
Trade Fair Entry Ticket : 30
Bira Production : 66360₹
Total → 1,18,388₹ + 66,360₹
≈ 184,748₹

Approved By
01.03.2026
Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Engg. & Tech. Dept. of Textile Engg. & Design
City University
Dhaka-1213

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Bill

Date: 01/03/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : office Advance

Description :

Advance to House owner → 17000₹
 (02 month rent)

Approved
 &
 Received By

 01/03/16

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বিস্মিত্তাহির রাহমানির সাক্ষীকৃত

বিস্মিত্তাহির রাহমানির রাহিম

ক্যাশ মেমো ম্যানেজারঃ ০১৭৭১-৯৩০১১৩

বিক্রমপুর ফার্ণিচার
Bikrampur Furniture

এখানে সকল প্রকার ফার্ণিচার সামগ্রী পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 কারখানা : ৫০৭/৩, ৫২, ময়নারবাগ, হোসেন মার্কেট, উত্তর বাডডা, ঢাকা-১২১২
 পো-কম : রোড # ১৪, প্লট # ১/সি, কিলেক্ট, নিকুঞ্জ-২, (সোটাস কমানি টাওয়ারের পাশে), ঢাকা-১২২১।
 ফোনঃ- ০১৮১৮-৪১৩১৭৪, ০১৬৭৭-১৫১৪৮৫

নং **626** তারিখ **০২/০২/০১৬**

নাম	জোনা মামু হোসেন			ক্রয়কার মোবা
ঠিকানা	রোড #			

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
১	৫ ½ জোনা মামু বেতিন + মামু বেতিন	৩৮		
২	২০০ বেতিন কাইল	১৮		
৩	সেতি মামু (বেতিন)	২৮	১৪০০	৩৯২০০

৫০০ টাকা
 paid
 02/02/16
 Approved BB
 02/02/16

মোট- ৩৯৬০০
 অর্থম- 4
 বাকী-

টাকা কথায়ঃ

নিজে নামাজ পড়ুন, অন্যকে নামাজ পড়তে উৎসাহিত করুন।
 বিঃদ্রঃ বিক্রিত মাল কেবল বেওয়া হয় না

ক্রয়কার স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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বিস্মিল্লাহির রাহমানির রাহিম

ক্যাশ মেমো

মোবা : ০১৯১৩-১৭২৭৭০
: ০১৯১৩-১৭২৭৭০

মিনহাজ বেডিং স্টোর MINHAJ BEDDING STORE

প্রোঃ মোঃ মিজান মিয়া

এখানে উন্নতমানের লেপ, তোষক, জাজিম, মশরী, পর্দা, বালিশের কভার, লেপের কভার বিছানার চাদর, ফোম কভার, কুশন ইত্যাদি কাজ সুদক্ষ কারিগর দ্বারা তৈরী ও বিক্রয় করা হয় এবং পুরাতন কাজ রিপিংয়ারিং করা হয়।

দোকান নং-২, রোড নং-১২, খিলক্ষেত টানপাড়া, নিকুঞ্জ, ঢাকা-১২২৯

নং- 74

তারিখ ২০ ২ ২৬

নাম ০১৭৩২০৮১১০৭

ডেলিঃ তারিখ ২ ২ ২৬

ঠিকানা

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
	<p>Approved By 02/02/26 Md. Anowar Hossain Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain Barrister (Dr.)</p>			২০০০
				৫০০
				৫০০

বিঃ দ্রঃ ২১ দিনের মধ্যে মাল ডেলিভারী নিতে হবে। ২১ দিন পরে মালের কোন ক্ষতি/নষ্ট হলে কর্তৃপক্ষ দায়ী থাকিবে না। বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না।

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Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva

Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

বিস্মিত্বাহির রাহমানির রাহিম

ক্যাশ মেমো মানোজারঃ ০১৭৭১-৯৩০১১৩

বিক্রমপুর ফার্নিচার
Bikrampur Furniture

এখানে সকল প্রকার ফার্নিচার সামগ্রী পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
কারখানা : ৫০৭/৩.৫২, ময়নারবাগ, হোসেন মার্কেট, উত্তর বাজড়া, ঢাকা-১২১২
শো-রুম : রোড # ১৪, গুট # ১/সি, বিনকেত, নিতুল-২, (সেটাস কমান টাওয়ারের পার্শ্ব), ঢাকা-১২২৯।
শোঃ- ০১৮১৮-৪১৩১৭৪, ০১৬৭৭-১৫১৪৮৫

নং **627** তারিখ **০৯/০৯/২০২৩**

নাম **জামাল হুসেইন** জেতার মোবা

ঠিকানা

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
০১	২'x৬' বর্ড	১৭	২৪০০/	২৪০০/
<p style="text-align: center;">Approved By Dr. Anowar Hossain ০৯/০২/২৩</p>				
			মোট-	২৪০০/০০
			অর্থম-	
			বাকী-	৭

টাকা কথায় :

নিজে নাশাং পড়ুন, অন্যকে নামাজ পড়তে উৎসাহিত করুন।

বিঃ দ্রঃ বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না

জেতার স্বাক্ষর বিক্রতার স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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বাংলা ————— ইংরেজি

হাওলাদার ফার্নিচার

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সূত্র : তারিখ : ৩-২-১৬

১) *কম্পিউটার ফর্ম ২৫ খাঁজের = ৪৮ = ৩৪০০৮*

Approved by

 02/02/16

৩৪০০৮

 1/2/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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শাহজাদা আব্দুল মান্নান রাস্তা
ক্যাশ মেমো
 বিক্রয় কেন্দ্র

রাফিক এন্ড ব্রাদার্স-৩
RAFIQUE & BROTHERS
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সবিস্তার গ্রাসের দরজা, ডোরার টেবিল, চেইটন, প্রেসসিট, পাওয়ার ট্রে, প্রাস্টিক (PVC) সিটের দরজা
 কাঠের দরজা, সেক্টর, গাঙ্গী পানির ট্যাক এবং গৃহস্থের সামগ্রী প্রস্তুতকারক বিক্রেতা ও সরবরাহকারী।
 বাড়ী # ১, বাসা ৪ ১৭, নিকুঞ্জ-২, জরসাংহারা, ঢাকা-১২২৯।
 ফোন হেড অফিস : ৯১২৪০১৪, ৯১১২৩৫৫ পো-কম : ০১৭৪৯-৫১৭৮১৬

নং- **349** চালান নং- তারিখ : 2/2/20

নাম :
 ঠিকানা:

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	দর	টাকা
১	২০' x ২০' (ক্যাশ)	২০	২০
২	২০' x ২০'	৫০	৫০
৩	২০' x ২০'	৫০	৫০
		বাকী-	

টাকা (ক্যাশ) :
 শর্তাবলী :
 * মোট মূল্যের কমপক্ষে ৫০% অগ্রিম এবং অবশিষ্ট মূল্য সরবরাহের সময় প্রদান করতে হবে। *সাধারণভাবে সরবরাহের তারিখ আন্তর্জাতিকভাবে ঠিক রাখা হবে। কিন্তু দুর্ঘটনা জনিত কারণে যদি সরবরাহের তারিখ পিছিয়ে যায় তার জন্য কোন ধরনের ক্ষতিপূরণ দাবী করতে পারবে না। *ক্রয় আদেশ পাওয়ার অব্যাহতি পূর্বে প্রস্তুতকরণ প্রক্রিয়া শুরু হবে। কাজেই ক্রয় আদেশ প্রদানের পর ক্রয় আদেশ ফরমে কোন রূপ পরিবর্তন আনা যাবে না।

ক্রয়কার স্বাক্ষর: বিঃ দ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না। পক্ষে- রাফিক এন্ড ব্রাদার্স

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date: 01/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Office Searching

Description:

Mohakhali to Nikunja → 10₳

Nikunja to Mohakhali → 45₳

(By Bus & Rickshaw)

Total → 55₳

Approved

&

Received By

01/01/16

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Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill
Date: 01/01/26
Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
Post: chaitman
Purpose: office searching at Mohakhali & Nikunja
Description :
Lunch Bill → 150f
Total → 150f
Approved & Received By
[Signature]
01/01/26

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

Date: 01/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Official Meeting at Modina Restaurant
with garments producers.

Description:

Coffee & light food → 500f

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
01/01/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Conveyance Bill

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain Date : 05/01/16

Post : Chairman

Purpose : office searching at Nikunja

Description :

Tongi office to Nikunja → 35₹
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)
 Nikunja to Tongi office → 25₹

Total → 60₹

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 05/01/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Mobile: 01711111111
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

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Lunch Bill

Date: 05/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: office searching at Nikunja

Description:

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
05/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Mobile: 01732231104
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

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Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD

Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh

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Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva

Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date: 06/01/2016

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Office furniture purchasing

Description :

Tongi office to Nikunja → 35f
(By Bus & Rickshaw)

Nikunja to Tongi office → 35f

Total → 70f

Approved

&

Received By

06/01/15

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

Chairman
City University
Dhaka

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 06/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Office furniture Purchasing

Description:

Lunch Bill ————— 150/-

Approved
 &
 Received By

 06/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Mobile: 01732681104
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD³ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

7

Conveyance Bill

Date: 07/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Visiting Garments factory at Salna, Joydevpur

Description:

Tongi office to Salna → 30f

(By Bus & Rickshaw)

Salna to Tongi Office → 30f

Total → 60f

Approved & Received By

 07/01/16

Engr M. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Textile, Color & Material Research Centre
 RMIT University
 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date : 07/01/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Visiting Garments factory at Salna, Joydevpur.

Description :

Approved
&
Received By
A. Hossain
07/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Mobile: 01722931104
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT
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Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD
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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Date: 08/01/16

Post: chairman

Purpose: visiting garments factory

Description :

Tongi office to Mirpur-01 → 90f

(By Bus & Rickshaw)

Mirpur-01 to Tongi office → 90f

Total → 180f

Approved and

Received By

(Signature)

08/01/16

(Signature)

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Date: 08/01/16

Post: chairman

Purpose: visiting Garments factory

Description:

Approved and

Received By

[Signature]
08/01/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²³ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
 Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
 Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

**Office Rent
January - 2016**

Date: 08/01/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : chairman

Description :

Office rent, Gazipur, Tongi → 2000₳

120

Approved By

[Signature]
08/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Mobile: 01712681104
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Received By

[Signature]
08/01/16
01715550402

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date: 09/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman

Purpose: Visiting Buying house at Uttara

Description:

Tongi office to Uttara buying → 40f
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)
 Uttara to Tongi office → 40f

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 09/01/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
 [Stamp]

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com, s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 5 March 2026.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD¹ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 09/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Visiting Buying house at Uttara.

Description:

Lunch Bill → 150₳

Total → 150₳

Approved & Received By

 09/03/16

Engr Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 RMIT University
 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
 Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date: 10/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: office pad & visiting card making

Description:

Tongi office to khilkhet → 25f
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

khilkhet to Tongi office → 25f

|
 Total → 50f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 10/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 International Professor & Research Consultant
 Bangladesh Textile Engineering Research Institute
 Dhaka, Bangladesh

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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 Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 10/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Office pad & visiting card making

Description:

Approved
&
Received By

Anowar
10/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Chairman
Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
Mobile: 017227931104
Email: anowar@rmit.edu.au, a.hossain@cityu.edu.hk

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 10/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Purchasing office seal (Chairman)

Description:

Office Seal —————→ 70f

Stamp pad —————→ 50f

Total → 120f

Approved
&

Received By

[Signature]
10/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 10/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Description:

- 1) Preparing office pad → 1200f
- 2) Making visiting card → 400f

Approved By

[Signature]
10/03/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 (Chairman)
 Bangladesh Textile Research Institute
 Member, Textile Research Centre
 Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD, DPhil

~~Approved~~
 Received By

01931118111

MD ALAM G/R

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Bill

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Date: 11/03/16

Post: chairman

Purpose: Sample Purchasing

Description:

1. Sample purchasing from Nikunja → 600f
(1 pc)
2. Sample purchasing from Gazipur → 250f
(02 pcs)
3. Sample purchasing from Board Bazar → 200f
(02 pcs)

Total → 1050f

Approved
&
Received By

Anowar
11/03/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Chairman
Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
Mobile: 01732581104
Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD³ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Conveyance Bill

Date: 11/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Market research & sample purchasing

Description:

- Tongi office to Nikunja → 15f
- Nikunja to Boatd Bazar → 20f
- Boatd Bazar to Gazipur chowrasta → 10f

Total → 55f

Approved
&
Received By

Anowar
11/01/16

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Lunch Bill

Date: 11/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Inquiry about office furniture purchasing

Description:

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
11/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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নিসমিত্তাহির রাহমানির রাহিম
ক্যাশ মেমো

লাদেন সুতা ঘর

প্রোঃ মোঃ সাহাব উদ্দিন

মোবাইল : ০১৭৩২-৫৪০০২৮, ০১৭৩০-৯৩৭৩৫০
এখানে সকল প্রকার গার্মেন্টস, টেক্সটাইল এ্যাম্ব্রয়ডারী সহ যাবতীয়
সুইং সুতা ও দেশী-বিদেশী লেইজ সুলভ মূল্যে বিক্রয় করা হয়।
কোনাবাড়ী নিউ মার্কেট, দোকান নং ডি-৫, কোনাবাড়ী, গাজীপুর।

নং 6766 তারিখ ১২/১/১৬

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
০১	২৫০০	২ kg	২০০	২০০০
০২				
০৩				
০৪				
০৫				
০৬				
০৭				
০৮				
০৯				
১০				
১১				
১২				
১৩				
১৪				
১৫				
	ধন্যবাদ আবার আসবেন।		মোট	২০০০

টাকা (কথায়) ২০০০
ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর [Signature] বিঃ দ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ফেরৎ লওয়া হয় না। [Signature]

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ক্যাল মেমো

মোবাইল : ০১৯২০-২২০৪০১

সাদিয়া হোসিয়ারী গার্মেন্ট

গোঃ মোঃ আলমগীর হোসেন

এখানে সকল প্রকার রেডিমেট গার্মেন্টস পোশাক পাইকারী বিক্রয় করা হয়।

১৪৫৭ নতুন বাজার, কোনাবাড়ী, গাজীপুর।

নং-

তারিখ ২২/৩/২০২৬

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
১	সাদিয়া ৩২/৩৬	২	৩৫৫	৭১০
২	-	৩	২০০	৬০০
৩	-	২	২৫০	৫০০
৪	৩৬/৪০	২	৩০০	৬০০
৫	চিকি ৩৬/৪০	২	৪০০	৮০০
৬	৩২/৩৬	২	২০৫	৪১০
৭	-	২৫	২৫	৬২৫
৮				২২৪০
৯				
১০				
১১				
১২				
১৩				
১৪				
১৫				
মোট =				

১২/০১/১৬
ক্রমিক স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রিত মাল কেবল নেওয়া হয়ে না।

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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Conveyance Bill

Date: 12/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Purchasing sample from Konabari

Description:

Tongi office to Konabari → 35₹

(By Bus & Rickshaw)

Konabari to Tongi office → 40₹

Total → 75₹

Approved & Received By

(Signature)
12/03/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Material Research Centre
 Textile, Color & Material Research Centre

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Lunch Bill

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Date: 12/01/16

Post: chairman

Purpose: Purchasing sample from Konabari

Description:

Lunch Bill → 150₳

Total → 150₳

Approved

&

Received By

12/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

Chairman
Mobile: +8801788396264

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Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD
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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill Date: 13/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Description:

Office Name plate —————→ 300f

Total → 300f

Approved By

Abbas

13/03/16

Received By

Abbas

13/03/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date: 13/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: office Nameplate making

Description :

Tongi office to khilkhet → 25₳
(By Bus & Rickshaw)

khilkhet to Tongi office → 25₳

↓
Total → 50₳

Approved
&
Received By
A. Hossain
13/01/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2,3} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill Date: 13/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Making office name plate

Description:

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
13/01/16

[Faint signature and text]

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

Date: 13/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Office stationery purchasing

Description:

A4 Size papers → 20₳

Pen refill → 30₳

Total → 50

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
13/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Mobile Bill Date: 14/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Official Mobile Bill

Description:

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
14/03/16

[Faint purple stamp]

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Internet Bill

Date: 14/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Official Internet Browning

Description:

Grameen phone internet → 300f

Approved

&

Received By

[Signature]

14/01/16

Engr M. Anowar Hossain

[Faint stamp]

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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 Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill Date: 14/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Burner purchasing for office
 Description:

Approved & Received By
 [Signature]
 14/03/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date: 14/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: office pad & visiting card receiving
 Business purchasing

Description:

Tongi office to Nikunja → 35₹
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Nikunja to Tongi office → 35₹

Total = 70₹

Approved
 &
 Received By

[Signature]
 14/01/16

[Faint stamp]

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 14/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: office pad & visiting card receiving
Buttner purchasing

Description:

Lunch Bill → 150₹

Total → 150₹

Approved
&
Received By

14/01/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Lunch Bill

Date: 16/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to factory, Salna.

Description:

Lunch Bill → 150f

Total → 150f

Approved
&
Received By

A. Hossain
16/01/16

[Faint handwritten notes and stamps]

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Conveyance Bill

Date: 16/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to factory, Salna.

Description:

Tongi office to salna → 30₳
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Salna to Tongi office → 30₳

Approved & Received By

[Signature]
 16/01/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Lunch Bill

Date: 17/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Bapari Garments & Impertial dyeing & finishing .

Description :

Approved
 &
 Received By
[Signature]
 17/01/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
 Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill Date: 17/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Bapari Garments & Imperial dyeing & finishing.

Description:

Tongi office to Bapari Garments → 80₹
 (Narayanganj)

Bapari Garments to Tongi Office → 80₹
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

|
 Total → 160₹

Approved & Received By

 17/01/16

Faint handwritten notes and stamps at the bottom of the bill.

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Conveyance Bill

Date: 18/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Noyamati Narayanganj

Description:

Tongi office to Noyamati → 140F
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Noyamati to Tongi office → 120F
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Approved
 &
 Received By

[Signature]
 18/01/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 18/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Noyamati, Narayanganj.

Description:

Approved & Received By

[Signature]
18/01/16

[Faint handwritten notes]

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Bill

Date: 18/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Noyamati, Narayanganj.

Description:

Approved
&
Received By

A. Hossain
18/01/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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 Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill Date: 19/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Market research at Tongi Zone

Description:

Approved & Received By

[Signature]
19/03/16

[Faint handwritten notes]

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 20/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Brca Production

Description:

Brca → $756 \times 60 = 45360\text{f}$

Box → $4200 \times 5 = 21000\text{f}$

Total → 66360f

Approved

&

Received By

20/03/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 21/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Salna, Gazipur for sample

Description:

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
21/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Conveyance Bill

Date: 21/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Salna, Gazipur for sample

Description:

Tongi office to Salna → 30₳
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Salna to Tongi office → 30₳

Total → 60₳

Approved
 &
 Received By

Anwar
 21/01/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain

Chairman, Textile Engineering Research Institute
 Dhaka, Bangladesh

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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 Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill

Date: 23/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Enquiry about sewing m/c price

Description:

Tongi office to Abdullahpur, Tongi → 20₳
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Abdullahpur to Tongi office → 15₳

Total → 35₳

Approved
&
Received By

(Signature)
23/01/16

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Lunch Bill

Date : 23/01/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Inquiry about sewing m/c price

Description :

Lunch Bill → 150f

Total → 150f

Approved
&

Received By

23/01/16

Faint handwritten notes in red ink, possibly a receipt or acknowledgment.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Tea Bill Date: 23/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Inquiry about sewing m/c purchasing

Description:

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
23/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chartered Engineer
 Member, Institution of Engineers (I.E.)
 Member, Institution of Mechanical Engineers (I.M.E.)
 Member, Institution of Textile Technologists (I.T.T.)

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

01 | ☒

Bill

Date: 23/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: stationery purchasing

Description:

A4 size paper —————> 10₳

Pen refill —————> 20₳

Total → 30₳

Approved
&
Received By

23/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Chairman
Barrister (Dr.)
Mobile: 01788396264
Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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 Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

4000

Bill

Date: 23/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Purchasing sample
 Description:

Lingerie purchasing from market → 500/-

Total → 500/-

Approved
 &
 Received By
 Anowar
 23/01/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, VIC 3056, Australia
 Mobile: +8801788396264
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

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Bill

Date: 25/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Trade fair entry ticket.

Description:

Trade fair entry ticket → 30f

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
25/01/16

Total → 30f

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill Date: 25/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Going to International Trade Fair-16
 Description:

Tongi office to Agargaon → 50₳
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Agargaon to Tongi office → 50₳

Total → 100₳

Approved
 &
 Received By

 25/03/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile Engineering Research Institute
 100/10/6, GPO, Dhaka-1000

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Lunch Bill

Date: 25/03/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Going to International trade fair-16.

Description :

Lunch Bill → 150₳

Total → 150₳

Approved
&
Received By

Anowar
25/03/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Chairman
Bangladesh Textile Mills Association
Member - 01, Dhaka 1214
e-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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 Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
 Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Date: 25/03/16

Bill
 Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Purchasing Tray & glam for Tea
 Description:

Gelams - 02 per	→	200f
Tray - 01 per	→	170f
stickers for office decoration	→	20f
		↓
		Total → 390f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 25/03/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Mobile: 01788396264
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 25/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Purchasing Hanger

Description:

Four Headed Hanger → ২০০₳
 (০৩ পিস)

For sample showing

Approved

&

Received By

25/03/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

Chairman

Bangladesh Textile & Fashion

Mirpur-12 Dhaka-1214

Phone: 01711244444

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill Date: 25/01/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post : Chairman
 Purpose : Mobile communication
 Description :

Approved
 &
 Received By

 25/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Mobile: 017 17883964
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

Date: 25/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Gp internet connection

Description:

Internet Bill → 200₳

Approved
&
Received By

A. Hossain
25/01/16

Total → 200₳

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Chairman
Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
Mobile: 017 3248 1104
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

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Lunch Bill

Date: 26/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Bank, Mohakhali Branch

Description:

Lunch Bill → 150f

Approved & Received By
Anowar
26/01/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
Chairman
Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
Melb: 017 32681104
Email: anowar@rmit.edu.au

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill Date : 26/01/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Going to Bank, Mohakhali Branch

Description :

Tongi office to Mohakhali (By Bus & Rickshaw)	→	30f
Mohakhali to Tongi office	→	30f

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
26/01/16

Engr Md Anowar Hossain
Chairman
Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
Mobile: 017 22681104
Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in technology and law

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Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT
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 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
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 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill No: **ART LOKATION**
 Shikary Art & Publicity

Name: *Md. Anowar Hossain* Date: *27-01-16*

Address: Mobile No:

SL	Particulars	Size / Qty	Total Feet	Rate	Amount
	<i>Stile Board</i>				<i>700</i>
	<i>1 PCS</i>				
PAID					
<i>Approved & Received By <i>Amr</i> 27/01/16</i>					
Total:					<i>700/-</i>
Advance:					
Due:					

Taka in words:

Customer's Sign: *Shikar*
 For Shikary Art

MohiUddin mantion, Kazi bar Road
 Gazipura, tongi, Gazipur. Mobile **01716-946480**
01956-244586

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KHES

কাজী হার্ডওয়্যার এড ইলেকট্রনিক্স কোর্স

শ্রোঃ কাজী রফিকুল ইসলাম

এখানে পেইন্ট, ভার্ণিস, বেস্ট বেয়ারিং, তার, তারকাটা, ড্রিল মেশিন এবং যাবতীয় হার্ডওয়্যার এর মালামাল পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।

হাজী আঃ খালেদ মার্কেট, গাজীপুরা, টঙ্গী, গাজীপুর।

মোবাইল : ০১৭০৩-৯১০৪৪৮

নং	430	তারিখ :	29/02/2026
নাম :			
ঠিকানা :			
ক্রঃ নং	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	টাকা
	১. ১০০ গ্রাম	১০০ গ্রাম	২০৳
	২. ১০০ গ্রাম	১০০ গ্রাম	৬০৳
	৩. ১০০ গ্রাম	১০০ গ্রাম	২০০৳
	৪. ১০০ গ্রাম	২০০ গ্রাম	৪৳
<p>Approved & Received By</p> <p>27/02/26</p> <p>Dr. Anowar Hossain</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant</p> <p>Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc</p>			
		মোট-	২৪৪৳

টাকা (কথায়)

বিঃ দ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না।

ক্ষেতার স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

27/02/26

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বিস্ময়কর বাস্তবতার স্বাক্ষর
ক্যাশ মেমো
 মোব ০১৭২৪-৩১১২০৬
 ০১০৪৪-৩০১০০৯

SAB এস.আলম বেডিং স্টোর
 প্লোঃ মোঃ এখলাস উদ্দিন

এখানে অটোমেটিক মেশিনে তুলা ধুলাই করে লেপ, তোষক, বালিশের কভার জাজিম, সোফা সেট, পর্দা, ইত্যাদি প্রস্তুতকারক ও সরবরাহকারী।
 কাজী মুল্লুক হোসেন রোড, গাজীপুরা, টঙ্গী, গাজীপুর।

নং **817** তারিখ **২২/১১/২০**

নাম : **শ্রী. শ্রী. মোঃ হুমায়ুন কবীর**

ঠিকানা : **৩০৯/১০**

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
	১. ১০০০	১০		
	২০০		৪০	৮০০
	৩০০		৬০	১৮০০
	৪০০		২০০	৮০০
	৫০০			১০০
	৬০০			১০০
	৭০০			১০০
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	১০০০			১০০
	১১০০			১০০
	১২০০			১০০
	১৩০০			১০০
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	১৫০০			১০০
	১৬০০			১০০
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	৯৯০০			১০০
	১০০০০			১০০

১৫ দিনের মধ্যে মাল জেলিভারী না নিলে কোন ক্ষতি হলে কতৃপক্ষ দায়ী নহে।

ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর _____ বিক্রিত মাল ফেরৎ লওয়া হয় না। বিক্রোক্তার স্বাক্ষর _____

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

01

Conveyance Bill Date: 31/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: office furniture purchasing

Description:

Tongi office to Tongi Bazar	15₹
Tongi Bazar to Tongi office	15₹
(By Bus & Rickshaw)	
Total → 30₹	

Approved & Received By

31/03/16
 Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile Fashion
 Mobile: 01722681104
 Email: engr.anowar@rmit.edu.au

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Conveyance Bill

Name : Mr. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : office shifting by pick-up

Description :

Tongi office to Nikunja office —————→ 1500₳

Labour cost —————→ 500₳

Approved & Received

By

Anowar

31/01/26

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman
 Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Mobile: 01732681104
 Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

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Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia

Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia

Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

ফ্যান মেমো

মোহাম্মদীয়া রেস্টুরেন্ট

এখানে উন্নতমানের খাবার যত্নসহকারে পরিবেশন করা হয়

এবং যে কোন অনুষ্ঠানে অর্ডার সরবরাহ করা হয়।

গাজীপুরা বাস স্ট্যান্ড, ময়মনসিংহ রোড, টঙ্গী, গাজীপুর।

মোবাস: ০১৭৪০-৯৫০১২৬

০১৯১৫-৩৮৪০৮১

তারিখ ৩১.০১.১৬

নামঃ				
ঠিকানা				
ক্রমিক নং	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
২	৩৬০০ চাউন			২৬০০
	বিবরণ			
			মোট	২৬০০
			অর্ডার	
			বাকী	

Approved & Received

By
31/01/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Chairman
Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
Mobile: 01732631104
Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

টাক কথায়.....

স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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হাওলাদার ফার্নিচার
HAWLADAR FURNITURE
 All Kinds of Latest T.V. Trolley, Chair, Coat Hanger And Office Furniture Retailer & Supplier
 Uttara Show Room Uttara Tower (Basement Floor), 1 Jashim Uddin Avenue, Sector # 03, Uttara, Dhaka-1230.
 MOBILE: ~~01610-610184~~ 01610-610184 E-mail: & fb: hawladarfurniture@yahoo.com

সূত্র: _____ তারিখ: ৩০-০১-১৬

১) ~~সুপার সফট~~ (H) ২২ পিস = ৬০০০০

২) ~~সুপার সফট~~ সফট সফট = ২০০০
 ৪০০০

Approved By

 Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
 International Professor & Research Consultant
 Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc

~~Full Price~~ = ৪০০০০

০১৬৮৩৫৭৩৫৫৪

~~সফট~~
 সফট

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বিশ্বমিত্রাহির রাহমানির রাহীম

জম জম পেপার হাউজ এন্ড স্টেশনারী ক্যাশ মেনো

JOM JOM PAPER HOUSE & STATIONARY

প্রোগ্রাম মোঃ গুন্নর ফারুক

এখানে সকল প্রকার কাগজ, খাতা, কলম, ফটোকপি পেপার, অফসেট পেপার ক্যালকুলেটরসহ অফিসিয়াল যাবতীয় মালামাল পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 মোবাইল : ০২-৯৮১৪৬৮৫, ০১৭৬২-৬৩১৬১৭, ০১৭৯৫-২৩৫৫২২
 সবুয়া মার্কেট, টঙ্গী বাজার, গাজীপুর মহানগর।

তারিখ: ৩০/৩/২০২৬

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
	খোলা মা ২৫	৬		১০৫০
	A-4 হাউজ	৫০০		৭০
	ড্রয়িং হাউজ	৫০০		৬০
	A-4 ২৫সিটার	১০		২৬০
	বেজিয়ার	২৫		৭০
	৫০৬২ কালি	১০		২৬০
	কালি	১০		২০
	সিগনেচার	১০		১২০
	কালি সাদা	১০		১৫০
	গ্লাস	১০		৪০
	কালি	১০		৬০
	কালি	১০		১০
	A-4 ২৫সিটার	১০		২৭০

কম্বায় : Approved By: ৩০/৩/২৬
 ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর: মোঃ নাজিম বেহেতের চাৰি
 মোট: ১৪৭,৭৭৪

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Conveyance Bill

Date: 30/01/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Purchasing stationery for office

Description:

Tongi office to Tongi Bazar → 15₳
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Tongi Bazar to Tongi office → 65₳
 (By Rickshaw)

Total → 80₳

Approved
 &
 Received By

 30/01/16

Md. Anowar Hossain
 Chairman

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Salary
2016- JANUARY

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain Date : 01/02/16

post : chairman

Description :

Salary of January → 50,000f

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
01/02/16

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Chairman
Department of Textile & Fashion
RMIT University
Melbourne, Australia

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Office Expenditure, January, 2016

Office Salary: 50,000₹

Office Advance: 17,000₹

Furniture: 29,490₹

Conveyance: 3,650₹

Lunch: 3,134₹

Entertainment: 500₹

Office rent: 2,000₹

Office stationery: 3,604₹

Sample purchasing: 3,690₹

Purchasing poly: 100₹

Office Nameplate: 1,000₹

Mobile Bill: 2,200₹

Internet Bill: 500₹

Burner: 900₹

Hanger: 200₹

Purchasing Tray & glass for tea: 390

Trade fair Entry Ticket: 30

Brca Production: 66,360₹

Total → 1,18,388₹ + 66,360₹
= 1,84,748₹

Approved By

01.02.2016

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Bangladesh
Chairman
Mobile: 017-22-22-22
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

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Bill

Date: 01/01/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post : Chairman
 Purpose : Office Advance
 Description :

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 01/01/16

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01

বিস্মিত্বাহির রাহমানির রাহিম

ক্যাশ মেমো

ম্যানেজারঃ ০১৭৭১-৯৩০১১৩

বিক্রমপুর ফার্নিচার Bikrampur Furniture

নং 626

এখানে সকল প্রকার ফার্নিচার সামগ্রী পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
কারখানাঃ ৫০৭/৩.৫২, ময়নারবাগ, হোসেন মার্কেট, উত্তর বাডতা, ঢাকা-১২১২
ফোন-কমঃ রোড # ১৪, গুট # ১/দি, বিল্ডিং-২, (সোটার কাফল টাওয়ারের পাশে), ঢাকা-১২২৯।
ফোনঃ- ০১৮১৮-৪১৩১৭৪, ০১৬৭৭-১৫১৪৮৫

তারিখঃ ০২/০২/০১৬

নামঃ শেখ মোঃ হোসেন ক্রেতার মোবাঃ

ঠিকানাঃ রোড #

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
১	৫ ½ ডিগ্রি (১ টি) + ১১ ১/২ ডিগ্রি (১ টি)	২৮		
২	২০১ ডিগ্রি কাইট	২৮		
৩	১০ ১/২ ডিগ্রি (১ টি)	২৮	২৪৮০০	৩৪৮০০
<p>০২/০২/০১৬</p> <p>Approved By</p> <p>০১/০২/১৬</p>				
			মোট-	২৪৮০০
			অর্থম-	
			বাকী-	৪

টাকা কথায়ঃ

নিজে নামাজ পড়ুন, অন্যকে নামাজ পড়তে উৎসাহিত করুন।

বিঃক্রঃ বিভিন্ন মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না

ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

বিস্মিল্লাহির রাহমানির রাহিম
ক্যাশ মেমো
মোবা : ০১৯১০-১৭২৭৭০
: ০১৯১৯-১৭২৭৭০

মিনহাজ বেডিং স্টোর
MINHAJ BEDING STORE
প্রোগ্রাম মোঃ মিজান মিয়া

এখানে উন্নতমানের লেপ, তোষক, জাজিব, মশারী, পর্দা, বালিশের কভার, লেপের কভার
বিছানার চাদর, ফোম কভার, ফুশন ইত্যাদি কাজ সুন্দর কারিগর দ্বারা তৈরী ও বিক্রয় করা হয়
এবং পুরাতন কাজ রিপিংয়ারিং করা হয়।

দোকান নং-২, রোড নং-১২, বিলক্ষেত টানপাড়া, নিকুঞ্জ, ঢাকা-১২২৯

নং: 74 তারিখ ২০২৬
নাম ০১৭৩২৬৮১১০৭৭ ডেলিভি তারিখ ২০২৬
ঠিকানা

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
				২০০০
			মোট-	২০০০
			অর্থীম-	৫০০
			বাকী-	১৫০০

বিঃ দ্রঃ ২১ দিনের মধ্যে মাল তেলিভারী নিতে হবে। ২১ দিন পরে মালের কোন
ক্ষতি/নষ্ট হলে কর্তৃপক্ষ দায়ী থাকিবে না। বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না।

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বিস্ময়কর রাহস্যময়

জম জম পেপার হাউজ এন্ড ষ্টেশনারী ক্যাশ মেমো

JOM JOM PAPER HOUSE & STATIONARY

শ্রোঃ মোঃ ওমর ফারুক

এখানে সকল প্রকার কাগজ, বাতা, কলম, ফটোকপি পেপার, অফসেট পেপার ক্যালকুলেটরসহ অফিসিয়াল যাবতীয় মালামাল পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 মোবাইল : ০২-৯৮১৪৬৮৫, ০১৭৬২-৬৩১৬১৭, ০১৭৯৫-২৩৫৫২২
 সবুয়া মার্কেট, টঙ্গী বাজার, গাজীপুর মহানগর।

নং	5919				তারিখ	
নাম						
ঠিকানা						
সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা		
				২০৬০০		
	কিউ	২৫	৮০	২০০০		
	১৫৫	১৫	৮০	১২০০		
				২০৬০০		
Approved By						
30/03/16						
কথায়ঃ	Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain				মোটা	২০৬০০
ক্রমিক নং	নামাজ বেহেস্তের চানি				বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর	

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com, s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 5 March 2026.

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Office Expenditure, February, 2016

- Office Salary → 50,000₹
- Office Rent → 12,000₹
- Mobile Bill → 1620₹
- Internet Bill → 1000₹
- Office Entertainment → 5790₹
- Conveyance → 2885
- Office cookery & cleaners → 2000₹
- Fan → 2650₹
- Name clearance certificate → 2000₹
- Furniture → 8000₹
- Purchasing sample → 1220₹
- Office. Beg → 1000₹
- chemical → 9990₹
- Telephone Box → 1280₹
- Trade license → 15000₹
- Labour cost → 1620₹
- Telephone connection → 5900₹
- Miscellaneous → 53415₹
-
- Total → 177370₹

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Mobila Bill

Date: 01/02/15

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: office mgt.

Description:

Approved
 &
 Received By
 Anowar
 01/02/15

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

Date: 01/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: office meeting

Description:

office entertainment → 500₳

Approved & Received By
Anowar
01/02/16

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 02/02/15

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: office Entertainment

Description:

Coffee	→	300₳
Milk	→	200₳
Biocuit	→	100₳

Total → 600₳

Approved
&
Received By

02/02/15

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Advance IT Technologies Limited
 1087

Thanks with Ait. Anowar

The Sum of Taka _____
 Month of Feb-20 Installation Charge _____ TK 500 + 500

DATE: 02/02/2016
 D D M M Y Y Y

Internet Section Software Section Domain Registration Web Hosting Training Section

Nikunja Office Uttara Office

Authorized Signature

DBBL bKashi

1919 25773191

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Bill

Date: 03/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Purchasing miscellaneous item

Description:

Tea Mog → 80₳

Sandel for washroom → 50₳

Balconi curtain → 300₳

Total → 430₳

Approved

&

Received By

A. H.

03/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

7/18

Conveyance Bill

Date: 05/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Narayanganj for order placement.

Description:

Nikunja office to Noyamati → 70₳

Noyamati to Nikunja office → 70₳

(By Bus & Kickstaco)

Total → 140₳

Approved

&

Received By

A.H.

05/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Tea Bill

Date: 05/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Going to Natrayangong for order placement.

Description :

Tea Bill → 20₳

Total → 20₳

Approved
&
Received By

05/02/16

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Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²³ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 05/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : chairman

Purpose : office cooking

Description :

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
05/02/16

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Lunch Bill

Date: 05/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Natogyangong

Description:

Lunch Bill → 150₳

Approved

&

Received By

Abub

05/02/16

Total → 150₳

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"কিন্তু কীভাবে রাখা যায় বাফি"

পাওয়ার হাউজ

POWER HOUSE

for electric & kitchen needs

এখানে সকল ধরনের ম্যান, হ্যাঞ্জার লাইট, গ্যাসের রুপান্তর যন্ত্রিকা ইলেকট্রিক মালামাল ও প্রান্তিক সামগ্রী বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 বাড়ী # ৫০, রোড # ১২, নিকুন্-২, ঢাকা-১২২৯।

ভাউচার

নামঃ _____ তারিখঃ 05/02/16

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	টাকা
০১	কম্পাউন্ড লাইট ০১	২৭৫/-
০২	গ্যাসের রুপান্তর যন্ত্রিকা ০১	২০০/-
মোট- ২৭৫/-		

কেন্দ্রীয় আফিসে।

কেন্দ্রীয় আফিস

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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01 25

Bill

Date: 06/02/15

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Purchasing Towel

Description:

Office Towel (02 pcs) → 450F

Approved
&
Received By

06/02/15

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 06/02/15

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
Post : chairman
Purpose : Electrical maintenance
Description :

Electrical maintenance charge (Fan) → 100f

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
06/02/15

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Conveyance Bill

Date: 07/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Banesti for market survey

Description:

Nikunja office to Banesti, Binadini → 40₳
 shopping complex

Banesti to Nikunja office → 40₳
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

Approved
&

Received By

Anowar
07/02/16

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Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Lunch Bill Date: 07/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Market survey

Description:

Lunch Bill (02 Person)	300f
Total → 300f	

Approved & Received By

 07/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Conveyance Bill

Date: 08/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Going to Registrar office of joint stock company .

Description :

Nikunja office to Kawranbazar → 80f

Kawranbazar to Nikunja office → 80f

(By Bus & Rickshaw)
02 person

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
08/02/16

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 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva

Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill Date: 09/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Going to Telephone office
 Description:

Nikunja office to Azomput, Ullatga → 30₳
 (By Bus & Rickshaw - 02 person)

Azomput, Ullatga to Nikunja office → 30₳

Total → 60₳

Approved
 &
 Received By

 09/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 09/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : chairman

Purpose : Going to Telephone office

Description :

Lunch Bill → 300f
 (02 person)

Total → 300f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 09/02/16

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Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 09/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to registration office of joint stock company.

Description:

Lunch Bill → 300₳
(02 person)

Total → 300₳

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
09/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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01/25

নিম্নলিখাতিব কাছমানির বারিসিহা

Bill

Date : 09/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : chairman

Purpose : Purchasing Sample

Description :

T-shirt - 02 per → 200/-

Approved
&
Received By
A.H.
09/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc⁵ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD⁶ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD⁷ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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বিক্রমপুর ফার্নিচার

Bikrampur Furniture

এখানে সকল প্রকার ফার্নিচার সামগ্রী পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 কারখানা : ৫০৭/৩.৫২, ময়নাবাগ, হোসেন মার্কেট, উত্তর বাজড়া, ঢাকা-১২১২
 মো-কম : রোড # ১৪, গুট # ১/সি, বিল্ডিং-২, (লেটাস কমাল টাওয়ারের পাশে), ঢাকা-১২২৯।

৬৭১ মোঃ- ০১৮১৮-৪১৩১৭৪, ০১৬৭৭-১৫১৪৮৫

তারিখ ৩/০২/২০২০

নং	৬৭১	তারিখ	৩/০২/২০২০
নাম	শেখ মোঃ হুমায়ুন কবীর	ফ্রেমের মোব	
ঠিকানা	রোড # ১৪	বা.প # ৩২	

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
১	ফার্নিচার সামগ্রী	২৫	১০০/-	২৫০০/-
			মোট-	২৫০০/-
			অগ্রিম-	
			বাকী-	২৫০০/-

টাকা কথায় :

নিজে নামাজ পড়ুন, অন্যকে নামাজ পড়তে উৎসাহিত করুন।

বিঃদ্রঃ বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না

ফ্রেমের স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

বিস্মিত্তাহির রাহমানির রাহিম

ক্যাশ মেমো

ম্যানেজারঃ ০১৭৭১-৯৩০১১৩

বিক্রমপুর ফার্নিচার Bikrampur Furniture

এখানে সকল প্রকার ফার্নিচার সামগ্রী পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
কারখানাঃ ৫০৭/৩.৫২, ময়নারবাগ, হোসেন মার্কেট, উত্তর বাডডা, ঢাকা-১২১২
ফোন-রুমঃ রোড # ১৪, গুট # ১/সি, খিলক্ষেত, বিকল্প-২, (লোটিস কামাল টাওয়ারের পাশে), ঢাকা-১২১৯।

৬৭৩ মোঃ- ০১৮১৮-৪১৩১৭৪, ০১৬৭৭-১৫১৪৮৫

নং

তারিখ ১১/০২/২০১৬

নাম মোঃ জিয়াবুল হক ক্রেতার মোবা .

ঠিকানা রোড # ১০ বায় # ২২

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
২/	৩৬x২৮ আফিস চেয়ার	২৫	২৭০০/-	২৭০০/-
				মোট- ২৭০০/-
				অগ্রিম- //
				বাকী- //

বাকী = ২৭০০/-

টাকা কথায়ঃ

নিজে নামাজ পড়ুন, অন্যকে নামাজ পড়তে উৎসাহিত করুন।

নিঃস্বঃ বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না

ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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চন্দন টেক্সটাইল

CHANDAN TEXTILE

উন্নতমানের টিম্পার্ট পাইকারী বিক্রেতা।
 ২নং নয়ামাটি, গিরীধারী মার্কেট, নারায়ণগঞ্জ।

ফোন : ০২-৭৬৪৪৭৯১, মোবা : ০১৮১৯-১২৯৬৪৫, ০১৭১২-৮১৩৯৭৪, ০১৮১৪-০৯৫৮৯১

নং	03	তারিখ	২০/০২/২০২৩		
নাম	শ্রী: জা/নয়ামাটি - হা/নয়ামাটি				
ঠিকানা					
নং	মালের বিবরণ	ডজন	পিছ	দর	টাকা
০১	৬২/৬৪ হা/নয়ামাটি		৬৫	৩৭০	২৪,২০৫
টাকা কথায় :			মোট-	২৪,২০৫	
ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর			বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর		

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০১

বিল অফিস - ৭৬৩৩৫৩৭

আনন্দ রেস্টোরাঁ

৪ শহীদ সোহরাওয়ার্দী রোড, নারায়ণগঞ্জ।

নং 454 তারিখ ২০/২/২০২৪

নামঃ

ক্রমিক	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
	কিচেন	২২০ম	২২০	২৪০৮
				মোট ২৪০৮

স্বাক্ষর: *[Signature]*
 পক্ষে - আনন্দ রেস্টোরাঁ

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Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill Date: 10/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to factory, Narayanganj.

Description:

Nikunja office to factory → 260f
(02 person)

Factory to Nikunja office → 260f
(By Bus & Rickshaw & Leguna)

Total → 520f

Approved & Received By
[Signature]
10/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 11/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Ulta's buying office

Description:

Lunch Bill (02 person) → 350₳

Total → 350₳

Approved

&

Received By

Signature

11/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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UT 123
Conveyance Bill Date: 11/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Purchasing office Bag

Description:

Nikunja office to Tongi Bazar → 25f
 Tongi Bazar to office → 25f

|
 Total → 50f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 11/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 12/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : Chairman

Purpose : Purchasing miscellaneous Item

Description :

Paposh (02 pes)	→	600₹
RFL knife	→	200₹
Biscuit	→	150₹
TEA	→	120₹
Milk	→	150₹
Sugar	→	20₹
Electric Balb	→	50₹
Electric Mixer	→	2700₹
Hanger - 06 pes	→	84₹
<hr/>		
Total →		4174₹

Approved
 &
 Received By

 12/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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01 | 20

Lunch Bill

Date: 13/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Binadini shopping complex

Description:

Approved
&
Received By
A. Hossain
13/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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 Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

01 23
Conveyance Bill Date: 13/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Going to Binadini market.
 Description:

Nikunja office to BANARSI → 60f
 BANARSI to NIKUNJA office → 60f
 (By Bus & Rickshaw - 02 person)

Total → 120f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 13/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Lunch Bill

Date: 14/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Bank, Mohakhali

Description:

Lunch Bill → 300₳
 (02 person)

Total → 300₳

Approved
 &
 Received By

 14/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

33

Conveyance Bill

Date: 14/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Bank, Mohakhali & Post office, Banani

Description:

Nikunja office to Bank, Mohakhali → 50₹

(By Bus & Rickshaw)

Bank, Mohakhali to Nikunja office → 20₹

(By Bus & Rickshaw)

Total → 70₹

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
14/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

Date: 15/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Office Guest Entertainment

Description:

Entertainment → 500₳
(03 person)

Approved
&
Received By

15/02/16

Total → 500₳

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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01 Bill Date: 15/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman

Purpose: Purchasing office Miscellaneous Item

Description:

Correction pen	—————→	40₳
Thread	—————→	30₳
Electrical switch	—————→	120₳
Small scissor (02 pcs)	—————→	60₳
Small scale	—————→	20₳
	—————	
	Total →	270₳

Approved
 &
 Received By

 15/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

Date: 15/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Purchasing office miscellaneous item

Description:

Laptop	→	35,000₳
Mobile	→	8,000₳
Small Fan	→	800₳
Cooking instrument	→	500₳
Toilet Brush & Bucket	→	350₳
Office File	→	300₳
Napkin	→	50₳
Sandel	→	60₳
Floor cleaner	→	400₳
Iron	→	600₳
Diatry	→	150₳
Multipluck (02 pcs)	→	450₳
Basket	→	60₳
Staplers	→	120₳
Punching m/c	→	100₳
		Total → 46,940₳

15/02/16

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 BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime, human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

০১ ২৪

আনোয়ার হোসেন ডিফেন্স স্টাডি স্কুল

ডিফেন্স স্টাডি সেন্টার, ডিফেন্স স্টাডি সেন্টার, ইন্টারনেট, ফ্রান্স, ব্রিটিশ, জিডিপি, সেমেন্টারি, ফটোগ্রাফি, স্টেশনারী, কেলনা সফটওয়্যার। মোব নং-১০, কার্ড নং-২৩, বিক্রম-২, কিশোরগঞ্জ, ঢাকা-১২২৯।

নাম: **ANOWER HOSSAIN** তারিখ: **15/02/16**

ঠিকানা:

ক্রমিক নং	মানের বিবরণ	দর	পরিমাণ	টাকা
	Print + Scam	20	20	20
মোট টাকা =				20

টাকা (কথায়):

১০০০০
 15/02/16

স্বাক্ষরিত: *[Signature]*
 ডিফেন্স স্টাডি সেন্টার

স্বাক্ষরিত: *[Signature]*
 ডিফেন্স স্টাডি সেন্টার

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E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

CHALLAN & MONEY RECEIPT

(SRO No. 17-AIN/2004/423-MUSAQ Dated-10/06/2004) B. No. **18897** Sl. No. **984833**

Musak-11

Name of Firm : DHL Worldwide Express (Bangladesh) Private Ltd.
 Address : Moly Capita Centre (Level 4 & 5), 78, Bir Uttam Mir Showket Road, Gulshan-1, Dhaka-1212, Ph. 9895810, Fax : 8823248, 8817406
 VAT Reg. No. : 18141005168

Date: 15-02-16

Customer Name : Bangladesh Textile & Fashion
 Address : _____
 Customer's VAT Identification No. : _____
 Cash / Cheque No. : _____ Cheque Date : _____ Bank : _____

ACCOUNT NO.	INVOICE / HAWB NO.	INV/HAWB DT.	VALUE OF SERVICES	NET AMOUNT (TK.)	TOTAL AMOUNT (TK.)
<u>Dhaka</u>	<u>D 0 1 0 2 2 5 7 9</u>				<u>1990/-</u>
CUSTOMER COPY					
Amounts in word : <u>one thousand nine hundred and ninety taka only.</u>					<u>1990/-</u>
Other Deductions : _____					Net Receipt : _____
Customer's Signature : <u>[Signature]</u>					Seller's Signature & Date : <u>[Signature]</u>

Hot Lines: +88 0192 111 2222, +88 02 9881700, 9886305, 8835804, 1635916666
 Banani: 02-9822276 Uttara: 02-892 329 K.Bazar: 02-9153930 DOHS: 02-58813129 Agrabad: 001-2522271-4 Narayanganj: 021-8954514 Gulshan-2: 02-9825555 Kuril: 02-841818 Mirzapur: 02-8754511 Gajipur: 02-9264240
 Moulvibazar: 02-9533511 Dhanmondi: 02-55610895 Mirpur: 02-9022411 Rajshahi: 02-8817846 Narayanganj: 02-7450384 Sylhet: 021-711618 R.K. Mission Road: 02-9511258 Shamoli: 02-9124242
 Bogura: 8805157159 Kaulibazar: 88086164083 Tejgaon Aangri: 01929997026 Umra Aangri: 01929997022 Comilla: 01711-431324 Khulna: 041-724711 Country Office: 02-9698181 Tejgaon: 02-9698181 CPD: 021-740418

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill Date: 15/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Purchasing chemical

Description:

Fragrance finished chemical → 8000f

↑

↓

Total → 8000f

Approved & Received By

15/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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১১ম

আনোয়ার হোসেন ডিফেন্স স্টাডিজ ফাউন্ডেশন

ডিফেন্স স্টাডিজ সেন্টার, কলিকাতা বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়, ইন্টারন্যাশনাল সেন্টার, টেক্সটাইল, ডিফেন্স, লেগিসলেশন, সফটওয়্যার, স্টেশনারি, বেনারাম স্যাম্পল। রোড নং- ১০, কাজী নূরুজ্জামান সড়ক-২, মিলফোর্ড, ঢাকা-১২১১।

নামঃ anowar তারিখঃ 15/02/16

ঠিকানাঃ

ক্রমিক নং	স্বালের বিবরণ	নং	পরিমাণ	টাকা	
	print out	10		10	১০৳
					২০৳
					৩০৳
					15৳
					3০৳
					1০৳
					০০৳
					০০৳
মোট টাকা =				10+10	

টাকা (কথায়) Sagor Army

Approved & Received By
Arnob
 16/02/16

Total → 415৳

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc⁵ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD⁶ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD⁷ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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 Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

আনোয়ার কম্পিউটার গ্র্যান্ড স্টুডিও

কম্পিউটার সফটওয়্যার, কপিরাইট, ইন্টারনেট, ফ্রন্টএন্ড, ব্যাকএন্ড, ডিজিটাল, লেআউট, ফটোশপ, পেইন্টস, বেসলা সফটওয়্যার। মোবাইল নং-১০, কার্ড নং-২৩, লিফট-২, মিনফেজ, হাট-১২৯।

তারিখ - 15/02/16

নামঃ Anowar

ঠিকানাঃ

ক্রমিক নং	মাগের বিবরণ	দর	পরিমাণ	টাকা
	print out	10		10
				20₹
				30₹
				15₹
				30₹
				10₹
				20₹
				20₹
মোট টাকা =				10+10

টাকা (কথায়) Sagor Amr

Approved & Received By
 16/02/16

Total → 415₹

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Date: _____

আবু সাহাব সফটওয়্যার প্রাইভেট লিমিটেড

সফটওয়্যার সার্ভিস, কম্পিউটার কন্সাল্ট, ইন্টারনেট, ফ্যান্ডিং, ইন্ডিং, ডিজিটাল, মোবাইল, সফটওয়্যার, স্ট্রাকচার, স্ট্রাকচার, স্ট্রাকচার। মোবাইল: ১৬০২-১০, ফোন: ১৬০২-১০, বিল্ডিং-২, বিল্ডিং, ঢাকা-১২১৬।

নাম: **SAGOR** তারিখ: **16/02/16**

ঠিকানা: _____

ক্রমিক নং	মালের বিবরণ	দর	পরিমাণ	টাকা
	Photo Copy			→ 120f → 30f → 15f → 30f → 20f → 100f → 100f
মোট টাকা =				15
টাকা (কথায়) _____				
ক্রয়ের স্বাক্ষর				 বিক্রয়ের স্বাক্ষর

Total → 415

Approved
&
Received By

16/02/16

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com, s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 5 March 2026.

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 Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill Date: 16/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post : Chairman
 Purpose: Purchasing Trade License form & others
 Description :

Form price	→	120f
Tiffin	→	30f
Print	→	15f
Photocopy	→	30f
Mobile	→	20f
Office Entertainment	→	100f
Carrying chair	→	100f

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 16/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post : chairman
 Purpose : Going to Telephone office
 Description :

Lunch Bill → 150f

Approved
 &
 Received By
A. Hossain
 16/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill Date: 16/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
Post: chairman
Purpose: Going to Telephone office

Description:

Nikunja office to Telephone office	→ 30f
Telephone office to Nikunja office	→ 30f
Total → 60f	

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
16/02/16

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বিস্মিতপ্রাহির রাহমানির রাহিম
ক্যাশ মেমো ম্যানেজারঃ ০১৭৭১-৯৩০১১৩

বিক্রমপুর ফার্ণিচার
Bikrampur Furniture

এখানে সকল প্রকার ফার্ণিচার সামগ্রী পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
কারখানাঃ ৫০৭/৩.৫২, মরনারবাগ, হোসেন মার্কেট, উত্তর বাড়তা, ঢাকা-১২১২
শো-রুমঃ বোর্ড # ১৪, গুট # ১/সি, বিনহেত, নিকুল-২, (নৌদাগ কামাল টাওয়ার পার্শে), ঢাকা-১২২৯।
ফোনঃ- ০১৮১৮-৪১৩১৭৪, ০১৬৭৭-১৫১৪৮৫

নং 697

তারিখ ১৬/০৩/২০১৬

নাম শে. সাদিকুল হক ফ্রেতার মোবা
ঠিকানা বোর্ড # ১৫ বর্ড # ১২

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
১/	জর্জিয়ান স্টেইন চেয়ার	৪৮	৩০০০/-	৩০০০/-
				মোট- ৩০০০/-
				অগ্রিম-
				বাকী- ৩০০০/-

টাকা কথায়ঃ

নিজে নামাজ পড়ুন, অন্যকে নামাজ পড়তে উৎসাহিত করুন।

বিঃ দ্রঃ বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত নেওয়া হয় না

ফ্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

পাওয়ার হাউজ
POWER HOUSE
 for electric & kitchen needs

এখানে সকল প্রকার ফ্যান, চার্জার লাইট, খুঁসেব ঘুলাসহ ব্যবহারী ইলেকট্রিক সামগ্র্য ও পারিষ্ক নামহী বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 বাড়ী # ৬০, রোড # ১২, বিল্ডিং-২, ঢাকা-১২১৯।

ডাউচার

নাম: _____ তারিখ: ৩৬/১২/১৬

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	টাকা
৬৬	ই-ক্যাব্রি সার্ভিস স্বতন্ত্র-৩০	৬৬৬

মোট: ৬৬৬

ডাঃ আব্দুল হাদ্দর

স্বাক্ষর: *Abdullah*
 ব্যবস্থাপক

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KHAN WATCH & GIFT GALLERY Cash Memo

Shop No. 31 (Ground Floor)
 Rajuk Commercial Complex, Uttara, Dhaka.

KHAN ELECTRONICS
 All Kinds of Electronics TV, DVD & Speaker
 Shop No. 19, 20, 31, 32 (2nd Floor)
 Rajuk Commercial Complex, Uttara, Dhaka.
 Cell : 01758944488, 01819462909

KHAN GIFT CORNER-1
 All Kinds of Cosmetics & Emulation Jewellery
 Shop # 20, 21, Rajuk Commercial Complex
 (G.F.), Uttara, Dhaka-1230.
 ☎ 02-8962346, 01819462909

Memo No. 2387

Date: 18 / 02 / 2016

Name: _____
 Address: _____

Qty.	Description	Model No.	Rate	Amount
①	Parra servie, Battary, 3.1.13.	T8880 8880 AA	1250₹ / 30₹	1250₹ 30₹
			Total Tk.	1280₹

● NO RETURN ● NO EXCHANGE ● NO GUARANTEE

Customer's Signature

For: KHAN WATCH/KHAN GIFT CORNER/KHAN ELECTRONICS

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Bill

Date: 18/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Trade License

Description:

Trade license fees → 9000₳

Filling cost → 6000₳

Approved
 &
 Received By
 Anowar
 18/02/16

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Lunch Bill & Tiffin

Date: 18/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Trade License

Description:

Lunch Bill —————→ 300₳
(02 person)

Tiffin —————→ 60₳
(02 person)

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
18/02/16

Total → 360₳

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Conveyance Bill

Date: 18/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
Post: Chairman
Purpose: Trade License
Description:

Nikunja office to Ulbarga → 30f
 (By Bus & Rickshaw
 02 person)

Ulbarga to Nikunja office → 30f

Approved
 &
 Received By
Abdus
 18/02/16

↑
 Total → 60f

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বিল অফিস - ৭৬৩৩৫৩৭

আনন্দ রেস্তোরাঁ

৪ শহীদ সোহরাওয়ার্দী রোড, নারায়নগঞ্জ।

নং 493 তারিখ ০৭.০২.২৬

নাম :

ক্রমিক নং	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
	মিষ্ণু -	২	২২০	২৪০
	ফোর হাঙ্গারী	৭	৬০	৬০
			মোট	২৭০

পক্ষে - আনন্দ রেস্তোরাঁ

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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Conveyance Bill Date: 19/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Natogyangong

Description:

Nikunja office to Natogyangong →	165₹
(By Bus & Rickshaw - 02 person)	
Natogyangong to Nikunja office →	310₹
(02-person & goods carrying cost)	
Road Tax →	20₹
Total →	495₹

Approved & Received By

[Signature]

19/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

Date: 19/02/16

Name: M^r. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Catering Goods

Description:

LABOUR COST → 320/-

Approved

Received By

TII - 1

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill Date: 19/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: office entertainment
 Description:

office guest entertainment → 140/-

Approved
 Received By

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

Date: 19/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Font: chaitman

Purpose: Mobile Bill

Description:

Mobile - Gsp → 320₳

Approved
&
Received By
Asif
19/02/16

Total → 320₳

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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 Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Lunch Bill

Date: 22-02-16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Going to Narayanganj
 Description:

Lunch Bill - 02 person → 300f

Approved
 &
 Received By
 Anowar
 22/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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01

Conveyance Bill

Date: 22-02-16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose : Going to Natayangong

Description :

Nikunja office to Noyamati —————→ 160₹
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)
 02 person

Noyamati to Nikunja office —————→ 510₹
 (Goods carrying)

22/02/16

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

01 24

Bill

Date : 22/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
Post : chairman
Purpose : Telephone connection
Description :

Telephone connection → 5900f
&
Filling cost for officers

Approved
&
Received By
[Signature]
22/02/16

Total → 5900f

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 23/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: office miscellaneous

Description:

Soap → 30f

Fitzbox → 20f

Lock & Lock ring → 96f

Locket pin → 5f

Water Bottle → 30f
(02 pcs)

Total → 181f

Approved

&

Received By

A. I.

23/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Lunch Bill

Date : 29/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post : Chairman
 Purpose : Going to BTCL office
 Description :

Lunch Bill → 150₹

Approved
 &
 RECEIVED BY
 Aash

Total → 150₹

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

202

Conveyance Bill

Date : 23/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to City corporation

Description:

Nikunja office to Ulbarga → 25₹

(By Bus & Rickshaw)

Ulbarga to Nikunja office → 25₹

Approved
&
Received By
Anowar
23/02/16

Total → 50₹

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

Date: 23/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman
 Purpose: Office Guest Entertainment.

Description:

Office Guest (02 person)

Entertainment cost → 300₹

Approved
 &
 Received By

 23/02/16

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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 23/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman
 Purpose: office labour cost
 Description:

Approved &
 Received By
 Anowar
 23/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Mobile Bill

Date: 26/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Mobile Bill

Description:

Office communication → 1000f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 26/02/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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ZAFRAN Restaurant
 House # 04, Road # 01, Nikunja-2, Dhaka-1229
 Mobile: 01683 191819

T No.- **2640** Date: **27/02/16**

No	Item Name	Quantity	Price
১	কুটি / পত্রটা		
২	সিলপনা / সমুদ্র / কাটকোট		
৩	জাজি / ডাল / ডাল-জাজি		
৪	চিকেন সুপ / সিল কলিঙ্গা		
৫	চিকেন মানগ্রাম / আল ফ্রাই / সোপেয়াজে / ডুনা / রোস্ট / আল মুব্বী		
৬	গরু- নেহরী / কালা ডুনা / ডুনা / ছাপ		60
৭	খামি- কলিঙ্গা / পায় / ডুনা / খামির ডাল / গুপি		
৮	ভর্তা / ভাজি / ফটকি ভর্তা / ওটকি ডুনা / সাউ পিউডি / কাফুরী		
৯	বিচড়ী চিকেন / বিফ / মটিন/ হালিস		
১০	চিকেন বিরিয়ানী / কাফি বিরিয়ানী / খাদা ভাত (কাটাই)		
১১	নই / ইলিশ / কে / বাহিলা / শৈল / মেংড়া মাছ		
১২	বোয়াল / পাবনা / চিংড়ি / বাইস / রুপচানা মাছ		
১৩	নান / পরেসি (প্রেইন / বাটার) / গরলিক নান		
১৪	মোপনাই / স্পেশাল মোপনাই / কিমা মোপনাই		
১৫	চিকেন ভন্দুরী / চিকেন টিফ (দেশী/ব্রয়লার) / চিকেন বটি		
১৬	বিফ শিক কাবার / মটিন বটি কাবার		
১৭	ব্রীল চিকেন- ফুল / হাফ / কোমটার / চিকেন শর্মা		
১৮	লাজি / ফালুদা / বোপহালী / পুজিং / নই / কিম্বি		
১৯	চা / কফি / মফট ড্রিঙ্কস / মিনারেল ওয়াটার / ফিল্টার ওয়াটার		
২০	অন্যান্য		
২১		মোট	

২৭/০২/১৬

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Office Salary

Date: 27/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Monthly Salary

Description:

Salary of February: 16 → 50,000₹

Total → 50,000₹

Approved

&

Received By

[Signature]

27/02/16

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date : 28/02/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Labour cost

Description :

Label joining & Box entry of product → 1000f

Total → 1000f

Approved &

Received By

Signature

28/02/16

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Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

Date: 28/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: company registration

Description:

Name clearance certificate → 1500₳

legal consultant → 500₳

Total → 2000₳

Approved
&

Received By

[Signature]

28/02/16

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01723 Bill Date: 29/02/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
Post: chairman
Purpose: Office Entertainment
Description:

Lunch Bill → 490f
(03 person)

Tiffin → 60f

Total → 550f

Approved & Received By
Anowar
29/02/16

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House rent

Date: 29/02/2016

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: House rent & related others

Description:

House rent (including all Bills) → 12,000f

Approved

&

Received By

Abub

29/02/16

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

01 23

Date: 31/03/26

Bill

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Expenditure of March

Description:

Office Salary	→	56452₹
Conveyance	→	1158₹
Office Entertainment	→	9525₹
Newspaper	→	300₹
Internet Bill	→	500₹
Mobile Bill	→	500₹
Dica & Rental Set	→	840₹
House rent	→	12000₹
Bus	→	4200₹
Freightance charges	→	8500₹
Postal Sending	→	2640₹
TIN ID	→	1500₹
Miscellaneous	→	22920₹
		Total → 111845₹

Approved by
 [Signature]
 31/03/26

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Bill

০৫/০৪/১৬

Md. Jahid Hossain

post Assistant merchandiser

Description

মঞ্জিল মার্চেন্ট হেল্পার
 মার্চেন্ট হেল্পার
 ৬৪৬২ ঢাকা

Approved By

 ০৫/০৪/১৬

Recd By

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²³ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

1/03/16

লক্ষ লক্ষ বিল -
 Lunch
 ২-৬৩ —
 ২-কবলাবাড়ী →
 ৩-ডাল →

30F
 40F
 10F
 মোট 80F

Approved by

[Signature]
 1/03/16

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স্বাক্ষরিত

তারিখ

02-03-16

২১০৭ ২০ -	260
২৫০০০ ১০ -	30
৩১০৫ ১০ -	10
	<hr/>
	300

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মা হার্ডওয়ার ইলেকট্রিক এ্যান্ড স্যানিটারি

কাশ বেহা

এখানে হার্ডওয়ার, ইলেকট্রিক এবং স্যানিটারি মাল-মাল, জি. আই. পাইপ, পি.ভি. সি পাইপ, ফিটিংস, কমেড, বেসিং সুলভ মূল্যে নিজেরা করা হয়।
 বাড়ী নং-৩৪, রোড নং-২, নিকুল-২, ঢাকা-১২২৯

মোবাইল :
 ০১৭১৪-৩৭১৯২২
 ০১৭৩৬-৭৬৪৩৮৪
 ০১৭৩০-৯২২৩২৪

নং:	8212	তারিখ:	02/06/23
নাম:			
ঠিকানা:			
ক্রঃ নং	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর
১	TNT বক্স - ৪০	৪০	৪০
২	TNT বক্স - ৩০	৩০	৩০
৩			৭০
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১৬			
১৭	ধন্যবাদ আবার আসবেন।		

বিঃ দ্রঃ বিক্রিত মাল কেবলমাত্র সপ্তমাহ হয় না।
 নিজের নামাঙ্ক পড়ুন, অন্যরকম নামাঙ্ক পড়তে উৎসাহিত করান।

বেতার স্বাক্ষর-

তারিখ: 02/06/23

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ঢাকা স্পাইস হোটেল এন্ড রেস্টুরেন্ট Dhaka Spice Hotel And Restaurant

কবি ফারুক স্মরণী, নিকুল-০২, খিলক্ষেত (রাজউক মার্কেট সংলগ্ন), ঢাকা-১২২৯
মোবাইল : ০১৬৮২ ৩০৫৩৮৮, ০১৮২২-৮০৭৬৩৩

নং- 2957 টেবিল নং..... তারিখ : ৪/৩/১৬

নাম :

বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
G. Chicken	2	80	160
P. nam	2	20	40
Warten	1	-	15
			205
		মোট	
		অস্বীকৃত	
		বাকী	

টাকা (কথায়) :

স্বাক্ষর-

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill Date: 05/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: mobile recharge

Description:

Flexi load → 500f

|

Total → 500f

Approved & Received By

A.H.
05/03/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

Date: 05/03/26

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Miscellaneous

Description:

Rubbers	—————→	20₳
Label printing	—————→	30₳
Pen - 03 pens	—————→	30₳
Pen (signature - 06 pens)	—————→	30₳
	—————	Total → 110₳

Approved
&

Received By

A. Hossain
05/03/26

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

Date : 05/03/26

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post : Chairman
 Purpose : Marketing conveyance
 Description :

Nikunja office to Barundhara → 20f
 Barundhara to Nikunja office → 20f
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)
 Nikunja office to Tongi → 20f
 Tongi to Nikunja office → 20f
 (By Bus & Rickshaw)

↑
 Total → 80f

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 05/03/26

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Lunch Bill

Date : 06/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post : chairman

Purpose : Lunch Bill for marketing

Description :

Lunch Bill → 4500₹
(March - 150/day)

Approved

&

Received By

AS

06/03/16

Total → 4500₹

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Bill

Date : 06/03/26

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post : chairman
 Purpose : office cleaning & cooking
 Description :

Approved
 &
 Received By

 06/03/26

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 BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime, human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

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Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Bill

Date: 06/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman
 Purpose: office Entertainment

Description:

Coffee	_____	300f
Milk	_____	220f
Biscuit	_____	200f
Fruit	_____	450f
Water Bottle	_____ →	30f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 06/03/16

↓
 Total → 1200f

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 06/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: office Entertainment

Description:

office Guest fooding → 300f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 06/03/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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পাওয়ার হাউজ
POWER HOUSE
 for electrical & kitchen needs
 এখানে সকল ধরনের ফ্যান, চার্জার লাইট, পায়লের চুলপাত ধাবাইয়া ইলেকট্রিক মালামাল ও প্রাচীর সামগ্রী বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 নাজি # ৫৩, রোড # ১২, বিল্ডিং-২, সলো-১২২৯।

ডাউটার

তারিখ: ১৭/০৩/২৬

নাম: ড. আনোয়ার হোসেন

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	টাকা
৯	নাসির চামের কাপ ৬ কিলো	২৫০/-

Signature

মোট: ২৫০/-

ধন্যবাদ আবার অস্বীকার।

Signature

ক্রয়ের স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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বিস্মিত্যাহির রাহমানির রাহিম

মায়ের দোয়া ভ্যারাইটিস স্টোর

এখানে চাউল, মুদি, ষ্টেশনারী প্রভৃতি যে কোন অনুষ্ঠানের মাধ্যমে
অর্ডার নেওয়া হয় এবং পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়

(মোঃ মোঃ মনোয়ার খান (মালিক))

১২নং রাস্তার মাথায়, মাতাঝর মার্কেট, নিকুল-২, বিলক্ষেত্র, ঢাকা।
মোবাইল: ০১৭১২-০৭১৩০১, ০১৯২৯-৬০৯০৪৮

সূত্র: _____ তারিখ: ১/৬/২৬

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	টাকা
	৬১ ২৮	৭০
		৭০
	মোট	
	অগ্রীম	
	বাকী	

স্বাক্ষর

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com, s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 5 March 2026.

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Advance IT Technologies Limited

1389

Thanks with: ait: Anwar

The Sum of Taka _____ TK 500/-

Month of March-16 Installation Charge _____

DATE: 09 03 2016
D D M M Y Y Y Y

Monir
Authorized Signature

Internet Section Software Section Domain Registration Web Hosting Training Section

Nikunja Office Uttara Office

#Kash : 01925773191

* প্রতিস্থাপন ব্যক্তি অপেক্ষা যোগ্য
 * প্রতি মাসে ১ তারিখের মধ্যে ১ মাসের বিল পরিশোধ করতে হবে।
 * সেবা টি বন্ধ করতে হবে অবশ্যই ১ (এক) মাস পূর্বে জানাতে হবে

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1

Bill

Date: 09/03/16

Md: Jahid Hossain

post: Assistant-Merchandiser

Purpose: marketing conveyance

Description:

Nikunja office to Chok Bazar → 30F

New marketing Nikunja office → 30F

┌
 ──┬──
 Total → 60F

Approved By

 10/03/16

Received By

 10-03-16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill Date: 13/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Going to Kercanigong, Kercanigong
 Description:

Nikunja office to Kercanigong → 140f
 (02 person)
 Kercanigong to Nikunja office → 150f

Approved & Received By
 [Signature]
 13/03/16

Total → 290f

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01

বিল

ad put
13-03-16

Md: জাহিদ হাভান

পোস্ট: এডমিন সারজুন ডায়াল

প্রাপ্ত : খিলঘেও থেকে আনুলী → ২০৮

বাস্তা থেকে মৌচাক → ০৬

মৌচাক থেকে খিলঘেও → ২০
মোটাল ৩২৮

→ প্রাপ্তি করে

Approved By

K-03-16

Received By

14-03-16

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Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD¹ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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বিল তারিখ-14-08-16

মো: জাহিদ হাজার
 প্রোফে এচিভমেন্ট স্মারচেং জাহিদ হাজার

অপেক্ষ: ছিলকোথ থেকে মনুনাপার্ক → ১০F
 গুলশান থেকে বাজার বিবিজি → ১০F
 বাজার থেকে বনশ্রী → ১০F
 বনশ্রী থেকে ছিলকোথ → ১০F
 লেটান ১০

Approved By

 15/08/16

Received By

 15-08-16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 15/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman

Purpose: Office Entertainment

Description:

Coffee	_____	300₳
Milk	_____	220₳
Fruit	_____	100₳
Biscuit	_____	100₳

|

 Total → 720₳

Approved
 &
 Received By

 15/03/16

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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 15/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Parcel Sending

Description:

Parcel to Jordia —————> 2000f

Parcel to Narayanganj —————> 80f

Parcel to Sadarqhat —————> 80f

2160f

Approved
 &
 Received By
 Anowar
 15/03/16

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PLACE OF BOOKING	DATE OF DELIVERY	NATURE OF GOODS	PCS	WT	CONSIGNMENT DECLARED VALUE	PLACE OF BOOKING	PLACE OF DELIVERY
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	15/03/16						
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

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TO Chairman, BGMEA University of Fashion & Textiles Ullaha, Dhaka						ACKNOWLEDGEMENT RECEIVED THE ABOVE MENTIONED CONSIGNMENT IN PERFECT AND GOOD CONDITION FROM SUNDARBAN COURIER SERVICE (PVT.) LTD. DELIVERED BY: _____ RECEIVED BY: SCS DATE: 15/08/16 8952941 (BRANCH)	
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Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
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International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

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Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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 মোবাইল : ০১৭২১-১৫২৯৯৯, ০১৬৭৬-৯০১০৮৮

নং: _____ তারিখ: _____
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ক্রমা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	মূল্য	টাকা
১	MAX - (MAX)	২	২০০০	৪০০০

কম্বার: _____

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বিল

তারিখ-15-03-16

মো: জাহিদ হাছান

গোষ্ঠে এচিভমেন্ট বারচুন্ন আইজার

প্রদেয়: গ্রিলস্কোথ থেকে আমদানী → ২০ F

বাজা থেকে সৌচক → ২০ F

সৌচক থেকে গ্রিলস্কোথ → ২০ F

টোটাল ৪০ F

Approved By

 16/03/16

Received By

 15-03-16

বিল

তারিখ 16-03-16

মো: জাহিদ হাছান

গোষ্ঠে এচিভমেন্ট বারচুন্ন আইজার

প্রদেয়: গ্রিলস্কোথ থেকে বরাদ্দ → ১০

জুল কার থেকে ফার্মগেট → ১০

ফার্মগেট থেকে গ্রিলস্কোথ → ২০

টোটাল ৪০

Approved By

 17-03-16

Received By

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19-03-16

কো: জাহিদ হাজার
 পোস্ট: প্রতিষ্ঠান হার চৌ চাইলার
 প্রাপ্য: অিলঙ্কোথ থেকে বসনী → ২৫৮
 বসনী থেকে কচুঙ্কোথ → ১০৮
 মিরপুর থেকে অিলঙ্কোথ → ২০৮
 মোট ৫০৮

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 19/03/16

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 19-03-16

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 Continental Courier Services Ltd.
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 Phone: 9390
 Tel: 7 9390 2 & 7 9390 8
 Fax: 7 9390 7 154228

From: ২২০০
 To: ১১

Consignee:
 Shipper:
 Date: ২২/৩/১৬

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 ৬৩৬-৬
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill Date: 21/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chartered Engineer
 Purpose: Purchasing chemical
 Description:

Fragrance chemical → 9500₹

Approved & Received By
 [Signature]
 21/03/16

বিল - ২১-০৩-১৬

কো: জাহিদুজ্জামান
 পোষ্ট: এন্টিবায়োটিক সার্ভিস ডাইরেক্টর

প্রাপ্য: ঝিলকোথ থেকে সোয়াখালি → ২০₹

সোয়াখালি থেকে অদর নাট → ২০₹

মোট → ৪০₹

খেসা ওরা → ৬০

জিনামিরা থেকে পারকোমুবি (Ricketia) → ৬০

কাঙ্ক্ষী গাজ থেকে জিনামিরা → ২০

অদর নাট থেকে ঝিলকোথ → মোট ১৪০

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 21/03/16

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 21-03-16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill Date: 21/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman
 Purpose: TIN Identification Number for Business Account

Description:

TIN (Personal) for Bank Account in Rupali Bank → 1500f

Approved & Received By
 A.H.
 21/03/16

Total → 1500f

Bill Date: 22/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman
 Purpose: office draw

Description:

4 Set draw for 02 person → 10.000f

Approved & Received By
 A.H.
 22/03/16

10.000f

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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PLACE OF BOOKING: 22/03/16 DATE: 22/03/16	PLACE OF DELIVERY: 22/03/16 DATE: 22/03/16	CONSIGNMENT DECLARED VALUE: ৳ ১০০০০ PLACE OF BOOKING: ৳ ১০০০০ PLACE OF DELIVERY: ৳ ১০০০০	RECEIVED BY: ৳ ১০০০০ DATE: ৳ ১০০০০
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বিল ২২-০৩-১৬

স্রো: জাহিদ রাজার

স্বাক্ষরে এচিফেটমস্টার হুজুর জাহেদ

প্রাপ্য: মিলছোত থেকে বানমসি → ৬০F

বানমসি থেকে মিরপুর ১০ → ২০F

মিরপুর ১০ থেকে মিলছোত → ৬০

মোট ১৪০

APPROVED BY **[Signature]** ২২/০৩/১৬

RECEIVED BY **[Signature]** ২৩-০৩-১৬

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বিল ২৩/০৩/১৬

কো: জাহিদ হোসেন
 পদবী: এচিএনআরএমএনজিএস.
 প্রার্থ্য: বিলকোত থেকে বানপুত্রা → ৫০ F.
 বাজা থেকে বিলকোত → ১০ F.
 মোট ৭০

APPROVED BY

 ২৩/০৩/১৬

RECEIVED BY

 ২৪/০৩/১৬

bill Date 24/03/16

Mr: Jahid Hossain
 post Assistant Merchandiser
 Purpose: বিলকোত থেকে বানপুত্রা → ২০ F
 বাজা থেকে বিলকোত → ১০ F
 মোট ৩০

APPROVED BY

 24/03/16

RECEIVED BY

 27/03/16

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ক্যাশ মেমো

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এখানে ব্যবহার্য হোসিয়ারী, পামেন্টস, ডল সুয়েটার, তোয়ালে
 কমাল, ব্রেসিয়ার ও পেরি পাইকারী বিক্রয়।

১৬৪, চক বাজার, ঢাকা-১২১১

নং- 165 তারিখ ২৭/৬/০৫

নাম

ঠিকানা

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	সাইজ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
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মোট

টাকার কথায়

বিশেষ নোট- বিক্রিত মাল ফেরৎ লওয়া হয় না।

ক্রয়কার স্বাক্ষর- বিক্রয়কার স্বাক্ষর-

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Bill

27/08/16

Md. Jahid Hossain

past Assitan Merchanduser

Description

খিলকোম্ব থেকে অকবায়ার →
 কৌচাক থেকে খিলকোম্ব ←

১৫ F
 20
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 35

Approved By

A.H.
 27/08/16

Received By

 27/08/16

Bill

27/08/16

Md. Jahid Hossain

past Assitan Merchanduser

Description

খিলকোম্ব থেকে অকবায়ার →
 কৌচাক থেকে খিলকোম্ব ←

১৫ F
 20
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 35

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Received By

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bill 29/03/16

Md: Jahid Hossain

Description

স্টেজারকি → ২০ F

আব ২০

Approved By

[Signature]
29/03/16

Received By

[Signature]
29/03/16

bill 29/03/16

Md: Jahid Hossain

past Assistan merchandiser

Description

মিনটেক্স থেকে কাহাবান → ২০ F

কাহাবান থেকে মজিবিল → ২ F

মজিবিল থেকে ডায়নোট → ২০ F

মজিবিল থেকে মিনটেক্স → ২০

আব ৪০

Approved By

[Signature]
29/03/16

Received By

[Signature]
29/03/16

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Bill Date: 30/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: Chairman
 Purpose: Office Entertainment
 Description:

Lunch Bill → 450f
 Total → 450f

Approved By
 A.H.
 30/03/16

Md. Jahid Hossain 30/03/16
 post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

ডিলক্কাত থেকে মিরপুর ২০ →	30F
মিরপুর থেকে ফার্মকোলে →	১৬F
ফার্মকোলে থেকে মিরপুর ২ →	20F
মিরপুর থেকে ডিলক্কাত →	30F
	১৬F

Approved By
 A.H.
 30/03/16

Receive By
 J.H.
 30/03/16

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill Date: 31/03/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman
 Purpose: Salary
 Description:
 Salary of March-16 ————— 50,000f

Approved
&
Received By
A. Hossain
31/03/16

Total → 50,000f

Bill Date: 31/03/16

Name: Md. Jahid Hossain
 Post: Assistant Merchandiser
 Purpose: office salary
 Description:
 Salary of March ————— 8000f

Approved
&
Received By
A. Hossain
31/03/16

Total → 8000f

Received By
A. Hossain
31/03/16

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

Date: 31/03/26

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Fee show room rental dealing.

Description:

Paying to market office → 2000f

Approved .
 &
 Received By
 A
 31/03/26

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Office Expenditure, April - 2016

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
Post: chairman

Purpose: Expenditure of April

Description:

- Office Salary → 60.000f
- Outlet Advance → 50.000f
- Outlet Goodn → 53230f
- Conveyance → 1894f
- Office Entertainment → 5280f
- Newspapers → 310f
- Internet Bill → 500f
- Mobile Bill → 2000f
- House rent → 12000f
- Miscellaneous → 2305f
- Banquet → 650f
- Stamp → 330f
- Show room Decoration → 20095f
- Total → 208594f

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01/04/16

Md. Jahid Hossain

Post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

নাজাবিল _____

(Office Entertainment)

Approved By

Ans

01/04/16

₹90F

মোট 490F

02/04/16

০১৭১২১১৪৯৪

* কাজের মত প্রমাণ

কাজের মত _____

৬৫০F

৬৫০F

০১৭১৫০০

০১/৪/১৬

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

02/04/16

Mr Zahid Hossain
 Post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

খিলছকাত থেকে মিরপুর ২ →
 মিরপুর থেকে কার্বন সেন্ট →
 বাঙ্গাবুবা থেকে খিলছকাত →

30 F
 15 F

15 F
 মোট 60 F

Approved By

 02/04/16

Received By

 02/03/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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ক্যাশ মেমো

রেনেসাঁ স্টেশনারী এন্ড লাইব্রেরী

এখানে স্কুল, কলেজ ও অফিসিয়াল স্টেশনারী, কম্পিউটার সামগ্রী, বই-পাতা, কলম ও পেনসিল খুচরা ও পাইকারী মূল্যে বিক্রয় ও অর্ডার সরবরাহ করা হয় এবং ফটোকপি, স্পাইরাল/বুক বান্ডিং, লেমিনেটিং ও প্রিন্ট করা হয়।
রাজউক ট্রেড সেন্টার, দোকান নং-১১বি/সি (নীচতলা, পশ্চিম গেইট সংলগ্ন), নিকুঞ্জ-২, হিঙ্গাজত, ঢাকা-১২২৯

নং 1304

মোবাইল : ০১৯১২-২২৬০৫০

তারিখ ০৬/০৪/২০১৬

নাম			
ঠিকানা			
বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
১৩০৪	৬	২২০	১৩২০/-
		মোট-	১৩২০/-

টাকা কথায় :

ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

কেন্দ্রীয়ভাবে শীতাতপ নিয়ন্ত্রিত।

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

04/04/16

MD. Zahid Hossain

Post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

শ্রমিকদের থেকে আদায়কৃত → 10 F

আদায়কৃত থেকে শ্রমিকদের → 10 F

মোট 20 F

Approved by

[Signature]
04/04/16

Received by

[Signature]
05/04/16

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Bill

~~05/04/16~~
05/04/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

past chairman

Descriptive

- খিলক্ষেত থেকে বহুবাজার →
- বহুবাজার থেকে খিলক্ষেত →
- খিলক্ষেত থেকে মনবাজার →
- মোহাম্মদিয়া থেকে খিলক্ষেত →

৬০ F
২৭০ F
৩০ F
১০ F

মোট ৩৬০ F

Approved by

06/04/16

Received by

06/04/16

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বিস্মিল্লাহির রাহমানির রাহিম

বাবলী ও মায়ের দোয়া ও আল্লার দান

BABLI & MAYER DOYA & ALLARDAN

এখানে হেংগার, বডি, সূতা ইত্যাদি পাওয়া যায়।

মহানগর কমপ্লেক্স, ২য় তলা
দোকান নং-১০৮/১১০/১১২
ফুলবাড়ীয়া, শাহবাগ, ঢাকা-১০০০।

বঙ্গবাজার কমপ্লেক্স ব্যবসায়ী সমিতি
দোকান নং-২৯৭/২৯৮, নীচ তলা
ফুলবাড়ীয়া, শাহবাগ, ঢাকা-১০০০।

কাশ মেসো

☎ 04475-985756
☎ 04475-985754
☎ 04475-985988
☎ 01799-597860
☎ 01857-751469
☎ 01679-100862

নং	2214	প্রোগ্রাম মোঃ বাবুল	তারিখ	০৫/০৪/২০
নাম	রাউফুল হক সৈয়দ			
ঠিকানা	সিমান এডভ. হা/খা			

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
১	৩০ গাউন এক্সপোজ	৫৪০	১৫	৮১০০
২	৩০ গাউন এক্সপোজ	৬৬০	৬	৩৯৬০
৩	৩০ গাউন এক্সপোজ	২৭০	৬২	১৬৭৪
৪	এক্সপোজ/নাইলন/সি/টা/১-২০	২০	৩১০	৬২০
৫	২০ গাউন এক্সপোজ	২০	২৫০	৫০০
৬	২০ গাউন এক্সপোজ	২০	২৫০	৫০০
৭	২০ গাউন এক্সপোজ	২০	২৫০	৫০০
৮				২৫৪০
৯				৬০
১০				২৬০০
১১				
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১৬				
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১৮				
১৯				
২০			মোট-	১৬৪৬০

তোমাদের মধ্যে শ্রেষ্ঠ, যে কোরআন নিজে শিখা করে এবং অপরকে শিখা দেয়।

ক্রোতার স্বাক্ষর- বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর-

সততা ব্যবসার মূলধন
বিঃদ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ফেরৎ পাওয়া হয় না।

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বিস্মিত্বাহির রাহমানির রাহিম

জিহাদ ইঞ্জিনিয়ারিং ওয়ার্কস

এখানে সর্বপ্রকার আলমারী, দরজা, জানালা, খীল
 কলাপসেবল গেইট, রোলিং সার্টার ইত্যাদি তৈরী ও
 এস.এস.এর কাজ সরবরাহ করা হয়।

৭১১, টঙ্গী ডাইজারশন রোড, মগবাজার রেলগেট, ঢাকা-১২১৭
 মোবাইল : ০১৭১৬-৮০১৭৩৮, ০১৯৪৭-১৬৬৮৭১

সূত্র

তারিখ : ০৫-০৪-২০১৫

ড্রইং নং : ০৭-০৪-২০১৫ বিক্রমে

* S.S 3/4 কাছির ইন্ডাস্ট্রি ইন্সট্রামেন্টে = ২৫০০ টাকা
 কাজ = ২০০০ টাকা
 মোট বিক্রয় ৬-০০ টাকা প্রতি

Signature
 ০৫-০৪-২০১৫

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

06/04/16
06/04/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

past chairman

Description

শিল্পক্ষেত্র থেকে অদ্বৈতগোষ্ঠী → ৫০ F

অদ্বৈতগোষ্ঠী থেকে শিল্পক্ষেত্র → ১০ F

ব্যয় বিতরণ → ১০ F

৫০ F
১০ F
১০ F

৭০ F

306

Approved By

06/04/16

Receb By

06/04/16

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০১৮৬৭৮২০৩৯৯

ক্যাশ মেমো

রোমান এন্টারপ্রাইজ

নং 634 এখানে স্কাবার টায়ার (সিল), সাইনবোর্ড ও ব্যালারশহ ব্যবসায় পিচিং কাজ করা হয়।
 টাংগাইল প্রাঙ্গণ, মোকাম নং-২১, ঝিলক্ষেত্র, ঢাকা-১২২৯।

তারিখ ৯/৪/১৫ তেলি ডা. ১৬/৪/১৫

নাম	পরিমাণ	বিবরণ	দর	টাকা
সাইন বোর্ড/ব্যানার	১	৪২x১৫	৩০০	৩০০
ডিজিটাল প্রিন্ট				
ডিজিটিং কার্ড				
ক্যাশ মেমো/স্বাক্ষর				
পত্রিকায় বিজ্ঞাপন				
			মোট	৩০০
			অগ্রীম	২০০
			বাকী	১০০

৯/৪/১৫

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

08/04/16

Name Md. Anowar Hossain

past chairman

Description.

শ্রিলঙ্কেশ থেকে আসলনা →

30 F

আসলনা থেকে শ্রিলঙ্কেশ →

30 F

60 F

স্বাক্ষর

Approved By & Received By

[Signature]
08/04/16

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01 2022 ফোনঃ ০১৯১৩ ৫৭২৫০৬

মায়ের দোয়া ইঞ্জিনিয়ারিং ওয়ার্কস
MAER DOYA ENGINEERING WORKS

শ্রেষ্ঠ মোঃ যাকারুল হোসেন

এখানে বাংলাদেশের গাম্বী, গোহাং শরণ, জানসা, কল্যাণসিক গেট, সাজির গেট, সীল আলমারী টাচ এর যন্ত্র, চেয়ার টেবিল সহ সীলের ব্যবহারী মালিককে তৈরী ও সরবরাহ করা হয়।
 মোড-০১, নাকী-০/১ নং, নিতুজ-০২, বিলকেত, টানগাড়া, ঢাকা-১২২৩।

Bill No. 163 তারিখ : ০১ - ০৪ - ২০২২

নাম :
 ঠিকানা :

ক্র. নং	বিবরণ	মুদ্রিত	দর	টাকা
০১	হে. ডায়াল ও পি.সি	-	-	৩২০/-
				৩২০/-

মোট ৩২০/-
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 Nikunja Office Uttara Office

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 Authorized Signature

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 * প্রতি মাসের ৫ তারিখের মধ্যে বিঃ শর্তসাপেক্ষে করতে হবে।
 * কোনোটি বদল করতে হলে অবশ্যই ১ (এক) মাস পূর্বে জানাতে হবে।

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01

শ্রীমতী সুলতানা হাছিনা

দশম শ্রেণী

হাসান পেপার হাউজ

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ঠিকানা: *Hasp-66*

বেস-২০০০-২০০১

২০০১

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এই বাড়ি থেকে অসহায় ছাত্রেরা স্কলারশিপ, স্টাডেন্ট লো, টেক্সটাইল, সিলিং, ইত্যাদি পরিষেবা পাবে।

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

BEST EXCHANGE
 100% Export Quality Knit & Woven Fabric Suppliers.
 Grewall City, Nolljani, Chowrasia, Joydebpur, Gazipur.
 Cell No. : +88-01737221855, +88-01916425737

Bill No: **120** **BILL** Date: **11.04.16**

Name of Factory: **BD Fashion Ltd**
 Address: **Kulikhat, Dhaka**

Sl. No.	Description	Challan No.	Quantity	Rate	Taka
(*)	Polo-shirt		27 PES	120	= 3240/-
(*)	P-shirt		36 PES	40	= 1440/-
					= 4680/-
	Polo shirt (Amber)		21 PES		4300
					8780/-

Taka (in words)

FOR : **BEST EXCHANGE**

Store In-Charge Received by Accountant Authorised by

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

11/04/16

Md. Zahid Hossain

post Assistant merchandiser

Description		
খিলছোত থেকে জালনা →		30 F
জালনার থেকে খিলছোত →		60 F
গাজীপুরা থেকে জালনা →		20 F
৳ বিক্রা →	৳	10 F
		<u>120</u>

Approved By

 11/04/16

Receb By

 11/04/16

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বিস্মিত্বাহির রাহমানির রাহীম

জম জম পেপার হাউজ এন্ড স্টেশনারী **কাশ মেমো**

JOM JOM PAPER HOUSE & STATIONARY

প্রোগ মোঃ ওমর ফারুক

এখানে সকল প্রকার কাগজ, খাতা, কলম, ফটোকপি পেপার, অফসেট পেপার ক্যালকুলেটরসহ অফিসিয়াল যাবতীয় মালামাল পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।

মোবাঃ ০২-৯৮১৪৬৮৫, ০১৭৬২-৬৩১৬১৭, ০১৭৯৫-২৩৫৫২২

সবুজ মাৰ্কেট, ঢাকা বাজার, গাজীপুর মহানগর।

নং	2776				তারিখ	২৯/০৪/২৬
নাম						
ঠিকানা						
সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা		
	১০০/খাতা	২৪		২৬৪/-		
কথারঃ				মোট ২৬৪/-		
কেন্দ্র স্বাক্ষর				নামাজ বেহেস্তের চাবি		

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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আনোয়ার হোসাইন গ্যারামেন্ট প্রাইভেট লিমিটেড
 কম্পিউটার সার্ভিসিং, কম্পিউটার কন্সাল্টিং, ই-টার্গেট, ফ্যান্ডিং, ব্লুটুথ, ডিজিটাল, স্টেমিং, ফটোকপি, ক্রেপমাস্টারী, কেমো সার্ভিস। হোত নং-১০, কার্টা নং-২৩, কিল্লিং-২, কিল্লিংকত, ঢাকা-১২২৯।

তারিখ: ২ 1 2016

নাম: ANOWAR HOSSAIN

ঠিকানা:

ক্রমিক নং	মালের বিবরণ	দর	পরিমাণ	টাকা
	Ted	60	1	

মোট টাকা = 60

টাকা (কথায়):

রিসেপ্টিভ সাক্ষর: *[Signature]* বিক্রয়কার সাক্ষর: *[Signature]*

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

1111

B211

12/04/16

Md. Zahid Hossain
 post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

খিলছোত থেকে বনানী → ০৫F
 বনানী থেকে খিলছোত ← ০৫F
 (মি 10)

APPROVED BY
 [Signature]
 12/04/16

Receb By
 [Signature]
 12/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

13/04/16

Md Zahid Hossain

Post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

ড্রিলড্রাক্স থেকে উটজোম লোড	→	20 F
উটজোম থেকে ঢাকা জর্জিন	→	25 F
		25 F
৳ বিক্রয়	→	20 F
হাউজ বিল্ডিং থেকে ড্রালপাড়া	→	20 F
৳ বিক্রয়	→	20 F
হাউজ বিল্ডিং থেকে ড্রিলড্রাক্স	→	20 F
৳ বিক্রয়	→	10
		<u>140</u>

10 140
 20 F
 10
 140
 20
 120

Approved by

 13/04/16

Received by

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

14/04/16
13/04/16

Md. Zahid Hossain

Post: Assistant Merchandiser

Description -

বিক্রয়ভাড়া	→	60 F 150 F
দোকানের চাঁদ	→	70 F
কারেন্ট	→	<u> </u>
		Total = 280 F

Approved By
A.H
13/04/16

Receb by

13/04/16

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Bik

13/04/16

Md. Zahid Hossain

Post Assistant Merchandiser

Description:

১৯/২৫ ————— ৮১০
 ৩৫/৬ ———— ৮১০

APPROVED BY

[Signature]
 10/04/16

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

14/04/16

Md. Jahid Hossain

Post: Assistant Merchandiser

Description

বিক্রয় কাজ →

দেওয়ানি কাজ →

মুদ্রা বিক্রয় →

20 F

50 F

10 F

সর্বমোট 80 F

Received By

14/04/16

Approved By

14/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

ক্যাশ মেমো

মেসার্স মাসুদ ইলেকট্রিক এন্ড হার্ডওয়্যার

যাবতীয় ইলেকট্রিক, হার্ডওয়্যার দ্রব্যাদি পাইকারী ও খুচরা
বিক্রয় এবং সরবরাহকারী।

শ্রীঃ আব্দুল আহাদ

দোকান নং-২১, বেইজমেন্ট, রাজউক ট্রেড সেন্টার,
নিকুঞ্জ-২, খিলক্ষেত, ঢাকা। মোবাইল : ০১১৯৯-৭৯০৯৯১

ক্রমিক নং- ৬৬১

তারিখঃ ০৭/০৪/২২

নাম :

ঠিকানাঃ

পরিমাণ	বিবরণ	দর	টাকা
	গুলা - AMBR ৬০ম	২৬০০	২৬০০
	ফলা - ৬০ম		২৬০০
		মোট=	৫২০০/-

বিঃ দ্রঃ বিক্রিত মাল কেন্দ্র বা বদলানো হয় না।

ক্ষেত্রার স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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Research office of Dr. Anwar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Phone : 9676679
 Mobile : 01677-188819
 : 01817-660795

Gasli Memo

ঢাকা স্টেশনারী
Dhaka Stationery
 90, New Super Market (Uttor) D-Block
 Ground Floor, Dhaka-1205.

No. **4052** Date: **০৬/৪/২১**

Name :

Address :

Qty	Description	Rate	Taka
০১ পিস	২১০x২১০ (বাড)	০৬০/-	০৬০/-
০২ "	জাকিয়ার	২০/-	২০/-
০২ "	ইলেক্ট্রিক জাকিয়ার	০৬০/-	০৬০/-
Total-			২০০/-

Goods once delivered will not be taken back.

(Signature)
 Signature

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Bill

Date: 17/04/26

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Show room decoration & related

Description:

Show room coloring	→	2200f
Electrical wiring	→	1200f
Hangers attaching	→	1200f
Electrical wire purchasing	→	1500f
Conveyance	→	50f
		<hr/>
		Total → 6150f

323

Approved

&

Received By

[Signature]

17/04/26

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bell

17/04/16

Md. Jahid Hossain

past Assistant Merchandiser

Description

খিলকাত থেকে বেলগোটে	→	10 F
		50 F
বিলগোটে থেকে খিলকাত	→	10 F
By বিক্রা	→	২০ F

APPROVED BY

 17/04/16

Received BY

 17/04/16

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“স্বিস্টারিয়ারি মাংসারি মাংসি”

পাওয়ার হাউজ
POWER HOUSE
 for electric & kitchen needs

এখানে সবল প্রকার বসান, ডাওয়ার লাইট, প্যানেল চলাসহ খাবারি ইলেকট্রিক মালামাল ও প্রারিক মাংসী কিনা করা হ।
 নারী # ৫০, প্রোজ # ১২, বিকুল-২, ঢাকা-১২২১।

ডাউচার

নাম : শ্রীঃ আনওয়ার হোসাইন তারিখ : ১৪/০৪/১৬

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	টাকা
*	ইলেক্ট্রিক ২০৬৩৫০০ বাতি	৩৬০০/=
*	ফ্রিজ কো কোড ৩	১৫০/=
*	বুথের মাংস	২২০/=
*	চুল	২৫০/=
*	শুট	২৬০/=
*	RFL টুন্স	২৪০/=
*	কম্পিউটার	৬০/=
	মোট	৪৩০০/=

ধন্যবাদ আবারি অধিকারি

ক্রয়ের স্বাক্ষর

(Signature)
 বিক্রয়ের স্বাক্ষর

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"সিলিকনবাহী বায়োটেকনিক্স"

পাওয়ার হাউজ

POWER HOUSE

for electrical & kitchen needs

এখানে সকল প্রকার হ্যান্ড, চার্জার লাইট, প্যাসেজ ফ্লাসক, বাতরী, ইলেকট্রিক মেশিনারি ও গ্রাফিক সামগ্রী বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 নাক্স # ৫০, রোড # ১২, নিউল-২, ঢাকা-১২২৯।

ভাউচার

নাম : তারিখ : ২৪/৪/২০২৬

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	টাকা
৫	হোটেল এনালজি ৪৫৫৮ ২৭	৫০০/=
<p>paid</p> <p>২৪/৪/২০২৬</p>		
		মোট- ৫০০/=

কেন্দ্রের আর্থার আলজেকব।

কেন্দ্রের স্বাক্ষর

২৪/৪
 কেন্দ্রের স্বাক্ষর

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 for electric & kitchen needs

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ফোন # ০২-৯৬০৮০০
 মোব # ০১৭১২-৯৬০৮০০

ভাউচার

নাম : তারিখ : ২৮/৪/২০

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	টাকা
*	সেটিনা এনার্জি ২০৫৫৫৪	২,৪০০/-
ওবজারভেশন paid ২৮/৪/২০		
		মোট- ২,৪০০/-

ধন্যবাদ আবার আশ্রয়দ :

ক্রমিক সংখ্যা

স্বাক্ষর
 বিক্রয়কার সংস্থা

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Bell

18-04-16

Md. Jahid Hossain

Post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

জাহিদ হোসেন

By বিজ্ঞা

Approved By

AS
18/04/16

30 F
10 F

সর্ব 40

Received by

18/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

ক্যাশ মেমো

বিউটি রেস্টোরা

সকল প্রকার খাবার এর অর্ডার নেওয়া হয়।

১নং নীলক্ষেত সিটি কর্পোরেশন মার্কেট, ঢাকা-১২০৫

মোবাইল: ০১৭৬৪-৬৯৪৭২১, ০১৮১৬-১৭৮৮৯১

০১৭২০-০০৭৭৯১, ০১৭২৩-৭৭৯৯১৩

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তারিখ: ২০ ০৭ ১৬

নাম: পদ. আনওয়ার হোসাইন
ঠিকানা:

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
	Lunch-02 pieces			১৫০৳
	ধন্যবাদ আবার আসবেন		মোট	১৫০৳

২০/০৭/১৬
ক্রমিক নং

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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শফিকঃ ০১৯১৭-২১২৯২২
 : ০১৬৭১-৭১৪৩৪৪
 রফিকঃ ০১৯৪১-৪৯০৬৪৮

আর, এস, পয়েন্ট
 শ্রোঃ মোঃ শফিকুল ইসলাম/রফিকুল ইসলাম
 সকল প্রকার পেঞ্জী প্রস্তুতকারক ও পাইকারী বিক্রেতা।

দোকান নং-ই-এস-২৯,৩০, মহানগর কমপ্লেক্স, ফনিব্র রোড, ফুলবাড়ীয়া, শাহাবাগ, ঢাকা-১০০০

পূর্ব গোপাল নগর, বক্তাবলী, ফতুল্লা, নারায়ণগঞ্জ।

নং- **3044** তারিখ **20/08/23**

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সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
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ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর **যে আলাহু কে পেল, সে সব পেল।** পক্ষেঃ আর, এস, পয়েন্ট

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বিস্মিত্যাহির রাহমানির রাহিম মোবাইলঃ ০১৭৩৬-৮৫০৭৯১
ঃ ০১৬৮৮-৯৪২৭০৪

ক্যাশ মেমো

কাওছার গার্মেন্টস KAWSER GARMENTS

খোঃ- মোঃ মিজানুর রহমান

অত্যাধুনিক ডিজাইনের গোল্ডি, শার্ট, গার্মেন্টস সামগ্রী পাইকারী বিক্রেতা।
মহানগর কমপ্লেক্স, দোকান নং-E-X-৩, ফুলবাড়ীয়া, শাহবাগ, ঢাকা-১০০০

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তারিখ

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ঠিকানা

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পিছ	দর	টাকা
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বিঃ দ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ফেরৎ নেওয়া হবে না।

ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

সততাই ব্যবসার মূলধন

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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হা অর চাহবানির দারিন মোবার ০১৭৫০-০৯৭১২০
 কাশ মেনে ০১৩৭৯-৮৮৭২১৪

সোহেল গার্মেন্টস
Shohel Garments

ক্রোর মোটর সিঙ্গার

৩০০০টির উত্তরে গারমেন্টস, ১০০০টির, ৫০০টির ব্যবসায়িক মেশিন সেবা কুমার গার্মেন্টস গার্মেন্টস।
 সোহেল গার্মেন্টস, মতলব অরোরা, মুগাচা গার্মেন্টস, (কুশি) হেড ওপেনসোর্সের গার্মেন্টস গার্মেন্টস।
 শুল্কগার্মেন্টস, কলকাতা, ভারত-১০০০১।

নং: 1123 তারিখ: ০১/০৩/২০২৩

নাম: সোহেল গার্মেন্টস

ঠিকানা:

ক্রমিক	স্বাক্ষর বিবরণ	আইডি	বিদ	মত	টাকার
১	সোহেল গার্মেন্টস	১০০০	১০০	১০০	১০০০
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শি প্রা- লিখিত স্বাক্ষর করণ করণ।
 মিলে স্বাক্ষর করণ, মিলে স্বাক্ষর করণ।

সোহেল গার্মেন্টস

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ব্যাণ্ড বোম্বা মোবাইল : ০৯৯১১৯৯৯৯৯
০৯৯১১-৯৯৯৯৯৯

আমিন এন্টারপ্রাইজ
AMIN ENTERPRISE
অধুনিক কলিন্দার সেবায় বুদ্ধিগত ব্রী-সিঙ্গ পাইকারী ও খুচরো বিক্রয় করা হয়।
৫৯০, বি-৯৯, চিশতিকা মার্কেট, গাজিপুর সদর। ফোন: ৯৯৯৯৯৯৯৯৯

নং: 170 তারিখ: ২০১৪/১৫

নাম: ২০০০১০(গদা) (বিজিএসএ) এন্ট্রা প্রাইভেট লিমিটেড

ক্র.সং	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
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কি.সং: বিলিয়ন মান, অক্ষর (অক্ষর) স্ব.সং. বিলিয়নের স্ব.সং.

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বিউটি প্যান্ট হাউজ
BEAUTY PANT HOUSE

কম্পিউটার প্রোগ্রামিং সফটওয়্যার

পা. 439

ক্র.সং.	কাস্টমারের নাম	পরিমাণ	মূল্য	টাকার
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কাল মেসো

০১৯৭১-১১১১১
 ০১৯৭৭-৯৯ ৬৬ ১১

মেসার্স নাঙ্গলকোট ট্রেডার্স M/S. NANGALKOT TRADERS

এখানে দেখী বিবরণী বা পেন্টি ও ড্র ইউজ পেটেন্টের আনুশঙ্গিকরক পাইকারী ও খুচর বিক্রয়
 ৩৯৩/বি-২, পাউছিয়া বাজার মার্কেট (২য় অলা, ঢাকা-১২০৫)

২২৫

তারিখ: ২০/০৪/১৬

নং: _____
 নাম: শ্রীমতী সত্যজিৎ দেবী
 ঠিকানা: নিবন্ধিত - কিস্তি ট্রেডার্স

ক্রমিক	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	মূল্য	টোল
০১	<u>১৫ বস্ত্রের কাপড়</u>	<u>১৫</u>	<u>২০০০</u>	<u>২০০০</u>
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			মোট	<u>২০০০</u>

বিঃদ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল্য সেরাং লওয়া হবে না।

ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc⁵ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD⁶ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD⁷ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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 Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

পারভেজ কালেকশন

পারভেজ কালেকশন
Parvaj Collection

এখানে সকল প্রকার
দেশী-বিদেশী শার্ট
পাইকারী বিক্রয় করা হয়।

৯৭৭ নং বঙ্গবাজার কমপ্লেক্স
(২য় তলা) ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০

Parvaj : 01718 152983
Liton : 01918 106695

নং- **2594** তারিখ **২০/৪/২০২৪**

নাম **বাংলাবন্দু**

ঠিকানা **৬ শিষ্টা**

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	দর	টাকা
১	শুক্রা A	৫	৪০০	২০০০
২				
৩	কো A	৫	৪০০	২০০০
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			মোট টাকা	

বৈচিত্র্যময় ক্রিশিলা পোশাকের এক অনন্য প্রতিষ্ঠান।

পাঁচ ওয়াক নামাক আদায় করুন।

বাহারী সব পথে চলিতা স্ট্রিক্টা করুন করে, তাহান শোনার বিত্ত বন্ধু। অঙ্গ-হাসিল

পক্ষে- পারভেজ কালেকশন

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

বিশ্বমিলাহির রাহমানির রাহিম
 কাশ মেমো Mobile : 01724-911667
 01718-326321

জহুরুল গার্মেন্টস
 Johurul Garments

প্রোগ মোঃ ফরহাদ খান

এখানে প্যান্ট, কোর্ট, জ্যাকেট পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 ৭৪৩-৪৪, ১৮৬৭ বঙ্গবাজার কমপ্লেক্স ব্যবসায়ী শো-রুম ৪ ৯৫০ বঙ্গবাজার কমপ্লেক্স
 সমিতি, ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০। (মহানগরী ২য় তলা) ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০।

নং- ৫২৬

নাম বাফলা (দেউ) (ডেইজি) তারিখ ২০/০৪/২৬

ঠিকানা বাফলা - বিক্রয় - গুলি/১০০০

নং	বিবরণ	শিট	মর	টাকা
১	বঙ্গ শিট বোনা	৪৪	২৪০০	২০২০৫
২				
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৪	স্ট্রাকচার	৪৪	৬৪০	৬০৪০
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নিজে নামাজ পড়ুন অপরকে নামাজের জন্য ডাকুন।

ক্রমিক নং স্বাক্ষর বিক্রমিক নং স্বাক্ষর

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com, s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 5 March 2026.

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১৫১. ০১/২৭৫৪৬০১
০১৭৪৭০১২৭০

ফাহিম ফ্যাশন
Fahim Fashion

এখানে উন্নত মানের দেশী-শ্রী পিছ পাইকারী বিক্রয়ের নির্ভরযোগ্য প্রতিষ্ঠান।
facebook.com/fahimfashion.com

৩৯৩/বি-৯০, নিউ চিশতিয়া মার্কেট, নীচ তলা (গাউছিয়া সংলগ্ন), ঢাকা-১২০৫।

নং ৭৬৫ তারিখ ২০ ০৪ ১৬

নাম বই নামের টেক্সটাইল এন্ড ম্যাটেরিয়াল

ঠিকানা ফাহিম ফ্যাশন

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	পিছ	দর	টাকা
১	জামা	০২	১০০০	২০০০
২	সামান্টা	০৬	১১০০	৬৬০০
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মোট

বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত লওয়া হয় না।

ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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ক্যাশ মেমো

দিপা ওড়না হাউজ
DEPA ORNA HOUSE

এখানে দেশী-বিদেশী ওড়না, কার্প এবং পাল্প পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রেতার একমাত্র নির্ভরযোগ্য প্রতিষ্ঠান
 ৩৯৩/বি-১০০, নিউ চিশতিয়া মার্কেট (নীচতলা), গাইছিরা সংলগ্ন, ঢাকা-১২০৫
 ফোনঃ ৯৬৭০৩৮৩, মোবাইলঃ ০১৭১৫-৯৫৫১১৩, ০১৮১৭-০৬১৮৫১

নং: 1565 তারিখ: ২০/৪/২১

নাম: *DR. ANOWAR HOSSAIN*

ঠিকানা:

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	পিস	দর	টাকা
০১	<i>ফ্যান শিট</i>	০৬	২০০	১২০০
০২	<i>সাদা ওড়না</i>	০৬	২৮০	১৬৮০
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বিঃ দ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ক্ষেত্রত লওয়া হয় না।

ক্রয়কার: *DR. ANOWAR HOSSAIN* | বিক্রয়কার: *DEPA ORNA HOUSE*

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মোবাঃ ০১৯২৬-২১৩২৫৫
০১৭৩৪-০৪০৭০২

ক্যাশ মেমো

MB **মা বাবার দোয়া গার্মেন্টস্**
DG **MAA BABAR DOA GARMENTS**

প্রোঃ মোঃ আমজাদ হোসেন

এখানে আধুনিক ডিজাইনের গেল্জি প্রস্তুতকারক এবং পাইকারী বিক্রেতা।
দোকান নং-এ-১/২, মহানগর কমপ্লেক্স, ফুলবাড়িয়া, শাহাবাগ, ঢাকা-১০০০

নং- **7230** (যে কোন তিজাইনের গেল্জি অর্ডার নেওয়া হয়) তারিখ **২০ ৪ ১৬**

নাম _____

ঠিকানা _____

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পিস	দর	টাকা
১		১২	১০০	৬৫০
২	বুজেন্টা T-shirt			
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মোট-

সততাই ব্যবসার মূলধন
বিঃ দ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত লওয়া হয় না।
ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর "নিজে নামাজ পড়ুন এবং অপরকে পড়তে উৎসাহিত করুন" বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia) & Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

ক্যাশ মেমো

নিউ

3 **থ্রী-স্টার গার্মেন্টস**
New Three Star Garments

প্রোগ্রাম : কাজী মোঃ আরিফ

আরিফ : ০১৭১২-২১৩৬১৪
 আরমিন : ০১৮১১-৫২৪৫৫৪
 : ০১৬১১-০০০৭৭৪

এখানে আধুনিক শর্ট প্যান্ট ও বাচ্চাদের গেঞ্জী সেট পাইকারী বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 দোকান নং-এ-৭৮/৭৯, মহানগর কমপ্লেক্স, (১০ ফুট গলি),
 ফুলবাড়ীয়া, শাহাবাগ, ঢাকা-১০০০।

নং- **1639** তারিখ **২০/০৭/২০২০**

নাম _____
 ঠিকানা _____

সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	সাইজ	পিছ	দর	টাকা
১	৪৫ নং প্যান্ট	২৪	২৭	২০২০	
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মোট- _____

পরিচালনায় : কাজী মোঃ আরমিন

ক্রমতার স্বাক্ষর "আল্লাহ ব্যবসাকে করেছে হালাল, সুদ করেছে হারাম" বিক্রমতার স্বাক্ষর

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill 20/04/16

Mr. Jahid Hossain
 post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

খিল থেকে কার্ড প্রিন্ট	→	80F
কার্ড প্রিন্ট থেকে ডিলিভারি	→	24F
ডিলিভারি থেকে খিল প্রিন্ট	→	90F
৳ বিক্রয়	→	10F
		<hr/>
		204F

APPROVED BY
 [Signature]
 20/04/16

Received by
 [Signature]
 20/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

21-04-16

Md. Jahid Hossain
 past Assistant Merchandiser

Description

ছান ছাড়া	→	250F
বিশ্রা ছাড়া	→	60F
আলাবিল	→	50F
		<u>360F</u>
	বাকী	15
		375F

Approved By

 21/04/16

Received By

 21-04-16

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"কিন্তু কিভাবেই তাই হোক"

পাওয়ার হাউজ

POWER HOUSE

for electric & kitchen needs

গরমের সকল প্রকার ফ্যান, চার্জার লাইট, শ্যামের চুল সহ আরও
ইলেকট্রিক হাঙ্গারস ও প্রাচীর সামগ্রী বিক্রয় করা হয়।
বাড়ি # ৫০, রোড # ১২, নিকুল-২, ঢাকা-১২২৯।

ভাউচার

নাম : _____ তারিখ : ২২/৪/২০২৫

সংখ্যা	বিবরণ	টাকা
	১০০০ কন্ডেক্স লাইট ২	১৪০
মোট-		১৪০

হেতুবাদ আবার আসবে।

ক্রয়কার স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/>

Bill

২২-০৪-১৬

Md. ANOWAR HOSSAIN

po chairman

Description

ফটোকপি কমিটী টি	→ 60F
নাজাবিল	ছাটে 60F
	150
	ছাটে 210F

Approved By

 ২২/০৪/১৬

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²³ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Bill 25-04-16

Md. Jahid Hossain
 past Assistant Merchandiser
 Description

প্রিলক্ষিত থেকে আডভান্সপূর → 05F
 10F
 আডভান্সপূর থেকে প্রিলক্ষিত → 15
 মাঠ
 Received By
 25/04-16

Approved By
 AS
 25/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Bill

২৬-০৪-১৬

Md. Jahid Hossain

post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

শিল্পকর্ম সরেছে আকস্মিক → 05 F

আকস্মিক সরেছে শিল্পকর্ম → 05 F

(৩১৬) 10 F

Approved By

 26/04/16

Received By

 26-04-16

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Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

26-04-16

Md. Jahid Hossain

Post Assistant Merchandiser

Description

খিলছোত থেকে সৌচক	→	15 F
সৌচক ২২২২ ফর্মুলেট	→	10 F
ফর্মুলেট ২২২২ খিলছোত	→	15 F
	সর্বমোট	40 F

Approved By

 26/04/16

Received By

 26-04-16

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Bill

27-04-16

Purpose: Price Tag
 Description:

সবচেয়ে কম দাম

→ 50 F
 মোট 50 F

Approved By

 27/04/16

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Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264

Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Bill

27-04-16

MR Jahid Hossain

post ASSISTANT Merchandiser

Description

অিলঙ্কোত হইল বহুবাডার → 50 F

বহুবাডার হইল অিলঙ্কোত → 50 F

অিলঙ্কোত হইল আজমপুর → 05

আজমপুর থেকে অিলঙ্কোত → 10

By বিক্রা

Approved By

27/04/16

Received By

(Signature)

27-04-16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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BBF ৬৭২ ৬০৬ ৩১৪ ৩০০৬ Mob: 01710-306095
 01942-367984

BHAI BHAI FASHION

সবকিছরের এক্সপোর্ট বেলগারানিটি টি-শার্ট, নামেরটিস পোষাক পরিবর্তী ও ফুটুরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
 মোবাইল- ৯৪৮৬, বন্দবাজার কমপ্লেক্সে ব্যবসায়ী সঙ্গিতি, ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০।

শো-রুম # ০২, যাবৎসে আরেকট পাতা। (প্রের পছন্দ প্রাপ্তে), লেবন নং- ০৪, নীলগা, ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০।

বিল/ দানার
 তারিখ: ২১/০৪/২৬

নং: 1954

নাম:
 ঠিকানা:

নং	বিবরণ	পরিমাণ	মূল্য	টাক
০৭	কাপড়	৫৫)	০৩৫	৫৫০
				৫৫০

মোট

কাস্টমার- সত্যতা ব্যবসায়ী মূলধন কর্তৃপক্ষ-

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com, s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au); 5 March 2026.

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Mob :01772-314915
: 01918-880718
মথার ফ্যাশন
MATHER FASHION

শ্রোঃ মোঃ রুবেল

এখানে সকল প্রকার প্যান্ট পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।
দোকান নং-১৪৪০, বঙ্গবাজার কমপ্লেক্স, ব্যবসায়ী সমিতি
ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০।

নং	916	তারিখ	১৭	০৫	১৬
নাম					
ঠিকানা					
সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পিছ	দর	টাকা	
১	শ্রোঃ মোঃ রুবেল	৬৫	২০০	১২৫০	
২				১২৫০	
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১৪					
১৫					
১৬		মোট-	১২৫০		

ক্রোকতার স্বাক্ষর

বিঃ দ্রঃ- বিক্রিত মাল ফেরত লওয়া হয় না

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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OG

উসমান গার্মেন্টস OSMAN Garments

৬১৪, বঙ্গবাজার কমপ্লেক্স ব্যবসায়ী
 সমিতি ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০

নং- 28

স্বাক্ষরিত হইবে ৩০ শ্রমিকদের দ্বারা স্বাক্ষর।

শ্রীঃ মোঃ হাবিব : 01839471739
 01848-346055

নাম

ঠিকানা

তারিখ: ২৭/৪/২০১৬

ক্রমিক নং	মালের বিবরণ	পিছ	দর	টাকা
১	শ্রী	৬	২৫০	১৫০
২				
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৪				
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৬				৩৫০
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১৬				
মোট				
জমা				
বাকী				

দাওয়াতের মেহনত করা উম্মতে মোহাম্মদির কাজ।

স্বাক্ষর

স্বাক্ষর

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আল-মদিনা ফ্যাশন
Al-Madina Fashion

Mob : 01711-821483
: 01672-414882

প্রোগ্রাম - মোঃ সামশের আলী

এখানে সর্বপ্রকার এক্সপোর্টের প্যান্ট, ট্রাউজার ইত্যাদি পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয় করা হয়।

দোকান নং-১৪৬৪-৬৫, বঙ্গবাজার কমপ্লেক্স ব্যবসায়ী সমিতি
ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০।

নং-	663	তারিখ	২৭	০৪	২০২৫
নাম					
ঠিকানা					
সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পিছ	দর	টাকা	
১	বড় জিন্স	৫৭৭৫	২৫৫	১৪৫৫	
২				১৪৫৫	
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১৬		মোট-			

"নিজে নামাজ পড়ুন অপরকে নামাজ পড়তে বলুন।"

ক্রয়কার স্বাক্ষর

বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর

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বিস্মিতশাহিন রাহমানির রাহিম
ক্যাশ মেমো Mob. S : 01716-041394
 Z : 01712-964749

 সিয়াম গার্মেন্টস
Syam Garments
মোঃ শাহিন

এখানে সকল প্রকার এক্সপোর্ট কোয়ালিটি গার্মেন্টস পোষাক পাইকারী ও খুচরা বিক্রয়তা।
 ১৬১৮, বঙ্গবাজার কমপ্লেক্স বাবসায়েী সমিতি 1618, Bango bazar Complex Babshai Somili
 (২য় তলা গুলিস্তান) ফুলবাড়ীয়া, ঢাকা-১০০০। (1st Floor, Gulistan) Fulbaria, Dhaka-1000.

নং-	980	তারিখ	29.8.26	
নাম	হাফিজুল ইসলাম চৌধুরী			
ঠিকানা	ফার্মন ২ নিকুঞ্জ ২ নং			
সংখ্যা	মালের বিবরণ	পিছ	দর	টাকা
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২				
৩	D জোরে গার্মেন্টস ১৪৮/৩০/৮৪০/৮			
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বিক্রয় বিক্রিত মাল ফেরৎ লওয়া হয় না।
 ক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর _____ বিক্রেতার স্বাক্ষর _____

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Research office of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

শিরমিন গার্মেন্টস Mob : 01714-394282
SHIRMIN GARMENTS 01927-765853
 01726-270675

Pro. Md. Shahin

All Kinds Of Jacket, Over Cot, Trauzar Jogging Set Wholesaler & Retailer.
 1679, Bangobazar Complex (1st Floor)

No **735** Gulisthan Market, Fulbaria, Dhaka-1000. Date **২৭/০৭/২১**

Name _____

Address _____

Sl No	Description	Pice	Rate	Amount
1	১১২৬	২/৩	৪০১-	৬৫০/-
2				
3				
4				
5				
6				
7				
8				
9				
10				
11				
12				
13				
14				
15				
16			Total-	

N.B : Goods Once Sold Cannot Be Taken Back

Receivir's Signature

For: Shirmin Garments

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

28/04/26

Name: Md. Jahid Hossain

Post: Asst. Merchandiser

Purpose: Salary

Description:

357

Approved By

[Signature]
28/04/26

Received By

[Signature]
21-05-16
Md. Jahid Hossain

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²³ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Date: 28/04/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman
 Purpose: office cleaning
 Description:

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 28/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Date: 28/04/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Mobile Bill

Description:

Mobile Bill → 2000₳

Approved
 &
 Received By

 28/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²³ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Bill

28-04-16

Purpose: priettag

Description

Approved By

AJ
 28/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Date : 30/04/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Lunch Bill

Description :

Lunch Bill of April → 4500f

Approved By
&

Received By

[Signature]
30/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc⁵ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD⁶ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD⁷ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post : Chairman
 Purpose : Salary
 Description :

Date: 30/04/16

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 30/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Bill

Date: 30/04/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman:

Purpose: Outlet Advance

Description:

Outlet Advance —————→ 50,000₹

Approved
&

Received By

[Signature]

30/04/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Office Expenditure . May-2016

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman

Purpose: Expenditure of May-16

Description :

- Office Salary —————→ 52000₹
- Office rent —————→ 10,000₹
- Conveyance —————→ 1000₹
- Office Entertainment —→ 200₹
- Newspaper —————→ 310₹
- Internet Bill —————→ 500₹
- Mobile Bill —————→ 1000₹
- Miscellaneous —————→ 4310₹

Total → 69320₹

Approved
 &
 Received By

 31/05/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Date: 03/05/16

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: office Entertainment

Description:

office fooding with buying

house merchandising

→ 200₳

Approved
 &
 Received By

 03/05/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Date: 04/05/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman
 Purpose: Hanger joining
 Description:

Hanger joining charge → 250f

Approved
 &
 Received By
 Anowar
 04/05/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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05/05/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Office cleaning

Description:

Office cleaning of May → 2000f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 05/05/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²³ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech in Textile Technology (CU, India), BSc in Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh)

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Name : Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post : chairman
 Purpose : Salary of May
 Description :

05/05/16

Approved
 &
 Received By
 [Signature]
 05/05/16

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

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Conveyance Bill 5/05/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to marketing

Description:

Office to Barundhata	—————>	20₺
Barundhata to office	—————>	20₺
		Total → 40₺

Approved
&
Received By

[Signature]
05/05/16

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AIT
Advance IT Technologies Limited
 6234

Nikunja Office: House -1/A, Road -12, 2nd Floor, Nikunja -2, Dhaka-1229, Ph: 01983300970 Cell: 01619090000, 01190090000
Uttara Office: R-14/B, H-1, 3rd floor, Sector-4, Uttara, Dhaka

DATE: 08 05 2016
 D D M M Y Y Y Y

Thanks with Dr. Anowar

The Sum of Taka _____ TK 500/-

Month of May-16 Installation Charge _____

Internet Section Software Section Domain Registration Web Hosting Training Section

Nikunja Office Uttara Office

Monir
 Authorized Signature

* প্রতিস্থাপন চার্জ অপেক্ষা বঞ্চিত
 * প্রতি মাসের ৫ তারিখের মধ্যে এ' মাসের বিল পরিশোধ করতে হবে
 * সেবা টি বন্ধ করতে হলে অবশ্যই ১ (এক) মাস পূর্ব জানাতে হবে।

bKash : 01925773191

HOTEL ABAKASH (Residential) VR.NO _____
 654, O.R. Nizam Road, Chittagong. Date 13/5/16
 Tel: 633960, 28563120
 DEBIT/CREDIT ACCOUNT _____

particulars	Taka	Ps
Received, Nine hundred = 900/-	900	
at 12th May/2016		
Room Rents only.	1	
One days only.		
TOTAL = 900/-	900	
Taka v Nine hundred only.		

Receiver's Signature _____ Manager/Proprietor 13/5/16 Cashier _____

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Bill

Date: 15/05/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Mobile Bill

Description:

Mobile Bill → 1000₳

Approved
&
Received By
Anowar
15/05/16

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Bill

15/05/26

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain
 Post: chairman
 Purpose: Miscellaneous expenditure
 Description:

Mobila Bill	→	3000f
Milk	→	450f
Cofee	→	350f
Office Guest entertainment	→	550f
Gift to shop owner (By providing Brra)	→	230f
		Total → 2580f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 15/05/26

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Bill

Date: 16/05/26

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: Going to Chittagong for marketing

Description:

Fooding → 2000f
 (Wednesday evening to Friday evening)

Conveyance (Rickshaw) → 250f

|
 Total → 2250f

Approved
 &
 Received By

 16/05/26

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Name : MR
Coach : [108-BRTC]
Departure Time : 01:15 PM
Seat Fare : TK. 480.00
Seats : [C1]
From : Chittagong
Boarding : Dampara Bus Point
Issued On : 13 May 2016

PNR : 57357A77E3F02
Journey Date : 13 May 2016
Reporting Time : 12:55 PM
Total Fare : TK. 480.00 x 2 = 960/-
To : Dhaka
Dropping :
Issued By : Mr. Nasir

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Serial # 18741 | Printed By: Mr. Nasir (operator)

আপনার হ্যান্ড লাগেজ অবশ্যই নিজ দায়িত্বে রাখবেন

অভিযোগ/পরামর্শ : ০১৮-৬৯-৮০২৭৪০ চট্টগ্রাম, ০১৮৬৯-৮০২৭২৭ ঢাকা

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Bill

Date: 29/05/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: Chairman

Purpose: office entertainment

Description:

Entertainment for office Guest - 03 person → 180₳

Approved & Received By

 29/05/16

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Bill

Date: 27/05/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: Going to Tangail for marketing

Description:

Journey by bus & Rickshaw → 250₳

Fooding (Lunch) → 100₳

Approved
 &
 Received By
 Anowar
 27/05/16

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Bill

Date : 31/05/16

Name: Md. Anowar Hossain

Post: chairman

Purpose: showroom cleaning

Description:

cleaning showroom by market cleaners → 50

377

Approved
&

Received By

31/05/16

Total → 50

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Bill

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Description:

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Page | 280

4 Legal authorization and signing

379

5 March 2026

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The author has contribution in conceptualization, visualization, resource, self-supervision, funding acquisition, project administration, research communications, research commercialization, planning and prediction, analysis, writing the original draft, manuscript editing, and publication process. The scholarship or funder has no scholarly role of the design of research, research idea or visualization, research and innovation, drafting of manuscript, editing of manuscript, and publication of manuscript.

380

6 Declaration of conflicting interests

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8 Data availability

All data generated during the coalescing of this article are included, attached and briefly cited in reference list.

9 Professional excellency of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, engr.anowar@yahoo.com <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>

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Page | 282

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Invitation of legal client for legal service to individual and/or organization.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13073.70249>
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Invitation of researchers in textile engineering in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.

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385

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International Professor and consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, Higher Education, PhD, & Postdoc)

BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; BPhil, MPhil, DPhil/PhD & Postdoc in applied law and criminology; research & publication; vice-chancellor, chancellor, and research director of university, quality in higher education; R & D in dyeing & process (textile & color engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials, defence research organization; public service, crime, human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court; textile, defence, law, education, and home ministry; crime analysis & judicial reporting; entrepreneur, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Scientist and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia

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Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

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- Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)
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- (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36807.51367>;
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

152. Hossain, M.A., *Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of "Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist" on "Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds"*. 2024: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36270.32328>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13182515>.
153. Hossain, M.A., *Coalesced the syllabus and course structures in textile engineering and relevant courses in the eighteen years duration academic and professional journey of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist from 2006 to 2024*. 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21803.66082>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13888294>.
154. Hossain, M.A., *A self-understanding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist about Bangladeshi Nobel laureate Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus and law implementation of Bangladesh Government*. 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 5 January 2024. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26912.35846>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10461097>.
155. Hossain, M.A., *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of 'free of cost google drive (2TB) access' to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com*. 2024, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28761.94568>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13994976>.
156. Hossain, M.A., *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia*. 2024: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>.
157. Hossain, M.A., *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education*. 2024: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699107>.
158. Hossain, M.A., *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is self-nominating for 'global excellence award' at Functional Textiles and Clothing (FTC), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India under the category of 'Leadership in Research' and/or 'Emerging Innovator' under the invitation of FTC team, IIT, Delhi, India*. 2024: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36325.61929>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14213757>.
159. Hossain, M.A., *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school*. 2025, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14934539>.

160. Hossain, M.A., *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching for the prestigious 'best researcher award' under the provisional nomination of organizing committee, research scientist awards of Indian government.* 2025, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36413.17128>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064119>.
161. Hossain, M.A., *Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist*, in *Scholarly Community Encyclopedia*. 2023 <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49098>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34177.43368>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10208384>.
162. Anowar Hossain, A.K.S., A. Bagchi, Kashmita Bhattacharya, *Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric*. *Journal of Materials Sciences and Applications*, American Association for Science and Technology (AASCIT), USA, 2016. 2(4): p. 25-34 <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16757.35048>.
163. Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, D.S., Barrister (Dr.), *Journal of Dr. Anowar*. 2025: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29003.30243>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15550150>.
164. Hossain, M.A., *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia.* 2025: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32735.16801>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718630>.
165. Hossain, M.A., *Local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country.* 2025: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28463.85929>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826808>.
166. Hossain, M.A., *Invitation of legal client for legal service to individual and/or organization.* 2025: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13073.70249>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16990186>.
167. Hossain, M.A., *Invitation of law researchers in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.* 2025: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30060.63369>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16995119>.
168. Hossain, M.A., *Invitation of researchers in textile engineering in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.* 2025: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17215.57765>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16960861>.
169. Hossain, M.A., *Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre.* 2025: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24765.32485>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16961335>.
170. Hossain, M.A., *A follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia.* 2025: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18369.83044>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17231359>.

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

171. Hossain, M.A., *Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia to United Nations*. 2025: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 24 October 2025. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21791.21922>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17430696>.
172. Hossain, M.A., *Let's dream a 'zero bombing philosophy' in the planet, let's shout and establish a peace surviving technique in the planet* in *Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA)*, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia 2026 <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14179.41766>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18884135>.

Simultaneous Dyeing and Finishing with Natural Dyes and Natural Finishing Agents on Cotton Textiles

A thesis published in fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of
Doctor of Philosophy in Textile Technology

Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta
35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, Kolkata, India.

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Type of publication and online display since 2017-2020

Year of research: 2015-2020

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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Author's biography since 1986

Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata].

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

1 Personal profile and professional achievement of author since 2006

Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata].

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

2 Relevant research of this first PhD¹ thesis was also studied for second PhD² to satisfy different philosophy at School of fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia (2020-2023)

UV-Visible-NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection. *Scientific Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31725-2>

3 Research and publication practice centre since 2006

Chief Researcher and Founder⁶; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁵; Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; study leave approved by City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh.

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Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)⁴; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh.

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Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)¹; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre¹; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, 40, Kemal Ataturk Avenue, Banani, Dhaka 1213, Bangladesh

Table 1. Evidences of scholarly witness and research publications to satisfy the PhD¹ requirement of research to issue PhD¹ certificate from University of Calcutta, India and/or Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur under the registration of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, University of Calcutta, India in 2015 in terms of chain extension of MTech research and study, 2015-2020[1].

SN	Title of publications	Journal (online)	DOI/ID	Author and author type	Registered supervisor/peer reviewer,
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“Expected Position: Chief Professor/Senior Professor/Vice-Chancellor/Chancellor/Chief Scientist/Research Director (Tech)/Chief Director (R & D)”
Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; PhD thesis on “simultaneous dyeing and finishing with natural dyes and natural finishing agents on cotton textiles” (2015-2020).

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					scholarly witness, external witness
1.	Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric, 2(4), 25-34 [2].	Journal of Materials Sciences and Applications	10.13140/RG.2.2.1 6757.35048	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, Dr. Kashmita Bhattacharya, Dr. Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik, CU, India
2.	Cyclodextrin for Aroma Finishing on Textile Substrate-A Review Article, 2019. 8(89) [3].	International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations	10.5281/zenodo.82 42756	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, CU, India
3.	Textile coloration and fragrance finishing for perfumed garments [Textile Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-70019, West Bengal, India][4].	MTech Thesis	10.13140/RG.2.2.1 5918.48965; 10.5281/zenodo.78 54437	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, CU, India
4.	Integrated dyeing and cosmetic finishing on cotton fabric 6th all India Inter Engineering college academic meet-2015 and Science & Technology exhibition for a sustainable society, Organised by Forum of Scientist, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET), 15N, Nelli Sengupta Sarani (Lindsay Street), Kolkata-7000087, India [5].	Conference	10.13140/RG.2.2.2 9340.2624; 10.5281/zenodo.13 304637	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, CU, India Professor (Dr.) Swapon Kumar Gosh (conference support) CU, India

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5.	Anowar's Handbook on Advance Textile Technology School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35 Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India (enr.anowar@yahoo.com) [6]	Preprint book ResearchGate Zenodo Searching 'Chief Professor/ Chief Scientist' category fund to accomplish the book	10.13140/RG.2.2.3 5648.8576; 10.5281/zenodo.15 068136	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Self
6.	Power Point Presentation on Applications and Engineering of Geotextiles (Department of Textile Engineering, City university, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh (enr.anowar@yahoo.com, Issue; 2015 [7, 8].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.1 7899.3152; 10.5281/zenodo.83 11345	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Self
7.	Power Point Presentation on Combined dyeing and cosmetic finishing of woven cotton fabric for garments (Department of Jute and Fibre technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, India, Issue; 2015 [9]	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.2 8804.5056; 10.5281/zenodo.83 11367	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, Dr. Arindam Bagchi, CU, India
8.	Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India, 2013-2015 [10].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.1 2565.0944; 10.5281/zenodo.15 068327	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Self
9.	Product analysis and merchandising of aroma encapsulated inner garments[11]	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.2 5123.92967; 10.5281/zenodo.18 885116	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain,	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India

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		Journal of Dr. Anowar		RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	
10.	<i>A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020)</i> R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh [12]	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.16273.08801; 10.5281/zenodo.17389964	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT University, Australia.
11.	Judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD1 achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia	ResearchGate Zenodo		Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT University, Australia.

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12.	A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre, 2019. 3(1): p. 1-3 [13].	International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering	10.29011/IJTSE-126/100026; 10.13140/RG.2.2.3 6811.36648; 10.5281/zenodo.82 45079	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India; Prof. (Dr.) Md. Nurul Abser, JU, Bangladesh; Dr. Ferdous Ara Dilruba, BJRI, Bangladesh
13.	Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent, 2018. 2(2): p. 1-8 [14].	Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing	MS.ID: 000132	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India
14.	Non-toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric using Non-toxic Colorant and Nontoxic Crosslinker, 2018. 8(5): p. 1-5 [15].	Journal of Textile Science & Engineering	10.4172/2165-8064.1000374	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India; Dr. Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik, CU, India; Dr. Padma S. Vankar, IIT, India; Dr. Dhara Shukla, IIT, India
15.	Organic Colouration and Antimicrobial Finishing of Organic Cotton Fabric by Exploiting Distillated Organic Extraction of Organic Tectona grandis and Azardirachta indica with Organic Mordanting Compare to Conventional Inorganic Mordants, 2018. 2018(1): p. 1-12[16].	International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering	10.29011/ IJTSE-113/100013	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India; Dr. Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik, CU, India; Dr. Padma S. Vankar, IIT, India; Dr. Dhara Shukla, IIT, India
16.	Pollution Free Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted from Swietenia macrophylla and Musa Acuminata as Unpolluted Dyes and Citrus. Limon (L.) as Unpolluted Mordanting Agent, 2018, 3(2): p. 1-8[17].	Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology	10.31031/TTEFT.2 018.03.000558	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India; Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, CU, Bangladesh

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17.	A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles, Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments (pp. 151-170) [18].	IntechOpen	10.5772/intechopen.92360	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India;
18.	Zero Toxic Approach of Cotton Fabric Coloration with Botanical Waste resource via Psidium P. guajava (Guava Leaves) as Natural Dyes and Citrus Lemon (Lemon Leaves) as Natural Mordanting Agent. 2019; [19].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.18112.75524	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Prof. (Dr.) Ashis Kumar Samanta, CU, India Prof. (Dr.) Md. Nurul Abser, JU, Bangladesh

Table 2. Charted overview of research and publications in five-years duration (full-time) PhD^{2*} and in textile technology, technical textiles & color Engineering; a thesis for Nobel prize¹ in physics and/or camouflage physics and/or color physics, 2020-2026 [1].

SN	Title of publications	Journal/ preprint/ conference (online)	DOI/ISSN	Author and author type	Registered Supervisor and/or scholarly witness
1.	Advancement in UV-Vis-IR camouflage Textiles for concealment of defense surveillance against multidimensional combat background; 2024, 19:45, P: 1-38 [20].	Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Engineering, Springer; Research Square	10.1186/s40712-024-00182-8	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia

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2.	Adaptive Camouflage Textiles with Thermochromic Colorant and Liquid Crystal for Multidimensional Combat Background, a Technical Approach for Advancement in Defence Protection; 9(1), 31-47, 2021 [21]	American Journal of Materials Engineering and Technology; Published by Science and Education Publishing	10.12691/materials-9-1-3	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
3.	Simulation of chromatic and achromatic assessments for camouflage textiles and combat background, 2022, 1-16 [22].	Journal of Defense Modeling and Simulation: Applications, Methodology, Technology; Sage	10.1177/15485129211067759	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
4.	Spectral simulation and method design of camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral imaging in UV-Vis-IR against multidimensional combat background, 1-12, 2021 [23]	The Journal of the Textile Institute; Taylor & Francis	10.1080/00405000.2022.2027074	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
5.	Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums, 3 April 2023; Volume 13, Pages: 306-319 [24]	MRS Communication s; Springer	10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
6.	Concealment, Detection, Recognition, and Identification of Target Signature on Water Background under Natural	International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations;	10.5281/zenodo.8242827 ; 10.13140/R	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain,	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert

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	Illumination, 10(117), 1-11, Article 1011721-01, 2021 [25]	ISSN: 2251-8843	G.2.2.10885.32487 Paper ID: 1011721-01	RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Shanks; RMIT, Australia
7.	Evaluation of Camouflage Coloration of Polyamide-6,6 Fabric by Comparing Simultaneous Spectrum in Visible and Near-Infrared Region for Defense Applications; (pp. 1-22); 2022 [26]	Colorimetry; IntechOpen	10.5772/intechopen.101537	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
8.	Coloration of polyamide-6,6 fabric with carbon black nano particle for camouflage textiles of simultaneous spectrum probe in visible and near infrared [27].	Advance Research in Textile Engineering, Austin Publishing Group.	10.13140/RG.2.2.36504.98560; 10.5281/zenodo.8297554	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
9.	Camouflage Assessment Of Aluminium Coated Textiles for Woodland and Desertland Combat Background in Visible and Infrared Spectrum under UV-Vis-IR Background Illumination, 1 July 2022; 72(3), 359-370 [28]	Defence Science Journal	10.14429/dsj.72.17731	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

10.	UV-Visible-NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection, 28 March 2023, 13:5021 [29]	Scientific Reports, Nature	10.1038/s41598-023-31725-2	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
11.	Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV-Visible-IR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging; Preprint (Version 1); 11 May 2023; 1-15 [30]	Heliyon Research Square	10.21203/rs.3.rs-2298847/v1	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
12.	Ecofriendly Camouflage Textiles with Natural Sand-based Silicon Dioxide against Simultaneous Combat Background of Woodland, Desertland, Rockland, Concreteland and Water/Marine. Preprint (Version 1) [30].	Research Square	10.21203/rs.3.rs-2359705/v1	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
13.	Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination (Presented in academic conference, First milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University, 12 February 2021, Issue [31].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7844692 ; 10.13140/RG.2.2.28897.48488	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
14.	My first presentation at PhD School for selection of PhD research proposal on camouflage textiles in 2020. Academic conference at PhD School, School of Fashion &	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7918250 ;	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain,	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert

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	Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Australia, Vic-3056 [32].		10.13140/R G.2.2.33383.11680	RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Shanks; RMIT, Australia
15.	Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Background (Presented in humanities and social context conference, second milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University; 15 February 2022, Issue [33].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.32252.92803; 10.5281/zenodo.7844729	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
16.	Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds (5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Accepted on 28 March 2023; Valencia, Spain, Issue [34].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.22550.73282; 10.5281/zenodo.7844652	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
17.	Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds (Global Summit on Chemical Engineering and Catalysis (ISTRCEC 2023), accepted on 20 March 2023; Rome, Italy, Issue [35].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7847802; 10.13140/R G.2.2.23969.17766	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231656>

18.	Advancement in UV-Visible-IR Camouflage Textiles and Camouflage Physics; 2023 [36]	Scholarly Community Encyclopedia	10.13140/R G.2.2.34177.43368; 10.5281/zenodo.10208384 ID: 49095	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
19.	Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination, PhD student: 3820066, First milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021] [37].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.15701.50403, 10.5281/zenodo.7898541	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
20.	Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, Second milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022] [38].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.15701.50403, 10.5281/zenodo.7898707	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
21.	Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University [39].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.29936.23048; 10.5281/zenodo.14282063	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
22.	Conference Presentation on "Camouflage Engineering and Camouflage Textiles for Defence Technology"; 2023 Philippine Textile Congress, Future Thinking for	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.19380.22407; 10.5281/zen	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain,	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert

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	Philippine Textiles, Philippine Textile Research Institute (PTRI), Department of Science and Technology-Central Office (DOST-CO), General Santos Avenue Bicutan, Taguig City, Metro Manila, 1631, Philippine; Speaker during the Textile for Human Security and Defense Session (Session 8) of the Congress on 20 November 2023; Accepted [40].		odo.10117340	RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Shanks; RMIT, Australia
23.	First Action and Support Plan at PhD School during COVID-19 in 2020, Supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks [41].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.26567.68006, 10.5281/zenodo.7923009	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
24.	My declaration, acknowledgement and dedication to achieve PhD degree (Fashion & Textiles) on “camouflage textiles with technical coloration and incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds” [Textile Engineering, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021] [42].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.18532.65925; 10.5281/zenodo.7898850	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
25.	An optical platform of material engineering for design of camouflage product against multidimensional combat backgrounds from 400 nm to 2500 nm (Scholars World Congress on Material Science and Nanotechnology” (MatScience 2023), Accepted on 18 April 2023, Issue [43].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7844597; 10.13140/RG.2.2.28176.28165	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia

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				sole author; chief researcher	
26.	Power Point Presentation on Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Vis-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds (5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Issue [44].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.8298582	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
27.	Power Point Presentation on Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds (School of fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022, Issue [45].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.8311145	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
28.	Presentation on Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, RMIT University [45]	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/RG.2.2.29042.48322; 10.5281/zenodo.8146048	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
29.	Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Scholarly Community Encyclopedia [46].	ResearchGate	10.13140/RG.2.2.34177.43368; 10.5281/zenodo.10208384; ID: 9098	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia

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30.	Video presentation of Anowar Hossain's PhD invention in PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. In. School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia [47]	ResearchGate	10.13140/R G.2.2.21104. 43524	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
31.	Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of “Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist” on “Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds” School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com) [48].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.36270. 32328; 10.5281/zen odo.1318251 5	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
32.	Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is self-nominating for ‘global excellence award’ at Functional Textiles and Clothing (FTC), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India under the category of ‘Leadership in Research’ and/or ‘Emerging Innovator’ under the invitation of FTC team, IIT, Delhi, India [49].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.36325. 61929; 10.5281/zen odo.1421375 7	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
33.	Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching for the prestigious ‘best researcher award’ under the provisional nomination of organizing committee, research scientist awards of Indian government [Grant]. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street,	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.36413. 17128; 10.5281/zen odo.1506411 9	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia

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	Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (enr.anowar@yahoo.com) [50].			sole author; chief researcher	
34.	A short summery and evidences of Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia [51].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.14593. 43368; 10.5281/zen odo.1272255 5	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
35.	Letter to Nobel committee for Nobel prize in camouflage physics [52].	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.36807. 51367; 10.5281/zen odo.1084243 5	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
36.	Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV-visible-NIR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging (supporting information), M.A. Hossain, Editor. 2026: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (enr.anowar@yahoo.com ; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au) [53]	Zenodo	10.5281/zen odo.1847653 3	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia
37.	Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV-visible-NIR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging (video of supporting information), M.A. Hossain, Editor. 2026: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (enr.anowar@yahoo.com ; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au)[54]	ResearchGate Zenodo	10.13140/R G.2.2.35535. 14244; 10.5281/zen odo.1848124 6	Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, RMIT, Australia; single/ sole author; chief researcher	Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks; RMIT, Australia

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Table 3. Total contents of the thesis

Description of the contents	Page numbers	Pages with separate numerical sequence
Title page of the thesis	1	
Personal details of author	2	
Personal profile and professional achievement of author since 1986	3	
Relevant research of this first PhD¹ thesis was also studied for second PhD² to satisfy different philosophy at School of fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia (2020-2023)	3	
Research and publication practice centre since 2006	3	
Evidences of scholarly witness and research publications to satisfy the PhD1 requirement of research to issue PhD1 certificate from University of Calcutta, India and/or Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur under the registration of Professor Dr. Ashis Kumar Samanta, University of Calcutta, India in 2015 in terms of chain extension of MTech research and study, 2015-2020	3-8	
Charted overview of research and publications in five-years duration (full-time) PhD²* and in textile technology, technical textiles & color Engineering; a thesis for Nobel prize1 in physics and/or camouflage physics and/or color physics, 2020-2026	8-17	
Total contents of the thesis	18-19	
Key themes and prospects of research contribution in terms of multidimensional source of research and future analysis	19	
Keynote of the thesis	19	
Research questions of the thesis	20	
Reference	21-25	
Introduction		
A review on technological and natural dyeing concepts for natural dyeing along with natural finishing on natural fibre	26-29	
Experimentations		
Organic colouration and antimicrobial finishing of organic cotton fabric by exploiting distilled organic extraction of organic <i>Tectona Grandis</i> and <i>Azardirachta Indica</i> with organic mordanting compare to conventional inorganic mordants	30-42	
Non-toxic coloration of cotton fabric using non-toxic colorant and nontoxic crosslinker	43-50	
Pollution free dyeing on cotton fabric extracted from <i>Swietenia Macrophylla</i> and <i>Musa Acuminata</i> as unpolluted dyes and Citrus. Limon (L.) as unpolluted mordanting agent	51-59	
Green dyeing on cotton fabric demodulated from <i>Diospyros Malabarica</i> and <i>Camellia Sinensis</i> with green mordanting agent	60-68	
Conclusion		
A practical guideline of few standardized ready made shades of natural dyed textiles, chemistry and technology of natural and synthetic dyes and pigments	69-89	
Research, trialing, and relevant analysis going on (2020-)	90	
A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020) R. U. School of Fashion and	91-266	

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Total pages of the thesis	1-266	
This thesis has the attachment of two separate files of PhD situation with the separate title and separate page numbers (Administrative functions of the thesis, PhD expertise of author, thesis development process, judicial functions of the PhD, administrative duty of researchers, evidences and relevant references, relevant approach, comments, and guidelines for PhD industries)		
Judicial requirements of academic, professional, and PhD law in universities, and a first PhD ¹ achievement of author at University of Calcutta, India since 2015-2020; Journal of Dr. Anowar (JDA), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia		1-257
PhD ⁰ thesis of author on “Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric.”		1-402

Figure 1. Key themes and prospects of research contribution in terms of multidimensional source of research and future analysis

4 Keynote of the thesis

Pollution in textile dyeing is a global challenge. Eco-friendly colorant is the existing demand in textile technology. Zero-toxic coloration is a global priority theme of research. The whole thesis was studied and concentrated on selected natural dyes for the colouring concepts of textile substances. The color properties of different natural dyed textiles were critically analysed and coalesced. Natural mordanting and non-mordanting process of natural dyeing was also approached with the synthetic mordanting. Medicinal property of natural dyed textiles can be used as antibacterial medical textiles. Therefore, this thesis has a broader scope of research, industrialization, and commercialization of natural dyed textiles in terms of textile colorant and medical textiles of dyeing-coating-printing, and material design of multidimensional purposes.

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5 Research questions and philosophical grounds of the PhD¹ thesis at University of Calcutta, India (2015-2020)

Research question-01
 To analyse the color properties of selected natural dyes on natural dyed textiles.

Research question-02
 To apply the dyeing techniques of natural mordanting, non-mordanting, and synthetic mordanting

Research question-03
 To develop the process of natural dyeing, product design, material design, and relevant approach of research commercialization

Research question-04
 (an extension of the research question of MTech and/or PhD thesis)
 To dye and finish of textile substances with new materials
 To analyse simultaneous property of dyed textiles, aroma textiles, medical textiles
 To standardize the methodology for the industrial applications for the product development.

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21

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Review Article

A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre

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Abstract

Natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural finishing agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing can be established by developing completely eco-friendly natural dyes and natural finishing agent which can be applied on cotton textiles (Oeko-Tech Products) by adopting a newer technique of simultaneous Mordanting-Dyeing-Finishing in a single step to reduce energy cost, process time, processing costs and effluent load as well as to develop the single step processes and also completely eco-friendly products of cotton textiles using selective natural dyes and natural finishing agents using bio mordants and bio finishing agents obtained from an extract of natural resources at reduced cost and energy. There is huge scope of commercialization of such Oeko-Tech (Eco-Friendly) products of natural dyed and finished cotton textile products for domestic and export market. Different selective natural dyes like teak leaf, turmeric, jackfruit wood, sappan wood, skin of onion, arjuna bark etc., bio-mordanting agent like bio-enzyme, harda, lemon as natural mordanting agents, extracted soyabean seed as natural chemical modification as well as natural finishing agent like coconut oil as UV absorber, neem and guava leaf as antimicrobial agent where all dyed and finished fabric can be scientifically tested by SEM, FTIR, DSC, HPLC, GCMS, TLC, CHNS, X-ray diffraction pattern etc.

27

Introduction

Worldwide growing consciousness for eco-friendly textile products is generating more and more customer's interests on natural fibres based textile as well as on natural dyes and natural finishing, particularly for the Export market. Considering this corner, textile sector has the highest scope to apply this research work for attracting the value-added customer. But, till today there is a huge lack of research and development of natural dyeing and finishing based textile product. There are ample scopes of doing scientific research on the application of natural dyes on cotton and other textiles aimed at obtaining newer shade with acceptable colour fastness behaviour and uniform and reproducible colour yield through appropriate techniques. Simultaneous natural dyeing and natural finishing: a new technique will thus serve process steps like energy and total process cost. Reducing process cost will minimize total cost of the product in the export market, it will be highly beneficial

to sustain in a competitive market if the expected research output can be applied successfully in Government and non-government textile mill at home and abroad.

Cotton is still a natural fibre of agro-origin that is used most in the world. About 46% of all fibre produced in the world is cotton. Even today cotton is the backbone of the world's textile trade. The cotton fibre presents many exceptional features like great flexibility, cohesive property, very small thickness, but high strength and wear resistance. Owing to these properties it is possible to process cotton fibres into yarns with greater diversity; from thick yarn for manufacturing coarse and different upholstery/furnishing as well as denim type apparel fabrics to very fine yarns for manufacturing thin and refined fabrics such as Batiste, Marquisette, Muslin, etc. Cotton fibre is widely used for making all types of apparels as well as all types of furnishing fabrics. In textile applications this biodegradable, environment-friendly and renewable fibre has some

distinct advantages such as moderate dry and wet tensile strength, appreciable moisture regains, agreeable feel, moderate extensibility, varied dye ability and appreciable UV-light stability. However, the major disadvantages of cotton lie in its dimensional instability as revealed by wash shrinkage, poor wrinkle recovery and ready susceptibility to microbial degradation.

Natural dyes are considered to be eco-friendly as these are obtained from renewable resources as compared to synthetic dyes which are derived from non-renewable petroleum resources. These are biodegradable and the residual vegetal matter left after extraction of dyes can be easily composted and used as fertilizer. They produce soft colours soothing to the eye which is in harmony with nature which is gradually gaining popularity due to its non-toxicity and eco-friendly character against possible unsafe ecotoxicity criteria of synthetic dyes. Most of the studies available for dyeing with natural dyes relates to cotton textiles and such studies on cotton are still insufficient to establish. Hence, there are ample scope of undertaking an integrated study in this area for cotton and chemically modified cotton to study its surface appearance, durability and dyeing of cotton and chemically modified cotton with natural dyes.

Literature Review

Growing consciousness for eco-friendly textile products has caused more interest on cotton fibre based natural dyeing and finishing. Productions of synthetic dyes are dependent on the petrochemical source and some of the synthetic dyes contain toxic/carcinogenic amines and are not eco-friendly. Contrary to this, most of the natural dyes as well as natural finish with few exceptions are based on vegetable/ animal origin and are renewable, biodegradable, energy-efficient and eco-friendly [1,2]. The most important issue now is origin and classification of some natural dyes applicable for different fibres are available in the literature [3-5]. Gupta, et al. [6] have documented some of the traditional processes of application of some natural dyes. Kawahito, et al. [7] have compared the dyeing of cellulosic fabric with natural indigo and synthetic indigo. Radhakrishnan [8] as well as Ajita, et al. [9] have reported the effect of different mordants on selective natural dyes. Grierson, et al. [10] has studied colour fastness characteristics of some natural dyes. Lee, et al. [11] have studied the colour fastness properties of some natural dyes by applying UV-absorbers. Effect of chemical structure on light fastness property of some natural dyes has been reported by Gupta, et al. [12]. Oda, et al. [13] has studied the effect of phenyl ester functional group on photofading of carthamin on cellulose acetate. Most of the studies are sporadic and insufficient in developing scientific knowledge base on the subject. Therefore, very less study on simultaneous natural dyeing and finishing, dyeing process variables and characterisation etc. Hence, an integrated scientific study for selective natural dye-fibre system, for selective natural dyes applied on cotton and other textiles is felt necessary, for establishing the process optimization in naturally dyed textiles. [14, 15 16, 17] Natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural fin-

ishing agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing were experimented in earlier research on natural coloration.

Application of Different Biomordanting with Biomordanting Agents

Effects of different degrees of biomordanting like bioenzyme, harda and lemon as natural mordanting agents and natural chemical modification extracted from soyabean seed on cotton fabric for altering its textile related properties and dye ability with selective natural dyes (say a teak leaf, turmeric, Jackfruit wood, sappan wood etc.) can be investigated. Effect of such biomodifications on colour parameters after dyeing of cotton and chemically and biochemically modified cotton and its colour fastness properties to light, washing, perspiration and rubbing can be studied. The photo fading behaviour of cotton and chemically and biochemically modified and dyed cotton materials after those modifications and pre-treatments and subsequent dyeing can be studied and an attempt can be taken to improve the same to a much better level of customer acceptability. Effects of different degree of chemical modifications on colour yield for the selective natural dyes can be studied. Cotton Textile materials dyed with natural dyes can be post-treated/finished with suitable natural agents for studying the effect of these after treatments on the improvement of colour yield, brightness and colour fastness behaviour of the dyed material. To improve the colour fastness properties for the selective natural dyes some pre or post-treatment with cationic or metallic complex compound or UV absorbers/suitable modifiers can be studied.

Process Development

The fabrics can be pre-treated by the eco-friendly enzyme-based chemical pre-treatment processes for preparing it for simultaneous dyeing and finishing. After that different natural dyes (say teak leaf, turmeric, jackfruit wood, sappan wood etc.) as well as natural finishing agent like coconut oil as UV absorber, neem and guava leaf as antimicrobial agent can be applied on cotton fabric for trailing and experimentations on application of dyes and finishing agent on cotton and optimization of dyeing process variables for improved colour development and improvement of colour fastness, all analytical testing. Effects of variations of dyeing process variables on colour yield and dyeing kinetics for application of selective natural dyes on cotton and chemically modified cotton substrate can be investigated to understand the dyeing isotherm, rate of dyeing and other thermodynamic parameters for such dyeing. This will help to understand the dyeing behaviours of different natural dyes applied on cotton to get an idea of formulating better colour yield having specific standardized dyeing recipe for combined/compound shades by use of binary or ternary mixture of these natural dyes. For use of combination of natural dyes for generating compound shades, a study on the compatibility of such binary and a ternary mixture of dyes can be also studied, to understand and find a compatible combination of such dyes for cotton

and chemically treated and modified cotton fabrics.

Process of Textile Properties and Dyeability Analysis

Changes in structural features for different degrees of chemical modifications (enzymatic hydrolysis, oxidation on cotton substrate) can be investigated with the help of Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), FTIR Spectroscopy and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), High-Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPLC), Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GCMS), Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC), Carbon, Hydrogen, Nitrogen and Sulphur (CHNS) analyzer and X-ray diffraction pattern etc. for explaining the major observations in these aspects. This will help to understand scientifically the scientific analysis of different changes in textile related property behaviour and dyeability in terms of changes in structural features of chemically modified cotton substrate along with changes in surface characteristics and durability etc.

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Research Article

Organic Colouration and Antimicrobial Finishing of Organic Cotton Fabric by Exploiting Distillated Organic Extraction of Organic *Tectona grandis* and *Azadirachta indica* with Organic Mordanting Compare to Conventional Inorganic Mordants

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Abstract

Eco-friendly dyeing on cotton fabric was conceded out with organic dyes distillate from organic extraction process of organic *Tectona grandis* (Teak Leaf) and *Azadirachta indica* (Neem Leaf) using ecofriendly metallic mordents and natural mordents (Ferrous Sulphate as ecofriendly metallic mordant and Lemon juice as an organic mordant) were used in the research work and their results were compared with results of Copper sulphate as conventionally used mordant. All the treated and untreated cotton fabric samples were tested for their Colour Strength and Colour fastness (colour fastness to Washing, UV-Light and Rubbing) properties, besides measurement of other colour interaction parameters (L^* , a^* , b^* and ΔE) as well as antibacterial performance as Per AATCC-100-2012 method. Results of colour parameters showed lower ΔE values are obtained when treated with lemon mordanting agent for both the case of dyeing cum finishing treatment with Teak leaf and Neem leaf (though amongst the two dye extract used, Neem leaf extract showed higher K/S value) as compared to conventional mordanting with Copper Sulphate. While, Ferrous Sulphate render moderate K/S value than all due to inherent own colour of iron in $FeSO_4$. Comparing lemon mordanting with conventional copper sulphate mordant, colour fastness properties of teak leaf extract with lemon mordanting are found to be better and is in the order of Rubbing Fastness > followed by colour fastness to Light > colour fastness to wash than that for synthetic mordanting, but for dyeing with extract of neem leaf with lemon mordanting showed very attractive colour fastness considering to all colour fastness properties studied here. In this study, a newer approach / attempt had been made to impart a simultaneous antibacterial finish along with above said natural dyeing. Hence, the antibacterial properties of neem leaf extract dyed cotton using lemon mordanted sample resulted better reduction/killing of bacteria. Thus, this work has led to development of a process of simultaneous dyeing and finishing with natural agents on organic cotton with organic mordents to make the fabric colour full and anti-bacterial too.

Keywords: Inorganic Mordanting; Organic Dyeing and Finishing; Organic Extraction; Organic Mordanting; Organic *Tectona grandis* (Teak Leaf) and *Azadirachta indica* (Neem Leaf.)

Introduction

Promoting traditional textiles by highlighting its value added aspects is a very common practice of Apparel Manufacturers/ prominent brands. Among the various value added tools employed presently with antimicrobial finish and natural dyed colour are on the major front. Natural dyes have a great demand in the international market. Due to the current economic and environmental consciousness, research in this front should be tilted towards the use of natural dyes for dyeing textile materials. Today, people around the globe are rediscovering colour through the use of renewable and non-toxic natural sources. For successful commercial use of natural dyes for any particular fibres, the appropriate scientific standardized techniques/procedures are to be derived. Thus, relevant scientific studies and its output on standardization of dyeing methods, dyeing process variables, dyeing kinetics and test of compatibility of selective natural dyes and natural mordents have become very important. Many natural mordents like hard, lemon juice and *Aloe vera* etc. are reported to be rarely used and these are till now renowned for human health benefits as well as beauty products, is now proving its prospect as a substantial mordant for natural dyes. Lemon juice is also selected as the most important natural mordant to standardize the dyeing effect. Most of the natural dyes as well as natural finish with few exceptions are based on vegetable/ animal origin and are renewable, biodegradable, energy-efficient and eco-friendly [1,2]. Single and binary mixtures of aqueous extracts of red sandalwood (RSW) with aqueous extract of other natural dyes like Man Jistha (MJ), Jack Fruit Wood (JFW), Mari Gold (MG), Sappan Wood (SW) and BaBool (BL) in different proportions are applied on bleached jute fabric for its dyeing after double pre-mordanted with myrobolan and aluminium sulphate applied in sequence under optimized conditions of mordanting with effects of use of different proportions of binary mixture of selective natural dyes on colour strength and other colour where good fastness properties were observed [3]. Bleached cotton fabric (after sequential pre-mordanting with myrobolan and then with aluminium sulphate applied in sequence) had been dyed with a pre-fixed concentration of purified binary mixtures of Jack Fruit Wood (JFW) and other natural dyes, like Man Jistha (MJ), Red Sandal Wood (RSW), Marie Gold (MG), Sappan Wood (SW) and BaBool (BL) in different proportions to obtain a variety of compound shades wherever colour strength (K/S values), washing and colour fastness properties were improved [4]. Natural extracted dyes, manjistha was applied on cotton fabric and observed the improvement of wash and light fastness properties [5]. Myobolan (Harda) and metallic salts (Potash

alum and aluminium sulphate) as mordents and aqueous extract of Tesu (Palash flower petals) as dyeing agent was used and found improved wash and light fastness [6]. Myrobo-lan (harda) and other mordants (metallic salts) followed by dyeing with aqueous extract of Jackfruit and found good color fastness properties [7]. Thomas bechtold & Rita Mussak were studied that main colorant of turmeric is curcumin (brown-red crystals) does not dissolve in water but it does in alcohol, ether and a polar solvent. In acid solution the dye changes color to scarlet; in alkali solution the color is first red and then violet [8]. Rajan. S was studied that Turmeric is a tropical plant is the most popular natural dye in textile dyeing. The root of the turmeric plant (*Curcuma longa*) creates strong colors, from bright yellow with no mordant to dark green with an iron modifier [9]. Md. Mahabub Hasan¹, Khandakar Abu Nayem, Abu Yousuf Mohammad AnwarulAzim were studied that Cotton and silk fabrics are dyed with the curcumin dye at a liquor ratio of 1:40 and concentrations on color strength, mordanting is carried out with three metallic salts such as; aluminium potassium sulphate, copper sulphate and tartaric acid. Mordanting is carried out through two ways: 1) pre-mordanting, 2) postmordanting. And observed that mordant has a great effect to increase the color strength of the fabric [10]. Bukhari. H, Heba. M & Khadijah.Q were studied that Neem leaves was extracted by grinding into fine powders and followed by mixing with methanol at room temperature then was left closed for 3 days. So this method is time consuming and might promote the degradation of color compounds [11]. Normal Pal, who is a Textile Engr. and is the Chief Executive Officer of NKP-Engineers & IPRs Consultants, Kolkata has developed neem medicated **textiles [12]. Deo & B.K.** Desai were studied that Tea (*Camellia sinensis*) is an evergreen plant that grows mainly in tropical and subtropical climates. *Camellia sinensis* which is the most popular non-alcoholic beverage in the world. Cotton and jute fabrics were dyed with an aqueous extract of tea, containing tannins as the main colorant species. The dyeing was carried out with and without metal salts as mordants, using three different dyeing methods: pre-mordanting, meta-mordanting and post-mordanting. The resulting wash and light fastness of the dyed fabrics were good to excellent. The color of the fabrics was investigated on computer color matching system in terms of K/S, and CIELAB color-difference values. Deep shades (K/S= 3.9) were obtained for jute in acidic media, while cotton fabrics could be dyed in medium depths (K/S= 2.0) under identical conditions of dyeing [12]. Varinder Kaur was studied that dyeing of cotton fabric with green tea as a natural colorant had been investigated. The dyeing process was carried out (with and without mordant) with dye extracted from three different qualities of tea leaves using four different mediums. The dyeing properties on cotton fabric had been evaluated and comparative study of optical density, washing fastness, light fastness, K/S and reflectance values were investigated. The build-up, color yield and washing fastness

were excellent and light fastness properties were found to be moderate to good. The dyeing properties on cotton fabric using dye extracted from tea leaves has been evaluated and comparative study of optical density, washing fastness, light fastness, K/S & reflectance values have been done. So, tea as a natural colorant gives good results on cotton [13]. Tea was applied on cotton fabric [14]. Nurizza Fauziyah & Luchman Hakim were studied that the fresh teak leaves were collected from home garden and plantation as natural dye. The extraction of teak leaves produces red hearts color. Young teak leaf contains several compounds, especially anthocyanin pigments. This anthocyanin compound gives red, purple, dark red. The results of teak leaf extract are also used as a dye for yarn well by the community of West Bengal, India [15]. Geeta Mahale was studied that the silk was dyed with teak extract, mordanting was done by mixing two mordants in different proportions and assessed the fastness properties of dyed silk [16]. Padma S Vankar was studied that the chemical composition of the teak leaves colorant is anthraquinoid compounds, with the leaves reportedly containing a yellow or red dye used for dyeing silk, in yellow, olive or related shades and *Tectona* can be used as a natural colorant in textile dyeing on a commercial scale [17]. Sanjay R. Malpani was studied that Aloe vera also possesses antifungal and antibacterial properties, which can be exploited for medical textile applications, such as wound dressing, suture bioactive textiles, etc. [18]. Abu Naser, Md. Ahsanul Haque were studied that Aloe Vera, till now renowned for human health benefits as well as beauty products, is now proving its prospect as a substantial mordant for natural dyes. For instance, Turmeric- the most popular natural dye does not only have coloring ability but also have anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, anti-parasitic and some other significant activities. [19]. Sundrarajan. M., Selvam. S., Rajiv Gandhi. R. and Sujesh. J. were studied that Marigold and Turmeric were used for the extraction of the natural dye material. Tannic acid, Cow dung, Pomegranate rind and Lemon juice were selected as natural mordant to standardize the dyeing effect of Marigold and Turmeric dyes on silk and knitted cotton fabric. The method appropriate for natural dye dyeing on knitted cotton was found to be pre-mordanting by studying with other methods such as simultaneous and post mordanting method. The color developed range on dyed materials is evaluated by dye uptake measurement and the improvement of color strength on fabric using mordants was also examined. Tannic acid and pomegranate increase the color strength effectively than the other. The dye uptake values have been found to be good in all dyed samples but some cases produced poor fastness. Marigold with tannic acid and pomegranate rind produced good dye uptake and fastness properties. All the mordanted fabric showed good dye uptake [20]. Abdu Zubairu, Yusuf M Sheliawere studied that coloration of fabric is a major process in the production of textile material. In this work, natural dye was extracted from onion skin and used to dye cotton fabrics using selected synthetic and natural

mordants. The synthetic mordants considered in this work are potassium dichromate, iron sulphate, copper sulphate and alum whereas the natural mordants are aloe Vera and lemon. Cotton fabrics were dyed using each of the selected mordants under three different conventional mordanting techniques; pre-mordanting, simultaneous-mordanting and post-mordanting, adopting the well-known vat dyeing method. A wide range of soft and light colors were obtained using the various mordants considered, also the mordanting technique was found to influence the results of the dyeing process. Natural mordants gave pale yellow colors, while synthetic mordant such as copper sulphate and alum also gave yellow colors. On the other hand, iron sulphate gave darker shades of colors. It was concluded that onion skin dye with iron sulphate as mordant under post-mordanting technique gave the best result of color fast of the onion skin dye. Natural Mordant's: Lemon juice and Aloe Vera were used as natural mordant's. This paper highlights the use of ferrous sulphate, copper sulphate, alum and tannic acid as mordants' in the pre-mordanting bath with cotton fabrics. After dyeing ferrous sulphate imparted darker impact whereas copper sulphate showed saddening effect on dyed fabrics, alum was responsible for increasing lightness but tannic acid made the dyed samples brilliant. Ferrous sulphate and copper sulphate mordanted samples showed good washing and light fastness but alum and then tannic acid helped the dyed fabrics to be poor to fair color fast to washing and light but fair to good to rubbing. Almost all the mordant's had less impact on perspiration fastness and shown appreciable loss of color [22]. Arsheen Moiz, M. Aleem Ahmed, Naheed Kausar, Kamran Ahmed, Munnaza Sohail were studied that aqueous extract of natural dye, tea was dyed on the wool fabric with dark brown for 2% and 5% shade. The tea containing tannins as the main colorant species to produce different shade with different mordant salts. The mordant salts Alum, CuSO_4 , FeSO_4 , ZnSO_4 , Na_2SO_4 , and MgSO_4 were used to dye fabric using three different dyeing methods: pre-mordanting, meta-mordanting and post-mordanting. The color of the fabric was investigated on Data Color matching system in terms of K/S and CIE Lab-color difference values. The post-mordanting method gave the great depth of shade of natural dye tea with 2% and 5% shade, it also gives good light fastness and wash fastness properties. Copper was found as a good mordant to achieve the best results with transition metal ions effect. Deep shades ($K/S = 17.50$) were obtained for original sample of 5% with color difference ΔE value is 0.17, as compare to 2% original sample of tea of light brown shades ($K/S = 10.50$) with color difference ΔE value is 0.50 under maintained temperature at 85°C for 35 min of dyeing [23]. Many recent report on standardization of natural dyeing and test of compatibility etc. are available in literature [24-28]. In last few years, FEAT, IIT Kanpur and Dept. of Jute and Fiber Technology, University of Calcutta jointly has standardized identification and

natural dyeing methods with more than six natural dyes and the same work is being continued now for another 4-5 natural dyes. The present work therefore is a small part of that endeavor supported financially by Ministry of Textiles, Govt of India through Textile Commissioner’s Office, Mumbai. India.

Materials and Experimental Methods

Materials Used:

Materials	Sources
Organic Cotton Fabric: GSM 150 (Scoured & Bleached)	From Local Markert , India and also from Alim Knit Bd Ltd., Kashimpur, Gagipur, Bangladesh
FeSO ₄ , CuSO ₄ (For Comparison), Distilled water	E Marc - India and also from Mother trade International Mirpur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Organic Lemon	Vegetable Garden, Ashulia, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
Organic Teak Leaf	Tree Garden at IIT-Kanpur and also from Ashulia, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
Organic Neem Leaf	Tree Garden, At IIT Kanpur and also from Ashulia, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Experimental Methods:

Dyeing and Finishing with Teak Leaf:

Stock Solution Preparation:

Teak leaf Solution: 3.5% Stock Solution

Process:

Preparation of FeSO₄ Stock Solution

FeSO₄ Solution: 5% Stock Solution

Process:

CuSO₄ Solution: 5% Stock Solution of CuSO₄ for Conventional mordanting process for comparison purpose.

Process:

Experiment: T- 1

Collected fresh Teak leaf was dried in sun light for one week. During drying it was checked several times that it was in cringe condition or not. After confirming fully drying it was converted into powder form by automatic blender machine. Then 3.5% solution of powder Teak leaf 100ml was prepared for dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric. After that 5gm fabric was dyed at (70 to 75)°C temperature running time of 30 minutes. Temperature checked by thermometer and finished with padding and drying method.

Dyeing Process Flowchart:

Experiment: T- 2

Collected fresh Teak leaf was dried in sun light for one week. During drying it was checked several times that it was in cringe condition or not. After confirming fully drying it was converted into powder form by automatic blender machine. Then 3.5% solution of powder Teak leaf 100ml was prepared for dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric as well as 30 ml Lemon solution was prepared. After that 5gm fabric was dyed at (70 to 75)^oC temperature running time of 30 minutes. Temperature checked by thermometer and finished with padding and drying method.

Dyeing Process Flowchart:

Experiment: T- 3

Collected fresh Teak leaf was dried in sun light for one week. During drying it was checked several times that it was in cringe condition or not. After confirming fully drying it was converted into powder form by automatic blender machine. Then 3.5% solution of powder Teak leaf 100ml was prepared for dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric as well as 5% stock solution of CuSO₄ 30 ml was prepared. After that 5gm fabric was dyed at (70 to 75)^oC temperature running time of 30 minutes. Temperature checked by thermometer and finished with padding and drying method.

Dyeing Process Flowchart:

Experiment: T- 4

Collected fresh Teak leaf was dried in sun light for one week. During drying it was checked several times that it was in cringe condition or not. After confirming fully drying it was converted into powder form by automatic blender machine. Then 3.5% solution of powder Teak leaf 100ml was prepared for dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric as well as 5% stock solution of FeSO₄ 30 ml was prepared. After that 5gm fabric was dyed at (70 to 75)^oC temperature running time of 30 minutes. Temperature checked by thermometer and finished with padding and drying method.

Dyeing Process Flowchart:

Dyeing and Finishing with Neem Leaf:

Stock Solution Preparation for Neem Leaf dyeing:

Neem Solution: 5% Stock Solution of Neem Laef

Process:

FeSO₄ Solution: 5% Stock Solution of FeSO₄

Process:

Experiment: N- 1

Collected fresh Neem leaf was dried in sun light for one week. During drying it was checked several times that it was in cringe condition or not. After confirming fully drying it was converted into powder form by automatic blender machine. Then 5% solution of powder Neem leaf 100ml was prepared for dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric. After that 5gm fabric was dyed at (70 to 75) °C temperature running time of 30 minutes. Temperature checked by thermometer and finished with padding and drying method.

CuSO₄ Solution: 5% Stock Solution

Process:

Dyeing Process Flowchart:

Experiment: N- 2

Collected fresh Neem leaf was dried in sun light for one week. During drying it was checked several times that it was in cringe condition or not. After confirming fully drying it was converted into powder form by automatic blender machine. Then 5% solution of powder Neem leaf 70ml was prepared for dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric as well as 30ml stock solution of Lemon was prepared. After that 5gm fabric was dyed at (70 to 75)°C temperature running time of 30 minutes. Temperature checked by thermometer and finished with padding and drying method.

Dyeing Process Flowchart:

Experiment: N- 3

Collected fresh Neem leaf was dried in sun light for one week. During drying it was checked several times that it was in cringe condition or not. After confirming fully drying it was converted into powder form by automatic blender machine. Then 5% solution of powder Neem leaf 70ml was prepared for dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric as well as 5% stock solution of CuSO₄ 30ml was prepared. After that 5gm fabric was dyed at (70 to 75)°C temperature running time of 30 minutes. Temperature checked by thermometer and finished with padding and drying method.

Dyeing Process Flowchart:

Experiment: N- 4

Collected fresh Neem leaf was dried in sun light for one week. During drying it was checked several times that it was in cringe condition or not. After confirming fully drying it was con-

verted into powder form by automatic blender machine. Then 5% solution of powder Neem leaf 70ml was prepared for dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric as well as 5% stock solution of FeSO_4 30ml was prepared. After that 5gm fabric was dyed at (70 to 75) °C temperature running time of 30 minutes. Temperature checked by thermometer and finished with padding and drying method.

Dyeing Process Flowchart:

Testing Methods

Color strength (K/S value) was measured by measuring surface reflectance value where Computer color measuring instrument (Macbeth 2020 plus spectrophotometer). Color strength of untreated and treated cotton fabric samples is measured from the reflectance value at maximum wave length from which surface color strength (K/S value) can be

$$\text{determined by Kubelka-Munk equation: } K/S = \frac{(1-R_{\lambda\max})}{2R_{\lambda\max}} \alpha CD$$

Where, K = coefficient of absorption, S = coefficient of scattering, $R_{\lambda\max}$ = reflectance of the substrate at maximum absorbance wavelength, CD = concentration of dye.

Light fastness was tested by AATCCTM16 in Q-SUNXE-2 Xenon Test chamber against blue wool standards (BS-1006-B01-1978).

Colour Fastness to washing was tested as per ISO-I method using 5gpl neutral soap at 50°C with 1:50 MLR for 45 min at 40 RPM using launder-o meter and was assessed with grey scale.

Color fastness to Rubbing was tested as per ISO 105-X12:2001(E) which finger and force were used in the test. Whether dry or wet rubbing was performed along with the percentage of soak the numerical rating for staining for each test specimen. The staining of the cotton rubbing cloths with the grey scale for staining under suitable illumination.

Antimicrobial Test Was done as per AATCC-100-2012 method.

Results & Discussions

Distinct appearance of natural color in Tea leaf and Teak leaf

had been studied with color order system like a^* , b^* , L^* , and ΔE in the terms of Da^* , Db^* , Dc^* and DE have been presented here in comparison to bleached cotton fabric and proved that deeper shade was produced for organic mordanted sample and ecofriendly inorganic and metallic mordanted sample comparing to Copper sulphate mordanted sample. Similarly, higher K/S value showed for lemon and ferrous sulphate mordanting for Teak Leaves as well as higher K/S value showed for lemon and ferrous sulphate mordanting for Tea Leaves with having minor differences than copper sulphate mordanted sample. The complex formation of Cu_2^+ and Fe_2^+ are responsible for higher k/S value but very good hand fell/softness of dyed cotton fabric was also observed by the researchers for organic mordanting due to absence of Cu_2^+ and Fe_2^+ . Both natural dyes in the presence of organic mordanting as well as hydrophilic nature of fiber improved the good leveling on the surface of cotton fabric. As per visual appearance of color difference both lemon mordanted sample dyed with tea and Teak Leaf extraction showed very even color distribution comparing to Copper Sulphate and Ferrous sulphate as per commented by present researcher team. As per dyeing theory, penetration and diffusion of the dye into the substrate is the main phenomenon to make the cotton fabric dyeing with natural coloring agent which confirmed the interaction taking place when dyes molecules like tannin and anthocyanin become absorbed by and evenly diffuse into the cotton fabric while mordanted with lemon containing with citric acid. So it may be confirmed that there was an equilibrium reaction of chemistry in dyeing reaction with good crosslinking and showed the balanced chemistry among organic dye-fiber-mordent's. The tea containing tannin and anthocyanin in teak leaf as the main colorant species to produce different shade with different natural and synthetic mordents' like Lemon containing Citric Acid, CuSO_4 and FeSO_4 . Lower ΔE values were found when treated with lemon mordanting both dyeing with Teak leaf and Neem leaf comparing to synthetic mordanting with Copper Sulphate and Ferrous Sulphate. For fastness properties of Teak leaf with lemon mordanting like color fastness to rubbing > Light fastness > color fastness to wash wherever better fastness were showed for synthetic mordanting, but for dyeing of Neem with lemon mordanting showed very attractive fastness considering to all parameters studied in this research work as well as an attempt had been made to approach of developing antibacterial finish also and the antibacterial testing of neem and lemon mordanted sample resulted killing of bacteria successfully where e-coli bacteria was trialed for the exceptional antibacterial property of organic mordanted sample.

[Comparison of (Table 1 & 2) indicates the color parameters for dyeing with Teak leaves and tea leaves on cotton fabric have been showed in Annex (Table 1) and Comparison of (Table 2 & 4) indicates the fastness properties of Teak leaves and Tea leaves on cotton fabric have been showed in Annex (Table 2)]

Treatments	Color Parameters				
	Da*	Db*	Dc*	DE	K/S value
Bleached untreated cotton	-	-	-	-	0.89
Treated fabric with Only Teak	10.01	11.25	14.02	5.17	1.2
Treated fabric with Teak Leaf & lemon	12.01	8.72	13.20	4.18	3.90
Treated fabric with Teak Leaf & CuSO ₄	1.02	15.63	15.63	6.98	2.80
Treated fabric with Teak Leaf & FeSO ₄	9.43	13.67	14.79	6.87	4.00

Table 1: Color Parameters for dyeing with Teak Leaves on cotton Fabric.

The color parameters of spectrophotometer tabulated in result table shows in graph that Da* Db* Dc* and DE have been presented here in comparison to bleached cotton fabric and proved that deeper shade was produced for organic mordanted sample and ecofriendly inorganic and metallic mordanted sample comparing to Copper sulphate modanted sample. Similarly, higher K/S value showed for organic lemon and ferrous sulphate mordanting than copper sulphate mordanted sample.

Figure 1: Color parameter, Da*.

Figure 2: Color parameter, Db*.

Figure 3: Color parameter, Dc*.

Figure 4: Color parameter, DE.

Figure 5: Color parameter, K/S Value.

Treatments	Color fastness to wash	Light fastness	Color fastness to Rubbing	
			Dry	Wet
Treated fabric with Only Teak Leaf	3	4	4	3
Treated fabric with Teak leaf & lemon	3-4	4	4	3
Treated fabric with Teak Leaf & CuSO ₄	3-4	4	3	2-3

Treated fabric with Teak Leaf & FeSO ₄	3-4	4	4	3
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Table 2: Fastness properties for dyeing with Teak Leaves on cotton fabric.

Fastness Properties for Dyeing with Teak Leaves on Cotton Fabric

The mordanted samples with Lemon and Ferrous Sulphate were confirmed less color difference, enhanced rubbing fastness under both crocking conditions in dry and wet, moderate to excellent color fastness to wash comparing to Copper Sulphate mordanting as well as almost no color change in light fastness property also observed when no mordanting agent was used with teak leaf due to having superior sustainability of remaining coloring agent in teak leaf i.e. anthocyanin pigments in teak leaf which is directly accelerating the establishment of present work to apply teak leaf as natural coloring agent. For Teak leaf the color fastness to wash tabulated in the result table shows in graph that the mordanted sample teak leaves with FeSO₄ and treated fabric have provided good color fastness and unmordanted sample only teak and teak with lemon have provided medium color fastness.

Figure 6: Color fastness to wash.

Figure 7: Color fastness to light.

Figure 8: Color fastness to rubbing (Dry).

Figure 9: Color fastness to rubbing (wet).

Color Parameters for Dyeing with Neem Leaves on Cotton Fabric

The color parameter to spectrophotometer tabulated in result table shows in graph that Da* Db* Dc* and DE have been presented here in comparison to bleached cotton fabric and proved that deeper shade was produced for organic mordanted sample and ecofriendly inorganic and metallic mordanted sample comparing to Copper sulphate mordanted sample. Similarly, higher K/S value showed for lemon and ferrous sulphate mordanting with having minor differences than copper sulphate mordanted sample.

Treatments	Color Parameters				
	Da*	Db*	Dc*	DE	K/S value
Bleached untreated cotton	-	-	-		0.89
Treated fabric with Only Neem	-0.63	14.37	14.38	4.57	1.99

Treated fabric with Neem & lemon	-1.04	9.92	9.98	3.00	4.00
Treated fabric with Neem & CuSO ₄	-4.66	20.26	20.75	8.10	4.50
Treated fabric with Neem & FeSO ₄	-3.23	15.35	18.27	6.00	4.20

Table 3: Color Parameters for dyeing with Neem Leaves on cotton Fabric.

Figure 12: Color parameter, Dc*.

Figure 13: Color parameter, DE.

Figure 14: Color parameter, K/S Value.

Figure 10: Color parameter, Da*.

Fastness Properties for Dyeing with Neem Leaves on Cotton Fabric

The colorfastness to sunlight tabulated in result table shows that the unmordanted sample, only Neem, Neem with Lemon samples exhibited better fastness than other mordanted samples to sunlight exposure. The Lemon mordanted samples was the best with little color change. Some mordanted samples dyed with Neem extract after with CuSO₄ Mordanting also showed good color fastness to Uv light.

Figure 11: Color parameter, Db*.

Treatment	Color fastness to wash	Light fastness	Color fastness to Rubbing	
			Dry	Wet
Treated fabric with Only Neem	2	4	4	3
Treated fabric with Neem and lemon	3	4	4	3

Treated fabric with Neem and CuSO_4	3	4	4	2
Treated fabric with Neem and FeSO_4	3	3	3	2

Table 4: Fastness properties for dyeing with Neem Leaves on cotton fabric.

Figure 15: color fastness to wash.

Figure 16: Color fastness to light.

Figure 17: Color fastness to rubbing (dry).

Figure 18: Color fastness to rubbing (wet).

Anti-bacterial Testing of Dyed and Finished Cotton Fabric with Neem and Lemon Mordating

Anti-bacterial testing of cotton fabric dyed and finished with Neem and Lemon had been tested in Bangladesh Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (BCSIR). In this testing, E-coli bacteria were applied on dyed and finished cotton fabric. After effective times, the E-coli bacteria were absent. From this testing result, we can say that this dyed and finished cotton fabric is anti-bacterial. So, natural dyeing and finishing with Neem and Lemon will be anti-bacterial.

41

Conclusions

Results of measurement of colour parameters showed that lower ΔE values are obtained when treated with lemon mordanting agent for both the case of dyeing cum finishing treatment with extract of Teak leaf and Neem leaf (though amongst the two dye extract used, Neem leaf extract showed higher K/S value) as compared to conventional mordanting with Copper Sulphate.

Ferrous Sulphate render moderate K/S value than all other mordants due to inherent own colour of iron in FeSO_4 . Comparing lemon mordanting with conventional copper sulphate mordant, colour fastness properties of teak leaf extract with lemon mordanting are found to be better and is in the order of Rubbing Fastness > colour fastness to Light > colour fastness to wash than that for synthetic CuSO_4 mordanting,

For dyeing with extract of neem leaf with lemon mordanting showed very attractive all round colour fastness properties studied here.

For the newer approach of natural dyeing cum simultaneous antibacterial finish the antibacterial properties of neem leaf extract dyed cotton using lemon mordanted sample resulted better reduction/ killing of bacteria.

Thus, the present work has led to development of a process of simultaneous dyeing and finishing with natural mordents (lemon juice) and natural dye (Neem leaf extract) to make the fabric colour full and anti-bacterial too.

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Non-toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric using Non-toxic Colorant and Non-toxic Crosslinker

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Abstract

A toxicity free cotton fabric coloration and antibacterial technique was developed where natural colorant curcumin and tannin were applied for instigating a substitute of toxic colorant. Considering the negative impacts of man-made dyes in environment, non-toxic coloring and sterile finishing was carried out with curcumin and tannin as non-toxic colorant quintessence from pure natural sources of *Curcuma longa* (Turmeric) and *Camellia sinensis* (Tea Leaf) using environment friendly lemon extracted (Natural Citric acid) solution as natural mordant and their color shading and functional outcomes were evaluated in variety of shades as compared with colour yield/outcomes with ferrous sulphate and copper sulphate as two most extensively practiced conventional chemical mordants. Critical performances of mordanted and unmordanted cotton fabric samples were tested for their color parameters like Colour Strength, K/S value and Colour fastness (color fastness to Washing, UV- Light and Rubbing) properties, besides measurement of other colour interaction parameters (L^* , a^* , b^* and ΔE) as well as anti-bacterial performance as Per AATCC-100-2012 method. The dye absorption determined by color spectrophotometer showed higher color strength when treated with curcumin and tannin colorant in the presence of natural extracted citric acid from lemon as toxic free mordanting agent compared to mordanting with Ferrous sulphate as well as conventional mordanting with Copper Sulphate. Higher rubbing fastness was observed for both dyeing with Turmeric and Tea Leaves when mordanting with lemon and ferrous sulphate. Curcumin demonstrates a pharmacological properties that curcumin found effective against *E. coli* bacteria in laboratory experiment well as FTIR study of Turmeric with lemon mordanted sample was confirmed the natural crosslinking among cotton fibre cellulose, turmeric curcumin and lemon-citric acid. Consequently, this work has led to development of a process of concurrent natural dyeing and finishing with natural extracted agents on cotton with natural mordants to make the fabric colour full and anti-bacterial also. If the present work is trailed commercially to make it feasible, undoubtedly present finding of research may be an exceptional source of eco-garments production which has a higher demand in local and foreign customer.

44

Keywords: Natural dyeing and finishing; Mordanting; *Curcuma longa* (Turmeric); *Camellia sinensis* (Tea Leaf)

Introduction

Environmental scientists and textile engineers concerns have been a great demand to have a pure concentration in green chemistry as the present panorama of environment is being a great threatening for the synthetic based dyeing and finishing and its negative impacts have been a great challenge both for the producers and consumers of textile sector as well as finding an alternative way has become a novel foundation of research for the scientist corner in home and abroad as everyone of human being want to get pleasure from his life. Present research works on toxic-free dyeing and finishing may impact directly to fulfil the demand of green chemistry as on-toxic dyes and mordants have been established to make coloration of cotton fabric because of the environment-friendly dyes and mordants can be reproduced again and again without hampering the environment which may vibrate the green eco-system of nature.

Chemical Structure of Tannin

Chemical Structure of Curcumin

Natural dyes like *Acacia*, *Catechu*, *Kerria lacca*, *Quercus infectoria*, *Rubia cordifolia* and *Rumex maritimus* were tested against common pathogens *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*,

Proteus vulgaris and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Quercus infectoria* dye was effective and showed maximum zone of inhibition thereby indicating best antimicrobial activities against all the microbes tested [1]. Experimental trailing was executed by a variety of the most commonly used mordants, namely potassium aluminium sulfate, copper(II) sulfate, iron(II) sulfate, and tin(II) chloride, were used for mordanting of cotton fabrics in order to compare the differently mordanted and unmordanted dyed fabrics' color efficiencies (K/S) and CIE L 'a' b' color values. It was found that mordant type had an effect on color efficiency and the color coordinates of fabrics dyed with both thyme and pomegranate fruit peel. Moreover, the antimicrobial properties of the fabrics dyed directly with thyme and pomegranate peel without any mordanting process were determined to demonstrate the usability of these natural dye sources without use of any mordanting agents. The obtained antimicrobial activities were compared with undyed samples. Undyed samples showed no antimicrobial activity,

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whereas significant antimicrobial activity was obtained after the dyeing procedure using thyme and pomegranate peel on unmordanted fabrics. Washing, rubbing, perspiration, and light fastness properties of dyed fabrics were also evaluated. Thyme and pomegranate fruit peel as natural dye sources revealed sufficient results even for un-mordanted samples [2]. A special method named Sonication in conjunction with metal mordanting has shown marked improvement in terms of dye adherence and fastness properties and can thus be recommended for industrial application [3]. Natural dyeing on textile substance using Annatto seed extract and the antimicrobial property of the ex-traced dye samples is studied by using Gram positive and Gram negative culture and provided constructive results [4]. Natural dyeing from the Acacia family, in the presence of a controlled amount of chitosan resulted in darker shades and imparted chitosan imparted excellent antibacterial properties to the cotton fabric [5]. Natural coloration of textiles from Acacia plant family with different mordanting showed acceptable fastness in shades [6].

Natural dyes selected from *Indigofera tinctoria*, *Mallotus philippinensis*, *Curcuma tinctoria* and *Lawsonia inermis* and assessed by measuring the colour strength (K/S) values of dyed samples using UV spectrophotometer where various fastness properties (wash, light and rub) of the dyed samples have been evaluated [7]. A natural colourant of Marigold flower (*Tagetes erecta*) was applied on 100% cotton utilized as mordants, cross linkers, finishing agents and experimentation had better colour fastness and enviable K/S value of cotton [8]. Natural dyeing with Chitosan pretreatment was effective to eliminate the difference in dye uptake between soybean and cotton fibers and antimicrobial activity was imparted [9].

Curcuma dye was investigated in the chitosan microspheres released from the chitosan through an adsorption process [10]. Natural dyeing with tamarind leaves as natural mordant was also investigated experimentally [11]. Natural dyeing with Kamala natural and found color depth with good fastness properties [12]. Natural dyeing of cationized cotton fabrics with the extractable solution of chicken feather using colouring matter extracted from acacia bark showed good color fastness [13]. Natural dyeing with extracted pea-nut pod powder with mordanting agents (Alum, Copper Sulphate and Ferrous Sulphate) and fast-ness properties were observed [14]. Natural dyes can be extracted from plant -leaves, roots and barks, insect secretions, and minerals which may create very minor side effect to environment [15]. Fresh Aloe Vera (*Aloe barbadensis*) could be used on cotton with the help of different mordants to produce different colours varying from yellow, pink, khaki to brown [16]. Natural biocides can be applied on textiles as natural antimicrobial agents [17]. Natural dyeing with roots of Ratanjot (*Onosma echinoides*) was applied on textile substance with different mordanting and found good fast-ness properties [18].

The timber industry releases considerable amount of wastes which contain natural dyes. Such wastes could serve as sources for the extraction of natural dyes for textile dyeing operations [19]. Natural dyeing with Callistemon citrinus plant applied on cotton textiles and found good light fastness, rub fastness and wash fastness in fabrics mordanted with ferrous sulphate [20]. In natural coloration of nontoxicity, Tannins are used in the dyestuff industry as cationic dyes (tannin dyes) [21]. All dyed fabrics acquired admirable rubbing as well as washing fastness, and the relevant dyeing mechanism has been analysed [22]. Natural dyes extracted from different types of microorganisms as well as various parts of the plants that contain coloring materials such as tannin, flavonoids and quinonoids [23]. Ethanolic dye extracts of Acacia eburnea (L.f.) Willd was dyed to the bleached cotton fabrics

were dyed with different chemical mordants using pre-mordanting, post-mordanting and simultaneous-mordanting method. In this method post mordanting of ferrous sulphate compound gave good K/S -value than others. The dyed fabrics showed good washing, light, rubbing fastness and perspiration fastness proper-ties. Antimicrobial activities of the dye extract were also studied [24].

Materials Used

Following material mentioned in below table is used during experiment (Table 1).

Experimental Works

Colorant preparation of curcumin and tannin

Green Turmeric was cut into very small pieces by knife and colorant extracted with automatic grinding, boiling and filtration method and pre-prepared 2.5% stock solution of turmeric for natural coloration on cotton fabric. Similarly Green Tea leaves was extracted with grinding, boiling and filtration to prepare 2.5% stock solution of Tannin colorant although several stock solution was trailed to find an optimum percentage of colorant solution.

Stock solution preparation of different mordants

Fresh Green lemon was cut and squeezed by manual pressure machine and after filtration got a clear ready solution for dye bath application as natural mordanting agent. 5% FeSO₄ and CuSO₄ solution was prepared with heating and boiling process with 700°C for 30 minutes where distilled water was used.

Dyeing with curcumin extracted from green turmeric

5 gm cotton fabric was dyed with cur-cumin solution extracted from Turmeric at 70 to 75°C temperature for 30 minutes by keeping a material and liquor ratio: 1:5 under open bath stirring condition while several ratio was also trailed to observe the penetration of color.

Dyeing with turmeric solution and different mordants

5 gm cotton fabric was dyed with cur-cumin solution extracted from Turmeric and (added 10% of total solution in dye bath) lemon, FeSO₄ and CuSO₄ solution at 70 to 75°C temperature for 30 minutes by keeping a material and liquor ratio: 1:5 under open bath stirring condition while several ratio was also experimented to observe the penetration of color.

Dyeing with tannin extracted from tea leaves

5 gm cotton fabric was dyed with Tannin solution extracted from Green Tea Leaves at 70 to 75°C temperature for 30 minutes by keeping a material and liquor ratio: 1:5 under open bath stirring condition while

Materials	Sources
Cotton Fabric: GSM 150 (Scoured & Bleached)	From Local Markert, India and also from Alim Knit Bd Ltd., Kashimpur, Gagipur, Bangladesh
FeSO ₄ , CuSO ₄ (For Comparison) Distilled water	E Marc –India and also from Mother trade International Mirpur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Green Lemon	Vegetable Garden, Ashulia, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
Green Tumeric	Vegetable Garden, At IIT Kanpur and also from Ashulia, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
Green Tea Leaf	Tree Garden at IIT-Kanpur and also from Ashulia, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Table 1: Material used for trialing works during experimentation.

several ratio was also monitored to maintain the optimum percentage of color penetration.

Dyeing with Tannin solution and different mordants: 5 gm cotton fabric was dyed with Tannin solution extracted from Tea Leaves and (added 10% of total solution in dye bath) lemon, FeSO₄ and CuSO₄ solution at (70 to 75)°C temperature for 30 minutes by keeping a material and liquor ratio: 1:5 under open bath stirring condition while several ratio was also assessment to observe the color penetration.

Testing Methods

- Color strength (K/S value)

Testing method: The K/S values were calculated by Kubelka Munk equation.

$$K/S = (1-R)^2 / 2R$$

Where, R is the light reflectance of the dyed samples at max. K is the absorption coefficient and S is the scattering coefficient.

Machine type: Macbeth Spectrophotometer

- Color fastness to light

Testing method: AATCC TM16

Machine type: Q-SUN XE-2 Xenon Test chamber against.

- Colour Fastness to washing

Testing method: ISO-I

Machine type: launder-o meter

- Color fastness to Rubbing

Testing method: ISO 105-X12:2001(E)

Testing type: Dry or wet rubbing

- Antimicrobial Testing

Testing method: AATCC-100-2012 method

Results and Discussion

Spectrophotometer analysis of natural colorant curcumin treated fabric showed higher color deposition and distribution on the surface of cotton fabric as curcumin (C₂₁H₂₀O₆) colorant structure is responsible to react with cellulosic structured cotton fabric, but k/s value was found double in case of lemon mordanting with curcumin comparing to FeSO₄ and CuSO₄ mordanting. Color parameters like Da*, Db*, Dc* are also deeply analysed for curcumin colorant where deeper color absorption was found for dyeing with curcumin and lemon mordanting and DE value was also similar comparing with FeSO₄ and CuSO₄ mordanting.

Spectrophotometer analysis of natural colorant Tannin treated fabric showed higher color deposition and distribution on the surface of cotton fabric as Tannin has OH group is conscientious to react with OH group of cellulosic structured cotton fabric, but k/s value was also found better having a very minor difference comparing to FeSO₄ and CuSO₄ mordanting. Color parameters like Da*, Db*, Dc* were also deeply analysed for Tannin colorant where deeper color absorption was found for dyeing with Tannin and lemon mordanting and DE value was also lower and almost similar comparing with FeSO₄ and CuSO₄ mordanting.

FTIR study of Turmeric with lemon mordanted sample was confirmed the natural crosslinking among cotton fibre-cellulose, turmeric-curcumin and lemon-citric acid.

Higher rubbing fastness was observed for both dyeing with Turmeric and Tea Leaves when mordanting with lemon and ferrous sulphate. Therefore, the antibacterial properties of Turmeric extracted dyed cotton fabric using lemon mordanted sample resulted better reduction/ killing of bacteria. Consequently, this work has led to development of a process of simultaneous natural dyeing and finishing with natural extracted agents on cotton with natural mordants to make the fabric non-toxic coloration and antiseptic also.

Color parameters for dyeing with turmeric on cotton fabric

Higher K/S value showed for the sample when treated with lemon mordanting and other color parameters to spectrophotometer marked in graph that the mordanted and unmordanted both samples (turmeric and turmeric with lemon) color parameters Da*, Db*, Dc* and DE always better color exhibited than mordanted samples (turmeric with CuSO₄ and FeSO₄) (Figures 1-5 and Table 2).

Fastness properties for dyeing with Turmeric on cotton fabric: Dyeing with Turmeric, the color fastness to wash marked in graph that the treated sample with mordanting with lemon and ferrous sulphate showed improved wash and light fast-ness comparing to synthetic and conventional Copper sulphate mordanting as well as very excellent rubbing fastness were showed both mordanting with lemon and ferrous sulphate comparing to copper sulphate (Table 3 and Figures 6-9).

46

Figure 1: Analysis of Color parameter: Da*.

Figure 2: Analysis of Color parameter: Db*.

Figure 3: Analysis of Color parameter: Dc*.

Figure 4: Analysis of Color parameter: DE.

Figure 5: Analysis of color strength, K/S value.

Treatments	Color Parameters				K/S value
	Da*	Db*	Dc*	DE	
Bleached untreated cotton	-	-	-	-	0.98
Treated fabric with Only Turmeric	13.50	73.02	74.12	13.04	2.00
Treated fabric with Turmeric & lemon	7.22	79.20	79.47	11.43	4.10
Treated fabric with Turmeric & CuSO ₄	5.63	71.53	71.70	9.75	2.90
Treated fabric with Turmeric & FeSO ₄	9.55	70.11	70.43	10.22	4.00

Table 2: Color parameters for dyeing with turmeric on cotton fabric.

Treatments	Analysis of Color fastness to wash	Light fastness	Color fastness to Rubbing	
			Dry	Wet
Treated fabric with Only Turmeric	2	3	3	2
Treated fabric with Turmeric & lemon	2-3	2	4	2
Treated fabric with Turmeric & CuSO ₄	3-4	4	4	3
Treated fabric with Turmeric & FeSO ₄	2-3	3	4	3

Table 3: Color fastness properties for dyeing with turmeric on cotton fabric.

Figure 6: Analysis of color fastness to wash.

Figure 7: Color fastness to light.

Figure 8: Analysis of Color Fastness to Rubbing (Dry).

Color parameters for dyeing of tea leaves on cotton fabric

Higher K/S value showed for the sample when treated with lemon mordanting and other color parameters to spectrophotometer marked in graph that the mordanted and unmordanted both samples (turmeric and turmeric with lemon) color parameter Da* Db* Dc* and DE* always better color exhibited than mordanted samples (turmeric with CuSO₄ and FeSO₄) (Table 4 and Figures 10-14).

Figure 9: Analysis of Color Fastness to Rubbing (wet).

Figure 12: Analysis of Color parameter: Dc*.

Treatments	Color Parameters				K/S value
	Da*	Db*	Dc*	DE	
Bleached untreated cotton	-	-	-	-	0.89
Treated fabric with Only Tea	11.55	23.09	25.29	8.97	1.25
Treated fabric with Tea Leaves & lemon	8.53	22.91	24.11	7.41	3.65
Treated fabric with Tea Leaves & CuSO4	7.57	15.02	16.32	7.18	2.80
Treated fabric with Tea Leaves & FeSO4	9.65	19.32	20.33	7.11	4.00

Table 4: Color parameters for dyeing of tea leaves on cotton fabric.

Figure 13: Analysis of Color parameter: DE.

48

Figure 10: Analysis of Color parameter: Da*.

Figure 14: Analysis of color Strength K/S value.

Figure 11: Analysis of Color parameter: Db*.

Fastness properties for dyeing with tea leaves on cotton fabric

For the treatment with Tea Leaves, the color fastness to wash marked in graph that the treated sample with natural mordanting, lemon and synthetic mordanting, ferrous sulphate showed improved wash fastness comparing to conventional copper sulphate mordanting as well as very excellent light and rubbing fastness showed both mordanting with lemon and ferrous sulphate comparing to copper sulphate (Table 5 and Figures 15-18).

FTIR study of natural colored cotton fabric

Fourier Transform Infra-Red (FTIR) graphical analysis for natural colored cotton fabric showed an interaction among Cellulose-Curcumin-Citric Acid and it was clearly focused a curve that is given below. In this graph, the acquaintance of cotton fabric with Turmeric-curcumin-Lemon is good (Figure 19).

Treatments	Analysis of Color fastness to wash	Light fastness	Color fastness to Rubbing	
			Dry	Wet
Treated fabric with Only Tea Leaves	2	4	4	3
Treated fabric with Tea leaves & lemon	2-3	4	4	3
Treated fabric with Tea Leaves & CuSO ₄	4	4	4	3
Treated fabric with Tea Leaves & FeSO ₄	3	4	4	3

Table 5: Color fastness properties for dyeing with Tea Leaves on cotton Fabric.

Figure 15: Analysis of Color Fastness to Wash.

Figure 16: Analysis of Color Fastness to light.

Figure 17: Analysis of Color Fastness to Rubbing (Dry).

Antibacterial Testing of natural colored Cotton Fabric: Curcumin demonstrates pharmacological properties that elements of curcumin colorant found effective against *E. coli* bacteria in laboratory experiment. Anti-bacterial testing of cotton fabric dyed and finished with Turmeric and Lemon had been tested in Bangladesh Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (BCSIR). In this testing, *E. coli* bacteria were applied on dyed and finished cotton fabric. After effective times, the *E. coli* bacteria were absent.

Figure 18: Analysis of Color Fastness to Rubbing (wet).

Figure 19: FTIR analysis for natural colored cotton fabric for Curcumin and Lemon.

Conclusion

Improved K/S values were investigated for both samples dyeing with curcumin and tannin colorant while mordanting with lemon comparing ferrous sulphate and copper sulphate mordanting. Curcumin and lemon dyed sample showed anti-bacterial under lab trailing of killing *E. coli* bacteria within a specific time interval which may spark the acceptance of customer requirements. Dyes and mordants concentration may influence the overall performance of dyeing and finishing. Public advertisement may increase to highlight the benefits of natural dyeing and finishing comparing toxicity of synthetic dyes used in modern manufacturing plant. In this work, there is scope to do future scientific study for green chemistry and have ample opportunities to be commercialized, if it can be confirmed same stringent standards of performance that can be applied instead of synthetic dyes.

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Pollution Free Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted from *Swietenia macrophylla* and *Musa Acuminata* as Unpolluted Dyes and *Citrus. Limon (L.)* as Unpolluted Mordanting Agent

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Abstract

Present research on pollution free dyeing and mordanting is indicated as a creative innovation of textile coloration on cotton fabric in which natural dyes were extracted from *Swietenia macrophylla* (Mahogany leaf) and *Musa acuminata* (Green Banana Pill) as an unpolluted dyes and *Citrus. limon (L.)* juice was applied as an unpolluted natural mordanting agent. There is no synthetic chemical was used during the whole progression in dyes extraction process and dyeing method. Both the treated and untreated fabric samples were tested for their dyeing performance in terms of color strength, K/S value and color fastness properties like color fastness to washing, rubbing and light. Higher K/S value of lemon mordanted sample was investigated by analysis of spectrophotometer for both dyeing with mahogany and green banana pill. Color fastness to washing and rubbing had been found moderately good for both dyeing with mahogany leaves and green banana pill with lemon mordanting. Moderately good color fastness to light had been found for dyeing with only mahogany leaves and green banana pill but improved light fastness was found for green banana pill with lemon mordanting. As per visual appearance, dyed fabric with green banana pill and lemon mordanting was found very even distribution of color on the surface of cotton fabric. An exceptionally attractive soft hand fell and color shading outcome was observed for dyeing with green banana pill comparing to mahogany leaves without having any additional application of synthetic softener which is the demand of both local and foreign customers in clothing industries.

Keywords: Natural dyeing; Natural mordanting; Mahogany leaf; Green banana pill; Lemon

Introduction

Textile materials are colored for value addition, looks and fulfilling the desires of customers. Textile industries are highly concentrated to synthetic dyes due to having availability as well as desired shade matching capability, but synthetic dyes are highly polluting the environment which has become an alarming issue for the scientist concerns of textile and environment engineering. So, natural dyes can be a permanent replacement for the development of pollution free concepts of dyeing and finishing. Anciently, this purpose of coloring textile was initiated using natural source, until synthetic dyes were invented in 1856. Natural dyes are dyes or colorants that are derived from plants, animals, insects and minerals. Most of natural dyes are prepared from dye bearing plants - leaves, stem, barks, seeds, flowers, roots etc. There are many trees in the Northeast Bangladesh, which can be used as the major sources of natural dyes. For example, *Swietenia macrophylla*, *Diospyros malabarica*, *Musa acuminata* etc. Natural dye has a great demand in the international market. Dyeing extracted from *Swietenia macrophylla* (Mahogany leaf) and *Musa acuminata* (Green banana pill) are not available in the brief study of literature review.

Due to the current economic and environmental consciousness, research in this front should be tilted towards the use of natural dyes for dyeing textile materials. Today, people around the globe are rediscovering color through the use of renewable and non-toxic natural sources. For successful commercial use of natural dyes for any particular fibers, the appropriate scientific standardized techniques/procedures are to be derived. Thus, relevant scientific studies and its output on standardization of dyeing methods, dyeing process variables, dyeing kinetics and test of compatibility of selective natural dyes and natural mordant have become very important. Lemon juice, Tamarind is also selected as the most important natural mordant to standardize the dyeing effect.

Growing consciousness for eco-friendly textile products has caused more interest on cotton fibre based natural dyeing and finishing. Productions of synthetic dyes are dependent on the petrochemical source and some of the synthetic dyes contain toxic/carcinogenic amines and are not eco-friendly. Contrary to this, most of the natural dyes as well as natural finish with few exceptions

are based on vegetable/animal origin and are renewable, biodegradable, energy-efficient and eco-friendly [1,2]. Single and binary mixtures of aqueous extracts of red sandalwood (RSW) with aqueous extract of other natural dyes like manjistha (M), jackfruit wood (JFW), marigold (MG), sappan wood (SW) and babool (BL) in different proportions are applied on bleached jute fabric for its dyeing after double pre-mordanted with myrobolan and aluminium sulphate applied in sequence under optimised conditions of mordanting with effects of use of different proportions of binary mixture of selective natural dyes on colour strength and other colour where good fastness properties were observed [3]. Bleached cotton fabric (after sequential pre-mordanting with myrobolan and then with aluminum sulfate applied in sequence) had been dyed with a pre-fixed concentration of purified binary mixtures of jackfruit wood (JFW) and other natural dyes, like manjistha (M), red sandalwood (RSW), marigold (MG), sappan wood (SW) and babool (BL) in different proportions to obtain a variety of compound shades wherever color strength (K/S values), washing and color fastness properties were improved [4]. Natural extracted dyes, manjistha was applied on cotton fabric and observed the improvement of wash and light fastness properties [5]. Myobolan (Harda) and metallic salts (Potash alum and aluminium sulphate) as mordants and aqueous extract of Tesu (Palash flower petals) as dyeing agent was used and found improved wash and light fastness [6]. Myrobolan (harda) and other mordants (metallic salts) followed by dyeing with aqueous extract of Jackfruit and found good color fastness properties [7].

Yasashri Ranganath studied that Bark of *Swietenia macrophylla* (Mahogany) is a valuable natural dye source for textile. 1% alkaline solution was used for the extraction of the dye from the finely crushed bark at 90 Celcius. Optimum dye extraction was obtained at 2 hours and optimum on weight goods (owg) ratio for extraction was 1:6. Usually a salt of Al, Fe, Cr, Cu, or Ti has to be used as the mordant to enhance the affinity of the nature dye to the fabric. In order to test the best mordant for this dye, 4% on weigh fiber (owf) solution of $Al_2(SO_4)_3$, $MgCl_2$, $FeSO_4$ were applied. $MgCl_2$ showed the best uniform dyeing, thus it was used as the optimized mordant for dyeing experiments. Adsorption of extracted mahogany dye to the cotton fabric and adsorption capacities are significantly affected by pH, initial dye concentration and temperature of the dye bath. In the current study the dye bath was maintained at pH=10 and temperature at 90 Celcius for 2 hours and 1:50 metal to liquor ratio of the mordant was used. Amount of dye adsorption reached to the saturation when dye concentration was at 200ppm. Dye adsorption data at 90 Celcius were analyzed using Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms and CIELab colour values was measured [8].

Rakesh Kumar & YC [9] Tripathi studied that atharveda carries description of natural dyes. Bhrigu Samhita was written about using natural dyes. Colour formed a basis to the various economic activities. Kautilya's Arthasastra dating back to 298 BC bears account of durations (days) allowed for various types of colouration and wages to be provided to the then professional artisans. Archaeological evidences shows that the dyeing was a widespread

industrial enterprise in Egypt, Indiana and Mesopotamia around third millennium BC. The art of dyeing was as old as human civilization. From the historical records it is learnt that natural colorants were available to people during Greco-Roman periods [9].

Prabhu & Aniket [10] deliberated that natural dyes, which were pushed during the last sixty years into the background by synthetic dyes, are recently again becoming object of consumer interests. This is due to the awareness of possible risks during production of synthetic dyes which involve use of petrochemical based raw materials and the violent chemical reactions for their synthesis. The manufacture of such dyes is energy intensive with adverse impact on environment adding to its pollution. Many of these dyes, especially the azo - based ones, are found to be carcinogenic. In this background, a brief review of natural colourant from plant sources, their classification, chemical constituents responsible for producing different colours, its activities and effect of different mordants on the hue is discussed. Different classes of mordants employed for fixation of natural colouration on textiles substrated, its mechanism and plant sources are also discussed [10].

Narayana & Gowda [11] studied that eco-friendly natural dye extracted from *Swietenia mahogany* leaves, has been used as eco-friendly dye to cotton and silk fabrics. The dyeing was carried out with and without the use of mordants and the fastness properties of the fabrics were determined. Colour values in terms of K/S and $L^* a^* b^* C$ and h colour coordinates were examined. A wide range of shades were obtained by using various mordants and mordanting techniques. Dye was tested for some eco-parameters using atomic absorption spectrophotometry and GC/MS. The effluent disposed at the end of the processing was also tested in some cases. The test results were compared with set standards to determine the eco-friendliness of natural dye, show that their concentrations are much below the stipulated limits [11].

Kumaresan [12] found that Fastness properties of the flower of *Spathodea campanulata* and *Cordia sebestena* dyed cotton fabric have been studied using different combination (1:3,1:1 and 3:1) of various mordants, such as myrobolan: nickel sulphate, myrobolan: aluminium sulphate, myrobolan: potassium dichromate, myrobolan: ferrous sulphate and myrobolan: stannous chloride. The wash, rubbing, light and perspiration fastness of the dyed samples have been evaluated. Comparing the fastness properties and colour strength of flower of *Spathodea campanulata* and *Cordia sebestena* dyed cotton by using combination of mordants. In the comparative study of fastness properties and colour strength of the dyed cotton samples *Spathodea campanulata* in simultaneous mordanting method with 1:3 mordant combinations gives better results than using flower of *Cordia sebestena* [12].

Ploysai Ohama, Nattida Tumpat confirmed that Natural dye extracted from *Caesalpinia sappan linn* was applied to a cotton fabric and silk yarn by dyeing process. The dyestuff component of *Caesalpinia sappan linn*. was extracted using water and ethanol. Analytical studies such as UV-VIS spectrophotometry and gravimetric analysis were performed on the extracts. Brazilein, the

major dyestuff component of *Caesalpinia sappan linn* was confirmed in both aqueous and ethanolic extracts by UV-VIS spectrum. The color of each dyed material was investigated in terms of the CIELAB (L^* , a^* and b^*) and K/S values. Cotton fabric dyed without mordant had a shade of reddish-brown, while those post-mordanted with aluminum potassium sulfate, ferrous sulfate and copper sulfate produced a variety of wine red to dark purple color shades. Cotton fabric and silk yarn dyeing was studied using aluminum potassium sulfate as a mordant. The observed color strength was enhanced with increase in mordant concentration [13].

Kartick & Basak S [14] studied that agro-waste, nanolignin, silk sericin and aloe vera have been successfully extracted and applied in textile substrates to protect its user from the harmful ultraviolet (UV) rays. The above natural ingredients and a few more from marigold, manjistha, annatto, neem, turmeric, sandalwood, tulasi, jasmine, lemon, lavender and sandalwood have also been explored for natural dyeing, UV protective, aroma and antimicrobial finishing of textile [14]. Sudipta & Subhas [15] was investigated that screen printing on cotton fabric using Cochineal natural dye in the presence of stannous chloride as the mordant. It was found that, the dye recipe using 6% Cochineal pigment in water-based solvent, where the fabric was soaked in the heated stannous chloride mordant for an hour and cured at 160 °C for 3min, produced the best screen print on 100% cotton fabric in terms of appearance and color wash fastness [15].

Mohammad & Felix [16] studied on natural dyed samples and conducted with several tests like wash fastness, rubbing fastness, light fastness and K/S value. Comparison also done among water extracted dyed samples and organic solvent (Methanol) extracted dyed samples and all the results came up with good results [16]. Jixian et al. [17] was found that the superior dyeing effect of cotton fabric was achieved by adjusting the dye bath pH. When the pH was

three, dyed cotton under 90 °C for 60min exhibited the greatest color strength with good rubbing, washing and perspiration color fastness [17]. Jyoti & Prerna [18] attempted made to extract natural dyes from a variety of plants sources (such as rhizomes of turmeric, *Curcuma longa*; fruits of harda, *Terminalia chebula*; petals of safflower, *Carthamus tinctorius*; roots of barberry, *Berberis lycium* etc.) using specific techniques. These dyes were tested for their dyeing potential on different textile materials (cotton, silk and wool). Dyeing was done using three different dyeing techniques (pre-, simultaneous- and post-mordanting) wherein different mordants such as alum, copper sulphate and ferrous sulphate etc., were used to fix dye on to the textile material. A rainbow of natural dyes was obtained with varied shades of each colour. Shade cards were prepared for each dye and the colour obtained varied depending on the type of the mordant applied and the mordanting technique used [18].

Smita & Nabaneeta [19] reviewed of interest in the use of natural dye in textile colouring is due to the stringent environmental standard imposed by many European countries in response to the toxic and allergic reaction associated with synthetic dyes. Germany was the first to take initiative to put ban on numerous specific azo-dyes for their manufacturing and applications. Netherlands, India and some other countries also followed the ban. Varieties of colour, shades from vibrant jewel tones to dusky heathers and pastels can be obtain from different sources [19]. Anowar & Samanta [20] was experimented and found that dyeing with green gaub fruit, color fastness to wash and rubbing=very excellent, color fastness to light=good and for dyeing with green tea leaf, color fastness to wash=very excellent, color fastness to rubbing=excellent, color fastness to light=good. An improved color strength, K/S value had been found for both dyeing with green gaub fruit and green tea leaf while mordanting was applied with green lemon juice [20] (Table 1).

54

Table 1: Materials used for experimental works.

Sl. No	Materials Name	Source
1.	Knitted Fabric: GSM 150 (Scoured & Bleached)	Apparel Village, khagan, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
2.	<i>Swietenia macrophylla</i> (Mahogany leaf), as natural dyeing agent	From the Garden, Ashulia, Khagan, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
3.	<i>Musa acuminata</i> (Green Banana Pill), as natural dyeing agent	Vegetable Garden Ashulia, Khagan, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
4.	Lemon as natural mordanting agent	Vegetable Garden Ashulia, Khagan, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
5.	Distilled Water	Mother Trade International Mirpur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Method Used for Experimental Works

Dyeing of cotton fabric with mahogany leaves and no mordanting in dye bath

Extraction process of mahogany leaves: Collected fresh Mahogany leaf from garden and smashed it and weighted 2gm powder by electronic balance. After that we took 98cc water and heated up to 80 °C for 40min. Then we filtered the total solution of powder by very fine mesh fabric and got the dye solution.

Dyeing process: Dyed the specific fabric with 5gm weight in 70 °C for 30min by keeping the material and liquor ratio: 1:6. Then we dyed the total fabric. Temperature checked by thermometer and finished with padding and drying method.

Dyeing of cotton fabric with mahogany leaves and lemon mordanting in dye bath

Green Lemon juice was extracted manually and lemon juice (15% of total solution i.e mahogany leaf extraction) was added.

After that we dyed the specific fabric with 5gm weight in 70 °C for 30min. Then we dyed the total fabric by keeping the material and liquor ratio: 1:6. Temperature checked by thermometer and finished with padding and drying method.

Dyeing of cotton fabric with green banana pill and no mordanting in dye bath

Green banana pill extraction process: First collected green banana from bazar and made into small split by knife and weighted 30gm by electronic balance. After that we took 70cc water and heated up to 80 °C for 40min. Then filtered the total solution of banana split and got the dye solution.

Dyeing process: Dyed the specific fabric with 5 gm weight in 70 °C for 30min by keeping material and liquor ratio: 1:6. Then dyed the total fabric. Temperature checked by thermometer and finished with padding and drying method.

Dyeing of cotton fabric with green banana pill and lemon mordanting in dye bath

Green Lemon juice was extracted manually and lemon juice (15% of total solution i.e banana pill extraction) was added. After that we dyed the specific fabric with 5gm weight in 70 °C for 30min by keeping the liquor ratio: 1:6. Then dyed the total fabric in similar way. Temperature checked by thermometer and finished with padding and drying method.

Methods used for different testing in research works

Color fastness to wash: was tested ISO 105-A05, Textiles Tests for color fastness - Part A05: Instrumental assessment of change in color for determination of grey scale rating with Launder-o-Meter.

Color fastness to light: was tested by AATCC TM16 in Q-SUN XE-2 Xenon test chamber against blue wool standards (BS -1006-B01-1978).

Color fastness to Rubbing: was tested ISO 105-X12:2001(E) which finger and force were used in the test. Whether dry or wet rubbing was performed along with the percentage of soak the

numerical rating for staining for each test specimen. The staining of the cotton rubbing cloths with the grey scale for staining 4.4 under suitable illumination.

Color strength (K/S value): was measured by measuring surface reflectance value where Computer color measuring instrument (Macbeth 2020 plus spectrophotometer). Color strength of untreated and treated cotton fabric samples is measured from the reflectance value at maximum wave length from which surface color strength (K/S value) can be determined by Kubelka-Munk equation:

$$\frac{K}{S_{\lambda_{\max}}} = \frac{(1 - R_{\lambda_{\max}})^2}{2R_{\lambda_{\max}}} = \alpha C_D$$

Where, K = coefficient of absorption

S = coefficient of scattering

$R_{\lambda_{\max}}$ = reflectance of the substrate at maximum absorbance wavelength

CD = concentration of dye

Results & Discussions

Natural dyeing on cotton fabric extracted from *Swietenia macrophylla* (Mahogany leaf), *Musa acuminata* (Banana Pill) with natural mordanting agent wherever both the treated and untreated fabric samples were tested for their dyeing performance in terms of color fastness properties (color fastness to washing and rubbing, light fastness). Color fastness to wash and rubbing had been found moderately good for dyeing with mahogany and lemon juice but moderately good color fastness to light had been found for dyeing with only mahogany without lemon juice as well as color fastness to wash, color fastness to rubbing was found moderately good and color fastness to light had found excellent for dyeing with green banana pill and lemon juice in addition to very attractive soft hand feel was observed by the researcher which one was dyed with green banana pill (Table 2).

Table 2: Assessments of color fastness parameters for dyeing with mahogany leaves and green banana pill.

Treatment	Color Fastness to Wash	Light Fastness	Color Fastness to Rubbing	
			Dry	Wet
Treated fabric with only Mahogany	3	3	3	2
Treated fabric with Mahogany & Lemon	4	2	4	3
Treated fabric with Only Banana Pill	3	2	3	2-3
Treated fabric with Banana Pill & Lemon	4	3	4-5	4

Color fastness to wash

For Mahogany, the color fastness to wash tabulated and showed in graph that the mordanted sample showed better color fastness. It has been investigated that naturally mehgony has good color fastness due to its natural chemistry i.e presence of ferrous. For

green banana pill, the color fastness to wash tabulated and showed in graph that the mordanted sample showed better color fastness. It has been investigated that naturally green banana pill has good color fastness due to its natural chemistry i.e presence of natural pigment (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Color fastness to wash.

Color fastness to light

Exceptional result had been remarked as the graph showing that treated fabric with only mahogany have better light fastness comparing to mordanted sample. In the presence of citric acid, color is slightly faded due to having ferrous and other compositional

contents in mahogany leaves. For banana pill, the colorfastness to light tabulated in table and graphical representation showed that the mordanted sample is better than an unmordanted fabric, but treated fabric with only banana pill had found good color fastness to light (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Color fastness to light.

Color fastness to rubbing

For both mahogany and banana pill, rubbing fastness from table and graph, it can be understood that the mordanted samples

exhibited better rubbing fastness under dry and wet conditions. The mordanted samples had good fastness under both crocking conditions (Figure 3 & 4; Table 3).

Table 3: Comparison of K/S value between mahogany leaves and green banana pill dyed fabric.

Sl. No	Treatments	K/S Value
1.	Untreated fabric	0.122
2.	Dyed fabric with Mahogany	1.90
3.	Dyed fabric with Mahogany and lemon as mordanting agent	2.34
4.	Dyed fabric with Green Banana Pill	1.20
5.	Dyed fabric with Green Banana Pill and lemon as mordanting agent	1.60

Figure 3: Color fastness to rubbing (dry).

Figure 4: Color fastness to rubbing (wet).

Color strength, K/S

From graphical demonstration of color strength measurement, it has been clearly confirmed that K/S value of mordanted sample was increased for both of dyeing with mahogany and green banana pill. As per compositional overview, Mahogany leaf contains

Ferrous which is responsible for making color and Banana pill has coloring pigment for making color which parameters are effecting to get higher k/s value for both dyeing. It can be also noted that crosslinking in both dye bath reaction is increasing due to presence of citric acid in lemon (Figure 5 & 6).

Figure 5: Color strength, K/S value of dyed fabric with mahogany leaves.

Figure 6: Color strength, K/S value of dyed fabric with green banana pill.

Conclusion

For both dyeing with mahogany leaves and green banana pill was found higher k/s value with lemon mordanting and moderate to excellent color fastness to washing and rubbing. Color fastness to light was found good for dyeing with only mahogany and banana pill

as well as improved color fastness to light was observed for green banana pill with lemon mordanted sample. Moderate to excellent fastness was found for rubbing, wash and light like color fastness to rubbing>Color fastness to wash>Color fastness to light. This new findings of present research can be considered for the practice of almost 100% ecofriendly dyeing of cotton fabric without having any

negative impact on environment due to 0% application of synthetic dyes and mordanting. So this research work may be accepted by the scientist as presently environment pollution of textile dyeing and finishing has become the major thinking matter of both scientist concern of textile engineering and environmental engineering. Furthermore chemical structure analysis of all extracted solution of mahogany, green banana pill and lemon can be studied deeply and if it can be matched accurately the related study and research can be purely established in the field of natural dyeing considering more fastness and K/S value which may be invented as ecofriendly dyeing of textile engineering. This research work can fulfill the versatile color demand as per customer discussed in literature review.

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59

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Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent

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Abstract

A combined green dyeing and mordanting method was applied on cotton fabric in which natural coloring agents were extracted from Diospyros malabarica (Green Gaub fruit) and Camellia sinensis (Green Tea Leaf) wherever green lemon juice had been used as green mordanting agent and there is no artificial chemical was used during demodulation process of coloring agent, dyeing and mordanting. Both the treated and untreated fabric samples were tested for their mechanical properties (color fastness to washing and rubbing) and dyeing performance in terms of color fastness properties (light fastness) and color strength, K/S value. For dyeing with green gaub fruit, color fastness to wash and rubbing = Very excellent, color fastness to light = good and for dyeing with green tea leaf, color fastness to wash= very excellent, color fastness to rubbing = excellent, color fastness to light = good. An improved color strength, K/S value had been found for both dyeing with green gaub fruit and green tea leaf while mordanting was applied with green lemon juice.

Abbreviations: RSW: Red Sandal Wood; MJ: Manjistha; JFW: Jack Fruit Wood; MG: Mari Gold; SW: Sappan Wood; BL: Babool; OWG: Optimum on Weight Goods; OWF: On Weigh Fiber

Introduction

Natural dyes are being called as green dyes which can be prepared from natural dye bearing plants like leaves, stem, barks, seeds, flowers, roots etc collected from completely natural sources and have no negative effect to environment as well as no harmful for the aquatic life. There are many trees available in Bangladesh and India which can be used as the major sources of natural dyes. For example: (green gaub fruit), Diospyros malabarica (green gaub fruit), Camellia sinensis (green tea leaf) etc. Natural dye has a great demand in the national and international market due to increasing rate of conscious person related to health and environment. Due to the current economic and environmental consciousness, research in this front should be titled towards the use of natural dyes for dyeing textile materials. Today, people around the globe are rediscovering color through the use of renewable and non-toxic natural sources. For successful commercial use of natural dyes

for any particular fibers, the appropriate scientific standardized techniques/procedures are to be derived. Thus, relevant scientific studies and its output on standardization of dyeing methods, dyeing process variables, dyeing kinetics and test of compatibility of selective natural dyes and natural mordant have become very important. Lemon juice, Tamarind is also selected as the most important natural mordant to standardize the dyeing effect.

Literature Review

Growing consciousness for eco-friendly textile products has caused more interest on cotton fiber based natural dyeing and finishing. Productions of synthetic dyes are dependent on the petrochemical source and some of the synthetic dyes contain toxic/carcinogenic amines and are not eco-friendly. Contrary to this, most of the natural dyes as well as natural finish with few exceptions are based on vegetable/ animal origin and are renewable,

biodegradable, energy-efficient and eco-friendly [1,2]. Single and binary mixtures of aqueous extracts of red sandalwood (RSW) with aqueous extract of other natural dyes like manjistha (M), jackfruit wood (JFW), marigold (MG), sappan wood (SW) and babool (BL) in different proportions are applied on bleached jute fabric for its dyeing after double pre-mordanted with myrobolan and aluminum sulphate applied in sequence under optimized conditions of mordanting with effects of use of different proportions of binary mixture of selective natural dyes on colour strength and other colour where good fastness properties were observed [3]. Bleached cotton fabric (after sequential pre-mordanting with myrobolan and then with aluminum sulfate applied in sequence) had been dyed with a pre-fixed concentration of purified binary mixtures of jackfruit wood (JFW) and other natural dyes, like manjistha (M), red sandalwood (RSW), Marie gold (MG), sappan wood (SW) and babool (BL) in different proportions to obtain a variety of compound shades wherever color strength (K/S values), washing and color fastness properties were improved [4].

Natural extracted dyes, manjistha was applied on cotton fabric and observed the improvement of wash and light fastness properties [5]. Myobolan (Harda) and metallic salts (Potash alum and aluminum sulphate) as mordents and aqueous extract of Tesu (Palash flower petals) as dyeing agent was used and found improved wash and light fastness [6]. Myrobolan (harda) and other mordents (metallic salts) followed by dyeing with aqueous extract of Jackfruit and found good color fastness properties [7]. Yasashri Ranganath Bark of Swietenia macrophylla (Mahogany) is a valuable natural dye source for textile. 1% alkaline solution was used for the extraction of the dye from the finely crushed bark at 90 Celcius. Optimum dye extraction was obtained at 2 hours and optimum on weight goods (OWG) ratio for extraction was 1:6. Usually a salt of Al, Fe, Cr, Cu, or Ti has to be used as the mordant to enhance the affinity of the nature dye to the fabric. In order to test the best mordant for this dye, 4% on weigh fiber (OWF) solution of $Al_2(SO_4)_3$, $MgCl_2$, $FeSO_4$ were applied. $MgCl_2$ showed the best uniform dyeing, thus it was used as the optimized mordant for dyeing experiments. Adsorption of extracted mahogany dye to the cotton fabric and adsorption capacities are significantly affected by pH, initial dye concentration and temperature of the dye bath. In the current study the dye bath was maintained at pH=10 and temperature at 90 Celcius for 2 hours and 1:50 metal to liquor ratio of the mordant was used. Amount of dye adsorption reached to the saturation when dye concentration was at 200ppm.

Dye adsorption data at 90 Celcius were analyzed using Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms and CIE Lab colour values was measured [8]. Rakesh Kumar and YC Tripathi were studied Atharveda carries description of natural dyes. Bhrigu Samhita is written using natural dyes. Colour formed a basis to the various economic activities. Kautilya's Arthashastra dating back to 298 BC bears account of durations (days) allowed for various types of colouration and wages

to be provided to the then professional artisans. Archaeological evidences shows that the dyeing was a widespread industrial enterprise in Egypt, Indiana and Mesopotamia around third millennium BC. The art of dyeing was as old as human civilization. From the historical records it is learnt that natural colorants were available to people during Greco-Roman periods [9]. KH Prabhu* and Aniket S Bhute were studied that Natural dyes, which were pushed during the last sixty years into the background by synthetic dyes, are recently again becoming object of consumer interests. This is due to the awareness of possible risks during production of synthetic dyes which involve use of petrochemical based raw materials and the violent chemical reactions for their synthesis. The manufacture of such dyes is energy intensive with adverse impact on environment adding to its pollution. Many of these dyes, especially the azo- based ones, are found to be carcinogenic. In this background, a brief review of natural colourant from plant sources, their classification, chemical constituents responsible for producing different colours, its activities and effect of different mordents on the hue is discussed. Different classes of mordents employed for fixation of natural colouration on textiles substrate, its mechanism and plant sources are also discussed [10].

V Narayana Swamy, Ninge Gowda K N were studied that Eco-friendly natural dye extracted from Swietenia mahogany leaves, has been used as eco-friendly dye to cotton and silk fabrics. The dyeing was carried out with and without the use of mordents and the fastness properties of the fabrics were determined. Colour values in terms of K/S and $L^* a^* b^* C$ and h colour coordinates were examined. A wide range of shades were obtained by using various mordents and mordanting techniques. Dye was tested for some eco-parameters using atomic absorption spectrophotometer and GC/MS. The effluent disposed at the end of the processing was also tested in some cases. The test results were compared with set standards to determine the eco-friendliness of natural dye, show that their concentrations are much below the stipulated limits. Narayana Swamy*, K.N. Ninge Gowda and R. Sudhakar were studied that extracted from Swietenia mahogany leaves, has been used as eco-friendly dye to cotton and silk fabrics. The dyeing was carried out with and without the use of mordents and the fastness properties of the fabrics were determined. Colour values in terms of K/S and $L^* a^* b^* C$ and h colour coordinates were examined. A wide range of shades were obtained by using various mordents and mordanting techniques. Dye was tested for some eco-parameters using atomic absorption spectrophotometer and GC/MS. The effluent disposed at the end of the processing was also tested in some cases. The test results were compared with set standards to determine the eco-friendliness of natural dye, show that their concentrations are much below the stipulated limits [11].

M. Kumaresan Fastness properties of the flower of Spathodea campanulata and Cordia sebestena dyed cotton fabric have been studied using different combination (1:3,1:1 and 3:1) of various

mordents, such as myrobolan: nickel sulphate, myrobolan: aluminum sulphate, myrobolan: potassium dichromate, myrobolan: ferrous sulphate and myrobolan: stannous chloride. The wash, rub, light and perspiration fastness of the dyed samples have been evaluated. Comparing the fastness properties and colour strength of flower of *Spathodea campanulata* and *Cordia sebestena* dyed cotton by using combination of mordents. In the comparative study of fastness properties and colour strength of the dyed cotton samples *Spathodea campanulata* in simultaneous mordanting method with 1: 3 mordant combinations gives better results than using flower of *Cordia sebestena* [12]. Ploysai Ohama, Nattida Tumpat were studied that Natural dye extracted from *Caesalpinia sappan* Linn was applied to a cotton fabric and silk yarn by dyeing process. The dyestuff component of *Caesalpinia sappan* Linn was extracted using water and ethanol. Analytical studies such as UV-VIS spectrophotometer and gravimetric analysis were performed on the extracts. Brazilein, the major dyestuff component of *Caesalpinia sappan* Linn was confirmed in both aqueous and ethanolic extracts by UV-VIS spectrum. The color of each dyed material was investigated in terms of the CIELAB (L^* , a^* and b^*) and K/S values. Cotton fabric dyed without mordant had a shade of reddish-brown, while those post-mordanted with aluminum potassium sulfate, ferrous sulfate and copper sulfate produced a variety of wine red to dark purple color shades. Cotton fabric and silk yarn dyeing was studied using aluminum potassium sulfate as a mordant. The observed color strength was enhanced with increase in mordant concentration [13].

Materials and Experimental Works

Materials Used

Table 1.

SL. NO	Materials Name	Source
1.	Knitted Fabric: GSM 150 (Scoured & Bleached)	Apparel Village, khagan, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
2.	<i>Diospyros malabarica</i> (Gaub Fruit)	From the Garden of Ashulia, Khagan, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
3.	<i>Camellia sinensis</i> (Tea Leaf)	Tea Garden, Sylhet, Bangladesh
4.	Lemon	Vegetable Garden Ashulia, Khagan, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
5.	Distilled Water	Mother trade International Mirpur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Experiment 01: First we collected Gaub Fruit from garden and split by knife and took 2.13gm. After that we took 100cc water and heated up to 70 0c for 30 min. Then we filtered the total solution of Gaub fruit and got the dye solution. After that we dyed the specific fabric with 1.72gm weight in 700c for 30 min. Then we dyed the

total fabric. Temperature checked by thermometer and finished with padding and drying method (Table 1).

Dyeing and Finishing with Natural Dyes Extracted from Gaub Fruit:

Diospyros malabarica 2.13gm
 ↓
 Distilled water (100cc)
 ↓
 Heat (70 0c×30min)
 ↓
 Filtering with very fine meshed fabric
 ↓
 Add Fabric 1.72gm
 ↓
 Dyeing
 ↓
 (700c×30min)
 ↓
 Padding and natural Drying

63

Experiment 02: First we collected Gaub Fruit from garden and split by knife and smashed it. We got 6gm powder. After that we took 200cc water and heated up to 70 0c for 30min. Then we filtered the total solution of Gaub fruit and got the dye solution. Then we added 45cc green lemon juice. After that we dyed the specific fabric with 10gm weight in 70 0c for 30min. Then we dyed the total fabric. Temperature checked by thermometer and finished with padding and drying method.

Combined Dyeing with Natural Dyes Extracted from *Diospyros Malabarica* and Natural Mordanting Agent Extracted from Green Lemon:

Diospyros malabarica 6gm
 ↓
 Distilled water (200cc)
 ↓
 Heat (70 0c×30min)
 ↓
 Filtering with very fine meshed fabric
 ↓

Experiment 03: First we collected Tea Leaf from bazaar and took 5gm. weight. After that we took 200cc water and heated up to 70 0c for 30 min. Then we filtered the total solution of tea leaf and got the dye solution. After that we dyed the specific fabric with 10gm weight in 70 0c for 30min. Then we dyed the total fabric. Temperature checked by thermometer and finished with padding and drying method.

Dyeing with Natural Dyes Extracted from Tea Leaf and Natural Mordanting Agent Extracted from Green Lemon:

Experiment 04: First we collected Tea Leaf from bazaar and took 5gm. weight. After that we took 200cc water and heated up to 70 0c for 30 min. Then we filtered the total solution of tea leaf and got the dye solution. After that we dyed the specific fabric with 10gm weight in 70 0c for 30 min. Then we dyed the total fabric. Temperature checked by thermometer and finished with padding and drying method.

Testing Methods

Color fastness to wash was tested ISO 105-A05, Textiles - Tests for color fastness - Part A05: Instrumental assessment of change in color for determination of grey scale rating with Launder-o-Meter.

Dyeing with Natural Dyes Extracted from Green Tea Leaf and Natural Mordanting Agent Extracted from Green Lemon:

Testing Methods

- a) Color fastness to wash was tested ISO 105-A05, Textiles - Tests for color fastness - Part A05: Instrumental assessment of change in color for determination of grey scale rating with Launder-o-Meter.
- b) Light fastness to wash was tested by AATCC TM16 in Q-SUN XE-2 Xenon Test chamber against blue wool standards (BS -1006-B01-1978).
- c) Color fastness to Rubbing was tested ISO 105-X12:2001(E) which finger and force were used in the test. Whether dry or wet rubbing was performed along with the percentage of soak the numerical rating for staining for each test specimen. The staining of the cotton rubbing cloths with the grey scale for staining 4.4 under suitable illumination.
- d) Color strength (K/S value) was measured by measuring surface reflectance value where Computer color measuring

instrument (Macbeth 2020 plus spectrophotometer). Color strength of untreated and treated cotton fabric samples is measured from the reflectance value at maximum wave length from which surface color strength (K/S value) can be determined by Kubelka-Munk equation:

$$K/S = \frac{(1 - R_{\lambda \max})}{2R_{\lambda \max}} \alpha C_D$$

Where, K = coefficient of absorption, S = coefficient of scattering.

$R_{\lambda \max}$ = reflectance of the substrate at maximum absorbance wavelength.

C_D = concentration of dye.

Result & Discussion

Diospyros malabarica (Green Gaub fruit) and *Camellia sinensis* (Green Tea Leaf) were extracted wherever green lemon juice had been used as green mordanting agent. Both the treated

and untreated fabric samples were tested for their mechanical properties (color fastness to washing and rubbing) and dyeing performance in terms of color fastness properties (light fastness) and color strength, K/S value. For dyeing with green gaub fruit, color fastness to wash and rubbing = Very excellent, color fastness to light = good and for dyeing with green tea leaf, color fastness to wash = very excellent, color fastness to rubbing = excellent, color fastness to light = good. An improved color strength, K/S value had been found for both dyeing with green gaub fruit and green tea leaf while mordanting was applied with green lemon juice.

Color Fastness to Wash for Green Gaub Fruit

For Gaub, the color fastness to wash tabulated in the result table shows in graph that the mordanted sample gaub with lemon have excellent color fastness.

For Green Gaub Fruit: (Table 2) (Figure 1)

Figure 1.

Table 2.

Treatment	Color fastness to wash	Light fastness	Colour fastness to Rubbing	
			Dry	Wet
Treated fabric with Only Green Gaub	2	1-2	3	2
Treated fabric with Green Gaub & Green lemon	4	2	4-5	3

a) Color Fastness to Light: The colorfastness to light tabulated in result table shows in graph that the mordanted samples of gaub with lemon had observed good light fastness property (Figure 2).

b) Color Fastness to Rubbing: Rub Fastness from result table it can be understood that mordanted samples were better than

unmordanted samples exhibited better rub fastness under dry and wet conditions. The mordanted samples had good fastness under both crocking conditions. We can say that the mordanted samples are good color fastness to provide here in Dry and Wet conditions (Figures 3 & 4).

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Study on K/S value for Green Gaub Fruit:

Table 3.

SL. No	Treatments	K/S Value
1.	Untreated fabric	0.112
2.	Dyed fabric with Green Gaub	2.32
3.	Dyed fabric with Green Gaub and lemon as mordanting agent	3.20

Figure 5.

Improved K/S value had been found due to mordanting with lemon while extracted solution of green gaub fruit was used as natural coloring agent (Table 3) (Figure 5).

For Tea Leaf

a) Color Fastness to Wash: Mordanted sample treated with green tea leaf and lemon showed excellent color fastness to wash comparing to sample where no mordanting agent was used (Figure 6).

Figure 6.

b) Color Fastness to Light: Sample treated with green tea leaf and lemon showed excellent color fastness to light comparing to sample where no mordanting agent were used (Figure 7).

Figure 7.

c) Color Fastness to Rubbing: Rub Fastness from the result table it can be understood that samples exhibited better rub fastness under dry and wet conditions. We can say that the unmordanted and mordanted both are good color fastness to provide here in dry and wet conditions (Figures 8 & 9).

Figure 8.

Figure 9.

Improved K/S value had been found due to mordanting with lemon while extracted solution of green tea leaf was used as natural coloring agent (Tables 4 & 5) (Figure 10).

Table 4.

Treatment	Color fastness to wash	Light fastness	Color fastness to Rubbing	
			Dry	Wet
Treated fabric with Green Tea Leaf	3	2-3	3	2
Treated fabric with Green Tea Leaf & lemon	4.5	3	4	3

Table 5.

SL. No	Treatments	K/S Value
1.	Untreated fabric	0.112
2.	Dyed fabric with Green Tea Leaf	2.55
3.	Dyed fabric with Green Tea Leaf and lemon as mordanting agent	3.35

Figure 10.

Conclusion

In favor of both dyeing with green gaub fruit and green tea leaf and mordanting with green lemon have been found excellent color fastness to wash and rubbing but color fastness to light had been found slightly less which can be established with further study of chemistry based reaction in presence of light, but both dyed fabric showed improved result of color strength, k/s value with very even distribution of color on the surface of fabric which may be ascertained in the corner of green dyeing of textile substrate and it will not only influence to create the green scenario of environment but also it will highly minimize the coloration cost if it can be further studied to put into practice in industrial based dyeing under great thinking of commercialization considering all negative effect of synthetic dyeing on textile substrate and availability of green sources of natural dyes mainly in Asian country like Bangladesh and India.

67

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A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles

Anowar Hossain

Abstract

Marigold flower *Tagetes erecta* L., Arjuna Bark *Terminalia Arjuna*, Eucalyptus leaves *Eucalyptus Radiata*, Peach/Jam Leaves *Acacia acuminata*, Pecker leaves *Cinnamomum tamala*, Guava leaves *Psidium guajava*, Basil leaves *Ocimum basilicum*, Jackfruit wood *Artocarpus heterophyllus*, Catachu fruit *Senegalia Catechu*, Bohera fruit *Terminalia bellirica*, Betel nut fruit *Areca catechu*, Haritaki fruit *Terminalia chebula*, Mahogany fruit peel, Mahogany seed peel, and Mahogany seed *Swietenia macrophylla* are the common natural sources in Bangladesh, an Asian country which were experimented in terms of mordanting free natural coloration on cotton fabric under conceptual confirmation of referred journal where author has been picked the idea from the generation of available shade in his research laboratory and tested from different laboratories and it may be establish as mordant free natural dyeing for specific colorant on the basis of color fastness and shading behaviors. Fifteen standardized Ready Made Shade (RMS) has been presented with CIE color parameters, color fastness, wash fastness, and light fastness grading. A reproducing guideline for every Ready Made Shade (RMS) has been mentioned in this chapter.

70

Keywords: readymade shade (RMS), natural dyeing, eco-friendly dyes, natural extraction, mordant free dyeing

1. Introduction

A concept of readymade shade (RMS) has been developed by using numerous number of natural dyes which were collected from agri-production unit and different village sources in Bangladesh prepared and powdered in color processing unit, extracted with water solvent process, dyed and experimented the feasibility of coloration in textile chemistry laboratory to generate different hues of natural dyes after effective implementation on natural fiber based textiles which outcome of color may be beneficial for primary selection of color tone by the textile technologist of natural coloration cum customers for the decision-making of specific color tone both for product development and fashion concerns who are genuinely searching an eco-friendly dyes under the consideration of repeated hue without which the real output of natural coloration, sustainability of dyes and natural dyeing process as well as its actual production of different hue is being a challenged now as the textile technologists are habituated the essence of readymade shading behavior of synthetic dyes whereas toxicity is the main endangered for the human being.

2. Background

Environment pollution is the great challenge of color scientists in dyeing and finishing plant, so eco-friendly coloration is the key target of recent researchers and manufacturers. Natural coloration is being accepted by the environment scientist and related committee [1–3]. Researchers in the area of natural coloration have an immense intension to minimize pollution [4]. Focus on science and engineering on natural dyes based research, extractions, purifications, and implementations are rapidly climbing [5–9]. In this chapter, mordant free natural coloration and its feasibility was experimented to minimize environment pollution load which is not limited to synthetic dyeing but also natural dyeing in terms of mordant free coloration concepts for specific standardized shade. Author also experimented to establish an approach of green mordanting [10, 11] in natural coloration [12–16] although mordant [17] has an effect for the augmentation of fiber surface color and surface chemistry [18] and its appropriate affinity in terms of fastness properties [1, 19–24]. Light fastness [21–24] of natural dyed fabric is a critical issue for natural colorant if dyes sources and collection processes are not maintained accurately. There are many sources of natural colorant, using by the researcher as per availability of origin to origin in the world. Researchers are already invented and proposed like *Jatropha* flower [25], red sandal wood [26], wood of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* [27], *Acalypha* [28], areca nut [29], *Butea monosperma* [30], neem leaves [31, 32], *Gomphrena globosa* [33], *Onosmaechiodes* [34], *Nerium oleander* flower [35], Kesula flowers [36], Parijataka (*Nyctanthes Arbor*) flowers pigment [37], *Hibiscus ovalifolius* and *Sesbania aegyptiaca* [38], Bark of *Macaranga Peltata* [39], Cutch, Ratanjot and Madder [40], Mesta Calyx [41], Kapila, Onion, Tesu [42], myrobalan, gallnut, pomegranate [43], Marigold flower [44, 45], *Areca Catechu* [46], Eucalyptus leaves [47], Eucalyptus bark [48, 49], Jackfruit wood [50], Peach [51], Arjuna [52, 53], Catechu [54] and others. Developments of natural indigo shade in comparison with synthetic dyes [55] are not only prime objects for coloration but also maximum natural dyes have medicinal value [56, 57], noncarcinogenic, production-friendly, and environment-friendly. Research and development of natural dyeing on cotton, jute, and silk fabric was done by Samanta and his researchers team at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India have an technical output, research impacts and motivation for future researchers, and manufacturing unit for the contributions of dyes selection, extraction, analysis, standardization, and commercialization [58–68]. Color matching [69] and reproducing of shade is another challenging issue for the manufacturing company and colorists when natural dye is compared with synthetic dyes but there are so many colorants of natural sources that can be possible to reproduce almost nearest shade. Tolerating percentage/ acceptable range of color differences, ΔE value, and other properties can be standardized in a convincing way with local and foreign customer of any country as the real customer of any textile product is not going to sell the product after shade matching with spectrophotometer without enjoying its esthetic value, so a little bit lightness and darkness matter is not a trading challenge of dyer and manufacturing plant. Comparing to synthetic dyes, natural dyed fabric has a great market demand as the people who are concern about the intimidation of environment. Thus natural dyes have diverse applications and multi fiber based production options that are already available in literature for cotton [68], jute [66], wool [70], silk [34] based dyeing, processing in both laboratory stage and bulk production (**Figures 1–15**).

RMS of Marigold (Figure 1): Waste Marigold flowers were collected from flower garden, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

3. Standardized Ready Made Shade (RMS) of natural dyed textiles

3.1 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Marigold flower, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Marigold tree. scientific name: *Tagetes erecta*

Figure 1.
RMS of Marigold.

3.2 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Arjuna Bark, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Arjuna tree, Scientific name: *Terminalia arjuna*

Figure 2.
RMS of Arjuna Bark.

3.3 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Eucalyptus leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: scientific name: *Eucalyptus radiata*

Figure 3.
RMS of *Eucalyptus* leaves.

Coloring components Zeaxanthin and Lutein structural group of marigold flower may be responsible for good color combination has OH group may be showed good color fastness properties with cellulosic fiber. Lutein (C₄₀H₅₆O₂) and Zeaxanthin (C₄₀H₅₆O₂) molecules may prevent UV damage for its strong antioxidant properties.

RMS of Arjuna Bark (Figure 2): Dried Arjuna bark were plucked from Arjuna tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

Ferrous ion of Arjuna Bark may be influencing the L*, a*, b*, Y value for providing outcome of deeper color and OH group is responsible for good fastness properties. Arjuna bark has phytosterol, lactones, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and tannins, glycosides where tannin may be responsible for coloring agent.

RMS of Eucalyptus Leaves (Figure 3): Semi-dried leaves were plucked from Eucalyptus tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group of cellulose can easily make a bonding with dyes group of Eucalyptus. Eucalyptol is a colorless compound which is responsible for antibacterial properties but may be remaining pigment or other phytochemical compound is making color on the fabric surface.

3.4 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Pecker leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Pecker tree, scientific name: *Cinnamomum tamala*

Figure 4.
RMS of Pecker leaves.

RMS of Pecker Leaves (Figure 4): Semi-dried leaves were plucked from pecker tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group of cellulose can easily make a bonding with dyes group of Pecker leaves. Eugenol is the main constituent of antimicrobial properties and other components like pinene, camphene, and limousine may be responsible for color formation.

RMS of Guava Leaves (Figure 5): Semi-dried leaves were plucked from tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group of dyes is responsible for good color fastness properties. Mixed components of flavonoid and tannin are highly responsible for bluish color of cotton fabric. Acidic pH and phenolic compound of guava leaves may generate flammable characteristics of guava leaves colored fabric.

RMS of Basil Leaves (Figure 6): Fresh and green Basil leaves were plucked from tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

α terpineol remaining in dyes of Basil leaves may be responsible for dyeing of cotton fiber and OH group is making strong affinity with cellulose. Phytochemical constituents and medicinal properties of Tulsi leaves may create pathogen protective finish of cotton fabric like antimicrobial, COVID 19, and other viruses.

3.5 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Guava leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Guava tree, scientific name: *Psidium guajava*

Figure 5.
RMS of Guava leaves.

3.6 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Basil leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Basil tree, scientific name: *Ocimum basilicum*

Figure 6.
RMS of Basil leaves.

3.7 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Jackfruit wood, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Jackfruit tree, scientific name: *Artocarpus heterophyllus*

Figure 7.
 RMS of Jackfruit wood.

3.8 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Catechu fruit peel, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Catechu tree, scientific name: *Senegalia catechu*

Figure 8.
 RMS of Catachu fruit.

3.9 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Bohera fruit peel, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Bohera tree, scientific name: *Terminalia bellirica*

Figure 9.
RMS of Bohera fruit.

RMS of Jackfruit Wood (Figure 7): Powder of Jackfruit wood were collected from saw mill, filtered and 5 days dried with summer sun light. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

Artocarpesin and Norartocarpetin group of golden yellow color jackfruit tree wood has phenolic compounds, apigenin, curcumin may be responsible for making a yellow color having an optimum value of L^* , a^* , b^* , Y as well as OH group is improving color fastness properties.

RMS of Catachu Fruit (Figure 8): Semidried Catachu fruit were plucked from tree, washed, fruit peel were cut into small piece, 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

Catachu is making off white color with soft hand feel and may be remaining natural pigment in the chemical components is responsible for dyeing without mordanting. Coloring component in the catechu is catechin having molecular formula $C_{15}H_{14}O_6$.

RMS of Bohera Fruit (Figure 9): Bohera fruit powder was purchased from herbal medicine shop, Tongi, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

3.10 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Mahogany seed, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Mahogany tree, scientific name: *Swietenia macrophylla*

Figure 10.
 RMS of Mahogany fruit, seed.

3.11 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Mahogany fruit (outer peel), types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Mahogany tree, scientific name: *Swietenia macrophylla*

Figure 11.
 RMS of Mahogany fruit, outer peel.

3.12 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Mahogany seed (outer peel), types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Mahogany tree, scientific name: *Swietenia macrophylla*

Figure 12. RMS of Mahogany fruit, outer peel of seed.

OH group and its tannin constituent may be created a natural shading environment on the surface of cotton fiber and its medicinal properties may create the dyed fabric antimicrobial. Flavonoid and falfvins constituent of Bohera fruit may have adaptive capabilities of viruses and microorganisms.

RMS of Mahogany Fruit, Seed (Figure 10): Semi-ripped Mahogany fruits were plucked from tree, washed, seeds were separated with sharp knife, cut into small pieces and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group may be responsible for good dye-absorption and ferrous ion may be responsible for dyeing. Phytochemical constituents and other medicinal properties may have a good source protective clothing like insect repellent, antimicrobial, COVID19, and other viruses.

3.13 Natural coloration of cotton natural coloration of cotton fabric with Haritaki fruit peel, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Haritaki tree, scientific name: *Terminalia chebula*

Figure 13.
RMS of Haritaki fruit.

3.14 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Betel nut, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Betel nut tree, scientific name: *Areca catechu*

Figure 14.
RMS of Betel nut.

3.15 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Peach leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Peach leaves, scientific name: *Acacia acuminata*

Figure 15.
RMS of Peach leaves.

RMS of Mahogany Fruit, Outer peel (Figure 11): Semi-ripped Mahogany fruit were plucked from tree, washed, fruit peels were separated with sharp knife, cut into small pieces and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group and ferrous ion may be responsible for good dye-fiber bonding phytochemical constituents and other medicinal properties may have a good source protective clothing like insect repellent, antimicrobial, COVID19, and other viruses.

RMS of Mahogany Fruit, Outer peel of Seed (Figure 12): Semi-ripped Mahogany fruit were plucked from tree, washed, seed peels were separated with sharp knife, cut into small pieces and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group and ferrous ion may be responsible for good dye-fiber bonding. Phytochemical constituents and other medicinal properties may have a good source protective clothing like insect repellent, antimicrobial, COVID19, and other viruses.

RMS of Haritaki Fruit (Figure 13): Haritaki fruit powder was purchased from herbal medicine shop Tongi, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group and ferrous ion may be responsible for good dye-fiber bonding. The plant is constituted of Glucoside, Tannins, Gallic acid, Ethyl gallate, and Chebulinic acid where tannin may be responsible for coloring the cotton fiber.

RMS of Betel Nut (Figure 14): Ripe Betel nut were purchased from local village shop, separated the peels, and grinded to make it powder form. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group can create a bond between dye and fiber and remaining curcumin may be responsible for coloration and dyed fabric may be slightly flammable due to having hydroxychavicol in the chemical constituent of betel nut.

RMS of Peach Leaves (Figure 15): Semi-dried Peach leaves were plucked from Peach tree garden. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

Minimum color strength is found but fastness is lightly higher, increasing dye percentage may improve the color on the fiber surface. Remaining ferrous, copper, and zinc may be responsible for coloring the cotton fiber. As per chemical constituent, antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory can be found.

4. Method of natural fixing for mordant free dyeing

Maximum natural dyes sources from natural tree leaves, roots or fruits have ferrous ion, tannin, curcumin, catechin, OH group, and other known and unknown phytochemical constituent. Ferrous ion, tannin, curcumin, and catechin are making various color formations, and OH group is creating affinity with cellulosic fiber as well as the fastness properties may be increased if the dyes have natural pigment which may influence the capability of remaining dyes on the fiber surface after washing. Drying/curing with higher temperature may impact the color making duller or brighter. So specific dye-fiber system of natural fixing for mordant free dyeing is also possible but exact curing/drying temperature should be fixed for getting expected outcome of shading. So expected mechanism of mordant free natural coloration may be proposed as below although dyes and fiber substances may create changing of it.

82

5. Testing process

5.1 Color fastness to wash method

ISO 105-C06:2010, color fastness to water method: ISO 105-E01 and color fastness to light was tested by AATCC TM16 in Q-SUN XE-2 Xenon Test chamber.

5.2 Machine used for color parameters

Color parameters (L^* , a^* , b^* , Y) were measured by Hunter Lab Spectrophotometer, machine name: ColorFlex EZ, Model 45/0 LAV, Geometry

Figure 16.
Color Flex EZ, Spectrophotometer.

45°/0°, viewing area: large, visible spectrum (400–700 nm), testing condition: D₆₅/10°, room temperature of testing lab: 18°C (**Figure 16**).

6. Representation of dyed fabric and picture of dyes sources

All dyed shades were scanned with HUAWEI Smart Phone, Camera-13 MP, distance between fabric sample and camera position: 12–16 inch. So there is a possibility of having difference with actual shade. Picture of actual dye-fiber system was also scanned with HP Scanjet 4890 Photo Scanner. All sources of dyes pictures have been mentioned on the basis of grown trees in Asian Countries, specially in Bangladesh and scientific name was used accordingly. All the pictures of chemical structure mentioned here indicate the group of tree, not exactly indicating the chemical structure of specific parts of trees which one is extracted and dyed on cotton fabric.

6.1 Overcoming contradiction of natural dyeing

A huge number of researchers are working on natural dyes, still have a challenging for uneven dyeing, appropriate mordanting and dyes availabilities, shade matching where I can put a logic to protect our environment and human life as well.

83

6.2 Uneven dyeing

Automation in extraction and dyeing process.

6.3 Appropriate mordanting and dyes availability

Selection of specific dyes for commercial production and/or wastage can be used as dyes sources.

6.4 Shade matching

Customers are not always asking for shade matching when they are shopping although some natural dyes have attractive shading and repeated shading also possible.

7. Conclusion

Mordanting free coloration was practiced establishing the feasibility of environment friendly natural coloration which is the ongoing research of author and a part

of his research has been included here. Shade variation of natural dyed fabric may influence the uncontrollable factors for the collection of natural dyes sources on the basis of season to season, region to region and a same source but different parts of same dye sample source. So it is very tough to make a specific declaration of shading behaviors by the textile technologist but specific expertise in natural dyes extraction and natural dyeing may minimize the problem whereas expertise in dyeing with synthetic dyes and dyeing with natural dyes are not same for bulk production.

Following directions for the real shade development mentioned above:

1. Fabric should be well scoured and bleached.
2. Dyes materials should be clean, dried and powdered properly, improper drying and inappropriate powder formation may be responsible for unexpected shading and uneven dyeing.
3. Extraction time, dyes percentage may be maximized or minimized if the actual color is not observed.
4. Improper filtration of dyes may create uneven dyeing.
5. Dyes should not be powdered in wet or sticky condition which may effect the changing of light fastness and color shading.
6. Insect affected dyes source may create the changing of shade.
7. Synthetic mordanting and chemical medium dyes extraction may improve the shade but the concern of chemical and cost.
8. For open bath dyeing, liquor ratio should be higher, and stirred continuously to reduce color mark on the dyed fabric.

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Research, trialing, relevant analysis, and searching of research fund is going on (2019-)

Zero Toxic Approach of Cotton Fabric Coloration with Botanical Waste Resource via *Psidium guajava* (Guava Leaves) as Natural Dyes and *Citrus Lemon* (Lemon Leaves) as Natural Mordanting Agent

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Page | 1

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Abstract

Zero toxic approach of cotton fabric coloration with botanical waste resource *Psidium guajava* (Guava leaves) was used as natural dyes and *Citrus Lemon* (Lemon leaves) was used as natural mordanting agent for nature friendly dyeing of cotton fabric. A color combination of orange and bluish color tone was experimented for dyeing of cotton fabric both dyeing process of guava leaves (bluish tone) and guava + lemon leaves (orange tone). An improvement of color combination was remarked for dyeing of guava leaves with lemon leaves comparing with only guava leaves under considering the color parameters studied with color measurement spectrophotometer. Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectroscopy analysis proved the presence of chromophore and auxochrome group in the dyed fabric with guava leaves and lemon leaves. UV-Vis spectral scan of guava leaves extracted solution of natural dyes showed highest and broaden absorption peak at wavelength 200-300 nm due to having chromophore group.

90

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, Zero Toxic Approach of Cotton Fabric Coloration with Botanical Waste Resource via *Psidium guajava* (Guava Leaves) as Natural Dyes and *Citrus Lemon* (Lemon Leaves) as Natural Mordanting Agent; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; 31 December 2019

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD⁵ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁸ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020)

Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)¹⁻⁶

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Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)⁵; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; Fund Claimed to Australian Government; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia;

Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)⁴; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh;

Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)³; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre³; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Research product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh;

Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)²; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre²; Fund Approved by City University; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh

Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)¹; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre¹; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, 40, Kemal Ataturk Avenue, Banani, Dhaka 1213, Bangladesh

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91

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Keynote

This is a six-month duration project completion report at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh. The service charge of researcher is discounted due to the minimum approval of the research fund of 1,00,000 BDT. The service charge is also subsidized and self-invested by the chief researcher. The additional costs are claimed to the funder. The publication was circulated at the relevant departments and the relevant expert panels. The quality versus time versus fund versus outcomes

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

versus the experience of the chief researcher is proportionally run to the goal of a researcher and/or funder. This project took more time due to the part-time service with the full-time service of the chief researcher. This project had no official study leave/research leave for the chief researcher at City University when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain parallelly performed as chief researcher, consultant, textile engineer, accountant, office assistant, office secretary, and administrative director of the project on dyes and textile coloration. Reasons of the financial crisis of professor community are critically explained in the section of discussion to satisfy the support to extend the support of the relevant community. Numerous limitations of research funding, research profession, higher education quality, and relevant contradictions have been remarked and analyzed for the understanding of funding authorities, universities, and research organizations. This assessment of quality enhancement and professional guideline charge to City University, Bangladesh should be 20,000 USD or one year duration full-time salary of a senior professor in Bangladesh or one year duration full-time salary of a chief researcher in Bangladesh. Therefore, City University may show/display this report for the research fund of Bangladesh government, university grants commission of Bangladesh, board of accreditation for engineering and technical education, Bangladesh accreditation council, institutional quality assurance cell of City University, higher education quality enhancement project (HEQEP), United Nations, and central peer review purposes of the university and/or department of textile engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Outcomes and approach of professional law for the university professors/researchers

1. Every chief researcher should get a prestigious amount of salary or a minimum salary of the equivalent salary of the mother job/main salary or a percentage of salary of lecturer, assistant professor, associate professor, professor, and senior professor at any university to satisfy the research practice to satisfy the research service for the whole project duration in a research project.
2. Every income of chief researcher and relevant expenditure in a research project/research organization/university should be tax free.
3. Every chief professor and chief researcher should have a standard amount of secretary allowance if the chief professor and chief researcher have no secretary. Moreover, a secretary can not serve for the chief professor/chief researcher, when necessary, where necessary. Moreover, a chief professor/chief researcher is the self-secretary of a chief professor/chief researcher (Hossain, 2025i).
4. An international standard peer review charge of a senior professor should be 4,000 USD. This charge should be applicable for one document peer review or one manuscript peer

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁸ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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review or one time peer review. This is necessity for the financial protection of an expert professor/chief professor/senior professor/chief researcher and quality enhancement.

5. Every standard peer review of a research project should be 3:3:3:3; Three individual expert in the relevant field, three individual peer review, three individual report of three times peer review of the project, three individual times of the project; such as: first time, middle time, and ending time of the project. So, the total peer review report of a research project should be: 9. Every report/publication of a peer review should be written, signed, and displayed by the chief researcher and chief director of the project. The quality of a peer reviewer should be higher than chief researcher/chief director in a research project.
6. Every chief researcher and/or chief director of a research project should have a standard allowance of sex partner, at least one office assistant and sex partner including the national and international travel allowance of the sex partner (1:1).

Keywords

Project Completion Report, Project Fund, Chief Researcher and Founder, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

1 Letter of Proceeding

7 October 2025

Professor Mir Akhter Hossain, Registrar, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh.

registrar@cityuniversity.ac.bd

1.1 Subject of reporting to the registrar, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Submission of project completion report to the office of registrar, City University, Bangladesh; registered by Ref No-City University/Reg./9083/2019.

Dear Registrar,

The approved fund of 1,00,000 BDT on 18 November 2019 was spent under the approved research proposal at City University, Bangladesh. Office of registrar, City University should take necessary action to send the approved amount of 1,00,000 BDT or full amount of 3,99,800.24 BDT (if applicable to consider the additional costs and/or subsidized costs and/or inflation of local currency

since 2019) to the bank account of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Bank account details: Md. Anowar Hossain, savings account no: 0178 12200003933, First security Islami bank PLC, Birulia Branch, Dhaka-(Routing No: 105260808).

At the end of the project completion report, research progress has been attached and submitted to research cell, City University for the consideration of expenditure and fund transfer to the bank account of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Chief Researcher.

Table 1. a summary of approved research fund versus the additional costs versus currency inflation versus subsidized fund of chief researcher for the assessment of fund transfer to the bank account, this table is also briefly discussed and cited in tables 2 & 3

Type of approved fund/subsidized fund of chief researcher	Currency in BDT
Approved fund of City University on 18 November 2019, attached the letter of evidence	1,00,000 BDT
Approached 20% currency inflation of the approved fund since 2019 (Hossain, 2025e)	20,000 BDT
Approached total cost of chief researcher, described in table 3	1,66,500.20 BDT
Approached 20% currency inflation of the total cost of chief researcher since 2019 (Hossain, 2025e)	1,99,800.24 BDT
Approached self-subsidized/self-invested research fund of chief researcher to write the research proposal, described in table 2 (M. A. Hossain et al., 2019)	1,00,000 BDT
Approached self-subsidized/self-invested research fund of chief researcher to write the administrative report of the mini project, described in table 2	1,00,000 BDT
Approached total cost of chief researcher with self-subsidized research fund at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh	3,99,800.24 BDT

2 Approved project details at office of registrar, City University, Bangladesh; registered by Ref No-City University/Reg./9083/2019

Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded); Textile, Color & Material Research Centre²; City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia (M. A. Hossain et al., 2019) (A. Hossain, 2020) (M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018) (Hossain, Samanta, NS, et al., 2018) (Hossain, Samanta, Bhaumik, et al., 2018) (Hossain, Islam, et al., 2018) (Hossain, 2019d; M. A. Hossain, 2023br, 2023ca; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025i)

City University approved research project on “zero toxic coloration of cotton fabric with natural dyes and natural mordanting agents.” (A. Hossain, 2020; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019)

Approved duration: six months, September 2019-February 2020

Value of approved project: 1,00,000 BDT (M. A. Hossain, 2023br).

Full name of chief researcher: Md. Anowar Hossain

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Designation and department: Lecturer (Textile Technology), Department of Textile Engineering

2.1 Time of research and service rate (2019-2020)

- Started the self-funded research project since September-October 2017
- Publication of research proposal: June-July 2019
- Meetings of fund approval at City University: September 2019-October 2019
- Fund approved on: 18 November 2019
- Publication of book chapter: 10 September 2020
- Letter of withdrawal of research fund: 22 November 2021

2.2 Time of billing (2025)

Submission of project completion report to funding authority: September-October 2025

2.3 Reason of late submission of billing

Full-time PhD research at RMIT University, Australia, crisis of research time, and crisis of filing time at City University, Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023bx). This project proposal was started earlier on 18 November 2019, when the project proposal was officially peer reviewed and approved by the registrar. Accordingly; chief researcher, Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain officially responded, notified and agreed to the registrar of City University. In the acceptance letter of the research fund, chief researcher also claimed to registrar and mentioned the consideration about the additional duty hours of chief researcher. Due to the crisis of filing and reporting time, the fund was withdrawn and reserved on 22 November 2021 by the chief researcher under the response of e-mail communication of City University, Dhaka. The relevant evidence is attached to satisfy the fund transfer to the personal bank account of the chief researcher.

2.4 Bill type

Table 1-3, approved research practice and research fund at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh (A. Hossain, 2020; Hossain, Islam, et al., 2018; Hossain, Samanta, Bhaumik, et al., 2018; Hossain, Samanta, NS, et al., 2018; Hossain, 2019d; M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019).

2.5 Type of research presentation and circulation against the research fund at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Book chapter publication, 10 September 2020 (A. Hossain, 2020)

Research outcomes are simply represented to notify the broader community of researcher and public to satisfy the understanding of non-technical field of researchers, non-textile engineering field of researchers, general field of researchers, and relevant funding authority.

Table 2. Number of publications/outcomes of the mini project at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh and approached the subsidized research fund of 2,00,000 BDT to City University, figure 1-3

Sole author research publication and self-funded as chief researcher; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia	Sole author administrative publication and self-funded as chief director; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia	Sole author design and publication of research proposal and self-funded as chief researcher; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia
<p>A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles. In A. K. Samanta & N. S. Awwad (Eds.), <i>Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments</i> (pp. 151-170). IntechOpen (A. Hossain, 2020)</p>	<p>A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)</p>	<p>A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre. <i>International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering</i>, 3(1), 1-3(M. A. Hossain et al., 2019)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Approved research fund of 1,00,000 BDT ➤ Approached 20% local currency inflation of the approved fund since 2019: 20,000 BDT (Hossain, 2025e) ➤ Total cost of chief researcher in 2019-2020: 1,66,500.20 BDT ➤ Approached 20% local currency inflation of the total cost since 2019: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Approached additional service charge/administrative charge/subsidized research fund of 1,00,000 BDT to the funder (if applicable). ➤ Approached to assess the subsidized research fund to the funder (if applicable). ➤ Served in routine holiday/additional duty hours at RMIT University/City University, Australia(M. A. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Approached to assess the charge of research proposal writing (M. A. Hossain et al., 2019). ➤ Approached subsidized research fund of 1,00,000 BDT to the funder (if applicable) ➤ Served in routine holiday and additional duty hours

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<p>33,300.04 BDT (Hossain, 2025e) ➤ Total cost with 20% local currency inflation of the total cost since 2019: 1,99,800.24 BDT</p>	<p>Hossain, 2023br; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).</p>	<p>at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh(M. A. Hossain, 2023br; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x).</p>
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2.6 Service rate (2019-2020)

Service rate is merged and discounted to City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh in terms of the target fund of mini project and service of project in 2019-2020.

2.7 Yearly currency inflation since 2019

Table 3, a yearly increment of project fund may be implemented and approved in terms of the rate of currency inflation in Bangladesh since 2019 (Hossain, 2025e). A total of 20% currency inflation rate in Bangladesh is approached and added with the total approved fund and total costs of the project. Therefore, the total approved fund is increased and approached from 1,00,000 BDT to 1,20,000 BDT. Accordingly, the total cost is also increased and approached from 1,66,500.20 BDT to 1,99,800.24 BDT (if applicable by the assessor/authority)

2.8 Category of service as additional responsibility at City University

Chief researcher, director, consultant in textile technology, peer review in textile technology; figure 1-3, table 1-3.

2.9 Approached the additional service charge/compensation of this administrative article of the mini project (if applicable by the peer reviewer)

Table 1, what should be the fund value of this article of this writing of the mini project? The mini fund of funder should be the one-time grant or gift or compensation or subsidiary fund to the researcher instead of the project fund where the chief researcher needs to subsidize and/or invest. The funder or research cell of City University may assess to transfer an additional service charge/compensation of 1,00,000 BDT to the bank account of the chief researcher. The funder policy of City University may be implemented to approve the additional service charge/compensation/subsidiary to the bank account of the chief researcher.

2.10 Approached the additional service charge/compensation of research proposal writing of the mini project (if applicable by the peer reviewer)

Table 1, what should be the fund value of research proposal writing of the mini project? Funder or research cell of City University may assess to transfer an additional service charge/compensation of 1,00,000 BDT to the bank account of the chief researcher. The funding policy of City University may be implemented to approve the additional service charge/compensation to the bank account of the chief researcher.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

2.11 Limitations of research and development as chief researcher, City University

- ✓ Limitation of trialing, limitation of testing, limitation of investigation, limitation of time, limitation of fund crisis of chief researcher at Textile, Color & Material Research Centre at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
- ✓ Double duty of theory teaching as lecturer, and research activities as chief researcher at City University, but single salary of teaching (theory) as lecturer, and research activities as chief researcher at City University.

Page | 8

2.12 Limitations of external peer review to represent the project completion report to the funding authority

- The core responsibilities of chief researcher of the project and outcomes of the research project was peer reviewed by the relevant expert in textile technology. Number of experts in textile technology in the peer review process in the publication process: 01, figure 1-3, table 1-3.
- The responsibilities of chief director of the research project, office secretary, administrative duty, project explanation, administrative segment, and the section of relevant discussion were not peer reviewed due to the financial crisis of the mini project and project completion report, figure 1-3, table 1-3.
- The responsibilities of account expert, billing and costs, financial proposal, and financial explanation were not peer reviewed by the relevant chartered accountant due to the financial crisis of the mini project, and project completion report, figure 1-3, table 1-3.
- The responsibilities of legal explanation were not peer reviewed by the relevant lawyer/barrister due to the financial crisis of the mini project, and project completion report, figure 1-3, table 1-3.

98

2.13 Communication, peer review, and verification of the mini project

If necessary, every communication of auditing/reviewing should have a full copy of this report of expenditure, research proposal, and publications/outcomes of the research project. Every document and relevant discussion of the chief researcher of this project has been attached for the auditing/peer review purposes of the funding authority, expert panels, legal reviews, and relevant peer reviews for the extension of the research fund at City University and/or government of Bangladesh and/or foreign authorities.

2.14 Limitation of the billing and filing to the funder of mini project at City University

1. Evidences of individual and unit costs, and relevant bank statements were not maintained and attached due to the limitation of the stuff/office assistant/secretary of the project due to the limitation of fund crisis of the mini project at City University, Bangladesh.

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Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵
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International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
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 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva

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 Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- Meeting costs of chief researcher with funder and unit fund receiving also minimized due to the fund crisis of mini project. Although chief researcher had five administrative meetings with the funding authority to approve the research fund of 1,00,000 BDT.
- Chief researcher is approaching the extra costs of meetings and legal reviews with the funder if it is necessary to satisfy the billing and reporting. Any extra costs and/or additional reports of the mini project should be implemented/offered as the approached grade of senior professor (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025g).

2.15 Function of registrar, City University, Bangladesh

City University should record a printed copy and a pdf file of this report for the future reference of City University and chief researcher, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.

Table 3. Service rate and total billing of project under the approved and registered research proposal at City University, Bangladesh; figure 1-3

Name and contact	Designation/ service type	Description of billing	Service rate/ service charge/ acknowledged/mentioned through publication
Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com ; Mobile: +8801788396264	Chief Researcher (Textile Technology)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Research team meeting, settling research proposal (M. A. Hossain et al., 2019), foreign tour from Bangladesh to India for face-to-face meeting, conveyance (from 5 November 2017 to 9 November 2017), VISA processing, food and refreshment, telephonic communication, e-mail communication. ➤ Routine holiday and casual leave for a foreign tour. ➤ Specialized consultant in textile technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 0 BDT ➤ Planned and started with self-funding at Textile, Color & Material Research Centre at City University, Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain et al., 2019) (A. Hossain, 2020) (M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018) (Hossain, Samanta, NS, et al., 2018) (Hossain, Samanta, Bhaumik, et al., 2018) (Hossain, Islam, et al., 2018) (Hossain, 2019d; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x) ➤ Self-paid, self-invested, and fully excluded from the approved fund at City University ➤ Acknowledged/

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Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Routine holiday at City University under the roster duty ➤ Reading research articles ➤ Research trialings ➤ Hence, writing research proposal and self-subsidized and/or self-invested the fund of 1,00,000 BDT, figure 2 (M. A. Hossain et al., 2019) 	mentioned to City University Bangladesh; Jahangirnagar University, Bangladesh; University of Calcutta, India.
Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com ; Mobile: +8801788396264	Chief researcher (Textile Technology)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Research planning, research thinking, material management, research trialing, and relevant administrative duty ➤ Routine holiday at City University under the roster duty ➤ Specialized consultant in textile technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 0 BDT ➤ Self-invested ➤ Self-paid, self-invested, and fully excluded from the approved fund at City University
Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com ; Mobile: +8801788396264	Chief researcher (Textile Technology)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Physically searched national experts at national organizations, such as: Professor's office at Bangladesh Textile University, scientist's office at Bangladesh Jute Research Institute, and scientist's office at Bangladesh Jute Corporation ➤ Conveyance and travel food 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 2,500 BDT

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**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

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 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
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 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Transport type: public/uber/other ➤ Three official days of routine holidays under the roster duty at City University 	
<p>Professor Dr. AK Samanta, Former Head of the Department, Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India E-mail: ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com Mobile Phone: +919831161529</p>	<p>Foreign consultant (Textile Technology)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Research team meeting, foreign tour from India to Bangladesh for face-to-face meeting (15, 16, 17 December 2019)(Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024y), car rent of two and half days, two days residential hotel, refreshment/travel food, telephonic communication, e-mail communication. ➤ Peer review service (research proposal stage) ➤ Expert review in natural dyes ➤ Meeting and routine holiday allowance of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain ➤ Foreign expert was included and approved in the project proposal ➤ Specialized consultant in textile technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 34,000 BDT (self-paid) ➤ Acknowledged to University of Calcutta, India.
<p>Professor Dr. Md. Nurul Absar, Former Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University (JU), Bangladesh</p>	<p>National consultant (Chemistry)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Research team meeting and refreshment ➤ Discussion about the research proposal (M. A. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 2,000 BDT (self-paid) ➤ Acknowledged to Jahangirnagar University, Bangladesh.

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<p>E-mail: abserju@yahoo.com, Mobile Phone: +880-1818459321</p> <p>Members of research laboratory: Ms. Taslima, MPhil researcher, JU Mr. Robbani, PhD researcher, JU</p>		<p>Hossain et al., 2019)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discussion about the laboratory ➤ Adaptation with the laboratory and researcher ➤ Routine holiday at City University ➤ Conveyance ➤ Sourcing and planning machine for laboratory ➤ Machine learning and trialing at analytical laboratory 	
<p>Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264</p>	<p>Chief researcher: Research proposal at City University</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Ten official days of routine weekly holidays at City University under the roster duty at City University. ➤ Specialized consultant in textile technology ➤ Writing research proposal and editing for the grant approval at City University ➤ Edition of research proposal under the comments of the funder at research cell, City University. ➤ Self-review and self-revision ➤ Self-supervision 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 16,666.70 BDT (self-paid) ➤ Standard daily charge of lecturer (research) category salary (50,000-60,000 BDT) in Bangladeshi University (1666.67) + 20% additional charge of additional duty allowance (excluded from the approved fund) ➤ Although Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was qualified as associate professor in 2019-2020 (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025g) ➤ Acknowledged to City University, Bangladesh.
<p>Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264</p>	<p>Chief researcher (Textile Technology)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Waiver of 100% publication charge of book chapter (A. Hossain, 2020) ➤ Waiver of 560 GBP (attached evidence) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 0 BDT ➤ Scholarly negotiated with the publisher for free of cost publication due to fund crisis of researcher

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 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
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Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

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<p>Professor Dr. AK Samanta, Former Head of the Department, Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India E-mail: ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com Mobile Phone: +919831161529</p>	<p>Foreign consultant (Textile Technology)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Peer review service for publication Expert review in natural dyes Specialized consultant in textile technology E-mail communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 10,000 BDT (non-paid) Acknowledged to University of Calcutta, India.
<p>Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264</p>	<p>Chief researcher: Research test</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hunter Lab Spectrophotometer, machine name: ColorFlex EZ Additional work hours and holidays at RMIT University (subsidized fund by chief researcher and self-invested by the chief researcher) (M. A. Hossain, 2023cf). Specialized consultant in textile technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0 BDT Acknowledged to City University, Bangladesh; and RMIT University, Australia.
<p>Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264</p>	<p>Chief researcher: Research analysis</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ten official days of routine weekly holidays/additional hours at City University/RMIT University Specialized consultant in textile technology Self-review Self-supervision 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 16,666.70 BDT (self-paid); Standard daily charge of lecturer (research) category monthly salary in Bangladeshi Universities (50,000-60,000 BDT) + 20% additional charge of additional duty allowance (excluded from the approved fund)

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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Although Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was qualified as associate professor in 2019-2020(Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025g) ➤ Acknowledged to City University, Bangladesh.
<p>Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264</p>	<p>Chief researcher: Manuscript planning and preparation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Thirty official days of routine weekly holidays under the roster duty at City University ➤ Specialized consultant in textile technology ➤ Book chapter writing, drafting, and editing of chief researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 50,000.10 BDT (self-paid) ➤ Standard daily charge of lecturer (research) category salary in Bangladeshi University (50,000-60,000 BDT) + 20% additional charge of additional duty allowance (excluded from the approved fund) ➤ Although Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was qualified as associate professor in 2019-2020 (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025g) ➤ Acknowledged to City University, Bangladesh.
<p>Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264</p>	<p>Chief researcher: Publication</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Ten official days of routine weekly holidays/additional hours at City University/RMIT University ➤ Specialized consultant in textile technology ➤ Communication with peer reviewer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 16,666.70 BDT (self-paid) ➤ Standard daily charge of lecturer (research) category salary in Bangladeshi University (50,000-60,000 BDT) + 20% additional charge of additional duty allowance (excluded

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ and publisher, and service of edition ➤ Book chapter publication and editing under the comments of peer reviewers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ from the approved fund) ➤ Although Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was qualified as associate professor in 2019-2020 (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025g) ➤ Acknowledged to City University, Bangladesh.
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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ scanner, office of chief researcher and chief director, and office space merged and supported with the scholarship fund at RMIT University, Australia. ➤ self-subsidized and/or self-invested the fund of 1,00,000 BDT for writing the brief project completion report of the mini project of City University, figure 2, (Hossain, 2025i) 	
Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com ; Mobile: +8801788396264	Chief researcher: Administrative service; tools and software charges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Personal laptop and maintenance ➤ Drafting manuscript ➤ Writing for publication ➤ Internet charge for online study and communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 4,500 BDT (self-paid) ➤ Acknowledged to City University, Bangladesh.
		Total cost of the project	1,66,500.20 BDT
		Approached 20% local currency inflation of the total cost since 2019 (Hossain, 2025e)	33,300.04 BDT
		Total cost with 20% local currency inflation of the total cost since 2019 (Hossain, 2025e)	1,99,800.24 BDT

3 Discussion

3.1 A good quality professor (Dr.)/researcher in technology should be richer and richer than king and king (Hossain, 2025a).

The reasons and facts are being explained and displayed for the support of the relevant communities, countries, United Nations, researchers, scientists, professors, universities, university grant commissions, funding authorities, research organizations, accreditation councils, and relevant ministries of a country. Sometimes, a professor can not ask money due to the limitation

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of self-prestige to overcome the critical situation of dishonor and losing the job. Possibly, a seventy percent of the total income of a private university should be paid and reserved for the salary of teachers and researchers and a thirty percent of the total income should be reserved for the administrative service and the continuous development service of the university. The administrative manpower should be minor in university when a professor can simultaneously perform the duty of office assistant, office secretary, and a technical person. Every university is a basket or umbrella or common infrastructure where professor (Dr.) in technology/researcher gets the umbrella to continue the practice of teaching, research, and education service. Possibly, a good quality/specialized medical practitioner in medical service proportionally earns more than the owner of the medical clinic. But, what is happening in the education service in the private universities in Bangladesh (Hossain, 2025g). The earning process of a professor in private university should be scrutinized and established. There are scope of research and development and relevant government funding to satisfy both parties. Every professional person is also an entrepreneur when he/she invests for his/her self-development when he/she parallelly serves for the country/organization. There is also a misunderstanding or miscounselling to define the term of the word of entrepreneur. If an industry owner is an entrepreneur, an engineer is also an entrepreneur. If private university/private clinic owner is an entrepreneur, a professor is also an entrepreneur. Every government is also an entrepreneur. A government practitioner/government entrepreneur/researcher may have higher peace of mind rather than private practitioner/private entrepreneur. What is the reason? The results tend to the currency inflation of a government of a country. The results tend to the imbalance in wealth distribution of a government. Who should take care the reasons? There are huge scope of research and development and relevant government funding. Comparatively, a government office assistant and his/her spouse/sex partner in Bangladesh gets life time pension/life time salary/compensation/gratuity who has a government contribution/academic achievement/service quality of ten class or eight class education in Bangladesh (Hossain, 2025e). Possibly, the threatening of job losing is also minor of a government office assistant in Bangladesh than the job of private organization. Who should take care the pension and gratuity scheme of a professor at City University in Bangladesh? If there is loss in any education business/service of any profession/entrepreneur, government should have a subsidiary in the name of government running/government service/government support of the education service in the name of currency inflation and/or merging with the government profit margin (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k). A government can print the money to adapt with the fund crisis to run the government, but the private entrepreneur can not print the money to adapt with the crisis with the situation to run the organization, so the actual financial crisis of a government is invisible/camouflage to the citizen. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has also service experience in the relevant field of research and development, democracy and advocacy, and peace surviving technique in the planet. The planet is not only the combination of inanimate object.

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3.2 What should be the standard earning process of a chief researcher? Who should take care in university?

Every chief researcher should get a prestigious salary or a minimum salary of the equivalence salary or the mother job/main job or the percentage of salary of lecturer, assistant professor, associate professor, professor, and senior professor at any university to satisfy the research practice to satisfy the research service of the whole project duration. Although the salary of scholarly/additional service should be higher than the general service/salary to satisfy the scholarly service, motivation, and gratuity to the researchers. Although general service law/public service law of additional service establishes and qualifies to pay higher than the routine duty/routine salary, but there is huge lack in the profession of research and publication. A worker of a compliance garments industry gets a higher rate of service for his/her additional duty hours. A researcher reads a book/article/manuscript to write to remark to understand to review few sentences, a researcher writes few sentences, a researcher reads a ready manuscript five to ten times to satisfy the self-editing and self-peer review but these are not service, but these are the self-investment of a scholar, so the scholar/reader gradually becomes financially poorer and weaker (M. A. Hossain, 2023aq). Global community should campaign and negotiate to develop the relevant field of research and development.

3.3 Time and investment of a researcher should not be a flying dust in the air beside the road

Figure 1-3, a researcher performs multidimensional tasks in his research. Every funder don't pay and consider the right investment and duty value of a researcher. As a result, researcher may tend to the financial weakness rather than another profession. These are the global headache in the profession of the researchers. People like to see the glory and glory of the research and researcher. But people like to see the invention. But funder don't invest for the practice support for the trialing support of the researchers. People don't invest for making a researcher. A researcher can not continue the research until the brain of researcher in one dimensional thinking and one-dimensional motivation. Every funder should pay to the researcher accordingly. University may offer one time research grant to the researcher instead of mini project. University may offer subsidiary fund to the researcher instead of mini project. Every mini project has the huge investment of researcher to satisfy the funder. The scholarly research grant may cover a partial support to the researcher which may minimize the administrative hassle and administrative costs of a researcher. A research project needs to satisfy the billing and enormous administrative function to the funder when a mini project can not satisfy/bear the full administrative cost and operational expenses of the project. Prepaid research fund should be prerequisite for the surviving support of the researcher. Therefore, scholarly performance/brand value of a researcher/outcome of a mini project may confuse due to the fund crisis of the funder/researcher. A lot of thinking time, a lot of planning time, a lot of reading time, a lot of practice time, a lot of writing time, a lot

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of trialing time, a lot of peer review time are not being claimed for the billing and requisition of fund transfer. To read a research paper for literature review/peer review, a researcher may claim five to thirty full-time working days/full office days/full billing days (Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, 2025). To write/publish a research article, a researcher may claim one year to five years duration full-time working days/full-time office days/full-time billing days. A full-time researcher can charge one to two years duration full-time service charge to develop a research proposal. A conference attendance should be a full-time duty of a researcher. A conference should have the payment of additional duty allowance, conveyance, residential hotel, and presentation. To make a Microsoft PowerPoint presentation, a researcher may claim five to thirty days duration full-time working days/full-time office days/full-time billing days. Therefore, time and investment of a researcher should not be a flying dust in the air beside the road. Internationally, research profession is not still recognized and established, there is still joking scenery with the research profession, there is still lacking to establish to understand to transparent to counsel to guide of both party of funder and researcher (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023bx). Research is a cultivation/farming/creation of knowledge. Knowledge grows like the chain growth of bacteria. There is knowledge production when the scientist is sleeping when the scientist is walking when the scientist is seating in the office desk. So, a scientist serves for twenty-four hours for his/her duty of knowledge cultivation for the university for the country. Therefore, funder and researcher jointly serve for the cultivation/farming/creation of knowledge at research centre at university of any country.

Figure 1. Comparison among approved fund versus total cost versus self-subsidized cost of chief researcher in a mini project at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

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Figure 2. General functions of chief researcher and chief director in a research project; a chief researcher also performs the duty of a chief director; a chief researcher also parallelly performs the duty of a chief director in the mini project to minimize the administrative cost of the service.

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Figure 3. Research and publication cycle of a researcher at university/research organization; every unit time of a researcher should be full paid by the university or research organization of any country.

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3.4 Writing a research proposal should not be a free of cost service to the funder if research of a researcher is also a profession

Figure 1-3 and table 1-3, every university/organization should approve the fund of research proposal writing if the proposal is accepted by the university or research organization. A good research proposal may also ensure the full prerequisite of a research degree. Laboratory works signifies the practical evidence of a research proposal. Writing a research proposal has huge investment of a chief researcher. Therefore, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain approached the additional fund of 1,00,000 BDT to the funder for the scholarly service of the chief researcher (M. A. Hossain et al., 2019).

3.5 Writing an administrative report or project completion report for the approved fund transfer of a mini project should not be a free of cost service to the funder if research of a researcher is also a profession

Figure 1-3 and table 1-3, every university/organization should approve the fund of administrative duty if the proposal is accepted by the university or research organization. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain approached the additional fund of 1,00,000 BDT to the funder for the administrative support of the chief researcher (Hossain, 2025i). This report of quality enhancement and professional guideline charge to City University, Bangladesh should be 20,000 USD or one year duration full- time salary of a senior professor in Bangladesh or one year duration full- time salary of a chief researcher in Bangladesh.

3.6 Category of service grade in research and development

There is also scope to category of service grade in research and development. Such as: proto grade of research; learning grade of research; practice grade of research; teaching grade of research; literature review grade of research; thinking, planning, experience, and drafting grade of research; science and development grade of research; peer review grade of research; publication grade of research; invention grade of research; product and implementation grade of research.

3.7 What should be the salary of a chief researcher in an approved project?

Figure 1-3 and table 1-3, a chief researcher may get a prestigious amount of salary or an equivalence amount of additional salary of lecturer/assistant professor/associate professor/professor/senior professor/chief professor/project director/centre director to satisfy the research service against the approved post of a university/research organization. A chief researcher should be responsible to continue one dimensional thinking, one-dimensional motivation, and one-dimensional research and development.

3.8 What should be the service load of a professor/senior professor/chief professor/research professor at university?

Let's establish the duty of a research professor in university to the funding authority of a government/universities. A professor should/may teach one research student to earn a full-time salary. A full-time category senior professor/professor at university may guide one Postdoc researcher by thesis/one PhD researcher by thesis (4 years duration) or two master degree by thesis (2 years + 2 years = 4 years duration) or four bachelor degree by thesis (1 year + 1 year + 1 year + 1 year = 4 years duration) in his relevant field of research and development. A Postdoc may vary from six month to five years duration depending on funding. If a professor/lecturer is responsible to teach/guide more student and more thesis, the professor/lecturer should get the additional salary should get the proportional salary for the service at university (M. A. Hossain, 2023au; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025b, 2025d). Therefore, a schematic of 20 years duration professional service of a research professor may be defined as five PhD researcher by thesis or ten master degree by thesis or twenty bachelor degree by thesis. Accordingly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain served to City University, Bangladesh under the over load of professional duty under the additional service at department of textile engineering under the limitation of research service under the limitation of time duration under the limitation of research fund (2017-2020).

3.9 What should be the salary of a head of the department/dean of the departments/chief researcher/vice chancellor/chancellor/project director/centre director/registrar in an approved project/university/research organization?

A head of the department/dean of the departments/chief researcher/vice chancellor/project director/centre director/registrar/study leave researcher may get a prestigious amount of salary or an equivalence amount of additional salary of lecturer/assistant professor/associate professor/professor/senior professor/chief professor to satisfy the administrative/research service/study leave service/research leave service against the approved post of a university/research organization. A head of the department/dean of the departments/chief researcher/vice chancellor/registrar should be responsible to continue one dimensional thinking and one-dimensional administrative service of a research organization/university (Hossain, 2025g). If a professor parallelly continues as a class teacher/research teacher, and head/dean/director/chief researcher/vice chancellor; the quality of service/research and development may decline and decline. Therefore, every service should be one dimensional to touch the right development and right peace in profession. Although the service of multidimensional post should also have a higher salary/merged salary of a university/research organization. A head of the department, dean of the departments, chief researcher, vice chancellor, chancellor, project director, centre director, and registrar are the administrative post of a professor/senior professor graded person in university/research organization. Every organization should have a prestigious gratuity

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fund to the scholars. Every organization should have a prestigious subsidiary fund to the scholars. Every organization should have a prestigious salary to the scholars. Who should take care the situation to lead the university/research organization?

3.10 Authentication of researcher/research degree/promotional display at university/research organization

Every professor, Dr., and researcher who are claiming Dr. before the name who are claiming the name of prestigious universities beside the name, they should display their relevant thesis/relevant publication of bachelor degree, master degree, PhD degree, and Postdoc degree. Therefore, every professor (Dr.) should authenticate their transparency of professional service, professional practice, transparency of research degree by thesis, and transparency of promotional thesis by research at university/research organization. (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025a, 2025g).

3.11 Who should be the chief scientist/scientist professional of a country?

Chief scientist should not be a general post of a research organization of any country. The post should not be the way of general appointment. These are the post of high-quality researcher. Research degree by quality thesis should be a primary prerequisite of a chief scientist professional of a country. An invention quality PhD achiever/an invention quality senior professor may serve may lead as chief scientist professional of a research organization of a country. A scientist is a self-assistant in his laboratory when he is not taking the salary of his assistant. A professor is a self-assistant in his laboratory/duty when he is not taking the salary of his assistant. The salary, safety, gratuity allowance, and pension allowance of a chief scientist should be few times higher than university professor in technology. Possibly, there is practice of limitations to appoint the chief scientist professionals of a country? Although Bangladesh has a few set-ups of ready teams like chief scientific officer and scientific officer. Who should lead the relevant teams? A chief scientist/scientist will lead the team. Who should take care the country? For example, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain visited Bangladesh atomic energy commission, Savar, Dhaka in 2022. It was a self-funding tour of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. A researcher asked to put the name in the author list of a publication in terms of his testing support/machine support of the organization. This is the situation of a PhD category researcher of a research organization in Bangladesh. Although, Bangladesh government sacrifices currency inflation to finance Bangladesh atomic energy commission.

3.12 Who should take care the peer review charge of promotion in university?

An assessment fees of a senior professor/professor (Dr.) category promotion should be 4,000 USD (Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, 2025). Who should pay the service charge

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to assess the promotion in university? Who should counsel the service? Every university should have a separate funding for the peer review service in university.

3.13 Where is the sole author thesis of Bachelor degree/Master degree/PhD degree/Postdoc degree/relevant claim of relevant degree?

Every administrative concerns/professional practitioner of Bachelor degree/Master degree/PhD degree/Postdoc degree/relevant claimers of degree should have a sole author thesis should keep their thesis at library or administrative data bank or online platform to satisfy the relevant community of the claimers or service centre at any university or the brand value of university or the brand value of the professional service centre in home and abroad (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain will not allow any practitioner at Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka without the relevant thesis of their any degree of any university. Every university degree is a professional degree is a professional symbol. Every university research is a professional trademark. Without having vigorous experience, the degree should be automatically invalid although the degree is certified by university. In general, people should not respect the degree by the name of country by the name of university. Similarly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also notified/campaigned and/or notifying/campaigning/alarmed to School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia; and Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India (Hossain, 2025a). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has the legal authentication to urge/charge a legal claim to City University, Bangladesh; University of Calcutta, India; and RMIT University, Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has also the legal authentication to urge/charge a legal claim to any university in Bangladesh, private universities, public universities, school of universities who are claiming their bachelor degree/master degree/PhD degree who are claiming their professional practices in universities. There are also rules to expel/suspend university and department of any country. Every university performance of research and development should be displayed and displayed. Every professor should be transparent peer reviewed in terms their promotional files and professional files. An academic promotion should not be a hidden file of an organization or a professor. Every academic promotion should be audited and peer reviewed by the university grants commission (UGC). UGC of Bangladesh is run by the printed money of the government. The administration of UGC is doing government job of public service. So, UGC of Bangladesh has the lacking of liability of their public service. UGC is an organization of public university and/or government organization. Possibly, UGC is not an active organization of City University. Who is the guardian of UGC? At bachelor degree of City University, at senior project of City University, City University had a very poor responsibility to train/accomplish/supervise/peer review the thesis of bachelor degree (2009-2010). City University had no professor graded teacher at Department of Textile Engineering (2009-2010) to supervise

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the senior project. Possibly, City University had no full professor graded teacher at Department of Textile Engineering since 2006. A professor graded person should be the UGC requirement to run any department at any University. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain showed his thesis of bachelor degree to the head of the department who showed zero responsibility to do/ensure the peer review of the thesis/senior project report of bachelor degree (2009-2010). Possibly, head of the department, department of textile engineering, City University had no responsibility about the thesis of bachelor degree/senior project of bachelor degree (2009-2020) if he had expertise about the degree by thesis if he is taking expert salary against the research degree/research expertise. If he has no research expertise, he should not continue his professional service at City University. Possibly head of the department had zero contribution of project activities/research activities for the students for the department of textile engineering but he was long-term serving/name plating as expert professional in the name of Dr./PhD. Every student/teacher/lecturer/assistant professor/associate professor/professor should also display their thesis/senior project report of BSc engineering degree/thesis of promotion to satisfy their professional practice at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh. If a university teacher is claiming a designation of lecturer/assistant professor/associate professor/professor/senior professor at any university, he/she should have thesis experience in his/her academic degree, he/she should be independently capable to supervise the thesis/project. If a lecturer/assistant professor/associate professor/professor/senior professor can not supervise the thesis he/she should be automatically expelled from the academic service at university level, he/she should not write the designation of lecturer/assistant professor/associate professor/professor/senior professor beside the name. To recover the thesis compensation of bachelor degree (2009-2010), City University should allow/approve the additional research fund/development fund of 10,00,000 BDT to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain whatever he recovered by self-investment, self-compensation, self-practice, and self-learning. Moreover, every graduate at Department of Textile Engineering, City University should get a free of cost project training to recover their quality to recover their self-investment of schooling at City University. For professional surviving, every graduate may/should take the 'no objection certificate' by showing their thesis of BSc engineering degree at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh if they need any supportive degree of BSc engineering/training to claim the degree of BSc in Textile Engineering of City University. The whole thesis of bachelor degree at City University should be audited and peer reviewed to ensure the quality of bachelor degree to ensure the brand value of BSc engineering degree to ensure the responsibility of the teachers at the department of textile engineering. Without which, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain will not take the liability of BSc engineering degree at City University. Every university should have professor graded teacher to supervise the thesis of bachelor degree. Every professor graded teacher should have the quality to supervise the thesis of bachelor degree. Every vice chancellor of university should be responsible and liable. Therefore, every university should be liable to

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train/supervise/accomplish the practice of senior project the practice of thesis at bachelor degree at university without which the relevant penalty should be applicable to the university to the UGC to the ministry. Possibly, there are bachelor degree/master degree who have no academic requirement of thesis/project, they are also claiming their degree of university, the relevant teachers/professors/administrations/experts are also enjoying the government salary/non-government salary. What is the actual scenery of quality of a bachelor degree in university/universities when the graduates are expecting and dreaming and investing to be chief executive officer and/or managing director and/or chief researcher and/or chief scientist and/or chief professor of a project/university? Therefore, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to recommend to enhance the priority of project/thesis activities at the level of bachelor degree by which way graduate will have a genuine chance to develop their career to the advance research to the advanced skill in the relevant field of study. Nobody should cheat, no university should cheat, no UGC should cheat, no professor should cheat, no vice chancellor should cheat, no pro vice chancellor should cheat, no chairman should cheat with the legal dream of the students who are investing and investing their finance, their time, their motivation for their self-development for the contribution of the country.

3.14 Remarking the quality of Bangladesh Textile University, Dhaka, Bangladesh; a government college was authorized as public university to enhance their public liability to enhance ethical liability of public service/research and development in Bangladesh

Possibly, Bangladesh Textile University had vice chancellor without master degree by thesis and/or PhD degree by thesis (2015-2021) in the relevant field of textile technology. But they couldn't honor the master degree of University of Calcutta due to having the BSc engineering degree of City University, Dhaka. If they did any national crime in the appointment policy of assistant professor (2.164/2013/volume 12/3064; 7 September 2017), they should be liable for their public service in Bangladesh Textile University (M. A. Hossain, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Are they respect or assess the brand value of university or the personal excellency. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to recommend to UGC or Bangladesh government to verify the truthiness of appointment in Bangladesh Textile University. Possibly, there is so many crimes in public service in public university including the service of public service commission. Everywhere should not be the crime in appointment policy (M. A. Hossain, 2023as). What is the responsibility of UGC? Who is monitoring the government fund of the higher education project in university? What is the standard peer review policy to monitor the government fund of the higher education project in university? The finance of public university is also the money of public if the university can not earn the money. Every public/education researcher/law researcher/national expert/international expert in the relevant of textile technology can legally

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claim to the government to the UGC to the ministry to the high court of Bangladesh about the right service of research and development if the name putting culture of research and publication is being practiced in the promotional cycle and/or appointment cycle at any university. Every national expert has right to verify the promotion file and appointment file of any university. Therefore, every professor of public university, every promotion, every appointment should be peer reviewed and audited to ensure the right protocol to ensure the judicial protocol of the higher education service in research and development in Bangladesh. Every thesis, every publication, every promotional file, every research, every contribution of a professor should be displayed and displayed for the public, student, researcher, and professor community to enhance the national and global value of the name of university if the university is funded by the government of Bangladesh if the university is funded by the public authority of the government. UGC should also have the suspension policy/magistracy policy of public university and private university. What should be the suspension policy. Who should say? Who should shout and shout? Who should implement? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not a paid consultant/member of UGC. What is the duty or expertise of the UGC member? What is the follow-up duty or expertise of the ministry of education? An ethical professor and/or researcher and/or government authority will take the whole control of the university for a certain period of the time for a suspending/assessment period of the time who will audit the whole professor who will audit the whole finance of the university who will report to the government who will judge and notify to the UGC to the ministry of education (Hossain, 2025g). Similarly, every public and private university should have the external peer review policy to enhance the quality of higher education of the government. Therefore, every grandfather or grandmother of the university should not be a vice chancellor of the university if the grandfather has no master degree by thesis and/or PhD degree by thesis and/or professor by thesis. Every university have legal right to appoint the professor of national quality and/or international quality and/or vice chancellor for the development of the university, these are not the matter of ego, these are the matter of public service, contribution, and development. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has full quality to be the chancellor or vice chancellor and chief professor of any branded university of any quality university of any government all over the world (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Let's assess the research and development of whole Bangladesh Textile University with the contribution of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). How many times peer reviewed the Bangladesh Textile University by UGC? Globally, there are far deviation between the regular certification of degree, and research and development. What is the amount of government funding to Bangladesh Textile University? What is the amount of government funding to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). What should be the liability of a government or the representative of a government or the expert representative of the government to ensure the funding support to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar

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Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)? Always, government does not mean the president, prime minister or chief advisor or minister or UGC of a country (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Hossain, 2025g). Where should be the present office and/or service centre of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in Bangladesh? The place of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should be Bangladesh Textile University or Bangladesh Jute Research Institute if they are claiming that they have the ready platform. Present leader/professor of Bangladesh Textile University is also an expert representative of Bangladesh government, funded by Bangladesh government, funded by public or citizen. They should not be blind. UGC should not be blind. Ministry of education should not be blind. Professor should not be blind. Research organization should not be blind. If they can not respect the brand value of RMIT University, University of Calcutta, and City University; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also expecting and demanding the assessment support and/or judicial support and/or administrative support and/or magistracy support and/or compensation support and/or subsidiary support of Bangladesh government, universities, relevant international authority, and relevant professor community. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is searching, asking, and inviting the brief curriculum vitae (CV), brief biodata, and brief promotion file of one senior category professor in textile technology who have sole author record of publication, thesis and contribution who can peer review the file of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain for the post of chief professor/senior professor in Bangladesh (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). Email address: engr.anowar@yahoo.com. In relevant assessment, every employer should pay the peer review fees of 4,000 USD to satisfy the international standard.

3.15 Proposal to City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh to education ministry and UGC of Bangladesh

If City University is the loss project and/or the subsidized project of the entrepreneur or founder or chairman of City University, the barristerial service of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain may try to convince to ensure to establish to approve the government subsidiary for the quality education service and research service in Bangladesh (Hossain, 2025b, 2025c). To satisfy the subsidiary, City University should display the total financial report from the date of founding of the university, total project cost and billing, financial audit report, report of financial peer review, report of quality peer review, report of education service, numbers of approved graduate/quality graduate, scholarly records of the graduates to satisfy the education ministry and UGC of Bangladesh. Either City University should invest like public university in Bangladesh like a standard private university in Bangladesh, neither City University should ask subsidiary fund to the government, neither City University should surrender to the government should ask full funding to the government of Bangladesh. If City University can not take the full liability of the department of textile engineering, the department may merge with the public university in

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Bangladesh; and/or City University may recommend to merge Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain with public university at Bangladesh Textile University and/or relevant research institute in Bangladesh. In these circumstances of education service, City University and/or government of Bangladesh and/or UGC of Bangladesh should fund/may fund in the research project in the name of “Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre”, proposed by Chief Researcher and Founder, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025i). These funds of research and development of education service may be jointly and/or individually. Vice Chancellor of City University and chairman of UGC of Bangladesh should assess should independently assess the situation about private university/universities in Bangladesh. Under the self-funding project of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain of higher education service, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh and/or education ministry and/or UGC of Bangladesh should pay to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain for writing report, convincing report, and self-investing against the limitation of higher education service/policy of the government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not an appointed consultant is not a paid consultant of higher education is not a paid consultant of UGC. Therefore, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also investing since 2006 at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh by his self-funded office and practice of research and publication (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). City University and/or government should have a value for his scholarly investment and scholarly convincing. Therefore, City University and/or education ministry and/or UGC of Bangladesh should also pay the standard salary, every allowance of professor, full funding to professor, standard gratuity scheme, and standard pension scheme to Nobel Nominee professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) for scholarly surviving in the profession for establishing the brand value of City University, Bangladesh. Who should take care the salary, pension, and gratuity scheme of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh? (M. A. Hossain, 2023aq, 2023as; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025g)

3.16 Research income of a chief researcher and expenditure of a scientific project should be tax free of a country, attached relevant legal acts of Australia and India

There is necessity to involve ethical professor under the support of UGC, ministry of education, and relevant government authority. No person/individual will invest for the research and publication when the research and development needs separate funding and expensive funding. Government should invest for the research if private universities are the profitable organization of a person/individual. No person/individual can invest for the research and publication. Expert professor/expensive professor may serve for the relevant duty. A publication is also research product of a university of a country. Moreover, publication is not a direct profitable/sellable business of a chief researcher or professor or university or founder like a garment product of a garments industry. A garments manufacturing industry is making garments and immediately

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selling and transferring the products to the customers and earning money. Moreover, research practice is also expensive and expensive. Research and publications tend to the professional development skill for the university promotion, professional degree in university, and scientist practice for the government. Research and publication extend the existing knowledge and technology of a country and/or global community. So, the research income of a chief researcher and expenditure in a scientific project should be tax free of a country. A research professor serves for the broader community/public through the university which indirectly develop the impact factor and earning capability of a university. A scientist also serves for the broader community/public through the government when product developing and marketing is not a core duty of a scientist when product marketing needs a separate planning, separate funding, and separate investment. Hiding the technology of a scientist is also tough when the scientist/research professor needs to display the service to survive in the profession to convince the community to hunt the research funding in the profession to satisfy the promotion/research degree at university/research organization. So, every research professor/scientist should get the surviving support through the printed money of the government through the government inflation and/or the profit margin of the government. If City University don't get the printed money of Bangladesh government, City University will not be a research university under the act of private university in Bangladesh when the university fund is administered by the founder of the university. In general, a founder will not be interested to serve for the government under the act of non-profitable personal business in higher education. So, a founder may tend to sacrifice the quality in higher education until the founder is planning to pay the donation of the total founding cost and/or the costs of the continuous operation. Oppositely, Professor Dr. Eng. Md. Anowar Hossain is writing this report to the City University and government authority of Bangladesh to improve the quality to satisfy the broader community but he can not directly sell this publication/report to any party. So, the financial benefit of Professor Dr. Eng. Md. Anowar Hossain is also declining and declining. Hence, there is scope of expert review, relevant research, relevant government funding for the research of Bangladeshi private universities to establish the core objectives of universities through the private universities in Bangladesh.

3.17 What should be the actual value of the mini project of 1,00,000 BDT and service charge of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at City University?

Every fund of a project is approved by the government to satisfy the target of the government. There is a matter of extra effort and extra service of chief researcher/chief director to the government behind the mother job and service at university. It is implemented/should be implemented from the office assistant to the director of the project. So, the standard amount of project fund and efficient planning is also necessity. For example: a permanent category office assistant is arranging and distributing tea and food in a meeting of the project. The office assistant

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should also get an extra allowance of his/her extra hour of service at university if director/chief director is also getting an extra salary for his/her extra hour of service. For example: Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain went to industries for getting the peer review report/support of higher education quality enhancement project (HEQEP), UGC at City University from the experts of textile industries. There was no allowance of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain under the operation of the head of the department, department of textile engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh (2018-2019). There was no allowance to the peer reviewers under the operation of the head of the department, department of textile engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh (2018-2019). Officially, an alumni and an industry expert are not liable to make a peer review report for the university and/or HEQEP without allowance. All professional peoples are busy and busy in the place of their work stations. So, the quality of peer review may also vary for the purpose of the research and development of the university. There was neglecting to allow to approve the additional duty allowance, additional study allowance, reporting allowance, e-mail communication, telephonic communication, filing support, conveyance, telephone allowance, and coordination with the alumni. There was also the duty of data collection from the alumni. The type of service may also be termed as ‘research assistant’ of the department/head of the department/HEQEP(Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024i). If the service is volunteer in the profession, it should have a certificate of contribution to the HEQEP from the office of chief researcher/director of City University. So, top administration should be transparent to satisfy the duty value to satisfy income support to the university teacher. Additional service of any project should not be a free of cost service at any university. The central operation of City University or any university is a higher education project of the government. Possibly, the cost of City University project and the cost of HEQEP is fully different from the source of funding. Moreover, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn’t get any publication of the report of City University and HEQEP. Possibly, the approved fund of HEQEP at City University was higher than the mini project of 1,00,000 BDT of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (Hossain, 2025i). So, what should be the actual value of this mini project? What should be the exact payment/exact salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to the chief researcher? Comparatively, what should be the actual service charge of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in this mini project of Textile, color, and material research centre? Moreover, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had no paid post of HEQEP project at department of textile engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get an amount of service charge at HEQEP project at department of textile engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh (if applicable by the authority). These are not charging attitude and writing to City University. These are the attitude and voice of quality enhancement project at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

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3.18 Global warning sign for university/research organization, crime and criminals are winning and surviving and earning

By nature, every human brain will not grow for the research profession in terms of multidimensional facts, such as: natural limitation, artificial limitation, lack of proper investment, lack of funding authority, and the limitation of self-motivation. University/research organization may have two types of researchers/professionals, such as ‘A’ and ‘B’ category of researchers/professionals. ‘B’ category of researchers/professionals have no tendency/confidence about the self-growth, self-capability, research, and publication. ‘A’ category of researcher tries to climb and tries to overcome the limitations, but ‘B’ category of researchers tries to harass and disturb against the genuine growth of ‘A’ category researchers (M. A. Hossain, 2023as), but ‘B’ category of researcher tries to climb to follow the alternative route of professional climbing and surviving, such as: financial dealing, relationship dealing, sex dealing, administrative convincing, and other techniques and thinking of surviving rather than techniques and thinking in research and development. ‘B’ category researcher/director/head of the department/teacher may try to decline the quality of ‘A’ category researcher/teacher. ‘A’ category researchers are busy to ensure the service, but ‘B’ category researchers are busy to apply the technique of conspiracy, harassment, and administrative force. One ‘B’ category researcher may pay/convince another ‘B’ category researcher/administrative person to make/apply a joint force and hidden force to ‘A’ category researcher. There is also possibility of high cementing and good relation between ‘B’ category researcher and ‘B’ category researcher. There is also possibility of clashing between ‘B’ category researchers and ‘A’ category researchers. Sometimes, ‘B’ category researcher tries to show the attitude of grandfather in the department/university/research organization. ‘A’ category researchers are be the climbing/surviving stair or rope of ‘B’ category researchers in terms of name putting culture in publication. ‘A’ long chain of ‘B’ category researchers/teachers is long term established in universities in higher education and long term practiced in universities in higher education due to lack of right administrative practice due to lack of eye looking of ethical practice in university. Sometimes, ‘B’ category researcher/top management may show the attitude of snake. The tail of the snake, the tail of curling of the snake may touch the family of ‘A’ category researcher. So, ‘A’ category teachers and researchers may face threatening, conspiracy, and life-threatening in university and research organization. Because, ‘B’ category teachers and researchers also try to earn more money to establish in profession rather than ‘A’ category teachers and researchers. But they don’t try to overcome their limitations in the proper way. They have also multidimensional techniques of illegal practice. These are the global warning sign for university/research organization (Hossain, 2025a, 2025g). Who should take care the universities? Possibly, there are Professor (Dr.) who have certificate without thesis who have promotion without thesis who have promotion without publication who are professor without thesis who have achievement without scholarly contribution who have no thesis of bachelor degree, master degree,

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PhD degree, and Postdoc degree/experience; they may continuously harass the students, scholars, professor, and researchers; they may quarrel and shout with the students, scholars, professor, and researchers; they may misguide/demotivate the students, scholars, professors, and researchers; they may apply administrative weapon and magistracy weapon against the support of natural growth of students, scholars, professor, and researchers; they may try to cease the ethical weapon of the students, scholars, professors, and researchers; they may kill the students, scholars, professor, and researchers for their self-surviving in the profession. Possibly, there are also research organization without scientist. Possibly, there are also university without professor. Possibly, there are also research degree without research. Possibly, there are also research degree in terms of name putting in publication. If a person can not perform as chief researcher, practically he/she should not get the research degree. This is very simple understanding. What is the actual beauty, actual scenery, and practice of higher education and higher investment in university? (M. A. Hossain, 2023bx)

4 Conclusion

A trialing of project work parallelly develops the administrative skill, research skill, and analytical skill to run the administration to run the organization to run the country to run the United Nations to run the whole world. Teaching theory of an instructor/teacher is the core practice of a primary school, high school, and college under the minor practice of project activities. Teaching research/practice of research should be the core function of university education under the minor practice of theory. Primary school student of Bangladesh government is also getting a small amount of schooling support without any billing process to the school administration. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain casually asked to few primary school students in Bangladesh, “what are you doing by the school money from your school?” Someone told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “I purchase food.” Someone told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “I purchase cloth.” Somebody replied to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “I deposit my money.” It seems that the primary school students independently spent their school money, when necessary, where necessary. Similarly, every university should allow or approve small amount of research grant or research fund or research gift without any billing process. These are the motivational funds for the researcher. If Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is serving to Bangladesh government is highlighting the limitations of education service in Bangladesh, he should have legal rights to get the surviving support/printed money of Bangladesh government. Every university teacher, founder, chairman, vice chancellor, director, researcher, professor should jointly continue the research practice to satisfy the word of university to satisfy the word of university teacher. There is also global limitation of knowledge culturing and right investment. Investment in higher education and research is the responsibility of a government. These are not

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the responsibilities of a person when a person/researcher/founder can not officially control the currency inflation of a country. A standard culturing process of knowledge in university is necessity for the development of science and technology, higher education, law, criminology, and personal excellency.

5 Acknowledgement

Sole author, Chief Director, PhD Research; Chief Director, Textile, Defence, and Law Research centre, RMIT; Chief Researcher, Textile, Color, and Material Research Centre, RMIT <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287> Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (**M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018**) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Hossain, Islam, et al., 2018; A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2019; A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2018; Hossain, Samanta, Bhaumik, et al., 2018; Hossain, Samanta, NS, et al., 2018; A. Hossain et al., 2019; Hossain, 2009, 2010b, 2010c, 2015a, 2019a, 2019c, 2019d; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; M. A. Hossain, 2023ap; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2019) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (**M. A. Hossain, 2023ai, 2023am, 2023bi, 2023ci, 2023cj**) (Anowar Hossain, 2016; A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2023; Hossain, 17 May 2023, 2010a, 2015b, 2015c, 2018, 2019b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; M. A. Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f, 2023h, 2023i, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023y, 2023z, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ae, 2023af, 2023ag, 2023ah, 2023ai, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ao, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023ar, 2023as, 2023at, 2023au, 2023av, 2023aw, 2023ax, 2023ay, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bl, 2023bm, 2023bn; M. A. Hossain, 2023a; M. A. Hossain, 2023bo, 2023bp, 2023bq, 2023br, 2023bs, 2023bt; M. A. Hossain, 2023b; M. A. Hossain, 2023bu, 2023bv, 2023bw; M. A. Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e; M. A. Hossain, 2023by, 2023bz, 2023ca, 2023cb, 2023cc, 2023cd, 2023ce; M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; M. A. Hossain, 2023cf, 2023cg, 2023ch, 2023ci, 2023cj, 2023ck, 2023cl; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g, 2024h, 2024i, 2024j, 2024k, 2024l, 2024m, 2024n, 2024o, 2024p, 2024q, 2024r, 2024s, 2024t, 2024u, 2024v, 2024w, 2024y, 2024z; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024aa; Hossain, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d, 2025e, 2025f, 2025g, 2025h, 2025j; Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, 2025); name of father: late Dr. Md. Abdur Rashid, medical practitioner; permanent residence (PR): village: Purbo Nuthurchar, post office: K. Mohonpur (1990), police station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia (PR by birth); nationality, national ID, passport and birth registration number: Bangladeshi,

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19862692620993890, A15988852/EE0444946/AF3831770, 003236; PhD (Doctor of Philosophy) application ID: 2612540, PhD student ID: 3820066, program name: DR213, PhD (fashion and textiles), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; lecturer on textile engineering (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh acknowledges RMIT University and the Australian government for funding through research training program (RTP) stipend scholarship, 2020-2025. Author, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>) also acknowledges ‘Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang’ (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7300-9271>) and ‘Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks’ (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3790-5148>) for their PhD supervision works at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

6 Proposal of quality funding at Textile, Color & Material Research Centre, City University, Bangladesh

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is asking quality funding at Textile, Color & Material Research Centre at City University, Bangladesh and/or research organization to the authority of City university and/or government of Bangladesh and/or foreign authority and/or United Nations (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025i).

7 Searching chief professor/senior professor category salary, office, and quality research fund on textile coloration

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, chief researcher is searching research fund to assess zero toxic coloration, natural material based textile coloration, and relevant field of textile technologies (M. A. Hossain et al., 2019) (A. Hossain, 2020) (M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018) (Hossain, Samanta, NS, et al., 2018) (Hossain, Samanta, Bhaumik, et al., 2018) (Hossain, Islam, et al., 2018) (Hossain, 2019d; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x; Hossain, 2025i). Funding authority of City University and/or any government authority and/or non-government authority may extend the relevant research fund. There is scope of research and development in the relevant field of textile technology.

8 Searching chief professor/senior professor category salary of international standard, office, and quality research fund to national and international universities

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is offering BSc Engineering degree by thesis in textile technology, Master of Technology by thesis in textile technology, Master of Science by thesis in textile technology, MPhil degree by thesis in textile technology, PhD degree by thesis in textile technology, Postdoc degree by thesis in textile technology (M. A. Hossain, 2023au; Hossain, 2025d). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also offering Bachelor degree by thesis in law, Master degree by thesis in law, MPhil degree by thesis in law, PhD degree by thesis in law, Postdoc degree by thesis in law (M. A. Hossain, 2023au; Hossain, 2025b). Accordingly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is approaching and asking quality funding and quality platform at national and international universities. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain will take 70% of the total tuition fees and university will take 30% of the total tuition fees. A subsidiary fund of university or scholarship, a government subsidiary fund or scholarship may be implemented to cover the costs of research fund, research student, and research professor (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023bx; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024i; Hossain, 2025i).

Page | 38

128

9 Author contribution and authorship status of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

The author has contribution in conceptualization, visualization, resource, self-supervision, funding acquisition, project administration, research communications, planning and prediction, analysis, writing the original draft, manuscript editing, and publication process. The scholarship or funder has no scholarly role of the design of research, research idea or visualization, research and innovation, drafting of manuscript, editing of manuscript, and publication of manuscript.

10 Declaration of conflicting interests

The author declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

11 Data availability

All data generated during the coalescing of this article are included, attached and briefly cited.

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12 If necessary, please visit online profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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13 Professional excellency of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, engr.anowar@yahoo.com.

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Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world.
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Page | 40

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130

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Invitation of law researchers in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30060.63369>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16995119>

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13073.70249>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16990186>

Invitation of researchers in textile engineering in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17215.57765>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16960861>

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14 Legal authorization and signing

7 October 2025

(Md. Anowar Hossain)

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16 Evidences of communication about research proposal, fund allotment and fund reservation at City University, Bangladesh

People's Republic of Bangladesh Office of the Notary Public-Bangladesh

S.N. ISLAM & ASSOCIATE'S
Advocate & Notary Public
(Whole Bangladesh)

According to the Section 8 (1)(h) of Notary ordinance 1961 Ad

Translated Copy

[City University Monogram]
Date: 18/11/2019

Ref No. - City University/Reg./9083/2019

To,
Mr. Md Anowar Hossain (Chief Researcher)
Lecturer
Textile Engineering Department
City University

Subject: Regarding research projects and allocation of approvals.

Dear Sir,

This is hereby informing you, for your kind consideration that, Your Recommended Research Project: Zero Toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural Mordanting Agents [A Six Months Duration of Project, September, 2019 - February, 2020 and the allotment of the said research Tk. 1,00,000/- (One Lac) was approved by the university authorities. The authority has to be notified before starting the project. After receiving your letter 50% of the money allocated to start the project, 25% in terms of getting a Progress Report at the end of the half term and upon completion of the project, the Project Completion Report (PCR) will submit and the remaining amount will be disbursed immediately after receiving it.

In this regards you are requested to begin the work of your proposed research project as soon as possible.

Thanking you,
Signature/ Illegible
18/11/2019
M.A Hannan
Registrar
City University

Permanent Certified University
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স্মারক নং- সিটি ইউনিভার্সিটি/রেজি./৯০৮৩/২০১৯ইং

বরাবর,
 জনাব মোঃ আনোয়ার হোসেন (প্রধান গবেষক)
 প্রভাষক
 টেক্সটাইল ইঞ্জিনিয়ারিং বিভাগ
 সিটি ইউনিভার্সিটি।

বিষয়ঃ গবেষণা প্রকল্প এবং বরাদ্দ অনুমোদন প্রসঙ্গে।

জনাব,
 আপনার সদয় অবগতির জন্য জানানো যাচ্ছে যে, আপনার প্রস্তাবিত গবেষণা প্রকল্প Zero Toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural Mordanting Agents [A Six Months Duration of Project, September, 2019- February, 2020] এবং উক্ত গবেষণার বরাদ্দ ১,০০,০০০/- (এক লক্ষ) টাকা বিশ্ববিদ্যালয় কর্তৃপক্ষ কর্তৃক অনুমোদিত হয়েছে। উক্ত প্রকল্পের কাজ শুরু করার অব্যবহিত পূর্বে কর্তৃপক্ষকে অবহিত করতে হবে। আপনার পত্র পাওয়ার পরে প্রকল্পের কাজ শুরু করার জন্য বরাদ্দকৃত অর্থের ৫০%, মেয়াদকালের অর্ধেককাল সমাপনান্তে সমন্বয়জনক অগ্রগতির প্রতিবেদন (Progress Report) পাওয়ার শর্তে ২৫% এবং প্রকল্প কাজ পূর্ণ সমাপনান্তে Project Completion Report (PCR) জমা এবং তা গৃহীত হওয়ার পরপরই বরাদ্দকৃত অর্থের অবশিষ্ট ২৫% অর্থ ছাড় করা হবে।

এমতাবস্থায় আপনার প্রস্তাবিত গবেষণা প্রকল্পের কাজ যথাশীঘ্র সম্ভব শুরু করার জন্য আপনাকে অনুরোধ করা হলো।

ধন্যবাদান্তে

 এম এ হোসেন
 রেজিস্ট্রার
 সিটি ইউনিভার্সিটি।

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 SHEIKH NURUL ISLAM
 Deputy Rector For Whole of Bangladesh
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 Office: Gacha Bazar, Dhaka-1000
 26 NOV 2019

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1

Research Proposal
On
Zero Toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural Mordanting Agents
[A Six Months Duration of Project, September, 2019-January, 2020]

Proposed By
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

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National consultants and experts in textile coloration:

Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, Assistant Professor and Head, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka.
 Dr. Md. Nurul Absar, Professor and Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka.
 Dr. Ferdous ara Dilruba, Chief Scientific Officer, Bangladesh Jute Research Institute (BJRI), Dhaka.

Foreign Consultants and experts in textile coloration:

Dr. AK Samanta, Professor and Former Chairman, Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India.
 Dr. Padma S. Vanakr, Professor & Principal Research FEAT Lab, Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Kanpur, India.

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3

Introduction:

Bangladesh is presently exporting a good quantum of coloured and decorative textile products made of natural fibres like silk, cotton and jute mainly to Japan, USA, Korea, European community countries and African countries. Worldwide growing consciousness for eco-friendly production process is generating more and more customer's interests on natural fibre, natural dyes and natural finished based textile products, particularly for the export market due to having an approach of zero toxic coloration of cotton fabric with natural dyes under consideration of toxic free product and environment friendly production process. Considering the product development and production process corner, textile sector has the highest scope to apply this research work for attracting the value-added customer. But, till today there is a huge lack of research and development of natural dyeing and finishing based textile product.

However, there are some discrete reports available that indicate the application of natural dyes for producing uncommon shades on natural fibers like cotton (Anowar and et al. 2018, 2019, Cristea and Vilarem 2006; Gahlot et al. 2008; Sentikumar et al. 2002), jute (Samanta and Agarwal 2008a; Samanta and Agarwal 2007; Samanta et al. 2008b; Samanta and Konar 2012a; Samanta and Konar 2015; Samanta et al. 2010, 2011; Samanta et al. 2012b; Samanta et al. 2008c; Samanta et al. 2012b, 2009), silk (Gahlot et al. 2008; Javali et al. 2009; Katti et al. 1996; Mahale et al. 2003a; Mahale et al. 2003b; Sidhu and Grewal 2008; Vankar and Shankar 2008; Vinod et al. 2010), wool (Gahlot, Fatima, and Papnai 2008; Gulrajani et al. 2003; Shanker and Vankar 2005; Yoshizumi and Crews 2003). Hence there are ample scopes of doing scientific research on the application of natural dyes on cotton and other textiles aimed at obtaining newer shade with acceptable colour fastness behavior, uniform and reproducible colour yield through appropriate techniques. Simultaneous natural dyeing, natural mordanting and natural finishing process can be a new approach of technique which will minimize the process steps different cost related production like energy and total process cost. Reducing process cost will minimize total cost of the product in the export market, it will be highly beneficial to sustain in a competitive market if the expected research output can be applied successfully in Government and non-government textile mill at home and abroad.

Natural dyes are considered to be eco-friendly as these are obtained from renewable resources as compared to synthetic dyes which are derived from non-renewable petroleum resources. These are biodegradable and the residual vegetal matter left after extraction of dyes can be easily composted and used as fertilizer. They produce soft colours soothing to the eye which is in harmony with nature which is gradually gaining popularity due to its non-toxicity and eco-friendly character against possible unsafe ecotoxicity criteria of synthetic dyes. Most of the studies available for dyeing with natural dyes relates to cotton textiles and such studies on cotton are still insufficient to establish. Hence, there are ample scope of undertaking an integrated study in this area for cotton and chemically modified cotton to study its surface appearance, durability and dyeing of cotton and chemically modified cotton with natural dyes.

The research and development in natural dyed based textile products conducted by textile researcher has been confused to solve technological problem for the production of ecofriendly based textiles and earlier investigation prove that the standard technology and production aspects are the core barrier for the standardization and commercialization of nature friendly textiles and there is unlimited technical demand for ensuring novel production and synthesis method for production process. Currently developed only natural dyed based textiles have so much limitations and have synthetic mordanting application which is not ecofriendly and not fulfilling the requirements of nontoxic coloration of textiles and till today there is a huge lack of research and development of natural dyed and finished textile products as reviewed in literature.

Proposed research on Zero Toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural mordanting agent generated by natural dyes and selective natural mordanting agent through selective dyeing process and the completely ecofriendly products was not experimented till now and the output of this research may be a greater and attractive invention for the development of value added textiles with the theokotex based textiles as well as improve the textiles with significant and special properties like UV protection and antibacterial property etc. comparing to reviewed method and developed natural dyed based textiles and there is little/limited research has been conducted with the proposed materials and method. Natural dyeing and finishing in the stage of development process and still many important accomplishments are hidden with the success corner of related researchers due to unavailability of testing standards for clothing, lower fastness properties and reproducibilities are the question marks to the textile scientist for natural dyed based textiles.

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Review of Literature:

Anowar and et al. (2018) were experimented in earlier research on natural coloration that natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural finishing agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing. A combined green dyeing and mordanting method was applied on cotton fabric in which natural coloring agents were extracted from Diospyros malabarica (Green Gaub fruit) and Camellia sinensis (Green Tea Leaf) where ever green lemon juice had been used as a green mordanting agent and there is no artificial chemical was used during demodulation process of coloring agent, dyeing and mordanting. Both the treated and untreated fabric samples were tested for the mechanical properties (color fastness to washing and rubbing) and dyeing performance in terms of color fastness properties (light fastness) and color strength, K/S value. For dyeing with green gaub fruit, color fastness to wash and rubbing = Very excellent, color fastness to light = good and for dyeing with green tea leaf, color fastness to wash = very excellent, color fastness to rubbing = excellent, color fastness to light = good. An improved color strength, K/S value had been found for both dyeing with green gaub fruit and green tea leaf while mordanting was applied with green lemon juice.

Anowar and et al. (2018) studied on pollution free dyeing and mordanting is indicated as a creative innovation of textile coloration on cotton fabric in which natural dyes were extracted from Swietenia macrophylla (Mahogany leaf) and Musa acuminata (Green Banana Peel) as an unpolluted dyes and Citrus limon (L.) juice was applied as an unpolluted natural mordanting agent. There is no synthetic chemical was used during the whole progression in dyes extraction process and dyeing method. Both the treated and untreated fabric samples were tested for their dyeing performance in terms of color strength, K/S value and color fastness properties like color fastness to washing, rubbing and light. Higher K/S value of lemon mordanted sample was investigated by analysis of spectrophotometer for both dyeing with mahogany and green banana pill. Color fastness to washing and rubbing had been found moderately good for both dyeing with mahogany leaves and green banana pill with lemon mordanting. Moderately good color fastness to light had been found for dyeing with only mahogany leaves and green banana pill but improved light fastness was found for green banana pill with lemon mordanting. As per visual appearance, dyed fabric with green banana pill and lemon mordanting was found very even distribution of color on the surface of cotton fabric. An exceptionally attractive soft hand feel and color shading outcome was observed for dyeing with green banana pill comparing to mahogany leaves without having any additional application of synthetic softer which is the demand of both local and foreign customers in clothing industries

Anowar and et al. (2018) focused that a toxicity free cotton fabric coloration and antibacterial technique was developed where natural colorant curcumin and tannin were applied for investigating a substitute of toxic colorant. Considering the negative impacts of man-made dyes in environment, non-toxic coloring and sterile finishing was carried out with curcumin and tannin as non-toxic colorant quintessence from pure natural sources of Curcuma longa (Turmeric) and Camellia sinensis (Tea Leaf) using environment friendly lemon extracted (Natural Citric acid) solution as natural mordant and their color shading and functional outcomes were evaluated in variety of shades as compared with colour yield/outcomes with ferrous sulphate and copper sulphate as two most extensively practiced conventional chemical mordants. Critical performances of mordanted and unmordanted cotton fabric samples were tested for their color parameters like Colour Strength, K/S value and Colour fastness (color fastness to Washing, UV- Light and Rubbing) properties, besides measurement of other colour interaction parameters (L*, a*, b* and ΔE) as well as anti-bacterial performance as Per AATCC-100-2012 method. The dye absorption determined by color spectrophotometer showed higher color strength when treated with curcumin and tannin colorant in the presence of natural extracted citric acid from lemon as toxic free mordanting agent compared to mordanting with Ferrous sulphate as well as conventional mordanting with Copper Sulphate. Higher rubbing fastness was observed for both dyeing with Turmeric and Tea Leaves when mordanting with lemon and ferrous sulphate. Curcumin demonstrates a pharmacological properties that curcumin found effective against E. coli bacteria in laboratory experiment well as FTIR study of Turmeric with lemon mordanted sample was confirmed the natural crosslinking among cotton fibre cellulose, turmeric curcumin and lemon-citric acid. Consequently, this work has led to development of a process of concurrent natural dyeing and finishing with natural extracted agents on cotton with natural mordants to make the fabric colour full and anti-bacterial also. If the present work is trailed commercially to make it feasible, undoubtedly present finding of research may be an exceptional source of eco-garments production which has a higher demand in local and foreign customer.

Anowar and et al. (2018) investigated that eco-friendly dyeing on cotton fabric was conceded out with organic dyes distillate from organic extraction process of organic Tectonagrandis (Teak Leaf) and Azadirachta indica (Neem Leaf) using ecofriendly metallic mordants and natural mordants (Ferrous Sulphate as ecofriendly metallic mordant and Lemon juice as an organic mordant were used in the research work and their results were compared with results of copper sulphate as conventionally used mordant. All the treated and untreated cotton fabric samples were tested for their Colour Strength and Colour fastness (colour fastness to Washing, UV Light and Rubbing) properties, besides measurement of other colour interaction parameters (L*, a*, b* and ΔE) as well as antibacterial performance as Per AATCC-100-2012 method. Results of colour parameters showed lower ΔE values are obtained when treated with lemon mordanting agent for both the case of dyeing cum finishing treatment with Teak leaf and Neem leaf (though amongst the two dye extract used, Neem leaf extract showed higher K/S value) as compared to

Proposed By Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Principal Investigator

5

conventional mordanting with Copper Sulphate. While, Ferrous Sulphate render moderate K/S value than all due to inherent own colour of ironinFeSO₄. comparing lemon mordanting with conventional copper sulphate mordant, colour fastness properties of teak leaf extract with lemon mordanting are found to be better and is in the order of Rubbing Fastness > followed by colour fastness to Light > colour fastness to wash than that for synthetic mordanting, but for dyeing with extract of neem leaf with lemon mordanting showed very attractive colour fastness considering to all colour fastness properties studied here. In this study, a newer approach / attempt had been made to impart a simultaneous antibacterial finish along with above said natural dyeing. Hence, the antibacterial properties of neem leaf extract dyed cotton using lemon mordant sample resulted better reduction/killing of bacteria. Thus, this work has led to development of a process of simultaneous dyeing and finishing with natural agents on organic cotton with organic mordants to make the fabric colour full and anti-bacterial too.

Page | 60

Anowar and et al. (2019) reviewed on Natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural finishing agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing can be established by developing completely eco-friendly natural dyes and natural finishing agent which can be applied on cotton textiles (Oeko-Tech Products) by adopting a newer technique of simultaneous Mordanting-Dyeing-Finishing in a single step to reduce energy cost, process time, processing costs and effluent load as well as to develop the single step processes and also completely eco-friendly products of cotton textiles using selective natural dyes and natural finishing agents using bio mordants and bio finishing agents obtained from an extract of natural resources at reduced cost and energy. There is huge scope of commercialization of such Oeko-Tech (Eco-Friendly) products of natural dyed and finished cotton textile products for domestic and export market. Different selective natural dyes like teak leaf, turmeric, jackfruit wood, sappan wood, skin of onion, arjuna bark etc., bio-mordanting agent like bio-enzyme, harda, lemon as natural mordanting agents, extracted soyabean seed as natural chemical modification as well as natural finishing agent like coconut oil as UV absorber, neem and guava leaf as antimicrobial agent where all dyed and finished fabric can be scientifically tested by SEM, FTIR, DSC, HPLC, GCMS, TLC, CHNS, X-ray diffraction pattern etc.

Samanta and et. al (2003) and **Dedhia E.M (1998)** studied that growing consciousness for eco-friendly textile products has created more interest on cotton fibre based natural dyeing and finishing. Productions of synthetic dyes are dependent on the petrochemical source and some of the synthetic dyes contain toxic/carcinogenic amines and are not eco-friendly. Contrary to this, most of the natural dyes as well as natural finish with few exceptions are based on vegetable/ animal origin and are renewable, biodegradable, energy-efficient and eco-friendly.

150

Kawahito, et al. (2002) have compared the dyeing of cellulosic fabric with natural indigo and synthetic indigo. Radhakrishnan as well as Ajita, et al. have reported the effect of different mordants on selective natural dyes. **Grierson, et al. (1995)** has studied colour fastness characteristics of some natural dyes. **Lee, et al. (2001)** have studied the colour fastness properties of some natural dyes by applying UV-absorbers. **Gupta, et al (1998)** have reported that the effect of chemical structure on light fastness property of some natural dyes.

Oda, et al. (2001) was studied the effect of phenyl ester functional group on photofading of carthamin on cellulose acetate. Most of the studies are sporadic and insufficient in developing scientific knowledge base on the subject. Therefore, very less study on simultaneous natural dyeing and finishing, dyeing process variables and characterisation etc.

Reviewed study shows that natural dyes was applied with synthetic mordanting agents on textile substrates and its feasibility of application has been positively remarked by the researcher in the area of textile coloration, but the application of completely biomordanting agents/natural mordanting agents/natural finishing agents, standardization of process development, industrial application and commercialization of natural dyed product are the major gaps of research and development in the area of natural dyeing and finishing which may be focused area of research in proposal on zero toxic coloration. Hence, an integrated scientific study for selective natural dye-fibre-mordanting system, for selective natural dyes and natural mordanting agents can be applied on cotton and other textiles is felt necessary, for establishing the ecofriendly process of textile colorations for natural dyed textiles.

The natural coloration on cotton fabric is an approach of zero toxic coloration of cotton fabric with natural dyes and natural mordanting agent will be the alternative way of conventional synthetic dyeing which is a threat of ecofriendly environment. Proposed technique can be implemented in the textile industries for having the nature friendly agro renewable sources of natural dyes. On the otherhand synthetic dyes is a petroleum sources of production. The concept and the workable procedures developed from the research can be transferred to industrial practice in home and abroad. The proposed research can provide simultaneous effect of dyeing, mordanting, technical finishing, ecofriendly coloration process in textiles is definitely a technological light in the door of colored textile production. Thus, there are sufficient scopes of doing scientific research on making standardization of technique, increasing color fastness to conventional process, adaptability, durability and suitability of process and product development.

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6

Objectives of Research:

- To develop completely eco friendly natural dyed and Natural Agent finished Cotton Textile Fabrics (Oeko-Tech Products) by adopting a Newer Technique of Simultaneous Natural Mordanting–Natural Dyeing–Natural Finishing in a single step to reduce energy cost, process Time , Processing costs and Effluent Load (which has not been done earlier).
- To investigate the single step processes and also completely eco-Friendly Products of cotton textiles using selective natural dyes and natural finishing agents using bio mordants and bio finishing agents obtained from extract of natural resources at reduced cost and energy.
- To analyse methods for specific identification of natural dyes on natural dyed and finished textile products for establishing natural dye mark.
- To commercialize of such oeko-tech (eco friendly) products of natural dyed and finished cotton textile products.

Materials and Methods:

Application of Different Biomordanting with Biomordanting Agents:

Effects of different degrees of premordanting, simultaneous mordanting, post mordanting with lemon leaves as natural mordanting agents and natural dye ability with selective natural dyes (say a banana pill, neem leaves, tea leaves, teak leaves, guava leaves, Jackfruit wood, basil leaves, eucalyptus leaves, pecker leaves, peach leaves as well as as per availability natural sources etc.) can be investigated. Effect of such biomodifications on colour parameters after dyeing of cotton and chemically and biochemically modified cotton and its colour fastness properties to light, washing, perspiration and rubbing can be studied. The photo fading behaviour of cotton and chemically and biochemically modified and dyed cotton materials after those modifications and pre-treatments and subsequent dyeing can be studied and an attempt can be taken to improve the same to a much better level of customer acceptability. Effects of different degree of chemical modifications on colour yield for the selective natural dyes can be studied. Cotton Textile materials dyed with natural dyes can be post-treated/finished with suitable natural agents for studying the effect of these after treatments on the improvement of colour yield, brightness and colour fastness behaviour of the dyed material. To improve the colour fastness properties for the selective natural dyes some pre or post-treatment with cationic or metallic complex compound or UV absorbers/suitable modifiers can be studied.

Process Development:

The fabrics can be pre-treated by the eco-friendly enzyme-based chemical pre-treatment processes for preparing it for simultaneous dyeing and finishing. After that different natural dyes say a banana pill, neem leaves, tea leaves, teak leaf, guava leaves, neem leaves, Jackfruit wood, basil leaves, eucalyptus leaves, pecker leaves, peach leaves as well as as per availability natural sources etc.) and natural finishing agent like coconut oil as UV absorber, neem and guava leaf as antimicrobial agent as well as selective mordanting agents can be applied on cotton fabric for trailing and experimentations on application of dyes and finishing agent on cotton and optimization of dyeing process variables for improved colour development and improvement of colour fastness, all analytical testing. Effects of variations of dyeing process variables on colour yield and dyeing kinetics for application of selective natural dyes on cotton and chemically modified cotton substrate can be investigated to understand the dyeing isotherm, rate of dyeing and other thermodynamic parameters for such dyeing. This will help to understand the dyeing behaviours of different natural dyes applied on cotton to get an idea of formulating better colour yield having specific standardized dyeing recipe for combined/compound shades by use of binary or ternary mixture of these natural dyes. For use of combination of natural dyes for generating compound shades, a study on the compatibility of such binary and a ternary mixture of dyes can be also studied, to understand and find a compatible combination of such dyes for cotton and chemically treated and modified cotton fabrics.

Process of Textile Properties and Dyeability Analysis:

Changes in structural features for different degrees of mordanting on cotton substrate can be investigated with the help of Spectrophotometer, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), FTIR Spectroscopy and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), High-Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPLC), Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GCMS), Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC), Carbon, Hydrogen, Nitrogen and Sulphur (CHNS) analyzer and X-ray diffraction pattern etc. and different fastness properties for explaining the major observations in these aspects. This will help to understand scientifically the scientific analysis of different changes in textile related property behaviour and dyeability in terms of changes in structural features of chemically modified cotton substrate along with changes in surface characteristics and durability etc.

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7

Major activities to be undertaken as follows during the total project implementation period :

[Implemented By Md. Anowar Hossain, Principal Investigator (PI)]

	Experimental Work Phases	Research Lab
1.	Extraction of natural dyes from dyed cotton textiles and their identification.	Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University
2.	Study of extraction of different natural dyes in different media and study of the chemistry and colour characteristics of the colour component of selective natural dyes to establish standard method and optimum conditions of extracting those natural dyes from different sources	Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University
3.	Studies on dyeing process variables and effect of different mordanting agents / mordanting methods on colour yield and fastness behaviour.	Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University
4.	Studies on effect of different degree of chemical modifications of cotton textiles on colour yield behaviour of selective natural dyes as well as natural mordanting.	Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University Dyeing lab-Mascom Composite Ltd, Konabari.
5.	Studies on effect of different degree of colour fastness behaviour of selective natural dyes as well as natural mordanting.	Wet Processing lab-Bangladesh Jute Research Institute (BJRI), Textile Dyeing lab-Mascom Composite Ltd, Konabari.
6.	Studies on authentication of test methods of identification of natural dye from outside nation and International accredited laboratories and analysis of results.	FEAT lab, Indian Institute of Technology, IIT, Kanpur, India Textile Coloration Lab, Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India
7.	Experimental Work-Phase –XII: Patenting and Publication of technical manuals/ notes Publication and Popularisation of natural dye standards at National and International level with establishing natural dye/finish mark to be implemented worldwide of natural dyed textiles.	City University
8.	Field Trial	Production Unit, Mascom Composite Ltd, Konabari.

Expected Outcomes:

Feasibility of natural dyeing, natural mordanting, natural finishing will be studied to achieve an ecofriendly approach of zero toxic coloration of cotton fabric with natural dyes and natural mordanting agents which will be tested by different advanced analytical method of natural coloration.

Natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural finishing agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing can be established by developing completely eco-friendly natural dyes and natural finishing agent which can be applied on cotton textiles (Oeko-Tech Products) by adopting a newer technique of simultaneous Mordanting-Dyeing-Finishing in a single step to reduce energy cost, process time, processing costs and effluent load as well as to develop the single step processes and also completely eco-friendly products of cotton textiles using selective natural dyes and natural finishing agents using bio mordants and bio finishing agents obtained from an extract of natural resources at reduced cost and energy. There is huge scope of commercialization of such Oeko-Tech (Eco-Friendly) products of natural dyed and finished cotton textile products for domestic and export market.

Proposed By Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Principal Investigator

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 M.Tech Textile Engg (CU, India), B.Sc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Researcher and Founder, Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Budget:	
Project activities with breakdown of cost of 1,50,000 BDT	Total Cost in BDT
Raw materials, Extraction, processing and experimentation charges: [Sample Collection (Natural Dyes) charge (10 Sample×500 BDT = 5000 BDT), Dyes preparation, Drying and Powder forming charge (10 Sample ×500 BDT = 5000 BDT), Machine charge for extraction of dyes: 5000 BDT, Fabric cost for trialing: 5000 BDT, Fabric pretreatment charge: 1500 BDT, Machine charge for dyeing and finishing (Laboratory stage trialing): 13000 BDT, Field trial = 5800 BDT]	35,300 BDT
Testing fees [Spectrophotometer (10 sample × 2000 BDT =20000 BDT), SEM-(5 sample × 2000 BDT =10000 BDT), Light fastness-(5 sample × 1000 BDT=5000 BDT), Color Fastness-(5 sample × 1000 BDT =5000 BDT), Wash Fastness (5 sample × 1000 BDT =5000 BDT), Color Fastness to perspiration (5 sample × 1000 BDT =5000 BDT)]	50,000 BDT
Conveyance, Research Coordination and Research Meeting Conveyance and allowance (Day Long) [Office/ residence to Jahangirnagar University (5 Day long × 300 BDT =1500 BDT), Residence to Mascom Composite (5 Day long×300 BDT=1500 BDT),Residence to Bangladesh Jute Research Institute (3 Day long × 500 BDT = 1500 BDT, Residence to Science Lab 3 Day long × 500BDT = 1500 BDT, Residence to SGS (Testing Lab) 2 Day long × 500 BDT=1000 BDT)] Conveyance and allowance (Half Day) [Office, Khagan to Jahangirnagar University (20 Day × 100 BDT=2000 BDT), Office to Mascom Composite Ltd. (20 Day×200BDT=4000 BDT),Permanent Campus to City Campus ,City University (10 Day× 500 BDT =5000 BDT)] Preliminary meeting with experts (2 expert×1000 BDT=2000 BDT), Meeting in experimental stage with experts (2 expert × 1000 BDT = 2000 BDT), Report preparation and review meeting (2 expert × 1000 BDT = 2000 BDT)] Mobile bill for raw material purchasing, Lab coordination, expert coordination and other coordination (6 Month × 1000 BDT= 6000 BDT).	30,000 BDT
Stationary and Administrative cost [Sample tube, Scissor, Tape, Tissue, Soap, Mask, Hand gloves, Sample file, Sample Swatch Board ,Aprone, Stapler, Punch m/c, Calculator, Pendrive, Filter paper, PH Strip, Seal, Tracing Paper, Note Book and others: 3000 BDT, Review allowance and study materials (Book/Journal): 2000 BDT, Networking and computer support (6 month× 500 BDT= 3000 BDT), Casual Personal Assistant Fees (10 days×400 BDT=4000 BDT), Refreshment for Lab assistant /Lab technician (20 Person×60 BDT=1200 BDT), Research Office access /Casual Office Refreshment (15 weeks×200 BDT=3000 BDT).	16200BDT
Report writing, edition and submission process Report writing allowance: 3000 BDT, Computer Compose allowance: 5000 BDT, Graphical Design & Edition allowance: 2000 BDT, Report Edition allowance: (5 time × 1000 BDT =5000 BDT, Printing and Drafting: (5 time × 200 BDT =1000 BDT, 10 Copy Thesis Binding: (10 copy × 250 BDT = 2500 BDT)	18,500BDT
Total	1,50,000BDT

[Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain will oversee the overall project and he will spend 20 hours/week as project investigator (additional duty of research and development), City University in different research laboratories like Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University, wet processing lab-Bangladesh Jute Research Institute, Textile Chemistry lab-City University, Dyeing lab-Mascom Composite Ltd, Konabari as well as others laboratory as per needs of proposed research.]

[A subsidiary fund (20,000 BDT) for working with research graded foreign lab (natural coloration lab, Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India) may be included with proposed budget/replaced with some activities (if possible) although foreign visit has been bamed in notification]

[Breakdown of cost may be changed/replaced by the principal investigator as per suitability of research progression during practical implementation of proposed research work]

Six Months/Twenty Four Weeks Timeline to Complete the Research:

Proposed By Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Principal Investigator

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Ph.D Researcher, School of Fashion and Textiles
RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
M. Tech. in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
engr.anowar@yahoo.com
Mobile: +61 452209738, +8801732681104

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head
Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Page | 64

Date: 22/11/2021

Professor Mir Akhter Hossain
Registrar
City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Letter of withdrawal the sanctioned research fund BDT 1, 00,000 (one lac), approved for Md. Anowar Hossain, lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Permanent campus, academic year: 2019-20.

Dear Sir,

I would like to notify that I am a lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science and Engineering; presently I am pursuing Ph.D research at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia funded by RTP stipend scholarship, an Australian Government Research program. I got a letter of "study leave" from registrar office, city university approved by Mr. M A Hannan, former Registrar, City University on 26 January 2020, ref: City University/Faculty/BSTE/4029/2020 and I left Bangladesh on 28 January 2020 and commenced Ph.D research at School of Fashion and Textiles on 5 February 2020.

154

In these circumstances, I would like to withdraw the official allotment of approved research fund BDT 1, 00, 000 (one lac), project duration: six months, academic year 2019-2020, notified by registrar office on 18 November 2019, proposal accepted by the committee of research cell, City University to continue the proposed research works on "zero toxic coloration on cotton fabric with natural dyes and natural mordanting agents" at office location, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, permanent campus and research location at chemistry lab, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka.

Thanks

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

Supporting information

Letter of research reporting issued by registrar office on 17 November 2021

Letter of study leave

Copy forwarded To

Professor (Dr.) Md. Humaun Kabir
Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Dean, Faculty of Science and Engineering

A/Professor (Dr.) Saiful Islam
Former Head, Department of Textile Engineering

16.1 Research Proposal

- Sabbih Hossain Rangan

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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- sabbih.hossain@gmail.com

To: me · Tue, Oct 22, 2019 at 11:17 AM

Message Body

Mr. Hossain

Please find the attached files. And send me the scanned copy of your reply by this afternoon.

Thank you.

S M Sabbih Hossain

Assistant Professor

Department of English

City University, Bangladesh

2 attachmentsDownload all

[Document 22 Oct 2019 11 11 am 1.jpgjpg · 1.3 MB](#)

[Document 22 Oct 2019 11 11 am 2.jpgjpg · 2.4 MB](#)

- Anowar Hossain

To: Sabbih · Tue, Oct 22, 2019 at 4:08 PM

Message Body

Dear Sir,

I acknowledge for primary selection of research funding and I am accepting the revised budget, one lac taka (only) for the research proposal on “Zero Toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural Mordanting Agents”.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain

Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Permanent Campus.

Page | 66

To

S. M. Sabbih Hossain

Member –Secretary

Research Cell

City University, Dhaka

Subject: Letter of Acceptation for the Revised Budget.

156

Dear Sir,

I acknowledge for primary selection of research funding and I am accepting the revised budget, one lac taka (only) for the research proposal on “Zero Toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural Mordanting Agents”.

Thanking you

Md. Anowar Hossain

Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Permanent Campus.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh);
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India, Australia, Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

October 22, 2019

Md. Anwar Hossain
Lecturer
Department of Textile Engineering
City University
13/A, Panthapath, Dhaka

Subject: Regarding your Research Proposal

Mr. Hossain

It is my pleasure to inform you that your research proposal: *Zero Toxic Coloration Fabric with Natural Dyes and Natural Mordanting Agents* is primarily selected for the 'funding' from the Research Cell, City University.

The budget you provided is reviewed and revised, and is attached to this letter. Please, go through the revised budget and reply to this letter with your comment (i.e. whether you accept it or not).

Thank you.

S. M. Sabbih Hossain
(22.10.19)

S. M. Sabbih Hossain
Member-Secretary
Research Cell
City University

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

115

Project activities with breakdown of cost of 1,00,000 BDT	Total Cost in BDT
Law materials, Extractions, processing and experimentation charges: Dye's Collection (Natural Dyes) charge (10 Sample×300 BDT = 3000 BDT), Dyes preparation, drying and Powder forming charge (10 Sample ×300 BDT = 3000 BDT), Machine charge for extraction of dyes: 5000 BDT, Fabric: 5000 BDT, Fabric pretreatment charge: 1500 BDT, Chemical/Apparatus: 5000BDT, Machine charge for dyeing and finishing (Laboratory stage trialing): 2000 BDT, Machine charge for dyeing and finishing (Field trialing): 10800 BDT]	30,000 BDT
Testing fees Spinning/Retraction (10 Sample × 1000 BDT =10000 BDT), SEM/FTIR sample × 2000 BDT =4000 BDT, Light fastness-(5 sample × 1000 BDT=5000 BDT), Color Fastness-(5 sample × 1,000 BDT =5000 BDT), Wash Fastness (5 sample × 1000 BDT =5000 BDT), Color Fastness to perspiration (5 sample × 1000 BDT =5000 BDT)	30,000 BDT
Research Meeting [Preliminary meeting with experts (2 expert×2000 BDT=4000 BDT), Meeting in experimental stage with experts (2 expert × 2000 BDT = 4000 BDT)]	8,000 BDT
Research Coordination with Pre-mentioned Laboratories Conveyance and allowance (Day Long) [Office/ residence to Jahangirnagar University (5 Day long × 300 BDT =1500 BDT), Residence to Mascom Composite (5 Day long×300 BDT=1500 BDT), Residence to Bangladesh Jute Research Institute (5 Day long × 500 BDT = 1500 BDT, Residence to Science Lab 5 Day long × 500 BDT = 1500 BDT) Conveyance and allowance (Half Day) [Office, Khagan to Jahangirnagar University (20 Day × 100 BDT=2000 BDT), Office to Mascom Composite Ltd. (20 Day×300 BDT=6000 BDT), Permanent Campus to City Campus ,City University (15 Day× 350 BDT =5250 BDT)]	16,000 BDT
Stationary and Administrative cost [Sample tube, Sample Box, Detergent, Mask, Hand gloves, Mask, Sample file, Sample Swatch Board, Pendrive, Filter paper, PH Strip, Seal, Tracing Paper, Note Book and others: 9750 BDT, Refreshment for Lab assistant /Lab technician in experimental stages (20 Person×60 BDT=1200 BDT)]	6,000 BDT
Report writing, edition, review and submission process [Report writing, edition and graphical Design: 6000 BDT, Review of report with expert: 5000 BDT, Printing and Drafting: (5 time × 300 BDT =1500 BDT, 10 Copy Thesis Binding: (10 copy × 300 BDT = 3000 BDT)]	10,000 BDT
Total: One Lac Taka Only	1,00,000 BDT

[Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain will oversee the overall project and he will spend 20 hours/week as project investigator (additional duty of research and development), City University in different research laboratories like Chemistry lab-Jahangirnagar University, wet processing lab-Bangladesh Jute Research Institute, Textile Chemistry lab-City University, Dyeing lab-Mascom Composite Ltd, Konabari as well as others laboratory as per needs of proposed research.]

[A subsidiary fund (20,000 BDT) for working with research grantee foreign lab (natural colorant lab, Department of Textile and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India) is being proposed as additional budget and/or the cost may be replaced with some activities (if possible) although foreign visit has been excluded in notification]

[Breakdown of cost/Categories of cost may be changed/replaced by the project investigator as per suitability reality of research progression during practical implementation of proposed research work as the work is laboratory based.]

Proposed By Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

**Research Cell
City University**

Notice

December 17, 2020

This is for your information that a meeting regarding the progress of the research project/s has been arranged by the Research Cell, City University on December 22, 2020 (Tuesday) at 10:30 a.m. at Pro-Vice-Chancellor's office. All the Principal Investigators are hereby requested to attend the meeting on due time.

159

(S. M. Sabbih Hossain)
Member-Secretary
Research Cell
City University

To:

1. Udayshankar Sarkar, Lecturer, Dept. of Business Administration
2. Rashedul Islam, Lecturer, Dept. of Business Administration
3. Md. Shakil, Lecturer, Dept. of Business Administration
4. Md. Anwar Hossain, Lecturer, Dept. of Textile
5. Shams Ul Islam, Lecturer, Dept of EEE
6. Md. Moniruzzaman Bhuyan, Lecturer, Dept. of ME
7. S. M. Sabbih Hossain, Assistant Professor, Dept. of English

16.2 Regarding the progress of your research project

- S. M. Sabbih Hossain

To: me, and 5 others · Thu, Dec 17, 2020 at 1:41 PM

Page | 70

Message Body

Please,

Find the attached file for a notice regarding the progress of the project.

Thank you.

With regards

(S. M. Sabbih Hossain)
Assistant Professor
Department of English
CITY UNIVERSITY
Permanent Campus: Khagan, Savar, Dhaka
City Campus: 13/A, Panthapath, Dhaka
Bangladesh
Mobile: +880 1717-049905
WhatsApp: +880 1717-049905
email: sabbih.hossain@cityuniversity.edu.bd / sabbih.hossain@gmail.com

160

17 Evidences of peer review of journal and publication

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- Sandra Maljavac
- sandra.m@intechopen.com

To: me · Thu, Sep 10, 2020 at 6:00 PM

Message Body

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia

Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Dear Dr. Hossain,

We are pleased to let you know that your chapter has now been published online. Congratulations!

Page | 71

Online First means chapters are published individually, after review and before the entire book is ready for publication, ensuring research is made available to the scientific community without delay.

Your chapter has been published in this way and is now searchable and citable by DOI, so you can start receiving citations and downloads immediately. Your open access chapter can be reused as you like, as the copyright remains yours and you gain impact immediately without being dependent on the last person to submit to the book.

Once the rest of the book is ready, it will become part of the broader publication.

161

You can view your chapter here: <https://www.intechopen.com/online-first/a-practical-guideline-of-few-standardized-ready-made-shades-of-natural-dyed-textiles>

Please check your publication promptly to ensure that it corresponds to the final version of your chapter.

Please feel free to share it with your colleagues and peers, and on social media.

Regards,

Sandra Maljavac
Author Service Manager

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London: 5 Princes Gate Court, London, SW7 2QJ, UK
+44 20 8089 5702
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IntechOpen - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Thu, Aug 27, 2020 at 1:46 PM

Message Body

Page | 72

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that all is well.

I have received the following email form our technical editors:

Corrections from the proof correction form have also been updated as per copy editing guidelines.

162

We have raised 11 queries to the author in the attached PDF. Please advise

Upon receiving your approval, we will do the required changes and re-upload the final package to panel. Thank you!

Please respond to these new queries as soon as you can so we can proceed with the final book preparation.

Regards,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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London: 10 Lower Thames Street, London, EC3R 6AF,
UK

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh); MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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**IntechOpen - Action Required - Proof Corrections - Chemistry and Technology of
Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments**

Page | 73

- Ms. Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Fri, Jul 31, 2020 at 1:43 AM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Your chapter in the book under the working title "Chemistry and Technology of
Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments," ISBN 978-1-78985-997-3 is ready for
proof corrections.

163

**NEXT STEP: Proof Corrections
DEADLINE: 06 August, 2020**

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This is the final round of corrections before the publication of your work and further editing will not be possible.

Page | 74

Once the rest of the book is ready, it will become part of the broader publication.

If you have any questions, feel free to contact me by phone or email.

Cordially,

Ms. Sandra Maljavac
Author Service Manager

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-
- Expand previously seen (1)
 - Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Mon, Aug 3, 2020 at 12:56 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Thank you, I have forwarded the corrections to our technical editors.

In case they'll have any additional questions, I'll let you know.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder, Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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All the best,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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- Re: IntechOpen - Action Required - Proof Corrections - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

Ms. Sandra Maljavac

CcBcc

Dear Ms. Sandra,

Thanks for your correction comments and working for improving the book chapter.

I have attached (pdf and word file) here all queries for your kind attention. Please try to shape this chapter by maintaining the “picture and text citation sequence” for readers easy understanding.

I have also uploaded the file in online system.

Please let me know if you face further difficulties to understand my comments for your edition process.

Thanks

Md. Anowar Hossain

On Friday, July 31, 2020, 05:43:25 AM GMT+10, Ms. Sandra Maljavac <sandra.m@intechopen.com> wrote:

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Your chapter in the book under the working title "Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments," ISBN 978-1-78985-997-3 is ready for proof corrections.

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This is the final round of corrections before the publication of your work and further editing will not be possible.

Once the rest of the book is ready, it will become part of the broader publication.

If you have any questions, feel free to contact me by phone or email.

Cordially,

Ms. Sandra Maljavac
 Author Service Manager

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2 attachments

Out of Office Re: IntechOpen - Action Required - Proof Corrections - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Jasna Bozic

To: me · Mon, Aug 3, 2020 at 8:06 AM

Message Body

Thank you for your email.

I am currently out of the office and will be back on August 17, 2020.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
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International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

My colleague, Ms. Sandra Maljavac (sandra.m@intechopen.com) will handle your inquiries and provide you with any assistance that you may need until my return.

Kind regards,
Jasna

Jasna Bozic | Author Service Manager
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- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Mon, Aug 3, 2020 at 7:56 AM

Message Body

Thank you for your email.

I am currently out of the office and will be back on August 3rd, 2020.

My colleague, Ms. Jasna Bozic (jasna.b@intechopen.com) will handle your inquiries and provide you with any assistance that you may need until my return.

Kind regards,
Sandra

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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IntechOpen - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Fri, Jul 10, 2020 at 12:46 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that you are doing well.

Our technical editors are currently working on your chapter and have sent me the following query:

- While editing, our editor found that the reference citations are missing in the manuscript but references are present. Kindly advise.

Please insert the reference citations in the text. I'm sending you the last version of the chapter attached to this email.

Looking forward to your response,

Sandra

--

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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- Expand previously seen (5)
- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Thu, Jul 16, 2020 at 1:56 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Thank you, I will forward your updated chapter.

Regards,

Sandra

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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FULL WAIVER - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Mon, Jun 29, 2020 at 4:56 PM

Message Body

171

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that you are doing well.

Since you haven't responded to none of my emails and we need to proceed with the book project, I would hereby like to grant a full waiver for the publication of your chapter.

This would save its contents and we still be able to enrich the final book product.

Please let me know if you agree with this offer.

Regards,

Sandra

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
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- Expand previously seen (1)
- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Tue, Jun 30, 2020 at 12:51 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Thank you for the confirmation.

I'll send you the typeset proof once it is ready.

Regards,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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London: 10 Lower Thames Street, London, EC3R 6AF, UK

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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URGENT- Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Wed, Jun 3, 2020 at 1:22 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that all is well on your side.

Please get in touch with me regarding your participation on the project. This task is **urgent**.

I am looking forward to your response.

Kind regards,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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Show trimmed content

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Wed, Jun 10, 2020 at 1:26 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Unfortunately, I still haven't received a response from your side.

Please note that any offer you may give will help us support the project financially.

I hope that you will respond and that we can continue with our collaboration.

Best,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 03. 06. 2020. 09:22, Sandra Maljavac wrote:

I hope that all is well on your side.

Please get in touch with me regarding your participation on the project. This task is **urgent**.

I am looking forward to your response.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Kind regards,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 28. 05. 2020. 12:40, Sandra Maljavac wrote:

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope to find you well.

Please let me know if you would be able to cover the minimum of 150 GBP.

We would be very grateful for your help in these regards and hope that you will response positively.

All the best,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 21. 05. 2020. 10:17, Sandra Maljavac wrote:

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Thank you for your reply, I appreciate your comprehensive explanation.

I understand your position and, if it were possible, would grant you a full waiver for the publication of your work.

However, we have already granted several full waivers in this project and the financial stats do not allow me to offer one to you as well.

For this reason, I kindly ask you to think about the amount that you would be able to pay in order to support the project's sustainability.

Even a smaller amount of, e.g. 150 GBP would help us to cover the basic expenses of processing your chapter and publishing it online.

Please let me know the amount that you would be able to afford, it would mean a lot to us.

Looking forward to your response,

Sandra

176

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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On 21. 05. 2020. 08:45, Anowar Hossain wrote:

177

Hi Sandra Maljavac,

I am very happy to work with you without payment and I am really sorry to response with your office that I am not prepared for publication of my book chapter under any payment condition. As contribution, I can just work for the development of publication, I can't pay, this is my professional limitation of any publication process.

Please I will be so much thankful if you avoid to send me discount message, I didn,t ask you for giving me any discount.

May I also request your office to publish free of cost as I wrote this manuscript for Intech.open, not for other publisher and as contributory support I gave you original experimental work, not as usual chapter writing. If you are not ready to publish free of cost, please give me back my manuscript and kindly send me the cancel notification of your acceptance due to disagree of author payment.

I think it will be my best reponse for your kind attention regarding payment issue for the publication of accepted chapter in the book of "Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments".

Thanks

Md. Anowar Hossain

On Wednesday, May 20, 2020, 06:29:50 PM GMT+10, Sandra Maljavac <sandra.m@intechopen.com> wrote:

Page | 88

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that you are doing well.

Unfortunately, I still haven't received your response.

In the meantime, I have discussed your chapter's registration with my Manager and we are open to offer you a 60% discount to the fee.

This would lower it to 560 GBP. Of course, the amount can be split into parts or among different sources that would cover it.

Please let me know if the discount could be acceptable to you.

178

Looking forward to your reply,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 13. 05. 2020. 10:06, Sandra Maljavac wrote:

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that all is well on your side.

Please get in touch with me regarding your participation on the project.

I am looking forward to your response.

Kind regards,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 06. 05. 2020. 08:14, Sandra Maljavac wrote:

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that you are doing well.

Since we haven't spoken for a while, I just wanted to check in to see if you have spoken to your library's management or found any other source of funding?

Please send me an update and let me know if there is anything I can help you with.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Looking forward to your reply,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 29. 04. 2020. 09:31, Sandra Maljavac wrote:

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Our authors are usually able to confirm the number of books their library or university will order prior to the book publication.

This is because, once the book is out, we have not way in managing your registration any longer and cannot generate an invoice retroactively.

Also, please note that your library can purchase books of any title, it doesn't have to be this book that you are currently contributing to.

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The following book will also be ready for publication in the following months, I believe it could be of interest for

you: <https://www.intechopen.com/welcome/36eb1ed7179e0790a029523c97f1df04>

Looking forward to your reply,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 29. 04. 2020. 01:54, Anowar Hossain wrote:

Hi Sandra,

Thanks for your explanation.

But I have no way to confirm the number of copy as it is fully controlled by university administration.

I can only make the purchase requisition after having the book in ready condition & all marketing process will have to deal by your intech. office and I have no rights to involve with this process.

Please give me a list of all of your textile engineering book if I need I will give purchase requisition.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Thanks

Md. Anowar Hossain

On Tuesday, April 28, 2020, 04:37:18 PM GMT+10, Sandra Maljavac <sandra.m@intechopen.com> wrote:

Page | 92

Dear Dr. Hossain,

We can define the quantity of book the library would buy now and the payment can be done after the book publication.

Please note that I need this information prior to the final publication because I need to plan the project's sustainability and report on its financial stats.

We would be grateful if you could contact you library and inquire regarding their funding abilities and if they could order the mentioned 9 hard copies (9 * 90 GBP = 810 GBP).

This way we could resolve the issue of your chapter's funding and the fee would be covered by the book purchase.

182

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Looking forward to your reply,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 27. 04. 2020. 22:41, Anowar Hossain wrote:

Hi Sandra,

As per your below mail reference I can fill the form of library when the book will be available in online for selling and library office will ensure library copy both in online & hardcopy for library study reference and my study support, but the quantity of book & price everything will be done by library administration as per rules of university and your Intech. office will be responsible for marketing & selling your book.

183

Additional inquiry from for my understanding: As I know, Intech is a open access publisher, please let me know if your book is available in online, why readers/library should purchase your book and if you sell the book what will be benefit for authors.

Thanks

Md. Anowar Hossain

On Monday, April 27, 2020, 04:34:21 PM GMT+10, Sandra
 Maljavac <sandra.m@intechopen.com> wrote:

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Thank you for your response.

Please find attached the list of chapters and authors whose chapters will be included in the final publication.

The official PDF of the book hasn't yet been generated so I can't send it to you, but this list reflects the work that we have collected so far.

As you can see, we will even include the editor's chapter. Please feel free to use this list and send it to your library.

Page | 94

I am sure that you will find the titles of interest as they all include very relevant and up-to-date research results.

Please let me know if your library would be interested to order several book copies (90 GBP per copy). They would need to order 9 copies so that we can grant the 40% discount offer.

We will make sure to send one hard copy to you for free.

Looking forward to your reply,

Sandra

184

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 26. 04. 2020. 07:41, Anowar Hossain wrote:

Dear Madam,

Hope you are fine & well protected from COVID 19.

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Sorry I am responding so delay when you are discussing with payment issue as I have a same reply again and again that I am completely unable to pay publication fees if you want to support my progress i.e fine.

Option as a Ph.D Researcher at RMIT University:

As per your option asked in previous mail, before confirming any book order at RMIT University I need to know all chapters and book in ready condition if any chapter matches with my present project here as study materials I have a rights to fill the requisition form to the library for your book purchasing.

Regards

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, M.Tech.

Ph.D Researcher

RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

On Monday, April 20, 2020, 04:11:45 PM GMT+10, Sandra Maljavac <sandra.m@intechopen.com> wrote:

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Thank you for your reply.

Please note that we have discussed the payment as early as mid-March where you have also expressed your inability to pay.

I have then sent you a list of options that might help you and haven't received your response since.

However, in order to save your work and progress, I am able to offer you a **40% discount** which would lower the fee to **840 GBP**.

This amount can be split into monthly installments or I can extend the payment deadline, if necessary.

Please let me know what you think. I am looking forward to your response.

Cordially,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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186

On 18. 04. 2020. 09:11, Anowar Hossain wrote:

Sandra Maljavac

Author Service Manager

Office of [intech. open](http://intech.open)

Dear Madam,

Thanks for your acceptance of my manuscript submission as a chapter of a book edited by Professor A K Samanta.

I am little bit confused with the below mail of payment.

Please proceed my publication without charging me.

Thanks for your kind acceptance with zero cost publication process.

Md. Anowar Hossain

On Friday, April 17, 2020, 12:00:12 AM GMT+10, Sandra Maljavac sandra.m@intechopen.com wrote:

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁸ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Dear Dr. Hossain,

Your OAPF Proforma Invoice is available on your Author Panel.

CHAPTER TITLE: A Pantone Book of Natural Dyes for Natural Coloration on Natural Fibre
 BOOK TITLE: Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments
 PROFORMA INVOICE NO.: 1641-2020
 YOUR PAYMENT IS DUE ON: 09 May, 2020

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 Please contact your Author Service Manager
 for further assistance.

DISCOUNT OFFER- Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Sandra Maljavac

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Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
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To: me · Wed, May 20, 2020 at 2:29 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Page | 98

I hope that you are doing well.

Unfortunately, I still haven't received your response.

In the meantime, I have discussed your chapter's registration with my Manager and we are open to offer you a 60% discount to the fee.

This would lower it to 560 GBP. Of course, the amount can be split into parts or among different sources that would cover it.

Please let me know if the discount could be acceptable to you.

188

Looking forward to your reply,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

According to our records we have not yet received your OAPF payment for:

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BOOK TITLE: Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

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Thank you for your attention regarding this matter.

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- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Thu, May 14, 2020 at 8:00 PM

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Dear Dr. Hossain,

We would like to inform you that your OAPF payment deadline has passed.

CHAPTER TITLE: A Pantone Book of Natural Dyes for Natural Coloration on Natural Fibre

BOOK TITLE: Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

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Thank you for your attention regarding this matter.

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To: me · Thu, Apr 16, 2020 at 8:00 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Your OAPF Proforma Invoice is available on your Author Panel.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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CHAPTER TITLE: A Pantone Book of Natural Dyes for Natural Coloration on Natural Fibre
 BOOK TITLE: Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments
 PROFORMA INVOICE NO.: 1641-2020
 YOUR PAYMENT IS DUE ON: 09 May, 2020

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Thank you for your attention regarding this matter.

 This is an automated message.
 Please contact your Author Service Manager
 for further assistance.

- Expand previously seen (9)
- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Wed, May 13, 2020 at 2:06 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that all is well on your side.

Please get in touch with me regarding your participation on the project.

I am looking forward to your response.

Page | 102

Kind regards,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

+44 20 8089 5700 | intechopen.com

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192

IntechOpen - OAPF Payment Reminder

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Mon, May 4, 2020 at 8:00 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

This is a reminder that your OAPF payment due date is approaching.

CHAPTER TITLE: A Pantone Book of Natural Dyes for Natural Coloration on Natural Fibre

BOOK TITLE: Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

PROFORMA INVOICE NO.: 1641-2020

PAYMENT DUE: 09 May, 2020

Please proceed to your Author Panel to complete your payment:

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Thank you for your attention regarding this matter.

URGENT- response needed

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Tue, Apr 14, 2020 at 2:59 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that all is well on your side.

Please get in touch with me regarding your participation on the project.

I am looking forward to your response.

Kind regards,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

+44 20 8089 5700 | intechopen.com

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IntechOpen - OAPF Payment

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Thu, Apr 9, 2020 at 4:01 AM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

194

Your OAPF Proforma Invoice is now available on your Author Panel.

CHAPTER TITLE: A Pantone Book of Natural Dyes for Natural Coloration on Natural Fibre

BOOK TITLE: Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

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IntechOpen - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Mon, Mar 30, 2020 at 11:47 AM

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope to find you well.

Please find attached the editor's comments regarding your chapter and the requested revision.

I am at your disposal in case of further questions or concerns.

Kind regards,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

+44 20 8089 5700 | intechopen.com

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IntechOpen - Final Notice of Acceptance - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Fri, Apr 3, 2020 at 5:00 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Following the submission of your revised chapter, please find your formal Notification of Chapter Acceptance attached to this email. Congratulations once again on your acceptance!

Next Step: Language Copyediting and Typeset

In order to ensure the highest quality of published content, your chapter will now enter Language

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Copyediting and Typeset. Our Language Copyeditors will proofread your chapter and improve grammar, spelling, style, and accuracy if necessary, while our Technical Editors prepare your chapter for online publication.

A finalized version of your work will be sent to you to be reviewed before publication.

Page | 106

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If you have any additional questions or concerns, do not hesitate to contact me.

Cordially,

196

Sandra Maljavac
Author Service Manager

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IntechOpen - Minor Review Requested - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

- Sandra Maljavac

To: me · Mon, Mar 30, 2020 at 11:46 AM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I am pleased to inform you that your chapter titled "A Pantone Book of Natural Dyes for Natural

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Coloration on Natural Fibre," submitted to the book under the working title "Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments," has been reviewed. The Editor has accepted your full chapter but requested that you implement some minor changes outlined in the review comments.

In the attachment you will find recommendations/suggestions for changes from the Editor(s) that would improve the overall quality of your chapter.

Current Step: Upload Revision

Upload your revised chapter on your Author Panel incorporating the review comments within the next 3 days.

Next Step:

Language Copyediting and Typeset Proof. Once your revision is uploaded, your paper will undergo specialized proofreading and editing to improve grammar, spelling, style, and accuracy at no additional charge, while our Technical Editors prepare your chapter for online publication.

By way of saying thank you for your hard work, when your full chapter is accepted for publication you can pre-order your book and get one print copy for free on the first order you place. All contributing authors can benefit from this exclusive promotion available only through your Author Panel.

If you have any additional questions or concerns, do not hesitate to contact me.

Cordially,

Sandra Maljavac
 Author Service Manager

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Chapter Submission for the book of "Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments (ISBN 978-1-78985-998-0)" edited by Professor A K Samanta

- Anowar Hossain

To: sandra.m@intechopen.com · Wed, Mar 18, 2020 at 7:21 AM

Message Body

Sandra Maljavac

Author Service Manager, IntechOpen

10 Lower Thames Street, London, EC3R 6AF, UK

Page | 108

Dear Madam,

Please below chapter is being submitted both in PDF and word format for the book of "Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments (ISBN 978-1-78985-998-0)" edited by Professor A K Samanta. I am fail to upload electronically as I have nothing to mention funding option which is the requirement to fill the second step of online uploading.

A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles

Md. Anowar Hossain

198

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Thanks for your kind action to publish my chapter.

Regards

Md. Anowar Hossain

Ph.D Researcher, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

2 attachmentsDownload all

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- Expand previously seen (2)
- Sandra Maljavac

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To: me · Mon, Mar 23, 2020 at 4:22 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

I hope that you are doing well.

Since we haven't spoken for a while, I just wanted to check in to see if you have reviewed my proposed solutions?

Please send me an update and let me know if there is anything I can help you with.

Looking forward to your reply,

Sandra

Subject: your chapter proposal is accepted and see in your author's panel in intech open site for book and also to See the mail to me from Ms Sandra Maljavac as new author service manager of IntechOpen - for the book on Chemistry and Technology of Natu...

- Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta

To: me, Cc: Prof. · Sat, Feb 15, 2020 at 11:35 PM

Message Body

From: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>

Sent: Friday, 14 February 2020, 17:58

To: anowar hossain

Subject: Fw: See the mail to me from Ms Sandra Maljavac as new author service manager of IntechOpen - for the book on Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments-- asking new chapter proposal

Dear anowar ,

Your chapter proposal is accepted with minor modification desired by the editor .

See the mail from new Author Service manager -Ms Sandra Maljavac to me for In Tech open wishing new chapter proposals alert to me when it will arrive etc

So do it now without delay ...to submit your full chapter with abstract after signing in with registeted id and password in In Tech open .com -under Book section by signing on ---and send

the same by mail also to ms sandra maljavac as new author service manager of intech , and also uploading it in intech open book site from author's panel . Get all your communicated transaction and communication for appointing you as aithor of this book from document and history menu in author's panel of you . Submit full chapter now as soon as possible to ms sandra maljavac (e mail : sandra.m@intechopen.com) .

Page | 110

See my comments as editor in tour aithor panel in intech open site by signing on there to see my all suugestons i.e to change title and to improve the chapter presentation as per template availble in author's panel. Do not give too much shades and pictures . Give all colorometric measurements and fastness for all important shades with setails of mordanting and dyeing process and conditions for each shade given.

Thanks

Prof A k Samanta

From: Sandra Maljavac <sandra.m@intechopen.com>

Sent: Friday, February 14, 2020 5:38 PM

To: Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>

Subject: Re: Wecome to Ms Sandra Maljavac as new author service manager of IntechOpen - for the book on Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

200

Dear Dr. Samanta,

Thank you for your email and your warm welcome.

I am happy to be on board with you on the project and will send you an update as soon as new chapters arrive.

Also, I will notify you once the review for your chapter comes in.

Have a nice day,

Sandra

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁸ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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On 14. 02. 2020. 12:44, Prof. Ashis kumar Samanta wrote:

201

Ms Sandra Maljavac
 Author Service Manager
 In Tech Open

for the Book on Chemistry and Technology of Natural and synthetic dyes and pigments

+44 20 8089 5700 | intechopen.com

Rijeka: Janeza Trdine 9, 51000 Rijeka, Croatia

London: 10 Lower Thames Street, London, EC3R 6AF, UK

Dear Sandra madam,

I welcome you as new author service manager for the book on Chemistry and
 Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments to be published by In Tech
 Open.

Pls see that i have done and completed review of new chapter proposal for Dr Anowar
 Hossain . Ask Dr anowar Hossain and others who have not yet uploaded their full
 chapter , to send/upload full chapter as soon as possible .

If any new chapter proposal is uploaded or registered , let me know with Mail alert to

complete my review soon.

My chapter is still under review. As soon as you get the review report, send it to me for action, if any to do.

Page | 112

Hoping everything well to complete this book within the time limit

Prof A K Samanta
Professor and Former HOD, DJFT, IJT, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

From: Sandra Maljavac <sandra.m@intechopen.com>
Sent: Thursday, February 13, 2020 6:32 PM
To: Nasser Awwad <nsawwad20@yahoo.com>
Cc: ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com <ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com>
Subject: Re: IntechOpen - Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments

202

Dear Dr. Anowar,

Thank you for your kind words.

We are currently waiting for a couple chapters to be finalized. One authors needs to send a revision and two others need to submit a chapter for review.

Also, Prof. Samanta's chapter is currently under review with an external reviewer and I will be sending the results soon.

I hope that the book will be ready for final processing in the upcoming month.

Kind regards,
Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

+44 20 8089 5700 | intechopen.com

Rijeka: Janeza Trdine 9, 51000 Rijeka, Croatia

London: 10 Lower Thames Street, London, EC3R 6AF, UK

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On 13. 02. 2020. 13:22, Nasser Awwad wrote:

Dear Mrs Sandra

welcome and happy to be with us as new Author Service Manager for our book project
 "Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments. I would ask you about
 , what the current status for this book .

203

my regards

Nasser Awwad

Nasser S Awwad

Professor of Inorganic and Radiochemistry

Chemistry department, faculty of Science, King Khalid University

Box office # 9004, postal code: 61413, Mobile: 00966549323204 & 00966563764476,

Telephone office: 0172417420

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<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3477-6996>

Page | 114

On Thursday, February 13, 2020, 3:09:19 PM GMT+3, Sandra Maljavac <sandra.m@intechopen.com> wrote:

Dear Prof. Samanta,

I hope that you are doing well.

I just wanted to reach out and introduce myself as the new Author Service Manager for the book project "Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments".

I hope that we will have a successful collaboration and that we will pick up from where you left off without any problems.

204

Please feel free to contact me in case you have further questions or concerns.

Cordially,

Sandra

Sandra Maljavac | Author Service Manager

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IntechOpen - Your Chapter Proposal has been Approved - "Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments"

- To: me · Thu, Feb 13, 2020 at 6:10 PM

Message Body

Dear Dr. Hossain,

Following up on my previous email, I would like to confirm that the editor, Prof. Samanta has approved your chapter proposal "A Pantone Book of Natural Dyes for Natural Coloration on Natural Fibre."

205

Below are some suggestions for you to incorporate in your full chapter manuscript:

"This is a very good chapter proposal for practical use to have and present a ready made variety of colored shades with details of recipe and process conditions for few standardized shades using single and mixture of natural colours .

BUt Author should avoid the term or word " Pantone " as it is a registered trade mark for particular company . Hence title should be rtevised as follows : 'A practical guideline of 'few standardized ready made shades of natural dyed textiles " .

It is not understood from abstract how much systematically the matter will be placed . My suggestion is to give Name of the Dye, chemical structure of dye , Name of the Moradant and Filbres concern ,with details of dye extraction , pre -mordanting and dyeing conditions and dyeing process followed for each such shades. Do not give more than 20 such shades and their details. Give an introduction for care and precaution needed for preparation of the fabric before mordanting and natural dyeing and after treatment , if any.

Authors must add all-round of colour fastness data and after treatment to improve it . For each shade, details of cares for tonal variations and estimated colour values like K/s and X, Y and Z values or RGB values must be given for each sahde for on line communication of colour without sending samples.

The chapter proposal may be accepted with incorporation of above matters."

If you have any questions or need any clarification regarding any of our editors suggestions, please let me know.

Page | 116

NEXT STEP: Submit your full chapter (10 to 20 pages) within the next 30 days.

For the preparation of your chapter please use the Templates that can be found by signing in to your Author Panel under the Quick Links section.

To sign in to your Author Panel please use the following link: <https://mts.intechopen.com/booksprocess/action/chapter/211890>

After the full chapter review, you will receive the notification regarding the definitive acceptance of your work in the book.

206

Let me know if you need any further help.

Cordially,

Sandra Maljavac
Author Service Manager

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18 Cited legal explanation of India and Australia about tax in research project

18.1 Expenditure on scientific research, Income Tax Act, 1961, India

35. (1) In respect of expenditure on scientific research, the following deductions shall be allowed—

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(i) any expenditure (not being in the nature of capital expenditure) laid out or expended on scientific research related to the business.

Explanation.—Where any such expenditure has been laid out or expended before the commencement of the business (not being expenditure laid out or expended before the 1st day of April, 1973) on payment of any salary as defined in Explanation 2 below sub-section (5) of section 40A to an employee engaged in such scientific research or on the purchase of materials used in such scientific research, the aggregate of the expenditure so laid out or expended within the three years immediately preceding the commencement of the business shall, to the extent it is certified by the prescribed authority to have been laid out or expended on such scientific research, be deemed to have been laid out or expended in the previous year in which the business is commenced ;

(ii) an amount equal to one and one half times of any sum paid to a research association which has as its object the undertaking of scientific research or to a university, college or other institution to be used for scientific research:

Provided that such association, university, college or other institution for the purposes of this clause—

(A) is for the time being approved, in accordance with the guidelines, in the manner and subject to such conditions as may be prescribed; and

(B) such association, university, college or other institution is specified as such, by notification in the Official Gazette, by the Central Government:

Provided further that where any sum is paid to such association, university, college or other institution in a previous year relevant to the assessment year beginning on or after the 1st day of April, 2021, the deduction under this clause shall be equal to the sum so paid;

(iia) any sum paid to a company to be used by it for scientific research:

Provided that such company—

(A) is registered in India,

(B) has as its main object the scientific research and development,

(C) is, for the purposes of this clause, for the time being approved by the prescribed authority in the prescribed manner, and

(D) fulfils such other conditions as may be prescribed;

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

(iii) any sum paid to a research association which has as its object the undertaking of research in social science or statistical research or to a university, college or other institution to be used for research in social science or statistical research:

Provided that such association, university, college or other institution for the purposes of this clause—

(A) is for the time being approved, in accordance with the guidelines, in the manner and subject to such conditions as may be prescribed; and

(B) such association, university, college or other institution is specified as such, by notification in the Official Gazette, by the Central Government.

Explanation.—The deduction, to which the assessee is entitled in respect of any sum paid to a research association, university, college or other institution to which clause (ii) or clause (iii) or to a company to which clause (iia) applies, shall not be denied merely on the ground that, subsequent to the payment of such sum by the assessee, the approval granted to the association, university, college or other institution referred to in clause (ii) or clause (iii) or to a company referred to in clause (iia) has been withdrawn;

(iv) in respect of any expenditure of a capital nature on scientific research related to the business carried on by the assessee, such deduction as may be admissible under the provisions of sub-section (2) :

Provided that the research association, university, college or other institution referred to in clause (ii) or clause (iii) shall make an application in the prescribed form and manner to the Central Government for the purpose of grant of approval, or continuance thereof, under clause (ii) or, as the case may be, clause (iii) :

Provided further that the Central Government may, before granting approval under clause (ii) or clause (iii), call for such documents (including audited annual accounts) or information from the research association, university, college or other institution as it thinks necessary in order to satisfy itself about the genuineness of the activities of the research association, university, college or other institution and that Government may also make such inquiries as it may deem necessary in this behalf :

Provided also that any notification issued, by the Central Government under clause (ii) or clause (iii), before the date on which the Taxation Laws (Amendment) Bill, 2006 receives the assent of the President, shall, at any one time, have effect for such assessment year or years, not exceeding

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three assessment years (including an assessment year or years commencing before the date on which such notification is issued) as may be specified in the notification:

Provided also that where an application under the first proviso is made on or after the date on which the Taxation Laws (Amendment) Bill, 2006 receives the assent of the President, every notification under clause (ii) or clause (iii) shall be issued or an order rejecting the application shall be passed within the period of twelve months from the end of the month in which such application was received by the Central Government:

Provided also that every notification under clause (ii) or clause (iii) in respect of the research association, university, college or other institution or under clause (iia) in respect of the company issued on or before the date on which this proviso has come into force, shall be deemed to have been withdrawn unless such research association, university, college or other institution referred to in clause (ii) or clause (iii) or the company referred to in clause (iia) makes an intimation in such form and manner, as may be prescribed, to the prescribed income-tax authority within three months from the date on which this proviso has come into force, and subject to such intimation the notification shall be valid for a period of five consecutive assessment years beginning with the assessment year commencing on or after the 1st day of April, 2022:

Provided also that any notification issued by the Central Government under clause (ii) or clause (iia) or clause (iii), after the date on which the Taxation and Other Laws (Relaxation and Amendment of Certain Provisions) Bill, 2020 receives the assent of the President, shall, at any one time, have effect for such assessment year or years, not exceeding five assessment years as may be specified in the notification.

(1A) Notwithstanding anything contained in sub-section (1), the deduction in respect of any sum paid to the research association, university, college or other institution referred to in clause (ii) or clause (iii), or the company referred to in clause (iia) of sub-section (1), shall not be allowed, unless such research association, university, college or other institution or company—

- i) prepares such statement for such period as may be prescribed and deliver or cause to be delivered to the said prescribed income-tax authority or the person authorised by such authority such statement in such form, verified in such manner, setting forth such particulars and within such time, as may be prescribed:

Provided that such research association, university, college or other institution or the company may also deliver to the prescribed authority a correction statement for rectification of any mistake or to add, delete or update the information furnished in the statement delivered under this sub-section in such form and verified in such manner as may be prescribed;

(ii) furnishes to the donor, a certificate specifying the amount of donation in such manner, containing such particulars and within such time from the date of receipt of sum, as may be prescribed.

(2) For the purposes of clause (iv) of sub-section (1),

(i) in a case where such capital expenditure is incurred before the 1st day of April, 1967, one-fifth of the capital expenditure incurred in any previous year shall be deducted for that previous year; and the balance of the expenditure shall be deducted in equal instalments for each of the four immediately succeeding previous years;

(ia) in a case where such capital expenditure is incurred after the 31st day of March, 1967, the whole of such capital expenditure incurred in any previous year shall be deducted for that previous year:

Provided that no deduction shall be admissible under this clause in respect of any expenditure incurred on the acquisition of any land, whether the land is acquired as such or as part of any property, after the 29th day of February, 1984.

Explanation 1. Where any capital expenditure has been incurred before the commencement of the business, the aggregate of the expenditure so incurred within the three years immediately preceding the commencement of the business shall be deemed to have been incurred in the previous year in which the business is commenced.

Explanation 2. For the purposes of this clause,

(a) "land" includes any interest in land ; and

(b) the acquisition of any land shall be deemed to have been made by the assessee on the date on which the instrument of transfer of such land to him has been registered under the Registration Act, 1908 (16 of 1908), or where he has taken or retained the possession of such land or any part thereof in part performance of a contract of the nature referred to in section 53A of the Transfer of Property Act, 1882 (4 of 1882), the date on which he has so taken or retained possession of such land or part ;

(ii) notwithstanding anything contained in clause (i), where an asset representing expenditure of a capital nature incurred before the 1st day of April, 1967, ceases to be used in a previous year for scientific research related to the business and the value of the asset at the time of the cessation, together with the aggregate of deductions already allowed under clause (i) falls short of the said expenditure, then—

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- (a) there shall be allowed a deduction for that previous year of an amount equal to such deficiency, and
- (b) no deduction shall be allowed under that clause for that previous year or for any subsequent previous year;
- (iii) if the asset mentioned in clause (ii) is sold, without having been used for other purposes, in the year of cessation, the sale price shall be taken to be the value of the asset at the time of the cessation ; and if the asset is sold, without having been used for other purposes, in a previous year subsequent to the year of cessation, and the sale price falls short of the value of the asset taken into account at the time of cessation, an amount equal to the deficiency shall be allowed as a deduction for the previous year in which the sale took place;
- (iv) where a deduction is allowed for any previous year under this section in respect of expenditure represented wholly or partly by an asset, no deduction shall be allowed under clause (ii) of sub-section (1) of section 32 for the same or any other previous year in respect of that asset;
- (v) where the asset mentioned in clause (ii) is used in the business after it ceases to be used for scientific research related to that business, depreciation shall be admissible under clause (ii) of sub-section (1) of section 32.

(2A) Where, before the 1st day of March, 1984, the assessee pays any sum (being any sum paid with a specific direction that the sum shall not be used for the acquisition of any land or building or construction of any building) to a scientific research association or university or college or other institution referred to in clause (ii) of sub-section (1) or to a public sector company to be used for scientific research undertaken under a programme approved in this behalf by the prescribed authority having regard to the social, economic and industrial needs of India, then,—

- (a) there shall be allowed a deduction of a sum equal to one and one-third times the sum so paid ; and
- (b) no deduction in respect of such sum shall be allowed under clause (ii) of sub-section (1) for the same or any other assessment year.

Explanation.—For the purposes of this sub-section, "public sector company" shall have the same meaning as in clause (b) of the Explanation below sub-section (2B) of section 32A.

(2AA) Where the assessee pays any sum to a National Laboratory or a University or an Indian Institute of Technology or a specified person with a specific direction that the said sum shall be

used for scientific research undertaken under a programme approved in this behalf by the prescribed authority, then—

(a) there shall be allowed a deduction of a sum equal to one and one-half times the sum so paid; and

(b) no deduction in respect of such sum shall be allowed under any other provision of this Act:

Provided that the prescribed authority shall, before granting approval, satisfy itself about the feasibility of carrying out the scientific research and shall submit its report to the Principal Chief Commissioner or Chief Commissioner or Principal Director General or Director General in such form as may be prescribed:

Provided further that where any sum is paid to such National Laboratory or university or Indian Institute of Technology or specified person in a previous year relevant to the assessment year beginning on or after the 1st day of April, 2021, the deduction under this sub-section shall be equal to the sum so paid.

Explanation 1.—The deduction, to which the assessee is entitled in respect of any sum paid to a National Laboratory, University, Indian Institute of Technology or a specified person for the approved programme referred to in this sub-section, shall not be denied merely on the ground that, subsequent to the payment of such sum by the assessee, the approval granted to,—

(a) such Laboratory, or specified person has been withdrawn; or

(b) the programme, undertaken by the National Laboratory, University, Indian Institute of Technology or specified person, has been withdrawn.

Explanation 2.—For the purposes of this section,—

(a) "National Laboratory" means a scientific laboratory functioning at the national level under the aegis of the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, the Indian Council of Medical Research, the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, the Defence Research and Development Organisation, the Department of Electronics, the Department of Bio-Technology or the Department of Atomic Energy and which is approved as a National Laboratory by the prescribed authority in such manner as may be prescribed ;

(b) "University" shall have the same meaning as in Explanation to clause (ix) of section 47 ;

(c) "Indian Institute of Technology" shall have the same meaning as that of "Institute" in clause (g) of section 3 of the Institutes of Technology Act, 1961 (59 of 1961);

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(d) "specified person" means such person as is approved by the prescribed authority.

(2AB)(1) Where a company engaged in the business of bio-technology or in any business of manufacture or production of any article or thing, not being an article or thing specified in the list of the Eleventh Schedule incurs any expenditure on scientific research (not being expenditure in the nature of cost of any land or building) on in-house research and development facility as approved by the prescribed authority, then, there shall be allowed a deduction of a sum equal to one and one-half times of the expenditure so incurred:

Provided that where such expenditure on scientific research (not being expenditure in the nature of cost of any land or building) on in-house research and development facility is incurred in a previous year relevant to the assessment year beginning on or after the 1st day of April, 2021, the deduction under this clause shall be equal to the expenditure so incurred.

Explanation.—For the purposes of this clause, "expenditure on scientific research", in relation to drugs and pharmaceuticals, shall include expenditure incurred on clinical drug trial, obtaining approval from any regulatory authority under any Central, State or Provincial Act and filing an application for a patent under the Patents Act, 1970 (39 of 1970).

- (2) No deduction shall be allowed in respect of the expenditure mentioned in clause (1) under any other provision of this Act.
- (3) No company shall be entitled for deduction under clause (1) unless it enters into an agreement with the prescribed authority for co-operation in such research and development facility and fulfils such conditions with regard to maintenance of accounts and audit thereof and furnishing of reports in such manner as may be prescribed.
- (4) The prescribed authority shall submit its report in relation to the approval of the said facility to the Principal Chief Commissioner or Chief Commissioner or Principal Director General or Director General in such form and within such time as may be prescribed.
- (5) [***]
- (6) No deduction shall be allowed to a company approved under sub-clause (C) of clause (ia) of sub-section (1) in respect of the expenditure referred to in clause (1) which is incurred after the 31st day of March, 2008.

(2B)(a) Where, before the 1st day of March, 1984, an asses see has incurred any expenditure (not being in the nature of capital expenditure incurred on the acquisition of any land or building or construction of any building) on scientific research undertaken under a programme approved in this behalf by the pre scribed authority having regard to the social, economic and industrial needs

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of India, he shall, subject to the provisions of this sub-section, be allowed a deduction of a sum equal to one and one-fourth times the amount of the expenditure certified by the prescribed authority to have been so incurred during the previous year.

(b) Where a deduction has been allowed under clause (a) for any previous year in respect of any expenditure, no deduction in respect of such expenditure shall be allowed under clause (i) of sub-section (1) or clause (ia) of sub-section (2) for the same or any other previous year.

(c) Where a deduction is allowed for any previous year under this sub-section in respect of expenditure represented wholly or partly by an asset, no deduction shall be allowed in respect of that asset under clause (ii) of sub-section (1) of section 32 for the same or any subsequent previous year.

(d) Any deduction made under this sub-section in respect of any expenditure on scientific research in excess of the expenditure actually incurred shall be deemed to have been wrongly made for the purposes of this Act if the assessee fails to furnish within one year of the period allowed by the prescribed authority for completion of the programme, a certificate of its completion obtained from that authority, and the provisions of sub-section (5B) of section 155 shall apply accordingly.

(3) If any question arises under this section as to whether, and if so, to what extent, any activity constitutes or constituted, or any asset is or was being used for, scientific research, the Board shall refer the question to—

(a) the Central Government, when such question relates to any activity under clauses (ii) and (iii) of sub-section (1), and its decision shall be final;

(b) the prescribed authority, when such question relates to any activity other than the activity specified in clause (a), whose decision shall be final.

(4) The provisions of sub-section (2) of section 32 shall apply in relation to deductions allowable under clause (iv) of sub-section (1) as they apply in relation to deductions allowable in respect of depreciation.

(5) Where, in a scheme of amalgamation, the amalgamating company sells or otherwise transfers to the amalgamated company (being an Indian company) any asset representing expenditure of a capital nature on scientific research,—

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(i) the amalgamating company shall not be allowed the deduction under clause (ii) or clause (iii) of sub-section (2); and

(ii) the provisions of this section shall, as far as may be, apply to the amalgamated company as they would have applied to the amalgamating company if the latter had not so sold or otherwise transferred the asset.

18.2 Expenditure on scientific research, income tax assessment act 1936, section 73A, Australia

(1A) This section has effect subject to Division 245 of the [Income Tax Assessment Act 1997](#) .

(1) The following payments made, and expenditure incurred, during the [year of income](#) (other than any amount which is allowable as a deduction under any other section of [this Act](#)) by a [person](#) carrying on a [business](#) for the purpose of gaining or producing [assessable income](#) shall be [allowable deductions](#):

215

(a) Payments to:

- (i) [an approved research institute](#) for [scientific research](#) related to that [business](#); or
- (ii) [an approved research institute](#), the object of which is the undertaking of [scientific research](#) related to the class of [business](#) to which that [business](#) belongs; and

(b) Expenditure of a capital nature on [scientific research](#) related to that [business](#) (except to the extent that it is expenditure on plant, machinery, land or buildings or on alterations, additions or extensions to buildings or in the acquisition of rights in or arising out of [scientific research](#)).

(2) Where, on or after the first day of the [year of income](#) ending on 30 June 1946, a [taxpayer](#) carrying on a [business](#) for the purpose of gaining or producing [assessable income](#) incurs expenditure of a capital nature in the construction or acquisition of a building, or part of a building, or in making any alteration or addition to a building, in which [scientific research](#) related to that [business](#) is to be carried on by or on behalf of the [taxpayer](#), and the building, part of a building, alteration or addition, as the case

may be, is of use for [scientific research](#) purposes only, an amount equal to one - third of that expenditure shall be an [allowable deduction](#):

(a) from the [assessable income](#) of the [year of income](#) in which the building, part of a building, alteration or addition is first used by or on behalf of the [taxpayer](#) for such [scientific research](#); and

Page | 126

(b) from the [assessable income](#) of each of the 2 years of income next succeeding that [year of income](#), if the [taxpayer](#) continues to carry on that [business](#) during the year in which that [assessable income](#) was derived.

(2A) [Subsection](#) (2) does not apply to expenditure incurred by a [taxpayer](#) in the construction of a building or part of a building, in the making of an alteration or addition to a building or in the acquisition of a building or part of a building unless:

(a) either of the following subparagraphs applies:

216

(i) that construction or making commenced, or that acquisition occurred, before 21 November 1987;

(ii) any contract in respect of that construction, making or acquisition was entered into before 21 November 1987; and

(b) if the expenditure was incurred after 20 November 1987--the [taxpayer](#) intended, on 20 November 1987, that:

(i) [scientific research](#), being research related to a [business](#) carried on by the [taxpayer](#) for the purpose of gaining or producing [assessable income](#), would be carried on by or on behalf of the [taxpayer](#) in the building; and

(ii) the building, part of the building, alteration or addition, as the case may be, would be of use for [scientific research](#) purposes only.

(3) Where any expenditure or payment to which this section refers is incurred or made outside [Australia](#) and the [business](#) in relation to which it is so incurred or made is carried on partly in and partly out of [Australia](#), the deduction allowable under this

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section shall be such part of the amount which would otherwise be allowable as the [Commissioner](#) considers reasonable in the circumstances.

(4) Where any expenditure has been allowed or is allowable as a deduction under [subsection](#) (2) and:

(a) the [taxpayer](#) sells, [transfers](#) or otherwise disposes of the building or any part thereof; or

(b) the building or any part thereof is destroyed;

the [termination value](#) of the building or part shall, to the extent of the expenditure so allowed or allowable as a deduction, be included in the [assessable income](#) of the [year of income](#) in which the disposal or destruction occurs:

[Provided](#) that where the [Commissioner](#) is of opinion that part only, or no part, of that [termination value](#) relates to the disposal or destruction of any [property](#) which was acquired or created by that expenditure, that part only, or no part, as the case may be, of the [termination value](#) shall be taken into account for the purposes of this [subsection](#).

(4A) If:

(a) a [person](#) has purchased from another [person](#) a building, or part of a building, where the vendor had incurred capital expenditure of a kind in respect of which deductions are or have been allowable under [subsection](#) (2); and

(b) it would be concluded that, having regard to any connection between the vendor and the purchaser or to any other [relevant circumstances](#), those [persons](#) were not dealing with each other at arm's length; and

(c) the purchase price is greater or lesser than the market value of the building, or the part of the building, at the time of the purchase;

the purchase price is, for all purposes of the application of [this Act](#) in relation to the vendor, taken to have been the amount of the market value of the [property](#) at the time of the purchase.

(5) If the purchase of the building is a [creditable acquisition](#) by the vendor, references in [subsection](#) (4A) to the purchase price are taken to be references to that price reduced by the amount of the [net input tax credit](#) to which the purchaser is entitled for the acquisition.

Page | 128

(6) In this section:

"an approved research institute" means the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organization, or any university, college, institute, association or organization which is approved in writing for the purposes of this section by that Organization, by the Chief Executive Officer of the [NHMRC](#) or by the [Research Secretary](#), as an institution, association or organization for undertaking [scientific research](#) which is or may prove to be of value to [Australia](#).

218

"NHMRC" means the National Health and Medical Research Council established by section [5B](#) of the [National Health and Medical Research Council Act 1992](#) .

"Research Secretary" means the Secretary of the Department administered by the Minister administering the [Australian Research Council Act 2001](#) .

"scientific research" means any activities in the fields of natural or applied science for the extension of knowledge.

"termination value" has the meaning given by [subsection](#) 995 - 1(1) of the [Income Tax Assessment Act 1997](#) .

(7) An approval for the purposes of [subsection](#) (6) may:

(a) operate as from a date, whether before or after the date of the approval, specified in the instrument of approval; and

(b) be withdrawn at any time.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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(8) In this section, any reference to scientific research related to a business or class of business shall be read as including a reference to:

(i) any scientific research which may lead to or facilitate an extension, or an improvement in the technical efficiency, of that business, or, as the case may be, of businesses of that class; and

(ii) any scientific research of a medical nature which is of special relation to the welfare of workers employed in that business or, as the case may be, in businesses of that class.

(9) This section does not apply in relation to payments made, or expenditure incurred, after 30 June 1995.

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

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Hossain, M. A. (2023bf). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-04)*.

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<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), M.Tech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre: RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre: RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder, Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28176.28165>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bm). *PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>;
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10116196>

Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking free of cost legal action to high court of Australia and/or fully funded PhD Scholarship for every cost of high court of Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27057.76642>;
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29042.48322>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048>

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Hossain, M. A. (2023bt). *Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist.* <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49098>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34177.43368>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10208384>

Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Bangladeshi Passport No: EE0444946; Bangladeshi Address: Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh is reporting life-*

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; 7 October 2025; email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

threatening conspiracy to Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Australian High Commissioner to Bangladesh located at 184 Gulshan Avenue, Gulshan, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28153.24164>;

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Hossain, M. A. (2023bv). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world.*

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10986579>

Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Reporting for psychologist involvement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University as per office order of RMIT University, Australia.*

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195451>

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder, Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>

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<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), M.Tech Textile Engg (CU, India), B.Sc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Hossain, M. A. (2023ck). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01).*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cl). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02).*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/0WXVkgicfKg>

Hossain, M. A. (2024a). *Advancement in UV-Vis-IR camouflage Textiles for concealment of defense surveillance against multidimensional combat background. Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Engineering.* <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40712-024-00182-8>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17601.12648>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14282484>

Hossain, M. A. (2024b). *Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14776.72967>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>

Hossain, M. A. (2024c). *Coalesced the syllabus and course structures in textile engineering and relevant courses in the eighteen years duration academic and professional journey of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist from 2006 to 2024.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21803.66082>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13888294>

Hossain, M. A. (2024d). *Cyber securities for protection of cyber-crimes.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14367.98729>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841349>

Hossain, M. A. (2024e). *A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964382>

Hossain, M. A. (2024f). *Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of “Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist” on “Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds” School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36270.32328;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13182515>

Hossain, M. A. (2024g). *Letter to Nobel committee for Nobel prize in camouflage physics.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36807.51367;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842435>

Hossain, M. A. (2024h). *Letter to Nobel Committee for Nobel Prize in Peace.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35129.79208;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842361>

Hossain, M. A. (2024i). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching research fund for surviving in research profession and self-learning.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22732.42888;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13997939>

Hossain, M. A. (2024j). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699107>

Hossain, M. A. (2024k). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>

Hossain, M. A. (2024l). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of 'free of cost google drive (2TB) access' to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com.*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13994976>

Hossain, M. A. (2024m). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is self-nominating for 'global excellence award' at Functional Textiles and Clothing (FTC), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India under the category of 'Leadership in Research' and/or 'Emerging Innovator' under the invitation of FTC team, IIT, Delhi, India.*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14213757>

Hossain, M. A. (2024n). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is asking an exemption of visa fees for the 'Australian global talent permanent*

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre: RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre: RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder, Textile, Color & Material Research Centre⁴; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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residence visa (subclass 858)' under the Australian migration act 45C (c), 1958 and 500.211,1994.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25869.14560>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12754106>

Hossain, M. A. (2024o). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Hossain, M. A. (2024p). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>

Hossain, M. A. (2024q). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Calcutta for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20869.15843>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842021>

Hossain, M. A. (2024r). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Dhaka for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36388.08325>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841964>

Hossain, M. A. (2024s). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is searching a good-looking lady for his marriage, a requirement of RMIT PhD school.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13112.97282>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747830>

Hossain, M. A. (2024t). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16628548>

Hossain, M. A. (2024u). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>

Hossain, M. A. (2024v). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an*

- international standard University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814275>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024w). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024x). *Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection* [Biodata]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15612185>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024y). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist represented his photographic memories of profession in textile engineering and casual life journey*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32669.69609>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10449995>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024z). *Research services, journal peer reviews, and editorial support of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15157.90080>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13142538>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024). *Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024aa). *A self-understanding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist about Bangladeshi Nobel laureate Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus and law implementation of Bangladesh Government*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26912.35846>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10461097>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025a). *A follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18369.83044>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17231359>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025b). *Invitation of law researchers in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30060.63369>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16995119>

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), M.Tech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia</p>	<p>Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre*; RMIT Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Hossain, M. A. (2025c). *Invitation of legal client for legal service to individual and/or organization.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13073.70249>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16990186>

Hossain, M. A. (2025d). *Invitation of researchers in textile engineering in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17215.57765>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16960861>

Hossain, M. A. (2025e). *Local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28463.85929>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826808>

Hossain, M. A. (2025f). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching for the prestigious 'best researcher award' under the provisional nomination of organizing committee, research scientist awards of Indian government [Grant].* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36413.17128>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064119>

Hossain, M. A. (2025g). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32735.16801>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718630>

Hossain, M. A. (2025h). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14934539>

Hossain, M. A. (2025i). *A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020)* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com.

Hossain, M. A. (2025j). *Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24765.32485>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16961335>

- Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. (2018). Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent. *Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing*, 2(2), 1-8. <http://dx.doi.org/10.32474/LTTFD.2018.02.000132>
- Hossain, M. A., Samanta, A., Abser, M. N., & Dilruba, F. A. (2019). A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 3(1), 1-3. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36811.36648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245079>
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241

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Review Article

A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre

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Abstract

Natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural finishing agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing can be established by developing completely eco-friendly natural dyes and natural finishing agent which can be applied on cotton textiles (Oeko-Tech Products) by adopting a newer technique of simultaneous Mordanting-Dyeing-Finishing in a single step to reduce energy cost, process time, processing costs and effluent load as well as to develop the single step processes and also completely eco-friendly products of cotton textiles using selective natural dyes and natural finishing agents using bio mordants and bio finishing agents obtained from an extract of natural resources at reduced cost and energy. There is huge scope of commercialization of such Oeko-Tech (Eco-Friendly) products of natural dyed and finished cotton textile products for domestic and export market. Different selective natural dyes like teak leaf, turmeric, jackfruit wood, sappan wood, skin of onion, arjuna bark etc., bio-mordanting agent like bio-enzyme, harda, lemon as natural mordanting agents, extracted soyabean seed as natural chemical modification as well as natural finishing agent like coconut oil as UV absorber, neem and guava leaf as antimicrobial agent where all dyed and finished fabric can be scientifically tested by SEM, FTIR, DSC, HPLC, GCMS, TLC, CHNS, X-ray diffraction pattern etc.

243

Introduction

Worldwide growing consciousness for eco-friendly textile products is generating more and more customer's interests on natural fibres based textile as well as on natural dyes and natural finishing, particularly for the Export market. Considering this corner, textile sector has the highest scope to apply this research work for attracting the value-added customer. But, till today there is a huge lack of research and development of natural dyeing and finishing based textile product. There are ample scopes of doing scientific research on the application of natural dyes on cotton and other textiles aimed at obtaining newer shade with acceptable colour fastness behaviour and uniform and reproducible colour yield through appropriate techniques. Simultaneous natural dyeing and natural finishing: a new technique will thus serve process steps like energy and total process cost. Reducing process cost will minimize total cost of the product in the export market, it will be highly beneficial

to sustain in a competitive market if the expected research output can be applied successfully in Government and non-government textile mill at home and abroad.

Cotton is still a natural fibre of agro-origin that is used most in the world. About 46% of all fibre produced in the world is cotton. Even today cotton is the backbone of the world's textile trade. The cotton fibre presents many exceptional features like great flexibility, cohesive property, very small thickness, but high strength and wear resistance. Owing to these properties it is possible to process cotton fibres into yarns with greater diversity; from thick yarn for manufacturing coarse and different upholstery/furnishing as well as denim type apparel fabrics to very fine yarns for manufacturing thin and refined fabrics such as Batiste, Marquisette, Muslin, etc. Cotton fibre is widely used for making all types of apparels as well as all types of furnishing fabrics. In textile applications this biodegradable, environment-friendly and renewable fibre has some

distinct advantages such as moderate dry and wet tensile strength, appreciable moisture regains, agreeable feel, moderate extensibility, varied dye ability and appreciable UV-light stability. However, the major disadvantages of cotton lie in its dimensional instability as revealed by wash shrinkage, poor wrinkle recovery and ready susceptibility to microbial degradation.

Natural dyes are considered to be eco-friendly as these are obtained from renewable resources as compared to synthetic dyes which are derived from non-renewable petroleum resources. These are biodegradable and the residual vegetal matter left after extraction of dyes can be easily composted and used as fertilizer. They produce soft colours soothing to the eye which is in harmony with nature which is gradually gaining popularity due to its non-toxicity and eco-friendly character against possible unsafe ecotoxicity criteria of synthetic dyes. Most of the studies available for dyeing with natural dyes relates to cotton textiles and such studies on cotton are still insufficient to establish. Hence, there are ample scope of undertaking an integrated study in this area for cotton and chemically modified cotton to study its surface appearance, durability and dyeing of cotton and chemically modified cotton with natural dyes.

Literature Review

Growing consciousness for eco-friendly textile products has caused more interest on cotton fibre based natural dyeing and finishing. Productions of synthetic dyes are dependent on the petrochemical source and some of the synthetic dyes contain toxic/carcinogenic amines and are not eco-friendly. Contrary to this, most of the natural dyes as well as natural finish with few exceptions are based on vegetable/ animal origin and are renewable, biodegradable, energy-efficient and eco-friendly [1,2]. The most important issue now is origin and classification of some natural dyes applicable for different fibres are available in the literature [3-5]. Gupta, et al. [6] have documented some of the traditional processes of application of some natural dyes. Kawahito, et al. [7] have compared the dyeing of cellulosic fabric with natural indigo and synthetic indigo. Radhakrishnan [8] as well as Ajita, et al. [9] have reported the effect of different mordants on selective natural dyes. Grierson, et al. [10] has studied colour fastness characteristics of some natural dyes. Lee, et al. [11] have studied the colour fastness properties of some natural dyes by applying UV-absorbers. Effect of chemical structure on light fastness property of some natural dyes has been reported by Gupta, et al. [12]. Oda, et al. [13] has studied the effect of phenyl ester functional group on photofading of carthamin on cellulose acetate. Most of the studies are sporadic and insufficient in developing scientific knowledge base on the subject. Therefore, very less study on simultaneous natural dyeing and finishing, dyeing process variables and characterisation etc. Hence, an integrated scientific study for selective natural dye-fibre system, for selective natural dyes applied on cotton and other textiles is felt necessary, for establishing the process optimization in naturally dyed textiles. [14, 15 16, 17] Natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural finishing

agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing were experimented in earlier research on natural coloration.

Application of Different Biomordanting with Biomordanting Agents

Effects of different degrees of biomordanting like bioenzyme, harda and lemon as natural mordanting agents and natural chemical modification extracted from soyabean seed on cotton fabric for altering its textile related properties and dye ability with selective natural dyes (say a teak leaf, turmeric, Jackfruit wood, sappan wood etc.) can be investigated. Effect of such biomodifications on colour parameters after dyeing of cotton and chemically and biochemically modified cotton and its colour fastness properties to light, washing, perspiration and rubbing can be studied. The photo fading behaviour of cotton and chemically and biochemically modified and dyed cotton materials after those modifications and pre-treatments and subsequent dyeing can be studied and an attempt can be taken to improve the same to a much better level of customer acceptability. Effects of different degree of chemical modifications on colour yield for the selective natural dyes can be studied. Cotton Textile materials dyed with natural dyes can be post-treated/finished with suitable natural agents for studying the effect of these after treatments on the improvement of colour yield, brightness and colour fastness behaviour of the dyed material. To improve the colour fastness properties for the selective natural dyes some pre or post-treatment with cationic or metallic complex compound or UV absorbers/suitable modifiers can be studied.

244

Process Development

The fabrics can be pre-treated by the eco-friendly enzyme-based chemical pre-treatment processes for preparing it for simultaneous dyeing and finishing. After that different natural dyes (say teak leaf, turmeric, jackfruit wood, sappan wood etc.) as well as natural finishing agent like coconut oil as UV absorber, neem and guava leaf as antimicrobial agent can be applied on cotton fabric for trailing and experimentations on application of dyes and finishing agent on cotton and optimization of dyeing process variables for improved colour development and improvement of colour fastness, all analytical testing. Effects of variations of dyeing process variables on colour yield and dyeing kinetics for application of selective natural dyes on cotton and chemically modified cotton substrate can be investigated to understand the dyeing isotherm, rate of dyeing and other thermodynamic parameters for such dyeing. This will help to understand the dyeing behaviours of different natural dyes applied on cotton to get an idea of formulating better colour yield having specific standardized dyeing recipe for combined/compound shades by use of binary or ternary mixture of these natural dyes. For use of combination of natural dyes for generating compound shades, a study on the compatibility of such binary and a ternary mixture of dyes can be also studied, to understand and find a compatible combination of such dyes for cotton

and chemically treated and modified cotton fabrics.

Process of Textile Properties and Dyeability Analysis

Changes in structural features for different degrees of chemical modifications (enzymatic hydrolysis, oxidation on cotton substrate) can be investigated with the help of Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), FTIR Spectroscopy and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), High-Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPLC), Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GCMS), Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC), Carbon, Hydrogen, Nitrogen and Sulphur (CHNS) analyzer and X-ray diffraction pattern etc. for explaining the major observations in these aspects. This will help to understand scientifically the scientific analysis of different changes in textile related property behaviour and dyeability in terms of changes in structural features of chemically modified cotton substrate along with changes in surface characteristics and durability etc.

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A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles

Anowar Hossain

Abstract

Marigold flower *Tagetes erecta* L., Arjuna Bark *Terminalia Arjuna*, Eucalyptus leaves *Eucalyptus Radiata*, Peach/Jam Leaves *Acacia acuminata*, Pecker leaves *Cinnamomum tamala*, Guava leaves *Psidium guajava*, Basil leaves *Ocimum basilicum*, Jackfruit wood *Artocarpus heterophyllus*, Catachu fruit *Senegalia Catechu*, Bohera fruit *Terminalia bellirica*, Betel nut fruit *Areca catechu*, Haritaki fruit *Terminalia chebula*, Mahogany fruit peel, Mahogany seed peel, and Mahogany seed *Swietenia macrophylla* are the common natural sources in Bangladesh, an Asian country which were experimented in terms of mordanting free natural coloration on cotton fabric under conceptual confirmation of referred journal where author has been picked the idea from the generation of available shade in his research laboratory and tested from different laboratories and it may be establish as mordant free natural dyeing for specific colorant on the basis of color fastness and shading behaviors. Fifteen standardized Ready Made Shade (RMS) has been presented with CIE color parameters, color fastness, wash fastness, and light fastness grading. A reproducing guideline for every Ready Made Shade (RMS) has been mentioned in this chapter.

247

Keywords: readymade shade (RMS), natural dyeing, eco-friendly dyes, natural extraction, mordant free dyeing

1. Introduction

A concept of readymade shade (RMS) has been developed by using numerous number of natural dyes which were collected from agri-production unit and different village sources in Bangladesh prepared and powdered in color processing unit, extracted with water solvent process, dyed and experimented the feasibility of coloration in textile chemistry laboratory to generate different hues of natural dyes after effective implementation on natural fiber based textiles which outcome of color may be beneficial for primary selection of color tone by the textile technologist of natural coloration cum customers for the decision-making of specific color tone both for product development and fashion concerns who are genuinely searching an eco-friendly dyes under the consideration of repeated hue without which the real output of natural coloration, sustainability of dyes and natural dyeing process as well as its actual production of different hue is being a challenged now as the textile technologists are habituated the essence of readymade shading behavior of synthetic dyes whereas toxicity is the main endangered for the human being.

2. Background

Environment pollution is the great challenge of color scientists in dyeing and finishing plant, so eco-friendly coloration is the key target of recent researchers and manufacturers. Natural coloration is being accepted by the environment scientist and related committee [1–3]. Researchers in the area of natural coloration have an immense intension to minimize pollution [4]. Focus on science and engineering on natural dyes based research, extractions, purifications, and implementations are rapidly climbing [5–9]. In this chapter, mordant free natural coloration and its feasibility was experimented to minimize environment pollution load which is not limited to synthetic dyeing but also natural dyeing in terms of mordant free coloration concepts for specific standardized shade. Author also experimented to establish an approach of green mordanting [10, 11] in natural coloration [12–16] although mordant [17] has an effect for the augmentation of fiber surface color and surface chemistry [18] and its appropriate affinity in terms of fastness properties [1, 19–24]. Light fastness [21–24] of natural dyed fabric is a critical issue for natural colorant if dyes sources and collection processes are not maintained accurately. There are many sources of natural colorant, using by the researcher as per availability of origin to origin in the world. Researchers are already invented and proposed like *Jatropha* flower [25], red sandal wood [26], wood of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* [27], *Acalypha* [28], areca nut [29], *Butea monosperma* [30], neem leaves [31, 32], *Gomphrena globosa* [33], *Onosmaechiodes* [34], *Nerium oleander* flower [35], Kesula flowers [36], Parijataka (*Nyctanthes Arbor*) flowers pigment [37], *Hibiscus ovalifolius* and *Sesbania aegyptiaca* [38], Bark of *Macaranga Peltata* [39], Cutch, Ratanjot and Madder [40], Mesta Calyx [41], Kapila, Onion, Tesu [42], myrobalan, gallnut, pomegranate [43], Marigold flower [44, 45], *Areca Catechu* [46], Eucalyptus leaves [47], Eucalyptus bark [48, 49], Jackfruit wood [50], Peach [51], Arjuna [52, 53], Catechu [54] and others. Developments of natural indigo shade in comparison with synthetic dyes [55] are not only prime objects for coloration but also maximum natural dyes have medicinal value [56, 57], noncarcinogenic, production-friendly, and environment-friendly. Research and development of natural dyeing on cotton, jute, and silk fabric was done by Samanta and his researchers team at DJFT, University of Calcutta, India have a technical output, research impacts and motivation for future researchers, and manufacturing unit for the contributions of dyes selection, extraction, analysis, standardization, and commercialization [58–68]. Color matching [69] and reproducing of shade is another challenging issue for the manufacturing company and colorists when natural dye is compared with synthetic dyes but there are so many colorants of natural sources that can be possible to reproduce almost nearest shade. Tolerating percentage/ acceptable range of color differences, ΔE value, and other properties can be standardized in a convincing way with local and foreign customer of any country as the real customer of any textile product is not going to sell the product after shade matching with spectrophotometer without enjoying its esthetic value, so a little bit lightness and darkness matter is not a trading challenge of dyer and manufacturing plant. Comparing to synthetic dyes, natural dyed fabric has a great market demand as the people who are concern about the intimidation of environment. Thus natural dyes have diverse applications and multi fiber based production options that are already available in literature for cotton [68], jute [66], wool [70], silk [34] based dyeing, processing in both laboratory stage and bulk production (**Figures 1–15**).

RMS of Marigold (Figure 1): Waste Marigold flowers were collected from flower garden, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

3. Standardized Ready Made Shade (RMS) of natural dyed textiles

3.1 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Marigold flower, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Marigold tree. scientific name: *Tagetes erecta*

Figure 1.
RMS of Marigold.

3.2 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Arjuna Bark, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Arjuna tree, Scientific name: *Terminalia arjuna*

Figure 2.
RMS of Arjuna Bark.

3.3 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Eucalyptus leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: scientific name: *Eucalyptus radiata*

Figure 3.
RMS of *Eucalyptus* leaves.

Coloring components Zeaxanthin and Lutein structural group of marigold flower may be responsible for good color combination has OH group may be showed good color fastness properties with cellulosic fiber. Lutein (C₄₀H₅₆O₂) and Zeaxanthin (C₄₀H₅₆O₂) molecules may prevent UV damage for its strong antioxidant properties.

RMS of Arjuna Bark (Figure 2): Dried Arjuna bark were plucked from Arjuna tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

Ferrous ion of Arjuna Bark may be influencing the L*, a*, b*, Y value for providing outcome of deeper color and OH group is responsible for good fastness properties. Arjuna bark has phytosterol, lactones, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and tannins, glycosides where tannin may be responsible for coloring agent.

RMS of Eucalyptus Leaves (Figure 3): Semi-dried leaves were plucked from Eucalyptus tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group of cellulose can easily make a bonding with dyes group of Eucalyptus. Eucalyptol is a colorless compound which is responsible for antibacterial properties but may be remaining pigment or other phytochemical compound is making color on the fabric surface.

3.4 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Pecker leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Pecker tree, scientific name: *Cinnamomum tamala*

Figure 4.
RMS of Pecker leaves.

RMS of Pecker Leaves (Figure 4): Semi-dried leaves were plucked from pecker tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group of cellulose can easily make a bonding with dyes group of Pecker leaves. Eugenol is the main constituent of antimicrobial properties and other components like pinene, camphene, and limousine may be responsible for color formation.

RMS of Guava Leaves (Figure 5): Semi-dried leaves were plucked from tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group of dyes is responsible for good color fastness properties. Mixed components of flavonoid and tannin are highly responsible for bluish color of cotton fabric. Acidic pH and phenolic compound of guava leaves may generate flammable characteristics of guava leaves colored fabric.

RMS of Basil Leaves (Figure 6): Fresh and green Basil leaves were plucked from tree, washed and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

α terpineol remaining in dyes of Basil leaves may be responsible for dyeing of cotton fiber and OH group is making strong affinity with cellulose. Phytochemical constituents and medicinal properties of Tulsi leaves may create pathogen protective finish of cotton fabric like antimicrobial, COVID 19, and other viruses.

3.5 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Guava leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Guava tree, scientific name: *Psidium guajava*

Figure 5.
RMS of Guava leaves.

3.6 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Basil leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Basil tree, scientific name: *Ocimum basilicum*

Figure 6.
RMS of Basil leaves.

3.7 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Jackfruit wood, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Jackfruit tree, scientific name: *Artocarpus heterophyllus*

Figure 7.
RMS of Jackfruit wood.

3.8 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Catechu fruit peel, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Catechu tree, scientific name: *Senegalia catechu*

Figure 8.
RMS of Catachu fruit.

3.9 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Bohera fruit peel, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Bohera tree, scientific name: *Terminalia bellirica*

Figure 9.
RMS of Bohera fruit.

RMS of Jackfruit Wood (Figure 7): Powder of Jackfruit wood were collected from saw mill, filtered and 5 days dried with summer sun light. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

Artocarpesin and Norartocarpetin group of golden yellow color jackfruit tree wood has phenolic compounds, apigenin, curcumin may be responsible for making a yellow color having an optimum value of L^* , a^* , b^* , Y as well as OH group is improving color fastness properties.

RMS of Catachu Fruit (Figure 8): Semidried Catachu fruit were plucked from tree, washed, fruit peel were cut into small piece, 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

Catachu is making off white color with soft hand feel and may be remaining natural pigment in the chemical components is responsible for dyeing without mordanting. Coloring component in the catechu is catechin having molecular formula $C_{15}H_{14}O_6$.

RMS of Bohera Fruit (Figure 9): Bohera fruit powder was purchased from herbal medicine shop, Tongi, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

3.10 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Mahogany seed, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Mahogany tree, scientific name: *Swietenia macrophylla*

Figure 10.
 RMS of Mahogany fruit, seed.

3.11 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Mahogany fruit (outer peel), types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Mahogany tree, scientific name: *Swietenia macrophylla*

Figure 11.
 RMS of Mahogany fruit, outer peel.

3.12 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Mahogany seed (outer peel), types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Mahogany tree, scientific name: *Swietenia macrophylla*

Figure 12. RMS of Mahogany fruit, outer peel of seed.

OH group and its tannin constituent may be created a natural shading environment on the surface of cotton fiber and its medicinal properties may create the dyed fabric antimicrobial. Flavonoid and falfvins constituent of Bohera fruit may have adaptive capabilities of viruses and microorganisms.

RMS of Mahogany Fruit, Seed (Figure 10): Semi-ripped Mahogany fruits were plucked from tree, washed, seeds were separated with sharp knife, cut into small pieces and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group may be responsible for good dye-absorption and ferrous ion may be responsible for dyeing. Phytochemical constituents and other medicinal properties may have a good source protective clothing like insect repellent, antimicrobial, COVID19, and other viruses.

3.13 Natural coloration of cotton natural coloration of cotton fabric with Haritaki fruit peel, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Haritaki tree, scientific name: *Terminalia chebula*

Figure 13.
 RMS of Haritaki fruit.

3.14 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Betel nut, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Betel nut tree, scientific name: *Areca catechu*

Figure 14.
 RMS of Betel nut.

3.15 Natural coloration of cotton fabric with Peach leaves, types of dyes: natural, source of dyes: Peach leaves, scientific name: *Acacia acuminata*

Figure 15.
RMS of Peach leaves.

RMS of Mahogany Fruit, Outer peel (Figure 11): Semi-ripped Mahogany fruit were plucked from tree, washed, fruit peels were separated with sharp knife, cut into small pieces and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group and ferrous ion may be responsible for good dye-fiber bonding phytochemical constituents and other medicinal properties may have a good source protective clothing like insect repellent, antimicrobial, COVID19, and other viruses.

RMS of Mahogany Fruit, Outer peel of Seed (Figure 12): Semi-ripped Mahogany fruit were plucked from tree, washed, seed peels were separated with sharp knife, cut into small pieces and 5 days dried with summer sun light, and made it crispy and fine powdered with grinding machine. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group and ferrous ion may be responsible for good dye-fiber bonding. Phytochemical constituents and other medicinal properties may have a good source protective clothing like insect repellent, antimicrobial, COVID19, and other viruses.

RMS of Haritaki Fruit (Figure 13): Haritaki fruit powder was purchased from herbal medicine shop Tongi, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group and ferrous ion may be responsible for good dye-fiber bonding. The plant is constituted of Glucoside, Tannins, Gallic acid, Ethyl gallate, and Chebulinic acid where tannin may be responsible for coloring the cotton fiber.

RMS of Betel Nut (Figure 14): Ripe Betel nut were purchased from local village shop, separated the peels, and grinded to make it powder form. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

OH group can create a bond between dye and fiber and remaining curcumin may be responsible for coloration and dyed fabric may be slightly flammable due to having hydroxychavicol in the chemical constituent of betel nut.

RMS of Peach Leaves (Figure 15): Semi-dried Peach leaves were plucked from Peach tree garden. Two gram powder was mixed with 100 ml water, heated at boiling temperature for 40 min, and filtered properly. The dyes solution was used for cotton fabric dyeing in open bath medium for 30 min at 80°C.

Minimum color strength is found but fastness is lightly higher, increasing dye percentage may improve the color on the fiber surface. Remaining ferrous, copper, and zinc may be responsible for coloring the cotton fiber. As per chemical constituent, antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory can be found.

4. Method of natural fixing for mordant free dyeing

Maximum natural dyes sources from natural tree leaves, roots or fruits have ferrous ion, tannin, curcumin, catechin, OH group, and other known and unknown phytochemical constituent. Ferrous ion, tannin, curcumin, and catechin are making various color formations, and OH group is creating affinity with cellulosic fiber as well as the fastness properties may be increased if the dyes have natural pigment which may influence the capability of remaining dyes on the fiber surface after washing. Drying/curing with higher temperature may impact the color making duller or brighter. So specific dye-fiber system of natural fixing for mordant free dyeing is also possible but exact curing/drying temperature should be fixed for getting expected outcome of shading. So expected mechanism of mordant free natural coloration may be proposed as below although dyes and fiber substances may create changing of it.

259

5. Testing process

5.1 Color fastness to wash method

ISO 105-C06:2010, color fastness to water method: ISO 105-E01 and color fastness to light was tested by AATCC TM16 in Q-SUN XE-2 Xenon Test chamber.

5.2 Machine used for color parameters

Color parameters (L^* , a^* , b^* , Y) were measured by Hunter Lab Spectrophotometer, machine name: ColorFlex EZ, Model 45/0 LAV, Geometry

Figure 16.
Color Flex EZ, Spectrophotometer.

45°/0°, viewing area: large, visible spectrum (400–700 nm), testing condition: D₆₅/10°, room temperature of testing lab: 18°C (**Figure 16**).

6. Representation of dyed fabric and picture of dyes sources

All dyed shades were scanned with HUAWEI Smart Phone, Camera-13 MP, distance between fabric sample and camera position: 12–16 inch. So there is a possibility of having difference with actual shade. Picture of actual dye-fiber system was also scanned with HP Scanjet 4890 Photo Scanner. All sources of dyes pictures have been mentioned on the basis of grown trees in Asian Countries, specially in Bangladesh and scientific name was used accordingly. All the pictures of chemical structure mentioned here indicate the group of tree, not exactly indicating the chemical structure of specific parts of trees which one is extracted and dyed on cotton fabric.

6.1 Overcoming contradiction of natural dyeing

A huge number of researchers are working on natural dyes, still have a challenging for uneven dyeing, appropriate mordanting and dyes availabilities, shade matching where I can put a logic to protect our environment and human life as well.

260

6.2 Uneven dyeing

Automation in extraction and dyeing process.

6.3 Appropriate mordanting and dyes availability

Selection of specific dyes for commercial production and/or wastage can be used as dyes sources.

6.4 Shade matching

Customers are not always asking for shade matching when they are shopping although some natural dyes have attractive shading and repeated shading also possible.

7. Conclusion

Mordanting free coloration was practiced establishing the feasibility of environment friendly natural coloration which is the ongoing research of author and a part

of his research has been included here. Shade variation of natural dyed fabric may influence the uncontrollable factors for the collection of natural dyes sources on the basis of season to season, region to region and a same source but different parts of same dye sample source. So it is very tough to make a specific declaration of shading behaviors by the textile technologist but specific expertise in natural dyes extraction and natural dyeing may minimize the problem whereas expertise in dyeing with synthetic dyes and dyeing with natural dyes are not same for bulk production.

Following directions for the real shade development mentioned above:

1. Fabric should be well scoured and bleached.
2. Dyes materials should be clean, dried and powdered properly, improper drying and inappropriate powder formation may be responsible for unexpected shading and uneven dyeing.
3. Extraction time, dyes percentage may be maximized or minimized if the actual color is not observed.
4. Improper filtration of dyes may create uneven dyeing.
5. Dyes should not be powdered in wet or sticky condition which may effect the changing of light fastness and color shading.
6. Insect affected dyes source may create the changing of shade.
7. Synthetic mordanting and chemical medium dyes extraction may improve the shade but the concern of chemical and cost.
8. For open bath dyeing, liquor ratio should be higher, and stirred continuously to reduce color mark on the dyed fabric.

261

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